

FINAL REPORT
The Fort Argyle Story:
Phase III Archaeological Investigations of Site 9BN28,
Bryan County,
Georgia

Contract W912HN15D0018
Delivery Order 0004

Report Submitted to:
U.S. Army, Fort Stewart
Cultural Resource Management, Environmental Division
Directorate of Public Works
1557 Veterans Parkway
Fort Stewart, GA 31314

Prepared by:

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ABSTRACT

This report details the historical and archaeological research conducted by LG² Environmental Solutions, Inc. (LG²ES) at the British colonial Fort Argyle site (9BN28) in Bryan County, Georgia. This cultural resource is located on property owned by the U.S. government and managed as part of the Fort Stewart Military Reservation. The site was discovered by Chad Braley and his Southeast Archeological Services (SAS) crew in 1985 and it was further explored by Daniel Elliott and his LAMAR Institute crew in 1995/1996. These two studies confirm that 9BN28 was the site of a colonial South Carolina and Georgia ranger fort that was garrisoned from 1733 to 1767. At least two forts, and possibly a third, were recognized by the LAMAR Institute's team. A 2012 environmental study by LG²ES determined that this important archaeological site is being rapidly impacted by shoreline erosion from the waters of the Ogeechee River, which flows along the eastern side of the site. Fort Stewart contracted with LG²ES for Phase III Data Recovery to mitigate the adverse impact from the ongoing erosion. LG²ES worked at Fort Argyle one week in April 2018, November-December 2018, and January through the first week of February 2019. This fieldwork included systematic metal detector survey, Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) survey and hand excavation of 136 test units distributed in 16 blocks. The field crew excavated a total of 270 m², or approximately 92 m³ at 9BN28. Of this area of excavation, approximately 3 m² overlapped with previously excavated blocks. The LG²ES team confirmed the existence of a third fort at the site, defined the shapes and extents of the previously identified forts better, uncovered and documented new features, and uncovered additional material culture whose volume and identity contributes to a more complete understanding of the colonial frontier. The project also explored various areas within and immediately outside of the three forts.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The report authors Daniel Elliott and Rita Folse Elliott wish to thank many individuals and agencies who assisted our efforts to explore Fort Argyle. First, we wish to thank the support staff of the Fort Stewart Military Reservation, particularly Mr. Brian Greer who has managed its cultural resources for more than a decade.

Several historians and archivists contributed, often unintentionally to the project. Thanks to Mr. Robert Scott Davis, Jr., an exceptional historian and fellow Georgian, who has made it his lifelong pursuit to introduce the world to Georgia and Georgians past. Dr. James Johnson, a fine military historian and fellow Georgian, whose study of British colonial rangers is an excellent work. Dr. Johnson also has encouraged our pursuit of Georgia's pre-Civil War military sites. Mr. Larry Ivers, another fine military historian, whose early studies of colonial fortifications and rangers in South Carolina and Georgia in the 1970s paved the way for the present study. Primary document researcher and transcriber, Ms. Mary Bondurant Warren generously provided us with her recently transcribed colonial records from Kew, England. These records contained numerous primary accounts pertaining to Fort Argyle and its people. Mr. Farris Cadle, avid Loyalist historian and coastal Georgia history researcher, also provided us with tidbits of Georgia's Trustee period history direct from England.

Several archaeologists (and friends) supported this work, even though they were not able to be there in the flesh during our fieldwork phase. Thanks to Mr. Chad O. Braley, the intrepid archaeologist who found Fort Argyle in 1985, helped us in 1995/1996, and whose results we have incorporated into this work. Thanks to Michael "Chief" Griffin, who endured the 1995/1996 excavations and coined the sarcastic phrase, "The dirt is not so bad!", in reference to the gummy soils of the fort that were nearly impossible to pass through the shaker screens. While Chief was unable to join us for the most recent dig, he offered additional humorous mental support that bolstered our efforts. Indeed, the dirt was not so bad, it was the ground water in the perched water table that nearly killed us! Thanks to Dr. Mark Williams, who conducted the pioneering remote sensing work at Fort Argyle in 1985, and who has supported our colonial fortification research through the ensuing decades. This report is dedicated to Mr. Joel Carl Jones, who left this earth during the laboratory analysis phase of this project. He served as an archaeological crew chief and assistant historian on the 1995/1996 excavations. Joel brought his extensive field skills, inquiring mind, vast archaeological experience, and fun, personable nature to the site. His departure is lamented by hundreds of archaeologists and other friends who knew Joel. Thanks Joel!

LG²ES field crew members and laboratory staff were involved. Rob Bowman provided excellent preparatory support by overseeing the vegetation clearing and helped with the re-establishment of the original site grid. Thanks Rob, great work! Paul Maggioni provided important logistical support, as well as contributing some important historical and geographical data. Thanks for the heavy lifting Paul! Michele Wiker and Ricky Hight performed heroic deeds as excavators in the field, precisely and scientifically excavated a tremendous amount of wet, clay-filled fortification trenches, and kept meticulous notes for which we were later most grateful. If we had a crew full of Micheles and Rickies no archaeological site would be lost. Thanks and thanks. Other archaeologists on the crew included Josh Logan and J.T. Patton. J.T.'s skills in operating sump pumps was especially useful on the water-retaining site and he and Josh ably pumped out the block units multiple times. LG²ES lab staff included Laboratory

Director Kelsey Noack Myers. She oversaw the initial lab analysis and was responsible for the artifact analysis undertaken by various temporary lab staff. Elizabeth Zieschang drafted digital drawings of field plans and profiles and created graphics from artifact images. Rhianna Bennett and Kathleen McCormick (who photographed artifacts) assisted in parts of this endeavor. Norma Harris and Rhianna Bennett made significant contributions to the analysis and artifact interpretation in the closing days of the laboratory and report writing phases, substantially so that their names are included as co-report author and contributor, respectively. Dan Boylan took our GIS and transit data combined from three excavations over a 34 year period and produced an excellent series of plan maps. We thank you! We appreciate Project Manager Wendy Drennon Puckett, who provided ongoing support prior, during, and after fieldwork. We thank her for her editorial assistance and encouragement, in spite of her heavy project load.

Thanks also to our cheerful, effervescent, and professional volunteers, George Gantt and Mary Elizabeth "Beth" Gantt. They helped us in our final week of fieldwork and without them, our job would have been far less complete. Beth, now you can say officially that you have worked at Fort Argyle, where the dirt is not so bad!

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1.0 INTRODUCTION

This report details the historical research and archaeological excavations and analysis from a British colonial ranger fortification in coastal Georgia. This report is a deliverable under Federal Delivery Order W912HN15D0018-0004 for Phase III Data Recovery Cultural Resource Management at archaeological site 9BN28, better known as Fort Argyle. The field crew excavated a total of 270 m², or approximately 92 m³ of the fort site. This work was performed under contract by LG² Environmental Solutions, Inc. [henceforth cited as LG²ES], an environmental and cultural resources firm based in Jacksonville, Florida.

This project took place on the Fort Stewart Military Reservation from portions of April 2018 to February 2019. U.S. Army Garrison, Fort Stewart and U.S. Army Garrison, Hunter Army Airfield form the largest Army Installation in the eastern United States. This Installation covers more than 285,000 acres in Bryan, Chatham, Evans, Liberty, Long and Tattnall counties, Georgia, and it is used for various training and deployment operations. Its rich archaeological record spans from the prehistoric to the modern age. Components from every major cultural period, except the Mission Period, can be found on Fort Stewart. Prior to the establishment of the Installation in 1941, much of the land was used for the naval stores industry and small subsistence farms (Espenshade et al. 2012). The U.S. Army is responsible for ensuring that its activities are conducted in compliance with Section 106 of the National Historic Preservation Act.

Wendy Drennon Puckett of LG²ES was the Project Manager. Daniel T. Elliott, temporary employee of LG²ES, served as the Principal Investigator, GPR specialist and senior report author. Kelsey Noack Myers, formerly of LG²ES, was the project laboratory director and oversaw laboratory processing, 1st level artifact analysis, artifact photography, database management and curatorial preparation for most of the project. Rita F. Elliott, temporary employee of LG²ES, served as field director and report co-author. Dan Boylan provided GIS spatial analysis expertise and he produced the GIS maps for the project report. Elizabeth Zieschang drafted and prepared many of the report illustrations. Norma Harris and Rhianna Bennett provided expertise and report text and appendix input during the laboratory and reporting phases. Norma also authored major portions of the prehistoric overview.

This report is organized in two volumes. The first contains eight chapters. Chapter 1 introduces the project to the reader. Chapter 2 provides an environmental context for the archaeological project. Chapter 3 consists of an overview of the cultural context from prehistory through the historic period. This chapter closes with a discussion of previous investigations at Fort Argyle. Chapter 4 details the historical research and archaeological methods employed by the project. Chapter 5 provides an in-depth history of Fort Argyle and the rangers and others who lived there. This chapter is organized chronologically and focuses on the period from 1732 to 1864. Chapter 6 details the results of archaeological investigations at Fort Argyle. Chapter 7 is comprised of the interpretations of the historical research and archaeological efforts to explain the ranger fort and its archaeological footprint. Chapter 8 contains a brief summary of the project and recommendations for future research at Fort Argyle and related colonial sites. A complete list of references cited or consulted throughout the project follows the report text. The report includes seven appendices, which are bound as a separate volume. These include: Appendix A- Artifact Inventory; Appendix B-Supplemental Portable X-ray Fluorescence (pXRF) Documentation; Appendix C-ethnobotanical Analysis; Appendix D-Palynology and Phytolith Analysis; Appendix E-Supplemental

Ground Penetrating Radar survey maps and profile views; Appendix F-Test Unit and Feature Locations, LG²ES 2018-2019 Excavations; and Appendix G-Fort Argyle 1985 through 1996 Excavations, Artifact Inventory.

Figure 1.1 Project location

2.0 ENVIRONMENTAL CONTEXT

The physical environment influences human land use and is important to consider in evaluating the archaeological potential of a given area and in interpreting prehistoric and historic site locations. This chapter describes the environmental characteristics of the project area.

2.1 Physiography, Topography, and Hydrology

The state of Georgia is split into five physiographic regions based upon physical geography. These Physiographic Provinces are the Coastal Plain, Piedmont Region, Blue Ridge Region, Ridge and Valley Region, and Appalachian Region (GMNH 2008). Fort Argyle is located within Georgia's Lower Coastal Plain region, a subregion of the Atlantic Coastal Plain. This subregion is characterized by barrier islands, marshes and swampy lowlands near the Atlantic Ocean, but grades to low rolling hills towards the interior. Most of the vegetation in this region consists of slash and loblolly pine, and oak-gum-cypress forests (Seabrook 2006; Wharton 1978; Hodler and Schretter 1986).

Fort Argyle is located in the Barrier Island Sequence District of the Southern Coastal Plain Province. The Barrier Island Sequence District was formed by successive and periodic Pleistocene sea level fluctuations due to periods of continental glaciation. Marine sediments deposited in the region caused a step-like progression of decreasing altitudes to form towards the sea. These terraces are remnants of former barrier island-salt marsh environments that are similar to those of the present coast. The far western sites are located within the Vidalia Upland District, a moderately dissected area with a well-developed dendric stream pattern on gravelly, clayey sands (Clark and Zisa 1976).

The general topography of Fort Stewart is a series of plains, each associated with a former sea level stand. Hodler and Schretter (1986:27) described the topography as "a series of ridges (old barrier island) alternating with pine flatwoods (old marshes) and river swamps (old tidal streams)." Overall, the landscape of Fort Stewart is flat with the only steep slopes occurring along river bluffs, such as Fort Argyle's bluff location.

The Ogeechee and Canoochee rivers are the two major streams that flow through the project area. Fort Argyle is located on the west bank of the Ogeechee River. Most of the surface water at Fort Stewart is part of the Ogeechee River drainage system. The Canoochee River is the largest tributary of the Ogeechee River. The Canoochee is a Coastal Plain river that originates in Emanuel County and flows east through Fort Stewart. The Ogeechee originates in the Piedmont, in Greene County, and flows through the Coastal Plain to empty into Ossabaw Sound. Both the Ogeechee and Canoochee rivers are characterized by a low gradient, severe meandering, and extensive riverside wetlands (Espenshade et al. 2012).

Bryan County receives between 44 and 52 inches of mean annual precipitation. It experiences from 230 to 290 frost-free days on average and the mean annual air temperature ranges from 64 to 70 degrees F.

Sea level fluctuation had a major effect on the prehistoric peoples of the Fort Stewart area. Not only did sea level determine where the coastline was located, but it also affected the formation, location, and behavior of rivers and estuaries. The location of gradients of freshwater to brackish water to sea water also shifted in response. Sea level along the Georgia Coast was within one meter of its present stand by about 4,000 rcybp (4,500 BP). However, some evidence indicates that it took another 2,500 years to reach its current level (Kirkland 2003:150-151). Espenshade et al. (1998) has argued that there was no uniform pattern of sea level change from the Late Archaic to the Mississippian periods in the Fort Stewart area.

2.2 Geological History

The underlying Quaternary geology of the region consists predominantly of sand and sandy clay that were deposited at former high sea levels (Cooke 1943; Lawton 1977).

The largest deposits of chert in eastern Georgia are found north of Fort Stewart, along Brier Creek in Burke and Screven counties (Goad 1979). Knapable stone is relatively scarce in the Coastal Plain. Cobbles of quartz rock and petrified wood occasionally occur in the lower Coastal Plain sections of the Ogeechee and Savannah rivers, particularly in stream beds and sand/gravel bars (Espenshade et al. 2012). These quartz pebbles and petrified wood chunks were used by prehistoric peoples for chipped stone tools.

Soils at Fort Argyle and the immediately surrounding area consist of Craven loamy fine sand, Ogeechee loamy fine sand and Pooler fine sandy loam (Wilkes et al. 1974; USDA - NRCS 2019). The archaeological site of Fort Argyle consists primarily of Craven loamy fine sand, having 0-2 percent slope. These soils are derived from marine deposits. Craven soils are described as moderately well drained and the depth to water table varies from about 18-42 inches in these soils. A typical profile for Craven soils is:

- 0-13 inches, loamy fine sand (H1)
- 13-48 inches, sandy clay (H2)
- 48-58 inches, sandy clay loam (H3)
- 58-80 inches, sandy clay loam (H4).

Ogeechee loamy fine sand are poorly drained soils that occur on flats, in depressions and drainages. It is also derived from marine deposits. The depth to water table in Ogeechee soils is from 0-12 inches. A typical profile of Ogeechee soils consists of:

- 0-8 inches, loamy fine sand (H1)
- 8-23 inches, sandy clay loam (H2)
- 23-42 inches, sandy clay (H3)
- 42-60 inches, sandy clay loam (H4).

Pooler fine sandy loam also is a poorly drained soil type with depth to water table from 0-12 inches. It occurs on depressions and flats and is derived from marine deposits. A typical soil profile of Pooler soils is:

0-6 inches, fine sandy loam (H1)
6-12 inches, sandy clay loam (H2)
12-52 inches, clay (H3)
52-72 inches, sandy clay loam (H4).

2.3 Ecology and Biota

The vegetation at Fort Stewart includes a rich assemblage of species that are relatively undisturbed by modern development. Most of the vegetation in this region consists of slash and loblolly pine, and oak-gum-cypress forests. The project area is located within the Southeastern Evergreen Coastal Plain Forest region, and the upland pine-oak forest found in the project area is representative of the Southern Evergreen Forest (Braun 1950; Wharton 1978). The understory of these kinds of forests is a dense cover of perennial grasses. Fire was and still is a shaping force in open pine forests. Frequent ground fires in these forests result in the selective recruitment of Longleaf pine seedlings, while excluding the young of most other arboreal species (Campbell et al. 2012). Researchers estimated that a two to six-year fire frequency is necessary to maintain the Southern Evergreen Forest (Chapman 1932; Harper 1943; Kozlowski and Ahlgren 1974; Wright and Bailey 1982). Throughout a period known as the Hypsithermal, ca. 8,000-5,000 rcybp, conditions were drier and warmer than prevails today (Healey et al. 2014:7-8). During this time, oak and hickory tree density reached a climax, while beech trees were reduced in areal range and gum trees' areal range increased. After 7,000 BP, the climate grew warmer and possibly drier, resulting in an increase in pine forests, replacing oak and hickory forests in the upper Coastal Plain. Historically, the upland forests of this region were dominated by longleaf pine but also included turkey oak and other oaks as subdominant species (Harper 1914).

Ethnobotanical analysis of selected soil samples from Fort Argyle was undertaken by ethnobotanist Jack Rossen, Ph.D. The full results of his analysis are included as Appendix C. Rossen identified southern yellow pine (*Pinus* sp.) and lesser amounts of red oak and maple wood charcoal in the samples. He identified cultigens corn (*Zea mays*) and possible bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*?). He identified traces of hickory (*Cary asp.*) and possibly acorn (*Quercus* sp.) or American chestnut (*Castanea dentata*). Sumac (*Rhus* sp.) also was identified by two seeds (Rossen 2019).

Palynological analysis and phytolith analysis performed by PaleoResearch Institute, Inc. for LG²ES provides some insight into the variety of plants that grew around Fort Argyle while it was a ranger fort. Their complete pollen, phytolith and parasite study is included as Appendix D in the second volume of this report. Summary information is extracted and is discussed in the following. Cummings and Miller (2019:17) summarize their work:

In general, the pollen signatures revealed that Fort Argyle was situated in an area of pine woods that also supported a wide variety of hardwood trees or shrubs likely growing along the Ogeechee River or in lower, wet areas. The pollen record indicates the presence of maples, alder, birch, hophornbeam/hornbeam, cypress family, chestnut, oak, ash, holly, hickory, walnut, sweetgum, willow, and elm trees. Grassy areas are suggested by moderately large quantities of Poaceae pollen throughout and particularly by the elevated Poaceae pollen frequency in Sample 384 [Fort A, North palisade trench, Fort A, F388 in Test Unit 227, Block AA], representing Palisade Trench

Southwest. Pollen suggests the presence of other herbaceous plants including members of the goosefoot/amaranth family, umbels, wormwood, thistle, ragweed and/or marshelder, other plants in the sunflower family, dandelion and related plants, members of the mustard family, bindweed, sedges, a member of the heath or blueberry family, spurge, two types of clover, legumes, wild buckwheat, wetland knotweed, a member of the buckthorn family, a member of the rose family, and globemallow.

In addition, the pollen record indicates local growth of grapes, rice, and corn, which is supported in the phytolith record by recovery of rice bulliforms and *Commelina* seed phytoliths. Dung fungal spores, recovered in one sample from Palisade Trench East, suggest the presence of grazing animals such as horses. The combined presence of *Oryza*-type pollen or *Oryza*-type bulliforms in all of the samples from this site suggests rice cultivation was important at this site. Ubiquitous distribution of the agricultural remnants of crops is most likely an indicator of their relative abundance. This was accompanied by recovery of *Commelina* seed phytoliths in all but one of the samples examined, suggesting dayflower was a persistent agricultural weed likely associated with rice agriculture.

Zea mays pollen was observed in samples from the cellar, the pit, the chimney base, and three of the Palisade Trench North samples, but not in the Palisade Trench East or Southwest samples. *Vitis* pollen, representing grapes, was noted only in Sample 292 from Palisade Trench East [Fort B, North palisade trench, F221 in Test Unit 120, Block W]. Grapes were a crop that was recommended as being less labor-intensive, so recovery of even this small quantity of *Vitis* pollen is indicative that this strategy was adopted to some extent at Fort Argyle. Recovery of a lenticular starch in Sample 317, collected from Palisade Trench North, suggests growing or processing wheat unless this starch represents seeds from a native festucoid or cool season grass with large seeds. It is not considered diagnostic but is common in seeds from the cultivated grains wheat, rye, oats, and barley and in their native counterparts.

Most of the plant species identified forming the fossil pollen and phytolith record retrieved from Fort Argyle's colonial features are found growing in Bryan County today. Notable exceptions include chestnut (which was decimated in eastern North America by a blight around 1918) and rice (an imported cultigen whose production in Georgia began a rapid decline by about 1864).

Rice was an important commodity and food source in eighteenth century Georgia. It is not surprising that rice is manifest in the fossil pollen and phytolith record of Fort Argyle. Rice agriculture developed quickly in coastal Georgia after slavery was introduced. Royal Governor James Wright owned several large plantations very near Fort Argyle, where his enslaved population tilled the labor-intensive rice dike and rice paddie systems. Other wealthy planters owned similar plantations adjacent to Governor Wright's rice farms. Captain John Milledge, who commanded Fort Argyle from 1742 to 1767, owned several thousand acres very near Fort Argyle as well, and although we have not located any written accounts of his plantation's rice production, it is a safe assume that rice was prominent in his agricultural produce (Smith 1991).

The cultivation of rice in coastal Georgia is no simple feat. Land that is too close to the coast contains water with high saline content, which is deadly to rice. Land that is too far upstream from the effects of the tides could only be cultivated by creating more labor-intensive, freshwater reservoirs, or by growing species of upland rice. Upland rice was cultivated in the Ebenezer settlement on the Savannah River watershed, as was the traditional wetlands rice. Upland rice, also known as dry rice, does not require flooded fields but is watered by rainfall (Oikeh et al. 2019). One modern upland rice cultigen sold by a seed farm in Maine, notes:

Traditionally, upland rice grows in drier conditions. All rice seems to prefer moist soils and we have found that it also does well in our flooded clay paddies. In drier conditions it will outperform lowland rices. Does better than lowland rice amongst other dryland agriculture crops. Neither upland nor lowland rice likes growing in sandy soils, but Upland varieties can tolerate more sandy composition than lowland varieties. I recommend mulching well, if growing in a dryer area. Upland rice is taller than lowland rice, and has less tillers. Each tiller is thicker and will produce more seeds. 12-24 tillers per plant. Heights top out around 4 feet (Wild Folk Farm 2019:1).

What we do not know is what use the rangers at Fort Argyle made of rice. Clearly, it would have provided a good source of nutrition and was locally available. Rice stalks and chaff would have been excellent fodder for their horses. Rice stalks and chaff also may have provided bedding for the soldiers.

Most rice agriculture in Georgia came to an abrupt halt in December 1864 after U.S. Army troops commanded by Major General William T. Sherman wrecked most of the local rice dike systems during its March to the Sea campaign. While some plantation owners tried to salvage rice production after the war they were unsuccessful due to various reasons, chiefly being the loss of their enslaved rice workers. Vestiges of some of the wetland rice fields survive today in Georgia and South Carolina and are visible in some areas (where the former fields are not obscured by heavy vegetation) on modern aerial imagery.

Cummings and Miller (2019:11-12) noted,

White rice (*O. sativa*) purportedly was introduced to South Carolina in 1686 from a cache of seed brought from Madagascar (Smith and Dilday 2003: vii-viii). By the end of the 17th century, rice production became the primary commodity exported from South Carolina. Red rice (*O. glaberrima*), native to the Niger River in western Africa and known colloquially as 'Guinea rice' or 'bearded rice', appears to have been a staple in the diet of slaves in Georgia by the end of the 18th century (Carney 2001:387-388)... Additional strains of red rice (*O. punctata* and *O. longistaminata*), known colloquially as 'Volunteer' rice and also native to Africa, were found at Georgia plantations, but were considered weeds and not harvested as commodities (Stewart 1996:160).

Other plants appear in the Fort Argyle archaeological record. Cummings and Miller (2019:17) noted that "a member of the rose family" was identified in Fort Argyle's fossil pollen record. Botanist Stephen Elliott wrote in 1821 that *Crateagus Arborescens*, common name lance-leaved hawthorn, was observed growing at Fort Argyle (Figure 2.1). This tree, a member of the rose family, grows to 20-30 feet in height, with

spreading branches (Elliott 1821, vol. 1:550; Nuttall and Michaux 1841: Plate XLV). One specimen of this tree was observed growing at Fort Argyle in early February 2019, where it was in bloom. Modern botanists do not recognize Stephen Elliott's species name, but four dozen other species of *Crateagus* genus are native to Georgia (Martin et al. 1951; Yarrow and Yarrow 1999).

Figure 2.1 *Crataegus Arborescens* (Nuttall and Michaux 1841: Plate XLV).

Grapes, which were identified as *Vitis* pollen, are more likely the native Muscadine, *Vitis rotundifolia*, which is found in abundance surrounding Fort Argyle today. Imported grapes from Europe never took hold in coastal Georgia. The muscadines, which are a native plant found throughout southeastern North America, represent an important, nutritional and tasty food source to both Native Americans and Euro-Americans living at Fort Argyle (Mohlenbrock 1991). For the rangers in the fort, these juicy muscadines may have provided the essential raw ingredients for distilling wine or brandy.

The pollen identified as a member of the buckthorn family represents *Frangula caroliniana*, or Carolina Buckthorn. This is a large, erect shrub or small tree native to the southeastern United States. Its clusters of small berries attract birds, although it is considered a minor food source. It also was consumed by large mammals, but again only as a minor food source. For humans, Carolina Buckthorn is edible and may have served as a famine food for the rangers and other occupants of the site (Miller and Miller 1999; Miller et al. 2005).

Corn is a cultigen represented in the pollen record by *Zea mays* and is currently grown in parts of Bryan and Chatham counties. Some local soils are well suited for corn agriculture, although most of these counties are forested today. Corn was a cultigen that developed in southeastern North America in prehistoric times. By the mid-eighteenth century, corn was an important food source for all residents of coastal Georgia. The presence of *Zea mays* pollen from Forts B and C contexts and its complete absence from the two Fort A palisade ditches that were sampled for fossil pollen may signal that corn became increasingly available during the life of Fort Argyle.

Modern fauna of the Coastal Marine Flatwoods is summarized by Wharton (1978) and includes diverse species of mammals, birds, fish, reptiles, and amphibians. It is believed a much wider variety of the extant fauna were available for exploitation during the prehistoric and early historic period habitations of the region (Golley 1962; Laerm et al. 1981, Rock et al. 2012, Wharton 1978, Espenshade et al. 2012).

2.5 Project Location

The project area is situated on the west bank of the Ogeechee River in Bryan County, Georgia. Figures 2.2 through 2.6 show a series of twentieth century cartographic and aerial imagery views of the Fort Argyle environment.

Figure 2.2. Aerial Photograph of Fort Argyle, 1947.

Figure 2.3. USGS Meldrim Quadrangle Sheet, Showing Fort Argyle, 1950.

Figure 2.4. Aerial Photograph Showing Fort Argyle, 1957

Figure 2.5. Aerial Photograph Showing Fort Argyle, 1966.

Figure 2.6. Aerial Photograph Showing Fort Argyle, 2001.

3.0 CULTURAL CONTEXT

The interpretation and discussion of archaeological sites is achieved by categorizing them by cultural regions, temporal periods, and functional site types. Interactions between humans, the environment, and different human groups dictate behavioral patterns which are interpreted from the material deposited in the archaeological record. These dynamic patterns can reflect the sociocultural developments, interactions, and behaviors of different human groups (Smith 2012).

The following overview outlines the cultural context at Fort Stewart as well as the general cultural developments of the southeastern United States from the Prehistoric period to the period when Fort Stewart was established. This cultural overview draws upon data presented in the revised Fort Stewart/Hunter Army Airfield (FS/HAAF) Site Significance Model (Healey et al. 2014) because it contains the most comprehensive and up to date synthesis of the southeastern Georgia cultural model. Other cultural models from the Middle Savannah River Valley (Sassaman et al. 1990:7) and the Lower Savannah River Valley (DePratter 1991:11), St. Catherines Island (Thomas 2008:990-1045) and the interior Coastal Plain (Stephenson and Snow 2004) contribute to our cultural context. It is almost certain that what is now the coast was inhabited during preceramic prehistory and the dearth of artifacts and sites dating to those times continue to remain a mystery (Healey et al. 2014:3).

3.1 Prehistoric Context

Coastal Georgia has a rich prehistoric record. It spans the Paleoindian Period through the Protohistoric Period. These are highlighted below.

3.1.1 Paleoindian Period

Debate continues as to the earliest dates that people crossed into the Americas. The traditional story of the First Americans crossing over from Asia to North America via Beringia exclusively seems to be in doubt. During (or shortly after) the last glacial maximum of the Pleistocene (ca. 21,000 cal yr BP), the accepted conventional interpretations were consistent among archaeologists (see Anderson and Sassaman 2012). Now a more complex story is emerging, challenged by data collected along the coast of South America and in the Northwestern United States (Anderson and Sassaman 2012; Anderson and Gillam 2000; Dillehay 1997; Faught 2006; Jantz and Owsley 2005). Clovis and pre-Clovis cultures (see Goodyear 2005) leave little behind for archaeologists to interpret their daily life. With few exceptions, lithic remains are all that survive.

The mobile lifestyle of early foragers and hunters was an adaptation to their environment of wild plants and large Pleistocene animals such as mammoth, mastodon, giant beavers and ground sloths, camels, horses, and bison. The animals that early Paleoindians depended on in the late Pleistocene soon became extinct and there are some researchers that think that the human population may have had a hand in their disappearance (for example see Fiedel 2005). A nondiagnostic point was found in a bison skull in the Wacissa River in Florida (Webb et al. 1984). More recent excavations on the Continental Shelf of the

eastern Gulf of Mexico have located Paleo and Archaic lithic tools in submerged contexts near the mouth of the Aucilla River (Faught 2004, 2006).

The Late Paleoindian Period (ca. 12,450 cal yrs BP to 11,500 cal yrs BP) material culture is vastly different from the previous large fluted and unfluted points. The Dalton point is much smaller and reflects a significant change in the plant and animal environments from the earlier periods. Most of the large megafauna were extinct and the Dalton point was used for smaller animals. There was also an increased use of plant resources at this time (Anderson 1995; Anderson and Sassaman 2012). Generally in the southeastern U.S., Dalton points are the most common formal tool encountered; however, there are few recorded in the Coastal Plain regions of South Carolina, Georgia, and none in peninsular Florida. Healey et al. (2014:6-7) reports only eight Daltons in their 10-county study area as context for Ft. Stewart/Hunter Army Airfield.

3.1.2 The Archaic Period

The Archaic Period (covering approximately 8,300 years) has long been divided into three subperiods by archaeologists: Early, Middle and Late. More recently a fourth subperiod, the Terminal Archaic has entered the archaeologist's lexicon. Each subperiod is defined by the traditional artifact assemblages, but the recent increase in research on all types of Archaic sites has contributed greatly to our understanding of the paleoenvironment of these past cultures. Each boundary between divisions generally coincides with climatic changes that can help describe and explain the increasing variation. Deeply stratified sites such as rock shelters and caves, floodplains and shell middens are contributing to a greater understanding in material culture, subsistence, settlement patterns, monumental constructions, ritual and mortuary practices throughout the Archaic period. By the end of the Archaic period, during the Terminal Archaic subperiod, crude fiber tempered pottery and soapstone bowls are added to the material culture inventory in Georgia (Anderson and Sassaman 2004, 2012; Elliott and Sassaman 1995; Kidder and Sassaman 2009; Thomas and Sanger 2010).

3.1.3 Woodland Period

The Woodland Period is frequently seen as a time of rapid expansion of populations, greater contact and/or transmission of ideas over a wide area of the southeast. Many groups adopted similar, if not exact manifestations of the same religious symbols, mound construction, and mortuary practices. Although geographically distant from the first appearance of these "panregional" influences, the ideas, artwork and ceremonialism spread from the Gulf and Coastal Plains, North Florida, the Lower Mississippi Valley, Midsouth and the Appalachians. Certain traits from the Hopewell homeland in the Midwest can be seen in assemblages in many of these culture areas by 3200 cal yrs BP, and as late as AD 1000. Some groups developed religious practices probably influenced by the Hopewellian rituals but are also seen as a continuation of some Late Archaic traditions (Anderson and Sassaman 2012:112).

Traditional research on the Woodland Period in the past has centered on some of the long-term inclinations of archaeologists to understand how it contributed to the rise of Mississippi Period, with its social inequality, agriculture of corn, beans and squash, and large civic centers. Another approach is

taken by Jefferies (2004) and others to look at the major trends of the Woodland Period itself, which include: increased dietary importance of seeds; increased sedentism; more elaborate mortuary ceremonialism and burial mounds; and widespread adoption of pottery (Jeffries 2004:115). Jeffries explains that all four common traits are present in the Archaic Period, but it is during the Woodland that these practices became the impetus for major changes that occur in the Southeast over the next 2,000 years.

The general dates for the Woodland Period are taken from Anderson and Sassaman (2012:115), but the specific inception of the culture traits associated with the Early, Middle, and Late Woodland, vary from region to region. The culture area that is the focus of this section is centered on the South Atlantic coast of Georgia (Coastal Plain and Coastal Strand), therefore the dates for each subperiod will be taken from literature applicable to those specific geographic areas.

The Early and Middle Woodland on the Georgia coast is defined by the appearance of Refuge and Deptford ceramics (see Caldwell and Waring 1939, DePratter 1978, Guerrero and Thomas 2008, Williams 1968). The range of Refuge types include sand and or fine grit tempering, with incised, simple stamped, plain and a dentate stamped (DePratter 1978).

Milanich (1971, 1973) offered the earliest model for Deptford culture. He described Deptford adaptations as having a primarily coastal orientation with bands staying near the coast for most of the year but moving as the seasons or resources required. Their subsistence methods consisted of gathering, hunting and fishing. Coastal sites are concentrated in the live oak forests bordering the marshlands where other plants, and animals such as deer, oysters, clams and turtles have been found in Deptford period archaeological context. Other less frequent remains found in Deptford middens are sea turtles, seals, porpoises and whales. Deptford sites occurring upriver in Georgia are common and Milanich suggested that the coastal populations were moving inland from time to time, maybe in association with seasonal resources inland (Milanich 1971, 1973, Stevenson et al 2002). A few burial mounds attributed to Deptford culture have been excavated (including Milanich's 1971 excavation on Cumberland Island).

Combining Refuge and Deptford periods, Reitz (2008) examined vertebrate remains from nine sites on St. Catherine's Island using data from the island-wide transect survey. The sites produced relatively few faunal remains (n=1491) and many of them were fish. Other bones found belonged to rabbit, racoon, deer, geese, turkey, alligator, pond turtle and terrapin. Fishes represented were gar, catfishes, seatrout and black drum (Reitz 2008:631). Here are some of Reitz's concluding hypotheses: Late Archaic focused almost exclusively on marine resources; post-Archaic occupants (including Woodland sites) preferred more continuity than change; occupation on the island was not seasonal for any time period; wild birds were rarely used; and small mammals were an important resource (Reitz 2008:663-664).

Early/Middle Woodland sites are common on the Georgia coast sea islands, and for some distance into the interior. One Chatham County mound site (the Irene Site) will be discussed in more detail later. The fill from both mounds contained large numbers of St. Simons, Refuge, Deptford and Wilmington Heavy Cord marked pottery. The impressive Mississippian Period Irene mounds were constructed on the Savannah

River on the same landscape that Late Archaic and Early/Middle and Late Woodland people lived for centuries (Caldwell and McCann 1941).

3.1.3 Mississippi Period

The dates for the Mississippi Period are based on a loose conglomeration of works by DePratter (1978, 1991), Crook (1986), Braley (1990) and the extensive data collected by Thomas et al (2008) on St. Catherines Island. Once again, the Mississippi Period begins on the Georgia Coast with a confusion in the ceramic assemblages in the Early and Middle Mississippi subperiods. Crook (1986) and Larson (1980) have clear opinions that do not support a distinct boundary between the Late Woodland and the Early Mississippi periods for Coastal Georgia. Thomas combines the Savannah and St. Catherine's phases into one that he calls St. Catherines (Thomas 2008b: 430-432). However, the view of the lifeways of the Mississippi people on the Coastal Strand do come together into a picture of a broader Mississippian period influence with distinct coastal adaptations, with just a few exceptions.

Early definitions of Southeastern cultures living between AD 1000 and AD 1580 started with an attempt to force the coastal Georgia peoples into a comparison with the large civic ceremonial centers that dwarfed the small mounds and villages of the Georgia coastline. The largest of these civilizations was centered around the Cahokia Mounds in Missouri. Other large ceremonial centers throughout the known Mississippian culture areas were targets for early "archaeologists" such as Clarence Bloomfield Moore in the late 1800s and early 1900s. Moore's methods were far from modern, but some information can be gleaned from his extensive excavations.

Although the mounds of coastal Georgia were indeed smaller, Moore found several that were worthy of his time (Moore 1897, also see introduction by Lewis Larson to reprinted volume, 1998). Moore visited several mound sites on Ossabaw Island at the mouth of the Ogeechee River but his steamboat, "The Gopher" made no excursions up the Ogeechee River. Moore visited the Irene Mound Site in 1897 and dug into the large platform mound but was more focused on the smaller burial mound. The Irene Mound complex was excavated by Caldwell in 1941 and he was one of the earliest archaeologists to address the ceramic chronology of the Savannah River Basin. Without the benefit of today's technology (radiocarbon dating, specifically), Caldwell was able to excavate both mounds and other large structural features and begin to establish the chronology, burial patterns, and ceremonial practices, thus beginning to understand Coastal Strand Mississippian people (Caldwell and McCann 1941).

3.2 Historic Context

3.2.1 Exploration Period

Beginning in the early 1500s, European adventurers explored the Southeast and contacted native Indian tribes. Some explorers made attempts at colonization. In 1521, Francisco de Gordillo sailed north up the Atlantic coast and encountered the coastal islands of Georgia. The first attempted European settlement in Georgia may date to as early as 1526, when 600 Spanish colonists under Lucas Vasquez de Ayllón went ashore in the Santee River area of what is now South Carolina, but moved after only a short time

either to another area in South Carolina or near Sapelo Sound, Georgia. The colonists starved and mostly died, including Ayllón. A few ragged survivors made it back to Hispaniola using crude boats (Healey et al. 2014:31-32; Hoffman 2004:32-38; Thomas 1993:12). During the winter of 1540, Hernando de Soto's army of 600 soldiers landed at what is now Tampa Bay and marched north through Georgia following a circuitous route throughout the Southeast. Only about half of those who began the adventure made it back to the Spanish town at Vera Cruz, Mexico in 1543 (Healey et al. 2014:32; Hudson 1997).

French settlements in 1562-1565 led by the Huguenot Jean Ribault proved just as ephemeral as the prior Spanish expeditions, with the French abandoning Charlesfort on Parris Island, South Carolina, and getting annihilated by the Spanish at Fort Caroline in present-day Florida. The Spanish in turn established their own settlement of Saint Augustine, the first permanent European settlement in what is now the United States (Healey et al. 2014:32; Milanich 2006: 78-86). The Spanish also founded the settlement of Santa Elena at the same location as Charlesfort in 1566 and quickly established relations with the Guale, the native population in the area (DePratter 2009:19; Healey et al. 2014:33). Although quickly abandoning Santa Elena, with their expulsion of the French and the successful settlement of Saint Augustine, the Spanish assumed control over the southern Atlantic coastline of the present-day southeastern United States (Healey et al. 2014:33; Thomas 1993:14; Ward 1985).

3.2.2 Mission Period (A.D. 1580-1680) and Contested Land (1680-1732)

By the end of the sixteenth century, the Franciscan Order established a series of missions along the South Carolina, Georgia, and Florida Atlantic coasts, and north-central Florida. The Franciscans promoted the adoption of farming and catechized the natives in the tenets of the Catholic faith.

3.2.3 English Colonial Period

In the early 1730s the British Crown's desire for a buffer colony to protect the Carolinas coincided with an effort led by James Edward Oglethorpe, an aristocrat and Member of Parliament, to resettle "the worthy poor" of England to an American colony (Oglethorpe 1742; 1873; Harris 1841; Ettinger 1984; Spaulding 1984). And so, mixing Christian charity with realpolitik, King George II granted the Trustees a charter to establish and govern the Colony of Georgia. Oglethorpe led the first settlers over the Atlantic and planted the colony at Yamacraw Bluff (Savannah), 24 kilometers up the Savannah River, on February 12, 1733.

The Trustees initially forbade slavery in the colonies, restricted the ownership and sale of property, and ruled the colony with little input from the colonists. These policies had the effect of economically stunting the colony during its earliest days, and throughout the 1730s colonists became ever more discontent (Coleman 1976:127). From 1739-1742, Great Britain fought a war with Spain. The fighting destabilized the fledgling colony, with many settlers moving to South Carolina for brighter economic prospects. South Carolina allowed slavery, at the time a necessary ingredient for the southern plantation economy, proving that economic laws do not always correspond with moral law. By 1743 only 300 people remained in Savannah. (Miller 1986:8). Finally, in 1750, the Trustees allowed land ownership in fee simple. They also

legalized slavery in the colony, giving rise in Georgia to the development of plantations on the South Carolina model, growing indigo—and rice (Sullivan 2003:24-25).

In 1752, the Trustees surrendered their charter to George II, making Georgia a colony governed directly by the Crown, with a Royal Governor and a House of Assembly (Sullivan 2003:26). In 1758, the Assembly created eight separate parishes (units of government) within the colony. This included Christ Church Parish, which would later become Chatham County after the Revolution (Sullivan 2003:28). Savannah and Christ Church Parish continued to be the primary population center and seat of government for the colony. During this time, government officials created a lazaretto (quarantine station) on the west side of Tybee Island to house sick passengers and prevent the disease from spreading to Savannah. (Miller 1986:8).

The colony's increasingly prosperous economy is illustrated by shipping statistics. In 1754, the port of Savannah shipped 1900 tons of commodities on 52 vessels. This increased to 10,500 tons on almost 150 ships in 1770 (Sullivan 2003:33). By the early 1770s the colony exported over two million feet of timber and nearly 60,000 pounds of tobacco. Some Georgia planters began growing indigo, although this industry remained small compared to South Carolina's (Reese 1963:127-132). However, rice dominated as the most important cash crop of the colony. The first year Georgia planters exported rice was 1756, with 2300 barrels shipped (Clifton 1978:282). By the 1770s this number had grown to nearly 24,000 barrels, accounting for a third of the value of all the colony's exports. The rice culture also firmly established slavery as the primary social and economic institution of the colony (Clifton 1978:282; Spaulding 1991:51-53). By the 1760s rice plantations lined the Georgia side of the Savannah River, from the town of Savannah upriver through the area opposite Argyle Island. In Georgia, planters adopted a new (to the colonial South) tidal method of rice irrigation. Many, if not most of these planters originally came from South Carolina (Reese 1963:121; Sullivan 2003:31).

However, political strife tore at the colony's bonds with the Mother Country. With Parliament passing the Stamp Act in 1765, the Sons of Liberty formed in Savannah to protest the government's imposition of taxes without colonial representation. In 1773-1774, many Georgians grew outraged at British treatment of Massachusetts in retaliation for colonists' destruction of tea in Boston Harbor, in protest of the Tea Act. The outbreak of open warfare in 1775 greatly diminished the authority of Georgia's Royal Governor, James Wright, who narrowly escaped the colony in February 1776 as power slipped into the hands of Savannah's Committee of Safety (Spaulding 1991:63-67).

3.2.5 Early American Period

In 1776 Georgia's Provincial Congress issued its first temporary constitution, replaced the colonial parishes with eight counties and sending delegates to Philadelphia to sign the Declaration of Independence (Coleman 1991:75; Sullivan 2003:37). In December 1778 the British retook Savannah, although Georgia's upcountry (Burke and Wilkes Counties) remained defiantly in the Patriot camp. In October 1779 French and Patriot forces tried and failed to take Savannah in a brief siege and a bloody direct assault. In turn, the British succeeded in capturing Charleston and an entire Continental Army there under General Lincoln in May 1780. With no force to oppose them, the British and Tories overran

most of Georgia except for remote corners of Wilkes and Richmond Counties. Glory crowned British arms with near-total control of the colony for about a year, until a Continental Army under General Nathaniel Greene took Augusta in June 1781, which again left the upcountry in the Patriots' hands (Coleman 1991:82-86). Savannah itself, however, remained under British control.

In July 1782, the British evacuated Georgia, and peace broke out a year later (Coleman 1991:86). Georgia's affairs had sunk to a sorry state, with a countryside devastated by what amounted to a civil war between Patriots and Loyalists, characterized by vicious back-and-forth raids and personal vendettas among former friends and neighbors. The new government expelled many of the more prominent citizens as Loyalists and confiscated their property.

Over the next twenty years Georgia recovered and began to prosper once again. Shortly after the Revolution, local self-government came to Georgia and the City of Savannah was incorporated in 1787. Throughout the period after the Revolution and well into the 1800s the State made numerous grants to families to settle deep into the interior of the state. As the state's frontiers pushed west, so did the capital, which moved from Savannah to Augusta in 1786, and then to Louisville in 1795 (Coleman 1991:91). Although never really the political center of the state, Savannah during this period continued to be the primary port of Georgia (Coleman 1991:113). Economically speaking, the coastal area around Savannah recovered slowly after the war. In addition, much energy in the state was directed at settlement and development in the upcountry.

3.3 Previous Investigations of Fort Argyle

Historical interest in Georgia's colonial military sites was sparked in the late 1800s with the publication of Charles C. Jones, Jr.'s *History of Georgia* (1883) and *Dead Towns of Georgia* (1878). Jones discussed Fort Barrington, Hardwick, Frederica, and Fort Argyle by making the best use of the colonial records that were available to him. Gazetteers of the state during the nineteenth century also identify Fort Argyle as a historical place (Sherwood 1829, 1860). The Fort Argyle place name lingered for decades after the fort was abandoned. Residents undoubtedly knew of the approximate location of the fort, and many relics were probably taken from the fort during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries by local history buffs. The Colonial Dames visited the presumed site of Fort Argyle in 1929 when the property was owned by R. C. Jacobs, and the organization's secretary provided this early description of the site's setting.

Today the site of this old fortification is in a large field which appears to have been an extensive Indian settlement. There is an inclined roadway cut through the bluff to the water's edge and directly opposite, where the Ogeechee River is about 200 feet wide at low water, is the end of a road which goes through a few hundred yards of a swamp on the Chatham side...the property is owned by Mr. Russell Calhoun Jacobs, a native of Minnesota and his wife, who was from Pennsylvania. The house occupies the site 50 feet from the pit which was much deeper when the Jacobs bought it twelve years ago. Tradition says the pit was the cellar within the fort. The pit is about 125 feet from the bluff, situated on a bend in the river. Between the pit and the bank is said to have been an old cemetery. The land has been plowed, and Mrs. Jacobs says she has many arrowheads which she has found there. A little distance from the house is a mound of earth

which is all that is left of an old brick yard of a period just after the Civil War. There is an old wheel near the mound. Mr. Jacobs has a saw mill and turpentine still on the river bank (Georgia Society Colonial Dames of America 1929).

Interest in Georgia's colonial forts was rekindled during the 1930s when New Deal archaeologists began searching for sites to excavate in coastal Georgia. Private citizens, such as Bessie Lewis, Margaret Davis Cate, Marmaduke Floyd, Dolores B. Floyd, Pearl Gnann and Lucian Lamar Knight also focused public attention on these sites and the wheels were set in motion to memorialize several of them as state and national historic sites (Knight 1913, Vol. 1:331-332). The grandest example was Fort Frederica, which was designated a National Monument. Extensive excavations were conducted at Frederica during the 1950s and 1960s. Several state historic sites also were established in Georgia because of these pioneering researchers. Sadly, Fort Argyle was not one of these sites.

The year after a short article on Fort Argyle appeared in the *Georgia Magazine* (Polk 1966), Alston C. Waylor, a representative of the Georgia Historical Commission, visited the fort vicinity at the request of Fort Stewart personnel. Waylor reconnoitered the suspected fort area off Road 59, which, "at that time was under consideration for a recreation area for the post personnel". Waylor concluded that "very little, if any, of the fort remains", since the site had been disturbed by construction of a brickyard and by years of cultivation. Waylor made a small collection of "some chinaware and glass fragments", which he estimated dated from the mid nineteenth to early twentieth century. He noted that the plans for the recreation area were dropped by Fort Stewart and nine acres in the vicinity were set aside for protection (Waylor 1968). The Georgia State Historic Preservation Office, Department of Natural Resources conducted a historical, archaeological and architectural survey of Fort Stewart in 1974 and Fort Argyle was determined eligible for the NRHP. A plat of the Fort Argyle vicinity, drawn in 1975 by Mr. Houston, showed some interesting features as well as some speculation about the location of the fort ruin. A portion of this plat was redrawn and presented in Elliott 1997 (Figure 4). Fort Argyle was listed on the National Register of Historic Places (NRHP) in 1976.

The Fort Argyle site was first recorded as an archaeological site (9Bry28, later renamed 9BN28) during a 1982 survey of Fort Stewart Military Reservation by archaeologists with Professional Analysts, located in Eugene, Oregon (Miller et al. 1983). Their work was a reconnaissance level effort and no shovel tests or excavations were conducted. They described the mounded area previously thought to be the fort location to be more likely associated with the nineteenth century brick factory. The area containing earthworks and a borrow pit were photographed, a sketch map was prepared, and several bricks were collected from the surface. The mound was described as, "about 2 m high, 50 m long, and 20 m wide with long axis oriented northwest-southeast" and, "flat topped and has two large central depressions at either end of the long axis"(Miller et al. 1983:215). The ruins of the brick factory presently are designated a separate archaeological site (9BN121), although the components of the two sites overlap horizontally. The Fort Argyle area was designated as off limits for training on July 13, 1982 following terrain damage by tracked vehicles (Fort Stewart, Disposition Form 1982).

In 1985, the National Park Service funded research by Southeastern Archeological Services (SAS) in Athens, Georgia to physically locate the remains of Fort Argyle (Braley et al. 1985). SAS was able to

locate and pinpoint the remains of a colonial fort. Historical research by Roy Doyon for SAS provided an excellent historical context for the site. Braley postulated a rectangular fort, based on a series of palisade ditches that he identified from his test excavations. That fort's measurements matched the 110-foot by 110-foot dimensions described by Georgia Governor James Wright in 1762.

The SAS project began with systematically placed shovel tests over the suspected fort area with tests spaced at 20 m intervals. From these data the approximate limits of eighteenth-century artifacts were mapped. The probable fort area was then examined by a series of 50 cm by 50 cm test units, larger 2 m by 2 m test units, and 1 m wide test trenches of varying lengths. The SAS work resulted in the excavation of 52 m² at Fort Argyle. Archaeologists identified palisade ditches, numerous other architectural features, and a shallow midden deposit of eighteenth-century artifacts, all of which were interpreted as the remains of the fort. Two types of remote sensing were conducted under the direction of archaeo-geophysicist Mark Williams on the suspected site. One of these methods, proton magnetometry, proved unsatisfactory because of the extensive presence of recent metal on the site. The other method, soil resistivity, yielded promising results. Williams mapped a series of soil resistivity anomalies. He interpreted some of these as structure ruins possibly associated with the fort. The results of Williams' soil resistivity survey are contained in Braley et al. (1985).

Chad Braley also made an impromptu exploratory scuba reconnaissance survey of the Ogeechee River bottom adjacent to the fort site (although it was outside of his Scope of Work) and he assessed the potential for submerged resources associated with the fort. SAS made a series of recommendations for site protection and management of these underwater resources. SAS also submitted a revised NRHP form in 1986 showing the enlarged site boundaries as well as providing additional historical and archaeological context for the site.

A U.S. Army military exercise, known as "Operation Deep Thrust", in December 1985 resulted in substantial ground disturbance on the northern portion of the Fort Argyle site. Another contract was issued to Carolina Archaeological Services (CAS) of Columbia, South Carolina to determine the extent of disturbance to a 20-acre area of the site. This work, documented in a research report by Martin and her colleagues (1986), included excavation of a series of 10 judgmentally-placed 50 cm by 50 cm test units and examination of the fill of nine recently excavated military foxholes at Fort Argyle. Archaeologist Newell Wright also conducted an underwater surface survey of the Ogeechee River bottom, as part of the CAS study. The CAS study focused north of the area examined by SAS and resulted in the identification of a post-colonial house ruin and shallow midden deposit. The CAS study found that "a light scatter of eighteenth-century materials extends from the river bluff to Fort Stewart Road 60C, and to a very limited extent, north of this road" (Martin et al. 1986:13).

The 20-acre portion of the site, designated Zone A by CAS, was assessed by Martin and her colleagues as secondary deposits, which did, "not contain significant cultural deposits associated with the National Register qualities of Fort Argyle" (Martin et al. 1986:20). The area immediately south of the CAS study area was investigated by the LAMAR Institute team in 1995/1996. The LAMAR Institute findings conflict with those presented by CAS. The LAMAR Institute suggested in 1997 that a reassessment be made of the land areas 'written off' by CAS, particularly the area of the bluff that is located south of the boat

launching ramp. This area of the site has a high likelihood of containing human burials. It also probably contains features and important material culture associated with Fort Argyle. Nothing would indicate that this area contains secondary deposits. The test units excavated by CAS actually yielded twice the frequency of artifacts per m² than the areas of the fort that were sampled by SAS and the LAMAR Institute. The fact that no features were found by CAS is perfectly logical when one considers that they sampled less than 3 m² in a 20-acre study area. CAS concluded that, "No evidence of substantial remnants associated with the eighteenth-century occupation of Fort Argyle, such as features or activity loci, was observed" (Martin et al. 1986:14, 16, 20).

We disagree with her conclusions regarding the archaeological potential for colonial period features and other relatively undisturbed, colonial occupational debris in this part of 9BN28. The areas sampled by SAS and the LAMAR Institute yielded a comparable density of features per m². The CAS' sample was inadequate to rule out the possibility of colonial-era features in this area. The distribution of colonial period artifacts found by CAS, particularly in Foxholes 7 and 8, and CAS Test Units 4 and 10, is not significantly less than the shovel test densities reported from some parts of the site within the colonial fort by SAS (Braley et al. 1985: Appendix A). Since the present study demonstrated that houses, burials, and other features exist outside the fort walls, then the possibility of additional satellite settlements north of the fort should be reassessed. It is known that 10 families were initially sent to settle at Fort Argyle. Some of these settlers may have built temporary lodging near the fort until their farmsteads could be developed. *Building 1* in Block N may be an example of this behavior. The density of colonial period artifacts associated with Building 1 was relatively low, and it is reasonable to expect that some house sites at Argyle have less material culture associated with them. However, this does not render them insignificant. An argument can be made that they may be more significant, since they may reveal a glimpse of a narrow span of time during the early frontier settlement at Argyle.

In our opinion the 1986 CAS survey of Zone A at 9BN28 was inadequate for a NRHP-listed site of such national significance as Fort Argyle. We recommend a re-survey of the 20 acres examined by CAS with systematic shovel tests (50 cm by 50 cm) on a 5 m grid (excluding areas of the gravel road, boat ramp and steep bank). Larger test excavations should be excavated in the areas north and south of the road to better determine the potential for subsurface features. Such an effort was beyond the scope of the present LG²ES project.

In 1995 and 1996, the LAMAR Institute, Inc., performed a study of Fort Argyle through a Department of Defense Legacy Grant (Elliott 1997). Their team excavated 82 m², which were configured as forty-one 2 m by 1 m test units. Some of these units were placed adjacent to units excavated 10 years earlier by SAS, which brought the total excavated area of Fort Argyle to slightly more than 134 m² by January 1996. The LAMAR Institute's study located more features and artifacts from the colonial period. Noteworthy findings from that work included the discovery of a second Fort Argyle, which was partially nested within the rectangular fort outline identified by SAS, portions of three colonial buildings, and one possible late nineteenth or early twentieth century grave (F177). Elliott suspected that a third, even larger fort had been constructed based on the presence of an eighteenth-century building footprint that was located outside of the second rectangular fort on the southern part of the site. At the end of that study, Elliott estimated that approximately 90 percent of Fort Argyle remained unexcavated. The LAMAR

Institute's archaeologists also shovel-test surveyed 150 acres surrounding Fort Argyle. While two previously unrecorded archaeological sites were located by that survey, neither dated to the colonial period.

In addition to the archaeological discoveries, LAMAR Institute's researchers Daniel Elliott and Joel Jones compiled extensive historical background information about the fort and its former inhabitants. The 2018 study draws freely from the previous history research by Elliott and Jones and includes significant information compiled in the earlier study. However, it should be noted that the 1996 study was done in the early years of the World Wide Web when many useful internet research resources, such as Google Books, Internet Archive and Ancestry.com, were either in their infancy or did not yet exist.

The LAMAR Institute's excavations in 1996 were the most recent archaeological excavations at Fort Argyle prior to the present LG²ES work. The U.S. Army Corps of Engineers funded a long-term management plan for Fort Argyle (Healey et al. 2013). Healey and his colleagues with LG²ES made three site visits to Fort Argyle as part of an erosion study. They documented the rate of soil loss at the site during 2012. LG²ES's recommendations for site management included Phase III Archaeological Excavation as one option. Their management study did not involve any new excavations and only two surface artifacts (both post-colonial era) were collected from the Ogeechee River shoreline.

The 2018/2019 investigations used successive lettering of excavation block units picking up where the 1996 excavations ended, to avoid confusion. In 1996 Elliott organized the previous test excavation data from the 1985 SAS project and the 1995-1996 LAMAR Institute project and grouped them into excavation blocks, which were assigned a letter designation (A through S). Excavation Blocks A through S at Fort Argyle were described previously in some detail in the LAMAR Institute's report by Elliott (1997). Only a brief overview of these previous excavations are presented here. Blocks D, F, H, L, M, O and R were excavated by Braley and his SAS team in 1985; Blocks A, B, G, I, K, P, Q and S were excavated by Elliott and his team in 1995-1996, and Blocks C, E, J, and N are composed of test units excavated by both Braley's and Elliott's excavation teams. Blocks A through S are discussed in more detail in Chapter 6. The 2018/2019 excavations begin with Block T and continue through Block AI.

4.0 METHODS

The present study of Fort Argyle combines historical research, archaeological survey and excavation, laboratory analysis and reporting to present an updated and increasingly detailed picture of eighteenth-century life at a Georgia ranger fort. The methods used for each of these phases of the project area are detailed below.

4.1 Historic Research Methods

The historical research on Fort Argyle and the Southern Rangers and Georgia Rangers that was conducted by the LAMAR Institute in 1996 was extensive, but it was by no means exhaustive. The number of relevant historical sources mushroomed rather than dwindled as the project progressed. Although research was conducted in many libraries, archives, and other research facilities in the southeastern U.S. many sources elsewhere in the United States and England were not examined. Whenever possible, published works from these sources were studied, but many were left unexamined since the undertaking would have been far beyond the intended scope of work and worthy of its own research project. Fortunately, many British records have been transcribed, published, or otherwise made available in the States.

Historical information was gathered from a variety of resources in Florida, Georgia, and South Carolina. Files pertaining to Fort Argyle at Fort Stewart were examined. Other sources consulted include the University of Florida Library, Gainesville, Florida; Georgia Historical Society, Savannah, Georgia; The Hargrett Rare Book and Manuscript Library, University of Georgia (UGA), Athens; Georgia Department of Archives and History, Atlanta and Morrow; Historic Preservation Division, Georgia Department of Natural Resources, Atlanta; the Laboratory of Archaeology, Department of Anthropology, University of Georgia, Athens; Bull Street Library, Genealogy Room, Savannah, Georgia and the Washington Memorial Library, Macon, Georgia. It should be noted that the holdings of the Georgia Historical Society were unavailable to researchers during our research period due to a two-year facility closure, so we were unable to physically examine any documents at that archive. Fortunately, previous research by the authors had examined some of that institution's relevant holdings. Limited information was gleaned from the Georgia Historical Society's online catalog.

Colonial records for South Carolina and Georgia, both published transcripts and original microfilmed documents, were examined. Georgia documents include 26 published volumes of Colonial Records of the State of Georgia edited by Candler (1904-1911); seven volumes edited by Coleman and Ready (Coleman 1982, 1985, 1986, 1990; Coleman and Ready 1977, 1979, 1985); and seven typescript volumes of colonial records on microfilm at the Georgia Department of Archives and History [henceforth, the Colonial Records of the State of Georgia are cited as CRG]. These records were gleaned from the British Public Records Office [henceforth, cited as BPRO] in England at the turn of the century. Other records were acquired from the BPRO in 1990 by Robert S. Davis, Jr. A three-volume guide to the BPRO and several other catalogues and guides to colonial and early state records also were examined (BPRO various dates; Griffin 1946; Jenkins and Hamrick 1950; Carson 1973).

Important collections that were consulted at UGA include: the BPRO Calendar of State Papers; Margaret Davis Cate (on microfilm, 1733-1961; Leslie 1976); Telemon Cuyler; and Keith Read collections. The Revolutionary Records of Georgia (three volumes), were consulted concerning events in Georgia during the American Revolution (Candler 1908). Documents of colonial and early state legislation were reviewed (Colonial Acts of Georgia various dates; Georgia 1836). Summaries of many early Georgia records were consulted (Adams 1983; Blake 1980; Bryant 1975; Clark 1981, 1983; Coulter 1947; Coulter and Saye 1949; Davis 1984, BPRO various dates; Adams 1983; Hemperley 1972, 1983; Utlely and Hemperley 1975).

Researchers made extensive use of transcripts of correspondence from 1732 to 1745 relating to the Trustees for Establishing the Colony of Georgia in America, held by the Hargrett Rare Book and Manuscript Library [Digital Library of Georgia 2019, henceforth cited as Phillips Collection (PC) 14200 through PC 14213]. This collection, previously cited as the Phillipps Collection, includes the Earl of Egmont papers. This collection was purchased by the University of Georgia in 1947 from the library of Sir Thomas Phillipps and these 14 volumes (of 20) were transcribed by historian E. Merton Coulter.

Other major primary sources of information pertinent to Fort Argyle are the detailed reports and additional records maintained by the Ebenezer colony of German-speaking Lutherans on the lower Savannah River in present-day Effingham County. The colonial Salzburgers, as they are collectively known today, were a tight-knit community of pietist Lutherans. Their pastors, primarily the Reverent Johann Martin Boltzius, maintained a daily record of life in the colony, which has since been translated, transcribed and published, largely due to the tireless efforts of German scholar George Fenwick Jones. These records include 18 volumes of annual detailed reports from 1733 through 1760 with some gaps (Jones 1968, 1969, 1984, 1985, 1986, 1988, 1989a-d, 1990, 1991, 1992a-b, 1993; Jones and Exley 1991; Jones and Hahn 1972; Jones and Savelle 1983; Jones and Wilson 1976, 1980, 1981).

South Carolina records were included in this search because during the first four years of the fort's existence, it received major financial support and manpower from South Carolina. South Carolina records that were examined include: Journals of the Upper and Lower House of Assembly; legislative acts; ledger books of the Treasury; early newspapers; records relating to the Indian trade; a number of published volumes; unpublished manuscripts on microfilm; and microfilm records in the Records of the State series (Salley 1947; Easterby 1951; Jenkins 1949; Jones 1969; McDowell 1992a-b).

General works on the colonial history of Georgia, South Carolina, and Florida also were examined during this study (Anderson 1929; Coleman 1960; 1976; 1977; Crane 1956; Mowat 1943; Scruggs 1975; Spaulding 1977; Stephens 1859; Wallace 1934, 1951; and Wright 1975).

Many eighteenth-century maps were examined that show the location of Fort Argyle. However, none of them depict the fort in any detail and were consequently of limited use (Anonymous ca. 1780; Avery 1780; Bowen 1748, 1752; Campbell 1780; DeBrahm 1756, 1757a-b, 1771; DeVorseley 1971; Wright 1763).

From 1732 to 1758 the Argyle vicinity was part of the "District of Ogeechee above Canoochee River". From 1758 to 1777 it was part of St. Philip's parish, and from 1777 to 1793 it was part of Effingham County. In 1793 Bryan County was created from portions of Chatham and Effingham County (Hemperley

1972: viii; Bryan County Historical Society 1986:5). Selected Chatham County deed records also were examined. Bryan County records that were studied include land plats, land warrants, deeds, and mortgages. Few early plats of the county were located. A fire at the Bryan County courthouse in 1866 destroyed records of the Ordinary Court, otherwise, early county records are relatively intact.

Genealogical and biographical information was consulted for individuals associated with Fort Argyle or the later plantation era. The two repositories providing most of this information were the Georgia Department of Archives and History and the South Carolina Historical Society. Published biographies and personal journals of important individuals, such as military ministers and high-ranking officers, also were consulted (Cashin 1989; Coxe 1798; Curnock 1916; Galloy 1989; Harris 1841; Hawes 1955, 1957, 1959; Hill 1989; McIntosh 1763-1838; Milledge 1755-1853; Milledge 1890; Spaulding 1984; Wesley 1909-1916; Wright 1867).

Contemporary accounts of colonial life and events in Georgia and adjacent areas, some available as reprints, were reviewed for information relevant to our study. These include writings by: an anonymous Georgia Ranger (Mereness 1916); Archibald Campbell (Campbell 1981); James Killpatrick (1978); Edward Kimber (1976); Lord Percival, Earl of Egmont (Historical Manuscripts Commission 1923; McPherson 1962); Benjamin Martyn (1842); William Stephens (Stephens 1958, 1966); and James Wright (1873). Microfilm copies of early newspapers and gazetteers at the University of Georgia libraries that were examined include: four from Georgia (*Gazette of the State of Georgia*, *Georgia Gazette*, *The Georgian*, and *Royal Georgia Gazette*); two from London (*Gentleman's Magazine* and *Annual Register*); and one from South Carolina (*South Carolina Gazette*).

Researchers reviewed and compiled information on archaeological and historical studies on other colonial forts in North America. These included works on colonial forts in:

- Alabama (Curren 1982; Waselkov 1989),
- Florida (Arana 1969; Arana and Manucy 1992; Carr 1974; Chatelain 1941; Deagan and MacMahon 1995; Faye 1942; Gray 1972; Manucy 1945, 1955, 1959, 1962; Manucy and Arana 1993),
- Georgia (Bailey 1957; Baker 1970; Caldwell n.d., 1941; Cook 1990; Deagan 1975; Elliott 1987; 1990, 1991a-b, 2003a-b, 2005a-b; 2006; Elliott and Elliott 1992, 1997, In press; Elliott et al. 1995; Fairbanks 1953; Franklin County Historical Society 1992; Georgia Department of Natural Resources n.d.; Goff various dates; Honerkamp 1980; Honerkamp et al. 1985; Ivers 1986; Kelso 1968, 1969, 1979; Midgette 1973; Robertson and Robertson 1986; Sheftall 1995; Shiner 1956, 1957, 1958a-b; Smith et al. 1988; Steed 1969; Steinen 1984; Walker 1974),
- Illinois (Babson 1968)
- Maine (Bradley 1981; Faulkner and Faulkner 1987),
- Maryland (Brown 1923),
- Michigan (Miller and Stone 1970; Williams and Shapiro 1982),
- New York (Brown 1931; Dunnigan 1985; Hanson and Hsu 1975; Huey 1990; Pell 1918),
- North Carolina (Porter 1985),
- Pennsylvania (Grimm 1970; Harrington 1978; Huston 1957; James and Stotz 1958; Sipe 1932),

- South Carolina (Bearss 1968; Caldwell 1974; Calmes 1968; Ferguson 1973; Ivers 1970, 1974; Joseph 1971; Joseph and Elliott 1993; Maness 1986; Polhemus 1971; South 1972, 1974; Trinkley et al. 1994; Williams 1995, 2009), and
- Virginia (Ansel 1984; Cook 1940; Mardis 1989; Powell 1988, 1989, 1990).

Various overviews of colonial forts in North America also were consulted (Grant 1965; Hammond 1915; Lewis 1979; Robinson 1977; Wade 1977).

Many primary and secondary sources on eighteenth-century military history were consulted for this study. Most of these references are summarized by Foote (1971), Harcourt (1902), Higham (1971), Houlding (1981; 1988), Jordan (1988), Lydon (1986), Myatt (1974), and Whitworth (1958). Particularly useful were recent studies by Cook (1990), Flynn (1991), Ivers (1974, 1984), Johnson (1992), Ready (1970), and Schwartz (1994). Numerous studies of British and American military regiments were reviewed, including Barnes (1967, 1969), Barthorp (1982), Carman (1951, 1982), Cole and Priestley (1936), Fortescue (1910-1935), Katcher (1981), Laver (1948), Luard (1852), Mollo (1975), and Sheppard (1959), but these provided no specific details on the Rangers in Georgia. Studies on King George's War (also known as the War of Jenkin's Ear) and the French and Indian War (also known as the War of Austrian Succession), were reviewed (Browning 1993; Hamilton 1962; Sonderegger 1964; Topping 1978). Researchers consulted several contemporary military manuals for information on fortifications, artillery and other military details (Bland 1743; LeBlond 1970 [1746]; Muller 1968 [1746]; Rudyerd 1970 [1793]; Vauban 1968 [1740]).

4.2 Archaeology Methods

4.2.1 Site Preparation

In the Spring of 2018 LG²ES archaeologist Rob Bowman supervised the mechanical clearing of brush from the area of the site intended for potential GPR and metal detector survey. All trees with diameters greater than three inches were left unmolested. Most of the leaf and root litter was raked to the interior side of the site.

4.2.2 Mapping

Archaeologists Daniel Elliott and Rita Elliott returned to the Fort Argyle site, joined by Rob Bowman on April 24, 2018 and began fieldwork by relocating the original site grid. Several grid nails from the original site grid at 9BN28 that was established by Braley in 1985 and continued by Elliott in 1996 were relocated. A U.S. government concrete benchmark established south of the site, which was mapped in 1985 and 1996, also was relocated. The original 1985 site grid had arbitrarily established a Grid North that was 17 degrees 45 minutes west of Magnetic North. This orientation was maintained by Elliott (1997) and later by the LG²ES team in 2018. Grid coordinates used for the 1985 and 1996 excavations referenced the South and West coordinates and grid numbers increased to the south and west.

A new site grid numbering system was established for the site by LG²ES archaeologists in April 2018. A Sokkia total station and TDS Recon data collector were used for mapping. The new grid was aligned

using the same north-south axis orientation as the earlier mapping work, but new grid numbers were used, which increased to the north and east rather than the opposite scheme used previously. The initial transit station used on April 24, 2018 was discovered when a grid nail from the previous archaeology work was relocated. The coordinates that were created for the site grid at this point were 8176.80E, 3005.7N. This datum corresponds to 551.19S, 499.76W on the previous site grid.

A more permanent datum was discovered soon after we began mapping the site. It was a vertical cement-filled PVC pipe even with the ground surface, that was located 10 m grid north of our first datum. Its location on the 2018 grid is 8176.80E 3015.7N. This PVC datum serves as the primary datum for mapping in this report. Its approximate UTM location is at Zone 17 468171.15E, 3543017.36N (WGS84). The site Grid-North remains oriented at 17 degrees 45 minutes west of Magnetic North. The magnetic declination at this location is approximately 6.95 degrees west of True North.

4.2.3 Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR)

The next phase of fieldwork at Fort Argyle involved Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) mapping. GPR data collection began on April 24 and was completed on April 26, 2018. The GPR work required no excavation. Field data collection was accomplished by Daniel Elliott with the able assistance of Rita Elliott and Rob Bowman.

GPR is an important remote sensing tool used by archaeologists (Conyers 2002, 2004; Conyers and Goodman 1997). The technology is particularly effective in mapping historic cemeteries as well as locating other feature types. The technology uses high frequency electromagnetic waves (microwaves) to acquire subsurface data. The device incorporates a transmitter antenna and closely spaced receiver antenna to detect changes in electromagnetic properties beneath them. The antennas are suspended just above the ground surface and are shielded to eliminate interference from sources other than directly beneath the device. The transmitting antenna emits a series of electromagnetic waves, which are distorted by differences in soil conductivity, dielectric permittivity, and magnetic permeability. The receiving antenna records the reflected waves for a specified length of time (in nanoseconds, or ns). The approximate depth of an object can be estimated with GPR by adjusting for electromagnetic propagation conditions.

The GPR sample block in this study area was composed of a series of parallel transects, or traverses, which yielded a two-dimensional cross-section or profile of the radar data. These samples are termed radargrams. This two-dimensional image is constructed from a sequence of thousands of individual radar traces. A succession of radar traces bouncing off a large buried object will produce a hyperbola, when viewed graphically in profile. Multiple large objects that are in proximity may produce multiple, overlapping hyperbolas, which are more difficult to interpret.

The GPR signals that are captured by the receiving antenna are recorded as an array of numerals, which can be converted to gray scale (or color) pixel values. The radargrams are essentially a vertical map of the radar reflection off objects and other soil anomalies. However, it is not an actual map of the objects. The radargram is produced in real time and is viewable on a computer monitor, mounted on the GPR cart. It is the post-processing of the data with various software that produces the most complete and reliable information.

GPR has been used successfully in Georgia's piedmont and coastal plain for archaeological and forensic anthropological applications to locate relatively shallow features, although the technique also can probe deeply into the ground. The machine is adjusted to probe to the depth of interest using different frequency range antennas. Higher frequency antennas are more useful at shallow depths, which is most often the case in archaeology. Also, the longer the receiving antenna is set to receive GPR signals the deeper the search. The effectiveness of GPR in various environments on the North American continent is widely variable and depends on solid conductivity, metallic content, and other pedo-chemical factors. Generally, Georgia's soils have moderately good properties for GPR application.

GPR signals cannot penetrate large metal objects and the signals are also significantly affected by the presence of saltwater. Although radar does not penetrate metal objects, it does generate a distinctive signal that is usually recognizable, particularly for larger metal objects, such as a cast iron cannon or manhole covers. The signal beneath these objects is often canceled out, which results in a pattern of horizontal lines on the radargram. For smaller objects, such as a scatter of nails, the signal may ricochet from the objects and produce a confusing signal. Rebar-reinforced concrete, as another example, generates an unmistakable radar pattern of rippled lines on the radargram.

Elliott has undertaken and published several GPR studies of eighteenth and nineteenth century sites in Georgia since 2002 (Elliott 2003, 2004, 2006, 2010a-d), in addition to dozens of other GPR projects. This equipment and survey methodology also proved successful on sites in the Georgia and South Carolina coastal plain. The equipment used for these studies (and the present study) consisted of a RAMAC/X3M Integrated Radar Control Unit, mounted on a wheeled-cart and linked to a RAMAC XV11 Monitor (Firmware, Version 3.2.36). A 500 megahertz (MHz) shielded antenna was used for the data gathering. MALÅ GeoScience's Ground Vision (Version 1.4.5) software was used to acquire and record the radar data (MALÅ GeoScience USA 2006). The radar information was displayed as a series of radargrams. Output from the survey was first viewed using GroundVision software. This provided immediate feedback about the suitability of GPR survey in the area and the effective operation of the equipment. The time window that was selected allowed data gathering to focus on the upper two meters of soil, which was the zone most likely to yield archaeological deposits. Additional filters were used to refine the radar information during post-processing, including adjustments to the gain. These alterations to the data are reversible and do not affect the original data that was collected.

Upon arrival at the site in April 2018, the RAMAC X3M Radar Unit was set up for the operation and calibrated. Areas of GPR survey were labeled GPR Blocks A, B, and C (lettering unassociated with excavation Block letters). GPR machinery and software settings and other pertinent logistical attributes of the survey of GPR Blocks A, B and C are listed in Table 4.1.

The initial GPR survey covered an irregular polygon that measured a maximum of 34 m East-West by 100 m North-South. Figure 4.1 shows the radargram plan for Blocks A, B and C. Individual radargrams are identified in this figure. Red and green bars denote locations where the GPR data collection stopped and resumed, which in most cases were starting point, ending point and tree or large bush obstacles encountered while en route. Archaeologists completed a GPR survey of a major portion of 9BN28 in 2018.

Surveyors collected data from 222 radargrams, which covered a total survey length of 4,835.7 m. The sample was collected in three sections (A, B and C), which were later grouped into one large block during data post-processing. The GPR grid north was aligned with the site's grid north. The southwestern corner of the GPR grid was designated (0,0) and was located at grid point 2961.32m North, 8154.75m East.

Table 4.1. Ground Penetrating Radar Settings for GPR Blocks A, B and C, 9BN28.

- Machine Settings, Blocks A, B and C
- Time Window: 64.6 ns
- Number of Stacks: 4
- Number of Samples: 512
- Sampling Frequency: 7,462.12 MHz
- Antenna: 500 MHz shielded
- Antenna Separation: 0.18 m
- Trigger: 0.04 m
- Radargram orientation: South to North (Grid North)
- Radargram progress: West to East
- Radargram Spacing: 50 cm
- Total Radargrams: 222
- Total Survey Length: 4,835.7 m
- Dimensions: 100 m N-S (maximum) by 34 m E-W (maximum)
- Southwest corner of survey grid: 2961.32 m North, 8154.75 m East.

Radar specialists returned to conduct supplemental GPR survey grids at Fort Argyle in late January 2019, which were designated GPR Blocks D, E, F, G and H. The additional GPR grids were placed in hopes of improving the GPR imaging within selected portions of the site, where the radar data from GPR Blocks A, B and C were ambiguous. All these additional GPR blocks are located within the larger polygon formed by GPR Blocks A, B and C. GPR equipment settings were the same as that used for GPR Blocks A-C, except where noted below.

GPR Block D was placed between Excavation Blocks Y and T. It was a long narrow sample that measured 13 m east-west by 1.25 m north-south. Its southwestern corner was at 2988.97N, 8163.87E. A total of 78 m of radargram data was collected from six radargrams in GPR Block D. These radargrams were collected from west to east, with each transect progressing from north to south. Data was collected using the 500 MHz antenna with 25 cm radargram transect spacing.

GPR Block E was placed between Excavation Blocks AA and W. It was a long narrow sample that measured 9 m north-south by 2 m east-west. Its southwestern corner was at 2997.17N, 8153.99E. A total of 81 m of radargram data was collected from nine radargrams in GPR Block E. Data was collected using the 500 MHz antenna with 25 cm radargram transect spacing and was collected from south to north with progress from west to east.

Figure 4.1 Radargram Plan of GPR Blocks A, B and C, 9BN28.

GPR Block F was placed south of Block W. It mapped the subsurface in an area within all three forts that was otherwise unexplored by any excavations. It covered an area from 6.5 to 11 m north-south by 5.25 m east-west. Its southwestern corner was at 2997.11N, 8159.17E. Data was collected using the 500 MHz antenna with 25 cm radargram transect spacing. A total of 188.6 m of radargram data was collected from 22 radargrams in GPR Block F that were collected from south to north, progressing from west to east.

GPR Block G covered the same area as GPR Block F but it was surveyed with the 800 MHz antenna, rather than the 500 MHz. Its southwestern corner was at 2997.11N, 8159.17E. A total of 184.1 m of radargram data was collected from 22 radargrams in GPR Block G that were collected from south to north, progressing from west to east.

GPR Block H was in the suspected cemetery vicinity surrounding Feature 177 (F177), north of Fort Argyle. GPR Block H mapped an area 12 m north-south by 5 m east-west. Its southwestern corner was at 3019.88N, 8174.50E. Data was collected using the 800 MHz antenna with 25 cm radargram transect spacing. A total of 237.1 m of radargram data was collected from 22 radargrams in GPR Block H, collected from south to north and progressing from west to east.

All GPR data from Fort Argyle were post-processed with GPR-Slice (Version 7.0). Dean Goodman's GPR-Slice program is recognized as the world leader in GPR imaging and it has proven quite effective in mapping historic sites (Goodman 2018). Mapping in 3D entailed merging the data from the series of radargrams for each block. Once this was accomplished, horizontal slices of the data were examined for important anomalies and patterns of anomalies, which were likely of cultural relevance. These data were displayed as aerial plan maps of the sample areas at varying depths below ground surface.

Horizontal views, or time-slices, display the radar information at a set time depth in nanoseconds (ns). Time-depth can be roughly equated to depth below ground. This equivalency relationship is an approximation that is calculated using a mathematical formula.

Selected GPR plan maps were incorporated into the GIS mapping project. Additional GPR data, including additional GPR plan maps and selected radargram profiles are included as Appendix E.

4.2.4 Metal Detector Survey (MD)

LG²ES archaeologists Dan Elliott and Rita Elliott, assisted by Rob Bowman, conducted a systematic metal detector survey of portions of 9BN28 in April 2018. Surveyors located and investigated all nonferrous signals, and larger/stronger ferrous signals along transects that were spaced 2 meters apart. These transects covered the same terrain as the southern portion of the GPR grid, extending from its southern edge and continuing north to 3030.26 m North along the site grid. Surveyors mapped and explored a total of 111 metallic "hits" within this area. These were investigated and mapped with the total station. Additional metal detecting was employed by Dan Elliott during 2019, which brought the total of explored metal finds to 158. Many hundreds of ferrous signals were not explored, nor were they mapped. The investigation of selected metal signals was accomplished with a trowel and shovel. Soils were only disturbed to a depth of 20 cm below ground surface in these tests. In several cases where large iron

objects or potential subsurface features were encountered, the surveyors made notes about these finds and left these metal finds in situ to be included in the test unit excavations.

4.2.5 Hand Excavation

A team of LG²ES archaeologists descended on 9BN28 in October and November 2018 for a six-week excavation project. The team hand excavated 270 m² (or approximately 92 m³) across the site. Excavation was generally done as individual 2 m by 1 m test units and groupings of these were designated as excavation Blocks. Excavation within each test unit began with the removal of the plow zone as a single stratum (Level 1). All contents of Level 1 were screened through ½ inch hardware cloth. This continued until all the test units within a block had been excavated to this level. Then the floor of each block was carefully troweled, photographed and mapped. Transit elevations for feature center points were taken. The floor of each partially excavated block was then covered with black plastic sheeting to protect the features from the elements. As noted above, the rainwater found its way into every block despite our attempts to divert it. Once most of the test units were excavated to the base of Level 1, feature excavation proceeded. Selected features were excavated. Abbreviated notation of "F" for "Feature" is used throughout this report (Example: Feature 36 is shown as F36). Most features exposed by the excavation blocks were not excavated. Additional excavation levels of selected units were excavated. Most of the test units in Blocks T through Z and AA through AI were completed in this manner.

Late 2018 and early 2019 was a particularly rainy spell at Fort Stewart. The bulk of LG²ES's fieldwork was conducted in December 2018 and January 2019. December saw greater-than-average rain fall at 4.2 inches contrasted with the average of 3.03" (The Weather Channel 2019). January's rainfall was below average; however, it still added another 1.21 inches to the overall water accumulation at the site. During the period of data recovery from November 26, 2018-February 5, 2019, a total of 5.58 inches of rain fell at Fort Stewart with the bulk of it in December and January (The Weather Channel 2019). We suspect that the actual amount of precipitation at Fort Argyle was several inches greater. While some of the rain occurred on the weekends, all of it contributed to submerge the block unit excavations throughout the entire project, as well as creating super-saturated soils around the excavations. Crew members pumped standing rainwater from the unit blocks numerous times throughout the project in order to complete our excavations (Figure 4.2 and Figure 4.3). The waterlogged clayey soils slowed work and made defining and following some features, particularly in the low-lying, rutted, northwestern part of the site more difficult. The inclement weather also led to a reduction in total feature sampling that the LG²ES crew was able to complete. Despite these odds our crew was able to exceed the required 78 cubic meters of excavation that was required under the government contract. We should also note that our original suggestion of mechanical stripping of the plow zone was nixed by Fort Stewart representatives. In hindsight their decision resulted in our acquiring a large sample of plowed (thoroughly mixed) cultural deposits from the site, which actually proved quite useful in understanding the site. The downside of Fort Stewart's decision was that our team was unable to completely uncover the architectural plan of the three forts or the buildings and other major features associated with the colonial fort. Consequently, we are left with many unanswered questions about the fort and its ancillary settlement.

Figure 4.2 Rain-Soaked Block Units at Fort Argyle, January 2019.

Figure 4.3 Sump Pump in Action at Fort Argyle's Rain-filled Excavation Blocks.

4.2.6 Laboratory Analysis

Artifacts from Fort Argyle were transported from the field to the laboratory in Jacksonville, Florida for processing by Kelsey Noak Myers and various permanent employees working part time in the lab. Myers prepared a database aligned with the curation needs at Fort Stewart. Functional classification groups below were assigned by Elliott and Elliott for research purposes in order to sort the data and use if for comparisons/contrasts to previous Ft. Argyle data and to other colonial fort sites.

Architecture Group

Reference resources for the identification of nails (Nelson 1968; Elliott 2010c; Frurip et al. 1983) and eighteenth-century building materials (Feister 1984) were consulted.

Clothing Group

Several sources were consulted for the identification of clothing artifacts (Noel Hume 1983; Stone 1974; South 1977). When relocated in the assemblage, buttons were analyzed by the Elliotts based on raw material, type of construction, and decoration. They were placed, when possible, in typologies developed by Stanley South (1977) and Olsen (1963) and dated accordingly. Numerous references on military uniforms were consulted (Barnes 1967, 1969; Barthorp 1982; Carman 1951, 1982; Haarmann 1971, 1977; Katcher 1981; Laver 1948; Luard 1852; McMaster 1911; Mollo 1975; Peterson 1968; Reid and Chappell 1993); buttons (Albert 1976; Epstein 1968; Luscomb 1967; Olsen 1963; South 1964; Stone 1974; Tice 1998; Troiani 2001), and buckles (Abbitt 1973; Booth 2019; Elliott and Elliott 1992; Noel Hume et al. 1973), Miller and Stone 1970).

Kitchen Group

Numerous references on glass bottles were consulted (Brown 1971; Fike 1987; Jones 1986; Jones and Sullivan 1985; Ketchum 1975, 1991; Lorain 1968; Newman 1970). Major sources on historic ceramics were consulted (Bartovics 1981; Baugher and Venables 1987; Bivens 1972; Charleston and Towner 1977; Cooper 1968; Curtis 1988; Draper 1984; Garrow 1982; Godden 1963; Goggin 1968; Ketchum 1991; Miller 1980, 1991; Miller and Hunter 1990; Miller and Stone 1970; Noël Hume 1977, 1983; Palmer 1976; Rauschenburg 1991a-b; Shaw 1829; South 1977, 1993; Towner 1978; Wheaton et al. 1983). When possible, the Elliotts re-categorized ceramics in the database by paste, glaze, and decoration to discover the type of each, date, and the country of origin.

Arms Group

Gun hardware and gunflints were analyzed with the aid of several references. These include works on Ammunition (Elliott and Seibert 2017; Sivilich 2016), guns and other weaponry (Bailey 1971, 2002, 2009; Blackmore 1961; Burke 1991; Caruana 1979; Gale 2010; Glendenning 1967; Hamilton 1976, 1980, 1982, 1987; Hanson 1966; Hanson and Hsu 1975; Kauffman 1960; LaCrosse 1989; Lenk 2007; Madaus 1981; Manucy 1985; Mullins 2008; Neumann 1967; Neumann and Kravic 1989; O'Meara 1965; Peterson 1956, 1969; Russell 2005) and gunflints (Ballin 2012; Durst 2009; Elliott 1992, 2018a; Hamilton and Emery 1988; Honerkamp and Harris 2005; Kenmotsu 1990; Kent 1983; Stevenson et al. 2007; Witthoft 1966). Gunflints relocated in the assemblage by the Elliotts and Norma Harris were weighed (to tenths of grams), measured in length, width (as determined by perpendicular to the gun barrel), and thickness (to

hundredths of mm) to identify the type of weapon with which they were used. Gunflints were also analyzed macroscopically by raw material type in an effort to determine the country of origin.

Tobacco Group

Tobacco pipes were analyzed by style and decoration in order to identify the pipe maker when possible. Pipe stem bore diameters were measured to discover the date of pipe manufacture, and ultimately, the date of specific areas and features within the site. The change in bore diameter of pipe stems through time allows archaeologists to measure the size of each pipe stem within the excavated sample and use a formula to calculate the date of occupation of the site or a specific area of the site (Binford 1962; Heighton and Deagan 1972). Detailed reference guides tobacco pipes were consulted, where available (Davey 1979-1994).

Personal Group

Coins were grouped by raw material type, date, and country of origin. They were identified and further researched by Dan Elliott. Modifications, alterations and use wear were noted for all examples (Bruce 1981; Seaby and Purvey 1980; Cuhaj and Michael 2010).

Activities Group

Various other reference guides were used for the identification of metal tools (Sloane 1964; Tunis 1965) and bottle glass tools (Elliott 1997; 2018b).

Portable X-Ray (pXRF) Fluorescence Analysis

Portable X-ray Fluorescence (pXRF) was conducted at the Elliott's laboratory in Rincon, Georgia by Daniel Elliott. This technology has been applied to many different media, including ceramics, stone and metal. The main targets of the pXRF elemental analysis at Fort Argyle were lead ammunition, although a sample of gun hardware, buttons, buckles, coins and other metal items was included in the study. The Fort Argyle lead ball pXRF data was collected with methods consistent with a previous study by Elliott, Seibert and others (Elliott and Seibert 2017; Seibert et al. 2018).

Raw data for the pXRF analysis was collected using a Bruker Tracer III-V portable laboratory. Each sample was run for 180 seconds without vacuum at 48 Kv and 29 microamps using the Black filter developed by the machine's inventor, Bruce Kaiser. S1PXRF Canada (Version 3.8.30) and XRayOps (Version 1.2.21) software was used in the initial data collection. A total of 540 pXRF samples was collected. Spectra ARTAX (Version 7.4.0.0) was used for secondary and comparative analysis. The resulting pXRF data is incorporated into the technical report as part of the artifact discussion. Supplemental data from the pXRF analysis, compiled by Daniel Elliott, is presented as Appendix B.

Ethnobotanical Analysis

Soil samples from selected excavated contexts at Fort Argyle were submitted to ethnobotanist Dr. Jack Rossen of Olde Seed Archaeological Consulting in Florida for ethnobotanical analysis. These results are summarized in the technical report and the full analysis report by Rossen is presented as Appendix C.

Palynological and Phytolith Analysis

Soil samples from selected excavated contexts at Fort Argyle were submitted to PaleoResearch Institute, Inc. in Golden, Colorado for palynological and phytolith analysis. The results of their analysis, authored by Cummings and Miller, are summarized in the report and the full analysis report by PaleoResearch Institute is presented as Appendix D. Extracts from their report are incorporated into the body of the technical report.

4.2.7 Reporting

This technical report details the background context, methods, results, and interpretations of the Phase III data recovery work at the Fort Argyle archaeological site (9BN28). The report is authored by Daniel Elliott, Rita Elliott and Norma Harris. Substantial contributions of labor were provided by LG²ES staff, including Dan Boylan (GIS mapping), Elizabeth Ziechang (Report figure preparation), Kelsey Myers (Laboratory direction and artifact and site database preparation), Rhianna Bennett (site database editing and report editing) and Wendy Puckett (Project management).

4.2.8 Curation

Artifacts, notes, maps and other records from the Phase III excavations at Fort Argyle are permanently curated at Fort Stewart Military Reservation in Bryan County, Georgia. LG²ES prepared the collections and digital data to Fort Stewart's specifications for cultural resources projects, which meets National Park Service standards for archaeological collections.

5.0 HISTORY OF FORT ARGYLE AND THE RANGERS

The control of Georgia was crucial to the survival of the British colony of South Carolina during the early eighteenth century. The thirteenth colony was to be a buffer between the English colonies and the French and Spanish colonies to the west and south. Georgia from the beginning, was a military colony. South Carolina had been concerned about these external threats since its birth in 1670, but it was not until the Tuscarora and Yamassee War at the beginning of the eighteenth century that the dangers of frontier defense were fully realized. In response to the Yamassee uprising, the South Carolina Rangers were organized in November 1716. They were a Provincial army consisting of one hundred men under two captains and two lieutenants. Troops were raised for a six-month tour of duty. These regular Rangers were paid £5 (Carolina currency, which was worth about £1.25 British Sterling) per month; the Lieutenants £10, (£2.5 Sterling) and the Captains £15 (£3.75 Sterling) (Ivers 1970).

In 1732, just prior to the formation of the new Georgia colony, South Carolina was protected by forts in the Charleston area, such as Fort Johnson, as well as Ranger garrisons at Fort Frederick, Port Royal; Fort Moore, Savana Town; Saltketchers Fort, Salkehatchee River; and Fort Prince George at Pallachacolas Old Town. Carolina established a garrison of 28 men at Port Royal in 1716 and Fort Moore was built on the Savannah River that same year. The following year South Carolina established Fort Congaree on the Congaree River near present-day Columbia, where 13 soldiers were stationed. However, by June 1718 the Company of Southern Rangers was disbanded. The South Carolina Rangers were revived in 1723, when South Carolina passed an Act, "for the Better Strengthening and Securing the Frontiers of this Province, by Continuing the Garrison at the Pallachicola, etc.". The South Carolina Rangers established a small fort garrisoned by 21 soldiers at the Apalachicolas Old Town on the Savannah River. Another South Carolina Act passed the following year, "for Regulating the Guard at Johnson's Fort, and for the keeping good orders in the Several Forts & Garrisons, etc." (Flynn 1991:36; McCusker 1989:1044- 1045; Crane 1956; Ivers 1970, 1974, 1984; BPRO, SCDAH 11:246-251, 344).

The first permanent English presence in coastal Georgia was Fort King George, which was established as a frontier point of defense by South Carolina in 1721 on the Altamaha River delta near present-day Darien, Georgia. As early as January 1703 the Commons House of Assembly of South Carolina discussed the intended location of a garrison to be built south and west of the Savannah River. This garrison was to be manned by no more than 50 men, who would be supplemented as the need arose by Yamassee gunmen (Salley 1934). On the heels of victory in the Tuscarora War and the Yamassee War, Colonel John Barnwell convinced the British authorities of the need for a military outpost south of Carolina that would serve as a first alert of an advancing Spanish attack, which was expected to occur at any time. Colonel Barnwell was provided a large contingent of soldiers, mostly sick and invalid, and it was no wonder to him that they died in droves after settling in Georgia. Recognizing the need for healthy skilled soldiers, Barnwell convinced the leaders of South Carolina to support the Fort King George company with seasoned hearty Rangers. Fort King George was manned by a sizable force until 1727, when troops were removed. That same year King George I died and was succeeded by his son George II. Fort King George was used in a limited capacity as late as 1734 by two South Carolina lookouts who were kept at this post to warn of Spanish attack.

5.1 1732

By 1730 South Carolina Governor Johnson wrote to King George II that the frontier defenses in South Carolina included forts Port Royal, Moore, Pallachacolas and Johnson, but of these only Port Royal had a garrison. It consisted of one independent company. The governor requested another company of 100 men be sent to the colony. On January 18, 1732, a committee was formed in the South Carolina Upper House of Assembly composed of Colonel Broughton, Arthur Middleton, Colonel Bull, and Colonel Fenwick, at the request of Governor Robert Johnson "for the encouraging [sic] & promoting the welfare" of Georgia. On the following day, the committee gave orders to Captain McPherson with 15 of his Rangers, "to cover and protect Mr. Oglethorpe" and to face "any insult that may be offered them- by the Indians and that they continue and abide there till the New Settlers have Enforced themselves and for such further time as His Excellency may think it necessary" (BPRO, SCDAAH 15:306; Jenkins 1949: Reel 2, 347-350). The Rangers were, "horsemen, and always kept in pay to discover the motions of the Indians" (White 1854:321, 323, 324).

Georgia originated as a Trustee colony. General James Oglethorpe and a group of 21 Georgia Trustees obtained a charter in 1732 from King George II, and the thirteenth and final British colony in America was founded in February 1733. The major towns established during the first three years of Georgia's founding were Savannah and New Ebenezer on the Savannah River; Darien near the mouth of the Altamaha River; and Frederica on the western side of St Simons Island. During the Trustee period (1733 to 1751) the northern boundary of the colony extended to the upper limits of tidal flow between the Savannah and Altamaha rivers.

Prior to 1737 military jurisdiction for the Georgia colony was maintained by South Carolina, who established a series of defensive outposts manned by Carolina Rangers (also known as Southern Rangers) to guard the colony against Spanish and Indian attack. Fort Argyle on the Ogeechee River was the first of these Ranger outposts in Georgia. Although James Oglethorpe and the Trustees oversaw the colony during the years from 1733 to 1738, the major military decisions and primary funding came from South Carolina. This fact greatly affected the politics and daily life at Fort Argyle. In 1732 Oglethorpe had been granted the authority to raise a Militia in Georgia and he fully exerted this authority by creating several English Ranger, Highland Ranger, and regular foot soldier units. These were a Provincial Army rather than part of the official British Army, but in the absence of regular British troops they were the only defense that was available (McPherson 1962:9).

5.2 1733

In January 1733, South Carolina Governor Johnson wrote to Thomas Pelham, Duke of Newcastle, who was Great Britain's Defense Minister, that "20 of our Rangers" were ordered to cover the settlers of Georgia from "any insults that may be offered them by stragling Indians or others" (BPRO, 1953, V. 40:29; Browning 1975). He sent Captain James McPherson to perform this task. Oglethorpe negotiated a treaty with the Creek Nation, which was signed in Savannah on May 21, 1733, giving England the right to settle on the tidal sections of the Ogeechee River (Spaulding 1984:79). This marked the formal beginning of a trust between Oglethorpe and the Creek Nation that was to last well beyond Oglethorpe's tenure and the

Trusteeship period of Georgia history. Captain McPherson reported to the Governor that month that, "it would be necessary to continue men there for sometime" (Jenkins 1949: Reel 2,452).

Thomas Lediard wrote this brief description of the first Fort Argyle on June 25,

On the twelfth of June, 1733 Mr. Oglethorpe went up to the Horse Quarter, which lies up the River. Six miles above Savannah, from whence he took with him Captain Mackpherson, with a detachment of his Rangers; and, after a march of forty miles to the westward, into the country, he chose a Post, which commands the Passages, by which the Indians used to Invade Carolina, in the late Wars. Upon this situation which is a very happy one, being an eminence which commands all the country round, with a great and deep river, at the foot of it. Captain Mackpherson has undertaken, pursuant to Mr. Oglethorpe's plan, to erect a fortification, to be called Fort Argyle, where he and his Rangers, are to be quartered, and ten families are to remove thither, from Savanna, to cultivate lands, which are to be granted them in that neighborhood (Lediard 1733; *The Derby Mercury* 1733:3).

A Charleston, South Carolina newspaper published a similar account the founding of Fort Argyle by the Carolina Rangers (*South Carolina Gazette*, July 7, 1733:3-4).

Fort Argyle was intended to defend the Carolina and Georgia colonies from Spanish attack, as Georgia's Secretary Benjamin Martyn noted: "A fort was likewise built at the narrow passages of an inland river (called Ogeechee) in order to protect the settlement from any inland invasion from Augustine". In June, Oglethorpe and the Rangers explored the frontier to find a suitable site for the fort. The original construction site, which was located at the crossing of a major foot path on the eastern bank of the Ogeechee River, was abandoned before the fort was completed because logging debris had choked the river and made it impassable for boat traffic at that point. The first site, later known as First Fort, was approximately 8 km upstream from the second fort site.

General Oglethorpe wrote to the Georgia Trustees on August 12, stating, "I have agreed with Mr. Macpherson Captain of the Rangers to build a Fort upon Hogatchee River, wch. I have named Argyll. It is already begun and in good forwardness and I have Supplied him from hence with Provision Cannon and Ammunition" (PC 14200:107).

Oglethorpe wrote to the Trustees on September 17,

In a former I gave You an Accot. of my having agreed with Capt. Mackpherson for him to build Fort Argyll for £200 Currency. The Trees that fell into the River and were carried down by great Floods stop'd the Passage below the Port in such a manner, as to prevent any possibility of getting up there by Water without immense Labour in cutting away the Trees. The Fort being about half finished when he represented this, I ordered him to begin another 10 miles lower and allowed him £50 Currency for the Work already done. He has finished the New Fort, the Guns are mounted, the Houses built and six Familys Settled there besides the Garrison. Boats of fifteen Ton burthen have been there (PC 14200:114).

Oglethorpe elaborated in his September 17 letter, "We have taken a Man that had Stole an Horse in Virginia; he was tried before the Court, pleaded guilty was condemned and sentenced to hard Labour during the Space of three Years at Argyll Fort on Ogeeche River, was delivered to Capt. Mackpherson and sent away instantly. The Horse is ordered to be sent to the Owner in Virginia" (PC 14200:113-114). It is noteworthy that the sentence for a horse thief, which was usually a capital crime, was service as a ranger in Fort Argyle. Possibly this was perceived by some as a fate worse than death!

Oglethorpe wrote from Savannah to the Trustees in December, "Finding our People increase fast I enlarged our Quarters by new Settlements and covered this place to the Southward by building Fort Argyle at about 20 miles distance" (PC 14200:125). Sometime between September and December of 1733 the second Fort Argyle was, "finished, the guns mounted, the houses built. and six families and the garrison settled there". Oglethorpe named the fort in honor of James Campbell, Duke of Argyle (Martyn 1842:286; Temple and Coleman 1961:42-43).

Fortifications evolved significantly during the eighteenth century. The brilliant French military engineer Sebastien Le Prestre marquis de Vauban (or as he was more commonly referred, Vauban), who died in 1707, published a book on fortifications that was used by military strategists and engineers for many decades to follow (Figure 5.1). Vauban's writings were translated into English and published as early as 1691, so Oglethorpe was almost certainly familiar with his writings and his methods and theories of fort construction when he arrived in Georgia (Swall 1691; Vauban 1726). Oglethorpe supervised the layout and design of many colonial forts in Georgia. What is unclear is whether those in charge of Fort Argyle, particularly captains James McPherson and John Milledge, were schooled in Vaubanian theory. If they were, then something appears to have been lost in the translation, as only a few vestiges of Vauban's designs are evident at Fort Argyle. Figure 5.2 shows the various parts of a fortification. Notable features include the bastion, banquette, counter scarp, covered way, curtain, ditch or moat, scarp, glacis, parade, parapet, rampart and terre plein. Fort Argyle likely possessed many, if not all of these features. Most of the features shown in this illustration are located above ground, and those features, if they were ever present at Fort Argyle, have been erased by decades of agricultural land use and erosion.

Figure 5.1 A Typical Vauban-designed Fortification Plan (Vauban 1726: Figure 35).

Figure 5.2 The Parts of a Fort (James and Stotz 1958).

A group of Moravians who had immigrated to Georgia was promised a land grant near the first, incomplete Fort Argyle site. The land selected for the Moravians included a half mile of Ogeechee River

frontage and extended two miles back into the forest. The group included the Moravians Spangenberg, Toltschig, Riedel, Seifert, Rose, Michael Haberland and Mr. Johnson, the Trustee's surveyor. They made the trip by boat to Fort Argyle from Savannah to inspect the 500 acres selected for the Moravians. After arriving at the completed Fort Argyle [Site 9BN28] and spending the night of August 28, 1733, two of their party (Spangenberg and Johnson), "accompanied by the Lieutenant from Fort Argyle and several of his rangers", rode out to inspect the land. After viewing the land, they returned to Fort Argyle. There was a failed attempt to visit an Indian settlement by the Moravians so they returned to their tract, which they surveyed. Pleased with their land, the Moravians returned to Fort Argyle and then departed by boat for Savannah. Despite this approval the Moravians never settled on the property, as their pacifist beliefs were not compatible with the hostilities of the Georgia frontier and living near a military fort (Fries 1967:72-76).

5.3 1734

In February 1734, the Georgia Trustees submitted to King George II a proposed "Act for maintaining the Peace with the Indians in the Province of Georgia", which included a provision that, "every Trader going to the Creeks to Trade shall be Obligated to pass both going and coming by the first Fort Argyll or by such other Fort or Forts as shall from time to time be appointed". Had Savannah become the primary export point for the Georgia Indian trade, this provision would have insured Fort Argyle's importance. However, Charleston remained the primary southern port for the deerskin trade throughout the colonial period. South Carolina siphoned off most of the merchandising and shipping of deerskins and furs from Georgia's traders, and the bulk of these animal hides exited the colony through Augusta instead of Savannah (CRG 1:40).

The first description of Fort Argyle was penned early in 1734. An anonymous author wrote from Savannah and described General Oglethorpe's visit shortly before February 8 to Fort Argyle. During Oglethorpe's exploration up the Ogeechee River in a row boat he and his fellow travelers, "lay in a house and upon beds, for the first time since they left Thunderbolt" and "The fortifications there, by the unwearied diligence of Captain McPherson, were finished, and very defensible; being well flanked, and having several pieces of Cannon mounted" (Harris 1841:80-81; Wright 1867:74-75; *South Carolina Gazette*, February 23, 1734:1; *The Pennsylvania Gazette*, April 4, 1734).

In March, only about six months after the completion of Fort Argyle, South Carolina Governor Johnson ordered Captain McPherson and his Rangers to Fort Prince George in South Carolina instead of Fort Argyle as initially had been planned (Public Records Office, Colonial Office Papers, 28 Mar 1734, 5/435:23, cited in Ivers 1974:27-29). McPherson's mounted troop of 30 rangers were divided into three groups of 10 each. McPherson commanded 10 rangers at Fort Argyle; Lieutenant William Elbert commanded another 10 at the first Fort Argyle site; and the other 10 men garrisoned Fort Prince George, which was located at Palachacolas Old Town on the Savannah River in South Carolina (Temple and Coleman 1961:42-43). The number of troops at the newly built Fort Argyle during this period ranged between 10 and 20.

By March the government of South Carolina had fallen far behind in paying Captain McPherson's Southern Rangers for their service. Governor Johnson wrote to England that they "lye under great Discouragement"

by "being kept so long out of their Pay". The Governor ordered Captain Palmiter of Fort Prince George [Palachocolas] discharged and directed that the "guns and stores" at Fort Prince George, "be delivered to the Honr. James Oglethorpe Esq. Order for the use of that Fort". The next month Speaker of the House Jenys wrote to Johnson informing him that the General Assembly had, "settled the pay of the captain of the Rangers at Fort Prince George at Two hundred and twenty pounds/ann. and that of the men at nine pounds/month" and that, "the place of their Rendezvous be at Fort Prince George, and that they Range up the Savannah River". That month the South Carolina Council distributed copies of the Act "for giving further Encouragement to the Soldiers serving in the Several Garrisons and Scouts in this Province to Captain McPherson, Captain Johnson & Captain McIntosh for their better Information". Meanwhile, the southern threat to South Carolina increased and Governor Johnson estimated the Spanish forces at St Augustine to be 400 soldiers (Jenkins 1949: Reel 2, S93-594. 609, 704; Martyn 1842:317).

The South Carolina Commons Lower House of Assembly allocated £3,873 (Carolina currency) for Captain McPherson and his Rangers in March 1734, which included:

To the Captain of the Rangers	£288
To the Serjeant	£168
To the Men being 20 at 12 [per] Month	£2880
Addition for 20 Men at Georgia	£480
Premium on Garrison Orders	£54 4 [shillings]

(Salley 1947:115-116).

On April 10. 1734, the South Carolina Upper House issued the following order, "Oder'd That the Secretary of this Province or his Deputy do give attested copys of the act for giving further Encouragement to the Soldiers serving in the several Garrisons and scouts in this Province to Capt. McPherson. Capt. Johnson & Captain McIntosh for their better Information" (Easterby 1951:704).

Yet by October, the Earl of Egmont wrote in his journal that South Carolina had "stopt payment of the 8090£ currency formerly granted by their Assembly to us on pretence we have not built a Fort, for which they Say they gave it up" (McPherson 1962:113). South Carolina's actions reflect the jealousy that existed between the two colonies and by stopping payment the leaders hoped to discourage Georgia from continuing its Indian trade.

Population estimates for other settlements in Georgia recorded by Lord Perceival, Earl of Egmont, during that year are provided below. Elsewhere the Earl estimated the size of the settlement at Ogekie [Ogeechee] at 22 persons, as of the spring of 1734. The Earl of Egmont recorded in his diary that Oglethorpe informed the Trustees by letter in September that "he had built a fort, called Arguile fort, furnished it with cannon and a garrison and placed six families in it". The actual number of people sent to Fort Argyle was not recorded; however, historical documents mention some individuals on occasion (Historical Manuscripts Commission 1923, v. 2:69, 112).

Samuel Eveleigh was a powerful advocate of the Georgia Indian trade and staunch supporter of Georgia. He advised Oglethorpe in November 1735 to build a fort on the Altamaha River on the south bank rather

than the north (which was where Fort King George was formerly located), in order to keep the Spanish from building a fort on the south side. Oglethorpe apparently valued Eveleigh's advice, since the fort that the Highlanders built at Darien two years later was located on the south bank of the river (PC 14200:125-128).

In a December 14 letter to Oglethorpe, Thomas Christie advised,

I must acquaint you that the People at Purisburgh, Thunderbolt, and Fort Argyle have been all Indian Traders since you have been gone, We have smartly forbid our People and Settlements as soon as we heard it, and indeed tho' they seem to like the Trade much, they readily Submitted to our Orders; I dont Question but the Trustees will Endeavour to Regulate and Secure that Trade to themselves as soon as possible (PC 14200:321).

5.4 1735

South Carolina passed an Act giving £3,873.4 (Carolina currency) in support of Fort Argyle for the period from March 25, 1734 to March 25, 1735. Other than providing financial support, the South Carolina government had little interaction with the Rangers in Georgia in 1735. Governor Johnson and other South Carolina politicians turned their attention to domestic affairs and seemed unconcerned with Georgia's defenses (Jenkins 1949:1734-1743 Acts, Reel 2b). Cost estimates for support of the Rangers in Georgia, presented to the Commons House of Assembly in South Carolina on April 18 totaled £3873 4 shillings, which included:

To the Captain of the Rangers	£288
To the Serjeant	£168
To the Men being 20 at 12 [per] Month	£2880
Addition for 20 Men at Georgia	£480
Premium on Garrison Orders	£54 4 [shillings]

(Salley 1947:167).

South Carolina's Royal Governor Robert Johnson died on May 5, 1735. Johnson had welcomed Oglethorpe and the Georgia colonists when they arrived in 1733. Johnson was succeeded in office by Lieutenant Governor Thomas Broughton.

In July 1735, the Georgia Trustees petitioned the Board of Trade for military supplies for Georgia's defense. Their request included:

Twenty four pieces of Cannon from Six pounds to eighteen pounds with Iron'd Carriages and Shott and Iron for twenty four Spare Carriages,
Four small long Field pieces with Carriages,
Eight Cohorns and Granadoes
Five hundred Small Arms and Shott Cartouch Boxes and Moulds and Flints
Two Flaggs and Two Pendants
Fifty Barrells of Powder

Spunges Ladles Rammers Crows & c.

to be delivered to your Petitioners as soon as Possible (CRG 1:225).

An unknown visitor to the colony wrote of his journey through South Carolina bound for Purysburg. During the journey he met James McPherson near a large savannah, called Godfrey's. This description provides one with a sense of the hazards of travel during that period, "I was got about half over, I overtook one Captain Macpherson, Captain of the Fort of Argyle, on the Ogechee river, in the colony of Georgia, being near to the Spanish settlement called Augustine. He was driving one hundred and fifty cattle to Savannah, Georgia by Mr. Oglethorpe's order, on the trustees' account." The anonymous author continued,

I rode in company with him for about six miles, when he was so kind as to offer me a servant to show me the way to a plantation of his about sixteen miles from thence, which he had newly settled, and where his wife then was. About six at night I crossed the salt-catchers, being the head of the Cambake river, in a small canoe, swimming our horses on one side of it. As soon as we crossed the river we came to a small savannah, where we had once a terrible battle with the Indians, and lost a great many of our men. There are several large pine trees now to be seen, full of bullets. About half a mile from thence I came to an old fort which has been demolished on account of setting the fort on Ogechee river, in the colony aforesaid, and from thence to Captain Macpherson's plantation, where I was handsomely received by his wife, considering it one of the out settlements (Anonymous 1842b).

Luring settlers to the Ogechee River area was extremely difficult in the first few years of Georgia's establishment because of the dangers that were present on the frontier. John Burnside, who came to Georgia with the intent of teaching school, wrote to the Trustees on January 16, stating, "I am Settled at Fort Argyle near 100 Miles from Town by Water at which Place I have Built a House and Clear'd Near two Acres of Land" (PC 14200:371). Patrick Tailfer, Patrick Houstoun and others wrote to the Trustees on March 15 complaining, "We had almost forgot to mention one thing which is likewise a great incumbrance upon those who are settled at Okecchy that the indians in passing backwards and forwards commonly demand provisions and frequently Stay there Eight or ten Days and being always allowed, them at Thunderbolt and Fort Argyle, they imagine it to be the same here and would take it very ill if they were refused" (PC 14200:478). Thomas Causton wrote to the Trustees in April, "The People at Fort Argyle are in good health Edgcomb is made Lieutenant (by the Captn.) Teesdale Finley and Jones are enter'd into the Scout Service Calvert and Roth are the only people there that minds Planting".

The Reverend John Martin Boltzius of New Ebenezer wrote in his diary that April: "Toward evening, a special post rode through our place in a great hurry in order to call the captain of Fort Ogechee from his estate in Carolina, for news had been received that the Spanish Indians are again making hostile moves against this colony". In July, Noble Jones wrote: "We have an Account that some Yam [Yamassee] Indians, supposed to be the same that killed Tomo Chaci's people, are now Sculking about Fort Argyle on that River" (PC 253-14200(2):262. 293; 14201:60; Jones 1969:70). Causton wrote in June of a feared Spanish Indian attack, which later proved to be a false alarm,

I wrote again to the Several Settlements to be upon their Guard and sent the Constables to warn them of the Danger and I hope the People will Continue their Watchfullness. At Ebenezer 6 men keep Guard every Night with a Day Centinall. At Hampstead and Highgate 1 Centinell night and Day, at Skidoway 1 Centineel Neight and Day. I also advised with Captain Machpherson, so soon as I received Mr. Mackays Letter and I don't doubt but proper Care is taken on that River by him and the Scotch Settlement [Sterling's Fort] (PC 14201:25).

William Elbert served as a lieutenant in Captain McPherson's Southern Rangers at Fort Argyle. Elbert resigned and was replaced in the Spring of 1735 by Arthur Ogle Edgecombe, a former Tythingman in Savannah, but by the fall of 1736, Edgecomb had also left Georgia (CRG 1:404; 2:43-44; 23:282; Ivers 1974:74). In a letter written by Elbert to the Georgia Trustees on April 20, 1742, he recounted his time in Georgia,

I Left my Native Cuntrey, England Veary young staid sometime in Carolina: from thence came to Georgia, in ye: yere 32 [year 1732] About two months after ye: first settlers, some small time after married into one of ye: first forty fameleys Obtain,d a Lott of Esqr: Oglethorpe, and Bult [built] a house thereon Conformable to ye: Honours Charter, I servd: your Honours as Lieutenant at Fort: Argyle under Captin: Jas: Mc:pherson, Better then two yeres, Commishon,d by ye: Esqr: After which servd: one yere as mesinjer to Chorls: Town [Charlestown] in Carolina

But as it is not posable to please all men kind, so it was wt: Mr: Causton: on Acc': of his neace: [niece] which i suppose Gentlemen you have heard of. Accuseing me of bringing Letters Contrary to his or hir Entrust: in which i could not Allow my guilty of: as it was not posable [possible] for me to know what Letters I Becived [received] in Carolina; by which mens he became my intire enemy and so has remain,d seeking all Ocations to Ruein Me and mine.

About fore [four] or five years agoe: I Reciv,d an Order on yr: Honours for 400 pounds Curreney of Carolina, which is £53: 6": 8d: Sterlg: which has Remain,d on paid tell know: at ye: time I Received ye: said Order. I paid it away in Carolina: which has been before your Honours in England: and sent Back: which I haveing had some small Accots: sencs in yr: Honours stores here: not Exceeding Ten pounds sterlg : Mtr Causton has charged me wth haveing fraudently reciv,d ye: said Order of 400 pounds Carolina Curreney: of yr: Honours: you are senceable ye: Commishonors Certified thirty two pounds some odd mon,y sterlg : to be paid by yr: Honours in England: which they say i have reciv,d But god and yr Honours knows I never apply'd home to you for it Thaire is an apperiant mistake of an Over charge in ye: store Books of fore pounds fore [four] shillings sterlg: which was Charg,d twice Over... (CRG 23:281-285).

Elbert statement, "400 pounds Curreney of Carolina, which is £53: 6": 8d: Sterlg:" provides us with a currency equivalence rate for comparing Carolina pounds to British Sterling pounds in the late 1730s-early 1740s (CRG 23:281-285). This is a very important clue in understanding the various finances of Colonial Georgia.

William Elbert's son, Samuel Elbert, was born in Savannah in 1740. His mother was Sarah Greenfield. Samuel Elbert would later become a general in the Georgia Continentals during the American Revolution and later a governor of Georgia. However, Samuel Elbert was never at Fort Argyle since his father's service at the fort ended before Samuel's birth (Ouzts 2017:25).

Thomas Causton wrote to the Trustees on June 20 stating, "Another Advice from Tomo Chachi brought me word (with too much truth, that near the River Alatomaha beyond Fort Argylle Some of his People had been Sett upon in their Camp and Seven were killed this was at first reported to be the Eucheas, But the Euche Indian whom they said was among them, was at that time at home in the Town, and they are Convinct that it was the Yamassees having been traced that way" (PC 14201:37). Noble Jones wrote on July 6, to Oglethorpe stating, "We have an Account that some Yamasee Indians, Supposed to be the same that killed Tomo Chachi's People, are now Sculking about Fort Argyle on that River, I therefore Set out to morrow with Mr. Spangenberg to run out Count Zinzendorff's Land, he having cleared above 3 Acres of his own Garden Lot; At the same time to See if we can come up with those Strollers who come to Spy and disturb our Peace, as Ranger I always think it my particular Duty to be the first out on those Occasions" (PC 14201:89-90).

An original 1735 muster roll of the South Carolina Rangers at Fort Argyle was sold at auction in New York in 1879. The auction catalog stated: "[Lot] 485 Muster-Roll. Commander James Mackpherson of the Southern Rangers at Fort Argyle, S.C., 1735. Very good. Very Rare. [No. of Pieces] 1" (Bechtel 1879:20). A 1735 muster and pay roll of William Richards was sold at auction in New York in 1887. The auction catalog stated: "[Lot] 440--- 1735, Sept. 29. Muster and pay roll of Wm. Richards, signed by James Mackpherson, Commander of the Southern Rangers, at Fort Argyle. V. good and rare" (Frossard 1887:20). The 1908 auction catalogue for the sale of the Late H.A. Chambers of Philadelphia included Lot 399, which was advertised as, "1735 South Carolina. Southern Rangers. Muster Roll of the 29 DAY of September ANNO 1735. Order for 84 £ for serving with the colors. Signed James Machperson COMMANDE of The Southern Rangers at fort Argyle. Creased but fine, 6 ¼ x 4 ½ inches" (Chapman 1908:25). Quite possibly this is the same document that appears for a fourth time in a 1998 auction in New York and this time, the auction catalog included a photograph of the item, which is reproduced in Figure 5.3 and transcribed below:

South Carolina. Southern Rangers.

Muster-Roll of the 29th Day of September Anno 1735

It is hereby certified, that Wm. Richards has serv'd at Fort Argyle from the 25 Day of March to the 29th Instant. For which Service there is due to the said William Richards on Order the Sum of Eighty four Pounds current Money of this Province, and also a Premium of Two and a half per Centum thereon, payable out of the Money raised, (or to be raised) for discharging of the publick Debts for the said Time. And this Certificate shall be taken in Payment of Tax, for the full Value above expressed, pursuant to Law.

Given under my hand the 29th Day of September 1735

Number in the Margin of the Muster-Roll (2_)

James Mackpherson Commander of the Southern rangers at Fort Argyle
(Stacks 1998:66).

Figure 5.3 William Richards 1735 Muster Receipt.

5.5 1736

The South Carolina establishment was intent on protecting its lucrative and fairly monopolistic regional Indian trade and upon seeing the success of Georgia on that front South Carolina made several moves to thwart its rival. Georgia, on the other hand, was making significant strides to cultivate the trade. After securing a treaty with the Creeks in 1733, Colonel Oglethorpe made plans in early 1736 to establish a fort deep in the Upper Creek country. This fort, had it reached its full potential, would have usurped the Indian trade from the French at Fort Toulouse on the Coosa River in Alabama. The presence of a Georgia fort in the Upper Creek country also would have given Georgia the upper hand over South Carolina in the Indian trade. Oglethorpe had earlier dispatched Patrick McKay and his Rangers to establish ties to construct such a fort, but on February 6, McKay's Ranger troop was dismissed by the Georgia Trustees after complaints were received from the South Carolina government about McKay's trading efforts with the Upper Creek. February was a busy month, in addition to those events, military fortifications were under construction on St. Simons Island and were nearing completion at Darien (Duncan n.d. 405).

Georgia continued to grow during that spring. The Creek chief Dogg King sent his assurances to Georgia from Ogeechee that his 60 people were prepared to come to Georgia's aid if the Spanish invaded (CRG 35:93). Oglethorpe briefly reported the progress that had been made in establishing communication links between the various settlements in Georgia, "Mr. M'pherson with the Rangers having marched over land from Savannah arrived at the Darien before I left that place so that there is a Communication opened for Horsemen between the two Towns, [and that a Surveyor] sent by me with a detachment of the Trustees men has run the Traverse Line from Savannah by Fort Argyle to the Darien from whence to this place is only 16 miles by water" (Oglethorpe 1873:14-15, 28-29).

By April, Fort Frederica on St. Simons Island was nearly finished, "consisting of 4 bastions and a ditch with Some bulwarks fraized round with Cedar Posts; the Works faced with Greensod, which grew very well", and in June the town of Augusta was laid out (McPherson 1962:147, 168). Oglethorpe, feeling that he was being given mixed messages from the Trustees regarding their commitment to the defense of the colony, expressed his frustration regarding the dissolution of McKay's troop. "Having raised fifty (50) Rangers and sent Captain McPherson with a part of his Rangers overland to support the Highlanders on the Altamaha river, it seems that the purpose of disbanding Captain Patrick Mackay's troop of Horsemen was to retire him, as this company of fifty Rangers is raised four days after the said reduction" (Duncan n.d. 405). Apparently these 50 Rangers were funded by the Georgia Trustees rather than the South Carolina government, although South Carolina retained authority over military matters in Georgia at that time. In March, Oglethorpe met with one of the Scottish Highlanders, Hugh Mackay, Sr., and a detachment of "new raised Rangers under his command". McKay was formerly a Lieutenant in Patrick McKay's Ranger troop (Oglethorpe 1873:19-20).

Samuel Eveleigh wrote to the Trustees in March regarding the prospects of raising a new company of Rangers, including a Captain and 20 men who would patrol between Savannah and Combahee. The plan included the erection of a fort on White Point mounted with 30 guns (CRG 35:95). However, the sentiment for strengthening the southern defenses among some Carolinians was quite the reverse as Colonel Prioleau and Captain Beale, members of the Common House, wrote to the Governor on March 18, 1736 stating,

On the prospect of Peace in Europe and the Measure taken by the British Parliment to strengthen the Sowestern Frontier of the English Possessions in North America, and the Independant Company being lately removed out of this Province to cover that of Georgia, we are therefore of Opinion that it is no longer necessary to continue at the Expense of this Province the Rangers and Capl Mackpherson the Scout Boat nor the Southern lookout. After ye 25 day of March Instant or the 25th of June next at farthest (Jenkins 1949, Easterby 1951:201-202).

The action of Prioleau and Beale met a quick response from General Oglethorpe, who wrote the South Carolina Governor on April 8, and expressed his desires that their support of the rangers and scout boats be continued. Oglethorpe's wishes were granted, at least for four months and a resolution was passed in the Upper House to continue funding the rangers until September 29, 1736. South Carolina also passed an Act providing £3,702 (Carolina currency) in support of the Fort Argyle Rangers for the period from

March 25, 1735 to March 25, 1736 (Easterby 1951:221-222, 273; Jenkins 1949:1734-1743 Acts, Reel 2b).

The Earl of Egmont wrote in his diary in May 1736 the receipt of letters from Oglethorpe, which included a discussion of the people of Ebenezer and matters relating to the defense of Georgia. His diary entry noted, "Mr. Oglethorp had not with him now above 200 effective men, but the Scots at Fort Argyle were ready to assist" (Historical Manuscript Commission 1923: volume 2: 274). This passing reference to "the Scots" may reflect the dominant ethnic makeup of the South Carolina Ranger troop at Fort Argyle in 1736.

Not all reports from the Georgia coast were favorable. A November report to the Trustees by Thomas Causton noted that Captain McPherson and his Rangers had settled at the fort, but he expressed doubts that more than one of them would make any real improvements to the land (CRG 21:270-275). "The Settlers at Fort Argyle are all of them entred into Captain Mcphersons Troop of Rangers, and (I believe) don't think of improving their Land (except Calvert) Arthur Ogle Edgcomb was appointed by the Captain to be his Lieutenant, but he has quitted his Service. & left the Colony, the Chief reason I can learn for this is: that no Rum could be allowed" (CRG 21:274).

In addition to the Rangers that were stationed at Fort Argyle, a Tythingman was employed there in 1736 to guard the civilian settlement. The title of Tythingman was derived from the word tything, or a group of 10 neighboring house lots in the colonial towns of Georgia. Ivers traces the origin of the tything to the early Middle Ages in England. The position of Tythingman was established in the Massachusetts Bay Colony as early as 1675. Initially these officers, who were "sober and discreet men", kept tabs on the liquor drinking conduct of 10 to 12 families under their charge. Their responsibilities later expanded to include other antisocial behaviors. The duties of the Tythingmen in Georgia not only included securing the peace within their tything, but they also had law enforcement authority further afield. The Tythingman at New Ebenezer for example, led a group of six Rangers in regular patrols between Frederica and New Ebenezer. In colonial Georgia groups of four tythings were considered a Ward and were policed by one constable with four tythingmen under his command (Jones 1984:154; Lender and Martin 1987:17; Moore 1840:97). Fort Argyle's Tythingman was paid an actual salary of £7.10.0 (PC 14207(Supp.):157a). Thomas Causton wrote from Savannah to England, "There are now four Constables and twelve Tythingmen in this Town in Comission as there are two Constables, for Thunderbolt. and Ebenezer and Six Tythingmen for the Severall Settlements of Tybey, Skidowa, Hempstead. Highgate, Fort Argyle and Abercorn" (CRG 21:287).

By November 1736, the Earl of Egmont recorded that Thomas Causton had informed him, "the settlers on the Ogikee river also made good improvement and the settlers at Fort Arguile had all entered themselves into the Rangers' troop, so that they did not think of improving [their land]". This simple statement is extremely important for our research because it serves to identify many of the Rangers who were at Fort Argyle during the early period as being synonymous with the settlers (Historical Manuscripts Commission 1923, v. 2:358; McPherson 1962:237).

In December the General Assembly of South Carolina passed a resolution that provided for Captain McPherson with 15 of the Rangers to cover and protect "the New Settlers until they enforced themselves and as they had occasion". This was probably in reference to McPherson and a portion of his troop being sent to support Highlanders who were settled at Darien during 1736 (Easterby 1951:155). Rangers established a small fort at Oakfuskie in the Upper Creek Nation in a modest challenge to the French at Fort Toulouse. The Oakfuskie fort, probably no more than a small stockade, was manned by Lieutenant Anthony Willey and eight men who had earlier served with Patrick McKay (CRG 21:304; Sonderegger 1964:141).

As the mood in Georgia became more belligerent towards Spain and its Indian allies, the Moravian colonists, who held pacifist beliefs, left Georgia for Pennsylvania. General Oglethorpe, who expected all the colonists to be prepared to defend themselves against attack, took no steps to block their exit (Fries 1967; Callaway 1948).

5.6 1737

In January 1737, the South Carolina General Assembly terminated financial support for the scout boats or rangers in Georgia, stating, "the House will provide for the Rangers & Scout boats to the 29th day of Sept. last and no longer", which amounted to £1,866 in support. The Georgia Trustees requested funds from Parliament of £419.16.2 for 25 Rangers at Fort Argyle and £7.10.0 for the Tythingman at Fort Argyle in March 1737. The Georgia Trustees requested £1,259.8.8 for, "50 Rangers or Forresters on Horseback to drive up the Cattle, kill Deer, and keep open the Communications through the Province". Several members of the South Carolina House stated, "that the Rangers were employed for three or four Months the last Spring in hunting for Cattle and driving them to Georgia, which Cattle Capt. McPherson Commander of the Rangers had bought and had agreed to deliver in Georgia to supply that Colony" (Easterby 1951:179-180, 321; PC 14207(Supp.):157e; PC 14208:460, 470).

In June of 1737 Oglethorpe was given a commission of General and Commander in Chief of all forces in South Carolina and Georgia, which authorized him to command the troops, administer death sentences, and appoint officers. Oglethorpe's Regiment, the 42nd Regiment of Foot, was established on August 25 and it performed duty in Georgia until officially disbanded on May 29, 1749. The main nucleus of Oglethorpe's 42nd Regiment of Foot consisted of three independent companies composed of former South Carolina soldiers who had been in the south since 1720. Another contingent was taken from the Earl of Roth's 25th Regiment of Foot. An additional 38 were soldiers in the Black Watch who had mutinied then were given a chance to redeem themselves in Georgia and were placed in the 42nd Regiment. Other troops were recruited in England and they arrived in Georgia on September 18 aboard five transports (BPRO, SCDAH 25:329-330; Clark 1983: xii).

By July, Oglethorpe was making payments (£100) drawn on the Trustees' account to Captain McPherson for his services after September 20, 1736. The Georgia records contain an entry for "A Certified Account for payment of the Southern Rangers at Fort Argyle amounting to four hundred twenty-five Pounds and four pence due to Capt James Mackpherson to Balance, and dated 2nd of October 1737 with a Letter of Advice thereof being brought also for payment" (CRG 2:179, 203, 222).

On August 11, the Georgia Office in London reviewed the following,

The Annual Expense of the Northern Division of Georgia. Capt. Macpherson and 25 rangers at Fort Argyll, 629£ 14s. 4d. (Note: If a supply has been voted at Charleston for Macpherson's rangers, there will be a saving on this article); John Cuthbert and 6 rangers, 168 [£]; Mr. Willy and 3 rangers, 96£; the storekeeper at Savannah, 50£; 3 clerks, 120£. (Note: This by the 2 clerks sent will be reduced lower and will answer for the advanced pay of Cuthbert and Willy above that of the rangers); provisions for 4 magistrates, 4 constables, 15 tithingmen at Savannah, constable and 6 tithingmen at Ebenezer, 7 peace-officers at Hampstead, Highgate, Skidoway, Tybee, Abercorn, Thunderbolt and Fort Argyll, 277£ 10s.; Capt. Mackintosh and 10 men at Fort Prince George, 241£ 1s.; capt., lieutenant and 15 men at the fort at Augusta, 324£ (Davies 1963:1-15).

In its October 4, 1737 to March 25, 1738 session the South Carolina Commons House listed several vouchers "wanting for the following Articles passed in the above Account", for the year 1732, which included,

Captain James McPherson, Commander of the Rangers	[£]125: 0: 0
John Westberry, Ranger	10: 0: 0
Joseph Wannell, do	2: 15: 6
Capt. James McPherson, do	90: 0:

(Easterby 1951:406).

That same document includes a list of Rangers and the amounts of their pay to March 1734. While this list does not specify their duty stations, most were likely part of Captain McPherson's Ranger troop. The list is transcribed in Table 5.1. These surnames appear to be nearly all English families.

Table 5.1 List of Rangers in Captain James McPherson's Troop in 1734.

- | | |
|--|---|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wm. Westberry • Wm. Small • Walter Pike • Geo. Pilkington • John Westberry • James Vincent • Wm. Fitchet • James Fitzgerald • Laurence Cooke • Wm. Richards | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saml. Kinsman • Wm. Gulliver • Wm. Burt • Wm. Gibson • Joseph Lowell • Gregory Fagan • Richard Smith • John Saunders • Morgan Davis • James Vincent • Jacob Brown |
|--|---|

(Easterby 1951:410-411).

Of these 21 men, Wm. [William] Richards is identified on another historical document as a Southern Ranger under Captain McPherson's command at Fort Argyle. In the absence of any extant payroll or muster lists for Captain McPherson's Rangers, this list serves as a defacto partial list of the South Carolina "Southern" Rangers, who saw service at Fort Argyle.

A South Carolina Act passed in 1737 provided, "for keeping good orders in the Several Forts & Garrisons under the Pay & Establishment of this government; and for encouraging the Several officers & soldiers therein", and it specified that no person was to enlist as a soldier for less than six months and, "That for the future, every Commander of the Several Forts and garrisons in this province shall twice every year, viz. on the Twenty-fifth day of March, and the Twenty-ninth Day of Sept., and at no other time make out a Muster Roll". The muster roll was to be made in triplicate with one copy to the Governor, one to the Treasurer, and one to the Commissary. Three entry receipts from McPherson's Muster Rolls for his Rangers at Fort Argyle were located during the historical research for this project and additional searches of the British Public Records may prove fruitful in locating the original muster rolls (Mackpherson 1735, 1736; Jenkins 1949:87-90).

Reverend John Wesley gave an account of the condition of the forts and settlements in Georgia on September 1737, in which he wrote,

Fort Argyle Stands 20 Miles above Sterlings Bluff on a high Bluff by the River Ogeechee. Tis a Small Square wooden Building, Musket proof, with Four little Cannon. The ten Freeholders Settled here cleared 30 Acres of Pine-Land, and built one house with part of another, but all of them except two are now gone. The Houses are rotting away. The walls of the fort are partly fallen already partly waiting for the next Gust of wind. And the land lying wast will in a few years, be as it was before (PC 14203:91; McPherson 1962:300; Wesley 1909, Vol. 1:406).

By October the Ranger Fort at Augusta was about half finished and progressing; the small fort at Thunderbolt was defended by nine cannons (but the walls were in disrepair); and the fort at Skidaway was in ruins (McPherson 1962:307).

South Carolina's Royal Governor Thomas Broughton died on November 22, 1737. Broughton was succeeded in office by Lieutenant Governor William Bull. Bull served as governor until the arrival of Royal Governor James Glen in 1743. Glen served as governor until he was recalled in 1756.

5.7 1738

As England celebrated the birth of the future King George III in 1738, nearly half the Cherokee Nation would succumb to smallpox. After four years of relative peace British troops were sent to Georgia to settle a border dispute with Spain. The size of the British Army, worldwide, stood at approximately 18,000 men. The Spanish at St Augustine were busy modernizing the Castillo de San Marcos in anticipation of a hostile visit by the English (Cole and Priestley 1936:53-55).

The early months of 1738 were a time of transition at Fort Argyle as new faces appeared and animosity between the leaders of Georgia and Captain James McPherson began to simmer. In a January 1738

report to Oglethorpe regarding indentured servants, "Seven Heads [7 German indentured servants were sent] to cultivate Lands at Fort Argyle clear'd by Capt. Mackpherson's Rangers", and in January the Trustees agreed to pay for seven German servants to, "cultivate Trust Lands at Fort Argule" (CRG 2:293; PC 12210:42). Thomas Causton wrote to the Trustees that month, "I humbly imagine, that you will easily believe, that Fort Argyle, every Garrison and Scout Boat, must be also attended with a Variety of expence; the particulars of which, generally arising from Repairs and unforeseen causes, could only be known, when they happen'd" (CRG 22(2):28). Captain McPherson was paid £215 (Carolina currency) by the South Carolina government in January and on March 3, the South Carolina Common House reported that £815 10 shillings had been paid to "Capt. McPherson Commander of the Rangers", which was, "on Account of the Rangers" under his command (Easterby 1951:406, 506, 526).

The minutes of the Georgia Trustees on January 25 of that same year record an account "for payment of Southern Rangers at Fort Argyle" amounting to 425£ 4d Sterling due to Captain James McPherson based on a request dated October 2, 1737" (CRG 2:222; PC 14209:181). Harmon Verelst, the Trustees' accountant, wrote to them in March that £906. 2.11 3/4. d Sterling were spent towards "the pay of the Garrison & Rangers" (CRG 33:1). In "An Account of Sundry Certificats Issued to be Pay'd in England—from 12. Augst. 1736 to 25 June 1738", the following entries pertain to Fort Argyle: "Octr. 1 [1737] James Mc person on Accot. Of the Garrison at Fort Argyle £424 19 8-3/4", and, "March 26, 1737 Ditto for Ditto £129 8 4-3/4" (PC 14203:302-305). In a "List of Debyts owing by the Store the 10th. Of October 1738", this entry pertained to Fort Argyle: "Fort Argyle £408 13 1" (PC 14203:306-308). An "Abstract of Sundry Charges for Establishing Georgia in America taken from the Accompt Books at Savannah from the 22d day of November 1736 to the 10th. of October 1738" included this payment, "Garrison at Fort Argyle £1331 13 5" (PC 14204:208). The Georgia Trustees paid for Southern Rangers in sola bills rather than in hard currency (Davies 1969:1-4). Sola bills were a paper currency developed by the Trustees for circulation in the colony of Georgia. The bills were backed by money deposited by the trustees in the Bank of England. This eliminated the ability of colonists to draw bills of exchange directly on individual Georgia Trustees for colony expenses (Jackson and Spalding 1984:200).

Thomas Causton wrote to the Georgia Trustees on February 14 explaining the financial situation with the South Carolina Rangers and Fort Argyle,

I am Sorry to find myself charg'd with presuming to disregard Your Honours Orders dated the 14th. of December 1737. by certifying the Accounts of Captain James Macpherson, Robert Williams and Comp. and Messrs. Ellis and Ryan, because I can take upon me to say, That every one of those persons were acquainted with those Your Orders, and were then told, that they must consequently hazard, such Objections as you would certainly make should payment for them be demanded in England.— Captain Macpherson as Comander of the Garrison at Fort Argyle demanded such Certificate and represented to me, That he had been at extraordinary Charges in providing Horses and necessarys for his Company on Credit, And that unless he was enabled to continue such a Credit to his people, by my Immediate Payment, or such an Assurance, As he could Raise a Credit upon, It was impossible for him to keep the People in Garrison, and threaten'd, That unless, I comply'd with his Demand, He and his men, would immediately quit the Service; This proceeding of Captain Macphersons, As it was Sudden and seem'd to be very

extraordinary, I could not, (with humble Submission) think it proper for me to deny his Request. Because such a Deniall, might have given him a Pretence to have executed his threats; which (if done) would certainly at that time, have expos'd the Colony to many Dangers, The Spaniards and French, being then, very busy among the Creeks and other neighbouring Nations of Indians in making Presents, forming Treatys and Stirring them up against us;— I was at that time, very dangerously ill, and therefore in a more particular manner than usuall consulted Collonel Stephens and the Majestrates as to this matter and now enclose, Copys of the Captains Letter and my Answer on that Occasion (CRG 22(2):67-68).

On March 24, William Stephens wrote in his journal,

Mr. Causton called on me this Morning as soon as he came to Town, and shewed me a Letter he had received from Mr. McPherson, Captain of the Rangers, wrote in an insolent and bullying Stile; wherein he told him, that as the Six Months were now expiring, which his People had engaged for, they would not continue on the same Terms; and unless Mr. Causton would comply with sundry Particulars required, as well relating to himself as his Men (most of which appeared to me to be exorbitant Demands) he would bid him farewell, and desired he would send somebody to take Charge of Fort Argyle: To which he expected his positive and full Answer on or before the 25th. I asked Mr. Causton, whether he had already sent him such an Answer (the Time and Occasion admitting of no Delay) and he told me he had; whereof he shewed me a Copy, desiring my Opinion; and on Perusal of it, I found he had so far given him Satisfaction about it, as to leave it to McPherson himself to make the best Terms with his Men that he could; and promising to conform to all that he insisted on besides, as far as it was in his Power; Which I readily concurred with him in, Necessity having no Law; and undoubtedly it would be better justified so to do, than risk the abandoning of that Fort, and dissolving the Company: Though we were both sensible that the Captain himself otherwise merited little Indulgence, being very seldom with his Men upon any Duty; making the Post a Sort of Sine-Cure, and putting so much Pay in his Pocket for little or nothing done (CRG 4:109-110).

On March 28, Stephens wrote in his journal, "Capt. McPherson came to Town, last from Fort Argyle, in order to settle Matters with Mr. Causton, pursuant to what passed lately betwixt them; I understand by him, that the Fort was become so ruinous, that there was a Necessity of his rebuilding of it" (CRG 4:113). That month Fort Argyle was garrisoned by 25 Rangers under the command of McPherson and this included a mixture of Georgians and South Carolinians. Oglethorpe sent the Duke of Newcastle a list of the forts under his command in early April, which included forts Moore, Prince George (Palachacolas), Johnson [in South Carolina], Argyle, and several others not itemized. Another of Oglethorpe's forts, St George, "which lay upon that part of the Alatomaha nearest to the river which the Spaniards call St John's", being very near the Spanish territory on the St John's River, had recently been withdrawn by Oglethorpe after protests by the Spanish (CRG 4:113; BPRO 1953, v. 44:59). Oglethorpe expressed his disbelief that the Spanish had not already made a play for control of Georgia: "The Spaniards though they had 1500 men at Augustine & there was nothing in Georgia but the Militia of the Countrey delayed attacking them till the Regular Troops arrived" (Oglethorpe 1873:48-49). Oglethorpe's 42nd Regiment of

500 men arrived in Georgia in September and the Georgia colonists breathed a sigh of relief. Two months later General Oglethorpe wrote to the Trustees:

The Parliament ought to enable the Trustees to pay these Debts for the following reasons. They granted £20,000 for the whole Expence of the Colony, but when they separated the Military from the Civil, they granted but £8,000 for the Civil Expence, supposing that a Regiment would arrive there which would take off the Military Expence, but it was near a year before the Regiment arrived all which time the Trustees Officers were obliged to continue the Expences for the Defence of the Province by maintaining the Militia who were under arms, by paying Scout boats, Rangers and Garrisons and supplying the Indians with Arms, Amunition and Necessaries, in order to keep them in readiness against the Spanish Invasion (Oglethorpe 1873:63).

Captain McPherson continued to argue with Causton during April over finances (CRG 4:115). The annual expense recorded in May 1738 of Captain McPherson and 25 Rangers at Fort Argyle, not including the wages of a peace officer, was £629.14.4. This represented the largest single military expense in the Georgia colony for that year, whose total defense budget was about £2,203. The total budget included Ranger forts in both Georgia and South Carolina and are inscribed in the records of colonial Georgia. The Georgia Trustees met in the Palace Court on May 10, 1738, where expenses of the Georgia colony were discussed. These included [£ per Annum] 629. 14. 4 for "The Expence of Capt. Mackpherson and twenty five Rangers at Fort Argyle" (CRG 2:234-235).

During May, Captain John Cuthbert, a resident of the Scottish settlement of Joseph's Town on the Savannah River, commanded a Troop of six Rangers. Cuthbert also served as a Ranger commander during the previous years when they were paid by South Carolina. By March 1739, Cuthbert and his men had established a cattle and horse path from Augusta to the Uchee Town at Mount Pleasant. However, by November 1739, Captain Cuthbert was dead, the victim of an "Epidemicall Distemper" (CRG 2:235; 22(2)245; 4:454; PC 14205:214).

On May 10, the Palace Court considered the Minutes of the Common Council of Georgia, which included recommendations for the government to pay, "the expenses of officers, rangers and men at the several forts, expenses of crews of pettiaugua and scoutboat etc. amounting to 2,203l. 7s. 2d." (Davies 1969:198).

Included in a boatload of indentured servants who arrived in Savannah in October 1738 were the Schlectermanns--a large family of 14 who were sent to serve the Trustees at Fort Argyle. This assignment was unfortunate, since most of the family died within a few years as a result of hardships on the frontier. Two male children, Jeremiah and Peter, survived into adulthood. Both may have served as Rangers at Fort Argyle, although definitive documentary evidence for this was not found. At least one of them spent some time with the Rangers, as suggested by Peter's later service as Armorer for the colony (Coulter and Saye 1949:48; Jones 1986:100). By the time the Schlectermanns arrived at Argyle the Rangers were becoming impatient over their tardy pay, as Oglethorpe wrote from Savannah on October 19 to the Trustees for Georgia:

The Scout Boatmen, Rangers and others who defended the Province are not paid, and starving whilst the Trustees owe them money; and yet they were not only contented to stay till my arrival, but when I told them the Trustees' circumstances their affection was so great, that they offered to serve on until the Trustees' affairs mended. I thanked them but reduced the Rangers since I could not feed them with hopes of what I could not make good. The Scout Boats I have for this month paid out of my own money since they are absolutely necessary and I will not charge the Trustees with new debts (BPRO 1953, v. 44:225-226).

In mid-November, Fort Argyle experienced a changing of the guard. The troops in Georgia, including Captain McPherson's Southern Rangers at Fort Argyle, were officially discharged whereupon McPherson returned to his plantation in southwestern South Carolina. Two Rangers, Lachlan McIntosh and William Francis, remained at Fort Argyle to serve as caretakers. McIntosh and Francis were paid by Oglethorpe from his personal account (Ivers 1974:85). These two men were the first official Georgia Rangers. Oglethorpe would soon establish other Georgia Ranger outposts in the hinterland including Mount Venture on the Altamaha River and Mount Pleasant on the Savannah River.

Meanwhile the mundane (non-military) tasks for the rangers continued. On December 16, Stephens wrote in his journal, "Thomas Young's Boy the Wheelwright, who lately run away from his Master, together with another who was a Servant to the Widow Brownjohn, were both taken at Fort Argyle, and brought home; upon which the Magistrates committed them to the Log-House, to remain there till Monday, when some farther Course should be taken with them" (CRG 4:248).

5.8 1739

In the spring of 1739 Oglethorpe set out with a large party of officers, traders, attendants, and servants to treat with the Creeks at Coweta on the Chattahoochee River. The trip took 25 days and it was several more months before Oglethorpe would be back on the Georgia coast to govern the colony. Oglethorpe hoped to gather support among the Creeks for his planned offensive against the Spanish at St. Augustine. In an anonymous account of Oglethorpe's trip to meet with the Creek Chiefs written in July, the author noted, "On this river [Ogeechee] Stands Fort Argyle, on the Road from Darien to Savannah" (PC 14205:173). Oglethorpe traveled up the Savannah River to Mount Pleasant where he met the Indian Trader Thomas Wiggins. Oglethorpe was so impressed with Wiggins and their trader's outpost at Mount Pleasant that he ordered a fort established there to be garrisoned by 12 Rangers under Wiggins' command. The actual garrison at Mount Pleasant was not established until two years later. In July, while on the same journey, General Oglethorpe also passed through Fort Argyle (CRG 4 (Supp.):86; P.C. v. 14205(1):98; Sonderegger 1964:154). Oglethorpe included this entry for May 1739, "19 Paid Lachlan Mackintosh & Will. Francis 6 months pay each, as Rangers at Fort Argyle from 19 Oct. to 19 April 1739 £24 - - p_ recpt." (PC 14204:47).

As tensions mounted between Spain and England one inauspicious naval incident precipitated the onset of war between the two powers. A suspected English smuggling schooner from Jamaica commanded by Captain Robert Jenkins was boarded by the Spanish. The commanding Spanish officer severed Jenkins' ear and instructed him to deliver it to King George. This event transpired shortly before March 1738 and served as a rallying cry in the British Parliament. The war, also known as King George's War, the War of

Austrian Succession, or the War of Jenkin's Ear, officially lasted from October 1739 until October 1748 (Barnwell 1927:141-168; Stanhope 1858. v. 2:57, 208). By the fall of 1739 Georgia was to become a military theater in King George's War. Admiral Vernon dealt a major blow to the Spanish in November when his ships captured the Spanish port of Porto Bello in Central America (Stanhope 1858, v. 2:57). However, with a skeleton staff of two Georgia Rangers, Fort Argyle was to be barely affected by the global events during this year.

Although Fort Argyle was experiencing a lull before the real action, the fort and its rangers remained on the minds of Georgia's leaders. The Earl of Egmont quoted Oglethorpe regarding the latter's actions of keeping Lachlan McIntosh and William Francis employed at Fort Argyle from October 1738 to April 1739 by saying "these rangers are absolutely necessary. They are emply'd in driving up cattel, & catching run away servants for which tsk [task] they are pd. the pt [paid the part] of their duty" (Coulter and Saye 1949:74). Oglethorpe realized the Trustees' reluctance to continue to pay the two Georgia Rangers, and wrote to the Earl about the matter on July 5. In his "Acct. of the Expenses of the Colony from 22 Septbr. 1738 to 20 June 1739 with his explanations", which contained, "An Acct. of Sundry Disbursments, made by Francis Moore, by my Order", Oglethorpe made this statement for 1738-9, "Fort Arguile being the middle way between the Darien & Savannah, when I dismist the 25 Rangers that were there, I was obliged to keep on two, They have been of use, having Stopt Several runaway Servts. assisted the Passengers, and furnish'd the German Servants that are Settled there, with provision by hunting. As soon as the German Servts. have got in their crop, I think to reduce those two rangers, & make a Saving" (PC 14204(5):37j, 46). General Oglethorpe also wrote to the Trustees about the Fort Argyle boat and the Schlechtermann family at Argyle: "The Fort Arguile boat; This was work'd by the Garison there; Having reduced that garison, I put a German family with 2 Cattel hunters there, and thereby Saved the charge of that garison there, and preserved the communication" (PC 14204(5):37v, 51-52). That same month Oglethorpe wrote to the Trustees of his plans to build "cleftboard houses" for accommodating the five companies of troops in Georgia. His instructions to build cleftboard, or clapboard, houses were likely given to the Rangers at Fort Argyle as well. Oglethorpe also stressed the need for the Rangers in Georgia:

Horsemen for pursuing in the Woods Felons, Runaway Servants, Outlaws and Slaves from Carolina., which have already molested the Inland parts of the Countrey; and thieving for want of Rangers to pursue them is grown so common that great numbers of Hogs and not a few Cattel have been killed in the Woods so that it is dangerous to let them out and People have neither Inclosures nor Food to keep them at home. The killing and stealing of Hogs has been so frequent at Savannah that there is hardly one person in that Town that has one, though when I left the Province there were several hundred there (BPRO 1953, v. 45:133-134).

Oglethorpe submitted a detailed plan to the Trustees in August for the establishment of the Georgia Rangers (CRG 35:234:272). In September, General Oglethorpe sent a reconnaissance party to the St. John's River in Florida to scout out the Spanish fortifications. He wrote to the Trustees on October 5 stating that he was "forced to put thirty Rangers upon footing to employ several Scout Boats, to promise to pay to the Indian Traders for raising the Indians to preserve the Province in this critical juncture" (Duncan n.d.:407; BPRO 1953, v. 45:196; Oglethorpe 1873:82).

In South Carolina, the Stono Rebellion, an insurrection by embittered slaves began in September (Wood 1974). Although Georgia was not a slave-owning colony, it became involved in the matter as runaways crossed through Georgia on their way to freedom in Spanish Florida. These escaped slaves, with the aid of the Spanish military, constructed Fort Mose and settled nearby in eastern Florida (Deagan and MacMahon 1995). In October, four or five runaway slaves from South Carolina, "some of whom belonged to Captain Macpherson" stole some of McPherson's horses, wounded his son, killed a man, and then headed for Florida by way of Georgia. They were pursued by the Rangers, but the Rangers, being "newly reduced", were not able to capture the runaways. The slaves were received by the Spanish with great honors (CRG 22(2):232). A London newspaper reported, "These [runaways] marched for Georgia, and were pursued; but the Rangers being then newly reduced, the Country People could not overtake them, tho' they were discover'd by the Saltburgher, as they passed by Ebenezer. They reached Augustin, one only being killed, and another wounded by the Indians in their Flight. They were received there with great Honours" (*The London Magazine, and Monthly Chronologer*, Vol. 9 (1740):152). Upon learning of the Stono Rebellion after he returned to Savannah from the Creek Nation, Oglethorpe,

immediately order'd a Troop of Rangers to be raised, to patrole thro' Georgia, placed some Men in the Garrison at Palichocolas, which was before abandon'd, and near which the Negroes formerly passed, being the only Place where Horses can come to swim over the River Savannah for near 100 Miles, order'd out the Indians in Pursuit, and a Detachment of the Garrison at Port Royal to assist the Planters on any Occasion, and publish'd a Proclamation, ordering all the Constables, &c. of Georgia to pursue and seize all Negroes, with a Reward for any who should be taken (*Gentleman's Magazine* 1740, volume 10:128-129).

Treaty talks between the British and the Lower Creek Indians at Coweta Town on the Chattahoochee River culminated on August 21, 1739 with the Treaty of Coweta (*The Georgia Historical Quarterly* 1920:3-16). This important event was followed by the death of Tomochichi, the Yamacraw chief who had befriended Oglethorpe upon his first arrival in Georgia. Tomochichi was buried in Savannah.

Oglethorpe wrote from Savannah to the Duke of Newcastle on October 8 stating, "I have raised a troop of horse rangers to hinder their [the Spanish] horse from succeeding in any attempts against Georgia upon the continent and to gain intelligence" (Davies 1994:192-215). Oglethorpe wrote to Herman Verelst in October, nearly a year after the South Carolina Rangers had left Georgia that, "Captain Mackpherson has a very considerable demand upon the Trust as appears by the Report of the Commissioners, he having made it appear that he was in the utmost distress I advanced him £61.4.0 which lessens the debt due by the Trust" (Oglethorpe 1873:86). Later that same month, in a letter to the Trustees, Oglethorpe noted that there were no provisions for Tythingmen or Constables at Abercorn, Augusta, Ebenezer, Hampstead, Highgate, Savannah, or Skidaway, and he requested that the Trustees use their influence in Parliament to secure funding for one troop of Rangers, "without which we shall lye entirely open to the Insults of the Spanish Horse and Indians upon the Continent, for it is impossible for one Regiment of Foot to cover such a vast Frontier". Oglethorpe also noted that he maintained a garrison of a Captain and ten men at Augusta. Oglethorpe repeated his request to the Trustees for a troop of Rangers the following month (Oglethorpe 1873:90, 92, 99). Oglethorpe compiled a "State of Georgia" report with the

longer title, "Introductory Discourse to the State of the Colony of Georgia" on October 11, in which he wrote, "These Settlements extend as far as the narrow Passages near Ogeechee, upon which River lies Fort Argyll in a Situation that Commands all the Provinces" (PC 14204:123, 127).

The Trustees' Secretary, Benjamin Martyn, noted that Andrew Grant, John Baillie, and David Douglas had abandoned their settlements upon the Ogeechee prior to May 1739. These men had been part of the Sterling's Bluff settlement, which was located several miles downstream from Fort Argyle. This suggests that Sterling's Fort was likely abandoned by that time, which left Argyle as the sole British defense on the Ogeechee River (CRG 30:108-109).

On November 13, Spaniards attacked and killed two British settlers on Amelia Island. Oglethorpe told the Duke of Newcastle: "they cut off their heads and mangled their bodies". In response General Oglethorpe "raised up two Troops of Rangers, or horsemen, and sent up captain Cuthbert to Carolina to buy Horses for them". Unfortunately, Captain John Cuthbert died from natural causes before completing the tasks. Lieutenant Scroggs assumed command of Cuthbert's "Troop of English Rangers" and "a handful of men were recruited into his troop and were stationed at Fort Argyle under the command of Lachlan Macintosh". Ivers notes that between four and eight Georgia Rangers were garrisoned at Fort Argyle under Lachlan Macintosh's command. The General also established a troop of seven horsemen (Rangers) at New Ebenezer and 12 horsemen at Mount Pleasant (PC 14205(1):124-132; CRG 35:234; Ivers 1974:137; BPRO 1953, v. 45:271).

On December 29, Oglethorpe wrote to the Trustees, "Horsemen also I am obliged to raise & have order'd 60 Rangers. Their Establishm'ts Mr. Horton has with him". In the same letter he noted: "The Forts that I built were run to ruin, being mostly of earth, having no means to repair them and having also orders not to fortify" (Oglethorpe 1873:98-100). Two days later Oglethorpe wrote from Frederica to the Duke of Newcastle requesting the formal establishment of a Ranger troop composed of a, "Captain, lieutenant, comet, 2 quartermasters, trumpet or french horn, 29 privates. cost 72£ 11 sh sterling per month, to find themselves with horses, arms, accoutrements and food. To enable them to do real service the officers and quartermasters must be allowed spare horses with servants for the officers, at an additional cost of 5£ 19 sh sterling per month. One other troop the same" (BPRO 1953, v. 45:271). Oglethorpe wrote to South Carolina Governor Bull the same day with this suggestion: " I should think the people of Carolina would do very well to raise a Troop of Rangers, under the Command of Capt McPherson who is a very good Officer." Captain McPherson was apparently still having difficulty in obtaining satisfaction for his services from Georgia. The Trustees voted to make payment to McPherson of £189.13.1 1/1. pence in March 1740, which they considered, "in full of all his Demands". This was in addition to £61 paid immediately prior to that. In July 1744 South Carolina Speaker of the House Jenys sent a prodding letter to the Trustees' Accountant, which ended with the comment, "pray have the Trustees (ordered payment), or when did they order payment of McPhersons Accot." Two other accounts were outstanding as of 1739, that: "of James Mackpherson for pay of Arthur Ogle Edgecomb and William Finley for Eighty-four pounds Currency" (Lanrung 1904:93; CRG 2:294, 359; 24:246).

General Oglethorpe requested money from the Trustees for repairing forts in Georgia in late December, but the letter was not received until the following May. He proposed spending £500 to repair Frederica,

£400 for St Andrews on Cumberland, and £100 for Amelia Island. The Trustees' accounts for 1739 include £262 14s Sterling for Rangers support at Argyle and Augusta (Oglethorpe 1873:100; CRG 3:254).

5.9 1740

Flush with confidence following Admiral Vernon's victory over the Spanish at Porto Bello, Great Britain launched an attack on the Spanish mainland in 1740. In April, Oglethorpe, also filled with a sense of euphoria over recent British victories, sent a document entitled, "Preparation for Attacking St. Augustine" to England and in it he included an account of the moneys necessary for the invasion. One troop of Rangers for the invasion was to be paid for by the South Carolina Assembly. The British military strength worldwide that year was estimated at 58,995 soldiers; including 3,402 in the Plantations [North American colonies]; and 684 in Georgia. The Georgia forces consisted of six companies of the 1st Regiment of Foot, commanded by General Oglethorpe, each containing 100 men. These foot soldiers were led by 84 officers. By November 1741 the number of troops in the Plantations rose slightly to 3,577 soldiers. Back in Europe the death of Charles VI in October set off a global struggle for the throne in Austria (*Gentleman's Magazine* 10:613-614; 11:508; Anderson 1995:224; Cole and Priestley 1936:55; CRG 35:260).

Lord Egmont wrote in his diary in mid-January 1740, "That there are forts in the southern Province, Fort Frederica, Fort St. Simon's, Fort St. Andrew's on Cumberland, Fort at New Inverness, Fort by way of look out at Amelia. And in the northern division, Fort Augusta, Fort Arguile, and one that had been begun at Savannah" (Historical Manuscripts Commission 1923, vol. 3:100). Summarizing the period from June 1740 to 1741, Secretary Benjamin Martyn noted that in Georgia there were: "six forts in the province, and a battery of cannon erected to secure the harbor of St. Simons. under which ships may safely lie". These included: "a strong fort" at Frederica; two forts on St Simons island south of Frederica; "a battery of cannon" at Savannah; and "a little Fort" at Darien manned by Scottish Highlanders (Martyn 1842:309; CRG 3:403; CRG 4:668). An account on the state of the province, dated November 10, 1740 noted, "Besides these Settlements. there are some others of five hundred Acres per Grant from the Trust, which extends far as the Ogeechey River: upon which River lies Fort Argyll, in such a Situation, as is intended thereby to command all the Passes in that Part of the Province" (CRG 4:668).

In January, Captain Mark Carr wrote from his Hermitage Plantation on the Altamaha River to General James Campbell regarding the formation of Carr's Marine Ranger troop:

He [General Oglethorpe] raised one additional Troop of Rangers, wch. he has hond. me with my Commission wch. is dated ye 19 Xbr. runs as Capt. I have a Lieut. Comet, Quarter master, two Corplls., one French horn & 29 private Men, my Range is to be from Fort St. Fransisco to ye Darien, wch. I judge is near 200 miles distant, they will be of great protection from ye little Excursion of the Spanish Indians upon this colony, in time of peace. but if the War continues, they'll be of the utmost consequences. The pay is very Small Scarce able to Subsist on, Setting aside ye hardships wch. perhapps is Lying 9 months in ye year on Bars ground without any Covering, & all for 2.6 p day, but the Genll. designs to push to have them on the Dragoon Establishmt. & I flatter my Self if such a thing come upon ye Carpett you'll give me yr. assistance, for its you I thank for the 2.6 (PC 14204:88-96).

The British Treasury office recorded (in August 1742) this transmission from Oglethorpe regarding the pending war between Georgia and South Carolina, and Spanish Florida,

Offensive:—If I had one battalion of land forces more, with a small train of artillery, engineers, and gunners from Europe, and an allowance for pioneers, whom I could raise in America, and for the two troops of Rangers, the Highland Company, the Indians, and for one hundred boatmen, and to buy such craft here as might oppose the half gallies, I think the place might be reduced this winter ...

Defensive:—If we are to act upon the defensive the two troops of Rangers, one hundred boatmen with proper craft and the 2 sloops that are now here [Frederica], the small garrisons that are in the country and the Highland Company will be necessary to be continued, as also some artillery and ammunition to be sent for the defence of the town and harbour, and the fortifications of Fort St. Andrews and Fort William to be improved, and orders for me to continue the fortifying this town, the barracks &c. ...If there is a war with France. It will be necessary to raise the Creek, Chickasaw, and Cherokee Indians and keep them in arms, and to augment the Rangers to 60 in a troop, to raise more Rangers, to fortify strongly at Mount Venture and Fort Augusta. For the French have 1,500 regular troops at the Mobile at New Orleans and on the river Mississippi, and can march from their advance fort to Charleston in about 20 days. But as they must pass over several great rivers in the Creek country, a large body of Rangers with the assistance of the Indians might stop them there. They can also march through the Cherokee country, but that is a much longer road. Both these nations are within the province of Georgia and faithfull to His Majesty and assisted us in the seige [sic, siege] at St. Augustine (Shaw 1903:63-72).

General Oglethorpe launched his offensive against Spanish Florida in May. His forces consisted of:

The 42nd Regiment of Foot. 500 men;
The South Carolina Regiment of Foot. 600 men;
Hugh McKay, Jr.'s Troop of English Rangers;
One Troop of Highland Rangers;
One Company of English Foot;
One Company of Highland Foot;
Volunteers from South Carolina;
Indians (probably Yuchi Troop of Foot under command of Thomas Wiggins); and
Boatmen

(Duncan n.d.:408).

The Gentleman's Magazine reported that in May General Oglethorpe had destroyed one Spanish fort in Florida and taken possession of another fort that was seven leagues from St Augustine. Oglethorpe's men attacked several Spanish Guard houses on the St. John's River. Oglethorpe's Indians captured and burned Fort Picolata, and Fort St. Francis de Pupa was taken by a group of Indians and Rangers.

Oglethorpe was able to gather considerable information on the Spanish defenses in Florida as a result of these conquests. He learned that the Spanish had other forts in Florida including forts Diego, Rossa, Chicketo, Pinnion, and Moosa [Mose], in addition to the formidable Castillo de San Marcos at St. Augustine (*Gentleman's Magazine 1740*, Vol. 10:242; Lanning 1954; Oglethorpe 1873:105-106).

Oglethorpe and his army attacked the Spanish at St. Augustine in June and the siege continued into early July. After capturing and manning Fort Mose in June, against orders by General Oglethorpe a group of Highlander Rangers (number unknown), 60 Highland foot soldiers, 40 Indians, and 13 English (Georgia) Rangers who were members of Captain Hugh McKay, Jr.'s troop, all under the command of Colonel Palmer of South Carolina, were surrounded, attacked, and captured by the Spanish. This defeat signaled the beginning of the breakdown of Oglethorpe's invasion plan and on July 10 Oglethorpe ordered a retreat. While only two lives were lost in the main assault on St Augustine, which consisted of a 27-day bombardment, the toll at Fort Mose was far more dismal for the British. Forty to 50 of the British or their allies were killed and another 10 to 20 were captured. Most of those killed were Highlanders from Darien, but some of the casualties may have included Rangers from Fort Argyle (PC 14205(1):32-33, 51; Sonderegger 1964:174; Duncan n.d.: 408). In, "An exact Acct. as well as could be gather'd of the Forces of the Spaniards at St. Augustine: together with an Acct. of their Loss; Also the number of our Forces, and what loss we Sustain'd during the Seige", were listed 50 Rangers. The total losses suffered by Oglethorpe's forces, which include 75 men killed in battle as well as 14 deserters and 47 souls who were, "Lost by Sickness, [and included?] Indians, Georgians & Carolinians" were 136 (PC 14205:106a).

After Captain McKay's defeat at Fort Mose, he was transferred to the 42nd Regiment where he served as Lieutenant. By 1741 Thomas Wiggins had replaced him as captain of the English Rangers, which consisted of 12 men. Serving under Captain Wiggins in their garrison at Mount Pleasant were Lieutenant Richard Scruggs and John Milledge, who was possibly an Ensign at that time. Milledge would later serve as commander of Fort Argyle (Duncan n.d.:409).

Harman Verelst communicated a petition to the Treasury on March 5, 1743, covering expenses for several years prior. These included, "A computation of one year's expense of the 2 troops of Rangers of 60 men each, the Highland Company of 100 men, the 100 boatmen and the 2 half-galleys proposed by Oglethorpe in July 1741, as necessary in Georgia during the war. (Total establishment 8,398l. 6s. 8d. per an.)" (Shaw 1903:242-260). In August 1740 General Oglethorpe established a Marine guard of 10 men at Wormsloe under command of Noble Jones. They were to watch the Skidaway Narrows and patrol the neighboring sounds and rivers (Duncan n.d.:408).

By that fall the troop strength at Fort Argyle was extremely light. Lachlan McIntosh oversaw Fort Argyle in September when in the absence of McIntosh and his Rangers, the place was attacked and plundered. Two servants, John and Helen Bere Smyth, were murdered. The tragedy happened sometime between September 6th and September 18th for on September 21, Governor Stephens wrote in his journal,

Towards Evening Laughlan McIntosh alighted at my Door, and gave me a dismal Relation of what happened at Fort Argyle, upon the River Oguchee: Which in Substance was, That having been some Days absent from the Fort on Business, partly at Savannah and elsewhere; on his Return

thither last Thursday Evening, he found the Doors all open, what Chests or Boxes were within rifled, much Blood spilt on the Bed, Floor, &c. and his Dog wrapt up in a Blanket with his Throat cut; from whence he concluded, that a Man and Woman Servant, whom he left there were both murdered. How it happened that so few Hands were left there, or why he himself, who had the Charge of the Place, left them so defenceless, it was not a Time for me to enter into an Enquiry of; but I soon called the Magistrates together, that due Examination might be taken of all Circumstances which could be come at: And then he deposed, that they had found the Servant Man's Body floating in the River a Mile or two lower, with no Head to it, which was supposed to have been cut off; but they could find no Token of what became of the Maid: He said, that when he went thither on Thursday last, he had in Company with him William Francis of this Town, who was appointed one to keep Garrison there; and before he came thence now, two or three other Men arrived there, under the same Appointment: It was observed, that during his Examination, he appeared very much disordered, by an uncommon Flutter of Spirits, which raised a Jealousy there was something more than ordinary which he had not discovered; wherefore it was thought best to defer a farther Examination till to-morrow; and in the mean while a watchful Eye was appointed to be near him, as a Companion, that he might not slip out of Town, whilst at the same Time he knew not himself to be under Confinement. Various were Peoples Conjectures on this Occasion, and indeed the whole Town was alarmed, most Part of them concluding, that it must be some Indians, but what Indians they could not tell, unless our own Friends and Neighbors, which there was not the least Grounds to suspect. My own Thoughts (which divers concurred with me in) were, that the Spanish Doctor, and the Irishman, who broke Prison, and escaped hence (as noted the 14th of August, &c. seq.) finding themselves under great Difficulties how to subsist, and make a thorough Escape, had joined themselves to some Negroes lately fled from Carolina, who were wandering Southward (as of late many of them had deserted; insomuch that there was a Party of Horse appointed always to scout on the Banks of the River, and guard the Passes out of that Province) and these so joined very probably might attempt such an Act, especially when they would meet with no Opposition; and what induced me the rather to include to this Opinion was, that among the several Particulars of Plunder carried off, which chiefly consisted of Eatables, I took particular Notice they had taken a Quire of Writing-Paper, which could be of no Use to an Indian; and moreover it is to be observed, that when an Indian kills, he always takes the Scalp alone; but the Negro most commonly takes the whole Head. We were next to wait for what farther Discoveries we could come at to-morrow (CRG 4:656-657).

The following day (September 22) Stephens wrote in his journal,

The Magistrates now met again, and took Depositions in Form of what Laughlan McIntosh had to say; which he made Affidavit of: And finding him abstruse in many Things, and differing from what he had reported Yesterday; they became more suspicious than before, that something at Bottom was not right; wherefore Mr. Parker the Magistrate, and Mr. Mercer the Constable, offering voluntarily to go to the Fort themselves, and endeavor to find out the Truth of the Whole, it was so agreed at my House; and as their readiest Way to come at it, was up the Oguchee from the Mouth of it, they purposed to go by Land to Noble Jones's Plantation; to whom I wrote an Order to be assisting to them, with his Guard-Boat, and proper Hands; and accordingly they set

out soon after. In the mean while proper Means were used to amuse Laughlan, and keep him in Town, till we should get some Report from Parker and Mercer how they found Matters at the Fort (CRG 4:657-658).

On September 29, Stephens wrote in his journal,

Fresh Intelligence being brought us this Evening, that the Spanish Doctor, who with his Companion broke Prison, and escaped hence some Time ago, had been seen that Morning near the Cow-Pen at Old Ebenezer...a Reward of 20 l. Sterling was promised upon catching them, or proportionable for either; being now pretty full in Opinion, that the late Murder and Plunder at Fort Argyle was perpetrated by that Crew; one at least, if not more, having lately joined them; but who, we could not tell (CRG 4:659-660).

On October 4, Stephens wrote in his journal of the capture of these two villains on the Savannah River at Mount Pleasant, or Uchee Town, where, "Rain had driven them for Shelter into a Hut, and our Pursuers surprising them, they were secured without Resistance; tho' they had Arms with them, which they took at Fort Argyle, and where they readily confessed they had murdered that Man and Woman, and made Plunder of what they liked" (CRG 4:661-662). The Spanish Doctor, who was named Joseph Anthony Mazzique, and William Shannon, the Irishman were both indicted for murder on October 7, Mazzique pleaded guilty, while Shannon did not but was found guilty, and on November 11, 1740 both murderers were hanged. Shannon's corpse was "immediately sent away in a Boat, in order to be hung in Chains at the Mouth of the River Ogeechey, by the General's Orders, upon my recommending it to his Excellency, which he approved" (CRG 4 (Supp.):8-9, 27-28). Stephens continued,

The General having ordered that William Shannon the Irishman. under sentence of death, should be hung in Chains at the Mouth of Ogeechey (the River whereon Fort Argyle Stands, where that horrible Murder was committed) it appearing that he was the foremost bloody Perpetrator of the Fact, in which the Spaniard, Joseph Anthony Mauique, was assisting; and this being such a Situation for a Gibbet, as would be conspicuous to all who passed to and fro (CRG 4(Supp.):23).

The Earl of Egmont recorded the slaughter at Fort Argyle in his journal that, "Fort Arguile had been broken open. and a Man and woman servant found murder'd, and he suspected it was done by the Spanish Doctor formerly mentioned and the Irish man with him, who had broken jail as formerly mentioned". The two suspected culprits were soon captured while hiding in a hut at Mount Pleasant and allegedly confessed to committing the atrocities at Fort Argyle. John Pye wrote to the Trustees that on October 7, Joseph Anthony Mazzique, and William Shannon were, "Indicated Arraignd Tryed & found Guilty" of the crime of murder. A warrant was issued to William Meers, Tythingman, "to convey the Body of Shennon to the Mouth of Ogeechee River, at the Entrance of Hosabaw Sound. And there hang him in Chains" (CRG 4:660-661; 5:397; 22(2):433, 435).

Noble Jones wrote to Harman Verelst on October 6, informing him,

On ye 6th Septemr. Lachlan McIntosh (who is employd by ye General to remain at & take care of Fort Argyle) same [sic, came] to Savannah and declared (as reported by his Friends at Jenkins's) That two Creek Indians came by the Fort, wth. Horses laden wth. Strouds, Trunks &c and told him that they had killed Jacob Matthews & Family, had plundered his Store & threatened the English--- He (Lachlan) avoided Seeing me, & went out of Town, I sent to ye Indian Town, for Tuanoy, (who was lately come from Mr. Matthews, then at ye Forks abot. 150 miles from Savannah). He (Tuanoy) declared that Matthews was very well, and promisd. To come to Savannah next Moon, that he was well assured their people, (the Creeks) would not hurt their Friends, the English, especially Jacob Mathews his Wife, being a Creek, by her Mother (CRG 22(2):427-428).

Jacob Mathews was Captain of the Ranger Company at Fort Mount Venture at Sansavilla Bluff on the Altamaha River. His wife was Mary Musgrove Mathews, a high-ranking Creek. This story of Jacob Matthews murder was false.

On October 12, Stephens wrote in his journal that he had received orders from General Oglethorpe for

Quarter-Master Darmer...to raise and bring up ten Rangers to garrison Fort Argyle, and Possession of fifty Acres of land for Planting, to be given to each of their Families; Mr. Darmer happening luckily to be now in Town, I immediately gave him the General's Directions and he appears ready and willing to fulfil them, as soon as may be...These Things appear to me to be the Result of the General's Deliberations upon what he was lately inform'd of from hence, touching that dreadful Murder at Fort Argyle, which was undoubtedly not tenable without a competent Number of Men; and considering how inevitably this Part of the Province lies exposed in such a Wilderness, to be ravaged by runaway Negroes from Carolina, or Parties of strolling Spanish Indians; we ought all of us to acknowledge the General's Care for our Safety, and to do what in us lies, for its being secured to us (CRG 4(Supp.):11-12).

Stephens noted that Darmer was a "foreigner", which indicates that he was not English. Jones (1986:16) suspects that Darmer /Dormer was German. Later in his journal in August 1741, Stephens refers to James Dormer and it is most likely that his earlier reference to Darmer was likely a misspelling or a transcription error (CRG 4(Supp.):222-227, 240-241). James Dormer also signed his name to a December 9, 1738 petition to the Georgia Trustees and is mentioned in the minutes of the Georgia Trustees on June 6, 1740 (CRG 2:335-336). From August 1741 to at least February 1743, Dormer was employed as a pilot and lookout on Tybee Island and was not associated with Fort Argyle. Thus, the period when James Dormer may have been posted at Fort Argyle would have been between October 13, 1740 and August 16, 1741. Dormer was dead by 1748 (CRG 2(Supp.):222-227, 240-241;6:59; Telemon Cuyler Collection, Miscellaneous & Late Records, Box 14:37).

Documents note other individuals associated with Fort Argyle in 1740. This includes Thomas Bichler, a resident of New Ebenezer, was appointed as a Tythingman by General Oglethorpe and placed in charge of six Rangers who were to patrol the section from Frederica to New Ebenezer. Although Bichler was never formally commissioned as an officer, he appears to have served that role for a number of years.

Since Fort Argyle was central along the overland route between these two points it is reasonable to deduce that Bichler and his Rangers were frequent visitors to Fort Argyle. As fall approached at Fort Argyle, Lachlan McIntosh remained in charge, under General Oglethorpe's employ. In addition, one Tythingman also was on the payroll at Fort Argyle, but his name was not recorded. Fort Argyle's Tythingman was paid 10 s per month that year (CRG 4(Supp):11-12; CRG 22(2):427).

Listed in an "Acct. of the Sums apply'd & expended for the Trust Service in the Northern part of the Colony of Georgia for 1 year, endg. Michlemass [Michaelmas, September 29] 1740", was this entry under "Boats, viz. provisions & c", "Arguile boat £0.0.9 [Particulars] £26. 5. 7 1/2". This account also contained, "To Slechtermans family, Sent to Fort Arguile £6.8.1 [Particulars] £41. 5. 4." (PC 14205:74a). Among those on a list of petitioners to the Trustees contained in a letter sent to Captain Tailfer by the Malcontents of Georgia in December 1740 was, "Will. Greenfeild [Remarks] his mark. Sent at the Tr. Expence Servt. & placed at Fort Arguile. arrived 1 feb. 1732/3". William Greenfield was among a list of 20 "Inmates and Servants" who were, "all Scotch Men" (PC 14205:261). We were unable to determine how many others of these 20 people were assigned to live at Fort Argyle.

By the end of 1740 Georgia was in a sad state of military affairs (Figure 5.4). Many of the settlers had fled to Carolina for protection from the Spanish. John Fallowfield estimated that 75 percent of the houses in Savannah lay empty and the outlying villages were also depopulated. Abercorn had only three families remaining; Highgate had two; Hampstead had one; Newington, Skidaway, and Tybee were completely abandoned; and the village at Ogeechee was "in the same state" (PC 14205(2):165- 174, 182). An account by William Stephens published in November cited five forts in Georgia and two on the Savannah River in South Carolina. The Georgia forts included a, "handsome fort, where there is a small garrison of about twelve or fifteen men, besides officers" at Augusta; "a little fort" at Darien; "a strong fort" at Frederica; and Forts St Andrews and William on Cumberland Island. The South Carolina forts included forts Palachocolas and Moore. It made no mention of Fort Argyle. In a published response to Stephens' 1740 account dated 1743, anonymous authors, possibly Thomas Stephens or Sir Richard Everhard, presented quite a different representation of Georgia's defenses: "there has been no muster there [Georgia] these four or five years, and that there is not a defensible fort in the province" (Stephens 1966:73-75; Anonymous 1842b:96). However, a State of the Province signed by 25 people in November described the forts in Georgia and specifically mentioned Argyle, Frederica, and Darien (CRG 35:311).

5.10 1741

Important British sieges against the Spanish at Cartagena and Santiago, Cuba were launched during the first half of 1741. By March approximately 800 Spanish troops had landed at St Augustine along with many shiploads of provisions. By July the British had retreated from unsuccessful attacks after suffering significant loss of life. The Spanish at St. Augustine continued to busy themselves for an invasion of Georgia (Stanhope 1858, v. 2:61, 65; *South Carolina Gazette*, July 2, 1741; June 8, 1741). An anonymous description of the Georgia colony that year noted: "The province is defended by 3 strong forts, Fort

Figure 5.4 Map of Georgia, 1740.

Argyle, Fort St Andrew and Fort St Augustine [an obvious error]; but in 1741 [Georgia] did not contain more than 1,000 souls" (*Gentleman's Magazine* 1756, vol. 26:19; *Georgia Historical Quarterly* 1918:40). Another Ranger fort at Mount Pleasant was added in February. Patrick Tailfer, one of the 'Clamorous Malcontents', provides the following description of Fort Argyle published in 1741, "Twenty miles above this [Sterlings Fort]. on a high bluff on the same river, stands fort Argyle: it is a small square wooden fort, musket-proof. Ten families were settled here and about it; now all gone; and the fort itself garrisoned by one officer, one Dutch servant, and one woman, who were lately surprised in the officer's

absence, by two prisoners that broke out of the log-house in Savannah, and both murdered" (Tailfer et al. 1741: 257).

Another anonymous commentary on Georgia contained this description of Fort Argyle, "At the narrow passages [of the Ogeechee] is Fort Argyle, in a situation that commands all the province. This was built in the year 1733. It is a large, strong palisade, eleven feet high. with flankers and loop-holes for small cannon at the angles" (Anonymous 1840:180). Larry Ivers states that Fort Argyle's outworks were completely reconstructed by 1741, although the specific citation to support this reference was not located during our archival research. Ivers also noted that, "the earthen wall and moat, with a pallisade planted in the bottom were not repaired. The new wall was a stockade, eleven feet high and constructed with upright logs; it was higher, tighter and more substantial than a pallisade. Fireplaces and chimneys built of brick were built in the barracks and house" (Ivers 1974:148). Our research suggests that the major reconstruction at Argyle did not take place until 1742 or 1743.

In January of 1741, Oglethorpe wrote to the Earl of Egmont summarizing his recent engagements with the Spanish and the state of defenses in Georgia,

I ventured to keep up the Rangers. and strove to recruit them, also to get Boats and men and have manned a sloop...Fortifications we have none of any consideration, we could not Fortify during the peace, and I have had neither Funds or time to make any Considerable works since the first Forts were made either of Wood or Earth, and easily went to ruin, there being no Fund either from the King or the Trustees for Supporting them. However, at my own hazard I ventured to make an Intrenchment round the Town of Frederica, to make a Battery or two upon Jekyll sound, to repair the Fort at St. Andrews, and make another little one on the South End of that Island. but you may easily guess what poor Works those must be, which a Gentlemen is able to Answer out of his own Fortune (PC 14205(1):132-139).

In his "State of the Colony of Georgia", written on February 19, Thomas Causton stated, "at Fort Argyle (under proper Fortifications) are Lodged a Troop of twenty horse under a Captain and Lieutenant". Causton reiterated, "Fort Argyle is a Garison for the Lodge of 20 Rangers under a Captain and Lieutenant, there was at first 10 Freeholders under a Tythingman and allowed Support Equal to other Settlements" (PC 14205:326-327, 347-348). Thomas Causton noted that the fortifications and settlements that were built at Skidaway, Thunderbolt, Sterling's Bluff, and "Robert Williams and company" had been abandoned. At the Skidaway Narrows, Noble Jones maintained a small fort [Wormsloe]. A small fort at Augusta was garrisoned by a, "Captain, Lieutenant. Sergeant, a constable and 15 private men". Garrisons also were maintained at Darien and St Simons Island (PC 14205(2):189-220). Causton described the trail system that connected Old Ebenezer to Fort Argyle, "Their first Settlement [Old Ebenezer] was on the Common Path from the most usual Ferry, whereby Travellers passed by Land from South Carolina to these parts, and which also near this place meets the Path from Fort Argyle, and the Creek Nation" (PC 14205:215).

Thomas Causton further commented on the situation at Fort Argyle,

They had no Success in planting, and very probably gave too willing an Ear to an Opinion, that nothing but Slaves could raise anything worthy of the Labour. They either left their Settlements or entered into the Troop. The Fort is Scituate near the Common fording place used by the Creek Indians &c, from their Nation to Savannah or Carolina which is called the Lower path. The Troop was broke in the year 1738, But as its Scituation is of great Consequence, three persons keep possession, and it is to be hoped such another troop will be thought proper to answer the End of the former (PC 14205:209).

In early March 1741 Colonel Stephens wrote that Fort Argyle was garrisoned by only four Georgia Rangers and the fort was "breaking up for want of pay" (Warren 2015:113). On March 3, Stephens wrote in his journal,

Joseph Pevey, a Freeholder of this Town, at present employed as one of those that keep Garrison at Fort Argyle, coming hither this Morning, acquainted me, that he believed they were all breaking up there (which All was no more than Four) the time they being engaged for being near expired; and that I might expect the Boat with two of them from thence, soon after he got back, for that he came on Horseback, and was to return to-morrow. I asked him what was the Reason of such an unexpected Desertion; to which he answered, that he believed Laughlin McIntosh (who was chief) had wrote to the General at Frederica, somewhat or other which his Excellence was not well pleased with, probably concerning their Pay, &c. Mr. Hird being not gone out of Town, I understood that the General had declared, as to Fort Argyle, he would not concern himself about it, but that Col. St. (meaning me) might do what he pleased with it, either maintain it, or give it up, as he saw good; which Mr. Hird assured me, he heard the General say. This must needs appear very strange to me, who had no Power given me in my Commission, to intermeddle with any Forts or Garrisons, much less to dismantle them, if I thought fit: Could I then dare to do it? All that was in my Power therefore at present, was to ask Pevey, whether or not he was determined to quit with the rest, or would be content to stay there with one more, till I could know the General's Pleasure, and have his positive Orders (for I had often heard his Excellence declare, that no Orders from him were to be deemed valid, unless in Writing signed by him) and I was old enough to take Caution, not to exceed Orders, but to fulfill them only when I had them. Pevey engaged with me, that he and another of the four would abide there, and take the best care they could of every Thing, when the others were gone, till I had Instructions concerning it, upon my promise to see him paid for that Time, which I could not refuse him (CRG 4(Supp.):98-99).

The following day Stephens wrote, "Pevey returned to Fort Argyle, well satisfied; and Hird went off again for Frederica, by whom I wrote to the General, intreating to have his Directions what I was to do, relating to the Matter above-mentioned. Nothing observable that came to my Knowledge" (CRG 4(Supp.):99).

On March 18, Thomas Jones wrote from Savannah to Oglethorpe noting,

Lacklan Mackintosh is also at Savannah together with Greenfield, (another belonging to Fort Argyle) having left Pavy [Joseph Pevey] alone at the Fort – Yesterday in the Afternoon Mr. Jacob Mathews applied to the Bailiffs here for a Warrant to apprehend Pavy, on a Complaint set forth in the Deposition of Evans...The Bailiffs together with Col. Stephens met Mr. Mathews to consider of the matter, and were of the Opinion That it was not proper to apprehend Pavy and bring him away from the Fort, untill some others were gone thither to take care thereof, -- That it did not appear to us by Evans's Deposition, That Pavy was charged therein with any Criminal Act – Mr. Mathews was very much displeased, But upon Col. Stephens and my promise that we would send for Pavy to Savannah when Lacklan returned to the Fort, He seemed satisfied – I have paid Lacklan for himself and the other persons employ'd at the Fort, forty eight pounds twelve Shillings on Account (PC 14205:273).

On March 30, Stephens wrote in his journal of his receiving news from General Oglethorpe of an attack on Mr. [Mark] Carr's plantation by a "Party of Spanish Indians, from Augustin and those Parts". Oglethorpe had ordered Stephens to, "give immediate Notice to the People at Fort Argyle, and to Wiggins, with his Men at Mount-Pleasant, that they keep a good Look-out" (CRG 4(Supp.):117).

On April 18, Stephens wrote in his journal, "Lachlin McIntosh, one of those few stationed at Fort Argyle, also came to Town [Savannah] whose principal Errand was to get more Provisions" (CRG 4(Supp.):127). Lachlan McIntosh continued to command the nearly vacant Fort Argyle as late as April 18 and possibly throughout the rest of 1741 and the first two months of 1742.

In June, Ranger Pevey, who evidently had returned to Fort Argyle as Stephens had requested, wrote to Stephens that he and Harry Myers [probably Henry Myers] had heard suspicious talking in the Ogeechee River swamp: "either Deserters from the Army, or Runaway Negroes, by their Speech, which did not sound like the Indian" (PC 14206:17). On June 15, Stephens wrote in his journal, "A Messenger from Fort Argyle coming to inform us, that one of our Men there, being out on the Scout, a little Way from the Fort, had divers Shot made at him from among the Thickets, he knew not by whom; it was apprehended they must be some Spanish Indians strolling to do Mischief: Whereupon the Messenger was dispatch'd back, with necessary Instructions, to be upon their Guard, &c." (CRG 4(Supp.):166).

That same month, General Oglethorpe sent Isaac Young to purchase more horses for the Rangers, and Mark Carr's plantation near Jekyll Island was attacked by a party of Spanish Indians. General Oglethorpe sent orders, "to the People at Fort Argyle, and to the Wiggins [Thomas Wiggins], with his Men at Mount-Pleasant, that they keep a good Look-out" (CRG 4(Supp.):117). General Oglethorpe wrote to the Trustees and to the Duke of Newcastle in April urging them for the authority to raise additional forces, including two troops of Rangers composed of 60 men each. These Rangers were to guard the inland country (Duncan n.d.:409).

In July 1741, Captain Patrick Tailfer presented a pamphlet to the Earl of Egmont, which listed Fort Arguile, "where 10 families were settled, now all gone" (Warren 2015:122-125).

Thomas Jones commanded the Ranger troop at Argyle for a brief period. The history of Jones' command is obscure. This haze may be confounded by the presence of more than one Thomas Jones in Georgia during the Trustee period. Oglethorpe paid Thomas Jones and "a Party of Rangers" £11 5s for their services from January to June 1739, which was before Jones was stationed at Argyle. Oglethorpe also supported Jones and his Rangers at Fort Argyle from September 1741 to September 1743 (P.C. 14204(5):37L; BPRO, AO1/162/441, Box 1, 1-1-01).

5.11 1742

The prohibition against the sale of alcoholic spirits in Georgia was lifted during 1742, which was an event that probably brought a smile to many a Ranger's face. That same year also witnessed the resignation of Minister Robert Walpole and Lord Perceival, Earl of Egmont-two of Georgia's most ardent supporters (Spaulding 1984:145). The Duke of Newcastle replaced Walpole in dealing with Oglethorpe in matters of state, but the Duke paid little attention to the Georgia colony. When Oglethorpe wrote back to England in June, describing the troop strength of the Georgia and South Carolina forces under his command he noted that "small parties of Rangers" were stationed at Fort Argyle, Fort Augusta, Mount Pleasant, Mount Venture, and Ebenezer. Lieutenant Anthony Willey, a veteran Georgia Ranger who had served with Patrick McKay's Rangers and was later stationed on the Savannah River, fell victim to a self-inflicted gunshot. History does not record if Lieutenant Willey's death was suicide or an accident that occurred while cleaning his weapon (CRG 4 (Supp.):85; 33:465).

In June and July, Georgia was invaded by the Spanish at St. Simons Island. Facing a Spanish fleet of more than 38 ships with between 5,000-6,000 soldiers General Oglethorpe and his army, which numbered fewer than 1,000 men, were able to repulse the Spanish. The Georgia Rangers participated in several engagements on the island during that campaign (Wright 1867:299-319).

On March 29, 1742, James Oglethorpe appointed John Milledge, "to be Quarter master of the Troop of English rangers" (Oglethorpe 1742). This appointment marks the beginning of Milledge's command of the Georgia Rangers at Fort Argyle. Milledge arrived in Georgia on February 12, 1733, on the ship Ann. Two other passengers, William Calvert and William Greenfield (William Calvert's nephew) were on the same vessel and served at Fort Argyle (Temple and Coleman 1961: Appendix, pp 254-256).

On March 29, 1742, Oglethorpe wrote from Frederica to Harman Verelst regarding Oglethorpe's actions and expenditures in his failed campaign on Spanish Florida, in which he noted, "The case of the Rangers and the Highland Company is much the same. I therefore ordered all to be recruited: the full establishment made a saving which is the fund for defraying the charge of the recruits" and, "Besides the regular troops it was absolutely necessary to keep up the two troops of Rangers raised for the siege of St. Augustine, also the Highland Company and the company of boatmen as well as garrisons at Fort Augusta, at Mount Pleasant, at Mount Venture, and fortify different places" (Shaw 1903:22-33).

In May Reverend Boltzius of New Ebenezer noted that "one of General Oglethorpe's soldiers (who must reconnoiter the woods between Fort Argyle and Old Ebenezer) came to me to fetch a letter for the general". He added that this was done regularly on the first day of every month. For the New Ebenezer

Rangers May was uneventful, as illustrated by Boltzius' comment that Thomas Bichler, commander of their Rangers, was able to continue his milling and be a Ranger. Boltzius explained this dual role as a result of there being, "little to do in that office (as commander of the Ebenezer Rangers), except if extraordinary steps would have to be taken to remove enemies such as Spaniards, Negroes, deserters, and other nefarious people who molest our place" (Jones 1988: 99, 121).

On June 26 a large Spanish fleet sailed into St. Simon's harbor landing on Cumberland Island, where the Spanish troops prepared for attack on St. Simon's Island. General Oglethorpe quickly responded by sending a force including about 700 soldiers, Highlanders, Captain Carr's Marine Rangers, Indians, and two troops of Georgia Rangers. The Georgia Rangers came from several posts, almost certainly including Rangers from Argyle, to defend the island. The garrison on the south end of the island was moved to Frederica and the cannons that defended their barracks at Fort St Simons were spiked to render them useless. The Spanish landed on the south end of St. Simon's Island and established themselves in the abandoned fort. The Spanish planned an attack on the town of Frederica, but before reaching the town they were surprised by Oglethorpe's Highland Rangers and the attack on the town was thwarted. The battles of Bloody Marsh and Gully Hole Creek resulted, which began on July 7 (Seibert 2019). Despite their superior troop strength and fire power, Oglethorpe successfully turned away the Spanish threat from Georgia's shores. By mid-July reinforcements including more than 600 men and 140 large guns under the command of Colonel Vander Dussen, set sail from South Carolina to St. Simon's Island to join with the Georgia troops. They were too late to be of any service. Oglethorpe was outraged at South Carolina's tardiness and he expressed his displeasure to those in England. Later that month John Milledge delivered an express account by Oglethorpe of skirmishing near St. Augustine. The message was sent from Savannah via Darien to Frederica (Rolt 1749; *South Carolina Gazette*, July 12. 1742; July 19. 1742; July 26, 1742; Duncan n.d:409; CRG 35:528).

Captain Thomas Wiggins, commander of the Georgia Rangers at Mount Pleasant, died in July and John Milledge was promoted to Lieutenant of Wiggins' Ranger Troop. Oglethorpe sensed the need to strengthen the southern defenses against another Spanish attack and he sent carpenters and smiths to aid in improving Fort Argyle. This reconstruction began after September and was completed by the following year. Oglethorpe raised another Ranger troop by July 30, which was garrisoned at Mt. Venture. This fort was located on the Altamaha River near the forks of the Oconee and Ocmulgee Rivers. Its first commander was Captain Jacob Matthews and William Francis was his lieutenant. Matthews died soon after he arrived. Richard Scruggs, who was Thomas Wiggins' former Lieutenant, was made captain of the post.

Lieutenant William Francis was formerly a Ranger at Fort Argyle from 1738 to 1741. He had actual command of Fort Mount Venture in November 1742 when that ranger fort met with major misfortune—namely the nearly complete massacre of the outpost by Spanish-allied Yamassees, which Jonathan Debell described:

This day is the 30th of Novemr. 1742 Last Thursday the 26th. Mr Stephens received from Genl. Oglethorpe the Melancholy Acct. of a Fort called Fort Venture about 60 Miles distant from Frederica being destroyed by the Spanish Indians. That the[y] murderd the Wife & Child of Wm.

Francis the Commander & Two of the Men and took the rest prisoners (tis said Wm Francis was at Frederica, and that Six Men, his wife & Child were in the Fort) one of which was an Indian Slave. This Indian as soon as he was taken began to leap arid rejoice for Joy that he was fallen into the hands of the Spanish Indians, telling them that the English had dealt Cruelly with him, by this be gained much liberty and they permitted, or sent him to Hunt for them: by this means he gave clear, and came safe to Frederica, being the only one that Escaped. He says the No of Spanish Indians which he saw were but 15. That their Design according to their Instructions from the Govr of St Augustine, was against the Darian, but that they made this in their way. We have great reason to fear that 2 Men more if not the Four were afterwards destroyed (CRG 23:437-438).

Other descriptions of the massacre at Fort Mount Venture were provided by Reverend Boltzius at Ebenezer, who was informed of the event on November 27 by two of Milledge's rangers, and a published account in the December 13 edition of the *South Carolina Gazette* (1742).

The massacre at Fort Mount Venture remained in the minds of the Brits, as evidenced by a 1760 essay published in London (*The London Magazine, Or, Gentleman's Monthly Intelligencer* 1760, vol. 29:279; *The London Chronicle* 1760, vol. 8:10). That story described how the fort, which was "about 96 miles from Savannah", had been built, "to protect the Indian traders, and keep the communication open for the friendly savages". It also referred to Mr. Francis, a brave and honest officer of Rangers", who had commanded the garrison.

Although Fort Mount Venture was rebuilt and continued to function as a ranger fort until at least 1759, Fort Argyle gained importance after its 1742 attack (CRG 5:657; Duncan n.d.:410). On November 18, General Oglethorpe appointed John Milledge as Captain of the 20 Rangers at Fort Argyle (Warren 2015:151, 163). The Earl of Egmont noted in his journal "Fort Argulie strengthened by 20 Rangers under command of John Milledge by Gen. Oglthorpe". Milledge remained as commander of Fort Argyle for the next five years and he served as an exceptionally good officer (CRG 5:657; Ivers 1974: 143, 148-149, 186).

The troop strength of the Georgia Rangers by December was just under 100 men and approximately one-fifth were stationed at Fort Argyle. Oglethorpe summarized, "The little Forts Argyle, Augusta. Mount Pleasant, Mount Venture and Ebenezer are dispersed on all the passages by which the communication is kept open with Carolina and Virginia as also the Indian Nation. The Rangers have also drove to us Large Gangs of cattle for Provisions-very Lately a party of them went and came again as far as Virginia by Land and fetched Horses and Recruits for the Rangers from thence as they can easily Augment though men are scarce in America. I have ordered them to do so. Five men were ordered to Argyle at that time to augment the 20 that were already present" (CRG 35:556-558). The Georgia Rangers were distributed as shown in Table 5.2.

As tensions mounted from the threat of Spanish attack in 1742, the minutes of William Stephens and his assistants record that many women sought refuge at Fort Argyle and that they, "were got with great Difficulty and in deep Distress to Fort Argyle, where providentially they found Provisions to refresh and

Table 5.2 Distribution of Georgia Rangers by Fort in 1742.

<u>Fort</u>	<u>Rangers</u>
Argyle	20
Augusta	20
Mount Pleasant	13
Mount Venture	20
Ebenezer	20
TOTAL	93

(CRG 35:556-558)

support them for a few Days; But it being necessary to pursue some Method for their farther Support; It was resolved to send a Boat to Fort Argyle, and convey them to the Orphan House, where we could more conveniently and with less Charge provide for them. Mr Habersham having removed all the People from thence to Mr Hugh Bryans in Carolina" (CRG 6:40-41).

Meanwhile, back in England, General Oglethorpe was not without his detractors. Lieutenant Colonel Cook addressed the Treasury Chambers at Whitehall, London on August 19, 1742. An abstract of his address states that Cook,

Acquaints my Lords that General Oglethorpe has a sloop and a schooner to cruise, about 7 men called Rangers, never saw any more, never saw them on horseback; the General sent to Virginia and listed some men; kept them at C.'s Plantation cutting wood. Takes the money employed to be [Georgia] Trustee's money. A fort built on the South of Cumberland [Island], whole expense of it about 70l. [70 pounds], the expense of repairing another about 12l. [12 pounds], another at his coming away about 340l. [340 pounds] The most that has been laid out in forts is about 500l. [500 pounds] The General has said there are a good many more than the 7 Rangers. The garrison of Fort Argyle consisted of an old Dutchman and a servant maid. Some of the regiments always went on board the sloop; 17 sailors and a master only employed. General Oglethorpe gives the commissions and sends over officers to recruit. Are clothed very poorly; three clothings since they went. The bedding has never been issued and is eaten up by vermin in the stores (Shaw 2010:69).

5.12 1743

The war between England and Spain continued to rage during 1743. Although France had not yet officially entered the fray, the French suffered a defeat by the English, losing 5,000 men compared to 3,000 British. At the German village of Dettingen, King George II led the charge marking the last time a royal monarch was directly involved in battle. War also broke out between the Creek and the Cherokee during June of that year. General Oglethorpe mounted a series of small-scale offensives against Spanish Florida during the late winter and spring as recounted by Edward Kimber, a soldier in Oglethorpe's regiment. Kimber noted that a detachment, which included Rangers, left Frederica for Florida in February. None of the officers on the mission were Rangers. He also noted that a few Rangers were settled on Jekyll Island at that time. Kimber mentioned that, in March, "the Rangers and their horses" were ferried over the St John's River. The *South Carolina Gazette* reported that the 1743 invasion had minimal effect other than

"alarming the Spaniards". Captain John Barnard was appointed commander of the Ranger garrison at Mount Pleasant in March of that year making him Lieutenant John Milledge's new commanding officer (Kimber 1976:6-7, 28; *South Carolina Gazette*, April 18, 1743; Sonderegger 1964:225; Cole and Priestley 1936:57-58; Duncan n.d.:410).

Unimpressed with Oglethorpe's progress or the way that their moneys were being spent, the Trustees sent word to William Stephens through their secretary Benjamin Martyn on May 10, 1743 stating that "they positively direct, that for the future no Charges relating to Fort Argyle be paid for by them, for they have nothing to do with the supporting any Fort in the Province." The Georgia establishment for Rangers was to be ended 24 December 1743. The payroll for the two Georgia Ranger troops, consisting of 140 men, for that year was £4,215. Oglethorpe issued temporary orders until new orders arrived from England, since no financial provisions were made for the Rangers. Fortunately repairs to Fort Argyle and other forts were completed at Oglethorpe's personal expense by September 1743. Oglethorpe traveled to England in July 1743 and while there he recruited additional men to serve as Scouts and Rangers for the Regiment. However, before General Oglethorpe could return to Georgia, he and his recruits were diverted to deal with the Jacobite uprising of 1745 (Clark 1983: xii, xxi, 973; CRG 2:235).

After sailing for England in 1743, James Oglethorpe never returned to America and he no longer directed the military activities at Fort Argyle or Georgia. Back in Georgia, Lieutenant Colonel William Horton assumed command of the Southern District, while William Stephens governed the Northern District. Fort Argyle fell somewhere in between these two jurisdictions geographically, but most likely it was included in the Northern District (CRG 30:282; 36:217; Manucy 1959:116, 121; Sonderegger 1964:226).

5.13 1744

In March 1744, France declared war on Great Britain and Hanover, followed in May by a declaration of war on Austria, making it truly a world war. The French had raised more than 80,000 troops by April. By 1744 the garrison of Rangers at Fort Augusta had nearly doubled. The exact size of the Argyle garrison during this period is not known, but it probably experienced a buildup as well (Ivers 1986:79; Anderson 1995:225). Meanwhile, the Rangers at Argyle busied themselves with domestic affairs. Reverend Boltzius noted in his diary that spring, "Our Rangers will bring these letters on the first of June to Old Ebenezer and from there to Frederica via Ft. Argyle" (Jones 1993:75) and in another entry he added: "Some Negroes [apparently runaways from South Carolina en route to safe haven in Spanish Florida] have been brought from Fort Argyle to Savannah, but then they were sent on to Frederica as prisoners, since the people there did not wish to give the reward he expected" (Jones 1993:50).

The threat from runaway slaves from South Carolina and Spanish prisoners continued to support the need for Fort Argyle and other frontier forts. In addition, the danger from Spanish-allied Indians had not diminished. For example, one of the townspeople in Frederica wrote of an engagement between the Georgia Rangers commanded by Lieutenant William Francis, and Yamasee Indians that took place in coastal Georgia in January 1744 (*The Pennsylvania Gazette* 1744:2-3). All these frontier menaces proved enough for continued funding and in May, Parliament authorized funds exceeding £19,167 Sterling, "For two Troops and one Company of Highland Rangers in Georgia, 19,167 l. 18 s. 4 d." (*Newcastle Courant* 1744:3).

On December 18, 1744 the Treasury Office in London read a petition from General Oglethorpe requesting payment for his, "extraordinary services in Georgia from 1738, Sept. 22, to 1743, Sept. 29. As to the extraordinaries since that time, had given credit to the Commander in Chief there to draw upon him to the amount of 19,168l. 18s. 4d., voted by Parliament for rangers, Highland Company, boatmen and half galleys; which services are of such a nature that no regular establishment can be made, being only paid as real necessity required, and are within the sum voted. Therefore prays that said sum be issued to him upon account", and Oglethorpe's petition was referred to the Treasury Chambers that day for the Auditor of Imprests for, "his opinion whether my Lords can issue that sum upon an estimate, there being no establishment" (Shaw 1903:537-543).

5.14 1745

In May 1745 the English were defeated by the French at Fontenoy, southwest of Belgium, with about 6,000 British soldiers killed or wounded. A rebellion of Jacobites, known as the Forty-Five's, was mounted in Scotland by Bonnie Prince Charles Edward Stuart and his supporters in July. James Oglethorpe, who was promoted to the rank of Major General in March 1745, was pulled into quelling this Jacobite Uprising. General Oglethorpe was in England recruiting soldiers for his Georgia Rangers at the time. The new recruits were already on board the ship *HMS Success*, which was bound for Georgia, when they were diverted to Hull, England. They joined General Wade's army in Newcastle on October 25, where they were ordered to assist in putting down the rebellion. After a three-day march that covered about 100 miles the Georgia Rangers arrived at Preston near the Scottish Lowlands on December 17, about four hours after the Jacobite rebels had left the town. The Rangers were soon joined by the Duke of Kingston's Horse under Lt. Col. Mordaunt and on the following day by General Oglethorpe. Upon rejoining his troops in Preston, Oglethorpe ordered the Georgia Rangers to pursue the rebels. At Lancaster, an advance group of about 12 Rangers were surprised by the rebels and one Ranger was shot and two were taken prisoner. The Georgia Rangers fought again at a battle at Clifton Moor on December 18, where more than 100 British were killed or wounded and the British troops retreated (Wright 1867:354; Wright 1867:355-356; *Scots Magazine* 1745a, vol. 7:575-577; *The Gentleman's Magazine, and Historical Chronicle* 1745:624; Henderson 1753:183-186; Royle 2016:53-57). The Jacobite uprising was put down at the battle of Culloden and the British throne made secure. Ironically, these newly recruited Georgia Rangers who fought and many of whom died in the campaign against the Jacobites in the English-Scottish borderlands probably never saw military service in Georgia, as detailed later below.

On April 18, The Treasury Office in London discussed Thomas Marriott's appointment as agent for Georgia and discussed financial matters stating,

My Lords observing that in the establishment of the troops of Rangers, Highland Companies, &c., in Georgia, commencing from the 30th of September, 1743, inclusive, no regulation is made of what proportion thereof is to be paid for subsistence as in other establishments of the forces; and my Lords apprehending that the said services have not yet been compleated, their Lordships order a letter to be writ to the Paymaster General that he issue at present to the agent of the said forces only such part of the amount of the said establishment as he shall be satisfied has been actually expended (Shaw 1903:679-686).

In July the Treasury Lords and Lords Justices in London signed a warrant, "directing the establishment of rangers, Highland Company, boatmen, officers and men, and schooners, &c., in Georgia, to commence from 1744, Sept. 30" (Shaw 1903:699-708). Meanwhile in Georgia, the troop strength of Oglethorpe's Regiment totaled 1,146 soldiers comprised of 804 men in Georgia and 342 men organized into three independent companies in South Carolina. The pacifistic Moravians, or Hernhutters as they were often referred to, who were among the earliest land grant recipients on the Ogeechee River near Fort Argyle, had all left Georgia by the end of the year (Anderson 1995:226; Cole and Priestley 1936:58-69; Callaway 1948:25; Fries 1967; Lewis 1954:69).

John Milledge petitioned to William Stephens and his assistants in January for a grant of 500 acres, "about a Mile below the said Fort [Argyle] on the North Side of the River Ogeechee". The Georgia Trustees confirmed this grant on January 7, 1745 (Warren 2015:171). Since Milledge already possessed a town lot and fifty acres in Savannah, the request was not immediately issued, although the Trustees agreed to grant him the land if he relinquished his town lot in Savannah. His petitions record that while in command of the Fort Argyle garrison, Milledge had made improvements on the requested tract of land. Milledge was later granted land above Fort Argyle on the south side of the Ogeechee River (CRG 1:494; 2:279; 6:125).

The Rangers on the Ogeechee River continued to serve as couriers and perform non-military tasks. That spring Reverend Boltzius at Ebenezer mentioned the arrival of a shipment of hemp seed, which, "he [Captain Williams] will probably send me a little sack full at the first opportunity to a certain fort between Savannah and Frederica, from which it can be brought to Savannah in a few hours" (Jones DR 1745 18:210). Reverend Boltzius wrote in March,

A captain of the Rangers on the Ogeechee River sent his boat here to buy twenty bushels of corn and have them ground, and this will be permitted him. He wishes to establish a town on the said river with some people brought from Virginia; and he told me that he had seen a very beautiful region that he would gladly grant to our people if I would send some of them to visit it. However, I sent him word that we did not desire any more land, certainly not so remote (Jones DR 1745, 18:207).

The Captain that Reverend Boltzius referred to was probably John Williams, commander of William's Fort at Sansavilla Bluff on the Altamaha River, rather than Captain Milledge. The exact relationship of Williams' ranger troop with the garrison at Fort Argyle remains unclear.

Parliament authorized grants in 1745 of £23,961 2 shillings and 11 pence for, "two troops rangers, a highland company, boatmen, and half-galleys or schooners, for the service of Georgia, from Sept. 30, 1744 to Dec. 24, 1745" (*The Scots Magazine* 1745b:197).

5.15 1746

The year 1746 was relatively quiet despite the continuance of the war. In July, Phillip V of Spain died. He was succeeded by Ferdinand VI. The wearing of tartans was outlawed in Great Britain. Meanwhile in

the American colonies, despite regulations to the contrary, plantation owners in Georgia were importing slaves. No activity was recorded at Fort Argyle, although the Rangers were still on the job (Grun 1991:345; Reese 1963:49). Great Britain's War Office presented an "Estimate of the Charge of Two Troops of Rangers, a Highland Company, Boatmen, Half-Gallies or Schooners, for the Service of Georgia, for the Year 1746" to the House of Commons in Parliament on January 16, 1746 (Great Britain, Parliament, House of Commons 1746, Volume 25:33). On June 16, Parliament granted £19,168, 18 shillings and 4 pence for this purpose (*The Scots Magazine* 1746a: 417).

Remaining unpaid bills from 1746 were submitted on March 17, 1747 by John Milledge to the British government for repayment, which included:

	<u>f. s. d.</u>
Remainder of a Bill to John Milledge, for [£]182. 7. 10 ½.	52 7 10 ½
Do of a Do to Do, for 31. 13. 7.	21 2 5
Do of a Do to Do, for 25.	16 13 4
Do of a Do to Do, for 34. 12. 7 ½ .	23 1 9 ½

(Great Britain, Parliament, House of Commons 1803:881).

In late August 1746, a General Court Martial began, "to enquire into the Conduct, Behaviour and proceedings of Major General Oglethorpe at or near Shap" (Terry 1902, Vol. 1:168). These charges were made in response to Oglethorpe's actions in the engagement at Clifton Moor on December 18, 1745 (*Scots Magazine* 1746b, vol. 8:498). General Oglethorpe was honorably acquitted of the charges against him on October 7, 1746. This inconvenience in the affairs of Oglethorpe undoubtedly was partially responsible for his failing to return to Georgia. In addition, Oglethorpe suffered from fever, which also may have contributed to his lack of return to Georgia, as noted in a letter that he wrote on March 11, 1747, "having had a return of my fever has prevented my waiting upon you" (Wright 1867:362). The plight of the new Georgia Ranger recruits is unclear. The HMS *Success*, which was the ship on which they had intended to travel to Georgia, remained "for a considerable time at Hull", and the Georgia recruits, "guarded the rebels in York Castle" (Wright 1867:362). The *Success* never did sail for Georgia and Oglethorpe's newly recruited Georgia Rangers probably never served on Georgia soil (Great Britain, Parliament, House of Commons 1803:887).

5.16 1747

The year 1747 saw upheavals in the Rangers across the entire Georgia colony. In June only 10 soldiers were active in Georgia. Lieutenant Colonel Alexander Heron returned to Frederica from England that month and assumed command of the 42nd Regiment. John Milledge and the Rangers at Fort Argyle were paid slightly more than £58 for their services for January through June 1747. Although the British suffered a major loss of 2,000 soldiers at Lauffeld in July 1747, Great Britain was near a peace settlement with Spain and King George II ordered the British troops in Georgia disbanded. In July, Colonel William Horton wrote to Reverend Bosomworth that the Rangers were "dismissed and no money allocated by Parliament for their support". John Milledge 's command at Fort Argyle was officially terminated, although he and his fellow Rangers probably continued to protect the area since many had families and farms in the vicinity. Certificates were submitted to the British government on August 7, 1749 for goods or services provided to Midsummer 1747, which included:

Certificate to John Milledge	[£] 74 9 10	[John] Nickleson.
Do [Ditto]	38 16 5	Do.
Do	21 10 11	
Do	6 11 10	

(Great Britain, Parliament, House of Commons 1803:883).

After an audit of the account submitted from Georgia on December 19, 1753, the British government authorized the payment for:

	Per Diem.	Per Annum.
	£. s. d.	£. s. d.
Two Troops of Rangers.		
Two Troops of Rangers, Captain-----	0 7 0	127 15 0
Two Lieutenants -----	0 8 0	146 0 0
Cornet -----	0 3 0	54 15 0
Consisting of 60 Four Quartermasters, each 2 s.	0 8 0	146 0 0
Private Men in Two French Horns, each 2 s.	0 4 0	73 0 0
60 Private Men, each 40s. per Month--	1,560 0 0	
In all 140 Men,	2,107 10 0	

Officers included:	One Troop more of the same Number and Rates	
	As the above-mentioned Troop	2,107 10 0
	Total of Two Troops	4,215 0 0

(Great Britain, Parliament, House of Commons 1803:889).

Colonel Horton considered himself responsible for moneys and bills that he paid out for the Ranger's salaries. If the Rangers at Fort Argyle continued to exist as a body from August 1747 to September 1756, they did so without pay (Cole and Priestley 1936:63; Johnson 1992:12; Barnwell 1927:141-168; CRG 36:296; Ivers 1974:205). Reverend Boltzius deeply regretted the dismissal of the Rangers at Ebenezer, and he reminisced in June of that year, "Before our rangers were stationed here, we had all sorts of difficulties with vagrants and riff-raff living in our woods. At night they came out and stole things and probably shot some pigs. Afterwards, we were not disturbed by either Negroes nor other runaways" (Jones 1989a:77).

On September 13, Major General Oglethorpe was promoted to the rank of Lieutenant General in the British Army (Wright 1867:362). While his strength had returned and he was frequently in attendance in the House of Commons, he never returned to Georgia. He continued to issue commands to the troops in Georgia; albeit now from his estate in England.

Cartographer Emanuel Bowen published a map of southeastern North America in 1747. A portion of that map, showing Fort Argyle, is reproduced in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5 Emanuel Bowen 1747 Map of the Southeast, Showing Fort Argyle (Bowen 1748).

5.17 1748

The year 1748 began as a dark one for British subjects in Georgia and South Carolina, as it appeared that all government support for their defense was gone. This left Georgia's colonists at the mercy of hostile French powers. However, King George's War ended before the year was over with peace being negotiated by the treaty at Aix-la-Chapelle. Peace negotiations began in March and were concluded in October. Realizing the vulnerability of Georgia to enemy attack, General Oglethorpe issued orders in May, which were delivered in August to Alexander Heron. He ordered Heron to garrison the frontier forts with the regular soldiers. The General's order read: "You are to send Captain George Dunbar's Compy to Darien who are to Remain there in Garrison, and detachment to be sent to Fort Argyle if it is in a condition to receive them, from that compy". No Rangers were on the payroll in Georgia during 1748. Nor has any documentary evidence been found to confirm that any of Captain Dunbar's Regulars were stationed at Argyle as a result of Oglethorpe's orders (CRG 36:402; Stanhope 1858, v. 2:57, 208; Anderson 1995:227). Ivers suspects that the troops were not sent because of the poor condition of the fort and, "the old ranger fortification continued to decay without a garrison" (CRG 36:402; Ivers 1974:206).

The British subjects in South Carolina also were concerned that their western and southern flanks were unprotected. A Petition to the Duke of Newcastle, signed by more than 100 landholders of St. Johns, St.

Helena, and Prince William parishes, was submitted in March. The Petition expressed concern at the disbanding of the troops in the province and provided these statements regarding the Rangers,

that your Petitioners having lately been informed that no Estimate of the Expense of two Troops of Rangers, Highland Company, Boatmen, Half Gallies, or Schooners for the Service of Georgia for the Present year, will be laid before Parliament. We think the Duty we owe to his Majesty calls upon us to lay before your Grace the great Dangers to which not only the Colony of Georgia but also this Province and more Particularly the Southern parts of it will be exposed by the Dismission of these Forces especially during the War with France and Spain.

We Humbly beg leave to Represent to your Grace, that if the several Forts which are Built on the Rivers Savannah and Ogechee [Ogechee] and which are garrison'd by these Troops are abandon'd that the Inhabitants of the Northern parts of Georgia will be so much exposed to the Insults of the Indians that they will be obliged to quit their Habitations and to remove into some other Country under less Melancholly circumstances than it appears to us to be in from the Reduction of these Forces. In that Case, My Lord the Southern Frontier of this Province would lye open to the Incursions and Ravages of the Indians.

Whereas whilst the Rangers in Georgia are Supported they not only serve to Keep the Indians in Obedience to His Majesty, but should they be influenced by the French to turn their Arms against His Majestys Subjects We should not only have notice of the motions of all the Partys from the Commanding officer of the Forts, but the Rangers would Harrass them in their Marches and greatly contribute to the Safety of his His Majestys Province and of his Loyal and faithful Subjects (BPRO, SCDAH, A&WI, v. 23:88-98).

Another copy of their petition contained slightly different wording, but the only significant addition regarding the Rangers was, "That those Forts and the Rangers have greatly contributed towards preserving the Peace between his Majesty's Subjects and the Indians and should the French Influence so far prevail (as it has very lately like to have done with the Indians as to turn their Against us, those Forts and Rangers would not only give the Inhabitant of this Province timely notice of the Motions of all their Partys, but prevent their Incursions into this Province on that side as they would dread to be intercepted in their Retreat" (BPRO, SCDAH, v. 23:88-98).

5.18 1749

During 1749 the British established a fortress at Halifax, Nova Scotia and tightened its grip on North America. On May 9 the British 42nd Regiment left Georgia, leaving the colony without an army. During their departure on May 29, Alexander Heron compiled a list of vessels and boats in Georgia belonging to the King and unfit for service, which noted that the, "Garrison Boat at Fort Argyle [was] never delivered by Mr. Milledge". Apparently Milledge's Rangers at Argyle had a pressing need for the boat. A group of Native Americans, supporting the claims of the Bosomworths, threatened to attack Savannah in late July but their advance was stopped by Captain Noble Jones and his Troop of Horse Militia. There were no Rangers on the payroll in Georgia during 1749, although historian Duncan contends that they remained active that year (Grun 1991:344; Duncan n.d.:411; CRG 25:468; Davis 1982:139).

The minutes of Governor William Stephens and his assistants in August contain references to talks with the Creek Chief Melatchee and his party and they note that, "the Interpreter came from the Chiefs requiring a quantity of Provisions to be Sent to Fort Argyle, to their followers, Women and Children for their Subsistence, until they came to Town; accordingly two Men with Horses were sent there with what was necessary for that purpose". Melatchee's followers apparently continued to remain at Fort Argyle and receive provisions from the government during November, as noted by the trader John Kinnard (CRG 6:258, 295; 25:460).

5.19 1750

In March 1750 George Cadogan wrote to South Carolina Governor Glen from Fort Moore, "I have also been informed that a large Body of Creeks are again gone against the Cherokees, that a Body of the Cherokees are come this Way against the Uchees and another Body of Notewas and Cherokees are set out to attach all, the Creeks, on the Ogeechey River at a Place called the Forks" (McDowell 1992b:11). Cadogan's warning must have caused alarm among Georgians living on the lower Ogeechee River. There were no Rangers on the payroll in Georgia that year. Although no official activity was recorded at Fort Argyle, John Milledge continued to be active in the area. He petitioned and received 400 acres on the Little Ogeechee River in October, where he referred to the disbanding of the Ranger troop by saying, "the Provincial Troops being broke". The board reviewing his petition noted that Milledge, "has at all Times appeared peculiarly Active to serve the Colony, whenever required, especially in all Disturbances with the Indians, being a good Horseman and well acquainted with the Woods". The minutes of President Stephens for July 25 record that John Milledge and others complained that they, "have received considerable Damage by Malatche and his People in their return to the Nation last August, the former [Milledge] setting forth, that they had killed in the Presence of his Servants Six Steers on Ogechee River, besides other Damages done in and about his House" (CRG 6:328, 344).

Melatchee was a ranking Creek chief of the mid-eighteenth century and he had been a strong ally of General Oglethorpe during most of the Trustee period. Milledge's complaints about him reflect the growing sentiment that the allegiance of the Creeks to the British crown was beginning to waiver. Possibly Milledge's attitude as well as that of other Georgians toward the Creeks also was beginning to change. Conflicts over land use developed as the region continued to welcome new European settlers. As the population increased, friction rose between the Creek hunters and Euro-American farmers and ranchers along the Ogeechee River. Furthermore, as settlers made improvements to their lands they had more to lose from the frequent trespasses by the Creeks.

That August Parliament repealed the ban against slaves in Georgia, but this was a moot point as slaves were already present throughout the colony (Reese 1963:49). While no slaves are documented at Fort Argyle, many of the officers owned slaves. Slaves would have almost certainly provided labor for any major rebuilding efforts at Argyle after 1750.

5.20 1751

In England, January 1 was officially declared the beginning of the new year-replacing the older calendrical system. Henry Parker replaced William Stephens as president of the colony. Parker served in this capacity for two years. The Spanish made additional improvements on their defenses at St Augustine. In the South Carolina Piedmont, the Cherokee were raiding plantations on the Saluda River and Governor Glen commissioned two small Ranger troops to patrol the Cherokee boundary. No activity was recorded at Argyle, and there were no Rangers on the official payroll (Grun 1991:347; McDowell 1992b:29.42-43, 48).

In April the Trustees recommended the formation of a militia in Georgia. Fort Argyle may have been garrisoned by militia on a sporadic basis after that date. The Militia Act required all those who owned 300 acres or more to appear fully provisioned on horseback as cavalry; and those with less property were to appear armed on foot. However, the fact that Fort Argyle is rarely mentioned in the colonial records from 1748 to 1756 tends to suggest that the fort was not used by the militia to any great extent (Duncan n.d.: 411).

On June 23 the Georgia Trustees relinquished the remaining year of their 20-year charter to King George II. Although most considered the Trustees experiment in Georgia a failure, the Trustees were able to successfully direct the Georgia colony through two crucial decades in its history. For the next two years Georgia was without a formal governing body. During this interim some military decisions were made by South Carolina (Coleman 1960:11).

In October, William Gerard DeBrahm arrived in Georgia with a colony of Swabians who settled at Bethany on the Savannah River. DeBrahm had been a military engineer in Europe and was appointed His Majesty's Surveyor of the Southern colonies. DeBrahm had a bright military mind and he aggressively promoted his plan to strengthen the forts throughout the region. Throughout his career he drafted many fort plans, including those for Charleston, Fort Johnson, and Prince George, South Carolina; New Ebenezer, Savannah, and Forts Barrington and George (Cockspur), Georgia; and Fort Loudoun in present-day Tennessee. Fort Argyle must not have appealed to DeBrahm as an important defensive location, since he did not mention the fort in his writings and made no plan for its defenses (Jones 1986; DeVorse 1971).

5.21 1752

A powerful hurricane, described as "the most violent and terrible ever was felt in this province" struck Charleston on September 14 and 15, 1752 causing extensive damage and its effects extended into eastern Georgia (*The South Carolina Gazette*, September 19, 1752:1; Grun 1991:346; Mercantini 2002:351-365). The storm likely caused no major damage at Fort Argyle. No Rangers were on the payroll in Georgia and Fort Argyle was not mentioned in the colonial records during 1752. Cartographer Emanuel Bowen published a map of the colonial Southeast. A portion of his map that shows Fort Argyle and its surroundings is reproduced in Figure 5.6.

Figure 5.6 Portion of Emanuel Bowen's later 1752 Map Showing Fort Argyle Vicinity (Bowen 1752).

5.22 1753

By 1753, Great Britain prepared for war against France, while activity at Fort Argyle was negligible. Meanwhile, French troops from Canada moved to seize control of the Ohio valley. Patrick Graham served as President of the Georgia colony in 1753 and the first part of 1754. In March, John Milledge was one of several appointed by an Act of legislature to be "Surveyors of the Highways" for the Southwest District, which included Fort Argyle (Stanhope 1858, v. 4:72; Grun 1991:346; CRG 18:89). No Rangers were on the payroll in Georgia and Fort Argyle was not mentioned in the colonial records during 1753.

5.23 1754

By 1754 the English and French were unofficially at war in North America, although Georgia had not yet entered the action. Both sides were seeking to establish their territorial boundaries in the most advantageous manner. Virginia's Statehouse appropriated £10,000 for an expedition against the French in the interior. George Washington's troops defeated the French in one of the first military engagements, and the British built Fort Necessity in present-day southwestern Pennsylvania, where the young commander George Washington was defeated by the French. Great Britain established a Royal government in Georgia and appointed Captain John Reynolds as its governor. There were no Rangers on the King's payroll in Georgia in 1754, and no record of activity at Fort Argyle was found for that year. However, a few dozen miles downstream from Argyle, 45 residents submitted an address to the Council in February requesting that a town be established "upon the Elbow on the great Ogechee River". This

was the beginning of Hardwick-later to become another of Georgia's "Dead Towns" (Schwartz 1994:21; Coleman 1960:12).

5.24 1755

A British defeat in 1755 served as a prelude to the Seven Years' War, which in America was later called the French and Indian War. General Braddock arrived in Virginia with a plan to defeat the French. In July, Braddock was defeated near Fort Duquesne on the Ohio River (present-day Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania) and the Major General was killed in action. The British rebounded in September with a victory at Lake George. The number of British soldiers worldwide was estimated at 51,000 men in December 1755. There were no Rangers on the payroll in Georgia in 1755, and Fort Argyle was largely forgotten (Anonymous 1972:20, 40, 51, 138).

An Act signed into law by Governor Reynolds on January 24 provided for the regulation of the militia in Georgia and for the defense of the colony. In April the town of Hardwick, originally named Georgetown, was established on the Ogeechee River. It was located at the "Elbow", today known as Seven Mile Bend, downstream from Fort Argyle. Hardwick was originally intended to be the capital city of the colony, replacing Savannah in this capacity, but it never achieved this status. The town consisted of 610 town lots that were not all occupied (CRG 6:423; 7:159-169; Duncan n.d:420).

By 1755 approximately 40 families from North Carolina and Virginia were squatters in the upper Ogeechee River valley. Their presence in the Creek's hunting lands greatly upset the Creeks who threatened retaliatory action (Stanhope 1858, v. 4:47; Grun 1991:348; Schwartz 1994:35-36; Bryan County Historical Society 1986:7; Middleton 1989:227; McDowell 1992a:67, 187).

Summarizing the British defenses in a book published that year, one anonymous writer briefly noted: "lower down [below Charleston] we find a few poor ones [forts] in Georgia, the southern frontier of the British territories", including Forts Moore and Augusta, which were, "not so well built, and are worse planned" (Anonymous 1972 [Reprint of 1755 edition]). Georgia was not paramount in the military minds of those charged with establishing British control of North America. Most attention was focused on events and territorial challenges in the northern colonies rather than the south, in part due to lower populations in the latter.

5.25 1756

In March 1756, General Louis Joseph de Montcalm-Grozon, Marquis de Montcalm, was appointed Commander in Chief of the French forces in North America and the Earl of Loudoun received a similar appointment in the British military by King George II. The French captured Minorca in the Mediterranean and upon hearing this news Great Britain officially declared war on France on May 18. The French reciprocated the following day and responded over the next few months by driving the British from the Great Lakes region in America. The great powers of the world chose sides. Austria, Russia, Saxony, and Sweden were allied with France, while Hanover and Prussia allied with Great Britain.

The French in Alabama attempted to incite their Cherokee allies to attack settlers in South Carolina and Georgia. During the summer a group of Creeks attacked several families of Virginian squatters on the Ogeechee River (near present-day Louisville, Georgia) and the Creek warriors stole their horses. Three Creek men were killed in the engagement. The Creek Headmen quickly apologized for this incident and friendly relations between the Creeks and Georgia were soon restored. The British government also apologized for the presence of the squatters on Creek land. The Creek chiefs asked Governor Reynolds to withdraw, "your People from Ogeechee all those that above the flowing of the Tide for [their] living so high up spoils our hunting Ground and Frightens away the Deer". Governor Reynolds balked at the request and it prompted him to re-establish a troop of Georgia Rangers (Schwartz 1994:73; Cole and Priestley 1936:71-73; Duncan n.d.:421; Reese 1963:115; McDowell 1992a:191-192; Davis 1982:139).

Throughout the Seven Years' War, France never made a play for control of coastal Georgia. When the war began, Fort Argyle was likely in ruins. Descriptions for land tracts granted to Edward Wamon (1753), Lewis Smyth (1755), and former Georgia Rangers Benjamin Goldwire and John Goldwire (1756), referred to Fort Argyle in the past tense. A 1755 petition by Thomas Mills for, "two hundred Acres of Land on the South Side of great Ogeechee River, at a Place where Fort Argyle formerly stood" was rejected by the Governor and his council since, "the said Land be reserved for Public Use". Later grants to Francis Pary, Elisha Butler, and former Georgia Ranger Moses Nunes in 1757 and 1758 no longer refer to Fort Argyle in the past tense. This implies that the Fort was re-established as a ranger fort by 1757 (CRG 6:393-394; CRG 7:159, 160, 331, 339, 360, 606, 744).

Governor Reynolds' term of office ended in 1756, but before he left, he compiled a summary of proposed defenses in Georgia. His list included forts at "Cockspur, Savannah, Hardwick, Fredrica, and Augusta". The governor also recommended forts at the land passages on the Savannah, great Ogeechee, and Altamaha rivers. He wrote to the Board of Trade in January bemoaning that the dilapidated fort at Augusta, "is the only fortification in the Province". His summary also included plans for enhancing these proposed defenses. Although Governor Reynolds made no specific reference to Fort Argyle, he did recommend stationing: "25 Rangers under the command of one Lieutenant at Hardwick; 25 Rangers at the Ogeechee Pass under the command of one Lieutenant, And 10 Rangers under the command of one Sergeant between the Ogeechee Pass and Hardwick". This latter location of Rangers between Ogeechee Pass and Hardwick may have been intended for Fort Argyle. Governor Reynolds' plan for fortifications at the Ogeechee, or the "Ferry over the Head of great Ogeechee River" consisted of a "Block house, in a Redoubt, of four Poligons 100 feet each, without any Bastion. being only a Protection of the Passage over the River". The fort at Ogeechee Pass was to be defended by eight cannons, including four 8-pounders and four 3-pounders. Its proposed garrison of 30 Regulars was to be reinforced by 35 militiamen and 35 Indian gun men. The present-day location of Ogeechee Pass was not determined by our research. It may refer to the First Fort Argyle, which was built at an important trail crossing, or more likely it was located farther upstream (CRG 27:103-107, 109, 245-252).

In May 1756 the Board of Trade referred a list of applications to the Privy Council, including one from Georgia for "Forts to be erected and supplied with Cannon and Stores and Garrisoned with regular Forces and for Two Troops of Rangers". Rangers were recruited for Fort Argyle the following year (Pargellis 1936:168).

In October 1756, Governor Reynolds, "ordered a Troop of 70 Rangers to be raised, and our Governor sent a Reinforcement from the Independent Companies to Augusta, for the Security of that Place, in Case the Creeks could not be satisfied, and Maners should come to Exemeties." The governor's action was in response to hostilities between the British settlers on the Ogeechee River and the Creeks. *The South Carolina Gazette* reported that in early September,

8 of the English settlers upon Ogeachy in Georgia, having (as we are told) some of their Horses stolen out of their Plantations by a few stragglng Creek Indians, armed themselves, and imprudently pursued the Indians to recover their Beasts; but the Indian firing upon them, their Fire was returned, two killed, one wounded, and the rest went off with the Death Whoop: The Ogeachy men returned to their Habitations, and after packing up what they could deserted them, then prudently apprehending terrible Consequences from their Rashness. The Accident occasioned the sending of many Expresses to this Government, for near a Fortnight together, while the Out Inhabitants of Georgia quitted their Settlements for Places of more Security, and resorted to and about Augusta, and there fortified themselves (*The South Carolina Gazette* 1756:2).

Also, in 1756, the King's Surveyor for the Southern Colonies, William DeBrahm, drew plans for a series of fortifications in coastal Georgia (DeBrahm 1756b). Improvements included new fortifications at Frederica, Hardwick and Savannah. His sketches are reproduced in Figure 5.7. Fort Argyle is not among his subjects in this sketch.

5.26 1757

The French won several victories in North America in 1757. In eastern Canada the British failed in their attempt to capture Louisbourg, Nova Scotia. After an unsuccessful attempt in March, French troops captured Fort William Henry by late summer. During the winter of 1756-1757, Rogers' Rangers, operating from their headquarters near Fort Edward on the Hudson River, harassed the French (Rogers 1966, 1988).

In May, Daniel Pepper, commander of Fort Moore, requested South Carolina Governor Lyttleton to advise Georgia's incoming Governor Henry Ellis not to, "allow the resettling of Ogetchee at this present Conjunction. It would be attended with very bad Consequences" (Schwartz 1994:83-84; McDowell 1992a:373).

Georgia's defenses languished under Governor Reynolds. His successor, Henry Ellis, who arrived in Savannah in February 1757 and took over officially as royal governor in May 1758, recorded this in his letters to the Board of Trade. Ellis noted in March that although two troops of Rangers, a total of 40 men, had been staffed by Reynolds, these existed mostly on paper. No provisions were made with the Treasury

Figure 5.7. William DeBrahm's 1756 Profile and Plan Drawings for Fortifications in Georgia (DeBrahm 1756b).

5.26 1757

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Office for their financial support. Governor Reynolds had appointed John Milledge as Captain of the troop and James Parker as its Lieutenant. Governor Ellis authorized commissions to the Ranger officers. By July only one troop of 20 Rangers had been raised, and these men were unpaid. Lacking funds for troops, Governor Ellis diverted money from road construction to fort construction and repairs in the Augusta and Savannah vicinities. In the absence of official funds for their support Governor Ellis funded the Ranger troop himself during 1757 and 1758 (Abbot 1959:63, 68-69; CRG 28(1):18-31, 4-15, 50-55, 92-94; Commissions Book B-1; Duncan n.d.:422).

An Act passed by the Georgia Assembly in 1757 provided for additional fort construction in Georgia. This Act enabled five forts to be built in different parts of Georgia, "one at Darien, one at Augusta. Another at Medway, a fourth at Ogeachy, and the principal one at Savannah". Many of William DeBrahm 's fort plans in Georgia date to this period (CRG 28(1):52).

Benjamin Martyn, Secretary of Georgia, wrote in March that,

It were greatly to be wished that those little forts which were intended to secure our frontier such as Augusta upon this River & Argyle upon the Ogechee, as well as the fortifications on the Islands towards the Spaniards were put into a defensible condition. At present they are quite in ruins & are rather marks of our weakness than power... the plan proposed by Mr Debrahme of fortifying the Province is judiciously concerted but so expensive that I despair of seeing it suddenly carried into execution. All therefore we can reasonably expect is what is absolutely & immediately necessary such as the reparation of fort Augusta, Argyle and Frederica. with two or three Troops of Irregulars (CRG 28:10).

William Pitt replaced the Duke of Newcastle as Secretary of State for the American colonies in 1756 and he brought with him a battle plan that included the capture of three northern forts (Middleton 1989). Governor Ellis wrote to William Pitt, congratulating him on his appointment and introducing him to the state of defenses in Georgia in May, noting, "things remaining here in a State of Quiet, tho from our weak and exposed condition, the activity of the French, and the disposition of the neighbouring Indians we are apprehensive that our tranquillity will not be of long duration" (Kimball 1906, Volume 1:68). In June, Lord Loudoun wrote to William Pitt stating, "I have, on Governor Ellis's Strong sollicitations, given him a Credit, on the Pay Master, for £850. Sterling, to support Rangers for their defence, which, with £150, that has been paid on the £200, which I acquainted You Governor Reynolds had drawn on me. to support Rangers, and to which I have hitherto receiv'd no Answer from you" (Kimball 1906, Volume 1:79).

Colonel Henry Bouquet, an officer in the 60th Regiment of Foot and commander of the King's forces in the Southern Department, wrote to Governor Ellis on July 14, 1757 regarding "The decayed state of forts in Georgia." Bouquet recommended that Georgians build, "large log forts to contain all the people about them. The cannons, &c scattered in the forts should be removed; can say nothing as to the rangers from Georgia. Will send 100 men, if they can be subsisted, at the expense of Georgia" (Pennsylvania Historical and Museum Commission 1940:2 [A.1. B.M. 21,63L]).

In October Captain Milledge and his Ranger troop were dispatched to Fort Argyle to escort a party of 150 Upper and Lower Creek Indians who were on their way to treaty with Governor Ellis and Colonel Henry Bouquet in Savannah. A conference with the British representatives and the Chiefs and Headmen of the Upper and Lower Creeks was held in Savannah on October 25-29. The Creek representatives were met by Governor Ellis and others and their conference was a success (CRG 7:644-645; Abbot 1959:76).

In December Governor Ellis wrote to William Pitt and placed greater emphasis on Georgia's need for British support of its military. In his words,

Before the late Governor's [Reynolds] departure be had begun (upon an alarm) to raise some Rangers. The Officers for three Troops were commissioned, but only about forty Men of the first Troop were levied. These for some time were subsisted by means of negotiable Certificates, which acquired Credit from a prevailing notion that the Crown would discharge them as it had done those issued in the last War by Mr Oglethorpe. That expedient soon failing I have since been enabled to maintain them by a Credit the Earl of Loudoun gave me upon the Deputy Pay Master at New York until his Lordship should hear from home-This is their present State and except those few Irregulars and Detachments of about 60 Men from one of the Independent Companies of South Carolina there are no Forces in this Province-I most beg leave to give it as my opinion Sir, that it would be highly advantageous to his Majesty's Service, to keep on foot a troop or two of these during the present War, as they are well calculated for this Company, being trained to charge both on foot. and on horseback and to ride full speed thro' the Woods (Kimball 1906, Volume 1:131).

Despite the documented existence of Milledge's Ranger troop during 1757, surviving records allowed the identification of only two persons as members of the troop. A Second Troop of Georgia Rangers was created in March 1757 and placed under command of William Francis. Francis was later replaced as commander of that troop by James Edward Powell. The Second Troop was not fully formed, however, until 1760. Ivers notes that the First and Second Troop of Rangers were classified as Provincial regulars, rather than British regulars. Their pay lists were submitted to General Thomas Gage and these documents, which span the period from May 18, 1759 to March 31, 1767 were transcribed and published by Murtie June Clark (Clark 1983, Volume 2:1009-1040; Duncan n.d.:410; Commission Book B-1:52-53, 120; Ivers 1986:83).

5.27 1758

The British Army made another attempt to capture Louisbourg, Nova Scotia in May 1758. Two months later the French suffered a major blow when they surrendered their force of 3,031 troops garrisoned at Louisbourg to the British. British Major General James Abercrombie failed to capture Fort Ticonderoga despite their superior troop strength (16,000 British versus 3,500 French). The French lost forts Frontenac and Duquesne to the British. By November, General Jeffery Amherst succeeded General Abercrombie as Commander in Chief of the British forces in North America. William Pitt continued to serve in the colonies as War Minister. Pitt brought with him to America three objectives; the capture of Louisbourg, Ticonderoga, and Duquesne. He was to achieve two of these goals during 1758. By years end the war

had turned in Britain's favor (*Annual Register* 1759:177; Schwartz 1994:91-92; Cole and Priestley 1936:74).

Legislation was enacted in March for erecting forts in Georgia and at Savannah. The forts were to be funded by taxes of one Shilling per head levied on all White Male Inhabitants. The law made no specific mention of Fort Argyle or St Phillip's parish (CRG 18:252-257). Royal Governor Ellis pleaded with the British Board of Trade on May 30 concerning Milledge's Rangers, "It is more than a year and a half since a troop of Rangers were begun to be raised here...I am now supporting them upon my own credit". The situation had not been resolved by October 28 when Ellis complained that, "the Rangers raised here by my predecessor, who are not yet upon any establishment; but have for many months past been maintained upon my own credit and risque. They are highly necessary to be kept on foot" (Duncan n.d.:423). That same month Governor Ellis complained to William Pitt that he had received no reply to his four letters to Major General James Abercrombie, Chief Commander of the King's Forces in North America, concerning funding for the Rangers. Governor Ellis presented this dismal view, "The Frontier forts are in a decayed condition, and no Other force is near except the few Rangers which for 8 or 9 months past have subsisted upon his own credit. and a small detachment of an Independent Company of S. Carolina. Altho' (as Lord Loudon agreed) the Rangers are necessary to be kept up he is afraid if he hears not[h]ing he will (very reluctantly) have to dismiss them" (Kimball 1906, Volume 1:377).

In February, the Board of Trade and Plantations in London noted in its journal, "Mr. [Benjamin] Martyn likewise laid before the Board a memorial addressed to the Lords Commissioners of the Treasury by several merchants and others, possessors of certificates given by the Governor and Lieutenant Governor of Georgia to the officers of one troop of Rangers raised in the said colony in 1756, certifying the pay due to the said officers and private men of the said troop, praying payment of the said certificates" (Ledward 1933:370-380). The Board of Trade and Plantations further noted,

Their lordships took into consideration the memorial addressed to the Lords Commissioners of the Treasury by several merchants and others, possessors of certificates given by the Governor and Lieutenant Governor of Georgia to the officers of a troop of Rangers raised there in 1756, certifying the pay due to the said officers and private men of the said troop; and Mr. Reynolds attending as desired was called in; and it appearing from his information that the said troop was raised when the province was under the greatest apprehension of being attacked by the Indians, that the establishment of it was upon a very reasonable foot, and that Lord Loudoun had approved the same and defrayed some part of the expence; their lordships approved of the memorial being presented to the Lords Commissioners of the Treasury for their directions upon it; and then Mr. Reynolds withdrew (Ledward 1933:370-380).

The Board of Trade and Plantations took up Governor Ellis' October 25 letter in its November 22 and its February, 1759 meetings, as noted in its journals, "The draught of a letter to Mr. Secretary Pitt, inclosing an extract of such parts of a letter from the Governor of Georgia of the 20th of May last, as relate to the state of the fortifications upon the southern frontier of that colony, and to the want of a proper establishment for the corps of Rangers kept on foot there at the Governor's own expence, having been

prepared pursuant to order, was agreed to, transcribed and signed" (Ledward 1933:419-432; 1935:10-21).

Thirty-three different individuals were soldiers in Captain Milledge's Troop in 1758 based on pay lists. However, it was not until the next year that Milledge's Ranger troop was on a firm financial footing (Clark 1983). Meanwhile, news from Savannah, dated November 10, informed readers in England of some of these events in Georgia,

Agreeable to an Invitation from our Governor, the principal Headmen and Warriors of 21 Towns in the Upper and Lower Creek Nations, arrived on Saturday the 29th ult. Escorted from Fort Argyle on Ogechee River, by Capt. Milledge's Troop of Rangers, to an open Savannah near this Town...Notwithstanding the short Notice the Governor had the Arrival of such a Number of Indians at Fort Argyle, every Thing, by his Care and Vigilance, whether regarding their Reception or Entertainment, was conducted with the utmost Order, Decency, and Grandeur, and gave great Satisfaction to every Individual; And the Indians in particular, whose Minds had been prepossessed with Jealousies by our common Enemies, who had neglected nothing to defeat this Interview, were in every Circumstance agreeably surprised, as they frequently acknowledged, and took all Opportunities of expressing a due and grateful Sense of (*Newcastle Courant* 1758:1-2).

5.28 1759

The French suffered major defeats by the British at Forts Ticonderoga and Niagara, and at Quebec. A British victory on the Plains of Abraham was won with few casualties and resulted in near control of Canada for Great Britain. William Pitt's plan to capture the three major French forts was completed, and the French were clearly on the defensive in North America. The worldwide troop strength of the British Army, estimated in December 1759, stood at 109,000, which was 18,000 more than the previous year and more than double what it had been in 1755 (*Annual Register* 1760; Schwartz 1994:105- 106; Middleton 1989:236; Cole and Priestley 1936:75-78).

Further south, the Cherokee made a short-lived peace with South Carolina. William Pitt wrote to General Amherst on March 15, 1759 regarding, "The defenceless state of Georgia. Rangers to be kept on foot at the expense of the Crown" (Kimball 1906, Volume 2:67):

Having received Letters from Henry Ellis Esqr, Governor of Georgia, setting forth the defenceless State of that Frontier Province, And that, upon some Alarming Appearances amongst their Indian Neighbours, the late Governor, in the year 1756, had begun to raise some Rangers for the Defence of the Colony; that the Officers for Three Troops were commissioned, and Forty Men for the first Troop levied, but never yet established; that He, Govr Ellis, in consequence of the King's Pleasure signified to him, that He should apply to the Commander in Chief of the King's Forces in North America, for any Assistance, that might be thought necessary for the Safety of that Province, had made several ineffectual Applications to Lord Loudoun [John Campbell, 4th Earl of Loudoun], and Genl Abercromby [James Abercrombie], upon this Head, and, after Two Years solliciting and remonstrating, is neither authorized to establish nor dismiss the above Troops of

Rangers, tho' necessity must oblige Him to the last Measure; if He don't receive Orders to the Contrary, he having subsisted the few Rangers that were raised, for Eight or Nine Months, upon His Credit, and as His own Risk.

I send you inclosed, a Copy of Governour Ellis's Letter, and I am commanded to signify to you the King's Pleasure, that you take the same into your Consideration; And, should it appear to you, that the Establishment of the above Rangers may be of use and materially conducive to the Security of His Majesty's Province of Georgia; You are, without Loss of Time, to give proper Directions to Governor Ellis, for establishing and keeping the same on foot; and you will also acquaint Govr Ellis, in what Manner He is to draw for the Expences attending this Service, which you will place to Account in the same Manner as you do with regard to the Rangers ordered to be raised in my Letter of the 29 Decr last.

Based on these pay lists the number of different individuals in Captain Milledge's Troop during 1759 was 78 (Clark 1983:1009-1070). Surviving pay bills for Captain Milledge's First Troop of Georgia Rangers, beginning on May 18, 1759 and continuing to March 31, 1767, indicate that the size of Milledge's troop more than doubled from the previous year. Similar pay lists for Captain James Edward Powell's Second Troop of Georgia Rangers exist for the period January 1760 to March 1767.

5.29 1760

King George II died on October 25, 1760 and was succeeded on the throne by his son George III. After battles at Quebec and Montreal, the French surrendered Canada to Great Britain. By September the war in the north was effectively over. Far to the south the Cherokee surprised a party of the Patrick Calhoun family, who were Scottish settlers. The party was massacred near Long Cane Creek. This ambush started a war between the Cherokee and South Carolina, which voided the peace treaty of the previous year. Next, the Cherokee attacked Fort Prince George near Keowee, but they were unsuccessful in taking the fort. The British retaliated for these actions by sending 1,200 troops under command of Colonel Montgomery whose men proceeded to burn many of the lower Cherokee towns during June. The Cherokee fought back in August at Fort Loudoun, a British fort located deep in the heart of Cherokee country on the Little Tennessee River. The fort was captured by the Cherokee, the British capitulated, and then the entire British garrison was slaughtered. Georgia's two Ranger troops took heed of the Cherokee threat by doubling in size (*Annual Register* 1761).

In February, Georgia's Royal Governor Henry Ellis described to William Pitt how, following the British attack on Fort Duquesne on the Ohio River, the Cherokee started, "an open War. Massacred the English trading in their Country; and fell upon the Out Settlers of the Adjacent Provinces, many of whom they cut off by surprize; and have since spread terror and desolation throughout the frontiers". Governor Ellis noted that the hostilities had not yet reached coastal Georgia, but he expressed his apprehension that it soon would and he had authorized the erection of, "Log forts in the parts most exposed, wherein the helpless people may take shelter in case of any sudden Emergency", and, "stationed the Rangers, lately augmented, still more backward, so that the Enemy cannot easily approach undiscovered". Governor Ellis noted in his letter that the Creek and Chickasaw remained loyal allies of Georgia (Kimball 1906, Volume 2:253-255).

That same month the General Assembly of Georgia funded several regiments of Militia to patrol the area between the Savannah and Altamaha rivers and several references were made to Fort Argyle in these proceedings. Governor Ellis resolved that, "Captain Milledge with his Rangers should march to Augusta for the better Securing that Settlement and the back Inhabitants from the Incursion of the Cherokee Indians". Governor Ellis sent Milledge the following instructions that were to be carried with his troop to Augusta, "A Publication to be made to our Friend Indians, that for every Enemy's Scalp they brought in they should receive for the same a Trading Gun. three Pound of Powder, six Pound of Shot, a Blanket, a Flap, a pair Indian Boots, and a Cag [keg] containing four Gallons of trading Rum" (CRG 8:248-250).

John Milledge and his Rangers were at Fort Augusta by March 1760, where they mounted regular patrols along the Cherokee frontier (Ivers 1986:82-83; Jones 1992:121). By June a troop of Rangers were stationed at New Ebenezer. It is not clear if the Rangers were a contingent of Milledge's Rangers or were members of Captain Powell's Troop. Reverend Boltzius recorded his annoyance with them, "Saturday, the 14th of June. Since last Sunday a troop of Rangers has been at our place, whose improper behavior has caused us no little trouble. They are surely miserable defenders of the land and people! We have learned nothing more of what the Creek Indians are planning" (Jones 1992:197).

Over the next two months Governor Ellis encouraged the Creeks and Chickasaw to fight against the Cherokee, and the governor's words were supplemented by many presents. His pleas met with only limited success, however, in April Governor Ellis presented a plan of attack against the French forts at Mobile to William Pitt, who liked the idea of a southern thrust, but his top priority was the Canada campaign and Ellis' plan was not pursued (Kimball 1906, Volume 2:277-279).

Legislation enacted in April for repairing and rebuilding the "several Log-Forts" in Georgia and for additional fortifications in Savannah empowered the commissioners to use Male slaves to repair and build forts (for periods less than six days). The fort commissioners of St. Phillip's parish, James Mackay, Joseph Butler, Elisha Butler, William Butler, and James Maxwell, were allocated £25 for this purpose (CRG 18:408-417). Repairs or new construction began at Fort Argyle about that time. In September, funds were transmitted by the Governor and his council to the Commissioners of Fortifications for Christ Church Parish for, "defraying the Expencc of a Fort at Barrington, and another Fort at great Ogechee, to the Amount of fifty Pounds each" (CRG 8:374). By November £550 were allocated by the Commons House, "towards finishing the Public Forts in this Province", and they concluded:

RESOLVED that the Sum of Two Hundred Pounds be allowed towards finishing the Fortifications of the Town of Savannah that the Sum of Seventy five Pounds be allowed towards finishing the Fortifications at Augusta, that the Sum of Twenty five Pounds be allowed toward finishing the Fort at Hallifax, that the Sum of One hundred and twenty Pounds be allowed towards finishing the Fortifications at Midway and Newport, that Eighty Pounds be allowed towards finishing the Fort at Darien, that twenty five Pounds be allow'd towards finishing the fort at Ebenezer and twenty five Pounds towards finishing the Fort at Great Ogeechee (CRG 13:458-459).

It is uncertain from these historical documents if the referenced fort on the Ogeechee was the same as Argyle, or if it referred to forts downstream at Hardwick, or at another location upstream from Fort Argyle. It most likely referred to the fort that protected the town of Hardwick.

In late May, 20 British traders who were living among the Upper Creeks on the Chattahoochee River were murdered. Traders among the Lower Creeks panicked and fled to Savannah seeking refuge. Some settlers on the interior abandoned their plantations. Governor Ellis quickly scheduled talks with the Creek headmen and temporarily diffused the inflamed political situation. Apparently, the murders were instigated by the French and Cherokee. However, it was clear from this act that the tight alliance between the British and the Creeks, which Georgia had enjoyed throughout the Trustee period, was beginning to collapse (Kimball 1906, Volume 2:312-315; Reese 1963:119).

In November Mr. Joseph Wrights, an Indian Trader, arrived at Fort Argyle with about 40 Creek Indians who were on their way to meet with Governor Ellis. They remained at Fort Argyle less than a week before continuing to Savannah. About that time James Wright replaced Henry Ellis as governor and Ellis returned to England (CRG 8:422-423; Kimball 1906, Volume 2).

In December 1760 or early January 1761, Royal Governor Wright ordered a, "Reinforcement of Georgia Rangers from Fort Argyle to Augusta, where there were 30 of the Corps before". This was in response to recent hostile action by the Cherokees at Fort Loudoun, as well as at Fort Pennington and elsewhere in the South Carolina upcountry and by Cherokee threats to attack the Chickasaws of New Windsor and the "White People of Augusta" (*The Pennsylvania Gazette* 1761:2).

By 1760 Captain Milledge had divided his ranger troop into at least two independent units. He sent part of the troop to garrison Fort Barrington on the Altamaha River. Newly appointed Governor James Wright assessed the troop strength in Georgia upon his arrival to include, "20 Royal Americans at Fort Augusta & 30 rangers in town of Augusta; 10 Royal Americans at Frederica; 25 Rangers at Fort Barrington; 15 Rangers at Fort Argyle; 19 at Ft George" (Wright 1760, cited in Jones 1883). The 25 Rangers at Fort Barrington were selected from Milledge's First Troop of Rangers under the command of one of his lieutenants. Fort George on Cockspur Island was garrisoned by Captain Powell's Second Troop of Rangers. The fact that more Rangers were stationed at Fort Barrington than at Fort Argyle that year signifies that Fort Argyle's location continued to become less strategic for defense. Fort Barrington was a larger and more substantial fort than Fort Argyle, built using William DeBrahm's design (Figure 5.8), and Fort Barrington began to receive a larger share of the defense funds than Fort Argyle (Stephens 1859:54-55).

A plat of 500 acres for John Milledge, recorded December of that year, depicts Fort Argyle as two small rectangle symbols east of Milledge's land. The fact that Milledge owned land adjacent to Fort Argyle leads one to infer that he continued to command from that post rather than move to Barrington. By 1760, Milledge had a grandson three years of age, although he was only 39 years old (Georgia, Colony of 1757-1761; Georgia, Colony of Various Dates). It is unclear what members of his family lived with him at that time.

Figure 5.8 William DeBrahm's Profile and Plan for Fort Barrington, ca. 1757 (King's Collection, The British Library ca. 1757; DeVorse 1971).

A plat of 500 acres for John Milledge, recorded December of that year, depicts Fort Argyle as two small rectangle symbols east of Milledge's land. The fact that Milledge owned land adjacent to Fort Argyle leads one to infer that he continued to command from that post rather than move to Barrington. By 1760, Milledge had a grandson three years of age, although he was only 39 years old (Georgia, Colony of 1757-1761; Georgia, Colony of Various Dates). It is unclear what members of his family lived with him at that time.

5.30 1761

Great Britain signed a peace treaty with the Cherokees in 1761. This time the Cherokee abided by the terms of the treaty and the northern threat to Georgia by the Cherokee greatly diminished. The Fort Argyle garrison numbered 36 rangers for that year, or approximately half of the Rangers under Captain Milledge's command. Lieutenant Robert Baillie commanded that part of Milledge's Troop that was garrisoned at Fort Barrington. In February, Governor Wright wrote to King George III requesting: "a Number of swivel guns, with a proper Quantity of shot...for the use of the Little Forts and Blockhouses". Legislation was enacted in December for erecting a fort and battery at Cockspur Island and a lookout and battery on the Midway River. The Rangers at Fort Argyle were probably engaged in fort repairs, and no military action was recorded in Georgia in 1761 (Schwartz 1994:148; CRG 18:472-479; 28(2):188; 34:373; Johnson 1992:38; Clark 1983).

5.31 1762

When Great Britain declared war against Spain in 1762, it must have seemed to the Rangers at Fort Argyle that the Seven Years' War would turn out to be another Hundred Years' War. Peace was only a year away. Grenada, Havana, Manila, and Martinique all were captured by the British. The French made a half-hearted attempt to recapture Newfoundland but failed. Peace talks commenced in November, which would lead to an end of the war between England and France the following year. Meanwhile, Governor Wright had written to the Secretary of War appealing for additional troops for Georgia, noting that two troops of Rangers were inadequate for the defense of Georgia (*Annual Register* 1763; Grun 1991:352; Cole and Priestley 1936:87; BPRO, MF 1174, Box 6, Folder 3-09).

It was in 1762 that the most detailed description of Fort Argyle was written. Governor James Wright wrote to the British Lords of Trade in February, "Fort Argyle about 19 Miles from Savannah, on great Ogechee River is a square Fort of 110 feet each way, with two Rows of Barracks and is in good condition, and garrisoned by thirty five of the Georgia Rangers paid as above". Wright provided troop numbers for the rangers garrisoned at the other forts in Georgia, which included: Savannah/Fort Halifax, about 30 rangers; Fort Augusta, 30 rangers; Fort St. John, 30 rangers (presently withdrawn); and Fort Barrington, 25 rangers. Wright cited seven forts in Georgia in his letter and he added that "besides these my Lords there are some small stockade Forts about the Province, not garrisoned, but just to shelter the Inhabitants in case of any Surprise or sudden Attack by the Indians" (Wright 1762; Figure 5.9).

A committee was formed by the Georgia Assembly in October to inspect the forts in the province of Georgia. Messrs. Butler and Maxwell were committee members who were appointed to inspect Fort Argyle and other fortifications in St Phillip's Parish. More than nine forts were cited by the fort inspection

committee (CRG 13:705-706; 28(2):188-189). The forts listed by Governor Wright and the inspection committee are listed in Tables 5.3 and 5.4. Reports by both Wright and the Inspection Committee demonstrate that Argyle remained a viable fort in 1762. The garrison of Rangers there continued under command of John Milledge, and it was another year on the Ogeechee River without any battles.

Table 5.3 Forts in Georgia, circa 1762, cited by Royal Governor James Wright.

<u>Fort</u>	<u>Configuration</u>	<u>Dimensions</u>
George (Cockspur)	None given	None given
Hallifax (Savannah)	Square	200 x 200 feet
Augusta	Square	110 x 110 feet
Argyle	Square	110 x 110 feet
St. John (Midway)	Square	110 x 110 feet
Barrington	Square	75 x 75 feet
William (South end, Cumberland Island)	None given	None given

Table 5.4. Forts in Georgia, Circa 1762, Cited During Formation of the Inspection Committee.

<u>Fort</u>
Hallifax (Savannah) and blockhouse round town
Cockspur Island
Ebenezer
Forts in St. George's Parish
Augusta
Fort Argyle and fortifications in St. Phillip's Parish
Forts in St. John's Parish
Fort Barrington and fortifications in St. Andrew's Parish
Fort and Fortifications in St. James' Parish

(CRG 13:459-460; 28(2):188-189)

5.32 1763

On February 10, 1763 Great Britain made peace with France and Spain at a treaty signed in Paris, thus marking the end of the Seven Years' War. The French relinquished possession of Canada and all the land east of the Mississippi, except for New Orleans. Florida was a major prize won by the British from the Spanish, in exchange for the return of Havana and Manila. Great Britain emerged from these talks as the supreme imperial power in the world. Lieutenant General Amherst was replaced by Lieutenant General Thomas Gage as Commander in Chief of the British Forces in North America.

A treaty between Great Britain and the Catawbas, Cherokee, Chickasaw, Choctaw, and Creeks was signed in Augusta in November. This treaty ceded a vast area of the interior to the Crown. It also opened additional areas of the lower Ogeechee River for British settlers. However, the provisions of the Treaty

of Augusta were not accepted by the entire Native American populace, resulting in many small raids on frontier settlements. For Fort Argyle this meant that the frontier had undergone a dramatic shift inland and the lower Ogeechee River area was no longer included in the backcountry. Fort Argyle was fast losing its status as a frontier fort. The Treaty of Augusta paved the way for additional British settlements at Brownsborough, Queensborough, and Wrightsborough during the 1770s. Of these three settlements, only Queensborough was within the Ogeechee River watershed.

Fort Argyle was barely mentioned in the historical documents of 1763, although Captain Milledge's Rangers continued to patrol the colony. Expenditures for the colony recorded in February included, "For Captain Milledge Ballance of Account for sundry Tools Iron Work &c for Fort Arguil a Sum not exceeding £32.6.8". This suggests that the repairs or new construction at Fort Argyle had been completed just in time for the Treaty of Paris (CRG 14:40). Ivers (1986:85) notes that all Rangers in North America under British pay were to be discharged in 1763 following the Treaty of Paris, but as a result of military bureaucratic inaction, the two troops of Georgia Rangers were kept on the payroll for four more years. This oversight must have pleased the Rangers at Fort Argyle who stood to benefit from four years of service as Rangers during peacetime. However, by 1763 the faces of conflict in the North American colonies were changing and some British subjects were beginning to react against the totalitarianism of the British monarchy (Stanhope 1858, v. 4:277; Schwartz 1994:147-148; Cashin 1989).

Figure 5.9 Portion of Wright's 1763 Map of Georgia and Florida (Wright 1763).

5.33 1764

The Spanish began their formal evacuation of St. Augustine and Florida in 1764 and that locale came firmly under British rule, which was to last until 1781/1785. This meant there was no longer a Spanish threat against Georgia, at least not one that emanated from St Augustine. The French threat to Georgia was also virtually eliminated. At this point the Georgia Rangers' responsibilities shifted almost exclusively to watching the Native Americans and performing internal law enforcement duties within the colony. The Fort Argyle garrison numbered 35 in 1764, or approximately half of the Georgia Rangers that were under Capt. Milledge's command. No other specific references to Fort Argyle were located for that year (CRG 28(2):188; Johnson 1992:38).

5.34 1765

A civilian reference to Fort Argyle was made in 1765. Jonathan Bryan, owner of many large plantations in Georgia, operated a large cow pen located 15 miles north of Argyle. Bryan herded his cattle through Fort Argyle while heading to the south (Galloy 1989:88). Fort Argyle did not appear in legislative or military documents during this year. Legislation did mention other forts and was enacted by the Georgia Assembly in March for building a fort and barracks near Augusta, a guard house in Savannah, and repairing the barracks at Frederica which were all in "a ruinous Condition" (CRG 18:639-649). Fort Argyle was not mentioned by this Act. Two other pieces of Parliamentary legislation were enacted that year, and both proved to be immensely unpopular in the colonies-the Quartering Act and the Stamp Act. The Quartering Act required the colonists to provide quarters, food and drink for the King's troops. This was a very unpopular law which added fuel to the flames of revolution. The Stamp Act became law on November 1 and with it was ushered in a new role for the Georgia Rangers, that of controlling internal strife as the threat to British security in the colony shifted from external to internal. The Rangers proved remarkably flexible in making this transition (Alden 1948:154; Stanhope 1858, v. 5:127).

5.35 1766

The Fort Argyle garrison continued to number 35 in 1766, still approximately half of the Georgia Rangers under Captain Milledge's command. By the end of the year garrison strength at Argyle had slipped to 15 Rangers, as it fell below Fort Barrington in importance (CRG 28(2):188; Johnson 1992:38). The 'stamps' arrived from England at the beginning of the year. When 200 Liberty Boys assembled in Savannah and surrounded the town on January 2 in protest of the Stamp Act, Governor Wright reacted by summoning 50 to 56 Georgia Rangers commanded by captains Milledge and Powell to guard the stamped papers (Stevens 1847:8). The papers were sent to Fort George on Cockspur Island for safe keeping by the Georgia Rangers (a Captain, two subalterns and 50 privates) who accompanied them. The Savannah stamp uprising was put down without violent incident. The unpopular Stamp Act was repealed before the year was out, but the seeds of discontent were already planted in Georgia. It was only a matter of time before revolution was thrust to the forefront (Stanhope 1858, v. 5:142).

Early in the year Governor Wright reported to England that Georgia possessed two troops of Rangers, totaling 120 men, "which occupy 5 forts or posts in different parts of the province". He described Forts St. John, William, and Barrington as in ruins, and Governor Wright made no mention of the condition at

Fort Argyle (Abbot 1959:114; *Pennsylvania Gazette*, Feb 13, 1766; CRG 28(2):189, 303, 317-318; 37:103-109, 110-111). By November the picture had changed somewhat. Georgia contained two troops of Rangers composed of five officers and 70 private men each, or a total of 160 Rangers. The troops were scattered about in "the most usefull manner in which such a hand full of men can be employed here" (CRG 37:141-142). The troops in Georgia included: "More than 30 Rangers and 20 Royal Americans at Fort Augusta; 10 Royal Americans at Frederica; More than 25 Rangers at Fort Barrington; 15 Rangers at Fort Argyle; 15 Rangers at Fort George; and the rest (less than 75) in Savannah" (CRG 37:141-142).

Governor Wright recorded this financial transaction involving Captain John Milledge and his ranger troop,

Exchange £200, Georgia 18 Nov. 1766

At 30 days sight of this my Third of Exchange (my first and second of same tenor and date not paid) please to pay Captain John Milledge or order £200 Sterling being for the pay and subsistence of his Majesty's First Troop of Rangers under his command from the 18th day of August 1766 to the 18th day of Nov. 1766 inclusive; and pass the same to account of the said service as advice from Sir your obedient servant,

Signed: Ja: Wright

To Abraham Mortier, Esq., Paymaster of his Majesty's forces New York.

Recorded 13 Feb. 1768 (Georgia, Colony of 1768:168).

5.36 1767

The dawn of the American Revolution marked the twilight of the Georgia Rangers. Following commands from England, General Thomas Gage ordered the disbanding of the Rangers in Georgia on February 27 and they were officially disbanded on March 31. Around the time of their discharge only 15 Rangers were stationed at Fort Argyle. General Gage's orders were promptly carried out as evidenced by a petition for land by John Milledge in May where he states that he had served as "Captain of his Majesty's first Troop of Rangers in this Province lately disbanded" (CRG 10:176; 27:14; 37:188, 208; Johnson 1992: 38, 53, 66-67).

Governor Wright lodged a futile complaint with General Gage on April 2 urging that he needed regular troops in the colony if the Rangers were to be disbanded. Gage replied on May 16 that the forts (Augusta, Frederica, and George) were in thickly settled parts of Georgia and for Provincial forts certainties, such as barracks and bedding should be supplied by the Province (CRG 37:245). General Gage contended, "I can't send troops into Forts where no provision is made to accomodate them with the common necessities of life, Capt. [Valentine] Fuser will affirm as many men for Fort Augusta & Frederica, as his numbers will permit, but he complains that the soldiers at Fort Augusta lye upon the boards & are continually seduced by the country people to desert" (CRG 37:245).

Governor Wright also wrote to the Earl of Shelbourne appealing for funds to feed and outfit the British troops in Georgia. His accounts to the Earl of Shelbourne, dated May 15, included a request for £4,072 for the annual support of two Ranger troops. The Governor's request was not honored-thus bringing the history of the Georgia Rangers at Fort Argyle to a conclusion (CRG 37:208). The Georgia government

remained optimistic that the Rangers would be reinstated. In May, Shem Butler petitioned for "One hundred Acres on great Ogechee to join Land of Moses Nunes", but his petition was rejected by the Council because the land was, "supposed to be a part of Lands reserved at Fort Argyle" (CRG 10:174). Although Fort Argyle was without a garrison in July, two hundred acres were reserved for Fort Argyle adjacent to Governor Wright's property. On July 30, Governor Wright ordered, "That a further Reserve of two hundred Acres of Land, by continuing the back Lines of three hundred Acres already laid out, be made on Ogechee for the use of Fort Argyle; and that his Excellency the Governour might have One thousand Acres of vacant Land granted him in family Right on Ogechee between the said reserved Land for the Use of the Fort and Land of Moses Nunes" (CRG 10:278).

Argyle's strategic importance to the colony was greatly diminished and its history as a Ranger fort ended in the Spring of 1767. Although the Georgia Rangers were reestablished in 1773, none of these Rangers were stationed at Fort Argyle. Most were positioned along the harbor entrance to Savannah or were garrisoned at the new frontier fort, Fort James, which was built deep in the piedmont region at the confluence of the Broad and Savannah Rivers to defend the newly acquired lands in Georgia (Johnson 1992:113). After General Gage's February 1767 orders to disband the Rangers were issued most of the soldiers at Fort Argyle turned their lives to other pursuits. Many became involved in politics or other bureaucratic positions. Some continued to serve as military men, but not at Fort Argyle. Others were content to manage their plantations in the areas surrounding Argyle and beyond.

5.37 1768 to 1782

Five forts in Georgia were listed by Governor Wright in the fall of 1773. These included: Fort George on Cockspur Island; Fort Halifax in Savannah; Fort Frederick in Frederica; Fort Augusta in Augusta; and Fort Barrington on the Altamaha River (CRG 38(1):121; Wright 1873:168-169). The frontier, it seems, had left Fort Argyle behind.

On September 6, 1773, Governor Wright resurrected the Georgia Rangers, whose purpose was, "to keep good order amongst, and for the protection of the Inhabitants in the new ceded Lands above Settlo [Satilla] River". The strength of the Georgia Ranger corps was to be one captain, three lieutenants, one quarter master, 1 surgeon, three sergeants, one drummer, and 65 privates. This strength was reached by 4 March 1773, when it not only mustered its authorized numbers, but one cadet and four privates over. The officers of the Georgia Rangers included Captain Edward Barnard, 1st Lieutenant Thomas Waters, and 2nd Lieutenant Edward Keating, 3rd Lieutenant Timothy Barnard, Quarter Master John Stuart, Senr., and Surgeon Francis Begbie. This military unit functioned until about March 1776 (Braisted 2001). The Ranger's pay was issued four times yearly, at the rate of three pounds per month for a sergeant, two pounds, five shillings per month for the drummer, and two pounds per month for each private. This pay was to be without any stoppages or deductions. The Rangers were provided with powder and ball, but each ranger was expected to victual himself and furnish his own uniform, arms and accoutrements. All men were also to be provided with a good horse, as the Georgia Rangers were always mounted (Braisted 2001). The Georgia Rangers' uniform was, "a Blue Coat faced with Red and a Red Jacket and Blue Cloth Boots on spatterdashes made to fit the Leg edged with Red and Gartered with a Black strap and Buckle to wear occasionally and Breeches either Blue Cloth or Buckskin also a good Fussee [fusil], a Putteau, a Black Leather shot Pouch and Belt of the same Edged with Red also a good

Powder horn." The Georgia Rangers were "to be all Healthy strong able Bodied Men fit for actual Duty and service", and were to, "keep themselves sober and clean, and behave orderly and discreetly, and to suffer no swearing or Drunkenness amongst them." The duty of the Georgia Rangers was basically to be that of a police force. The ranger troop was divided into three divisions, each under the command of an officer and a sergeant. Each division was to be on constant duty, patrolling the frontiers (or the "ceded lands") and keep the Indians and settlers from stealing each other's horses and cattle. The Georgia Rangers also were to prevent any new white settlers from infringing upon Indian land and monitor any Indians entering from the West. The Georgia Rangers were to apprehend "all Horse Thieves, Vagrants and other Disorderly persons" and deal with them according to Georgia law (Braisted 2001).

By 1779, Fort Argyle was no longer located along a major transportation route. This is evident from contemporary maps that show major crossings of the Ogeechee River located several miles below and many miles above Fort Argyle (*Universal Magazine of Knowledge and Pleasure* 1779, vol. 64:168). See also Figure 5.10.

During the colonial period a public ferry located at Pine Bluff near present-day U.S. Highway 17, several kilometers downstream from Fort Argyle, was the primary crossing on the Ogeechee River. As early as April 1761 a committee was formed by the Commons House, composed of Mr. Read, Mr. James Deveaux, and Mr. Butler, "to propose a Bill to establish a ferry over the great Ogeechee River" and to "Vest the Same in M John Deveaux for the Space of Seven Years pursuant to an agreement made between the Commissioners for the South West Road and the said John Deveaux and to settle the rates for Ferriage". In 1768 a public ferry over the Great Ogeechee River at Pine Bluff' was authorized by a colonial act. The creation of the Pine Bluff ferry, then known as King's Ferry, and the great road that it served, effectively terminated Fort Argyle's position on an important transportation route and river crossing. Just a few years later during the American Revolution it was proposed that a redoubt be thrown up at Ogeechee Ferry (Colonial Acts of Georgia, September 1773:308-309; CRG 13:525-526; 19(1):59-67,337-345; 38(2):534).

Figure 5.10 Portions of an Anonymous Map Showing Coastal Georgia (Anonymous ca. 1780).

The compiled Revolutionary War Records of Georgia include absolutely no references to Fort Argyle, which shows that the fort and its location were not strategically significant during that era, if the fort was manned at all. The Americans controlled the Georgia tidewater region during the early years of the war. The British invaded Georgia with a large force in late 1778, led by Lieutenant Colonel Archibald Campbell. Campbell's journal and maps of his invasion and the journal of his Engineer John Wilson have survived. Neither Campbell nor Wilson made any specific references to Fort Argyle in their maps or writings (Campbell 1981). After the fall of Savannah by early 1779 most of coastal Georgia was under British control. The British were routed from control of the colony by American General Anthony Wayne and his rag-tag troops in 1782 (Candler 1908). The only specific reference to Argyle that was located by our research for the Revolutionary War period was an order issued by Samuel Elbert to Colonel Habersham in December, 1777, where Elbert wrote, "You are to march immediately with the detachment under your command and take the shortest route to Greate Ogeechee which you are to cross either at Fort Arguile or higher up, so as to get into the fork between that river & Coonuchie when you are either by bribes, threats or otherwise to try if possible & get information of the Florida Scout who I have in intelligence are in small parties collecting cattle up Ogeechee" (DeRenne 1902:75).

One notable battle at the "Great Ogeechee" occurred on November 2, 1781. The exact location of this battle remains unclear, but it was most likely located downstream from Fort Argyle, at or near, Kings Ferry (the present crossing of U.S. Highway 17 over the Ogeechee River). Although this battle took place nearly a month after the American and French victory at Yorktown, the war in Georgia was by no means concluded.

The Patriot version of this military engagement is recorded in a letter from Lieutenant Colonel James Jackson from his Georgia Legion's "camp on Ogeechee" to Brigadier General David Twiggs, commander of the Georgia militia on November 5, 1781. This letter was accompanied by Jackson's crude sketch of the battleground (Jackson 1781; n.d. [ca. November 1781]). Jackson's letter read:

Agreeable to your order I marched from your camp at Briar Creek, having a detachment of one hundred and forty men, consisting of colonel McKay, and capt. Grant's volunteers, and a part of my own corps, with intention of surprizing the post of British dragoons at Ogeechee. On the 2d of November we arrived at the Ogeechee settlements, and about two miles from our object, had the good fortune to take two prisoners, who informed us they had not discovered our route or the distance we were from them, but that they knew of our advance down the country. A council of officers were called, when on further information that the enemy's dragoon horses were chiefly out, it was determined to attack them. We farther found they had been reinforced by all the dragoons they could possibly raise, with about one hundred infantry divided into three parts, with the militia of the country, at near a mile distant from each other; we advanced in three columns. The dragoons of my own and captain Cacis, volunteer corps in the center, with colonel McKay's riflemen, and captain Grant's on the flanks, under the command of that colonel, orders were then given to the dragoons to charge through the yard of the enemies station, and the riflemen to range on each side the house, which had a strong piazza, and keep up a brisk fire, should the enemy take to the house, the dragoons charged through, and the enemy, as foreseen, took the

house, and actually surrendered, but unfortunately had time to resume their arms, owing to the falling of the brave captain Grant, who led one of the rifle columns, and which broke on his death, and a mistake of orders in the other, who took after the runaways in the neighboring swamp; finding ourselves under the disagreeable necessity of quitting our object, on that account, of the neighbouring posts, and apprehending the mischief that might be done by the militia joined with the regulars in case of a retreat, it was resolved to route them, which was accordingly done, killing eleven and taking five, or six prisoners. I then determined to retreat, when my reconnoitering parties returned and brought intelligence the enemy were advanceing in a collective body, the most proper position our then circumstances would admit was made; the enemy charged and routed our riflemen, our dragoons charged in return and broke their column, when a smart little action ensued for about twenty minutes, our loss was trifling; the enemy's loss was great. Private accounts from Savannah acknowledge between thirty and forty killed, including the officers, and six wagon loads of wounded.

The British version of the battle tells a far different story, as recorded in the November 8, 1781 edition of *The Royal Georgia Gazette*, a Loyalist newspaper published in Savannah,

Savannah, November 8. Last Friday morning the Rebel Col. Jackson, with about 200 men, made an attack on Capt. Johnston's post at Great Ogeechee, but was soon obliged to retire with the loss of Captains Grant and Lucas, and several privates. Col. Campbell, who commanded at Ogeechee, and whose quarters were half a mile distant, marched on the first alarm with the dragoons of his own regiment and Col. Brown's, under the command of Captain Wylly. Joining Capt. Johnston, he proceeded with 85 dragoons in quest of the enemy, who he found advantageously drawn up at the edge of a swamp. Col. Campbell attempted to draw the Rebels out, but finding that the superiority of their numbers (being more than two to one) did not give them confidence enough to venture in the open field, he ordered an immediate charge, which was executed with that spirited firmness which will always insure victory, and reflect lasting honour on every one concerned. The Rebels being twice charged through retreated in great confusion, leaving many of their dead on the field. The pursuit was continued near four miles, and the country people who have since come in declare that the Rebel wounded and dead are to be seen in many places 12 miles from the field of action. Our loss was 12 killed and some wounded, among the first was the gallant Cornet Hardenbrook of Col. Campbell's dragoons, who fell gloriously in the first charge. The loyal country people are daily taking prisoners; they have brought in Capt. Bugg of the Rebel dragoons and several privates and have intelligence of many more that are skulking in the swamps.

It is with the utmost horror we mention, that, after the signal repulse of the Rebels at Capt. Johnston's post on Friday last, the whole of their force proceeded to the plantation of James Butler, Esq., where about 15 militiamen were posted; they set fire to that gentleman's dwelling-house, and finding Capt. Howell (brother to the famous picaroon of that name) in it sick, and unable to extricate himself from the flames, they dragged him out, and barbarously murdered him in the yard. Capt. Goldsmith, Mr. Dunbar Gray, Mr. Mackinon, Mr. John Lemar, and Mr. Stephen Christopher, here unfortunately fell into their ruffian hands, and were soon after

murdered in cold blood; Capt. Goldsmith, a gentleman against whom the rebels could have nothing to allege but an ever firm attachment to the British government, was most inhumanly butchered by Samuel West, who, for this and his many other crimes, will in due time meet with an ample reward. Capt. Paddy Carr, remarkable for his being concerned in many murders committed on the loyal inhabitants of this province, is missed by the Rebels, and we hope is among the slain.

The severe check the rebels have received from the heroic Col. Campbell, and the brave officers and men he had the honor to command in the engagement of Friday last, must deter them from making incursions in future into the settlements of the loyal inhabitants of this province, who entertain a grateful sense of, and cannot too much applaud the services of the army on that occasion (*The Royal Georgia Gazette* 1781).

Our evaluation of this battle, or heavy skirmish, is that it was a Patriot victory. Another engagement between the Patriot forces and the British took place near the same place [near Harris' Bridge on the Ogeechee Road, approximately 7 miles from Savannah, approaching the Ogeechee Ferry] in late May 1782. That engagement, which is described in a May 24 letter by Major General Anthony Wayne published in a Patriot newspaper, is also best described as a Patriot victory (Wayne 1782; *The Independent Gazetteer* 1782:2).

5.38 1783-1827

Following the American victory in the Revolutionary War, many tracts of land in the 13 colonies owned by Loyalists were confiscated and awarded or sold to Patriots. On December 17, 1783, the Commissioners for the sales of confiscated estates offered for sale, "500 acres, late the property of Sir James Wright, pine land, and known by the name of Fort Argyle Tract" (Warren 2018). Governor Wright had owned thousands of acres in coastal Georgia, including the Fort Argyle Tract, which were all confiscated and sold.

Fort Argyle's military role was briefly revived in the late 1780s as the State of Georgia responded to a threat of Indian attack. In Brigade Orders issued on February 14, 1788, Fort Argyle was made a rendezvous point for the Chatham County Battalion, Georgia militia. The orders stated, "Those of Chatham to rendezvous at Fort Argyle as well to protect the specific supplies lodged at the Ferry..." (Lucas 1862:3). On February 17, 1788, in response to the Indian threat, Lieutenant Sheftall, commanding a detachment of Chatham County militia, was ordered by Brigadier General James Jackson to march from Savannah and establish a post, "as close to Fort Argyle as possible". Jackson ordered Sheftall to, "Keep a scout up and down from Fort Argyle" (Wilson 1889:81-82). Colonel Caleb Howell, Georgia militia, wrote to George Walton on October 4, 1789 from Buck Creek in Effingham County stating,

I am last eveing from Great ogechee and am exceeding Sorrey to inform your honour the unhappey Situation of those inhabitation on the South of the river their disagreeable newes we have from -- the treatye Ground and the depredations Committed Since McGilverys departure on Capt Bird by taking fore [four] -- negroes and one hors [horse] and three horses from Mr Lastinger theare [there] is a party in pursute who had not returned when I left that -- -- I have two Six

pounders which I Shall immediately Send to the protection of this County if your honour thinks fit I will have the old forts put in repeare [repair] we Shall want som powder and balls Swords if to be had and likewise Some way of suppleys as we Shall not be able to Git men in to the field with out -- in the absents of Genearel Jackson I Shall forward every accremft [accoutrement] necessary and Shall be happy to heare from your honour as Soon as Convenient (Howell 1789:1-2).

By this period Fort Argyle was primarily used as a reference point in documents dealing with civilian activities. It was a useful reference for plats, deeds, and newspaper advertisements associated with civilian properties in and around Fort Argyle. Several such examples are cited below.

Thomas Savage owned property very near Fort Argyle by the late eighteenth century. Charles Hateley, an engineer, placed a notice in the Savannah newspaper in June, 1785, which stated, "Carpenters, Bricklayers, Smiths, and other Artificers, with a few Negro Axemen, may be sure of employ, good treatment, and regular pay, by applying to Mr. Savage at Ogechee, or, at Fort Argyle" (*The Gazette of the State of Georgia* 1785:2). A Sheriff's sale on February 1, 1792, advertised lands, "being the Real Estate of the late Thomas Savage, Esq. deceased, seized and taken under execution", which included a 500-acre tract of land, "situate near Fort Argyle" (*Georgia Gazette* 1792a:2). A Sheriff's sale in May, 1792, advertised, "all those Two Tracts of land, containing in the whole 1,000 ac, in the parish of St. Philip, bounded by public lands where Fort Argyle formerly stood, and creeks leading from Great Ogechee river, seized and taken under execution as of the estate and property of the late Thomas Savage esquire" (*Georgia Gazette* 1792b:2). A Sheriff's sale in November, 1826, advertised lands, "formerly the property of the estate of Thos. Savage, the elder, deceased", which included a 500-acre tract, "situate in the county of Bryan, on the said river Ogechee, near old fort Argyle" (*Savannah Georgian* 1826:3).

The Savage name continued in the Fort Argyle area. William Savage purchased a 2,229-acre plantation known as Silk Hope in 1839 (Bryan County Deed Book E:385). The large tract was immediately upstream from Fort Argyle.

John Milledge (probably John Milledge, Jr.) also owned property near Fort Argyle in the early nineteenth century. Two real estate advertisements that mentioned Fort Argyle appeared in an 1811 Savannah newspaper. The first was placed by John Milledge of Augusta, Georgia, which offered, "A tract in Scriven County near Fort Argyle, on Ogechee river, containing eleven hundred acres" (*Columbian Museum and Savannah Advertiser* 1811a:3). The other advertisement offered 500 acres, Parish of St. Philip, bounded Northeast by William Butler and John Milledge by Thomas Burrington. 500 Acres bounded north by Great Ogechee River, northwest by Fort Argyle Tract, east by D.N. Rivers, South by D. Huguenin, and Southwest by Jas. Reid. The above two tracts confiscated as the property of Sir James Wright" (*Columbian Museum and Savannah Advertiser* 1811b:2).

Assorted documents mention another Fort Argyle resident in passing. John Waldron is listed as a resident of Fort Argyle in an April 1793 list of letters being held in the Savannah post office (*Georgia Gazette* 1793:2). An 1802 newspaper advertisement placed by Hannah Green, administratrix of the estate of John Waldron, stated, "On Monday the 13th of September next, will be sold, at the house of Jacob Green,

at Fort Argyle, in Bryan County, All the Personal Estate of John Waldron, deceased" (*Georgia Gazette* 1802:2).

5.39 1828-1863

Civil Engineer Benjamin Wright wrote in 1828 about the feasibility of constructing a canal to connect the Altamaha and Ogeechee rivers, which would have gone "near Fort Argyle" (*Southern Recorder* 1828:2). While a canal was completed that connected the Savannah and Ogeechee rivers, the Altamaha to Ogeechee canal was never built.

Adiel Sherwood wrote this brief description of Fort Argyle in 1829, "fort Argyle is on the west bank of the Ogechee, in Bryan co., 4 miles above the mouth of the Canoochee, & 6 above Ogechee bridge. This Fort was built in 1733, to protect the early settlers from invasion by the Spaniards, but it is now in ruins. Here the canal from Savannah enters the Ogechee" (Sherwood 1829:109). Sherwood further added, "The canal from the Alatomaha to Savannah passes this river near Fort Argyle, and when completed, will much enhance the value of lands on the Ogechee" (Sherwood 1829:144).

A bill was passed in the Georgia Legislature in 1835, "To authorize Benjamin S. Waldin to establish a ferry across the Great Ogeechee, at or near Fort Argyle, in the county of Bryan" (*The Federal Union* 1835:2). The 1835 Act was to, "authorize and empower Benjamin S. Wauldin, his heirs and assigns, of the county of Bryan, to establish a ferry across the Great Ogeechee river, at or near Fort Argyle, in the county of Bryan: Provided, it does not interfere with the rights of any other person". The act authorized Wauldin:

to demand and receive toll at the several rates established by the following table, to wit: for each foot passenger, six and a quarter cents; for each horse and rider, twelve and a half cents; for each gig and sulky, twenty-five cents; for every cart and horse, twelve and a half cents; for each cart and two horses, eighteen and three-fourths cents; for every wagon and team, fifty cents; for every four wheel pleasure carriage, fifty cents; for every stage, or carriage of like description, seventy-five cents; for every two horse wagon, thirty-seven and a half cents; for every four wheel wagon, drawn by one horse, eighteen and three quarter cents; for each horse or mule, six and a quarter cents; for every head of neat or stock cattle, two cents; for every head of hogs or sheep, one cent: Provided, also, that the said Benjamin S. Wauldin shall be responsible for accidents that may occur in passing said ferry on account of negligence or inability of the ferry-man... And be it further enacted by the authority aforesaid, That it shall be the duty of the said Benjamin S. Wauldin, his heirs and assigns, as soon as said ferry goes into operation, to fix a board in a conspicuous situation on each landing place thereof, which board shall be painted black, with white legible characters written on the same, noting the different rates of ferriage as herein allowed; and in case of refusal or neglect so to do, he shall incur the forfeit pointed out by law in the twelfth division of the chapter of Prince's Digest, relating to roads, bridges and ferries (State of Georgia 1835, Volume 1:96-97).

A newspaper summary of the meeting of Commissioners of Public Roads for Chatham County in December 1839 noted that the commissioners had authorized a new road, "to be opened from or near

the 8 mile post on the Great Ogeechee Road to Fort Argyle Ferry on the Great Ogeechee River" (*Savannah Daily Georgian* 1839:2).

Acts passed by the Georgia Legislature in 1849 included, "An act to authorize John Dillon, of the county of Chatham, to erect a Toll Bridge over the great Ogeechee River, on his own land, near Fort Argyle" (*Daily Constitutionalist* 1849:2). The 1849 Act authorized John Dillon to,

erect a toll bridge over the Great Ogeechee river on his own land, near Fort Argyle, and to demand and receive the same rates of toll as are now demanded and received for ferriage at Fort Argyle ferry: Provided, That said bridge shall have a draw sufficient for the free passage of vessels or steamboats navigating the said river [Illegible Text] and that the piles and supporters of the same shall be so placed as not to impede the navigation of the river by [Illegible Text] flats, floats, or boats (Georgia, State of 1849-1850, Vol. 1:65).

Several nineteenth century state Supreme Court cases involved bridge construction near the site of Fort Argyle. The Georgia Supreme Court decided the case of Richard McLeod and other trustees versus Henry K. Burroughs, defendant in 1851. The case addressed a dispute over the construction of a bridge near Fort Argyle (Jenkins 1851:215-223). The Georgia Supreme Court, in the case of Richard H. McLeod and others versus The Savannah, Albany and Gulf Railroad Company, defendants, was decided in 1858. It also involved a dispute over construction of a bridge on the Ogeechee River. The Legislature, in 1806, authorized Joseph Hill to,

erect a toll bridge across the Great Ogeechee, at a particular place; and the Act provides that it shall not be lawful for any one to erect any other bridge within five miles above or below. The toll bridge was built, and has been kept up ever since. In 1847 and 1851, the Legislature authorized the construction of a railway across the same river, between Savannah and Albany, which would necessarily cross near the first bridge, and which was actually carried across, within a mile and a half below the same.

Held, that the franchise granted to the Railroad Company was not the same as that conferred on the first grantee, nor so similar as to be deemed an infringement upon the prior charter, in the senses in which a new bridge or ferry interferes with one previously established at the same point; and that no injunction will be granted, nor compensation decreed, by way of damages in such case (Erskine 1859:445-463).

The earliest deed record noting that it contained Fort Argyle was the March 8, 1852 sale of the 200-acre Fort Argyle Tract from Obediah Maye to George Moore (Bryan County Deed Book G:276). That deed noted that the tract was originally granted to Benjamin Waldron. A loose plat dated March 5, 1832 indicated the original grant of 200 acres on the west side of the Ogeechee River, which contained "Argyle bluff", was issued to Benjamin Waldron. No records of Waldron's ownership have been located elsewhere in the surviving Bryan County land records (Braley et al. 1985:27, 28, Figure 6).

5.40 1864

On December 8, 1864, Major General Howard and General Corse, U.S. Army officers in William T. Sherman's March to the Sea campaign, examined the crossing conditions on the Ogeechee River. General Howard noted,

On reaching the Savannah Canal, we found the canal bridge burned. A new one was made in less than half an hour. The Ogeechee bridge, near the canal's mouth, called Dillen's Ferry, a mile and a half above, I found practicable for a pontoon-bridge. During the day that section of the pontoon-bridge which had been with General Blair's column, was sent to Dillen's Ferry, near Fort Argyle, and laid across the Ogeechee, thus substantially uniting my two right columns (Moore 1866, Vol. 9:15).

The following day, General Howard further noted, "that section of the pontoon-bridge which had been with General Blair's column, was sent to Dillen's Ferry, near Fort Argyle, and laid across the Ogeechee, thus substantially uniting my two right columns". On December 10, Howard noted that General Judson Kilpatrick had been directed, "to aid me in opening communication with the fleet. I therefore sent him across the pontoon-bridges, near Fort Argyle, to reconnoiter Fort McAllister and the inlets in that vicinity, and, if practicable, to take the Fort" (Moore 1866, vol. 9:16).

Sometime prior to 1891 the Fort Argyle Brick and Lumber Company was founded. It purchased the Fort Argyle Tract. That company sold a portion of their land holdings, including the brick kiln and several associated buildings to Hull and Company in 1891. The Fort Argyle Brick and Lumber Company sold additional lands to Stephen Allen Roake in 1911. Roake, who apparently acquired the Fort Argyle Tract from Hull and Company, leased the Fort Argyle Tract in 1912 to the Georgia-Carolina Lumber Company. The Georgia-Carolina Lumber Company later purchased the property, although their deed included a clause that prohibited the company from disturbing, "the trees and grounds around the Old Fort Argyle Residence Location containing one acre." The property was leased and later purchased from the Georgia-Carolina Lumber Company by R.C. Jacobs (Bryan County Deed Books Q:587; FF:150, 408-410; 2X:484; Braley et al. 1985:27, 29).

Fort Argyle's role as a military place ceased after Sherman's troops conquered the Georgia coast in December 1864. It would not be resurrected until the creation of Fort Stewart as a U.S. Army base in July 1940, when the U.S. Army purchased 5,000 acres near Hinesville, Georgia as an artillery training center, officially designated as Camp Stewart. The U.S. Government purchased the property from R.C. Jacobs in 1942 as part of the Fort Stewart Reservation (Bryan County Deed Books 2X:484). The military base grew dramatically during World War II. Camp Stewart was deactivated on September 30, 1945 but the base was reopened in August 1950 as a result of the Korean crisis. By late 1953, the base's role as an artillery training center was expanded to include tank training. On March 21, 1956 Camp Stewart was renamed Fort Stewart. Fort Stewart became home to the 24th Infantry Division and the 3rd Infantry Division. The fort remains a U.S. Army installation and has grown to more than 280,000 acres (not including Hunter AAF) covering portions of five Georgia counties, which makes it the largest U.S. army installation east of the Mississippi River. Today, Fort Argyle site rests on the eastern edge of the very active Fort Stewart Military Reservation (Thomas et al. 1995; MARCOA Media 2014).

6.0 ARCHAEOLOGY AT FORT ARGYLE

6.1 Metal Detector Survey Results

The systematic metal detector (MD) survey of most of the Fort Argyle site explored 159 metal readings, or targets. The MD survey covered all areas within the GPR survey grid, as well as additional areas to the west, northwest and southwest of the GPR grids.

6.2 GPR Survey Results

Most of the Fort Argyle site was sampled by ground penetrating radar (GPR). Radar data from eight GPR grids were collected. GPR Blocks A, B and C were surveyed in April 2018, while GPR Blocks D through H were surveyed in January 2019.

GPR Blocks A, B and C provided the most extensive GPR coverage. These three blocks covered the area from 2961N to 3061N and from 8154E to 8189.5E. The bank of the Ogeechee River dictated the eastern boundary of these three grid blocks. A total of 4,835.7 m of radargram data was collected from 222 radargrams that were gathered in these three grid blocks.

As the project fieldwork neared its conclusion in late January, additional GPR samples were collected from selected portions of the site where excavation information was lacking. Within these grid samples the transect spacing was narrowed from 50 cm to 25 cm. This closer interval provides a refined view of the radar data. In two of the blocks (GPR Blocks G and H) an 800 MHz antenna was used in place of the 500 MHz. The 800 MHz antenna provides better radar information for shallow subsurface features.

6.3 Previous Excavation Blocks A through S

Excavation Blocks A through S were defined by Elliott (1997) as applied to the 1985 and 1995-1996 test unit excavations at Fort Argyle. The following section contains brief summaries of each of these excavation blocks. Readers desiring greater details on any of these early excavation blocks are directed to Elliott (1997) or Braley et al. (1985). Appendix H is a composite plan map of features and excavation areas from the 1985 and 1995-1996 excavations, as well as the 2018-2019 investigations.

Block A was a 2 m by 2 m block excavated near the northern end of 9BN28 in 1996. It was composed of two, 2 m east-west by 1 m north-south tests (Test Units 38 and 40). Its southwestern corner was at 3034.7N, 8174.8E. It yielded one feature, F191, which was a possible pit. Block A yielded 38 historic and 59 aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of six historic sherds from Block A produced a Mean Ceramic Date (MCD) of 1732.5 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 103).

Block B was an irregular-shaped block excavated in 1996. It was composed of Test Units 33, 39 and 41. Its southwestern corner (Test Unit 33) was at 3023.7N, 8176.8E. Block B yielded one feature, F177, which was a probable historic human burial shaft. Block B was revisited in 2019 with the excavation of Block AI. Block B was located north of Fort Argyle. Block B yielded 33 historic and 24 aboriginal artifacts (Elliott 1997:106, Table 2). No MCD was calculated for Block B because of the low frequency of ceramics.

Block C was composed of three, 1 m by 1 m units (Test Units 43, 44 and 45), which were excavated in 1985 and three, 2 m by 1 m units (Test Units 36, 37 and 42) excavated in 1996. Its southwestern corner (Test Unit 42) was at 3008.7N, 8174.8E. This block explored the northeastern corner of Fort Argyle. Block C yielded 11 features, including Features 63-68 (F63-F68), and Features 182, 183, 186, 187 and 192 (F182, F183, F186, F187 & F192). Block C produced 481 historic and 34 aboriginal artifacts. A sample of 36 historic sherds from Block C produced an MCD of 1734.4 (Elliott 1997:106, Table 2; 110).

Block D was excavated in 1985. It was composed of five, 1 m by 1 m units (Test Units 46-50), which formed a 5 m north-south by 1 m east-west excavation. The block's southwestern corner was at 3009.7N, 8165.8E. Block D uncovered six features, including Features 27, 28, 31, 32, 34 and 35 (F27, F28, F31, F32, F34 & F35). Block D yielded 249 historic and 21 aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 16 historic sherds from Block D produced an MCD of 1734.1 (Elliott 1997:106, Table 2; 110).

Block E was composed of a 2 m by 2 m square (Test Unit 69), which was excavated in 1985 and four, 2 m by 1 m units (Test Units 13-16) excavated in 1996. Its southwestern corner (Test Unit 15) was at 3004.7N 8164.8E. Block E contained 21 features, including Features 1-9, 138, 139, 141-144, 146, 147, 149, and 150-152 (F1-F9, F138, F139, F141-F144, F146, F147, F149 & F150-F152). A small portion of Block E was revisited in 2018 and 2019 with the excavation of Block U. Block E yielded 382 historic and 42 aboriginal artifacts. A sample of 60 historic sherds from Block E produced an MCD of 1738.5 and a sample of 31 pipe stems yielded a tobacco pipe stem date of 1734.2 (Elliott 1997:106, Table 2; 113).

Block F was composed of a single 2 m by 2 m square (Test Unit 68), which was excavated in 1985. Its southwestern corner was at 3009.7N, 8149.8E. Block F yielded one feature, F36. Block F produced 130 historic and 15 aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 21 historic sherds from Block F produced an MCD of 1743.2 (Elliott 1997:106, Table 2; 113).

Block G was composed of one, 2 m east-west by 1 m north-south unit (Test Unit 35), which was excavated in 1996. Its southwestern corner was at 2999.7N, 8171.8E. Block G uncovered two features, F180 and F181. Block G yielded 90 historic and five aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 12 historic sherds from Block G produced an MCD of 1734.8 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 113).

Block H was composed of one, 2 m by 2 m excavation (designated Test Unit 237), which was dug in 1985. Its southwestern corner was at 2995.7N, 8156.8E. Block H encompassed one feature, F54. Block H contained 70 historic and four aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of nine historic sherds from Block H produced an MCD of 1739.6 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 113).

Block I was composed of one, 2 m north-south by 1 m east-west test unit (Test Unit 32) excavated in 1996. Its southwestern corner was at 2991.7N, 8165.8E. Block I yielded one feature, F176. Block I relinquished 251 historic and 17 aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 19 historic sherds from Block C produced an MCD of 1749.7 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 113).

Block J was a large, irregular excavation block composed of one, 2 m by 2 m square (Test Unit 71) excavated in 1985 and Test Units 18, 19, 20, 26, 28, 29, 30, 31 and 34), which were excavated in 1996. Block J's southwestern corner (Test Unit 30) was at 2987.7N, 8166.8E. Block J encompassed 23 features, including F154-F164, F166, F167, F172-F175, F178, F179, F184, F185, F188, and F189. A small portion of Block J was further explored in 2018 and 2019 within Block T. Block J yielded 2,587 historic and 47 aboriginal artifacts. A sample of 229 historic sherds from Block J produced an MCD of 1747.8 and a sample of 54 tobacco pipe stems yielded a tobacco pipe stem date of 1747.6 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 123).

Block K was a 4 m by 1 m excavation composed of two, 2 m east-west by 1 m north-south units (Test Units 23 and 27), which were completed in 1996. The block's southwestern corner was at 2988.7N, 8151.8E. Block K yielded one feature, F165. Block K contained 165 historic and 27 aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 18 historic sherds from Block K produced an MCD of 1738.2 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 123).

Block L was a 5 m east-west by 1 m north-south excavation composed of five, 1 m by 1 m units (Test Units 51-55), which were excavated in 1985. Its southwestern corner was at 2985.7N 8139.8E. Block L revealed three features, F24-F26. Block L had a total of 380 historic and 39 aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 27 historic sherds from Block L produced an MCD of 1735.3 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 123).

Block M was composed of one, 2 m by 2 m test (Test Unit 72), which was excavated in 1985. Its southwestern corner was at 2982.7N, 8175.8E. Block M yielded four features, F19-F22. Block M tallied 261 historic and one aboriginal artifacts. A sample of 48 historic sherds from Block M produced an MCD of 1739.7 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 123).

Block N was a large, irregular excavation composed of five, 1 m by 1 m tests (Test Units 56, 57, 58, 59 and 60) and one, 3 m by 1 m test (Test Unit 74) excavated in 1985 and eleven, 2 m by 1 m units (Test Units 2-12), which were excavated in 1996. The southwestern corner of Block N (Test Unit 10) was at 2973.7N, 8171.8E. Block N uncovered 38 features, which included F11-F19, F43, F44, F101-F108, F111-F113, F115, F117, F119-F130, F132, F134 and F141. Block N unearthed 1,158 historic and 87 aboriginal artifacts. A sample of 250 historic sherds from Block N produced an MCD of 1741.7 and a sample of 54 tobacco pipe stems yielded a tobacco pipe stem date of 1752.6 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 124).

Block O was composed of one, 2 m by 2 m square (Test Unit 73), which was excavated in 1985. Its southwestern corner was at 2977.7N, 8151.8E. It contained 12 features, which included F38-F42 and F45-F51). Block O yielded 104 historic and eight aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 13 historic sherds from Block O produced an MCD of 1747.4 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 124).

Block P was composed of Test Unit 22, which measured 2 m north-south by 1 m east-west. This unit was excavated in 1996. Its southwestern corner was at 2981.7N, 8140.8E. It was located on the southwestern side of Fort Argyle. Block P yielded no cultural features. Block P produced 102 historic and four aboriginal artifacts (Elliott 1997:106, Table 2). Block P contained no dateable ceramics.

Block Q was excavated in 1996 and was composed of Test Units 24 and 25. These two, 2 m by 1 m tests formed a 4 m north-south by 1 m east-west block. It was located south of Fort Argyle and its southwestern corner was at 2967.7N, 8170.8E. Block Q encompassed no cultural features. Block Q yielded 57 historic and two aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 13 historic sherds from Block Q produced an MCD of 1743.4 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 128).

Block R was excavated in 1985 and was composed of Test Units 61-67. Each of these units measured 1 m by 1 m. The block was located on the southwestern side of Fort Argyle and its southwestern corner was at 2973.7N, 8141.8E. Block R uncovered no cultural features. The block yielded 121 historic and 26 aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 14 historic sherds from Block R produced an MCD of 1745.1 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 128).

Block S was excavated in 1996 and consisted of Test Unit 1, a 2 m by 1 m excavation. It was located on the southeastern edge of Fort Argyle and its southwestern corner was at 2977.7N, 8176.8E. Block S yielded one feature, F100. Block S contained 43 historic and seven aboriginal artifacts. A small sample of 12 historic sherds from Block S produced an MCD of 1746.7 (Elliott 1997: 106, Table 2; 129).

Artifact totals from Excavation Blocks A-S comprise approximately 7,171 specimens, excluding brick, daub and mortar. These include 6,702 historic and 469 aboriginal examples. This sample consists of 2,277 architectural (34%), 3,013 kitchen (42%), 193 arms (2.9%), 615 tobacco (9.2%), 26 clothing (0.4%), 10 personal (0.1%), 104 activities (1.6%) and 464 miscellaneous group (6.9%) artifacts.

6.4 LG²ES' Excavations

6.4.1 Excavation Block T

Block T was the first block unit excavated by LG²ES in November 2018 and Test Unit 100 was the first unit designation (Figures 6.1 and Figure 6.2). Block T is composed of four, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 100-103) with the later addition of one, 1 m by 1 m test unit (Test Unit 220). The block exposed 9 m² in the southeastern portion of Fort Argyle and its southwestern corner was at 2984.85N, 8167.89E. These units formed an irregular block that measured 4 m east-west by 3 m north-south. Block T was excavated to intersect a portion of F175, the H-chimney that had been mostly uncovered in Block J in 1996. A major purpose for Block T excavation was to reestablish the 23-year-old site grid by relocating a known feature that contained intact brickwork that could be found relatively easily.

Southern portions of F175F, which were uncovered in Block J by the LAMAR Institute team in 1995/1996, were explored in Block T. These include intact brickwork from the H-shaped chimney pad in Test Units 100 and 220. An associated stain in Test Unit 100 also was excavated. Other features contained in Block T included F200-F205. These features are probable posts and were mapped in plan but were not excavated.

Figure 6.1 Block T, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.2 Block T, photo at base of Level 1

A sample of 40 historic sherds from Block T produced an MCD of 1752.88. The block had a TPQ of 1765 based on the presence of overglaze hand painted creamware ceramics.

6.4.2 Excavation Block U

Block U is an irregular-shaped block composed of twelve, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 109-116, and 141-144) (Figures 6.3-6.6). The block exposed 24 m² in the north-central and northeastern portions of Fort Argyle. Block U contained Features 8, 192A, 207 through 209 and 211 through 216 (F8, F192A, F207-F209 & F211-F216). The westernmost test unit in Block U sought to relocate and complete the excavation of F8. Braley's previous test unit in Block E had sampled a portion of that feature.

A sample of 96 historic sherds from Block U produced an MCD of 1739.60. The block had a TPQ of 1740 based on the presence of Jackfield ceramics.

Figure 6.3 Block U, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.4 Block U, photo at base of Level 1, TU 111-113; 141-144

Figure 6.5 Block U, photo at base of Level 1, TU 109

Figure 6.6 Block U, photo at base of Level 1, TU 110, 112, 114-116

6.4.3 Excavation Block V

Block V is an L-shaped block composed of Test Units 104-108 (Figure 6.7 and Figure 6.8). It exposed 10 m² in the south-central portion of Fort Argyle. This block explored the area adjacent and west of Block I (Test Unit 32), which was excavated in 1995-1996 and discovered F176. The northwestern corner of Test Unit 32 was relocated near the eastern margin of Block V in Test Unit 105 at approximately 2992.76N, 8165.77E. Block V work included additional excavation of portions of F176, as well as F206. F176 was sampled in Test Units 104 and 105 within Block V. F206 was a circular stain in Test Unit 108 in the northern part of Block V. Upon excavation it proved to be quite shallow and lacking in cultural material.

A small sample of 22 historic sherds from Block V produced an MCD of 1754.98. The block had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

Figure 6.7 Block V, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.8 Block V, photo at base of Level 1

Figure 6.9 Block W, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.10 Block W, photo at base of Level 1, west side

Figure 6.11 Block W, photo at base of Level 1

6.4.4 Excavation Block W

Block W is composed of fourteen, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 117 through 128, 218, 229 and 235) (Figures 6.9-6.11). It exposed 28 m² in the northeastern portion of Fort Argyle. This block was exploratory and was placed in an area where no previous excavations were conducted. Archaeologists identified a concentration of non-ferrous metal objects in this general vicinity during the systematic metal detector survey in April 2018, which suggested an area worth examining. Block W contained Features 231 through 255 and 395 through 397 (F231-F255 & F395-F397).

A sample of 95 historic sherds from Block W produced an MCD of 1742.24. The block had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

6.4.5 Excavation Block X

Block X is composed of twelve, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 129 through 140) (Figure 6.12 and Figure 6.13). It exposed 24 m² in the northeastern portion of Fort Argyle. Block X contained Features 217 through 230 (F217-F230).

A sample of 81 historic sherds from Block X produced an MCD of 1747.09. The block had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

Figure 6.12 Block X, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.13 Block X, photo at base of Level 1

6.4.6 Excavation Block Y

Block Y is composed of twenty, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 149 through 160, 179 and 180) (Figure 6.14 and Figure 6.15). The block exposed 36 m² in the east-central portion of Fort Argyle. It yielded Features 256 through 291, 375 and 376 (F256-F291, F375 & F376).

A sample of 158 historic sherds from Block Y produced an MCD of 1736.07. The block had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

Figure 6.14 Block Y, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.15 Block Y, photo at base of Level 1

6.4.7 Excavation Block Z

Block Z is composed of twenty, 2 m by 1 test units (Test Units 161 through 178, 228, 233) and one, 1 m by 1 m unit (Test Unit 234) (Figures 6.16-6.18). Block Z exposed 41 m² in the northeastern portion of Fort Argyle. It contained 25 features, including Features 292 through 309, 391 through 394, and 399 through 401 (F292-F309, F391-F394, F399-F401).

A sample of 105 historic sherds from Block Z produced an MCD of 1743.59. The block had a TPO of 1760 based on the presence of Wedgwood red, dry-bodied, engine-turned, stoneware ceramics.

Figure 6.16 Block Z, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.17 Block Z, photo at base of Level 1, west half

Figure 6.18 Block Z, photo at base of Level 1, east half

6.4.8 Excavation Block AA

Block AA is composed of twelve, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 181 through 186, 202 through 205, 219 and 227) (Figure 6.19 and Figure 6.20). It exposed 24 m² in the northwestern portion of Fort Argyle. It contained Features 310 through 326, 338, 377, 388 and 389 (F310-F326, F338, F377, F388 & F389).

A sample of 114 historic sherds from Block AA produced an MCD of 1744.05. The block had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

Figure 6.19 Block AA, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.20 Block AA, photo at base of Level 1

6.4.9 Excavation Block AB

Block AB is composed of 16, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 187 through 201 and 218) (Figures 6.21-6.24). The block exposed 34 m² in the northwestern portion of Fort Argyle. It contained Features 327 through 337, 339 through 349, and 352 through 357 (F327-F337, F339-F349, F352-F357).

A sample of 139 historic sherds from Block AB produced an MCD of 1751.54. The block had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

Figure 6.21 Block AB, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.22 Block AB, photo at base of Level 1, SE portion of Block

Figure 6.23 Block AB, photo at base of Level 1, N portion of block

Figure 6.24 Block AB, photo at base of Level 1, NW extension portion of Block

6.4.10 Excavation Block AC

Block AC is composed of four, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 206 through 209) (Figure 6.25 and Figure 6.26). It exposed 8 m² in the southwestern portion of Fort Argyle. It yielded Features 350 and 351 (F350 & F351).

A sample of 23 historic sherds from Block AC produced an MCD of 1744.76. The block had a TPQ of 1733 based on the presence of coarse earthenware ceramics.

6.4.11 Excavation Block AD

Block AD is composed of six, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 210 through 215) (Figure 6.27 and Figure 6.28). The block exposed 12 m² in the northeastern portion of Fort Argyle. It contained Features 358 through 363, 373 and 374 (F358-F363; F373 & F374).

A sample of 55 historic sherds from Block AD produced an MCD of 1742.09. The block had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

Figure 6.25 Block AC, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.26 Block AC, photo at base of Level 1

Figure 6.27 Block AD, plan map at base of Level 1

6.4.12 Excavation Block AE

Block AE is composed of two, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 216 and 217) (Figure 6.29 and Figure 6.30). The block exposed 4 m² in the south-central portion of Fort Argyle. It revealed Features 364 through 372 (F364-F372).

A very small sample of eight historic sherds from Block AE produced an MCD of 1752.56. The block had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

Figure 6.28 Block AD, photo at base of Level 1

Figure 6.29 Block AE, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.30 Block AE, photo at base of Level 1

6.4.13 Excavation Block AF

Block AF is composed of four, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 221 through 223, and 226) (Figure 6.31 and Figure 6.32). The block exposed 8 m² in the southwestern portion of Fort Argyle. It contained Features 378 through 387 (F378-387).

A sample of 46 historic sherds from Block AF produced an MCD of 1744.16. The block had a TPQ of 1742 based on the presence of English soft-paste porcelain ceramics.

6.4.14 Excavation Block AG

Block AG is composed of two, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 224 and 225) (Figure 6.31 and Figure 6.32). The block exposed 4 m² in the northeastern portion of Fort Argyle. It yielded one feature, F390.

A small sample of 24 historic sherds from Block AG produced an MCD of 1741.69. The block had a TPQ of 1740 based on the presence of Jackfield ceramics.

Figure 6.31 Block AG, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.32 Block AG, photo at base of Level 1

6.4.15 Excavation Block AH

Block AH is composed of three, 2 m by 1 m test units (Test Units 230 through 232) (Figures 6.33-6.36). It exposed 6 m², well to the north of Fort Argyle. This block was focused on the relocation of F177, a potential human grave first discovered in Block B in 1996, as well as the search for other possible historic human burial shafts located in this vicinity. The block contained two features in addition to F177, which were Features 398 and 402 (F398 & F402).

An extremely small sample of three historic sherds from Block AH produced an MCD of 1771.67. The block had a TPO of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

6.4.16 Excavation Block AI

Block AI is composed of one, 2 m by 1 m test unit (Test Unit 236) (Figures 6.39 and 6.40). It exposed 2 m² at the southern end of Fort Argyle. It yielded Features 403, 404 and 405 (F403, F404 & F405). This was the final test unit excavated by the LG²ES team. A small sample of nine historic sherds from Block AI produced an MCD of 1753.44. The block had a TPO of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics.

Figure 6.33 Block AH, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.34 Block AH, photo at base of Level 1, TU 231

Figure 6.35 Block AH, photo at base of Level 1, TU 230

Figure 6.36 Block AH, photo at base of Level 1

Figure 6.37 Block AI, plan map at base of Level 1

Figure 6.38 Block AI, photo a base of Level 1

6.4.17 Trenches

Nineteen features were identified as portions of fortification palisade trenches at Fort Argyle during the 2018-2019 field work. All features that were excavated or sampled by LG²ES are listed in Table 6.1. Due to the nature of the site with myriad fortification trenches running in assorted directions and the excavation of the site in large blocks both concurrently and sequentially, many of these feature numbers represent different segments of trenches rather than each feature number representing a unique palisade trench. Archaeologists sampled the trenches by excavating 16 of the 19 features in one-meter segments. Time and budgetary constraints, due in part to the protracted inclement weather, prohibited the excavation of the remaining three samples.

A 20-35 cm historic plow zone across the site truncated the upper portions of the trenches. The resultant spreading of soil made feature edges undetectable in that uppermost stratum. Extant portions of trenches below the plow zone generally ranged from 48-82 cm thick, with 64 cm being both the average and median thickness (n=13). Three trenches had problematic bases and were not included in the average and median thickness calculations. Two of the features with problematic bases (F225 and F291) were shallow and difficult to follow. These may represent a different feature type than the others, or merely a shallower trench type.

Linear trench features dominated the assemblage, with features maintaining relatively straight axes. There were three feature intersections at 90-degree angles. F208, F209, and F214 all intersected F207 perpendicularly. Other features constituted acute angular trench corners. This included two discrete palisade corners meeting at 45-degree angles, one in F314 and F388, and the other within F401. Only one obtuse angle trench corner was identified. That was in F363 during excavation.

Trench features uncovered at the base of the plow zone often appeared wider in plan than they were until they were shovel-shaved or troweled to reveal their true sizes. The measurement of feature profiles, at their widest, was a true representation of feature widths. Excavated trenches ranged in width from 30-105 cm, with the average width measuring 64.4 cm. The median width was 58 cm, with half of the trenches wider and half narrower than that.

The profile shapes of the sampled trenches (n=16) fell into several categories. The majority (n=11) had vertical sides, with 10 having flat bottoms and 1 a basin-shaped base. Three other trenches had somewhat more sloping sides that became vertical, with two of these ending at a flat bottom and the other at a slightly angled bottom. The two problematic trench features had either basin shaped or vertical profiles depending on where the real feature bases were.

Table 6.1 Trench Features at Fort Argyle Located by LG²ES

Feature No.	Grid Orientation	Width (cm)		Minimum Estimated Length ¹ (m)	Depth (cm) (Thickness) of Trench	Profile Shape	Evidence of Posts	Linear Infilled Center Trough?	Same as Feature No. (any block) ²	Location in ²		Soils	Comments
		Top Plan	Profile							Block(s)	Test Unit(s)		
176C	NW-SE	80	80	17	70	Vertical sides, flat bottom	Yes	Yes	314; 176A (PE)	V	104, 105, 106; 32 (PE)	10YR4/2 dark grayish brown loamy sand (Zone C) mottled in Zones D & E with 7.5YR5/6 strong brown clay and 5YR4/6 yellowish red clay	Row of posts in central zone, with trench fill zones on both sides.
207 (F8A)	E-W	63	40	31	54	Vertical sides, flat bottom	No	No	251, 327	U	109, 111, 141, 143; 14?, 13? and 42? (PE)	Mottled 10YR4/1 dark gray loamy sand and 10YR5/3 brown sand	The 1985 F8 was actually part of this trench rather than the the cellar it was interpreted as. Feature intersects F208, F209, and F214 at right angles.
208	N-S	40	NS ³	1.32	NS ³	NS ³	NS ³	NS ³	None apparent	U	111, 113	10YR4/1 dark gray loamy sand mottled with 10YR3/1 very dark gray loamy sand and 2.5YR4/6 red and 10YR5/4 yellowish brown clays	Intersects F207 trench at right angle. May be zone associated w/F209. Feature not sampled due to time constraints.
209	N-S	47	NS ³	1.18	NS ³	NS ³	NS ³	NS ³	None apparent	U	111, 113	10YR4/1 dark gray loamy sand mottled with 10YR4/6 dark yellowish brown and 10YR5/4 yellowish brown clays	Intersects F207 trench at right angle. May be zone associated w/F208. Feature not sampled due to time constraints.
214	N-S	105	105	14	82	Vertical sides, flat bottom	Yes	Yes	221, 230, 287	U	143, 144	10YR4/1 dark gray loamy sand mottled with 10YR3/1 very dark gray loamy sand in Zone A and with 2.5YR4/6 red clay and 10YR5/4 yellowish brown clay in Zone B	Intersects F207 trench at right angle.
221	N-S	74	52	14	72	Vertical sides, flat bottom	Yes	Yes	214, 230, 287	X	130, 133, 136	10YR4/2 dark grayish brown loamy sand (Zone A), 10YR5/4 yellowish brown loamy sand mottled with 7.5YR4/6 strong brown clay (Zone B)	
225	N-S	52	30	10	20; poss. 40 or 60+	Basin; or if deeper, vertical sides	Possibly	No	291	X	131, 134, 137	10YR4/2 dark grayish brown loamy sand; overlying 10YR5/3 and 4/3 brown loamy sand and 5YR4/4 reddish brown clay	Both F225 and F291 were similar in shape, soils and difficulty in following. May represent another trench or feature type.
251	E-W	60-100	100	31	48	Sloping to a stepped, vertical side; flat bottom.	No	No	207, 327	W	117, 118, 120, 121, 122	10YR4/1 dark gray loamy sand with small mottles of 7.5YR5/6 strong brown clay (Zone A) overlying 10YR5/6 yellowish brown clay mottled with 10YR4/1 loamy sand.	
287	N-S	60	60	14	76	Vertical sides; flat bottom except at pointed post mold	Yes	Yes	214, 221, 230	Y	147, 148, 151, 152, 155, 156, 159, 160	10YR4/1 dark gray loamy sand mottled with 10YR3/1 very dark gray loamy sand and 10YR5/4 yellowish brown clay (Zone A); 10YR3/2 very dark grayish brown sandy clay mottled with 10YR5/4 yellowish brown clay (Zone B); 2.5Y3/1 very dark gray sandy clay (postmold)	

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Feature No.	Grid Orientation	Width (cm)		Minimum Estimated Length ¹ (m)	Depth (cm) (Thickness) of Trench	Profile Shape	Evidence of Posts	Linear Infilled Center Trough?	Same as Feature No. (any block) ²	Location in ²		Soils	Comments
		Top Plan	Profile							Block(s)	Test Unit(s)		
291	N-S	43	38	10	18; poss. 38+	Basin; or if deeper, vertical sides	Possibly	No	225	Y	179, 180	10YR4/3 brown clayey sand (Zone A); 7.5YR4/4 brown clay mottled with 7.5YR4/6 strong brown clay (Zone B)	Both F225 and F291 were similar in shape, soils and difficulty in following. May represent another trench or feature type.
299	E-W	90	36	12	52	Vertical sides; flat bottom	Yes	Yes	None	Z	161-172 inclusive	10YR3/1 very dark gray sandy loam	Top of feature poorly defined prior to additional troweling. Large daub chinking in posts. Daub has impressions.
304	NW-SE	88	78	4.4	72	Sloping to vertical sides, angled bottom	Yes	Yes	401	Z	164, 165, 171	10YR4/2 dark grayish brown coarse sand mottled with 10YR5/6 yellowish brown sandy clay and 5YR4/6 yellowish red clay; postmolds are 10YR3/1 and 2/2clayey sand. Aligns with F401 and may intersect F299 at obtuse angle.	
314	NW-SE	50	56	17	60	Vertical sides; flat bottom; pointed post	Yes	Yes	176C; 176A (PE)	AA	203	10YR4/2 dark grayish brown loamy sand (Zone A); 10YR5/4 yellowish brown and 2.5YR4/6 red clays mottled with Zone A soil (Zone B)	Intersects F388 trench at 45 degree angle.
327	E-W	40	42	31	54	Sloping sides; flat bottom	Possibly	Possibly	207, 251; F 36 Blk F (PE)	AB	187	10YR4/2 dark grayish brown loamy sand mottled with 10YR5/6 yellowish brown clay	Extremely wet fill made it difficult to discern posts and linear zones.
350	N-S	30	NS ³	4	NS ³	NS ³	NS ³	NS ³	None apparent	AC	206-209	10YR4/1 dark gray loamy sand mottled with 7.5YR4/6 strong brown clay	Feature not sampled due to time constraints.
363	E-W then angles NW-SE	68	66	2	70	Vertical sides; flat bottom	Possibly	Possibly	None apparent	AD	214, 215	10YR4/1 dark gray loamy sand mottled with 10YR3/1 very dark gray loamy sand and 10YR6/4 light yellowish brown and 7.5YR4/4 brown clays	Angle in plan not visible on plan map due to scale. Extremely we fill made it difficult to discern posts v tree stains, and linear zones.
388	NE-SW	60	56	1.3	60	Vertical sides; flat bottom	Yes	Yes	None apparent	AA extension	202, 227	10YR4/2 dark grayish brown loamy sand with 10YR5/4 yellowish brown and 2.5YR4/6 red clays (Zone A); 10YR5/4 and 2.5YR4/6 clays mottled with 10YR4/2 loamy sand	Intersects F314 trench at 45 degree angle.
390	NW-SE	200	100	200	28+	Vertical sides; flat bottom	Possibly	Possibly	None apparent	AG	224	Mottled 10YR4/2 dark grayish brown sandy loam, 10YR4/6 dark yellowish brown and 2.5YR3/6 dark red clays	Entire unit full of feature stains. Extremely wet fill made it difficult to discern posts and linear zones, and impossible to excavate deeply without water infiltrating.
401	NW-SE; NE-SW	103	92+	4.4	64	Vertical sides; basin bottom. Bi-lobed.	No	No	304	Z	233	10YR4/2 dark grayish brown loamy sand mottled with 10YR5/4 yellowish brown sandy clay	Corner trench. 45 degree angle intersection. East line appears to align with F304; west line alignment is unclear.

¹Estimate overall length of trench including other trench feature sections on site plan map that appear to go with it.

²PE denotes number from a previous excavation.

³NS-Feature Not Sampled.

Excluding the three trenches with problematic bases, the trenches excavated during the 2018/2019 fieldwork extended deeply below the base of the plow zone. Trenches ranged from 48- 82 cm thick. The average thickness was 64.1 cm (n=13). The median thickness was 64 cm. Several trenches shared the same thicknesses, including two trenches each having measurements of either 54, 60, 70, and 72 cm. Outliers include trenches measuring 48, 52, 76, and 82 cm thick. While the 20-35 cm plow zone likely obliterated the upper parts of the trenches, reducing their recordable thickness, trenches would have had to extend relatively deeply beneath the plow zone if they were to uphold tall and/or large palisade posts. Four palisade corners or intersections were excavated. Three extended to 60 or 64 cm and one to 82 cm. One might expect these to be deeper than straight-run palisades in order to provide taller supports at corner angles. Five straight-run palisades had thicknesses of 70-76 cm, deeper than three of the corner palisades. Four straight-run trenches were shallower than the corner palisades.

Trench features generally were composed of two soil groups. Those trenches that contained post holes, post molds, and/or a linear infilled zone down the center of the feature usually had 10YR4/1 dark gray or 10YR 4/2 dark grayish brown loamy sand fill. Such loamy sands were the result of decomposing post and topsoil thrown around the posts when the palisade was constructed or repaired. Zones paralleling either side of the feature most often contained mottled clays and with smaller amounts of the loamy sand. The clays were often a mix of red (2.5YR4/6), strong brown (7.5YR4/6) and yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clays. Trenches with only one recognizable zone were usually a mottled mix of these soils. The clay soils were the result of digging deep trenches through sandy clay and into the clay subsoil, then backfilling the trenches with that soil mixture during the completion of palisade construction.

Post holes and post molds were enigmatic in palisade trenches. They were positively identified in seven of the sampled trenches and possibly observed in another four trenches. None could be defined in the remaining five trenches. Post molds in many of the seven trenches did not appear uniformly in the fill and most did not show up at the top of the feature, but mid-way through the feature fill or sometimes not until closer to the base of the feature. Some post molds appeared and disappeared sporadically within trench fill. The reason for post mold ambiguity is unclear, but likely has to do with the following several factors. These include heavy leaching of organic materials in the sandy soil zones, bioturbation of features during and after their use, as well as the contemporary removal and replacement of wooden palisade posts during fort maintenance, fort razing, and fort reconstruction. Such activity undoubtedly disturbed rotting posts, post mold profiles, and soil stratigraphy within trenches. It also resulted in soil from the adjacent and overlying strata falling into and filling cavities made by rotting and/or removed posts. The activities mentioned above also appear to have disturbed linear center troughs dug within the trench and used to erect posts side-by-side rather than individually in post holes or by hammering individual posts into the soil. Such linear center troughs or "infilled centers" were visible in half (n=8) of the excavated trenches, and possibly in an additional three others.

Perhaps one of the most useful characteristics of the trench features is their orientation as revealed by mapping them in plan view. Trench orientations and locations can provide some clues about the shape and size of the forts to which they belong, as well as the number of forts present. This is discussed in greater detail in the interpretations section of this report, while the data is described here. The 19 fortification trenches mapped during fieldwork are aligned as follows. Eight are oriented N-S. Five are

oriented E-W, with one then angling to the NW-SE. An additional five trenches have their axis aligned NW-SE, with one of these an acute corner whose second trench runs NE-SW. An additional trench is oriented NE-SW as well. The slightly greater number of trenches oriented north-south likely merely reflects the greater preponderance of excavation blocks oriented east-west. Those blocks uncovered longer sections of east-west trenches that were in turn given fewer feature numbers than their less-connected north-south counterparts.

The 19 features at Fort Argyle that archaeologists designated as palisade trenches are described below in numerical order. Feature plan views are located on the site map, as well as close ups on the enlarged Block Plan Maps. Feature profiles and photographs are included below. The reader is referred to Table 6.2 for measurements and other specific information related to each feature.

Feature 176C

This feature, located in Block V, is the western extension of a palisade trench originally located during the 1995/1996 excavations (Elliott 1997). At that time archaeologists found and sampled a trench in Test Unit 32, Block I that they labeled F176A and F176B. To avoid confusion and maintain continuity archaeologists in 2018/2019 labeled the newly exposed section of trench "Feature 176C" (Figure 6.39). This feature contained Zones A through D, as well as a separate feature designated F176D. F176C provides one of the better examples of palisade posts aligned along a central axis in the middle of the trench, as well as showcasing the ephemeral nature of the post molds (Figure 6.40). The post molds were not visible in the upper-most plan of F176C. Portions of six posts appeared sporadically vertically with some starting six cm below the extant top of the feature and others not until 20 cm below. The post molds were pointed in profile and disappeared at different elevations ranging from 28 to 40 cm below the extant top of the feature. Likewise, the post mold edges shifted horizontally with depth, changing the linear zone down the center of F176C to a zig-zag pattern in plan. The post mold center zone and trench fill zones on either side were somewhat challenging to follow but were distinct zones and were most visible in the feature profile. The upper zone of the feature contained F176D. This feature was initially recorded during the 2018/2019 metal detector survey when archaeologists located a concentration of lead balls. The number of artifacts and their depth indicated that it was an intact feature, so they postponed further excavation until the completion of the controlled metal detector survey and the beginning of the excavation portion of the project when test units were established around the lead concentration. F176D is discussed elsewhere in this report.

Table 6.2 Fort Argyle Investigated Features 2018/2019 (measurements in cm)

Number	Function	Block	TU	Length	Width	Grid Orientation	Depth (feature thickness)	North	East
175F	Chimney/Hearth	J&T	26,28,29,31, 34 (PE); 100, 220	150	120	E-W	10+	2986.61	8171.36
176C	Palisade Trench	I&V	104,105, 106; 32 (PE)		80	NW-SE	70	2992.02	8164.04
176D	Cache, Lead Balls	V	104	40	21	E-W	7	2993.02	8164.29
177	Possible Burial	B &AH	33 (PE), 232	110	63	NW-SE	44+ Shaft Unexcavated	3024.86	8177.76
206	Post	V	108	35	35	NS-EW	8	2995.68	8163.82
207 (F8A)	Palisade Trench	U	109,111,141,143;14?,13? and 42? (PE)		63	E-W	54	3008.41	8171.13
208	Palisade Trench	U	111, 113	continues	40	N-S	Unexcavated	3007.68	8170.04
209	Palisade Trench	U	111, 113	continues	47	N-S	Unexcavated	3007.60	8170.40
214	Palisade Trench	U	143.144	continues	105	N-S	82	3007.91	8173.97
221	Palisade Trench	X	130, 133, 136	continues	74	N-S	72	3003.12	8173.72
225	Palisade Trench	X	131,134,137	continues	52	N-S	20; poss. 40 or 60+	3003.15	8176.39
250	Natural Soil Zone	W	120,123,124,126	230	194	E-W	1	3008.15	8156.05
251	Palisade Trench	W	117, 118, 120,121,122	continues	100	E-W	48	3009.29	8155.76
251A	Low Spot in Plow Zone	W	120,123	80	47	NE-SW	1		
254	Pit (or?)	W	117,118	314	62	E-W	32	3009.73	8156.26
256	Post	Y	149, 153	40	35	N-S	116	2995.03	8168.41
257	Post	Y	150	32	6	NW-SE	11	2995.67	8170.21
258	Post	Y	145	63	43	NE-SW	29	2996.29	8167.81

Number	Function	Block	TU	Length	Width	Grid Orientation	Depth (feature thickness)	North	East
259	Post(or possible pit)	Y	145,16,149,150	43	42	N-S	34	2995.93	8169.15
260	Post	Y	150	42	36	NW-SE	15	2995.64	8170.88
261	Post	Y	146, 150	47	40	NE-SW	25	2995.78	8169.91
262	Low Spot in Plow Zone	Y	150, 154	70	68	E-W	4	2995.30	8170.44
263	Low Spot in Plow Zone	Y	154	24	13	N-S	2	2994.09	8169.72
264	Low Spot in Plow Zone	Y	158	46	34	E-W	20	2993.45	8169.72
265	Post Mold	Y	157	26	19	N-S	27	2993.35	8168.95
266	Post	Y	157	44	44	Square	28	2993.50	8168.36
267	Post Mold	Y	153	57	54	E-W	39	2994.42	8168.46
268	Post	Y	154	21	16	E-W	6	2994.67	8170.62
269	Post	Y	157	33	10	E-W	4	2992.98	8167.28
270	Post	Y	158	23	20	E-W	7	2993.72	8170.42
271	Post Mold in Post Hole	Y	153, 157	60	57	N-S	29	2993.71	8167.62
272	Post	Y	153	33	24	NW-SE	5	2994.56	8167.25
273	Post	Y	153	13	12	NE-SW	7	2994.45	8167.62
274	Post	Y	157	27	13	E-W	17	2992.96	8168.28
275	Post	Y	154	28	26	E-W	6	2994.25	8169.28
276	Post	Y	153	20	20	E-W	4	2994.55	8168.98
277	Post	Y	149, 150	52	47	E-W	34	2995.41	8169.03
278	Post	Y	150	53	45	NW-SE	18	2995.42	8169.66
279	Post	Y	150	262	24	NW-SE	8	2995.15	8170.08
280	Post	Y	147,151	58	44	NE-SW	58	2995.72	8171.83
281	Post	Y	158	26	25	E-W	8	2993.07	8170.12
282	Post	Y	158	27	25	NE-SW	6	2993.27	8170.83
283	Post	Y	151	26	20	E-W	8	2995.40	8172.12
284	Post	Y	146	24	22	NE-SW	5	2996.37	8170.93

Number	Function	Block	TU	Length	Width	Grid Orientation	Depth (feature thickness)	North	East
285	Post Under Low Spot in Plow Zone	Y	146,147,151	273	84	E-W	17	2996.25	8172.28
286	Bioturbation	Y	151	36	30	NW-SE	45	2995.49	8172.45
287	Palisade Trench	Y	147,148,151,152,155,156,159,160	continues	60	N-S	76	2994.39	8173.32
288	Low Spot in Plow Zone	Y	155	44	43	N-S	0.5	2994.24	8172.89
289	Midden Lens	Y	148,152,156	257	155	N-S	4	2995.72	8174.32
290	Post, hypothesized	Y	160	25	25	Circular	Unexcavated	2993.00	8174.18
291	Palisade Trench	Y	179, 180	continues	43	N-S	18;poss. 38+	2995.76	8176.45
299	Palisade Trench	Z	161-172	Continues	90	E-W	52	3014.34	8149.99
301	Refuse-Filled Stump Hole	Z	176	90	27	E-W	34	3012.38	8155.49
302	Tree	Z	170,171,176,177	112	104	E-W	32+	3013.33	8156.45
304	Palisade Trench	Z	164,165,171	continues	88	NW-SE	72	3015.01	8157.84
305	Post	Z	165	44	28	N-S	9	3014.55	8157.69
306	Modern Disturbance, Rut	Z	165,171	125	50	NE-SW	10	3013.96	8157.69
307	Low Spot in Plow Zone	Z	171,177	171	68	NE-SW	8	3013.17	8157.77
308	Refuse-Filled Stump Hole	Z	171,172,177,178	90	80	E-W	81	3013.47	8158.96
314	Palisade Trench	AA	203	continues	50	NW-SE	60	2995.33	8152.08
327	Palisade Trench	AB	187; Block F (PE)	continues	40	E-W	54	3009.67	8146.04

Number	Function	Block	TU	Length	Width	Grid Orientation	Depth (feature thickness)	North	East
328	Cellar	AB	188,189,218;Block F (PE)	200+	146+	E-W	30	3009.80	8148.90
329	Previous Excavation, Blk F	AB	Block F (PE)	200	200	Square	50	3008.92	8150.48
334	Post	AB	194	33	30	E-W	9	3007.48	8147.27
335	Post	AB	194	34	27	NW-SE	10	3007.46	8147.60
337	Pit, Shallow Remnant?	AB	194	85	68	N-S	7	3007.35	8148.32
338	Tree, sterile	AB	200,201	24	24	Circular	83	3004.73	8151.06
343	Pit	AB	197, 199	130	65+	N-S	42	3005.76	8152.91
347	Pit, Shallow Remnant?	AB	197	57+	55	N-S	8	3006.60	8151.10
348	Refuse-Filled Stump Hole	AB	197	60	38+	NE-SW	70	3006.77	8151.79
350	Palisade Trench	AC	206-209	continues	30	N-S	Unexcavated	2997.90	8145.04
353	Disturbance	AB	192,195	100	36	N-S	11	3007.46	8150.87
362	Pit	AD	213,214	96	86	E-W	14	3013.09	8171.40
363	Palisade Trench	AD	214,215		30	N-S	70	3012.17	8171.11
365	Indeterminate . Wall Trench, Plow Scar, Dripline?	AE	216	200	14	e-W	5	2979.24	8158.90

Figure 6.39 F176C palisade trench west profile photo (left) and scaled drawing (right), Test Units 104 and 105

F176C yielded a wide assortment of colonial period artifacts. Most notably it contained 153 lead balls of various sizes, as well as one lead sprue casting strip from a gang mold. This latter item indicates that lead balls were being cast nearby. More of these lead balls were located inside the palisade wall compared to outside, in the excavated sample of the south palisade wall. The majority of the lead balls were small shot, which suggests that the South Carolina Rangers living inside the fort were shooting at targets along the inside of the wall, or perhaps near the summit of the palisade posts. Birds or squirrels may have been their intended targets. An alternate, and certainly feasible explanation for this distribution of lead shot is that it represents a lead ball manufacturing location within Fort A. The lead balls were distributed throughout the feature from top to bottom. The zones yielded lead ball counts as shown below:

Zone	Lead Balls
• A	37
• B	1
• C	24
• D	67
• E	9
• F	15
• TOTAL	153

- A. 10YR5/8 Yellowish Brown mottled with 10YR5/1 Gray Sand and 7.5YR5/6 Reddish Yellow Clay
- B. Posts. 10YR5/1 Gray Loamy Sand, generally Zone C
- C. Musket ball 80cmbd

- A. Musket Ball 50 cmbd
 - B. Brass Buckle 55 cmbd
 - C. Medium size lead shot 57 cmbd
 - D. Medium size lead shot 56 cmbd
 - E. Cluster of 2 medium size and 1 very tiny shot 58 cmbd
 - F. Charcoal sample 82 cmbd
- Original Zone C Edge @99.7 cmbd
 - Darker Stains visible at 47 cmbd (north line) and 70 cmbd (south line)

F176 Zone C. 10YR5/1 Gray Loamy Sand with areas of 10YR3/1 Very Dark Gray Sandy Clay
 F176 Zone D. Mottled 5YR5/8 Yellowish Red Clay with 10YR5/1 Gray Sand and 7.5YR7/6 Reddish Yellow Clay
 F176 Zone E. Same as Zone D but with largers areas of red and orange clay and more 10YR5/1 Gray Sand

Figure 6.40 F176C palisade trench, south profile (top) and plan in progress (bottom), Test Units 104 and 105, Block V

The 153 lead balls represent 59.1% of the artifacts from F176C. With the exception of F176D (the lead ball cache located at the top of F176C), F176C yielded the highest frequency of lead balls from the Fort Argyle site. Four gunflints also came from F176C, which represents 1.5% of the artifacts from this feature. Combined, the lead balls and gunflints represent 60.6 percent of the F176C assemblage. This is well above the upper end of South's predicted range (6.9%) for Arms Group artifacts in the Frontier Artifact Pattern (South 1977). F176C has nearly nine times the expected amount of Arms Group artifacts when compared with other colonial sites in South's study.

The Arms Group artifacts found in F176C reveal a very different pattern when compared with those from F176A-B, which were excavated in 1995/1996 and are located immediately east of F176C. F176A-B yielded only a single lead ball, one cast iron case shot and five English spall-type gunflints. These seven artifacts represent only 5.7 percent of the total F176A-B assemblage. The drastic change from 60.6% arms artifacts in F176C to 5.7% in F176A-B probably indicates that some barrier, such as a wall or plank floor separated these two sections of palisade wall so that no small lead shot were able to accumulate to the east. Feature 176C contained five gunflints or gunflint fragments. Zone A contained 2 English spall type gray gunflints and 1 English spall-type gray gunflint fragment; Zone C contained 1 English spall-type gray gunflint; and Zone D contained 1 French spall-type (Honey) gunflint. Interestingly, no additional cast iron shot were located in F176C or elsewhere at Fort Argyle by the LG²ES team.

Furthermore, tobacco pipes are poorly represented in F176C. Only five pipe fragments were located, or less than 2% of the artifacts from this feature. Conversely, the 17 tobacco pipe fragments recovered from F176A-B represent 13.9% of artifacts from that portion of the palisade ditch. This frequency is more than six times higher than that observed in F176C immediately to the west (13.9% versus 2%, respectively). This may indicate that smoking was taboo in the vicinity of F176C, perhaps because that area contained stores of black powder or other flammable substances. This difference supports the theory of a wall separating these two close spaces, with different activities on either side of it.

The limited ceramics recovered from F176C suggest they were the trash of the private rangers, rather than the officers. No porcelain and only one other example of expensive imported tea service, a refined salt-glazed stoneware sherd, is represented in the assemblage. Only one goblet glass sherd was recovered, which further supports this interpretation. An extremely small sample of nine pottery sherds from F176C provided an MCD of 1740.92. This feature had a TPQ of 1733 based on the presence of coarse earthenware ceramics. These ceramics provide support that this palisade wall from Fort A dates to the earliest years of Fort Argyle, ca. 1733-1741, when it was garrisoned by South Carolina Rangers and a skeleton staff of Georgia Rangers. The feature yielded 259 artifacts, which are summarized in Table 6.3.

A small sample of six sherds from F176C provided an MCD of 1740.92. While this date is not statistically valid, it does suggest that the feature is likely an early one on the site. This feature had a TPQ of 1733 based on the earliest begin date for ceramics. The presence of one Kasita Red Filmed sherd shows some interaction with Creek people.

Table 6.3 Feature 176C, North One-Quarter, Artifact Summary

Description	Count
Base of Plow zone	
Lead gunflint patch	1
Zone A	
Brick, indeterminate	1*
Daub	423*
Fired clay	25*
Nail fragment, unidentified square	17
Coarse earthenware	1
Burnished plain sherds	2
Undecorated pottery	3
Mission Red pottery	1
Kasita Red Filmed pottery	1
Fired clay	1
Possible Colonoware	3
Yellow Slipware, plain	2
Plain sand tempered sherd	1
Bone, unidentifiable fragment	25*
Goblet base, clear	1
Olive green spirit bottle glass	2
Lead balls	37
Sprue casting strip, lead	1
European flint tool	1
Flint debitage	1
Gunflint	2
Kaolin tobacco pipe	4
Unidentified metal alloy object	1
Flake, chert	2
Zone B	
Yellow Slipware, plain	1
Olive-green spirit bottle glass	2
Lead ball	1
Zone C	
Brick fragment	5*
Fired clay	3*
Nail fragment, unidentified square	1
British brown salt-glazed stoneware	1
Bone, unidentifiable fragment	2*
Lead balls	24
Biface, chert	1
Kaolin tobacco pipe	1

Description	Count
Zone D	
Nail fragment, unidentified square	35
Buckle, strap type, iron and brass	1
Bone, unidentified calcined	3*
Lead balls	67
Gunflint	2
Zone E	
Brick fragment	1*
Mortar, unidentifiable fragment	8
Nail fragment, unidentified square	2
Olive green spirit bottle glass	1
Lead balls	9
Unidentified iron object	2
Zone F	
Nail fragment, unidentified square	1
Refined white salt-glazed stoneware	1
Bone, unidentified	
Lead balls	15
TOTAL F176c	259

*Not included in total

Feature 207 (F207, aka F8A)

Feature 207 was a palisade trench that was uncovered in Test Unit 109 (Block U), when archaeologists established that unit to uncover and excavate the northern part of F8 recorded in 1985 investigations (Block E) (Braley et al. 1985). Excavation of the southern half of Test Unit 109 relocated the 1985 unit, which extended 60 cm out of the south wall and 160 cm east out of the west wall and contained a layer of degraded clear plastic sheeting covering old excavation fill (Figure 6.41). Further excavation of the northern and southern halves of Test Unit 109 showed that F8 was not actually a cellar, as described in the 1985 interpretation and clipped by that excavation unit, but it was a 20 cm wide part of a palisade trench that ran east eight meters across Block U and aligned to the west with palisade trench F251 and F327, for a total length of 31 meters east-west. These combined features create the longest section of palisade trench on the site. The portion of the F207 trench located in Test Unit 109 was labeled F207W to distinguish it from the remainder of F207 to the east. A one-meter sample of F207 was excavated in Block U, but to the east of Test Unit 109, in Test Unit 111 (Figure 6.42 and Figure 6.43). This sample contained no obvious evidence of post molds and the fill was mottled loamy sand. F207 contained the greatest number of trench intersections, with three trenches extending at right angles to the south. These include features 208, 209, and 214.

Artifacts recovered from Zone A, 28-77 cmbd included 41 g of brick, 4.7 g of daub, and 5 unidentified square nails. In addition, Feature 207, Zone A contained 2 possible colonoware sherds, 3 Stalling Plain sherds, 6 yellow slipware (1 dotted rim, 1 plain base and 2 plain body, and 1 trailed), 5 *Sus scrofa* (Pig) teeth, 4 amber bottle glass, 6 lead balls, 4 kaolin tobacco pipe stems 5/64", and 1 kaolin tobacco pipe

bowl fragment. The eastern half of Zone A excavated from 50-80 cm contained 1 plain yellow slipware base and 1 thin, pharmaceutical bottle fragment. Additional information on the elemental composition of the lead balls is provided in Appendix B.

Six pottery sherds from F207 provided an MCD of 1733.0. While this date is not statistically valid, it does indicate that the feature is likely one of the older ones on the site. This feature had a TPQ of 1670 based on the earliest begin date for yellow slipware ceramics. The presence of two Kasita Red Filmed sherds shows some interaction with Creek people.

Figure 6.41 F176C 207W palisade trench, plan and photograph in Test Unit 109, base of Level 1, Block U

1. 10YR4/3 Brown Loamy Sand
2. 7.5YR5/8 Strong Brown mottled with 5YR5/8 Yellowish Red Clay
3. 10YR5/6 Yellowish Brown Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR5/2 Grayish Brown Loamy Sand
4. 10YR5/6 mottled with 10YR5/2 Loamy Sand
5. 7.5YR5/8 Strong Brown mottled with 5YR5/8 Yellowish Brown Clay

Figure 6.42 Feature 207E palisade trench, plan at 80 cmbd in Test Unit 111, Block U

Features 208 and 209

Both F208 and F209 extended off and south of F207 in Block U. F209 is adjacent and east of F208. F208 contained some mottles of red clay in plan view, while both features had 10YR darker loamy sands and yellowish-brown clays. It is possible that both features are zones within one palisade trench. Combined, they are the approximate width of trench F207. Neither feature was sampled due to time constraints. F208 and F209 parallel F214, which is located 290 cm to the east. In plan F208, F209, F214, and F207 form three sides of a rectangle visible in Block U. The open portion of the rectangle is located on the southern side of the block, where F208, F209, and F214 extend into the south wall. It cannot be determined, therefore, whether this was an enclosed rectangle in the past.

Feature 214

F214 extends south off of F207. It aligns with F221, F230, and F287 further south creating a 14 m long section of trench oriented north-south. It parallels the river, and in turn parallels F225 and F291. Those features form a linear trench approximately 2.4 and 2.7 m to the east of F214. Archaeologists excavated a one-meter sample of F214 in the southern half of Test Unit 144 (Figure 6.44). The feature contained Zone A mottled loamy soils in the upper 16 cm of the fill, in a small strip meandering down the middle of the trench. This zone was identified as having contained palisade posts. The zone became thin, mottled, and impossible to discern below 16 cm and throughout the remainder of the feature.

1. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR5/3 Brown Sand
2. 10YR5/3 Brown Sand
3. 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Sandy Clay
4. 7.5YR6/8 Reddish Yellow Clay
5. 5YR4/6 Yellowish Red Clay mottled with 10YR6/8 Brownish Yellow Sandy Clay

A - Macrobotanical sample area
 B - Pollen/phytolith sample area

Figure 6.43 Feature 207E palisade trench, photograph and east bisection profile, in Test Unit 111, Block U

Zone A in the southern half of the feature contained the following artifacts from 30-43 cmbd: 122.7 g brick, 2.6 g mortar, and 8 unidentified square nail fragments. It also had 2 colonoware sherds, 3 Kasita Red Filmed body sherds, 4 yellow slipware (1 plain body, 2 combed body and 1 pie crust rim), 4.8 g unidentified animal bone, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe stem 5/64" bore, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe bowl fragment, and 1 g wood. Zone B in the southern half of the feature had the following artifacts from 30-112 cmbd: 9.8 g brick, 4.3 g mortar, 17 unidentified square nails, 8 colonoware sherds, 9 Kasita Red Filmed body sherds, 10.8 g unidentified animal bone, 1 olive green bottle fragment, 1 English spall type gray gunflint fragment, 9 kaolin pipe stems 5/64" bore, 4 kaolin pipe bowl fragments, 1 English gray flint flake, and 9.8 g charred wood.

1. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR3/1 Very Dark Gray Loamy Sand
2. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Clay and 2.5YR 4/6 Red Clay
3. Matrix- 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Clay mottled with 2.5YR4/6 Red Clay

Figure 6.44 Feature 214 palisade trench photograph and north bisection profile, in Test Unit 144, Block U

A small sample of four sherds from F214 provided an MCD of 1733.0. While this date is not statistically valid, it does provide a clue as to the early age for this feature relative to the site. This feature had a TPO of 1670 based on the earliest begin date for ceramics. The recovery of 12 Kasita Red Filmed sherds from F214 was the most abundant find of this ware in the excavations at Fort Argyle. These sherds reveal interaction with Creek people.

Feature 221

F221 is a continuation of the north-south trench running along the eastern edge of the site in Block X. It is aligned with F214, F230, and F287. F230 may or may not be linear in nature. Extensive large tree roots obscured the eastern side of this feature and the southern side extended into the test unit wall, therefore F230 was not excavated. It may or may not be part of the palisade trench associated with F221 and F287. A one-meter section of F221 was sampled in Test Unit 130. This trench also contained a grayish brown loamy sand zone running along the center of the feature (Figure 6.45). It was visible as a post mold in the feature profile (Figure 6.46). Soil zones on either side and below the post zone contained mottled loam and clay and were consistent with soils and zones in features retaining evidence of palisade posts in their trenches.

One melted lead fragment was recovered from this feature at the base of Level 1. At 34 cmbd archaeologists recorded two lead balls. Additional artifacts came from Zone A, 34-49 cmbd. This included 3.2 g brick, 1 plain delft ointment jar base, 3.4 g unidentified animal bone, 1 olive green bottle glass, 5 lead balls, 1 brass trigger guard, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe 5/64" bore, and 1 melted lead fragment. At 49 cmbd 4 brick fragments weighing 997.2 g were recorded. Zone B extended from 49-105 cmbd. Artifacts within it included 8 unidentified square nails, 1 blue and white porcelain rim sherd, 18.2 g of unidentified

animal bone, 3 olive green bottle glass, 6 lead balls, 1 English spall type gray gunflint, 2 kaolin tobacco pipe stems 5/64" bore, and 1 lead piece. Zone B, 53-95 cmbd contained 1 kaolin tobacco pipe stems 4/64" bore. Other artifacts in Zone B included 3 English spall-type gray gunflints (2 burned), and 1 chert debitage. Additional information on the lead balls is provided in Appendix B.

20 cm

Brick

1. 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Loamy Sand mottled with 7.5YR4/6 Strong Brown Clay
2. 10YR7/2 Light Gray Sand
3. 10YR5/3 Brown Sand
4. 10YR4/2 Dark Grayish Brown Loamy Sand with charcoal
5. 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Loamy Sand mottled with 7.5YR4/6 Strong Brown Clay
6. 10YR4/2 dark grayish brown

A. Bone Fragment
 B. Bone Fragment

Figure 6.45 Feature 221 photograph and plan at base of Zone A, in Test Unit 130, Block X

1. 10YR2/1 Black Loamy Sand
2. 10YR4/2 Dark Brown Loamy Sand
3. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sand
4. 10YR5/3 Brown Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR6/4 Light Yellowish Brown Clay
5. 10YR5/2 Grayish Brown Loamy Sand
6. 7.5YR4/6 Strong Brown Clay
- A. Macrobotanical sample
- B. Phytolith sample

Figure 6.46 Feature 221 photograph and north bisection profile in Test Unit 130, Block X

An extremely small sample of two sherds from F207 provided an MCD of 1765. While this date is not statistically valid, it suggests a late date for this feature relative to other features at Fort Argyle. This feature had a TPQ of 1742 based on the earliest beginning date for ceramics.

Feature 225

F225 is a trench that aligns with F291 to form the eastern-most palisade trenches thus far uncovered at Fort Argyle. Both are oriented north-south and are located near the current edge of the river bluff where they parallel the river and both F225 and F291 have similar physical characteristics. Archaeologists excavated a one-meter sample of F225 in Test Unit 131. The upper zone of the feature was clearly defined as a small basin-shaped pit 20 cm thick containing dark grayish brown loamy sand (Figure 6.47). Beneath this, soils became a mix of clays and loam and the feature edges and base were difficult to follow. The feature was excavated 42 cm below the bottom of the clearly-defined upper zone; however, it is unclear if the base of F225 lies within that depth or deeper. The upper clearly defined zone may represent a palisade post zone, but no definitive post molds could be identified during excavation. Its profile width is one of the smallest of the trenches, at 30 cm. F225 either represents a different non-trench feature type, or a trench with unusual characteristics. Zone A, 31-51 cmbd, contained 1 unidentified animal bone weighing less than 0.1 g, 1 chert flake fragment, 1 unidentified square nail fragment, and 1 olive green bottle glass.

Figure 6.47 Feature 225 photograph and north bisection profile, in Test Unit 131, Block X

Feature 251/F254

F251 is part of the long east-west palisade trench that includes F207 and F327 in Block W. The south side of F251 was first sampled in a one-meter section located in the northwestern quadrant of Test Unit 120. Excavation revealed F251A, adjacent and to the south of F251, to be a modern disturbance or plow zone remnant containing plastic. The northern part of F251 was then excavated in Test Unit 117 in order to better define the feature as well as its relationship with adjoining F254, a feature discussed elsewhere in this report. Excavation of F251 identified a slightly different trench shape in the east and west wall profile than other trenches (Figure 6.48). The F251 trench had a wider upper zone with sloping walls at the top of the feature profile. This zone sat horizontally above the lower more trench-like zone exhibiting vertical walls and a flat bottom. The feature was well-defined and while upper zone soils were dominated by loamy sand in contrast to lower mottled clay and sandy soils, there were no obvious indications of post molds in plan or profile.

Zone A (North and South halves) of F251 extended from 29-53 cmbd and contained: 701.1 g brick, 38.2 daub, and 21.7 mortar. Other artifacts in that zone included 1 blue and white porcelain sherd, 1 refined white salt-glazed stoneware, 1 g unidentified animal bone, 1 lead ball, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe stem 5/64" bore, 4 kaolin tobacco pipe bowl fragments, and 1 grit tempered plain body sherd. Zone B (North and South halves), 53-85 cmbd contained 59.5 g brick, 2 g daub, 4 unidentified square nails, and 1 eye bolt. Zone B (West Wall) 48-66 cmbd, had 2 square nail fragments and less than 0.1 g of unidentified animal bone. Additional elemental information on the lead ball is provided in Appendix B.

Artifacts from F251A (28-36 cmbd) included 5.2 g brick, 1 goblet stem, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe bowl fragment, and 2 pieces of plastic.

Figure 6.48 Feature 251 photograph and west bisection profile, in Test Units 120 and 117, Block W

Soils at the interface of these two stains (F251/F254) in Level 2, 26-37 cmbd contained some artifacts. These consisted of 700 g of brick/daub, 1 unidentified square nail fragment, 1 coarse earthenware rim, 3 olive green bottle glass, and 3 kaolin tobacco pipe stems 5/64" bore. One olive green bottle glass bottle glass and one handmade brick fragment (6 g) were located in F254 at a depth of 12-48 cmbd. This feature had a TPQ of 1742 based on the earliest begin date for English soft-paste porcelain.

Feature 287

F287 shares alignment with trench F214 and F221, as well as with F230. F287 is the southernmost portion of this north-south trench line. In plan view F287 appears to have a linear stain extending off its western side at a slightly northwest-southeast angle that archaeologists labeled F285. While F285 looked like a trench in plan view, excavation determined that it was not, and it is discussed elsewhere in this report. F287 was sampled in a one-meter north-south section encompassing the eastern 30 cm of Test Unit 147 and the western 50 cm of Test Unit 148. The profile of F287 is typical of the site trenches having very vertical walls, two soil zones (a loamy sand/clay and a mottled clay and sand), and vertical post molds (Figure 6.49).

A limited assortment of colonial artifacts was recovered from F287. The only piece of mirror glass recovered from the site, however, came from this feature. Only three lead balls came from F287, which represents 2.5% of the artifacts from this feature. The feature also contained two English spall type gray gunflints and one burned, spall gunflint. This is well within the predicted range for the Arms Group in the Frontier Artifact Pattern (South 1977). Fourteen tobacco pipe fragments were recovered from F287. This represents 11.7% of the artifacts from this feature.

Figure 6.49 Feature 287 photograph and south bisection profile, in Test Units 147 and 148, Block Y

Feature 291

North-south oriented F291 is a trench that aligns with F225 on the east side of the site (Figure 6.50). Archaeologists excavated a one-meter section of F291 running through Test Unit 179. F291 had a basin-shaped upper zone of clay and loam overlying an indistinct area of mottled clay that may or may not be feature fill (Figure 6.51). No infilled trench was identified in the center of F291, other than the shallow basin zone. No post molds could be discerned with certainty, although it is possible that some of the mottled areas were of that origin. F291 parallels F287 for minimally two meters and likely further. The two features may be related.

Only one dateable sherd was recovered from F291, a plain, yellow slipware, which has a median date of 1733.0. While this date is not statistically valid, it does provide a clue as to the early age of this feature in the life of Fort Argyle. This feature had a TPO of 1670 based on the earliest begin date for yellow slipware ceramics, which were manufactured in England. The presence of one Kasita Red Filmed sherd in F291 shows some interaction with Creek people.

No porcelain or other expensive imported tea service pieces were recovered from F287 and only one possible crystal glass tableware sherd was found there. This suggests that the debris deposited in F287 was mostly that of the private rangers and not their officers. This feature had a TPO of 1733 based on the presence of coarse earthenware ceramics. The feature yielded 86 artifacts, which are summarized in Table 6.4. A small sample of eight sherds from F287 provided an MCD of 1750.63. While this date is not

statistically valid, it does provide a clue as to the “middle age” date of this feature in the life of Fort Argyle for this feature. This feature had a TPQ of 1733 based on the earliest begin date for ceramics.

Table 6.4 Feature 287, North One-Quarter, Artifact Summary

Description	Count
Nail Fragment, unidentified square	52
Nail, unidentified	10
Spike, wrought fragment	3
Coarse earthenware	6
Yellow Slipware, brown	2
Sand tempered sherd	2
Sand/grog tempered sherd	1
Clear curved bottle glass, probable tableware	1
Olive green spirit bottle glass	8
Other bottle glass	1
Mirror glass	2
Lead balls	3
Gunflint, Spall type, burned	1
Gunflint fragment, Spall, English	2
Kaolin tobacco pipe	14
Unidentified iron object	10
Petrified wood	1
Secondary flake, chert	1
Uniface	1
TOTAL F287	120

Feature 299

F299 is minimally a 12 m long section of an east-west palisade trench. It is the northern-most trench aligned in that direction that was uncovered. No other trench features could be identified as directly associated with F299. Much of this feature appears very wide in plan – up to 90 cm. Additional troweling revealed a better-defined feature that was narrower in profile measuring 36 cm wide. F299 was first sampled in a one-meter section in the east half of Test Unit 164. The mottled soils at the base of Level 1 in Test Unit 164 and surrounding units made it difficult to clearly identify the boundaries of F299 and other features. For that reason, archaeologists excavated Level 2 to define the features more clearly. Most of the eastern half of Test Unit 165, Level 2 consisted of F299 fill, as did much of the eastern half of Test Unit 171, Level 2. Following the removal of Level 2 in test units 164, 165, and 171, they sampled a two-meter section of the more clearly defined F299 lying in Test Unit 165 and 171 (Figure 6.52). The east profile of this feature section (along the east walls of Test Unit 165 and Test Unit 171) bisected a post mold full of daub (Figure 6.53). The daub likely served as chinking to hold the post erect and secure. One

Figure 6.50 Feature 291 plan, in Test Unit 179, Block Y

Figure 6.51 Feature 291 north bisection profile, in Test Unit 179, Block Y

large piece of daub had a series of deep impressions left by sticks/wood, or wattle. The impressions were not large enough to be from a palisade post, suggesting that the daub was a by-product of another structure that likely had a mud and stick chimney. Daub from this structure was recycled as post reinforcement chinking when needed in the palisade trench. F299 profile also revealed vertical sides and a flat bottom, in addition to the post mold. The feature showed evidence of the linear infilled zone in the center where posts were located.

Level 2 of F299 extended from 20-31 cmbd and contained 74 g of brick, 76 g of daub, 91.3 g of mortar, 5 unidentified square nail fragments, 1 unidentified refined earthenware sherd, and 2 lead balls. Level 3 of this feature was 31-65 cmbd. Artifacts within Level 3 included 428.7 g of brick, 21.3 g of daub, 10 unidentified square nails, 2 coarse earthenware bases, 1 Stallings Plain body sherd, 4 g of unidentified animal bone, 1 lead ball, 1 English spall type gray gunflint, 3 kaolin tobacco pipe stems (5/64" bore) and 1 pipe bowl fragment, and 1 unidentified iron. Zone A, Level 2 was 47-57 cmbd and contained 0.7 g of brick and 1 tertiary quartz flake. More information on the lead balls from F299 is found in Appendix B.

Figure 6.52 Feature 299 plan at base of Level, in Test Units 165 and 171, Block Z

Figure 6.53 Feature 299 and Feature 299A photograph and east bisection profile, in Test Units 165 and 171, Block Z

Feature 299A is an individual post mold located within the F299 palisade trench. F299A, Level 3 was 65-90 cmbd and encompassed 154.8 g of daub with wattle impressions, 2 unidentified square nails, and 1 unidentified iron object. Excavation from 80-90 cmbd recovered 4 square nail fragments, 1 scratch blue saltglazed stoneware cup base, and 1 aboriginal ceramic.

A small sample of three sherds from F299 provided an MCD of 1757.67. While this date is not statistically valid, it does provide a clue as to the late age of this feature in the lifecycle of Fort Argyle. This feature had a TPQ of 1744 based on the earliest begin date for its scratch blue stoneware ceramics.

Feature 304

F304 is a trench that aligns at an acute angle with F401 corner trench to the northwest. F304 may also make an obtuse angle with F299 given the former's orientation and proximity to the latter. Features 305 and 306 add to the mottled soil confusion at the possible intersection of F304 and F299. F305 is likely a post and F306 may be a modern and intrusive rut extending above and between F304 and F299. Features 305 and 306 are discussed elsewhere in this report. Archaeologists excavated the one-meter section of

F304 that extended out of the north walls of Test Unit 164 (east side) and Test Unit 165 (west side). Excavation clarified the eastern edge of the trench here, identifying it as a sharp edge running at a NW-SE direction rather than a wide trench extending further northeast and almost two meters east of the feature's western edge. While post molds could not be clearly defined in plan during excavation, archaeologists noted that the soil in the center and base of the trench was very soft in places and likely once contained palisade posts (Figure 6.54). The north profile of the feature along the north wall of Block Z depicts two areas of sandy clay that appear to be portions of a post and replacement post in the upper 24 cm of the feature (Figure 6.55) The walls of this portion of the feature slope and then become vertical for length of 40 additional centimeters where they terminate across an angled base. It is likely that this lower vertical portion also contained a vertical post.

Figure 6.54 Plan View of Feature 304 photograph and north bisection profile, in Test Units 164 and 165, Block Z.

Figure 6.55 Feature 304 photograph and north bisection profile, in Test Units 164 and 165, Block Z

Seven lead balls came from F304, representing 10.5% of the artifacts from this feature. One French spall type honey-colored gunflint fragment also came from F304 and represents only 1.5% of the assemblage. However, when combined, the Arms Group artifacts make up 12% of the artifacts from F304. This is well above the upper end of South's predicted range (6.9%) for the Frontier Artifact Pattern (South 1977). The presence of nine melted lead pieces in F304 also may be related to lead ball production in this part of the fort. Five tobacco pipe fragments came from F304, which represents 7.5% of the artifacts from this feature.

F304 contained only a few historic pottery sherds, so no MCD estimates were attempted. These sherd included English delftware, Refined white salt-glazed stoneware, coarse earthenware and an unidentified white-glazed sherd. It also yielded two Kasita Red Filmed sherds. This feature dates after 1740, based on the presence of Refined White salt-glazed stoneware. The presence of Kasita Red Filmed sherds shows some interaction with Creek people. The feature yielded 66 artifacts, excluding brick and daub, which are summarized in Table 6.5.

Feature 314

F314 is a trench that aligns with trench F176 C as well as previously excavated F176A (Elliott 1997) to create minimally a 17 m long trench. F314 is oriented NW-SE and runs into F388 at an acute angle, making an incontrovertible palisade trench corner (Figure 6.56). Archaeologists excavated a one-meter section of F314 from its tip in Test Unit 202 to an additional 60 cm in Test Unit 203. Both F314 and F388

had many gunflints. All but one in F314 were located deep in the feature fill at 50 cm below the top of the feature. The gunflints in F388, however, were in the top 10-15 cm of that feature fill. F314 exhibited the classic profile of a palisade trench on the site that contained a linear infilled center zone, another zone, and palisade posts (Figure 6.57). The feature was vertical on the sides and had a flat bottom. A likely post mold with a pointed bottom is visible in the east bisection profile.

Table 6.5 Feature 304, Artifact Summary

Description	Count
Brick fragment	31
Daub	13
Nail fragment, unidentified square	20
Kasita Red Filmed pottery	2
Undecorated sand tempered pottery	2
Coarse earthenware	1
English delftware	1
Refined white salt-glazed stoneware	1
Unidentified white-glazed ceramic	1
Amber-olive spirit bottle	1
Olive-green spirit bottle glass	1
Lead balls	7
French spall type honey gunflint fragment	2
Kaolin tobacco pipe	5
Unidentified iron object	6
Melted lead	9
Utilized flake fragment, chert	1

Figure 6.56 Feature 314 and Feature 388 intersection after excavation; photographs facing north and east in Test Unit 202 and 203, Block AA

Figure 6.57 Feature 314 photograph and east bisection profile, in Test Unit 203, Block AA

Sixteen lead balls came from F314, which represents 7.9% of the artifacts from this feature. Six gunflints, five English spall and one French blade types, were recovered, representing 3.9% of the artifacts from this feature. The feature also yielded two lead gunflint patches. Combined, the lead balls and gunflints represent 11.8% of the artifact assemblage from F314. This is well above the predicted range for the Arms Group in the Frontier Artifact Pattern (South 1977). Forty-one tobacco pipe fragments were recovered from F314, which represents 20.2% of the artifacts from this feature. This high frequency of smoking-related artifacts is noteworthy.

The ceramics in F314 represent mostly inexpensive wares and no fancy tea service is represented. Only one possible tableware crystal glass ware sherd was recovered. This suggests that this debris was left by the private Rangers, rather than the officers. An extremely small sample of seven pottery sherds from F314 provided an MCD of 1752. This feature had a TPQ of 1733 based on the presence of coarse earthenware ceramics. The presence of one Kasita Red Filmed sherd shows some interaction with Creek people. The feature yielded 203 artifacts, excluding brick, daub and mortar, which are summarized in Table 6.6.

The artifacts in F314 are suggestive of soldiers manning their guard posts at the southwestern corner of Fort A, the earliest fort at Fort Argyle, while smoking tobacco and occasionally dropping weaponry

accoutrements. These artifacts are most likely the residue left by the South Carolina Rangers or the skeleton crew of Georgia Rangers who manned the fort ca. 1733-1742.

Table 6.6 Feature 314. Artifact Summary

Description	Count
Brick fragment	48
Daub	20
Mortar, unidentifiable fragment	24
Nail fragment, unidentified square	24
Button, composite type, pewter	1
Coarse earthenware	4
Colonoware, sand temper	2
English delftware, blue and white	2
Redware	7
Rhenish blue stoneware	1
Kasita Red Filmed pottery	1
Undecorated sand tempered pottery	6
Clear curved glass, probable tableware	2
Indeterminate glass, pink	2
Indeterminate glass, light blue	2
Olive-green spirit bottle glass	49
Other bottle glass, light green	5
Nail fragment, unidentified	6
Lead balls	16
Lead gunflint patch	2
Possible gun barrel plug	1
Gunflint, Blade type, French	1
Gunflint, Spall type, English	5
Kaolin tobacco pipe	40
Glass tool	3
Melted lead	3
F314/F388 Boundary	
Brick fragments	10
Mortar, unidentifiable fragment	9
Nail fragments, unidentified square	3
Amber-olive spirit bottle glass	2
Kaolin tobacco pipe	1
Unidentified iron object	9
TOTAL F314	311

Feature 327

F327 is a trench located on the western end of a 31 m alignment that includes F251 and F207. F327 was oriented east-west and extended out of the north wall of Test Unit 187 42 cm. A one-meter portion of the feature was excavated in the eastern half of Test Unit 187. Following excavation, a core of the feature's north wall indicated that the trench extended approximately 35 cm north beyond the test unit

and block, giving F327 a total width of 77 cm rather than the 42 uncovered within the block. The east profile of this segment of the trench revealed one zone of loamy sand mottled with clay (Figure 6.58). No other zones were encountered, and no post molds were visible in plan during excavation or in profile. F327 had sloping sides and a flat base.

Figure 6.58 Feature 327 east bisection profile, in Test Unit 187, Block AA

An extremely small sample of five pottery sherds from F327 provided an MCD of 1763.4. This feature had a TPO of 1762 based on the presence of plain creamware ceramics. The feature yielded 24 artifacts, excluding brick, mortar and fired clay, which are summarized in Table 6.7. While this artifact sample is small, the presence of two creamware sherds indicate that this feature is associated with Fort C, the final manifestation of the Fort Argyle Georgia Ranger fort. The presence of one Kasita Red Filmed sherd shows some interaction with Creek people.

Feature 350

F350 was the western-most trench uncovered on the site. It ran through the western edge of Block AC, for four meters. No other features appear to be aligned or specifically associated with F350. At 30 cm wide in plan, it is one of the narrowest of the trench features uncovered. F350 could not be sampled due to time constraints.

Feature 363

At the top of the plan drawing of F363 it appeared that the stain was aligned on an east-west axis. Upon excavation the feature axes shifted slightly so that it extended east off the west wall of the block and Test Unit 214 for 44 cm. At that point F363 angled slightly to the southeast. This slight curve and direction of the trench make it dissimilar to the other trench features uncovered. It is likely that F363 is part of a

Table 6.7 Feature 327, Artifact Summary

Description	Count
Brick fragment	31
Mortar, unidentifiable fragment	3
Nail fragment, unidentified square	2
Kasita Red Filmed pottery	1
Undecorated sand tempered ceramics	1
Fired clay	1
Coarse earthenware	2
Colonoware, sand temper	1
Creamware plain	2
English soft-paste porcelain	1
Olive-green spirit bottle glass	1
Kaolin tobacco pipe	1
Unidentified iron object	7
Biface fragment, chert	1
Chunk/Shatter, quartz	1
TOTAL F327	56

larger fort corner bastion, possibly associated with the large and amorphous stains in Block AG just to the northeast and to trench F390 within that block. Archaeologists sampled a section of F363 starting at the west wall of Test Unit 214 and extending east one meter. They encountered one soil zone consisting of loamy sand mottled with clay. Feature fill was very wet. The feature had vertical sides and a flat base (Figure 6.59). Archaeologists noted three round stains measuring 4-6 cm in diameter in the eastern edge of the base of the feature (Figure 6.60). Excavation of these revealed that F363B was non-cultural. F363A and F363C were shallow 2 and 4 cm thick stains that may represent the lowest pointed portions of palisade posts, or they may be non-cultural.

Lead balls were notably absent from F363. The feature yielded two English spall-type gray gunflints and one English spall-type brown gunflint fragment and one brass trigger guard. Combined, these two artifacts from the Arms Group represent 4.3% of the artifacts from F363. This is well within the predicted range for the Arms Group in the Frontier Artifact Pattern (South 1977). Six tobacco pipe fragments came from F363, representing 12.8% of the artifacts from this feature.

An extremely small sample of pottery sherds from F363 provided an MCD of 1747.5. This feature had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of one plain creamware sherd. This sherd, which was retrieved from near the bottom of the palisade trench clearly indicates that F363 is associated with the final Fort Argyle occupation by Georgia Rangers in Fort C, ca. 1757-1767. The presence of two Kasita Red Filmed sherds shows some interaction with Creek people. The feature yielded 47 artifacts, excluding brick, daub and mortar, which are summarized in Table 6.8.

Figure 6.59 Feature 363 photograph and east bisection profile, in Test Unit 214, Block AD

Figure 6.60 Feature 363 photograph and plan after excavation, in Test Unit 214, Block AD

Table 6.8. Feature 363, Artifact Summary.

Description	Count
Brick fragment	2
Daub	10
Mortar, unidentifiable fragment	23
Nail fragment, unidentified square	16
Kasita Red Filmed	2
Creamware	1
Yellow slipware, plain	2
Yellow slipware, trailed	1
Clear curved glass, possible tableware	2
Indeterminate glass, aqua	1
Olive-green spirit bottle glass	4
Coin, silver cob, Spanish, Mexico mint	1
Triggerguard, brass	3
Kaolin tobacco pipe	6
Unidentified iron object	4
Flint flake fragment, brown flint	1
Gunflint, English spall-type, gray	1
Flint core, gray flint	1
TOTAL F363	81

Feature 388

This straight feature intersected F314 at an acute angle, creating a palisade corner (Figure 6.61). F388 was oriented NE-SW and 1.3 m of it was uncovered in the Block AA extension. No other trench features were uncovered that align with F388, despite attempts to locate some through the excavation of Block W and the Block W extension. F388 was excavated in its entirety, with the arbitrary line separating F314 from F388 being the south wall of Test Unit 227. Archaeologists removed the F388 fill in Test Unit 227, exposing two zones of soil including predominantly loamy sand with some clay as well as a second zone consisting primarily of mottled sandy clay. The south and east bisection wall profiles of F388 depict a palisade trench with vertical sides and a flat bottom (Figure 6.62 and Figure 6.63). The first zone was a linear one of loamy sand that contained palisade posts. This zone was vertical in one profile and basin shaped sloping to vertical in the second profile. The second zone in both profiles was a vertical trench. Both segments of F388 exhibited flat bottoms, although the south profile showed evidence of the post mold impacting the base of the trench, causing the feature bottom to make a dip beneath the post.

F388 Zone A. 10YR4/2 Dark Grayish Brown Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Clay and 2.5YR4/6 Red Clay
 F388 Zone B. 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Clay and 2.5YR4/6 Red Clay mottled with 10YR4/2 Dark Grayish Brown Loamy Sand
 Subsoil. 10YR7/1 Light Gray Sand mottled with 10YR5/2 Grayish Brown Sand

Figure 6.61 Feature 388 plan at 52 cm below datum with deeper piece plots, in Test Unit 227, Block AA

1. 10YR4/2 Loamy Sand
 F388 Zone A. 10YR4/2 Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR5/4 Clay and 2.5YR4/6 Red Clay
 F388 Zone B. 10YR5/4 Clay mottled with 2.5YR4/6 Red Clay and 10YR4/2 Loamy Sand
 Subsoil. 10YR7/1 Sand mottled with 10YR5/2 Sand
 Clay Subsoil. 10YR5/4 Clay mottled with 2.5YR4/6 Clay

Figure 6.62 Feature 388 photograph and east bisection profile, in Test Unit 227, Block AA

Figure 6.63 Feature 388 photograph and south bisection profile, in Test Unit 227, Block AA

Twenty-nine lead balls came from F388, or 11.1% of the artifacts from this feature. Five gunflints and three gunflint fragments in the feature fill reflect 2.3% of the artifacts. The gunflints included: 4 English spall-type, 1 French spall-type and 3 English spall-type fragments. The lead balls and gunflints combined represent 13.4% of the artifacts from F388. This is far greater than the predicted range for the Arms Group in the Frontier Artifact Pattern (South 1977). Thirty-four tobacco pipe fragments were documented in F388, which represents nearly 13% of the artifacts from this feature.

Twenty-three sherds from F388 provided an MCD of 1748.24. This feature had a TPO of 1733 based on the presence of coarse earthenware ceramics. The presence of one Kasita Red Filmed sherd in Zone A shows some interaction with Creek people. The feature yielded 261 artifacts, excluding brick, mortar, fired clay and one modern plate glass, which are summarized in Table 6.9. The early dates for the historic ceramics and the high incidence of Arms Group and Tobacco Group artifacts is similar to that observed in F314, which is immediately adjacent to F388. This debris represents trash left by the South Carolina Rangers or the skeleton staff of Georgia Rangers who were manning the post on the southwestern corner of Fort A at Fort Argyle, ca. 1733-1741.

Feature 390

Archaeologists established a small block unit (AG) at this location to try to find a northeast corner palisade that might be associated with palisade trenches discovered in Block AD to the southwest and Block U to the south. They uncovered a large stain occupying all the two-meter square of Block AG that they designated F390. Troweling defined its orientation as Northwest-Southeast, lying in two main zones, one central zone of dark gray loamy sand (Zone B) and the other of loamy sand mottled with clay (Zones A and C) on either side of the central zone (Figure 6.64). The large size of the feature in plan and its orientation on an axis other than north-south or east-west suggests that F390 trench is part of a corner

Table 6.9 Feature 388, Artifact Summary

Description	Count
Zone A	
Brick fragment	33
Fired Clay	1
Mortar	53
Glass, thick	1
Nail fragment, unidentified square	17
Bead glass, cane, white	1
British brown salt-glazed stoneware	1
Kasita Red Filmed pottery	1
Coarse earthenware	7
Colonoware	1
English delftware, blue and white	2
English delftware, polychrome	1
Redware	7
Yellow Slipware, plain	1
Yellow Slipware, unusual trailed, pie crust rim	1
Amber-olive spirit bottle glass	3
Clear curved glass, possible tableware	2
Indeterminate glass, amethyst	1
Indeterminate glass, light blue	3
Indeterminate glass, various colors	23
Olive-green spirit bottle glass	43
Other bottle glass, green	3
Nail fragment, unidentified	17
Lead balls	18
Gunflint fragment, Spall, English flint	1
Gunflint, Spall, English flint	4
Gunflint, Spall/Blade, French Honey flint	1
Kaolin tobacco pipe	30
Unidentified copper object	7
Unidentified iron object	13
Melted lead	2
Zone B	
Brick fragment	6
Mortar, unidentifiable fragment	26
Nail fragment, unidentified square	11
Bead, glass, cane, white	1
Coarse earthenware	1
English delftware, plain	1
Yellow Slipware, plain	1
Amber-olive spirit bottle glass	10
Olive-green spirit bottle glass	4
Gunflint fragment, Spall, English	1
Lead balls	11
Chunk/shatter, chert	2
Kaolin tobacco pipe	4
Iron concretion	2
Melted lead	2
TOTAL F388	381

bastion palisade. Archaeologists excavated Zone B in Test Unit 225 to 60 cmbd. They sampled a one-meter section of Zone A in Test Unit 224 to 64 cmbd. Excavation terminated when the soils became too saturated with excessive water seepage to accurately follow the strata. No palisade posts were identified in the trench; however, dark lensing across Zone B may be indicative of decayed posts. The north profile of Block AD and F390 revealed a moderately deep 28 cm thick plow zone in this area of the site. The core of F390 in Zone A exhibited vertical walls and a 30 cm wide trench. Zone B was not excavated beyond 40 cmbd here, so it is unclear if the F390 profile extended beyond the main trench or not. Although, the lowest 2-4 cm of the profile suggest that the feature may have extended an additional 14 cm on the west and 26 cm on the east, making F390 measure minimally 70 cm wide. The large width of the feature and the small size of the block prohibited a precise alignment of F390 to other exposed palisade trenches. In addition, its appearance and location in relation to the other palisade trenches indicate that this is likely a complex corner design rather than merely a singular acute or obtuse angle intersection.

Zone A of F390 ranged from 41-64 cmbd and contained 1 grit tempered plain sherd and 1 olive green bottle glass fragment. Zone B of F390 extended from 41-60 cmbd. Artifacts in that zone included 4.4 g of mortar, 1 unidentified square nail fragment, 1 blue and white and 1 plain delft sherd, 3 grit tempered plain body sherds, 1 white salt glazed stoneware body sherd, 1 unidentified iron object, and 1 Late Archaic stemmed chert PPK.

Feature 401

F401 was uncovered when archaeologists excavated TU 233, a detached extension of Block Z to the north. They established a unit here to locate a hypothesized intersection of F304 and a northern extension of F299. The search was successful as F401 proved to be a corner trench exhibiting a 45-degree angle, with one arm extending toward F304 and the other arm towards the northern-most point of F299 (Figure 6.65). This angle was quite clear both in plan after excavation and in profile, despite large tree roots growing in the unit. Fill was consistent throughout the entire feature with the one zone dominated by loamy sand with some sandy clay mottling. No palisade posts or linear infilled trough was visible in this feature. Archaeologists excavated all of F401 lying within the test unit, producing a south profile of the feature along the unit's southern wall (Figure 6.66). That profile was located one-meter south of the trench angle vertex, revealing how F401 split into the two divergent trenches heading towards F304 and F299. This appears as a bi-lobed feature in profile. F401 exhibited vertical sides extending to a basin-shaped bottom 64 cm below the base of the plow zone.

Artifacts were recorded from 44-109 cmbd in F401. They were comprised of 5 unidentified square nails, 1 aboriginal plain sherd, 4 coarse earthenware body sherds, 1 blue and white delft body sherd, 12 red slipped sand tempered body sherds, 3 plain grit tempered sherds, 4 olive green bottle glass (1 heat treated), 7 tobacco pipe fragments (1 bowl, 1 fragment, and 3 stems). Several additional artifacts were recovered from the south profile between 72-103 cmbd. They included 2 aboriginal sand tempered sherds, possibly incised, 0.3 g of shell, and 1 kaolin pipe stem with a 5/64" bore.

Figure 6.64 Feature 390 and Test Unit 224, photograph and north profiles, Block AG

6.4.18 Cellar

Only one cellar, F328, was excavated during the 2018/2019 investigations and no other cellars have been excavated to-date. Although F8 was interpreted as a cellar in 1985 by Braley, it was not fully excavated completely at that time (Braley et al. 1985). F8 was revisited in 2018/2019 and determined not to be a cellar, as discussed elsewhere in this report. Cellars at Fort Argyle may have been a bad idea for multiple reasons. While the soil is exceedingly clayey and hard to dig, that would not deter officers from commanding soldiers or others under their control to do the tedious digging. Modern excavations in the late twentieth and early twenty-first centuries have shown that the current water table is elevated. In addition, ground water easily and quickly seeps through the walls of a hole, where the clay soils retain it as standing water. These natural characteristics and the discovery of only one cellar on the site suggest that those in charge of constructing the various forts at Argyle quickly learned this lesson and dug no addition, ground water easily and quickly seeps through the walls of a hole, where the clay soils retain it as standing water.

Figure 6.65 Feature 401 palisade corner before excavation photo (left) and plan drawing (right) at base of Level 1, Test Unit 233, Block Z

Figure 6.66 Feature 401 south bisection profile and photograph, in Test Unit 233, Block Z

On the other hand, cellars were a vital method for keeping food chilled during the times before modern refrigeration. Even with the persistent groundwater/flooding issues, some cellars at Fort Argyle were essential for food safety and preservation.

F328 was discovered in Block AB. Following the removal of a thin plow zone stratum (12-18 cm) in Level 1 of Test Units 188, 189, and 218, archaeologists uncovered a large stain extending across all three units that they designated F328. This feature proved to be a shallow, large cellar measuring minimally 200 cm East-West by minimally 146 cm North-South. The feature continued into the north wall of TU 218, beyond the limits of Block AB (Figure 6.67). The feature was truncated on the eastern side by a 1985 test unit, as discussed below. The southwestern corner of F328 was intact, but no other corners were located and archaeologists were unable to determine the absolute size of the cellar.

Figure 6.67 Feature 328 north bisection profile, in Test Unit 218, Block AB

A stain occupying a 40 cm wide portion of the entire eastern edge of TU 218 truncated F328 and appeared to be a modern disturbance. This disturbance was labeled F329 and it continued south of the unit, across all of TU 189, forming a point at its junction with TU 189 and 192. Degrading clear plastic was observed around this juncture as well as in the center of the stain in TU 189 and other parts of this disturbance. This and GIS mapping revealed that the disturbance is the infilled 2 m by 2 m test unit excavated in 1985 numbered "547S, 525W" (Braley et al. 1985:50) and labeled "Block F" on the consolidated 2018/2019 site map. Braley's excavation unit was apparently misplotted by the SAS excavation team as well as the southwestern corner of the 1985 excavation. It actually aligns with the point of the stain in TU 189 designated F329. The southwestern corner of the 1985 excavation falls at 3008.9N, 8149.84E on the 2018/2019 grid. The west wall of the 1985 test unit clearly truncated F328 in TU 189 as well as the feature occupying the entire length of the eastern 40 cm of TU 218. The north wall of the 1985 TU aligns closely with the north wall of TU 218. Modern vehicle ruts were observed cutting through the plow zone of Block F, as well as TU 189, and the northwestern portion of TU 218.

The 1985 test unit recorded a trench, with a post mold in a post hole, running East-West through the mid-section of their 2 m by 2 m unit. Braley designated the stain F36. This feature from 1985 aligns with

F327 trench discovered in TU 187, Block AB, in LG²ES's 2018/2019 excavations. The plan and profile of the 1985 unit also depicts a 45 cm thick stratum on the north side of the F36 trench, directly under the plow zone and extending into the north wall of the unit. Braley et al. (1985:48) interpreted this stain as "...a dug-out area that defies interpretation at this time". The similar alignment, soils, and depth of this unnumbered stain clearly indicates that it is a portion of the F328 cellar located by archaeologists in the 2018/2019 excavations of TU 188, 189, and 218. These later excavations uncovered a large enough area of the feature in plan and profile to interpret it, along with the portion uncovered in 1985, as a cellar. These details are described below.

The F328 cellar was sampled by the excavation of that portion of the feature occupying all of TU 218. Following the completion of that excavation, archaeologists excavated the portion of the cellar F328 and trench F327 lying in TU 188. In TU 218, archaeologists first separately excavated the modern vehicle rut ("Rut") in the northwest corner of the unit consisting of very dark brown (10YR2/2) coarse sand. It extended approximately 17 cm and contained 8 unidentified metal and 13 brick fragments. Next, they excavated a smaller stain (Zone C) beneath the rut approximately 9 cm thick and consisting of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand. Zone C contained a small lead ball and 12 brick fragments. After this, archaeologists excavated Zones B and A. Zone B was located on the northeastern part of the feature and ran beneath Zone A and through the center of the unit. Zone B soil consisted of strong brown (7.5YR5/8) clay mottled with gray (10YR5/1) loamy sand. The zone varied in thickness from 7-21 cm. Zone B was sterile. Zone A constituted the bulk of F328. It had gray (10YR5/1) loamy sand mottled with brown (7.5RY5/8) clay soil. Zone A overlaid Zone C, as well as portions of Zone B and portions of subsoil. Zone A ranged from 10-31 cm thick.

Lead balls, which were prevalent in other parts of the excavations, are notably absent from F328. One English spall type gray gunflint and four English gray flint flakes were present in this feature. Fourteen tobacco pipe fragments came from the feature, which represents 14.4% of the artifacts from this feature. This high frequency of smoking-related artifacts is noteworthy.

The presence of several higher status artifacts, such as white salt glazed stoneware, hand painted tumblers and other crystal glass tableware may indicate that the debris in F328 likely is associated with officers at Fort Argyle. Sixteen pottery sherds from F328 provided an MCD of 1749.38. This feature had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of creamware ceramics. The feature yielded 96 artifacts, excluding brick and mortar, which are summarized in Table 6.10. The dating of the artifacts suggests that this feature is associated with the First Troop of Georgia Rangers and possibly the earlier Georgia rangers as well. The presence of three Kasita Red Filmed sherds shows some interaction with Creek people.

Excavation in TU 188 revealed a highly disturbed context in which the F328 cellar and its later fill cut into the F327 trench fill (Figure 6.68). Boundaries of the two features and their mottled clay fills were difficult to determine due, in part because it appears that trench posts were pulled at some point contributing to the mix of soil from the two features. In addition, one of the modern vehicle ruts cuts through the plow zone and into the features in this unit. It was not until the deepest 10-15 cm of excavation of F328, Zone A soil that archaeologists could differentiate soils from F327 trench fill. For that reason, artifacts in this lower fill definitively constituting the bottom of F327 were bagged separately from the artifacts above it

originally assumed to be Zone A of F328 but observed to be of mixed context of the two features F328 and F327.

Table 6.10 Feature 328, Artifact Summary

Description	Count
Brick fragment	54
Mortar, unidentifiable fragment	5
Nail fragment, unidentified square	14
Coarse earthenware	3
Colonoware, sand temper	5
English delftware, plain	4
Redware	1
White salt-glazed stoneware	4
Kasita Red Filmed	3
Sand tempered sherd	2
Savannah Fine Cord Marked pottery	1
Yellow Slipware, trailed	3
Clear curved glass, possible tableware	1
Tableware, clear glass	3
Tumbler, polychrome hand-painted	1
Olive-green spirit bottle glass	16
Kaolin tobacco pipe	14
Unidentified iron object	7
Flake, chert	1
Aboriginal Ceramic	2
Gunflint, English spall type, gray	1
Debitage, English gray flint	4
Debitage, French honey flint	1
Yellow slipware, brown and yellow	1
Creamware, plain	1
Iron concretions	3
TOTAL F328	155

Artifacts in the base of trench F327 in TU 188 included 2 plain creamware, 1 gunflint fragment, 2 brick fragments, and prehistoric artifacts. Artifacts in the mixed F328/F327 context above included 1 redware, 2 tobacco pipe stems, 1 coarse earthenware, 5 bottle glass, 1 metal handle, 7 unidentified nails, 1 wood charcoal, 25 brick fragments and prehistoric artifacts.

The angle of the southern edge of F328 in plan suggests that the cellar is not totally aligned with the Fort Argyle grid. The feature profiles, therefore, do not cut the cellar walls at 90-degree angles and as a result do not reflect the feature's original true angles. Having said that, it is of some utility to note the documented feature profile. Archaeologists made scaled profile drawings of the south, west, and north sides of the feature in TU 218 walls. The north and south profiles show a flat feature bottom with gently sloping sides to the base of the plow zone. The plow zone obliterated the feature's profile so it is unclear what the upper portion of the feature walls looked like. The profiles suggest the relative order of cellar infilling. Three zones were identified, Zone A, Zone B, and Zone C.

Figure 6.68 Features 328 and 327 photograph and west bisection profiles, in Test Units 218 and 188, Block AB

The north profile indicates that F328 cellar was dug along what are now the bottom lines of Zone B and what became Zone A and Zone C. Prior to and/or during the creation of the cellar, a tree/tree stump was taken down to approximately 40 cm below ground. Following construction and use of the cellar it was filled in with Zone B soils (clay subsoil mottled with loamy sand). At some point thereafter either Zone B fill was cut into and removed then later refilled with Zone A, or Zone B fill only occupied the far eastern portion of the feature and Zone A soil was infilled adjacent to Zone B fill. Zone C soil occupies the lowest 6 cm, just under Zone A. Zone C postdates Zone B and predates Zone A, which sits on top of it. Zone C is dark gray loamy sand that may represent remnant soil or decayed wood flooring original to the bottom of the cellar. Less likely, it may represent a fill episode prior to Zone A infilling.

While the relative dating of cellar infill described above is reasonably straightforward, the relative dating of the F328 cellar and F327 trench is challenging due to several factors, including the very wet nature of the soils in this area and modern disturbances such as vehicle ruts. The west profile of the 1985 unit shows the southern three-fourths of the F36 trench and associated post mold intact. However, the northern one-fourth shows feature fill from what we now know to be the cellar inside the post mold. At this spot it appears that the cellar just clipped the northern quarter or edge of the trench. The 2018/2019 plan map depicts F328 as curving to the southwest from this spot and then angling further southwest to the southwest corner of the feature. It is this remaining portion of F328 that appears to have cut through a 160 cm (East-West) section of the F327 trench as indicated during the excavations of the features in TU 218 and 188. The removal of wooden posts from the trench feature, the construction of the cellar, and the later infilling of the cellar all contributed to the confusing boundaries between F328 and F327 and the presence of cellar feature fill inside trench post molds. In summary, it appears that the portion of the northern palisade trench (F327) in TU 188, 189, and 214 was no longer in use by the time the F328 cellar was constructed. The F328 cellar is located within and three meters south of F299, the northern-most palisade trench identified to date. These data suggest that the F328 cellar was within Fort Argyle's final construction phase [See discussion of Fort C later in this report].

6.4.19 Chimney, Feature 175

Only one chimney/hearth, F175, has been excavated to-date at Fort Argyle. This one may be associated with barracks or officers' quarters. It is less likely to be associated with a kitchen given its H-shaped plan, indicative of a double-room building; American colonial kitchens were more often single rooms separate from living quarters and with a single hearth. One would expect there to be more hearths/chimneys in various living quarters over various fort construction periods. It is possible others were built of mud and stick, although no large areas of daub have been located other than small areas interpreted during the 1985 excavations as being daub associated with burned clay chinking in the north palisade wall (Braley et al. 1985).

Excavations in 1995/1996 had located portions of the chimney base and hearth (F175A-E) primarily in Test Units 28 and 34, but also extending into Test Units 26, 29, and 31 in Block J (Figure 6.69). LG²ES archaeologists excavated Test Unit 100, a 2 by 1 m excavation in Block T in 2018/2019 to relocate this feature in order to better re-establish and cross-check the new and old site grids, and to expand the area investigated around the chimney base and hearth. They uncovered the southwestern portion of the H-shaped firebox extending out of the north wall of TU 100, just west of the unit's center line. In order to avoid potential confusion, archaeologists called the part of the chimney base and hearth uncovered in 2018/2019 F175F. Following this, LG²ES archaeologists established Test Unit 220, a 1 m by 1 m unit adjacent to the north wall of TU 100, situated on the eastern side. TU 220 encountered the central portion of the F175 double hearth on its south side as well as more of the southwest portion located in the west wall of the unit (Figure 6.70). Both TU 220 and TU 100 were established in areas not previously excavated. Archaeologists excavated the Level 1 plow zone in both units until they uncovered the top of the hearth (Figure 6.71). In addition to various artifacts in the 20 cm thick plow zone, they noted a piece of red, overglazed, hand-painted creamware. This type of creamware was not manufactured by Josiah Wedgwood until 1765. This sherd was observed directly on top of the hearth bricks in TU 220.

Figure 6.69 Features 157, 173 and 175 Excavated, Block J, Facing South, 9BN28 (Elliott 1997).

Figure 6.70 Feature 175F photograph and plan at base of Test Unit 220, Block T

Figure 6.71 Feature 175F and Test Unit 220 and west wall profiles, in Block T

The fill from F175F in TU 100 and 220 was excavated separately. A soil sample was removed from the hearth interior in TU 202 for fine screening, as well as for future pollen/phytolith and macro-botanical soil samples.

Two brick samples and one mortar sample were collected from the hearth. Hearth soils were divided by test unit. Artifacts in TU 100 (FS 334) were recovered from 23-25 cm and included 28.2 g of brick fragments, 1 window glass sherd, 1 coarse earthenware body, 1 hand painted (red) overglaze enameled creamware body, 4.1 g unidentified animal bone, and 1 kaolin pipe stem 5/64" bore. Artifacts in TU 220 (FS 337) came from 23-30 cmbd and consisted of 103.7 g of brick fragments, 43.7 g of daub, 2 g of mortar, 1 unidentified square nail, 1 black glazed redware sherd, 2 yellow slipware (1 plain and 1 brown), 1.7 g unidentified bone, 1 clear indeterminate glass, and 1 English gray flint gunflint fragment.

The additional excavations in the chimney area in 2018/2019 located a site grid nail from previous archaeological excavations that was helpful in tying the current grid to previous site grids. The 2019 work also uncovered the remaining portions of the hearth, confirming that it was definitely an H-shaped double fireplace designed for a room on either side of it. Bricks uncovered in TU 220 showed that the base of the hearth was constructed using a mixture of bricks that had broken in half or even in thirds. This suggests that the chimney was constructed when the soldiers had inadequate access to a decent brick supply. They appear to be recycling brick from either somewhere else on the site, or more likely from somewhere else entirely. These recycled bricks may have come from structures in the surrounding area or as ballast on vessels. Interestingly, recycling continued to play a part in this feature's history, as the chimney itself was later recycled when the bricks taken away and used elsewhere. Where the bricks went is unclear, but they do not appear in any of the areas that have been excavated in 1985, 1995/96, or 2018/2019 across the site. The 2019 work garnered good measurements and samples of the few whole hand-made bricks uncovered in the feature, as well as samples of the mortar.

The location of the F175F chimney/hearth is interesting. The northeastern corner of the brick feature previously excavated in 1996 (TUs 26 and 28) cuts the acute angle bastion excavated previously in TU 26 and TU 29. This indicates that the chimney post-dates this particular fort wall construction for the first Fort Argyle (See discussion of Fort A later in this report). This has been discussed previously, as well as the fact that a brick in the chimney excavated at that time contained an embedded refined white salt glazed stoneware sherd (a pottery type not invented in England until about 1740) indicating that the brick and chimney had to date to 1740 or later (Elliott 1997:123). In addition, the chimney is not oriented on the same angle as a structure previously located in Block N, therefore is probably unrelated to that construction, as well. The chimney may be related structurally or chronologically to the palisade trench features running North-South in previously excavated TU 18 and TU 19 (Block J) and TU72 (Block M). The red overglazed hand-painted creamware sherd that was recovered from F175F in TU220 was not manufactured until 1765 or later. This serves to enhance the range when this chimney was in use—from sometime after 1740 until sometime after 1765. Since the fort was shut down in 1767, this indicates that the chimney was used in the final Fort C phase, but it also may have existed in the Fort B phase.

6.4.20 Pits

One might expect a large number of pits to have been dug, used, and infilled with refuse on a military fort site. However, the discovery of refuse pit features at Fort Argyle was rare in the 2018/2019 excavations as well as in previous excavation efforts. Only five excavated features may be pits, and only two of these were well-defined. Both F343 and F362 exhibit classic pit characteristics such as basin-shaped profiles and well-defined edges. None of the pit features can be described as refuse filled, although some artifacts were sparsely scattered in their fill. All five pit features are discussed below.

F254 was documented in Test Units 117 and 118, Block W. It is possibly a pit or other feature type associated with the F251 trench. F254 lies adjacent to the northern edge of F251 for a distance of 3.14 m. Archaeologists sampled a one-meter section of F254 in Test Units 117, following the removal of Level 1 in those units and Level 2 in the southwestern quadrant of TU 117. F254 fill consisted of dark grayish brown (10YR4/2) loamy sand mottled with pale brown (10YR6/3) loamy sand. F254 is bi-lobed in profile, with the western 32 cm of the feature extending 16 cm below the base of the plow zone and the adjacent lobe to the east of that extending to 32 cm (Figure 6.72). The feature's eastern profile in that sample appears to cut Zone A (the uppermost stratum) of the F251 trench. F254 does not cut the vertical trench portion of F251 (Zone B), however, because F254 is 24 cm north of it (Figure 6.73). The fact that F254 cuts the upper portion of F251 indicates that it post-dates the trench. The length of time between construction of the F251 trench and the creation of F254 cannot be precisely determined. While F254 was created after F251, the linear and adjacent nature of the two features strongly suggests that F254 was made while F251 was in use and that the function of F254 is likely tied closely to the presence of the F254 trench and associated structure.

Figure 6.72 Feature 254 photograph and north bisection profile, in Test Unit 117, Block W

Figure 6.73 Features 254 and 251 east bisection profiles, in Test Units 117 and 120, Block W

F337 was a very shallow soil stain at 7 cm thick that may potentially be the remnant of the very bottom of a pit whose upper portion was erased in the plow zone (Figure 6.74). It was located in Test Unit 194 in Block AB. It was a fairly large oval in plan measuring 85 cm North-South by 68 cm East-West. Feature fill was very dark gray (10YR3/1) loamy sand. Excavation of the west half of the feature revealed its profile to be an irregular basin shape. Archaeologists recovered five small fragments of brick/daub, 1 unidentified square nail, and 1 coarse earthenware sherd at an elevation of 44-51 cmbd.

F343 was a pit whose western half extended into Test Units 197 and 199 in Block AB. Additional troweling of the feature after it was identified on the block plan map revealed it to be half of a likely circular stain. The exposed half of the feature measured 130 cm North-South by 65 cm East-West. The elevation of the northeastern edge of the feature three centimeters below the ground surface suggests that this feature might not be from one of the fort periods. However, the relative preponderance of historic artifacts suggests otherwise. Artifacts were located between 29-71 cmbd and consisted of 250 g brick/daub, 4 unidentified square nails, 3 plain grit/sand tempered body sherds, 2 refined white salt glazed stoneware bases, 1 clear and 1 light aqua indeterminate glass, 2 small lead balls, 1 English spall-type gray gunflint, 2 iron hinge fragments and 2 unidentified nails. More information on the elemental composition of the lead balls is found in Appendix B.

1. 10YR3/1 Very Dark Gray Loamy Sand
2. 10YR6/2 Light Brownish Gray Coarse Sand matrix

Figure 6.74 Feature 337 east profile, Test Unit 194, Block AB

Excavation of the western half of the feature revealed a 42 cm deep feature (Figure 6.75 and Figure 6.76). Its northern edge sloped and contained a pocket of fill consisting of gray (10YR5/1) loamy sand with mottles of brown (7.5YR4/4) sand. The base of the feature had an irregular basin shape sloping up to a poorly defined vertical south wall. A lens of gray (10YR5/1) loamy sand with light brownish gray (10YR6/2) sand covered the lower six cm of the south side of the feature. Dominant feature fill in most of the remaining portions was gray (10YR5/1) loamy sand with brick fragments. The presence of plow scars in the excavation block at 100 and 130 cm south of the feature, as well as a low dip in the top of the south side of the feature where the plan map depicts a plow scar intruding through F343 reveals that this area of the site was plowed along with most of the rest of the site. Had there been no evidence for plowing one could argue that the extent of F343 so high in the uppermost stratum was where historic features should be located had they not been plowed. It is possible that this pit may not be historic but merely contain older historic artifacts redeposited in a modern dug and infilled pit. However, given the artifact assemblage, it is more likely that F343 is colonial-era and survived hits from the plow- particularly on its north side – where the plow may have encountered clay pockets or stumps causing the plow to skip over small areas.

F347 may have been the bottom remnant of a shallow pit located in Test Unit 197, Block AB. In plan it appeared to be an oval post mold in a rounded square post hole, but excavation revealed only one type of soil in the feature profile. That was dark grayish brown (10YR4/2) loamy sand measuring 8 cm thick. The feature measured more than 57 cm North-South as it extended into the north wall of Test Unit 197, which was also the north wall of that part of Block AB. Archaeologists excavated the south half of the feature and documented a very shallow, sloping profile more suggestive of a low spot in the plow zone, but still possibly the very base of a shallow pit (Figure 6.77). The only cultural items in the fill were six very small brick fragments that were not recovered.

Figure 6.75 Feature 343 plan after excavation, in Test Unit 197 and 199, Block AB

F362 was a well-defined pit in plan and profile. It was located predominantly in Test Unit 213 while extending slightly on the southern edge into Test Unit 214, Block AD. The feature was located 30 cm north of trench F363. The F362 pit measured 96 cm East-West by 86 cm North-South. It was oval in plan. Feature fill was very dark gray (10YR3/1) loamy sand with mottles of very dark brown (10YR2/2) loamy sand. Archaeologists bisected the feature on an East-West axis and removed the south half first. Excavation of the south half of the feature revealed a shallow basin profile extending 14 cm with a sloping west wall and an almost vertical east wall (Figure 6.78). Archaeologists then excavated the north half of the feature. Artifacts were recovered from 26-40 cmbd. The northern half of this feature had 1 piece of dotted yellow slipware and 2 olive green wine bottle fragments in it. The southern half of the feature contained 4.2 g daub, 4 unidentified square nail fragments, 4 dotted yellow slipware bodies and bases, 1 olive green bottle glass, and 3.1 g of unidentified animal bone.

Figure 6.76 Feature 343 photograph and east bisection profile, Test Units 197 and 199, Block AB

Figure 6.77 Feature 347 north profile, Test Unit 197, Block AB

Figure 6.78 Feature 362 photograph and north bisection profile, Tets Units 213 and 214, Block AD

6.4.21 Post Features (Posts, Post Holes, Post Molds, and Post Molds in Holes)

Excluding posts in trenches, LG²ES archaeologists excavated a total of 35 posts, post holes, and post molds in 2018/2019 (Figures 6.79-6.82). Additional stains were mapped in plan that had characteristics of posts, post holes, and/or post molds. However, these were not excavated so their origins –whether cultural posts, natural tree stains, rodent burrows, or some other identity cannot be confirmed. Post features that were investigated were sampled by archaeologists who generally excavated the southern half of the feature unless noted otherwise. This report characterizes post features as follows: “post molds” are the generally homogenous soil stains left when posts rot in the ground; “post holes” are the holes dug before posts are erected within the holes and the holes are then backfilled with soil, resulting in mottled fill particularly if the post was pulled out later; “post molds within holes” occur when both the post mold and the hole can be identified in the same feature; and “posts” are used when features cannot be differentiated between post molds and post holes. Many of the small round and square features at Fort Argyle fell into the “post” category as a result of years of plowing that mixed the upper zone of stratum often leaving only a very shallow remnant of the very bottom of the post mold or post hole surviving below the base of Level 1. So, for the purposes of this discussion, the features have been categorized into the following, below: posts/post holes, post molds, and post molds within post holes.

The largest concentration of post-related stains uncovered in 2018/2019 was recorded in Block Y (n=27). A total of eight other features across the site that were excavated were identified as post-related following their excavation. There are other features in the 2018/2019 excavations that are likely posts, but this was not the main focus of excavation efforts. Post-related features are detailed below. All depth measurements reflect the surviving remnants of the features below the base of the plow zone, unless otherwise noted. Generally, this was near the base of Level 1, although in some areas the transition between the base of the plow zone and the base of Level 1 occupied another vertical 10 cm to what was the base of Level 2.

The post features in Block Y clustered predominantly in the western half of the block. They formed a swath extending from (and into) the southwestern corner of the block and continued across the block at a north-northeastern angle. All but two of the post or post-like feature stains were located west of the F287 palisade, or inside Fort Argyle A.

Posts

F206 was an extremely shallow, 8 cm deep post with a basin-shaped profile. It was generally circular in plan and measured 35 cm in diameter. Feature fill was a light brownish gray (10YR6/2) sandy loam mottled with grayish brown (10YR5/2) sandy loam. It was located in Block V, Test Unit 108. The excavated southern half of this feature was sterile of artifacts.

F256 straddled Test Units 149 and 153 in Block Y. This post measured 40 cm North-South by 35 cm. It was rectangular to square in plan view. At 16 cm of vertical fill below the base of Level 1, this was one of the more substantial posts. It had primarily vertical sides and a flat bottom in profile. It was a well-defined post with feature fill consisting of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy clay with mottles of grayish brown (10YR5/2) clayey coarse sand. The southern half was excavated, and it lacked artifacts.

F257 was also located in Block Y, Test Unit 150. It measured 32 cm by 6 cm and was oriented Northwest-Southeast. The post was rectangular in plan view and basin shaped in profile. It contained dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand with very dark gray (10YR3/1) loamy sand and yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay. A total of 11 cm of this feature survived beneath the base of Level 1. No artifacts were located within the feature's excavated southern half.

F258 was a post. It was an irregular ovoid in plan, measuring 63 cm by 43 cm on a Northeast-Southwest axis. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature. The south half of this feature, from 22-51 cmbd, contained one unidentified square nail fragment and one lead ball weighing 4.1 g. More information on the lead ball (and others) is found in Appendix B. Feature fill was dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand. The feature had a vertical wall on the western side that extended 29 cm to a flat base, which united a sloping wall on the eastern side. This feature was recorded in Block Y, Test Unit 145.

Figure 6.79 Posts, Block Y

F266. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Sandy Loam mottled with 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Loamy Sand and 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Clay
 Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

F267. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand

F268. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand and 10YR6/3 Pale Gray Loamy Sand and 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Clay
 Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

F269. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Sandy Loam
 Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

F270. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Sandy Loam
 Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

1. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand
2. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Loamy Sand and 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Clay
3. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Loamy Sand
4. 2.5YR4/6 Red Clay mottled with 10YR5/4 Yellowish Brown Clay

F272. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Sandy Loam
 Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

F273. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Sandy Loam
 Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

Figure 6.80 Posts, Block Y

F274. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Sandy Loam Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay
 B. Brick

F277. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Sandy Loam Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

F275. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand

F278. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand mottled with 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay
 Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

F276. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand

F279. 10YR4/1 Dark Gray Loamy Sand Matrix. 10YR6/3 Pale Brown Sandy Clay

Figure 6.81 Posts, Block Y

Figure 6.82 Posts, Block Y

F259 was a post or possible small pit. It fell at the junction of Test Units 145, 146, 149, and 150 in Block Y. The feature was an irregular ovoid in plan and oriented North-South. It measured 43 cm by 42 cm. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature. One Stalling Plain sherd was recovered from 25-59 cmbd. The feature had slightly sloping vertical walls with basin shaped corners terminating in a flat bottom. It extended to 34 cm depth. Feature fill was yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay with dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand and 2.5YR4/6 red clay.

F260 was a post located in Test Unit 150, Block Y. It was sub-rectangular in plan and basin shaped in profile. The post measured 42 cm by 36 cm and was oriented Northwest-Southeast. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature, recovering one unidentified square nail. The feature contained yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay with dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand and red (2.5YR4/6) clay that terminated 15 cm below the base of Level 1.

F261 was a post located in Block Y, Test Units 146 and 150. It was oval in plan, measuring 47 cm by 40 cm and aligned on a Northeast-Southwest axis. In profile the feature was basin shaped. F261 consisted of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand with very dark gray (10YR3/1) loamy sand. The feature had a depth of 25 cm below the plow zone. Artifacts in the southern half of the feature included 4.8 g of daub, one unidentified square nail fragment, and one small lead ball weighing less than 0.1 g.

F266 was a square post located in Block Y, Test Unit 157. It measured 44 cm in plan and extended to 28 cm in depth. The feature had slightly sloping vertical walls that terminated in basin shaped corners and a flat bottom. Feature fill consisted of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand, pale brown (10YR6/3) loamy sand, and yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay. The excavated southern half of the feature was sterile.

F268 was the base remnant of a post located in Test Unit 154, Block Y. The stain was rectangular in plan view and oriented East-West. Feature fill consisted of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand, pale brown (10YR6/3) loamy sand, and yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay. It was a shallow basin in profile that extended only 6 cm below the base of Level 1. It was a shallow basin in profile. No artifacts were recovered from the feature's southern half.

F269 was another very shallow post remnant in Block Y. It was located in Test Unit 157. The feature was irregular in plan and measured 33 cm East-West by 10 cm North-South. Feature fill was dark gray (10YR4/1) sandy loam. The feature was a slight, shallow basin in profile that only reached 4 cm below the base of Level 1. No artifacts were recovered from the feature's southern half.

F270 was similar to many other of the shallow posts in Block Y. It was recorded in Test Unit 158 as a rectangular stain in plan view. F270 measured 23 cm by 20 cm and had an East-West long axis. Fill was a homogeneous dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand that extended to 7 cm below the base of Level 1. The feature was basin shaped in profile. Archaeologists recovered no artifacts from the southern half.

F272 was located in Test Unit 153, Block Y. It was a very shallow post extending 5 cm below the base of Level 1. The feature was irregular in plan and oriented Northwest-Southeast. It measured 33 cm by

24 cm. Feature fill was dark gray (10YR4/1) sandy clay. It was basin shaped in profile. The excavated northern half contained one yellow slipware sherd.

F273 was a shallow post uncovered in Test Unit 153, Block Y. It was rectangular in plan and was oriented on a Northeast-Southwest axis. The post measured 13 cm by 12 cm in plan view. The fill was dark gray (10YR4/1) sandy loam. F273 appeared basin shaped in profile and extended 7 cm below the base of Level 1. No artifacts were located in the sampled northern half.

F274 was a post located in Test Unit 157, Block Y. The feature was sub-rectangular in plan and contained dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand. It measured 27 cm East-West by 13 cm North-South. Archaeologists excavated the northern half of the feature, revealing the profile in the southern wall of Block Y. The feature was somewhat basin shaped, but with a sloping eastern wall and slightly sloping vertical western wall that terminated at a rounded base. It extended 17 cm below the base of Level 1. Artifacts included a brick fragment in the profile as well as one unidentified iron object.

F275 was a small remnant of the bottom of a post recorded in Test Unit 154, Block Y. It was oval in plan with an East-West orientation. The feature measured 28 cm by 26 cm. Fill consisted of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand. The feature was an irregular basin in profile and had a depth of 6 cm. The southern half of the feature contained only one artifact, a small piece of daub that was noted and not recovered.

F276 was another basal post remnant, this one located in Test Unit 153, Block Y. It was an oval stain oriented slightly East-West. F276 measured 20 cm in both directions. Fill was consistent with other post remnants, dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand. The southern half of the feature was excavated, revealing a bi-lobed northern profile with each basin shaped lobe extending only 4 cm beneath the base of Level 1. The bi-lobed nature of the feature suggests that this may be the remnants of two post bottoms. One piece of plain yellow slipware was excavated from the southern half of the feature.

F277 was one of the larger and deeper posts in Block Y, extending to 34 cm below the base of Level 1. It was located mostly in Test Unit 149 and extended on the eastern edge into Test Unit 150. The feature was ovoid in plan with an East-West axis. It measured 52 cm by 47 cm. The feature contained dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand fill. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature, exposing slightly sloping vertical walls terminating in a relatively flat bottom with rounded corners. One pebble was noted in the excavated fill and no artifacts.

F278 contained a moderate portion of post that survived beneath the base of Level 1 in Test Unit 150, Block Y. The feature was sub-rectangular in plan and measured 53 cm on its long axis and 45 cm on its short axis. It was aligned Northwest-Southeast. Feature fill was dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand intermixed with pale brown (10YR6/3) loamy sand matrix soils. F278 was basin shaped in profile and extended to 18 cm. Archaeologists excavated the feature's southern half and recorded one prehistoric indeterminate quartz tool and one pebble.

F279 was a shallow, 8 cm deep post remnant located in Test Unit 150, Block Y. It appeared triangular in plan, with a Northwest-Southeast alignment. The feature measured 26 cm by 24 cm. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature, revealing a basin shaped profile. Feature fill was typical dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand. The excavated portion of the feature was devoid of artifacts.

F280 was one of the larger post features in Block Y. It was recorded in the northern part of Test Unit 151 and extended into the southern edge of Test Unit 147. The feature was sub-rectangular in plan and was oriented Northeast-Southwest. It measured 58 cm by 44 cm. The southern half of the feature was excavated revealing vertical walls extending 58 cm to a flat bottom. Feature fill was considerably different from most of the excavated posts in Block Y. F280 contained a mix of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand, very dark gray (10YR3/1) loamy sand, and lumps of light red (2.5YR6/6) clay, as well as charcoal flecks and daub. The lowest 8 cm of feature fill consisted of a level stratum of compacted pale brown (10YR6/3) sand, similar in color to soil matrices near other features, but lacking the gradation to the light red (2.5YR6/6) clay seen in the soil matrix surrounding F280. In addition to soil differences, F280 had considerably more artifacts than virtually all other posts. Several artifacts were recovered from the southern half of F280. This included 150 g of brick/daub, 0.2 g of calcined unidentified animal bone fragments, one small lead ball weighing 0.6 g, and one kaolin tobacco pipe stem with a hole measuring 5/64", one unidentified iron object, and one burned English gray flint flake (probably ballast stone).

F281 represented a shallow post remnant in Test Unit 158 of Block Y. The stain was oval in plan and measured 26 cm by 25 cm. Its long axis ran East-West. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature, which revealed a shallow basin profile. The feature contained dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand and terminated at 8 cm below base of Level 1. Archaeologists recovered one daub fragment (6.9 g) from the excavated half of the feature.

F282 was another shallow post in Block Y. It was documented in Test Unit 158 as a rectangular stain. The feature measured 27 cm by 25 cm and was oriented Northeast-Southwest. It was a shallow basin in profile terminating at 6 cm below the base of Level 1. Feature fill was typical and consisted of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand. There were no artifacts in the feature's excavated southern half.

F283 was a post located in Test Unit 151, Block Y. It was oval in plan, measuring 26 cm East-West by 20 cm North-South. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature which had dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand mottled with pale brown (10YR6/3) sand fill. The feature had sloping sides that terminated in a point. It was 8 cm thick. Only four pieces of brick/daub fragments (90.4 g) were noted from 27-35 cmbd.

F284 was a very shallow, 5 cm deep post remnant located in Test Unit 146 of Block Y. It was sub-rectangular in plan and oriented Northeast-Southwest. F284 measured 24 cm by 22 cm. Excavation of the southern half revealed mottled feature fill of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand, pale brown (10YR6/3) loamy sand and dark yellowish brown (10YR3/4) clay. The profile was basin shaped on the east side with a thin lens extending off the top of the feature on the western side. One lead ball weighing less than 0.1 g came from the southern half of this feature

F285 was a somewhat complicated feature recorded in Test Units 146, 147, and 151 in Block B. Initially F285 was a large irregular feature in plan measuring 273 cm East-West by 84 cm North-South. When archaeologists began excavating adjacent trench F287 in Test Units 147 and 148 they discovered that F285 was merely a low spot in the base of Level 1. The eastern half of F285 contained artifacts from 26-43 cmbd. This included 1.5 kg of brick/daub, 16 unidentified square nail fragments, 2 coarse earthenware sherd bases, 1 lead glazed coarse earthenware, 3 combed yellow slipware body sherds, 1 light-blue bottle glass, two olive green bottle glass, 1 lead ball weighing 2.6 g, and two kaolin tobacco pipe fragments with 5/64" bore diameters. As they removed a portion of this low spot through troweling, they uncovered a possible post below it on, at the intersection of the western edge of F287 and the eastern edge of F285, in Test Unit 147. The profile here revealed that F285 was reduced to 70 cm wide on its North-South axis. In profile it was an irregular shallow basin extending from 8 cm deep to a deeper lowspot in the center terminating at 16 cm and indicative of a former post but without a post mold outline. That deeper section of the feature contained a 6 cm tall piece of daub that may have been chinking to hold a post upright as well as other daub and brick fragments. Feature fill consisted of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand mottled with pale brown (10YR6/3) loamy sand, yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay, and 2.5YR4/6 clay. The latter two soil types were the same as the surrounding matrix. After drawing this western profile, archaeologists removed the remnants of the base of Level 1 designated F285. They did this in a 1 m section beginning at the profile at the above stated intersection with F287 and extending westward further into Test Unit 147. At the western end of that intersection they encountered a scatter of daub and brick in the base of Level 1 fill and uncovered a post in plan view and labeled it F375. Feature fill visible in plan view did not appear to contain daub or brick. F375 was photographed but not excavated.

F305 was a post located in Test Unit 165, Block Z. It was identified at the base of Level 1 (23 cmbd) within the F299 trench. F305 was excavated from 23-32 cmbd in what would have been Level 2 within that unit. The feature measured 44 cm by 28 cm and was oriented North-South. It was irregular in plan and was a shallow basin shape in profile. Feature fill consisted of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand and included 1.5 kg of brick and daub. Artifacts within this feature are all contained within the feature Level 2 bag and include 6 pieces of lead, one green bottle glass, 3 nails, 1 sand/grit tempered plain sherd, and 4 pieces of daub.

F334 was an oval post stain uncovered in TU 194, Block AB. The feature measured 33 cm by 30 cm and was oriented East-West. Feature fill was very dark gray (10YR3/2) loamy sand. It was generally basin-shaped in profile, although the walls were slightly more vertical than sloping. Archaeologists excavated the western half of the 9 cm deep feature and recorded seven daub fragments and one pebble.

F335 was a rectangular-shaped stain also located in TU 194, Block AB. Its long axis was Northwest-Southeast, and it measured 34 cm by 27 cm. This post was similar to F334 post in that it had the same type of feature fill, very dark gray (10YR3/2) loamy sand and was also basin shaped. F335 was 10 cm thick. Archaeologists excavated the western side of the feature, which contained 1 olive-amber bottle glass and 2 unidentified nail fragments located between 44-54 cmbd.

F376 was a shallow, 7 cm thick post remnant recorded in Test Unit 148, Block Y. After troweling an area containing a soil stain, a circular stain appeared beneath the initial discoloration. The circular stain was

designated F376 and measured 35 cm by 19 cm in plan. The fill consisted of a thin lens of dark grayish brown (10YR4/2) loamy sand overlying very dark gray (10YR3/1) loamy sand, with a small pocket beneath that on the north side of grayish brown (10YR5/2) sand. F376 was oriented North-South. The stain extended from the eastern edge of trench F287. Archaeologists removed the western half of the feature first, which contained one piece of daub (5.2 g). The profile revealed an irregular basin shape. The eastern half of the feature fill was also sparse, with eight brick/daub fragments (105.3 g) recorded. All artifacts came from 30-37 cmbd.

Post Molds

F265 was documented in Test Unit 157 of Block Y. It appeared to be a post mold, with a pointed base and homogeneous dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand fill. The feature was square in plan view and measured 26 cm by 19 cm along a North-South axis. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature. In profile the upper 20 cm of were fairly vertical, at which point the feature stepped in slightly and then made a conical descent to its pointed base. The shape of the upper portion of the feature suggests that part may have been a hole to accommodate the pointed post before the post was driven into the ground; however, there is no separate post mold stain visible in the profile, rather the entire feature fill appears to be the mold. Alternatively, F165 could be a post hole with a particularly vertical and pointed base, but this seems less likely. Three daub fragments (7.2 g) were recorded from F265.

F267 was located in Test Unit 153 in Block Y. It is likely a post mold given its pointed base, somewhat vertical sides, and homogenous dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand fill. The feature was oval in plan, measuring 57 cm East-West by 53 cm. The base terminated at 39 cm. Archaeologists excavated the feature's southern half, which was sterile.

F380 was a post mold that extended south from the north wall of Test Unit 222, Block AF. The feature measured 40 cm East-West by minimally 20 cm north-south. It was rectangular in plan and contained dark gray (10YR4/1) sandy loam. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature, revealing a profile with sharply sloping sides tapering into a pointed base. The feature was 39 cm thick, with the lowest 4 cm extending into the clay subsoil. The southern half of F380 fill encompassed a small quantity of brick/daub and 1 unidentified square nail from 36-75 cmbd.

F385 was a post mold located in Test Unit 226, Block AF. It measured 54 cm by 37 cm and lay on an East-West axis. The stain was rectangular in plan. Archaeologists excavated the west half of the feature, revealing a pointed post with sharp, sloping angled walls. Feature fill was dark grayish brown (10YR4/2) loamy sand and was 12-13 cm thick. The pointed base and homogeneous soil suggest that this feature is a post mold rather than a post hole. The western half of this feature encapsulated artifacts from 32-44 cmbd. This included 84 g of brick fragments, 1 clear glass, 1 small lead ball, and 1 unidentified copper fragment. Additional information on the lead ball is found in Appendix B.

F397 was a post mold extending out of the west wall of Test Unit 235, Block W. It measured minimally 36 cm out of the unit's west wall by 32 cm North-South. The portion of the feature extending from the wall was oblong in plan. The extant top of the feature at 16 cmbd contained a brick cluster. Archaeologists bisected the feature on an East-West axis and removed the southern half. This left a profile in the west

wall as well as the north wall. The upper 10 cm of the feature sloped into a curve and then had vertical walls for the remaining 52 cm until reaching a fairly flat base. The narrow width of the feature in profile (between 10-20 cm) in the north and west walls, as well as the vertical nature of the walls and the flat base suggests that F397 was a deep post mold. The upper 32 cm of feature fill consisted of dark grayish brown (10YR4/2) loamy sand. The remaining lower portion of fill was pale brown (10YR6/3) sand. The southern half of F397 contained artifacts from 16-84 cmbd, which included 440g of brick, 1.4 g mortar and 1 unidentified flat iron fragment. One brick fragment with an unusual surface was collected.

Post Molds in Holes

F271 was a post mold in a post hole. It was located in Test Units 153 and 157, Block Y. The feature had a circular plan with a slight North-South orientation. The entire feature measured 60 cm by 57 cm in plan view. The post mold measured 24 cm in diameter and contained homogeneous dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand. In profile the post was pointed at the bottom and had slightly tapering, vertical sides. It extended 29 cm below the base of Level 1, from the top to the bottom of the feature post hole. The post hole was slightly angled in profile and had a flat base. Post hole fill was dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand mottled with pale brown (10YR6/3) loamy sand and yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay. The southern half of this feature from 28-57 cmbd contained one dotted yellow slipware body sherd, one plain yellow slipware body sherd, and one piece of lead scrap weighing 3.8 g.

6.4.22 Refuse-filled Stump Holes

A curious feature type at Fort Argyle is refuse-filled stump holes. The 1985 investigations mention one example of a sterile clay-filled tree stump (Braley et al. 1985:42) and the 1995/1996 report includes one example of a pit "...that had been intruded by a tree, or which had been placed above an older tree stump hole" (Elliott 1997). While trees often grow through rich, organic features leaving a confusing mix of cultural and natural manifestations in the profile and soil stains, the refuse-filled stump holes appear to be a different entity. This feature type has specific characteristics on the Ft. Argyle site, including a disproportionately higher frequency of artifacts in general as well as artifacts such as gunflints, lead balls, and other diagnostics, relative to amounts found in posts and small pits. Another characteristic of refuse-filled stump holes is that the features are primarily moderate-sized stump holes containing artifacts rather than being artifact bearing post holes or pits with a tree growing through. The 2018/2019 excavations located six features interpreted as refuse-filled stump holes. Refuse-filled stump holes was a feature type clustered in the northwestern quadrant of the site, with one lone feature in the southwestern quadrant.

The six features were located in four blocks, Block AB (n=1); Block AF(n=2), Block AI (n=1), and Block Z (n=2). With the exception of Block AI, the remaining four features form an arc. However, their patterning and distribution may not reflect any intentional activity or plan. It appears from these features that Ft. Argyle rangers disposed of their trash in stump holes as a way to get rid of debris, including sharp bottle glass fragments, and as a way to help minimize dangerous or at least inconvenient holes. Some of the debris is burned, either as a result of burning trash and then throwing it in the hole, or more likely burned when some of the stumps were set on fire to reduce them to below-ground features rather than above-ground obstacles. Some of the refuse may have been placed in stump holes during phases of fort expansion and construction when such holes needed infilling as a necessity and when more debris was present after a period of site occupation.

F301 was a refuse-filled stump hole located in Test Unit 176, Block Z. It extended north out of the southern wall of Block Z. The feature was located approximately 125 cm south of trench F299. F301 measured 90 cm East-West by 27 cm North-South. The feature appeared basin shaped in profile, taking on groundwater at 34 cm below the base of Level 1 plow zone. This made it impossible to determine whether a tap root and/or small roots extended deeper. The profile contained three areas of distinctive fill zones: very dark gray (10YR3/1) sandy loam and daub; dark gray (10YR4/1) sandy loam; and light brownish gray (10YR6/2) sandy loam with yellow (10YR7/6) sandy clay.

The northern half of F301 was excavated from 22-56 cmbd. It contained 169.7 g of brick, 3.3 g of mortar, 7 unidentified square nails, 1 British brown salt glazed stoneware body, 1 combed yellow slipware body, 2.7 g of unidentified calcined animal bone, 1 indeterminate stone object, 2 small lead balls, 1 gunflint, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe 4/64", 1 unidentified iron, and 0.9 g of charcoal.

F308 was an extremely deep stump hole containing refuse located in Block Z (Figure 6.83). It occupied parts of Test Units 171, 172, 177, and 178. The stain was irregular and in plan it ran 90 East-West by 80 cm North-South. Archaeologists bisected the feature on a north-south axis along the east wall of Test Unit 171. They excavated the entire western side of the feature within TU 171. The well-defined profile revealed a very deep feature with a northern edge that initially was sloped and then became mostly vertical for approximately 50 cm. The southern edge of the feature was an arbitrary vertical line at the north wall of TU 177. Root stains ran irregularly off the feature profile. At the base of TU 171, Level 2 (35 cmbd), archaeologists began to excavate F308. They excavated it as one zone. Most of the artifacts, including the burned ones, were primarily in the upper 40 cm of fill with a gradual decline in recovery with depth. No artifacts were recovered near the base of the feature. The upper 40 cm of the feature contained dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand mottled with grayish brown (10YR5/2) sand. This leached into very dark grayish brown (10YR3/2) loamy sand for the remaining 40 cm. This fill continued beyond the termination of the feature and was cored to a minimum of another 20 cm. Part of a wooden stump was observed rising out of the final 20 cm of the base of the feature.

The upper zone of F308, from 29-35 cmbd contained 49 g of brick fragments, 51.7g of daub, and 30.2g of mortar. 1 glazed redware sherd, 2 olive green bottle glass, 1 lead sprue casting strip and 0.3 g of unidentified animal bone. Artifacts from 35-108 cmbd included 1.1 g of brick fragments, 17 unidentified square nails, 1 white salt glazed stoneware body sherd, 1 amber-olive bottle glass, 4 clear glass, 1 English spall gray gunflint fragment, 1 kaolin pipe bowl fragment, 1 kaolin pipe stem with a 5/64" bore, 9 melted lead, 3 charcoal fragments, 12 lead balls, and 6.6 g of calcined animal bone. Artifacts in the east half of TU 171, Level 2 (on top the area designated as F308) included: 4 small pieces of lead, 1 red earthenware, 2 glass, 1 pipe stem, 1 burned English spall type gunflint, brick and daub. Additional information on the elemental composition of the lead balls is found in Appendix B.

Figure 6.83 Feature 308 photograph and east bisection, in Test Unit 171, Block Z

F348 was a refuse-filled stump hole located along the north wall of Test Unit 197, Block AB. Upon further troweling, the feature measured 60 cm Northeast-Southwest by more than 38 cm where it extended into the unit and block wall. Two zones were documented in plan and profile (Figure 6.84). Zone A was an interior, circular zone measuring 24 cm East-West by 17+ cm. Zone A fill consisted of very dark gray (10YR3/1) sand with brown (10YR5/3) sand and extended from 20-40 cmbd. Zone B was the surrounding, oblong stain representing overall feature dimensions. Zone B fill was black (10YR2/1) clayey sand with some mottling and brick fragments. It occupied a depth of 20-70 cmbd. Archaeologists excavated the southern half of the feature, separating soils and artifacts from Zone A, Zone B (20-48 cmbd), and Zone B (48-70 cmbd). The feature first appeared in profile to be a post but increasing excavation revealed that the lower part of the feature was highly irregular and numerous root tunnels extended off it. Artifact density was high throughout the entire feature continuing down into its base. Excavation was terminated at 70 cmbd due to the decreasing size and amorphous nature of the fill and the infiltration of ground water.

Figure 6.84 Feature 348 photograph and plan at 27 cmbd, in Test Unit 197, Block AB

Eight lead balls came from F348 representing 16% of the artifacts from this feature. Five gunflints and one gunflint fragment also were recovered, constituting 8% of the artifacts. These included: 2 English spall type gray flints, 1 French blade type (honey flint), 1 French spall type (honey flint) and 1 English spall type gray flint fragment. Combined lead balls and gunflints account for 24% of the artifacts from F348. One French honey-colored flint flake also was present. The feature also contained two lead casting sprue strips, which indicate that lead balls were cast in a gang mold nearby. This high frequency of arms-related artifacts is notable. It is well above the predicted range for the Arms Group in the Frontier Artifact Pattern (South 1977). Four tobacco pipe fragments came from F348, which represents 8% of the artifacts from this feature.

An extremely small sample of 11 pottery sherds from F348 provided an MCD of 1753.91. This feature had a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of one plain creamware sherd. The presence of creamware in F348 suggests that it was filled by Georgia Rangers during the Fort C period, ca. 1757-1767. The feature yielded 39 artifacts, which are summarized in Table 6.11.

Table 6.11 Feature 348, Artifact Summary

Artifact Description	Count
Brick fragment	1
Coarse Earthenware	1
Undecorated Pottery	1
Kaolin tobacco pipe stem	1
Fossiliferous Limestone	1
Quartzite, non-cultural	2
Total Zone A	7
Brick fragment	13
Mortar	4
Nail, unidentified	2
Coarse Earthenware	4
Redware	1
Slipware, yellow	1
Container glass, olive green	3
Container glass, aqua	1
Kaolin tobacco pipe bowl	1
Gunflint, blade type, English	1
Flake, honey colored flint	1
Total Zone B	32
TOTAL FEATURE 348	39

F379 was initially thought to be a small post with a small sapling growing through it. However, the preponderance of artifacts within this small feature suggests that it more closely fits the characteristics of a refuse-filled stump hole, albeit a small one. The feature was recorded extending out of the east wall of Test Unit 222, Block AF. In plan view it measured 42 by 40 cm and was aligned on an East-West axis. Archaeologists excavated the western half of the feature. In profile the top of the feature was poorly defined, but noticeable as dark gray (10YR4/1) sandy loam at or near the base of the dark grayish brown (10YR4/2) loamy sand plow zone. In profile the feature exhibited sharply sloping sides leading into a

vertical 4 cm wide stain indicative of a tap root. This small tree stain contained a disproportionately large number of artifacts, particularly dark green bottle glass.

Artifacts were recovered from the western half of F379 between 32-52 cmbd. Architectural items included 9.4 g of brick fragments, 5.8 g of mortar, and 1 unidentified square nail fragment. The feature also contained 1 coarse earthenware sherd, 1 blue and white porcelain sherd, 1 residual delftware without glaze, 1 clear glass rim/goblet base, 13 olive green bottle glass fragments, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe stem with a 5/64" bore hole, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe bowl fragment, 5 unidentified cast iron fragments, 1 primary flake, and 32 charred wood fragments.

F384 exhibited classic signs of a refuse-filled stump hole. The feature appeared to be a possible post in plan and profile, but a deep tap root and relatively large concentration of historic artifacts suggested it was likely a stump hole infilled with trash during the fort period. F384 extended from the north wall of Test Unit 222, Block AF. In plan it was sub-rectangular and measured 35 cm East-West by 26 cm before entering the unit's north wall. Archaeologists excavated the south half of the feature. The feature's north profile depicted sharply sloping walls angling to a narrow point where a tap root stain continued downward. Excavation terminated at 48 cm below the base of Level 1, however, a tube core showed that the lower feature fill continued for an additional 29 cm below the excavation base. This was indicative of a tap root. The upper 32 cm of feature fill was dark gray (10YR4/1) sandy loam overlying gray (10YR5/1) sandy loam for the remainder of the feature.

Soil in the southern half of the feature between 36-116 cmbd included 7.3 g of brick/daub, 1 unidentified square nail, 2 coarse earthenware body sherds, 1 combed yellow slipware, 1 plain yellow slipware, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe stem, 1 clear goblet glass, and less than 0.1 g of unidentified calcined animal bone.

F403 was identified in the field during excavation as a tree. Its relatively high frequency of artifacts is the reason it is placed in the "refuse-filled stump hole" category. F403 was recorded in TU 236, Block AI. It measured 70 by 61 cm and was somewhat circular with a slight North-South orientation. Feature fill was dark grayish brown (10YR4/2) loamy sand mottled with yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay and red (2.5YR4/6) sandy clay. Archaeologists bisected the feature and excavated the east half. The west profile showed a basin shape in the upper 9 cm leading to wavy vertical wall on the south side and a vertical wall turning into a steeply sloping wall on the north side. The upper portion of the fill contained mostly brick and daub, and the upper 50 cm contained large pieces of wood charcoal. Evidence of a root system was observed. The feature extended 97 cm at which point archaeologists terminated the excavation. Archaeologists recovered artifacts from the eastern half of F403 between 35-132 cmbd. The assemblage included brick/daub (1017.2 g), 5.2 g of mortar, 2 unidentified square nails, 1 dotted yellow slipware rim, 1 plain yellow slipware body, 1 olive green bottle glass (heat treated), 2 kaolin pipe stems with 4/64" diameter, 1 kaolin pipe bowl fragment, and 1 tertiary chert flake. The feature fill and shape indicate that this is a relict tree. The artifacts and their locations at the top of the feature, as well as evidence of tree burning, suggest that this may be a natural feature turned into a cultural one through its use as a refuse-filled stump hole.

6.4.23 Probable Human Burials

F177 was uncovered in Test Unit 232, Block AH. The soil stain was discovered originally during the 1996 excavations (Test Unit 33, Block B) and assumed to be a burial based on the shape of the feature and the artifacts in the upper fill (Elliott 1997). Archaeologists relocated the feature in 2019 in order to excavate additional units around it in an attempt to define a potential cemetery there. They excavated a 2 m by 1 m unit (TU 232) on an East-West axis. They established the west half of the unit on top of where they expected the north half of the 1996 unit (TU 33) to be. This proved to be a successful relocation of the feature, which retained the same number (F177) in 2019 (Figure 6.85). The feature is rectangular in shape, with the exposed portion in plan measuring 110 cm by 63 cm. The feature is aligned on a Northwest-Southeast angle of the site grid, or with the northern end of the feature facing approximately 117 degrees east-southeast in relation to magnetic north. The feature extends into a large portion of the TU 232 south wall. Archaeologists excavated most of TU 232 to 27 cmbd, or approximately 20-24 cm below the ground surface, except F177 itself, which they excavated to 50 cm (approximately 44 cm below ground surface) (Figure 6.86). They relocated the two items found previously and reburied, a small porcelain bisque rabbit figurine (15 cmbd) and portion of a red-painted whelk shell (21 cmbd). These were piece-plotted and returned to the F177 stain during 2019 backfilling of TU 232. They are shown in Figure 6.89.

F177 was drawn in profile as part of the south profile of TU 232. Most of the feature in profile contained strong brown (7.5YR4/6) clay, strong brown (7.5YR5/6) clay and yellowish red (5YR4/6) clay. In profile the feature elevation started partially from the ground surface on the east and sloped down to the top of a large pocket of mottled gray (10YR6/1) clayey sand and strong brown (7.5YR5/6) sandy clay extending across the western two-thirds of the feature to the base of excavation. Ground water infiltrated at 50 cmbd. A tube core sample indicated that the upper most zone extended an additional 10 cm on the east side, overlying at least 20 cm of gray (10YR6/1) sand. The water table prohibited additional tube coring of soil strata at this point. Other than the two artifacts mentioned, the only cultural material discovered in 2019 were two brick fragments and prehistoric artifacts including 1 chert flake and 1 pottery sherd from 25-47 cmbd. Three natural pebbles were noted.

F402 was a stain recorded in Test Unit 232, adjacent to F177 in Block AH. F402 appears to be below the depth excavated in the TU 33 excavations in 1996 (see above) as it was not recorded on that earlier plan view. F402 extended east from the west wall of TU 232, running from the northwestern balk to the mid-section of the western edge of F177. F402 was oriented Northwest-Southeast with a long axis measuring minimally 232 cm by minimally 97 cm. Feature fill consisted of grayish brown (10YR5/2) loamy sand. The plans and profiles suggest that F177 truncates F402, indicating that F402 predates F177. As with F177, archaeologists did not excavate F402 based on communications between LG²ES and Fort Stewart archaeologist, Brian Greer. A tube core of F402 near the unit's south profile indicates that the same color soil as the feature extends minimally to 78 cm below ground surface, or 60 cm below the extant top of the feature. Standing ground water was encountered at that depth in the tube corer.

1. 10YR5/2 Grayish Brown Loamy Sand
2. Mottled 10YR6/1 Gray Clayey Sand and 7.5YR5/6 Strong Brown Sandy Clay
3. 10YR6/1 Gray Clayey Sand
4. 10YR6/2 Light Brownish Gray Coarse Sand
5. Mottled 7.5YR5/6 Strong Brown Sandy Clay

Figure 6.85 Features 177 and 402 photograph and plan at 27 cmbd, in Test Unit 232, Block AH

Figure 6.86 Features 177 and 402 in Test Unit 232, photograph and plan at base of unit, Block AH

Sheet Midden

F289 was a rare section of sheet midden uncovered in Test Units 148, 152, and 156 in Block Z. The midden was oriented on a North-South axis and lay adjacent to the eastern edge of trench F287. It was approximately 4 cm thick, extending from 30-34 cm below Test Unit 148 datum. The lens contained mottled fill of dark gray (10YR4/1) loamy sand with pale brown (10YR6/3) loamy sand and yellowish brown (10YR5/4) clay. Brick fragments were concentrated in the central portion of the feature, and at the southern end extending into F287. Brick and daub, which was discarded, weighed 0.25 kg. Artifacts from 30-34 cmbd included 1.7 g daub and 200 g brick/daub. Other artifacts consisted of 1 coarse earthenware sherd, 1 sand tempered plain body sherd, 1 olive green spirit bottle glass fragment, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe bowl fragment, 5 unidentified iron fragments, and 3 lead balls (1 weighing 22.4 g and the other two having a combined weight of 0.6 g). Two plain aboriginal sherds were also located.

Figure 6.87 Ceramic Rabbit and Painted Whelk, F177.

Miscellaneous Features

F176D was a lead ball cache within the F176C palisade trench, Block V. Archaeologists first discovered the cache during the 2018 controlled metal detector survey. It was assigned MD77 as the metal detector find number when recorded with the laser transit. During the location and excavation of this MD target, archaeologists realized it was an intact feature rather than one or two artifacts. For this reason, they curtailed its excavation, recorded it, backfilled, and decided to establish a test unit around it during the second portion of the project many months later. They did this with the establishment of Test Unit 104 and the surrounding Test Units 105 and 106 in Block V. F176D was located in the southwestern corner of Test Unit 104. Archaeologists uncovered the feature following the removal of Level 1 in the test unit and the subsequent troweling and removal of the base of the plow zone there. At the same time they uncovered a large portion of F176C (the palisade trench), including its upper two areas designated Zone A and Zone B. The lead ball cache was in Zone A (Figure 6.88).

F176D was an oblong stain measuring 40 cm East-West by 21 cm North-South. It primarily consisted of 104 lead balls in a 7 cm thick concentration (Figure 6.89). What small amount of soil that existed around them was dark gray (10YR4/1) sandy clay loam. The lead balls were of varying sizes, from a large ball (n=1) to medium large balls (n=22), to medium small (n=77) to small (n=4). Other artifacts in addition to items possibly from the feature but at the interface of Zone A of F176 included an English spall gunflint and lead scrap, as well as the lead balls and lead scrap recovered in MD 77 from the metal detector survey. Other gunflints, a lead patch, and arms-related materials were found around F176D, primarily in Zone A of F176C. Additional metric and elemental information about these balls is provided in Appendix B.

Figure 6.88 Feature 176D, excavating lead ball cache (left) and plan of cache (right), base of Level 1, Test Units 104 and 105, Block V

The concentration of many lead balls and their arrangement in a small, compact area on top of one another strongly suggests that the balls were originally in a container such as a leather pouch, fabric bag, wooden box, or basket. Given the lack of a noticeable stain and pattern around the edge of the feature, it is likely that it wasn't a box, but perhaps a leather pouch or fabric bag that left less evidence when it decayed in the ground. The location of the lead balls, in trench F176C is interesting. In plan it was mapped almost midway between the north and south edges of the trench, but within Zone A. This aligns it closely with the location of the post mold depicted in the west profile of F176C. In fact, the lead ball concentration of F176D would have been near the top of that post mold stain as well as the next post mold stain to the east (shown in the south bisection profile of F176C in progress). Due to the lack of clarity of the post molds in plan view, it is difficult to say with certainty whether the cache was placed on top of an infilled area of rotted posts, was placed in the trench during its construction and forgotten and buried with construction activity, or was placed adjacent to the bottom of two posts in the palisade line during active use of the fort and ultimately became forgotten and buried over time, particularly with the continual maintenance of the fort palisades and their razing and reconstructions. This last hypothesis seems most likely. At any rate, F176D represents the loss of many lead balls, which would have been valuable to the rangers at the fort.

Figure 6.89 Feature 176D, cache of lead balls in situ (top) and in field after excavation (bottom, in Test Units 104 and 105, Block V)

Indeterminate Features

F353 was found in Test Units 192 and 195, Block AB. It was located at the base of Level 1, at the plow zone transition. The feature was rectangular in plan and initially measured 100 by 36 cm. Subsequent troweling showed it to be smaller in size, at 31 cm by 20 cm with a North-South alignment. Feature fill was very dark grayish brown (10YR3/2) loamy sand mottled with dark brown (7.5YR3/2) loamy sand. In profile the 11 cm deep feature was irregular with a flat bottom. Artifacts were recovered from 20-31 cmbd in this shallow stain and included: 1 coarse earthenware, 1 window glass, 1 unidentified iron piece, and 5 brick fragments (8.1 g).

F365 was a shallow, linear feature uncovered in Test Unit 216, Block AE. It measured 14 cm wide and ran East-West into both the east and west walls of the test unit. The grayish brown (10YR5/2) loamy sand fill of the feature was well defined. Archaeologists excavated a 1 m section of the feature in the east half of the unit. The sandy fill was easy to excavate, and the feature ended within 3-5 cm of its extant top, suggestive of a dripline. In profile it was sloped on the north side, angled on the south side and slightly pointed in the middle, suggesting a plow scar. Its linear nature was well-defined. While it is likely that the upper 24 cm of plow zone contained more of the feature, the remnants of it seem shallow when contrasted with other wall and palisade trench features. The lack of plow scars elsewhere in the block and in the immediate area suggest that this is not a plow scar. For these reasons, a building's roof dripline seems to be the most likely function of this feature. If so, it indicates that a structure was nearby. No artifacts were recovered from sifting the feature fill through one-quarter inch mesh. However, artifacts found in driplines tend to be very small, so it is possible that they were not recovered but it is just as likely that this portion of the feature was sterile.

F378

F378 was a feature of questionable function that may be the result of bioturbation. The feature was discovered extending out of the north wall of Test Unit 221, Block AF. It measured 75 cm by 50 cm, had a North-South axis, and was rectangular in plan. Archaeologists bisected the feature and excavated the west side of it. The east profile revealed black (10YR2/1) loamy sand fill. It had an extremely undulating base and irregular side (Figure 6.90). It was a shallow feature measuring only 8 cm at its deepest. Five brick fragments were in the fill. It is likely that this feature was the result of bioturbation from animals or roots, given its dark, organic soil and irregular shape. The western half of F378 had 11.5 g of brick fragments between 35-43 cmbd.

Figure 6.90 Feature 378 east profile, Test Unit 221, Block AF

Excavated Features Revealed to be Non-cultural or Modern Disturbances

F250 was a natural soil zone. F251A, F262, F263, F264, F265, F288 and F307 all were low spots in the plow zone. These shallow features disappeared soon after their excavations began. F307 (eastern half) contained 9.2 g of brick, 2.0 g of mortar, less than 0.1 g of animal bone, and 1 unidentified metal artifact between 27-30 cmbd. F286 was a soil stain that resulted from bioturbation caused by roots and rodents. Two artifact types were found in the eastern half of this feature between 28-73 cmbd. There were 36.9 g of brick fragments and one brass strap buckle. F302 and F338 were tree root stains. The southern half of F302 extended from 0-32+ cm and contained 18.1 g of brick, 10.8 g of mortar, 1 olive green bottle glass, and 1 lead ball. F338 yielded no artifacts in the excavated half. F306 was a relatively recent disturbance, most likely a modern military vehicle rut. Artifacts were recovered from the eastern and western sides of this feature, 22-34 cmbd. These include 2.1 g of brick fragments and 23.1 g of mortar and 2 amber-olive bottle glass, 1 gunflint fragment, 1 kaolin tobacco pipe stem with a 5/64" bore, 1 melted lead, 1 unidentified iron, and 1 piece of petrified wood.

6.5 Material Culture

Previous excavations at Fort Argyle yielded approximately 7,171 artifacts, excluding brick, daub and mortar. Of these, approximately 469 artifacts were associated with Native Americans. The remainder (n=6,702) are almost all associated with the colonial occupation. Approximately 5,626 historic artifacts, excluding brick, daub and mortar, were excavated from Fort Argyle by the LG²ES crew in 2018 and 2019.

6.5.1 Architecture Group

Spikes

Six wrought iron spikes were previously recovered from Fort Argyle and three of these were from Excavation Block J (Elliott 1997:149). Only two spikes were recovered by the LG²ES team. Both were located in the plow zone—one from Block Y and the other from Block AB.

Nails

By the 1730s a number of blacksmiths were making wrought nails in Georgia for local consumption. During the colonial era at Ebenezer, for example, more than seven blacksmiths plied their trade. Most likely all of these men made nails in their slack times. One well-documented blacksmith, Rupert Schrempff, made many nails in his Ebenezer blacksmith shop (Elliott and Elliott 1992). Throughout the colonial period nails were commonly imported to Georgia from England. The ratio between imports and local production is a worthy subject of study for which no statistics have been compiled. Despite the widespread local production of wrought nails by blacksmiths, merchant's newspaper advertisements from the colonial period show that quantities of nails were imported in casks. The source of these nails is not usually specified in the advertisements but many of the announced shiploads of goods hailed from England. Prior to 1790 all nails were hand wrought. The first machine cut nail manufacturing devices were patented in 1790. Numerous machine designs were introduced. None of these patents or designs have been traced to Georgia or the other southern states. Machine cut nails were imported to Georgia through the port of Savannah as early as 1796. This was only six years after the first nail making machines were in operation (Elliott 2010).

Nails at Fort Argyle were poorly preserved, which rendered their identification difficult. This problem was first recognized by Braley et al. (1985:61), who recovered 886 nails or spikes from his 1985 excavations, although he notes that many of these nails were associated with the brick kiln south of Fort Argyle. Elliott (1997:149) noted that 345 nails from the 1996 excavations were square nails, but only five were conclusively identified as wrought. None of the 1996 assemblage were strictly identified as machine-cut nails.

The proper identification of nails continued to be problematic for the LG²ES team. A total of 1,254 nails or nail fragments were recovered by LG²ES. Of these, and because of their severely corroded and decomposed condition, none was conclusively identified as wrought nails. Researchers were forced to rely on the default categories of unidentified square nails, or unidentified nails. Nearly all of these, are actually wrought nails in an extremely poor state of preservation since Fort Argyle was abandoned about 23 years before nail making machines were invented.

Door Hardware

Elliott (1997:149) reported recovering one wrought iron strap hinge from Excavation Block A in 1996. The LG²ES team found two additional wrought iron strap hinges. One was recovered from the plow zone during the metal detector survey and the other fragmented hinge came from F337. One iron door lock mechanism was recovered by LG²ES.

Window Glass

Window glass was quite rare at Fort Argyle. All previous excavations there combined yielded only 146 small window glass sherds. Most of these likely post-date the colonial fort. Braley recovered 90 fragments of clear window glass from his 1985 excavations. He noted that none of these examples was likely associated with the eighteenth-century component. Braley also noted that 46 window glass sherds came from his excavations on the west side of Fort Argyle (Excavation Block L) where he suspected the remains from a later structure lay underground. The other window glass sherds Braley's team recovered

were lightly scattered “across the bluff outside the fort walls” (Braley et al. 1985:62). On the northern end of 9BN28, Martin and her colleagues derived a mean window glass date of 1904.0 from a sample of 34 window glass sherds (Martin et al. 1986:15-16). Their assemblage attests to the presence of late nineteenth- to early twentieth-century activities, which is unrelated to the colonial fort. The LAMAR Institute team recovered only 22 window glass sherds (Elliott 1997:149). LG²ES also identified very few windowpane sherds from its excavations as well, with only 24 small sherds recovered. These were found in excavation blocks T, V, W, Y, Z, AA, AB, AD and AI . Only three features contained any window glass--F175F in Block T, F353 in Block AB, and F388 in Block AA.

Daub, Brick and Mortar

Ceramic building materials, including daub, brick, and mortar, were the most common artifacts in the architecture group at Fort Argyle. LG²ES unearthed 154.4 kg (339.7 lbs) of these materials combined. Of this mass, approximately 1.4 kg was mortar, and the rest (153 kg) was either daub or brick fragments. Most of this was weighed in the field and discarded. The only complete bricks recovered by LG²ES were two specimens from F175F (a portion of the H-shaped brick chimney pad in Block J first discovered in 1995/1996) in Test Unit 220. One of these (Brick Sample 1) weighed 1.45 kg and the other (Brick Sample 2) weighed 1.11 kg.

Brick is relatively rare at Fort Argyle. This is ironic given that a later brick factory, the Fort Argyle Brick and Lumber Company, operated just south of the fort and it produced many thousands of bricks (*The Morning News* 1890:8; Braley et al. 1985:27; Greer 2006:12; Leon 2017:35). Elliott (1997:149) noted that slightly more than 207 kg of brick fragments were previously excavated from the site. Braley et al. (1985:61) observed the complete absence of whole bricks from his 1985 excavations, although he did state that “the river bottom is littered with whole bricks” during his underwater reconnaissance offshore from the fort. Braley also noted a concentration of brick fragments, “in the southeast corner of Fort Argyle, and just between the palisade and the river”. Martin and her colleagues (1986:17-19) recovered examples of whole bricks from their underwater reconnaissance survey of the Ogeechee River. They obtained measurements of 8 3/8 inches by 4 inches by 2.5 inches, which they interpreted as eighteenth-century bricks. Elliott (1997:149) provides additional measurements for whole brick examples. One from F186 measured 7.5 inches by 3.75 inches by 2.25 inches. Another from F175D in Block J measured 8 inches by 4 inches by 2.5 inches.

Only one feature (F175) displayed any intact brickwork and it was composed almost exclusively of brick fragments and not complete bricks. One of the bricks in F175, which was unearthed in 1996, contained an embedded historic ceramic (undecorated refined white salt-glazed stoneware), which was an important find in dating the bricks used in constructing the H-chimney at F175. South (1977) provides a begin date for refined white salt-glazed stoneware of 1740. Historical records reveal that the Georgia Rangers were supplied with bricks for their forts located in interior Georgia in 1742 or 1743. These two lines of evidence suggest that the bricks used in constructing F175 probably were manufactured after 1740.

Daub, or fired clay, was common across Fort Argyle. Elliott (1997:149) noted that more than 14 kg of daub were previously excavated from the site. Braley et al. (1985:61-62) observed a concentration of

daub along the north palisade wall. Daub was mostly represented by small formless blobs of baked clay. It was difficult to distinguish small fragments of clay from small, interior fragments of poorly fired brick. These daub pieces were weighed and discarded. One large, well-preserved example of daub, which displayed a series of small log impressions, was unearthed in F299 in Excavation Block Z (Figure 6.91). This specimen was clearly from an architectural context, possibly from a mud and stick chimney. Mud and stick chimneys were common in other parts of the Georgia coast in the Trustee period, such as Ebenezer and the Ebenezer Mill District (Elliott and Elliott 1992; Elliott and Smith 1985; Smith 1986). Daub also was likely used as chinking between logs in log buildings (Jordan 1985; Kniffen and Glassie 1986).

Figure 6.91 Architectural artifact (Daub with wattle impressions, LN201.457.001).

Mortar was uncommon at Fort Argyle. Elliott (1997:150) noted that more than 33 kg of mortar were recorded from previous excavations, although he cautions that nearly all of this came from a single provenience in Excavation Block J. In stark contrast, the LG²ES excavations yielded only 1.4 kg of mortar. Table 6.12 shows the distribution of nails, brick/daub and mortar in LG²ES's excavation.

Table 6.12 Architectural Artifacts Per Square Meter Excavated.

Block	Per Square Meter			
	Excavated Area	Nails (Count)	Brick/Daub (grams)	Mortar (grams)
T	9	5.0	2059	6.1
U	24	3.5	175	2.3
V	10	7.6	299	0.3
W	28	1.5	761	2.7
X	24	3.4	735	0
Y	36	10.2	823	0.9
Z	41	3.3	434	12.6
AA	24	6.2	233	12.1
AB	34	3.8	556	5.8
AC	8	1.8	120	0
AD	12	3.6	610	14
AE	4	8.8	987	0
AF	8	2.1	284	0.7
AG	4	2.3	288	1.1
AH	6	0.8	43.4	0
AI	2	10.0	259	2.6

6.5.2 Clothing Group

We have only limited information on what uniforms were worn by the rangers at Fort Argyle. Oglethorpe noted in 1736 that the Highland Rangers at Darien “made a most manly appearance with their Plads, broad Swords, Targets & Fire Arms.” The uniform worn by regular Georgia troops during King George’s War consisted of a black hat with a green cockade and a blue coat with red trim (Elliott 1997:150). Georgia Rangers, who were new recruits in 1745, wore uniforms of “blue faced with red”, with “green cockades in their hats” (Wright 1867:355). Georgia Rangers in the Ceded Lands in 1774 wore uniforms that included, “a Blue Coat faced with Red and a Red Jacket and Blue Cloth Boots as spatterdashes made to fit the Leg edged with Red and Gartered with Black strap and buckle to wear occasionally and Breeches either Blue cloth or Buckskin also a good Fussee, a Putteau, a Black Leather shot Pouch and Belt of the same Edged with Red also a good Powder Horn” (Zedric and Dilley 1996:29).

Artist Eric Manders presents his interpretation of an English Ranger in Georgia, circa 1740, which is reproduced in Figure 6.92. This hypothetical Georgia Ranger’s uniform consists of a faded and drab forest green, long-sleeved coat with one row of plain buttons and no insignia. His hat is a black felt, tri-corner garment adorned with a black bow. His long-sleeved shirt is a checkered blue and white gingham cloth and he wears a black neckerchief around his throat. Gaiters were worn on top of leather shoes and khaki trousers. His accoutrements include a flintlock musket with a short barrel, a single flintlock pistol (tucked into a belt), and a trade ax that is suspended in a holder draped below the belt. He is not shown with his horse, pack, or any other weapons accoutrements (Manders 1995:Plate 709).

Figure 6.92 Artist Eric Manders' Interpretation of an English Ranger, circa 1740 (Manders 1995: Plate 709).

Elliott (1997:150-152) noted that only 26 artifacts in the clothing group were recovered from previous excavations at Fort Argyle. These consisted of 13 brass buttons, seven shoe buckles or fragments, and two small brass buckles. The buttons include three South Type 1; three South Type 7 and one South Type 4. Martin and her colleagues (Martin et al. 1986:27) recovered one brass button from the northern end of 9BN28, but they provide no other details. LG²ES also recovered relatively few clothing group artifacts; only 25 artifacts were recovered. Of this total, 13 were found by the metal detector survey.

Buttons

LG²ES recovered 14 metal buttons or button fragments from its excavations. Half of these were located by the metal detector survey. No bone, shell or ivory buttons were located at the site. Archaeologists have excavated no identifiable regimental buttons from Fort Argyle. A limited variety of civilian buttons have been identified. All of the recovered buttons were eighteenth-century types, and all 11 brass buttons recovered by LG²ES were plain. Four were domed buttons and the other identifiable buttons were flat types (Figure 6.93a and b). One composite-type pewter button was recovered. It was poorly preserved and bore no obvious surface decoration. Archaeologists recovered two engraved, octagonal, silver buttons from the metal detector survey. Both were engraved on the front with a geometric floral motif. While these two buttons weighed the same (0.6 g) and were nearly the same diameter, they were widely separated in space. One was found at 2969.43N, 8176.79E and the other was at 2983.7N 8168.19E. The senior author analyzed 12 metal buttons from the Fort Argyle assemblage for their elemental content using pXRF technology. The complete results of this exercise are included in Appendix B.

Figure 6.93a Clothing artifacts, buttons (a. Pewter composite button back, LN201.392.035; b. and c. Domed, brass composite, LN201.181.001 and LN201.010.001; d. Flat brass undecorated, LN201.004.001; e. Brass composite, drilled back, LN201.229.001).

Figure 6.93b Clothing artifacts, buttons (a. and b. Silver engraved octagonal buttons, LN201.067.001 and LN201.086.001; c. Domed brass button, drilled back, LN201.226.001; d. Flat brass undecorated button, iron loop back, LN201.023.001; e. and f. Brass flat buttons, LN201.133.018 and LN201.207.007).

Buckles

LG²ES archaeologists recovered a total of nine buckle fragments, of which five were found by the metal detector survey. This included six brass shoe buckle fragments. No complete examples were found, the surviving fragments are parts of typical eighteenth-century style buckles (Figure 6.94). These were all civilian buckles and not military issue. These forms of buckles were used on eighteenth-century footwear and have been recovered from many colonial sites in Georgia (Miller and Stone 1970; Abbitt 1973; Elliott 1991; Booth 2019). Many metal buttons manufactured during this period are made of an alloy of copper and zinc (or brass) known as “Pinchbeck”, so named for its inventor the esteemed London clockmaker Christopher Pinchbeck (Quinion 2004). Two different ratios were used to produce pinchbeck: Copper 89% and Zinc 11%, or Copper 93% and Zinc 7% (Chemistry Learner 2019). Pinchbeck buckles were gold in appearance, appearing to be valuable, but actually cheaply produced. The firm of Kelsall, Darling and Munro of Savannah offered for sale in May 1765, “pinchbeck buckles” (*The Georgia Gazette* May 2, 1765:6). By the nineteenth-century pinchbeck jewelry had become synonymous with the notion of cheap imitation as unscrupulous jewelers passed it off as gold, and it fell from favor as a metal of choice. Pinchbeck was not commonly used for jewelry after the 1840s.

The senior author analyzed six buckle fragments from the Fort Argyle assemblage for their elemental content using pXRF technology. The complete results of this exercise are included in Appendix B. The combined total net photons for Copper (Cu K12) and Zinc (Zn K12) were compared for these six artifacts

Figure 6.94 Clothing artifacts, buckles (a. Brass gun strap buckle, LN201.312.003; b. Ornate brass shoe buckle, LN201.281.010; c. Silvered brass shoe buckle, LN201.223.001; d. Brass shoe buckle, LN201.013.001; e. Brass D-buckle, LN201.188.001; f. and g. Brass buckles, LN201.168.002 and LN201.082.001).

which indicated Copper was approximately 88.4% and Zinc was approximately 11.6%. This ratio of Copper to Zinc (88.4:11.6) falls very near that specified for pinchbeck (89:11). Other metals contained in significant quantities in the Fort Argyle buckle sample include Antimony (Sb K12), Arsenic (As K12), Cadmium (Cd K12), Iron (Fe K12), Silver (AG K12), Tin (Sn K12) and Zirconium (Zr K12). The metal composition of the archaeologically recovered shoe buckle fragments from Fort Argyle match up with the historically defined composition of Pinchbeck in England. Furthermore, local merchants advertised “pinchbeck buckles” for sale during the final period of Fort Argyle’s life as a ranger fort. These soldiers probably purchased their shoe buckles in the Savannah market.

Glass Beads

Eight glass trade beads were previously excavated from Fort Argyle (Elliott 1997:154). One Cornaline d’Alleppo bead was recovered by the SAS team from Excavation Block J. Another of that type was recovered from the northern end of 9BN28 by the CAS team (Martin et al. 1986:33). Other bead types

recovered include two faceted blue wire wound glass beads and one blue glass seed bead. All these beads are common eighteenth-century types (Marvin T. Smith personal communication 1996). The LG²ES excavations recovered only three extremely small glass beads. All three were drawn, tumbled tubular white glass beads. These also were common eighteenth-century bead types. The relatively low frequency of glass beads at Fort Argyle may indicate that only minimal trade with Native Americans was conducted within the fort.

Spurs

Spurs are an important horseman's accoutrement, which cross over two of South's functional categories—clothing and activities. Spurs have been used from the Middle Ages to the present and many functional, stylistic and fashion changes over time have been noted (Lacy 1904). The firm of Morel and Telfair of Savannah in June 1763 advertised for sale, "silver plated steel and brass spurs" (*The Georgia Gazette* June 16, 1763:4). LG²ES recovered one brass spur fragment from the plow zone in Block AG. It was a slender midsection that was missing the two rowels (jagged spinning part used to jab the horse) and the two strap attachments. It possessed no markings or decorative elements. The Fort Argyle spur is similar to an early eighteenth-century spur and another spur dating to the reign of George II, as illustrated by Lacy (1904:Plate 34, Figure 2; Plate 46, Figure 1) in his *The History of the Spur*. Lacy's illustration is reproduced in Figure 6.95. Lacy noted that by the early eighteenth-century spurs had changed from their more elaborate predecessors, as he described,

The necks were now made much shorter, and, when not curved slightly downwards, were straight, much as they are now [1904]. The rowels, too, were much smaller, and usually of many points, and seldom more than three quarters of an inch in diameter...After the reign of Queen Anne no very great changes were made in the fashions of spurs. Rowels by degrees were made smaller, and ornament and elaboration became less and less, until, by easy stages, the form of spur much as we have now was arrived at (Lacy 1904:57).

The senior author analyzed the spur from Block AG for its elemental content using pXRF technology. The complete results of this analysis are included in Appendix B.

Figure 6.95 George II Period Spur (Lacy 1904: Plate 43f, Fig. 1).

6.5.3 Kitchen Group

Bottle Glass

Braley's initial excavations at Fort Argyle yielded 394 pieces of bottle glass. Most of these (n=336, or 85%) were dark (olive) green spirit bottle glass. These were followed in frequency by clear glass (n=33) (Braley et al. 1985:58-59). Elliott (1997:146) noted 769 olive-green spirit bottle glass sherds were excavated from Fort Argyle from the 1985 and 1996 excavations.

LG²ES recovered 1,010 fragments of olive-green spirit bottle glass. No intact bottles, or even major portions of bottles were included in the inventory. Diagnostic bottle parts that were observed include bottle necks and lips and basal kick-ups. These traits, along with many stretched air bubbles within the glass sherds demonstrate that these were once rum, gin, wine and other spirit bottles. As such they all likely contained alcoholic beverages during their first usage. Strong drink, or hard liquor, was prohibited in Georgia during the initial years of the Georgia Trustee period. The Trustees passed an act on April 3, 1735, entitled "An Act to prevent the importation and Use of rum and brandies in the Province of Georgia, or any kind of spirits or strong waters whatsoever" (Georgia Trustees 1735). In December 1742, this prohibition was relaxed when the Georgia Trustees passed an act to repeal the importation and use of rum and brandies in Georgia, and for, "suppressing the odious and loathsome sin of drunkenness" (White 1854:19). From a legal standpoint, this means that the South Carolina Rangers who garrisoned Fort Argyle were not allowed any hard liquor after June 24, 1735, when the act took effect. Similarly, during the first six or seven years of the Georgia Rangers tenure strong drink also was forbidden. Liquor was allowed for the last five years of the first iteration of Georgia Rangers (1742-1747) and was completely legal during the second iteration of Georgia Rangers (1757-1767). In theory, this implies that the earliest two ranger occupations (1733-1747) had less access to hard liquor than the rangers during the third and final occupation (1757-1767).

In reality, olive-green bottle glass is widely distributed throughout the fort, which suggests that these bottles were the debris of all three ranger troops. Excavation Block AA exhibited the highest frequency of olive-green spirit bottle glass, (10.6 sherds/m²), while Block AH displayed the lowest frequency (0.5 sherds/ m²). Blocks Y, AC, AD, AF and AI contained moderate amounts of olive-green glass (4.2, 4.3, 4.6, 6.3 and 4.5 sherds/ m², respectively). The other excavation blocks ranged between 1.6 and 3.7 sherds/ m².

Medicines were important in colonial Georgia, as many diseases and illnesses raged among the populace. The Ebenezer settlement promoted its medicines to other Georgians (Wilson 2008). The archaeological evidence for medicines at Fort Argyle is meager. Braley et al. (1985) recovered only one pharmaceutical bottle glass sherd. Elliott (1997:148) stated that 29 pharmaceutical bottle glass sherds were excavated from Fort Argyle from the 1985 and 1996 excavations. LG²ES recovered only four fragments recognized by the laboratory crew as pharmaceutical bottle glass. Another 18 light-blue and light aqua-colored bottle glass recovered by LG²ES may also be medicine bottle fragments. Six of these bottle sherds came from feature contexts. The rest were from plow zone contexts in Blocks T, U, V, W, X, Y, Z and AG.

Soldiers in garrisons in the eighteenth century were prone to contagious diseases but no references were found from our research concerning any medical practice at Fort Argyle. No doctors or surgeons were

among the rosters of rangers under Captain John Milledge's command. So, what happened to rangers who became sick? Those who could afford it may have traveled to Savannah where some medical care was available. That was the case with Captain Jacob Matthews, commander of the Georgia Ranger Fort Mount Venture at Sansavilla Bluff. Matthews was the husband of Mary Musgrove. Mary had accompanied her husband to Savannah to seek medical attention and both were there when Fort Mount Venture was attacked and burned by Spanish-allied Indians (Elliott 2005a). Jacob Matthews died from his illness. Captain John Cuthbert, who commanded a small Georgia Ranger troop at Josephstown on the lower Savannah River, also died prematurely from an unknown illness. Margaretha Leimberger, formerly married to Georgia Ranger Gabriel Bach, contracted a venereal disease while at Fort Argyle and, after moving back to Ebenezer, she traveled to town to obtain medicine for her "infirmities" (Jones 1984). Many of the rangers living at Fort Argyle undoubtedly suffered similarly from their social interactions. However, given the state of medical practice in the mid-eighteenth century and its risky outcomes, the dearth of drugs and medical care at Fort Argyle may actually have been a blessing.

Tableware Glass

Drinking goblet fragments recovered from Fort Argyle attest to the consumption of wine or other low-alcohol beverages. While hard liquor was forbidden from June 1735 to 1745, beer, wine and ale were not. On the frontier, crystal glassware was an expensive, high status item and something it is unlikely that most private soldiers could afford. Thus, areas where it is located within Fort Argyle may provide clues as to the higher status discard by officers, who were more likely to be able to afford such luxuries.

Previous excavations at Fort Argyle yielded 18 goblet glass sherds and 76 clear, curved glass sherds, which probably represent small fragments of tableware, most likely goblet glass (Elliott 1997:148). LG²ES recovered 80 sherds of probable tableware glass. Most of these were small fragments of curved clear glass that are possibly goblet fragments. Tableware glass was located in 11 features, including F175F, F176C, F251A, F287, F314, F328, F343, F363, F379, F384 and F388 (Figure 6.96). Blocks AC, AG, AH and AI contained no evidence of tableware glass. Block AE located near the south-central part of Forts B and C contained the most tableware glass (n=9, or 2.25 sherds/m²). Block X, on the east side of Fort Argyle's A-C, contained the second highest frequency of tableware glass (n=16, or 0.67 sherds/ m²). The remaining blocks contained moderate to low amounts of this high-status ware. One goblet stem, a small fragment, was excavated from the Block W plow zone and a goblet base came from the plow zone of Block V. Tumblers are another type of glass drinking vessel seen at Fort Argyle. Excavations in blocks W and AB each yielded single fragments of polychrome, hand-painted, clear-glass tumbler sherds. Blocks AA and AB each yielded single examples of an etched clear tableware glass vessel.

Ceramics

The 1985 excavations at Fort Argyle yielded approximately 383 historic ceramic sherds. This assemblage was dominated by yellow slipwares (n=178, or 46.7%), followed by unrefined lead-glazed coarse earthenwares (n=99, or 25%), salt-glazed stonewares (n=39, or slightly more than 10%), English delftware (n=17), plain creamware (n=12), porcelain (n=10), Jackfield (n=9), whiteware (n=8), pearlware (n=4), Whieldon ware (n=3), Agateware (n=1) and Astbury ware (n=1). The pearlware and

Figure 6.96 Kitchen artifacts, tableware (a. Clear floral etched glass rim, LN201.371.002; b. Clear glass polychrome, hand-painted tumbler, LN201.125.009; c. Clear goblet stem, LN201.422.003; d. Clear goblet base, LN201.294.004).

whiteware sherds clearly post-date the ranger occupation of Fort Argyle (Braley et al. 1985:55-58). Braley used 265 sherds to calculate a mean occupation date of 1738.3 for this Fort Argyle assemblage. Martin and her colleagues (1986:14-15) reported an MCD of 1859.3 (n=59) for the northern end of 9BN28. When they removed the obvious nineteenth-century artifacts from their calculations, they obtained an MCD of 1744.4 (n=11). Elliott summarized the ceramics recovered from the 1985 and 1996 excavations. These included: English delftware (n=74), Spanish Majolica (n=1), Whieldon ware (n=26), creamware (n=43), and pearlware (n=10), refined white salt-glazed stoneware (n=103), molded white salt-glazed stoneware (n=9), scratch blue salt-glazed stoneware (n=15), brown salt-glazed stoneware (n=29), Nottingham stoneware (n=24), Rhenish stoneware (n=5), yellow slipware (n=508), Jackfield ware (n=23), Astbury ware (n=4), Metropolitan ware (n=2), refined Agateware (n=2), coarse lead-glazed earthenware (n=264) and porcelain (n=38) (Elliott et al. 2020: Appendix A, Elliott 1997:142-146).

LG²ES recovered a similar assortment of historic ceramic sherds compared with the previous excavations (Figure 6.97 and Figure 6.98). LG²ES's sample of 1,020 sherds with known mean manufacture dates from the colonial period (or estimated mean use in colonial Georgia, as in the case of lead-glazed coarse earthenware and redware) was used to calculate mean ceramic dates for various contexts at Fort Argyle. This sample produced a site wide MCD of 1742.42. These data also were used to calculate MCDs for each excavation block and for selected features. Terminus post quem (TPQ) dates were used to compare the beginning manufacture dates for the latest ware type in various contexts at the site. Specific ceramic types at Fort Argyle are examined below.

English delftware is a tin-enameled, low-fired ceramic that was produced in England from about 1640 to 1800. The firm of Morel and Telfair of Savannah advertised "delft ware" for sale as late as May 1765 (*The Georgia Gazette* 1765:5). Eighteenth-century varieties of English delftware include polychrome hand-painted, blue hand-painted and undecorated types. Delftware was a common table service before it was displaced by the production of creamware around 1762. English delftware continued in use for chamber pots and apothecary jars. In Georgia delftware occurs from 1733 until the American Revolution, when it virtually disappears from the archaeological record.

Yellow slipware is a low-fired, lead-glazed pottery that was produced in England in the eighteenth century. The main center of manufacture for this widely popular ceramic was the Staffordshire region. Decorative styles include combed, trailed, dotted, combinations of these decorative techniques, and plain, undecorated yellow slipware. Marbling is another, less common design technique used on these wares. Yellow slipware was produced from about 1670 until about 1795 (South 1977:211; Cooper 1968). It was used to make plates, platters, cups, and small bowls. In Georgia, this pottery type occurs from 1733 until the American Revolution. Yellow slipware was the most common pottery recovered from Fort Argyle prior to the LG²ES excavations.

Stoneware is fired at high temperatures in a kiln. It was primarily a utilitarian ware, although refined stonewares were popular in the mid eighteenth-century. Rhenish (or Westerwald) stoneware was produced in the eighteenth-century in Germany. Surface decorations on this thick ware include incising, molding and blue (most common), purple and brown glaze on a dull gray paste. Drinking tankards and chamber pots made of this ware are relatively common on British colonial sites. In America, Rhenish stoneware dates from about 1700 to 1775. In Georgia, Rhenish stoneware occurs from 1733 until the American Revolution. The Fort Argyle examples of Rhenish stoneware are highly fragmented. Twenty examples were identified from the LG²ES excavations and only five sherds came from previous excavations.

British Brown stoneware is a generic term for large utilitarian brown salt-glazed stoneware vessels produced in England from about 1690 and 1775. It is derived from similar wares produced in Germany in the seventeenth century. In colonial Georgia British Brown Stoneware was used from 1733 until the American Revolution (South 1977).

Nottingham stoneware is a refined, brown, salt-glazed stoneware that contains a tell-tale thin layer of cream-colored slip beneath the salt glaze. This ware was produced in England from about 1700 to 1810 (South 1977:210). Nottingham ware is very uncommon on archaeological sites in Georgia after the American Revolution.

Burslem stoneware is a refined, brown, salt-glazed stoneware similar to Nottingham stoneware but lacking the cream-colored slip. Burslem stoneware is often decorated with rouletted punctations or molded lines (South 1977:210; Noel Hume 1983:111-114). This ware was produced in England from in the mid-eighteenth century.

Figure 6.97 Kitchen artifacts, ceramics (a. Underglazed hand-painted porcelain, rim sherds, one geometric design, one with red edged rim, LN201.163.016; b. Underglazed hand-painted porcelain bowl lid with red edged rim, LN201.171.017; c. Underglazed hand-painted porcelain body, LN201.168.010; d. Underglazed hand-painted porcelain blue and brown rim, LN201.177.015; e. Underglazed hand-painted porcelain blue and brown rim, LN201.161.019; f. Underglazed hand-painted porcelain rim, LN201.111.002; g. Underglazed hand-painted porcelain teacup, LN201.145.024; h. Underglazed hand-painted porcelain body, LN201.353.006; i. Refined salt-glazed molded plate rim, dot, diaper, and basket, LN201.104.016; j. Rhenish stoneware body, LN201.159.022; k. Scratch blue salt-glazed stoneware body, LN201.125.001).

Figure 6.98 Kitchen artifacts, ceramics, additional examples (a. Refined white salt-glazed stoneware base, LN201.153.010; b. British brown salt-glazed stoneware body, LN201.161.014; c. Coarse earthenware rim, LN201.115.005; d. Delft, glazeless and hand-painted blue and white bodies, LN201.142.003; e. Polychrome hand-painted delft, LN201.172.006; f. Trailed yellow slipware with piecrust rim, LN201.164.019; g. Dotted yellow slipware base, LN201.310.006; h. Combed yellow slipware body, LN201.145.016; i. Unusual trailed yellow slipware with piecrust rim, LN201.366.021; j. Trailed yellow slipware body, LN201.155.021; k. Trailed/swirled yellow slipware with piecrust rim).

Black basalt is a refined, dry-bodied stoneware that has a distinctive black paste. It was usually unglazed. It was produced by Josiah Wedgwood in England using a variety of methods including, after 1760, geometric engine turning. The Florida Museum dates Black basalt from about 1750 to 1820 (Florida Museum 2019).

Elers-type stoneware is a red, dry-bodied refined stoneware that was produced in Staffordshire, England beginning in 1684. Production of this ware temporarily ceased around 1700 but was revived about 1750 when this ceramic technique was emulated by other English potters that followed the more famous Elers brothers, to whom this ware is typically attributed. Engine-turned, dry-bodied, red stoneware was not produced until 1760, when it was made by Josiah Wedgwood's pottery. Vessel forms include tea services, beer steins and other tableware (Woollisroft 2019; South 1977; Noel Hume 1983; Florida Museum 2019). The single example of an engine-turned, dry-bodied red stoneware teapot was recovered from Block Z plow zone at Fort Argyle. This sherd probably dates after 1760 but prior to 1800 and it has a mean production date of 1780.

Refined white salt-glazed stoneware was produced in England from about 1720 until about 1805. White salt-glazed stoneware was used for table service in the mid-eighteenth century. Molded plate rims were produced after 1740, including Dot, Diaper and Basket; Bead and Reel; and Barley motifs (Noel Hume 1983, 2001; Florida Museum 2019). Molded salt-glazed stoneware plates were produced until about 1765 (South 1977:210; Noel Hume 1983:116).

Scratch blue salt-glazed stoneware was produced as table service in England from about 1744 until 1775. It has an estimated mean manufacture date of 1759.5. A debased form of Scratch blue stoneware was produced as late as 1795, but no sherds of the debased ware were observed in the Fort Argyle assemblage. Small bowls and saucers are the most common vessel form for scratch blue ceramics (South 1977:210; Noel Hume 1983:117).

Coarse earthenware was a low-fired pottery produced in England and in southeastern North America in the eighteenth century. Its low fired nature made it less durable, but also less expensive than stonewares. It was a common lead-glazed (and unglazed) ceramic that was fashioned into a variety of utilitarian forms, including storage jars, cooking pots, creampans, pitchers and water bottles. Less commonly, this vernacular ware was made as table service, including saucers and sugar bowls. Coarse earthenware is extremely common on pre-Revolutionary War sites in eastern Effingham County, in particular at the settlement of Ebenezer, which has yielded vast amounts of this ware. Excavations at the Ebenezer Mill District revealed that more than 90 percent of the farmstead's ceramic assemblage was coarse earthenware (Elliott and Smith 1985; Smith 1986). It was the second most frequent ware found at Fort Argyle from previous excavations (Braley et al. 1985; Elliott 1997: Appendix 1). While coarse earthenware has a long history of production in Europe, its occurrence on archaeological sites in coastal Georgia, particularly at Ebenezer (9EF28), is more tightly constrained to between 1734 and 1780 (Elliott 2016b:45). It does not appear on sites in coastal Georgia dating after the American Revolution.

Coarse earthenware is not easily distinguished from unrefined redware, which was also usually lead glazed. Recent excavations by the LAMAR Institute at the South Carolina colonial town of Purysburg

located a pottery manufacturing site from the late 1730s-early 1740s. A pottery waster deposit there yielded several thousand sherds of a lead glazed red-bodied to buff bodied ware, which was produced in vessel forms that are nearly identical in paste, glaze, and vessel form to the thousands of coarse earthenware sherds that the LAMAR Institute has excavated from the town of Ebenezer (located just a few miles upstream from Purysburg on the Georgia side of the Savannah River) (Elliott 2016a-b; Elliott and Elliott 2017). The town of Ebenezer boasted one potter, Jacob Gnann, who arrived and set up his pottery operation after 1751 at Bethany, a satellite settlement of Ebenezer located a few miles upstream.

Since both coarse earthenware and redware (both employing lead glazes) were extremely popular throughout the colonial period in Georgia but end abruptly at the time of the American Revolution, we have used a date range of 1734 to 1780 for both of these ceramic types. While we acknowledge that these two ware types had a far greater lifespan in other parts of the world, both seem to be relatively good time markers for coastal Georgia and have been included in our Mean Ceramic Date (MCD) calculations. A mean date of 1756.5, which was derived from the median between 1733 and 1780, was used for both types.

Jackfield ware is a black lead-glazed redware pottery made in Jackfield, Shropshire, England from about 1740 or 1750 to about 1775-1790 (South 1977:211). It is not common on sites in Georgia dating after 1780. This ware has a thin, refined red clay body. Vessel forms made of Jackfield include tea service (teapots, sugar bowls) and decorative figurines.

Refined earthenwares of the eighteenth century were thin cream-colored wares with a light-colored paste. These wares were fired at a moderately high temperature. Most were manufactured in England, although some local potters, such as John Bartlam in Cainhoy, South Carolina and other potters in the Moravian Wachovia settlement of central North Carolina, were producing similar wares in North America (Bivins 1972). Refined earthenwares included types such as Whieldon ware, creamware, and pearlware.

Whieldon ware is a colorful, refined tableware that was created in England in the mid-eighteenth century. Thomas Whieldon produced this ceramic with its characteristic tortoiseshell glaze on top of a cream-colored ware beginning around 1740 (South 1977; University of Florida Museum 2019). He produced a range of table service, as well as figurines. Between 1759 and 1764 English potters Thomas Whieldon and Josiah Wedgwood collaborated in the manufacture of a series of cauliflower motif table settings. Complete intact examples of these pottery vessels, which include teapots and other table service, have survived and attest to the skill of these master potters (Florida International University 2019). In Georgia, Whieldon ware occurs on sites from about 1740 until shortly after 1755.

Creamware, or Queensware, was first produced in England in 1762 by Josiah Wedgwood. Its durable nature and decorative qualities quickly became a popular ware that supplanted English delftware and refined white salt-glazed stoneware for common table service. Creamware remained in production until about 1830. This ware is distinguished from later ceramics, such as pearlware and whiteware, by its cream-colored finish. Creamware has an estimated mean manufacture date of 1796. South (1993) excavated the pottery waster site of John Bartlam, who operated a pottery at Cainhoy, South Carolina.

Bartlam's work is nearly indistinguishable from the Whieldon ware and creamware produced in Staffordshire.

Pearlware ceramics were produced in England by 1774 where it rivaled creamware as a popular table service in the British Empire. Pearlware is a refined white-bodied, white paste ware, which is often recognized by a distinctive light blue pooling in the vessel seams and crevices. When compared to its successor, whiteware, pearlware often has a distinctive blue tint. Any pearlware, whiteware or ironstone sherds found at Fort Argyle would post-date the colonial ranger fort era.

Metal cookware

The firm of Morel and Telfair of Savannah advertised for sale in May 1765, "iron pots, skillets, and frying pans" (*The Georgia Gazette* 1765:5). Previous excavations at Fort Argyle yielded 14 sherds of cast iron cookware and one large iron cooking spoon (Elliott 1997:148). No cooking spoons or forks were located by the LG²ES team. LG²ES recovered only seven sherds of cast iron cookware. Five of these were located by the metal detector survey.

6.5.4 Furniture Group

Archaeologists previously located no artifacts from the furniture group from excavations at Fort Argyle (Elliott 1997:165). The absence of furniture hardware was confirmed by the LG²ES team.

6.5.5 Personal Group

Braley et al. (1985:66) reported finding only one artifact in the personal group—a slate pencil. Personal items recovered during the LG²ES excavations consisted primarily of a few coins and tokens and one piece of mirror glass.

Coins and Tokens

Colonial coins are extremely rare at Fort Argyle, only three have been recovered by archaeologists. One worn, copper British halfpenny (ca. 1729-1754) was previously excavated at Fort Argyle from the plow zone in Excavation Block J (Elliott 1997:154). LG²ES's team confirmed the rarity of coinage at Fort Argyle, recovering only two coins—one silver and one copper (Figure 6.99).

Archaeologists discovered a silver Spanish reale near the bottom of a palisade ditch (F363) in the northeastern part of Fort Argyle in Excavation Block AD. The silver coin from Fort Argyle is a heavily clipped, irregular-shaped polygon measuring 19.28 mm at its maximum dimension and 1.99 mm in thickness. Irregularly shaped silver coins were often illegally clipped along their edges to steal small amounts of silver, while also trying to maintain the original value of the stamped coin. The silver reale at Fort Argyle weighs 3.7 g. It has a raised "M", which signifies that it was minted in Mexico. The Spanish colony of Mexico discontinued the manufacture of stamped cob coins such as this one in 1732, when they replaced them with circular, milled coins that could not be clipped.

Figure 6.99 Personal artifacts, coins and tokens (a. Counterfeit, extremely worn 18th century British halfpence, LN201.159.001; b. Pre-1732 Spanish silver real cob coin, LN201.319.001; c. Pre-1791 copper token perforated for wearing, LN201.025.001).

While its date was lacking, this style of “cob” coin was minted decades before Fort Argyle was constructed. Still, its presence at Fort Argyle is not totally unexpected. Older Spanish silver coins remained in circulation in southeastern North America long after they were minted. This was in response to the scarcity of coinage in the British colonies. Spanish silver coins were relatively common around the world, if not at Fort Argyle, and they remained legal currency in Georgia until the Coinage Act of 1857 (Martin 1977:1009-1027).

The silver coin's pXRF results were compared with a Bolivia minted Spanish cob silver coin in Elliott's private collection. These two coins were strikingly similar in their elemental content. The complete results of this exercise are included in Appendix B.

The other coin find in 2018/2019 was a heavily worn copper planchet that was discovered from excavations in the Level 1 plow-disturbed zone of Excavation Block Y. This presumed coin was initially identified in the lab as a British half penny. The date had been completely worn off and only faint traces of King George II or III's bust were visible on the obverse and a seated Britannia was faintly visible on the reverse. The disc measures 27.52 mm in diameter and it weighs 6.9 g. Its metric attributes were compared with two British half pennies, both minted in the reign of King George II, in the Elliott's private collection. One 1737 coin measured 28.61 mm in diameter, and it weighed 8.6 g, and a 1738 coin measured 28.1 mm and it weighed 8.7 g. The Fort Argyle half penny measured slightly smaller in diameter and weighed slightly less than the two compared examples. The bust of King George on British half pennies was alternated several times during his reign. Coins minted prior to 1729 have a right-facing bust and those minted in 1729 and later are left-facing. Coins minted between 1729 and 1739 depict a young King George II, while those minted from 1740 and later show a much older king. Half pennies minted in the early years of King George III display a right-facing bust (Seaby and Purvey 1980:225, Bruce 1981).

A solid copper British half penny (or halfpence) in the eighteenth-century was worth 1/24 Shilling or 1/480 pounds sterling. The original standard weight of British halfpence was 46 to the pound avoirdupois (0.35 ounces or 9.92 g each). King George II's 1742 British half pennies measured 28 mm in diameter and weighed 9.86 g and 1770 British half pennies, minted during the reign of George III, measured between 28.5 and 30 mm in diameter and weighed an average of 9.9 g.

Earlier in our analysis the copper coin from Fort Argyle was suspected of being either a British half penny that was minted during the reign of King George II or King George III. Our pXRF analysis of the coin's elemental content, however, proved that this was not the case. It is in fact a historic counterfeit. The Fort Argyle coin was composed of a variety of elements, including copper, but when the pXRF results from this specimen were compared with two British half pennies, stark differences became apparent. The 1737 and 1738 coins contained substantially more copper and less other metals than the Fort Argyle coin. The complete results of this exercise are included in Appendix B.

It seems that counterfeit British half pennies from the eighteenth century are not particularly uncommon (Parrott 1751; Snelling 1766; Jordan 2019a-c). The Brits have been producing counterfeits since Roman times and the British halfpence of the eighteenth century was a repeated target. Writing on the subject in 1751, Richard Parrott noted, "Of counterfeit Half-pence there are now almost infinite Sorts. Every Town and Village has its Mint, where many of our Master-Manufacturers get them coined as cheap as they can for their own Use to pay their Workmen with. Each endeavours the under-coin his Rival, in order to under-sell him in his Trade" (Parrott 1751:2). Parrott addresses the metal content of counterfeit halfpence made after 1736, noting, "the Counterfeit is full as large and heavy as the true one. The Deficiency is not in Weight but in Goodness of Metal; they yield about three-fourths Copper, the remaining fourth being Dross or Lead of no value at all; The Coiner's Gain in these is Four-pence as

before; Three pence by deficiency of Copper, and the one Penny allowed the Mint" (Parrott 1751:3-4). Cast and struck varieties of counterfeits were produced. Counterfeit halfpence were produced in the American colonies beginning around 1741 (Betts 1886:2).

Several examples of counterfeit half pennies made during King George II's reign are documented (Jordan 2019a). Counterfeit halfpence, possibly including some made in America, are dated 1741, 1744, 1747 and 1757 (Betts 1886:2). One example made after 1729 measures 28.58 mm in diameter and weighs 7.87 g. One example made after 1736 measures 27.8 mm in diameter and weighs 8.59 g. One cast example minted after 1739 measures 27.63 mm in diameter and weighs 10.7 g. One cast example dating after 1745 measured 28.0 mm in diameter and weighted 7.64 g (Jordan 2019a). In comparison, the example recovered from Fort Argyle in 2018/2019 measured 27.52 mm in diameter and weighed 6.9 g.

The legal problem with counterfeit British coins continued in King George III's times. Undated examples made in the reign of King George III include one that measures 26.7 mm in diameter and weighs 4.38 g and another that measures 27.7 mm in diameter weighing 6.48 g (Jordan 2019b). Counterfeiting in the American colonies was such a problem that in 1767, the Rhode Island legislature passed an act, "making it death for any person to counterfeit any British or foreign coin, or to pass the same, knowing it to be such" (*The South Carolina Gazette* February 16, 1767).

From 1730-1770, the daily wage in Great Britain for a skilled tradesman held steady at about 2 shillings (The National Archive 2019). For that same time period an average 10 days' wages of a skilled tradesman could be bought for one pound Sterling. One cow cost five pounds Sterling and 1 horse was worth seven pounds Sterling. It took 480 halfpence to equal one pound Sterling and it would have required 3,360 halfpence to purchase a horse anytime from 1730s through the 1760s. It seems ludicrous to us today that it would have been worth the counterfeiter's time and effort to make fakes of the low denomination British halfpence, but they did and in great quantities and the counterfeit coins were used throughout the colonies, including at Fort Argyle.

LG²ES archaeologists also unearthed a thin, stamped brass token during the metal detector survey. This token depicted Lady Liberty with 13 small stars in the surround. The token was only decorated on one side and it was perforated with a single hole above Lady Liberty's head. This object clearly post-dates the Rangers' occupation at Fort Argyle, but it may represent a personal item that was lost during the brief, early Federal military occupation of the 1780s and 1790s.

6.5.6 Arms Group

Initial excavations in 1985 revealed an assortment of Arms Group artifacts including musket or pistol balls (n=4), lead shot (n=15), lead waste and sprues, and gunflints (n=9). The lead balls ranged in size from .55 to .59 caliber and the lead shot ranged from .09 to .36 caliber (Braley et al. 1985:62-63). Braley wrote that "the majority of the musket balls, shot, and gun flints" were recovered from the northern and eastern portion of Fort Argyle. Elliott (1997:156) noted that 193 arms group artifacts were previously excavated from Fort Argyle from 1985-1996. The LG²ES excavations substantially added to the quantity and variety of the Arms Group category.

Cannons, Swivel Guns and Wall Guns

Artillery played an important role at Fort Argyle, as it did throughout the eighteenth-century world (Manucy 1985; Peterson 1969). All artillery in the colonial era were smoothbore guns. These included cannons, mortars and howitzers. Archaeologists have recovered two iron cannon fragments from two distinct cannons at the Georgia Ranger fort at Mount Pleasant on the Savannah River and these weapons were likely similar to ordnance at Fort Argyle. Both cannons at Mount Pleasant apparently exploded during use and the fragments were located on opposite sides of the ridge containing the ranger fort. Both forts Argyle and Mount Pleasant were never under attack and no major hostilities ever took place at either fort (Elliott 1991a:13-21, 1997:27-63; Ivers 1974; Johnson 1992).

From its earliest days in 1734 Fort Argyle was defended by four cannons. The number of cannons mounted in the fort in later times is not recorded and may have been higher. The size of the cannons and other important attributes about the heavy ordinance at Fort Argyle went unrecorded.

While no cannons have been found at Fort Argyle, one piece of ammunition for them has been unearthed. This was a small cast iron ball (42 mm or 1.65 in in diameter, weighing 260 g, or 0.57 lbs.) that was recovered from 1996 dig at Excavation Block I (Elliott 1997:158). We suspect that this ball probably was intended to be fired as cannister shot rather than as a single shot. If it was intended for use as a single shot, it would have most likely have been fired from a 1-pounder cannon (Collins 2019; Melton 2019). A large lead ball, .82 caliber, also was recovered in the 1996 excavations (Elliott 1997:158). A large lead ball of this size was fired either as case shot, or as a single shot in a large caliber, mounted wall gun. No cast iron balls or larger caliber lead balls were recovered from LG²ES excavations at Fort Argyle.

Small Arms

Eighteenth century English trade guns, or the Carolina gun have been the subject of study by numerous scholars since the mid-twentieth century (Peterson 1956; Hanson 1966:18-23; Neumann 1967; Hamilton 1976, 1980; Madaus 1981; Burke 1991:2-16). In an inventory of a Virginia trader from the period 1732-1740, were "40 Carolina guns", whose value was 11 shillings 4 pence each. Burke (1991:7) described one complete example of a Carolina gun as, "a light weight, fully stocked, smooth bore, flintlock, measuring 61 inches overall, with a 46 ½ inch barrel of .628 inch bore (or about 19 gauge). Present weight, unloaded, with wood ramrod in place, is 5 pounds 5 ounces". Its stock was made of beech wood. This general description may apply to some of the weapons carried by the South Carolina Rangers and Georgia Rangers at Fort Argyle. The single gun barrel section recovered by LG²ES from Fort Argyle had an estimated bore diameter slightly larger than .60 inch. Other archaeological evidence suggests that shorter weapons with smaller bore diameters were used in coastal Georgia. British records from 1773 state that Georgia Rangers were to be equipped with "a rifle, two dragoon pistols, a hanger (sword), a powder horn, a shot pouch, and a tomahawk" (P.R.O., Audit Office, Georgia Loyalist Claims AO 13/37, Thomas Waters, June 16, 1773). Captain Waters' Georgia Rangers were posted at a fort at the forks of the Savannah and Broad rivers in northeastern Georgia. Waters' ranger troop post-dates those at Fort Argyle by about six years, but his men's equipage was generally the same. It is interesting to note that the word "rifle" was used to describe their long arms. Archaeologists have found no direct evidence for rifles at either forts Argyle or Mount Pleasant, only smoothbores.

The Georgia Ranger fort at Mount Pleasant (Site 9EF169) has yielded a large assemblage of early arms associated with the Yuchi village, deerskin traders and Georgia Rangers who inhabited the Mount Pleasant bluff. Among these weapons was a single example of a blunderbuss. The blunderbuss was an early version of a shotgun. Marchant (1760) defines blunderbuss as, "a short gun, with a large bore, which discharges many bullets at once". The weapon had a flaring barrel that permitted the use of ammunition of various sizes. This class of firearm was quite useful for crowd control and in marine settings, useful for defending against boarding parties. The blunderbuss would only be effective at close range (generally less than 15 meters). The Fort Mount Pleasant blunderbuss was discarded after the gun exploded near the breech (Elliott 1991a:13-21). While no evidence for blunderbusses was located at Fort Argyle, the presence of one at another, contemporary Georgia Ranger fort on the Savannah River may indicate that similar weapons were present at Fort Argyle. While Argyle was not the permanent home to a large group of Creek or Yuchi Indians, hundreds of Creeks stopped at the fort, often for weeks at a time, while enroute to Savannah. The rangers may have kept such weapons on hand for potential crowd control.

Ivers (1986:79) insisted that the Georgia Rangers were outfitted with the British long land muskets, but archaeological evidence observed thus far at Fort Argyle and Fort Mount Pleasant suggests otherwise. The British long land musket, also known as the Brown Bess, had a .75 caliber bore diameter and typically fired around a .69-.70 caliber ball. The Fort Argyle lead ball assemblage includes only a couple of examples of balls in this caliber range, indicating that Ivers assertion is wrong. Brown Bess muskets were extremely rare at Fort Argyle, if they were ever present.

Gun hardware is amazingly rare at Fort Argyle. This is ironic given that the fort served as a military site and was garrisoned by dozens of armed rangers for over two decades. Previous excavations at Fort Argyle found only one example of gun hardware, which was a small section of an iron gun barrel that had been intentionally flattened, possibly for use as a flesher or a chisel (Elliott 1997:156-157). The scarcity of gun parts is surprising given that other evidence of small arms in the form of ammunition and gunflints have been recovered in significant quantities. The Fort Argyle gun hardware inventory stands in drastic contrast to the many dozens of brass and iron gun parts recovered from Fort Mount Pleasant, a contemporary Georgia Ranger fort on the lower Savannah River (Elliott in press b).

The metal detector survey in 2018 by LG²ES located seven pieces of brass gun hardware and one made of iron. The largest item was a straight section of an iron gun barrel that was recovered from the base of the plow zone in Block Z, where it was lying horizontally at the upper surface of F299 (a northern palisade trench) (Figure 6.100). This gun barrel was heavily corroded and is being conserved. Preliminary measurements of the barrel's interior bore diameter indicate that it was slightly greater than 0.60 caliber.

LG²ES archaeologists recovered three fragments of brass trigger guards from flintlock weapons. The most complete specimen came from F221 (an eastern palisade trench) in Excavation Block X. It is shown in Figure 6.101. Another trigger guard was excavated from F363 (a northern palisade trench) in Excavation Block AD. It was a crude trigger guard made of a narrow strip of thin sheet brass that had broken into three sections. A third example was a cast brass trigger guard midsection that was recovered from the plowzone in Block AA. None of the trigger guards bear any markings.

Archaeologists recovered one small piece of a stamped sheet-brass dragon side plate from a flintlock weapon. It is shown in Figure 6.102. It included the head of the dragon, a motif common on Indian trade guns throughout the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries. This motif also occurs on weapons used by non-Native Americans. Dragon side plates are quite common in the contemporary arms assemblage at Forts Frederica and Mount Pleasant (Hamilton 1980; Elliott in press b).

Figure 6.100 Gun barrel at interface of plowzone and Feature 299 palisade trench

Figure 6.101 Arms artifacts, brass trigger guards (a. LN201.329.007, b. LN201.189.001, c. LN201.319.020).

Figure 6.102 Arms artifacts, lead patches and brass gun parts (a. and b. Lead gunflint patch, LN201.417.001 and LN201.452.001; c. Brass dragon sideplate fragment, LN201.231.001; d. Brass gun part, LN201.009.001; e. Brass decorate gun escutcheon, LN201.242.001; f. Brass rear ramrod guide fragment, LN201.241.001; g. Brass floral hangar guard fragment, LN201.073.002).

The metal detector survey located one complete brass escutcheon with a portion of an iron screw attached. It bears no markings other than stamped or engraved lines near the finial, which served a decorative purpose. (See previous figure.) The fact that this artifact was lost or discarded with a screw attachment may indicate that it likely remained attached to the wooden gunstock when it was left in or on the soil.

The metal detector survey also located a tail-end fragment of a rear ramrod guide that was cast from brass. (See previous figure). We were unable to identify the specific weapon type for which this ramrod guide was intended, but our comparisons indicate that it is not from a British Brown Bess musket.

The senior author analyzed six brass gun parts from the Fort Argyle assemblage for their elemental content using pXRF technology. The complete results of this exercise are included in Appendix B.

Lead Balls

Lead balls and small lead shot are another common artifact type on eighteenth-century military sites, including Fort Argyle. The monetary value of lead ammunition also was relatively low in colonial Georgia. The 1733 Treaty of Savannah recorded the agreed price of 60 bullets for one buckskin, or two doeskins (Juricek 1989:15-17).

Lead was an important commodity for both Native Americans and Euro-Americans living in the southeastern frontier. Newman (1977:37-39) analyzed a sample of 51 lead balls excavated from the Cherokee town of Chota-Tanassee. They ranged in diameter from 9.5-19 mm, or .370-.741 caliber. Most (n=33) of that sample were from .526 to .585 caliber, or 13.5-15 mm in diameter. Newman made a distinction between larger lead balls and small lead shot. He noted that 21 lead shot from this site fell between 3-5 mm in diameter. He also noted that the excavations yielded 213 pieces of lead sprue and lead scrap that indicated bullet manufacturing at Chota-Tanassee.

Many lead balls and other arms-related goods in the 1730s were imported to Georgia via Charleston, South Carolina. *The South Carolina Gazette* reported on November 9 and 16, 1734 of the arrival of the ship *Mary Ann* from London, which contained an assortment of goods for sale including, "drop shot, bullets, Carolina guns, gun-powder, pewter, nails, axes, hoes, frying-pan", and non-durable goods (*The South Carolina Gazette* 1734). The same newspaper announced on January 29, 1737 the arrival of the ship, *William Francis Baker* from London, whose cargo included, "cutlery, haberdashery, china, earthen and glass ware...pewter...stockings and shoes, short [sic, shot], bullets, gun powder, Indian trading guns, flints...and sundry other Goods" (*The South Carolina Gazette* 1737). The newspaper noted the arrival of the ship *Samuel* in August 31, 1738, whose cargo included: "trading Guns...Brass Kettles...Guilt Belts and Hatchets, Silver polish'd Earrings, and Stone Rings, fine Needles, and most sorts of Haberdashery ware, Brass Candlesticks...Bullets, Swan and drop Shott and Gunpowder...with sundry Goods" (*The South Carolina Gazette* 1738). Some of these goods, particularly the shot, bullets, flints and gunpowder, may have found their way to Fort Argyle with the South Carolina Rangers.

Lead balls recently recovered from the battlefield at Gully Hole Creek on St. Simons Island, provide some clues to the weapon class used by Georgia troops under General Oglethorpe's command in July 1742. The Georgia Rangers are historically documented participants in this battle. These may have included rangers from Fort Argyle. Seibert and his team recovered seven large lead balls ranging from 0.54 to 0.65 caliber and smaller buckshot. Calibers of these seven balls were derived using the Sivilich Formula (Seibert 2019:12). None of these balls are large enough for British Brown Bess musket ammunition. Continuing research on the elemental content of the balls recovered from the Gully Hole Creek battlefield promises to shed further light on Georgia Ranger's weaponry.

Fort Argyle has revealed a much larger sample of lead balls associated with the South Carolina and Georgia Rangers, circa 1733-1767. Elliott (1997:160) measured the diameters of lead balls recovered from the 1995-1996 excavations. In the sample of 20 balls, Elliott observed only four balls larger in diameter than .60 caliber. Only one of these balls was in the size range suitable for use with a .75 caliber musket. Elliott's sample indicated three groupings of lead balls by size. The smallest group included balls from .14 to .16 caliber. These were followed by a larger group that included balls from .21 to .39 caliber and a third group that ranged from .55 to .61 caliber. The largest lead ball reported from the 1996 excavations, which measured approximately 0.81 caliber, was not likely fired from a handgun but was more likely used with a wall gun, or as a case shot load fired from a cannon (Elliott 1997:158, 160, Table 5).

A much larger sample of lead balls (N=504) was recovered at Fort Argyle by LG²ES excavations. Most of these lead balls were analyzed with pXRF technology. This provides detailed information on the elemental content of each ball. This documentation builds on a growing research database of eighteenth and early nineteenth-century lead balls in eastern North America. Since 2015 researchers have gathered elemental data on lead balls from battlefields and other military and domestic sites from dozens of archaeological sites along the Eastern Seaboard. While the bulk of these samples date to the American Revolutionary War period (1775-1782), several sizeable samples date to the period when Fort Argyle was occupied. These include Fort Frederica and Fort Mount Pleasant, Georgia; Fort Moore, South Carolina; Fort Necessity, Pennsylvania and most recently, Arbuckle's Fort, West Virginia (Elliott and Seibert 2017; Seibert et al. 2018; Elliott 2018c).

For the present study, Mr. Elliott conducted pXRF analysis on a sample of a variety of lead items, including cast lead balls, smaller lead shot, lead ball casting sprue, melted lead and assorted lead scrap excavated by LG²ES from Fort Argyle. These results are discussed and summarized below and additional documentation from the pXRF analysis is presented in Appendix B of this report. Figure 6.103 shows examples of some types of lead recovered.

Researchers struggled to make a distinction between cast lead balls and smaller pellets, or small shot, which were produced by different methods. Many previous researchers avoided this problem by simply lumping all the smaller lead balls into a small shot, buckshot, birdshot or similar less rigorous category. The discussion below examines this issue in greater detail.

Rupert shot was produced by pouring molten lead through a brass colander suspended above a water container. The colander created small lead clumps that formed spherical shapes when pulled towards the ground by gravity until stopped and cooled by the water. This method was first promoted by Prince Rupert in 1665. The process yields a slightly oval-shaped shot with a small dimple on one surface. Shot towers were used to produce small spherical shot by the late eighteenth century (Hooke 1665; Page 2018). In 1782 William Watts, of Bristol, England, obtained the first patent for the production of drop shot from shot towers (Neely 2009:1-4; Rendell 2012). Shot towers were not likely in use during Fort Argyle's time.

Figure 6.103 Arms artifacts, lead balls and related items (a. and c. Lead ball, impacted, LN201.034.001 and LN201.248.001; b. Lead ball, cut, LN201.247.001; d. Lead casting sprue strips, gang mold, LN201.294.005; e. Modified lead cylinder, LN201.228.001).

Lead has a melting point of 621.5 degrees Fahrenheit (F). Antimony melts at 1,167 degrees F. Tin melts at 449.47 degrees F. Cast balls were produced by pouring molten lead into a two-part ball mold. A wide variety of bullet molds were in use in the eighteenth century. They ranged from molds that made a single ball to larger versions that produced multiple balls, the latter often referred to as “gang molds”. Many gang molds produced a variety of ball sizes. Many molds were made for specific weapons, particularly rifles, since most rifles were produced by individual craftsmen and were produced one at a time. The individual nature and variability of the weapon barrel’s diameter necessitated ball molds for a specific weapon. Ball molds were made of brass, iron, and soapstone.

Hamilton (1980:130-133) notes that Rupert shot and mold-cast balls can be distinguished by the mold seam and sprue cut-off scars on the cast shot, versus the dimple characteristic that results from the Rupert process. However, this distinction on archaeological specimens is not so simple or readily apparent as many of the small balls are heavily corroded or corticated, erasing evidence of casting or Rupert shot dimpling.

Morand (1994:40-43) noted that Rupert shot were frequently found at Fort Michilimackinac in Michigan. She noted that “some of this shot still has tails, indicating that it was possibly run at the fort”.

Gang molds were used to cast large and small shot. One example produced one .60 caliber ball; four.28 caliber; and six .16 caliber shot (Hanson 2001:7-13, cited in Neely 2009:1-4). With molds capable of making balls as small as .16 caliber, then it is feasible that most of the small balls at Fort Argyle were produced using this method.

Dropped musket balls and non-impacted small shot were grouped together in the pXRF analysis. These data were sorted based on the diameters of each specimen (measured in mm). The sample formed three tight size clusters, designated Class 1, 2, and 3, and detailed below.

Class 1 balls are the most common and the smallest shot grouping, which included balls from about .104 to .204 caliber. This category corresponds to the vernacular “bird shot” and would not have been particularly lethal when fired at human targets. The Rangers at Fort Argyle, along with other residents of coastal Georgia, undoubtedly spent part of their days hunting game birds, which were plentiful along the Ogeechee River. The firm of Morel and Telfair of Savannah advertised for sale, “swan, goose, turkey, duck, and bird shot” in a May 1765 newspaper advertisement (*The Georgia Gazette* 1765:5). While this smaller shot may have been intended for shooting various sizes of birds, some also were used on humans. *The South Carolina Gazette* reported on February 3, 1733, that “a Negro Man belonging to John Carmichael, Esq: at Spoon’s Savannah, was found dead, with 10 Swan Shot in his Head about 3 or 400 yards from his House’ (*The South Carolina Gazette* 1733). In this enslaved man’s case, bird shot did prove lethal.

Class 2 is the second largest shot group, which included balls from about .285 to .398 caliber. This category includes buck shot and possibly smaller pistol or rifle shot. The “buck and ball” load would not become popular in North America until the American Revolution. This type of load consisted of one large ball and two to three smaller balls. History does not record whether the Rangers in Georgia used this type of ammunition load. The Rangers did have many lead balls in the size range of buckshot, as evidenced by the Fort Argyle sample. The gunflint evidence does indicate that Fort Argyle’s Rangers carried pistols, so many of this smaller shot were possibly intended for use with that weapon class.

Class 3 is the third largest shot group, which included balls from about .524 to .637 caliber. This category contains balls intended for carbines, fusils and tradeguns.

Only five lead balls in the LG²ES sample measure .65 caliber or higher and these do not appear to be particularly clustered. These Class 4 balls were intended for larger military muskets, such as the British Brown Bess. Alternatively, some of these balls may have been intended for use as case shot in artillery loads.

Casting Sprue

LG²ES excavations confirmed that lead balls were manufactured on site at Fort Argyle. This was suggested from the data from 1996, where lead sprue and several discarded mis-cast lead balls were observed (Elliott 1997:158-159, Figure 53f). Lead sprue and melted lead was found throughout Fort Argyle from all excavation efforts. A small number of these displayed evidence that they were casting debris, likely from bullet molds. While technically this artifact type is classed under the Activities Group, it is described here because it relates to the manufacture of lead balls, which are in the Arms Group.

Gunflint Patches

Archaeologists recovered four large lead patches from the LG²ES excavations that are interpreted as lead patches intended to secure gunflints in flintlock weapons. Two were recovered from F314, one came

from F176C and one was found in the plowzone in Block AE. Two examples are illustrated in a previous figure.

Elliott's team excavated a portion of the British Spring Hill Redoubt ditch work at Savannah (used ca. October 9, 1779) and recovered an excellent example of a large French gunflint that remained encased in its protective lead patch (Figure 6.104; R. Elliott 2011). Numerous other examples of small thin, lead strips or lead scrap were found throughout the Fort Argyle excavations, but these were not conclusively identified for an intended use with firearms. Lead patches were individually fashioned by the rangers, probably by flattening a single musket ball.

Figure 6.104 French Flint with Lead Patch Intact, Spring Hill Redoubt, ca. October 9, 1779 (Courtesy of Rita Elliott).

Gunflints

Gunflints are a common artifact type on eighteenth-century military sites, including Fort Argyle. They also have immense research value for interpreting the past (Witthoft 1966; Hanson and Hsu 1970; Stone 1970; White 1975; Kent 1983; Skertchly 1984; Hamilton and Emery 1988; Kenmotsu 1990; Elliott 1992, 2018a). The monetary value of gunflints in eighteenth century Georgia was relatively low. Under the terms of the 1733 Treaty of Savannah between the Colony of Georgia and the Lower Creek Nation prices were set for various trade goods, including gunflints. One buckskin, or two doeskins, would purchase 18 gunflints. Compare this with the price of 10 buckskins or twenty doeskins, for a trade gun; five buckskins or 10 doeskins for a pistol; or four buckskins or eight doeskins for a gun lock (Juricek 1989:15-17).

Archaeologists have identified four morphological classes of gunflints in British North America based on manufacture technology: the spall and the blade (most of which were manufactured in Europe), bifacial (of Native American manufacture made from local and European ballast flint), and the chip gunflint (used during the period 1580 to 1650). The spall category includes those made from English and French flint rock, while the blade types, prior to the 1790s, were made exclusively from French flint rock. The English spall and the French blade gunflint were both in use by the mid-1600s and probably continued through

the American Revolution. The chip gunflint is not reported in the Southeastern literature, predates Fort Argyle, and is not discussed further in this study.

Elliott's (1992, 2018) study of gunflints in the southeastern United States was premised on Thomas Hamilton and Thomas Emery's seminal research (Hamilton and Emery 1988; Elliott 1992). Hamilton stated that the width of the gunflint, or that measurement perpendicular to the long axis of the gun barrel, was quite specific to the type of weapon with which it was used. The gunflint could be no wider than that allowed by the gun hardware, and, although these flintlock weapons were hand-made, by the eighteenth century, some degree of standardization in sizes had been achieved. This was particularly true among military issue weapons. Hamilton and Emery cite a French gunflint contract from 1740 that specified sizes for flints--the only such document from the period. However, it is not known how closely gunflint manufacturers adhered to these standards. At least six French musket gunflints from Fort Frederica, for example, exceeded the size specifications. It should be pointed out that Hamilton and Emery's gunflint size classification omits any discussion of gunflints used in rifles, wall guns, or blunderbusses. All three of these weapon groups were used in the colonial southeast and each has been documented archaeologically in colonial Georgia. Nevertheless, Hamilton's scheme is a useful tool for sorting gunflints into meaningful groups. Hamilton and Emery (1988) presented these width ranges for gunflints:

- Pistols, or small tradeguns - flints <20 mm
- Tradeguns - flints from 20-28 mm
- Carbines, or fowlers - flints from 28-34 mm
- Military muskets - flints >34 mm

Elliott (1992, 2018) surmised that if Hamilton and Emery's gunflint size gradations are valid divisions, then an assemblage grouped by gunflint width should reflect the types of weapons that were present on any given site. In many cases, gunflint width was actually longer than the length. Widths were measured to the nearest tenth of a millimeter. This philosophy and analysis strategy was applied to the gunflints recovered from Fort Argyle.

Forty-five gunflints or gunflint fragments were previously excavated in 1985 and 1995/1996 at Fort Argyle. Elliott (1997:161-164, Table 6; Ballin 2012:137) examined a sample of 24 complete, or nearly complete gunflints from Fort Argyle in a gunflint study. That gunflint sample included 23 spall types (17 English, 3 French, 1 local chert, 1 olive-green bottle glass) and one French blade type. Measurements of this sample yielded a mean gunflint width of 23.8 mm (width measured perpendicular to the gun barrel), mean gunflint length of 20.7 mm and mean gunflint thickness of 7.6 mm. The gunflints in the 1996 sample ranged in width from 13 to 35.6 mm.

The LG²ES excavations yielded a considerably larger sample of 172 gunflints or gunflint fragments. These specimens were analyzed following the sample strategy as that used in Elliott's earlier study. Detailed metrics were collected for 67 of these flints. The LG²ES sample subset included 56 spall type, 8 blade type, 3 spall/blade type and 2 indeterminate (broken) type flints. Complete measurements were taken from 67 gunflints. These averaged 22.32 mm in length, 27.50 mm in width, 8.43 mm in thickness and

6.14 g in weight. The gunflints had an estimated average surface area of 627.24 mm². The gunflints in the LG²ES sample subset ranged in width from 13.67 mm to 38.37 mm.

Eight flints were identified as blade-types (Figure 6.105). Five of these were likely of French origin, owing to their blade shape and honey colored flint. One was a burned example and one was made from gray flint and is tentatively identified as English. The country of origin of the other two flints remains undetermined. The blade flints averaged 20.33 mm in length, 26.62 mm in width, 9.83 mm in thickness and 5.86 g in weight. The blade-type gunflints had an estimated average surface area of 558.69 mm². The blade gunflints in the LG²ES sample ranged in width from 18.77 mm to 35.93 mm.

Fifty-six flints were identified as spall-types (Figure 6.106). These averaged 22.75 mm in length, 27.53 mm in width, 8.26 mm in thickness and 6.16 g in weight. The spall-type gunflints had an estimated average surface area of 640.81 mm². The spall gunflints in the LG²ES sample ranged in width from 13.67 mm to 38.37 mm.

Three flints in the LG²ES sample were identified as either blade or spall because each displayed attributes of both types. Two of these were identified as French in origin and the other burned example was not assigned a country of origin. Figure 6.107 shows examples of burned gunflints. This sample averaged 19.48 mm in length, 29.37 mm in width, 7.84 mm in thickness and 6.4 g in weight. The spall/blade-type gunflints had an estimated average surface area

A combined gunflint sample of 90 gunflints excavated from 1985, 1995/1996 and the 2018/2019 LG²ES excavations reveal an average gunflint length of 21.87 mm, an average width of 26.55 mm and an average thickness of 8.21 mm. The combined sample of gunflints had an estimated average surface area of 580.69 mm² and ranged in width from 13 mm to 35.93 mm. Based on the gunflint widths and Hamilton and Emery's gunflint to weapon size ranges, the predicted weapon type composition of the Fort Argyle arsenal consisted of: tradeguns (n=38), carbines or fowlers (n=29), pistols or small tradeguns (n=15), muskets (n=7) and tradegun or carbine (n=1). of 572.41 mm². The three spall/blade gunflints ranged in width from 26.30 mm to 31.32 mm.

Military muskets required gunflints greater than 34 mm wide. In Elliott's (1992) gunflint analysis musket flints comprised 11 percent of the southeastern assemblage. Frederica had the highest (39%) while six sites had no musket flints including Ackia, Mississippi; Fort Moore and New Windsor, South Carolina; and Mialoquo, Tennessee. New Ebenezer had the next highest (9%) followed by Savano, South Carolina and Fort Mount Pleasant, Georgia. Muskets were military issue, but all military units did not have muskets. The sites in our sample with known British military components include Frederica, Mount Pleasant, Fort Moore, Ackia, and New Ebenezer. Of these only Ackia had no musket flints.

Figure 6.105 Arms artifacts, French gunflints (blade and spall types), (a.-d., f. French blade types, LN201.312.001, LN201.375.004, LN201.205.001, LN201.279.001, and LN201.163.003; e. French spall type, LN201.142.020).

The musket-sized gunflint grouping from Fort Argyle includes 5 English, 1 French and 1 of unknown origin. This group contains 1 blade and 6 spall types. One of these specimens was burned. This group ranges in length from 25 to 33.2 mm, in width from 34.5 to 38.4 mm, in thickness from 8.5 to 11.5 mm, and from 898.3 to 1181.9 mm² average surface area.

Carbines, fowlers, or civilian muskets have gunflints greater than 28 mm and less than 34 mm wide. In Elliott's (1992) gunflint analysis this class of weapons comprised 34 percent of the overall southeastern sample. Frederica also had the highest frequency of carbine flints with 45 percent. The Savannah River sites were below average with sites near Augusta at 30 percent, New Ebenezer at 24 percent and Mount Pleasant at 17 percent.

The carbine-sized gunflint group sample from Fort Argyle includes 23 English, 3 French, and 3 of unknown origin. This group contains 3 blade, 2 spall/blade and 24 spall types. Four were burned. Carbine-sized gunflints range in length from 19.1 to 36 mm, in width from 28.6 to 33.3 mm, in thickness from 6.5 to 11.3 mm, and from 546.5 to 1081.6 mm² average surface area.

Figure 6.106 Arms artifacts, English spall-type gunflints (a. LN201.168.004, b. LN201.281.001, c. LN201.411.004, d. LN201.190.001, e. LN201.151.007, f. LN201199.003, g. LN201.187.003, h. LN201.191.002, i. LN201.447.001, j. LN201.456.004, k. LN201.375.0).

Figure 6.107 Arms artifacts, gunflints, burned (a. LN201.103.001, b. LN201.361.003, c. LN201.195.007, d. LN201.456.003, f. LN201.375.003, g. LN201.169.014).

Tradeguns are represented by gunflints 28 mm or less wide. In Elliott's (1992) gunflint analysis, these weapons comprised 52 percent of the overall southeastern assemblage. Several aboriginal sites contained more than 80 percent tradegun flints. Frederica had the lowest frequency of tradegun flints (15%), while the Savannah River sites had substantial amounts: Mount Pleasant (68%), Ft. Moore, South Carolina (63%), New Ebenezer and New Windsor, South Carolina (61%), and Native American Savano Town, South Carolina (47%). Savano Town percentage at 47 percent is low compared with other Native American towns. Only Savano Town and Frederica are below average, and they represent two very different sites in terms of ethnic composition, site function, and geography. An alternate interpretation is that the Savano Town gunflints are actually not associated with a Native American group.

The tradegun/carbine group includes only two English spall type flints. This small sample is an artifact of the flaw in Hamilton and Emery's division between weapon groups, whereas flints measuring 28.0 mm in width fell in two categories—tradeguns and carbines.

The tradegun group from Fort Argyle includes 31 English, 4 French and 2 of unknown origin. This group contains 1 blade, 1 spall/blade and 35 spall types. Three of these specimens were burned. This group ranges in length from 15.7 to 27.2 mm, in width from 20.2 to 27.8 mm, in thickness from 5.5 to 10.8 mm. and from 340.9 to 753.4 mm² average surface area.

Pistol flints were rare on all of the sites that were examined in Elliott's (1992) gunflint analysis comprising less than three percent of the gunflints. Frederica, New Ebenezer and Oakfuskenena, Georgia; Savano Town, South Carolina; Old Mobile, Alabama; and Ackia, Mississippi each had one pistol flint, and Mialoquo, Tennessee and New Windsor, South Carolina each had two. Mount Pleasant and Frederica, Georgia; and Fort Moore and Daniels Island, South Carolina; yielded no pistol flints. From this one can infer that pistols also were relatively rare in the Southeast during the eighteenth century.

The pistol group in the Fort Argyle sample includes 5 English, 5 French, 1 possibly local and 4 of unknown origin. This group contains 4 blade and 11 spall types. Two are burned. The pistol group averages 17.3 mm in length, 17.5 mm in width, 8.21 mm in thickness and an average surface area of 305.3 mm². This group ranges in length from 13.6 to 24 mm, in width from 13 to 19.8 mm, in thickness from 5.3 to 21.2 mm. and from 195.1 to 460.2 mm² average surface area.

Based on its gunflint assemblage (n=90) the Fort Argyle arsenal included 38 tradeguns, 29 carbines or fowlers, 15 pistols or small tradeguns, 7 muskets and 1 tradegun/carbine. By comparison the 34 gunflints from the Fort Mount Pleasant Georgia Ranger fort contained 23 tradeguns, 6 carbines, 4 tradegun/carbines, 1 musket and no pistols. An analyzed sample of 133 gunflints from Frederica, Georgia reflects a different arsenal composition, represented by 59 carbines, 45 muskets, 27 tradeguns, 1 tradegun/carbine and 1 pistol (Elliott 1992).

The interpreted Fort Argyle gunflint data was compared with flints from five other sites in colonial Georgia (Table 6.13). These are Fort Frederica, Ebenezer, Fort St. Andrews, and Georgia Ranger forts Mt. Pleasant, and Mt. Venture at Sansavilla Bluff. As noted earlier, Fort Argyle was dominated by Tradeguns (42.2%), followed by Carbines (32.2%). In contrast, Frederica is dominated by Carbines (45.4%), followed by Muskets (33.8%). Fort Mt. Pleasant was dominated by Tradeguns (67.6%), followed by Carbines (55.6%). Fort Mt. Venture was dominated by Carbines (63.2%), followed by Tradeguns (21.1%). Fort St. Andrews was dominated by Carbines (55.6%), followed by Tradeguns (25.0%). Ebenezer was dominated by Tradeguns (57.6%), followed by Carbines (24.2%).

The Fort Argyle gunflint analysis reveals several interesting aspects of gunflint preference or availability by weapon category. In order of abundance tradeguns dominate the assemblage followed by carbines, pistols, and muskets. The prevalence of tradeguns over other weapon types is intriguing, given that the Fort Argyle rangers were not licensed to trade with the Native Americans. If the rangers were outfitted with poor quality tradeguns, then their performance in battle would likely have been compromised.

Table 6.13 Gunflints and Arsenals from Six Sites in Colonial Georgia.

Site	Pistol		Tradegun		Tradegun/Carbine		Carbine		Musket		TOTAL
	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count	%	Count
Frederica	1	0.8	25	19.2	1	0.8	59	45.4	44	33.8	130
Ft. Argyle	15	16.7	38	42.2	1	1.1	29	32.2	7	7.8	90
Ft. Mt. Pleasant	0	0.0	23	67.6	4	11.8	20	55.6	1	2.9	48
Ft. St. Andrews	0	0.0	9	25.0	1	2.8	20	55.6	6	16.7	36
Ebenezer	1	3.0	19	57.6	2	6.1	8	24.2	3	9.1	33
Ft. Mt. Venture/Sansavilla	0	0.0	4	21.1	3	15.8	12	63.2	0	0.0	19
TOTAL	17	4.8	118	33.1	12	3.4	148	41.6	61	17.1	356
(Source: Elliott 2018)											

The musket, carbine, and tradegun gunflint groups are dominated by English spall type flints. However, pistol flints are nearly equally split between English, French and other sources. The pistol flint group is dominated by spall types over blade types but the ratio of blade to spall is higher than in other weapon categories (Blades- 40% versus Spalls 60%). The preference for higher quality French flints for pistols may indicate the personal choice of each ranger.

Elliott's (1992, 2018a) study of gunflints from a series of eighteenth-century forts and settlements in southeastern North America revealed that 28 percent of the gunflint sample consisted of French gunflints. At the French town of Old Mobile gunflints were 100 percent French chert, as might be expected with a coastal town populated by the French citizens and soldiers. The highest frequency of French flints at a non-French ethnic site was observed at Frederica (43%), while four sites, Ackia, Mississippi, New Windsor and Savano Town, South Carolina produced no French flints. The gunflint assemblages at New Ebenezer and Daniels Island, South Carolina each had 27% French flints, Fort Moore, South Carolina had 13%, and Fort Mount Pleasant, Georgia had 9%. The Upper Creek town of Oakfuskenena, Georgia had 19% French flints and the Upper Cherokee town of Mialoquo, Tennessee had 11%.

Most scholars, gun enthusiasts, and eighteenth-century re-enactors agree that French blade-style flints were superior to the English spall-type flints. Hamilton and Emery (1988) demonstrated the superior firing capability when using French versus English flints. A preference for French flints also is documented in contemporary accounts by military men of the eighteenth century. Throughout most of the eighteenth century the French were at odds militarily with the British and this served to restrict the availability of French gunflints in the British colonies.

Edged Weapons

Archaeologists recovered one cast brass sword guard fragment during the 2018/2019 metal detector survey. Only a small portion of the decorative design remains, but it appears to be a raised-relief, geometric double floral or star-burst motif, as shown in a previous figure. It measures 34.25 mm maximum dimension and it weighs 9 g. It served as a cross-guard, perpendicular to the blade, to protect the hand from injury during a sword fight. This small fragment attests to the presence of edged weaponry at Fort Argyle. The fragment is too small to determine exactly what size weapon was attached. Non-commissioned British officers in the eighteenth century carried small swords or "hangers" as part of their

uniform. The lowest ranking enlisted men did not carry swords. The arms accoutrements possessed by the rangers on the frontier may have differed from the regular British military.

Neumann (1991: 63-68, Figures 6.S, 7.S, 8.S and 9.S) illustrates several examples of English hangers that are similar in form to the small fragment recovered from Fort Argyle. Probably the closest fit to the Fort Argyle specimen is Figure 6.S, which Neumann brackets between ca. 1690-1710 (Figure 6.108). It is described as, "References to one of the common British infantry hangers of this period speak of a brass guard, simple cutting edge, and an antler grip. A number of this basic pattern are known. The decorated knuckle bow divides into two tails which, in turn, support an oval outboard shell guard bearing raised cherub and floral designs. Its slightly curving single-edged blade has no fuller. The brass knuckle bow and guard were cast as a single piece (without an inboard shell)." Neumann's example shown in Figure 130 measured 29.25 inches in length and its blade measured 24 5/8 inches by 1 1/8 inches, and it weighed 1.2 pounds. While the Fort Argyle hanger is not an identical match with Neumann's example because the Fort Argyle example is not circular in outline, its floral design elements are extremely similar. We conclude that the small brass fragment from Fort Argyle is a portion of an English hanger of a style manufactured in the late seventeenth to early eighteenth centuries. This type of weapon was part of the uniform of a non-commissioned officer in the British infantry and this version was probably owned by one of the non-commissioned South Carolina or Georgia rangers garrisoned at Fort Argyle.

Figure 6.108. Close-up of Sword Guard on a Circa 1690-1710 English Hanger Showing Raised Cherub and Floral Motif (Neumann 1991:63, Figure 6.S).

6.5.7 Tobacco Group

Tobacco smoking was a popular pastime in colonial Georgia and clay smoking pipes were a preferred vehicle for ingesting nicotine. Most imported tobacco pipes in Georgia were made in England. The firm of Morel and Telfair of Savannah advertised for sale among their imports in June 1763 "hunters and long pipes" and in May 1765, the firm advertised "short and long pipes" (*The Georgia Gazette* June 16, 1763:4; May 2, 1765:5). We suspect that the Rangers probably preferred the hunter/short varieties of tobacco pipes.

Kaolin or ball clay tobacco smoking pipe fragments are the sole artifact type representing the Tobacco Group at Fort Argyle. Elliott (1997:154) noted that 615 tobacco pipe parts have been excavated from the site. Braley et al. (1985:65-66) reported 284 tobacco pipe fragments. He identified two pipes marked, "TD" and a third marked "IW". Using measurements of the bore diameters of 188 pipe stems, Braley derived a mean tobacco pipe date of 1761.59. Martin and her colleagues (1986:15) recovered five pipe stems from their excavations on the northern part of 9BN28. While their sample was too small for tobacco pipe date calculations, they noted that all five examples had a bore diameter of 5/64 inch. Elliott (1997:154-156) used a sample of 205 pipe stems excavated from the site to obtain a tobacco pipe stem date of 1748.39. Elliott also reported finding another "TD" pipe from the 1996 excavations.

LG²ES recovered 569 clay tobacco pipe fragments from its excavations (Figure 6.109). Archaeologists measured 235 pipestem bore diameters from the LG²ES excavations and calculated a mean pipestem date, using Heighton and Deagan's pipestem date formula (Heighton and Deagan 1972:220-229). The 235 specimens yielded an average bore diameter of 4.821 mm (0.189 inch). Heighton and Deagan's two-part formula is expressed as the following equation: $X = -\log Y + 1.04435/0.05234$, where Y is the mean borehole diameter, followed by inserting the X value into this equation: $\text{date} = 1600 + 22 * X$. The Fort Argyle pipestems were calculated for $X = -\log (4.821) + 1.04435/0.05234$, which yielded an X value of 6.787. These calculations resulted in a sitewide tobacco pipestem date of 1749.314. The LG²ES pipestem data also was calculated using Binford's formula, which yielded a date of 1747.399. These two pipestem date calculations differ by less than two years. The date of 1749.314 from the Heighton and Deagan formula is quite close to the historically determined occupation median date (calculated as $(1767-1733)/2 + 1733$), or 1750.

Braley et al. (1985: Table 5) calculated a tobacco pipestem date of 1761.59 based on a sample of 188 pipestems and using the Binford formula. Braley's date is slightly more than a year and a half later than the historical median date. These results support McMillan's conclusion that the Heighton and Deagan formula is more accurate than the Binford formula and the Fort Argyle data strongly supports the usefulness of the Heighton and Deagan formula as applied to colonial Georgia archaeological sites (Heighton and Deagan 1972; McMillan 2016:18-42).

One hundred pipestems were recovered from 22 features in the LG²ES excavations. These features were located in blocks T, U, V, W, X, Y, Z, AA, AB, AD and AF. All measured examples had a bore diameter of 5/64 inch. Maker's marks observed in the LG²ES tobacco pipe assemblage included one "RW" from the plow zone of Block Y. Another pipestem was found in the plow zone of Block U, which bore the barely discernable raised letters of either "RG", "RB", "PG", or "PB" on its stem.

Figure 6.109 Tobacco artifacts, kaolin pipe bowls and stems (a. and b. Pipe bowls, LN201.390.021 and LN201.392.033; c. Pipe stem with “RW” on foot, LN201.160.021; d. Pipe bowl with initials on stem, LN201.113.004).

6.5.8 Activities Group

Braley et al. (1985:66) reported finding only two artifacts in the activities group from his 1985 excavations. These were two iron hoes. One of these came from the riverbank and the other was recovered from his underwater reconnaissance of the Ogeechee Riverbed. Elliott (1997:165) estimates that 104 activities group artifacts were previously excavated from Fort Argyle. Elliott (1997:166) noted that the most common type of activity group artifacts at Fort Argyle was non-ferrous metal scrap, including lead, brass and pewter. Examples of activities artifacts, such as a thimble, flaked glass tool, lead fishing weight and other items are displayed in Figure 6.110.

Horse Tack

Many, if not most, of Fort Argyle's rangers were mounted on horseback. William Stephens (1966: described the Georgia Ranger troop at Fort Mount Pleasant in 1742 as “all well mounted”, and the same was likely true for the rangers posted at Fort Argyle. Horses and their various accoutrements were expected to be reflected in the archaeological record. The only definite artifact that fell into this category was a single fragment of an eighteenth-century brass spur. This poor representation of horse tack items at Fort Argyle stands in contrast to numerous objects recovered from Fort Mount Pleasant, which included two iron snaffle bits, an iron saddle tree, and two iron stirrups, and a brass rosette, possibly from a bridle (Elliott In Press). A portion of the iron and brass buckles that were recovered from Fort Argyle may represent horse tack.

Figure 6.110 Activities artifacts (a. Brass thimble, LN201.181.002; b. Olive green bottle glass flaked tool, LN201.392.016; c. Lead fishing weight, LN201.140.015; d. Brass rivet, LN201.369.001; e. Brass spur, LN201.362.001; f. Brass/copper brad/stud for leather, LN201.101.001

Boat Tack

Historical documents attest to the existence of a marine vessel that carried Fort Argyle's Rangers up and down the Ogeechee River. This vessel was constructed of wood, but it likely possessed iron or brass hardware. These items may have included oar locks, cleats and copper nails or spikes. No artifacts were identified in LG²ES's artifact inventory that confirm the presence of boats, or marine-related paraphernalia at Fort Argyle. Similarly, archaeological investigations at Fort Mount Pleasant, which was another Georgia Ranger fort on the Savannah River that also should have a marine component, failed to yield any boat hardware.

Flaked Glass Tools

Elliott (1991) previously documented numerous chipped glass tools made from olive-green spirit bottle glass and clear goblet stemware at the Fort Mount Pleasant Georgia Ranger fort and Yuchi Indian village. Elliott and his colleagues also have documented many examples of bottle glass tools at eighteenth and early nineteenth century Lower Creek and Yuchi Indian settlements on the middle Chattahoochee River (Elliott 1999). Elliott (1997) noted the presence of five bottle glass tools and related debitage with olive-green bottle glass tools found in Fort Argyle in previously excavated blocks G, J, K, N and S and glass flakes found in Excavation Blocks C, E, G, I, J, N and S. The LG²ES laboratory team identified only two bottle glass tools. One from F314 in Block AA was made from olive green bottle glass and the other from the plow zone in Block W was made from aqua bottle glass.

6.5.9 Aboriginal Ceramics

LG²ES recovered a total of 366 aboriginal ceramics (1298.5 grams) at Fort Argyle. Most of the ceramics were highly fragmented and could only be classified by temper and sometimes indeterminate surface treatments. The Colonial component disturbed much of the Prehistoric sites there and plowing scattered the artifacts further. Below is a discussion of datable ceramics and their contexts.

Terminal Archaic Pottery

The Ogeechee River watershed and other parts of Georgia and South Carolina are home to the oldest ceramic tradition in North America—Stallings fiber tempered wares. LG²ES recovered 11 Stallings Plain fiber tempered sherds from Fort Argyle (Elliott and Sassaman 1995). Three sherds were from F207. Two sherds were recovered from F401 between 44 and 109 cmbd. One sherd came from Level 3 of F299. The others were from the plow zone in Blocks Z (n=2), AB (n=1) and AD (n=3). While scant in their density and relatively small in size, their widespread distribution across the site indicates that possibly more than one family used and disposed of these early fiber tempered wares.

Woodland Pottery

Dunlap/Refuge/Deptford Pottery

Some of the key characteristics of the Woodland period include the proliferation in pottery styles and use. The Early/Middle Woodland Dunlap/Refuge/Deptford pottery was made by coiling and without any plant fibers. One Dunlap Fabric Marked sherds was recovered from the plow zone of Block AB. One Refuge Simple Stamp was recovered in Test Unit 214 in Block AD. Typical surface treatments in Refuge classifications consist of Incised, Punctated, Simple Stamped, Plain and Dentate Stamped (Waring 1968; Caldwell 1939; DePratter 1979, 1991; Guerrero and Thomas 2008). LG²ES recovered 13 Deptford sherds from Fort Argyle. These included nine Deptford Cordmarked and five Deptford Check Stamped sherds. Two Deptford sherds were from F328 in Block AB. The others were from the plow zone in Blocks U (n=2), W (n=1), Y (n=2), Z (n=1), and AB (n=5).

Wilmington

Late Woodland Wilmington Cord Marked pottery has its entire exterior surfaces decorated by a cord-wrapped paddle with the cordage impressions generally running parallel to each other and vertical to the vessel. Its paste is composed of crushed sherds or more commonly low-fired clay particles and vessels are usually thick and lumpy (DePratter 1991:177-179). Fabric marking, Brushing occurs, in addition to Cord marking and of course, the majority type: Wilmington Plain. LG²ES recovered four Wilmington sherds (2 Cord Marked and 2 Plain) from Fort Argyle, one of them being a straight rim. All were located from Level 1 in Blocks Z and AA. A concentration in Block Z indicates a localized short-term habitation area.

Mississippian Pottery

Savannah/St. Catherines

The cultural characteristics that archaeologists refer to as Mississippian developed in the central Mississippi River Valley during the late first millennium A.D. and spread primarily east, southeast, and south. A change in the ceramic assemblage is seen in the archaeological record of the northern Georgia

Coast in the Middle Mississippian Period Savannah sherds with the inclusions in the paste of cord-marked vessels changed from sherd/clay to coarse sand and grit, with cord-marked, burnished plain, and plain surface finished varieties. St. Catherines ceramics include crushed sherds or low fired lumps of clay in Plain, Burnished Plain, Cord Marked and Net Marked. The combined Savannah and St. Catherines (DePratter 1979, in Thomas 2008, Guerrero and Thomas 2008) includes sand and/or grit tempered Savannah Cord Marked, Burnished Plain and Plain. LG²ES recovered: 2 Savannah Fine Cord Marked, 1 Savannah Cord Marked, 1 St. Catherines Plain, 2 Savannah/St. Catherines Fine Cord Marked Nx 2 Savannah or St. Catherines Cord Marked sherds from Fort Argyle. Most of these sherds came from the plow zone (Level 1), although examples were recovered from four features (F176C, 314, 328 and 390).

Lamar/Irene

Another shift in ceramic style is used as the marker for the Late Mississippian subperiod along the northern Georgia Coast (Caldwell and McCann 1941). Irene pottery is tempered with grit and sometimes gravel in a fine sand matrix. Plain, incised, burnishing and complicated stamps characterize decorations on Coastal Irene ceramics. Many rims are folded and decorated with hollow reed and other punctations. The most common motif recognized in Georgia and South Carolina is the filfot cross. Irene pottery is replaced by Altamaha/San Marcos sometime in the early Mission and Colonial periods. LG²ES did not recover any obvious Lamar/Irene pottery from Fort Argyle; however, the assemblage does contain a number of grit-tempered sherds (N=97) that could be part of the Irene tradition, but they are too small or have some other characteristic that does not fit traditional Irene Plain. One folded rim with an applied node could be called either Irene or Altamaha (Deagan and Thomas 2009).

Historic Aboriginal Pottery

Historical documents attest to the repeated presence of hundreds of Creek Indians at Fort Argyle. Their stay at the fort left surprisingly little archaeological evidence. A scant deposit of Creek ceramics was identified in the Fort Argyle artifact assemblage.

Chattahoochee Brushed was widely produced by the historic Upper and Lower Creek tribes in the eighteenth century, as well as the Yuchi. LG²ES recovered five Chattahoochee Brushed sherds from Fort Argyle. The Chattahoochee Brushed sherds came from the plow zone in Block Y and may represent sherds from one vessel.

LG²ES recovered five sherds identified as Mission Red from Fort Argyle. Mission Red is a Florida pottery type not widely recognized in coastal Georgia and it is unlikely that any Mission Red pots from Florida made their way to Fort Argyle during its period of occupation, as the Rangers were not on friendly terms with the Spanish-allied groups.

Kasita Red Filmed pottery type was produced as a minority ware by Upper and Lower Creek tribes in present-day Alabama and Georgia. Tribal representatives of the Creek Confederacy from both of these areas (Upper Creek and Lower Creek) passed through Fort Argyle on their way to treaty talks in Savannah in the 1730s. Thirty-seven Kasita Red Filmed pottery sherds were identified in the Fort Argyle pottery assemblage. This ware was distributed across eight excavation blocks. It was best represented in Block U, which yielded 15 sherds, followed by Block AB, which had seven sherds, and Block AD, which had

four sherds. Fewer sherds were located in Blocks T, V, Y, Z and AA. Kasita Red Filmed sherds were recovered from 10 cultural features, including Features 176C, 207, 214, 291, 304, 314, 327, 328, 363 and 388.

6.5.10 Aboriginal Stone Tools and Debris

One Madison small triangular chipped stone PPK made from coastal plain chert was recovered from previous excavations at Fort Argyle (Elliott 1997). It was from Excavation Block Q on the south end of Fort Argyle. The LG²ES team recovered no historic aboriginal chipped stone weapons associated with the Creek or Yuchi tribes from its excavations.

While the chipped stone tools recovered by the LG²ES team included several projectile points/knives (PPKs), these all predate the British colonial period by several millennium. LG²ES recovered three Late Archaic stemmed PPKs from Fort Argyle (Elliott and Sassaman 1995). These are illustrated in Figure 6.111. Single examples were recovered from F390 in Block AG and in the plow zone in blocks W and Z. These tools may be associated with the same group who used and discarded Stallings Plain pottery at the site.

A total of 110 Aboriginal Lithics of various kinds was recovered from LG²ES excavations at Fort Argyle (Table 6.14). Four PPK or fragments were collected, including three Late Archaic types. A Savannah River Point (with a broken tip) was found within F390 in Block AG. The two other Late Archaic PPKs were stemmed examples, but were too fragmented for a specific type identification. As with other Prehistoric artifacts from this site, it was out of context in a Colonial period wall trench feature.

Flakes, debitage and biface fragments were relatively evenly distributed across the excavation blocks, similar to the general pattern of the ceramics. One small soapstone fragment, consistent with the sparse Late/Terminal Archaic component (marked by Stallings Plain pottery) was found in Block AF.

Block AB and Block Z (N=22 and N=15 respectfully) produced the largest numbers of lithic artifacts. However, the small sample size of the lithic assemblage may not be statistically significant as these two blocks covered a substantial area of the excavations on the site.

Table 6.14 Aboriginal Lithics Recovered from Excavations

Artifact Description	Count
Biface	11
Biface Fragment	26
Debitage	6
Flake	16
Flake Fragment	8
Savannah River PPK	4
Stemmed Late Archaic PPKs	2
Primary Flake	3
Scraper	1

Artifact Description	Count
Secondary flake	4
Shatter	1
Soapstone, worked	1
Tertiary Flake	16
Thinning Flake	1
Uniface	1
Utilized Flake	9

Figure 6.111 Native American lithics (a. Non diagnostic, distal fragment reworked into complete PPK, LN201.431.001, b., c., and d. Late Archaic stemmed point, LN201.169.010, LN201.377.003, LN201.128.003).

7.0 INTERPRETATIONS

In past excavations, SAS excavated 57 m², the LAMAR Institute excavated 82 m², and CAS excavated just under 3 m². This represents a combined total of approximately 139 m² excavated at Fort Argyle prior to the LG²ES Phase III fieldwork. LG²ES excavated approximately 270 m² of the site. (An additional 3 m² overlapped with previous excavations by SAS and the LAMAR Institute). The LG²ES work brings the combined excavation to approximately 402 m² as of March 2019. The reader is referred to Appendix H for a composite plan map of features and excavation areas from 1985-2019.

The SAS and LAMAR excavations at Fort Argyle reveal an artifact density of approximately 52 historic artifacts per m². Interestingly, the artifact density observed by CAS on the northern part of the site was twice that—104 artifacts per m². Many of the artifacts found by CAS were associated with a later historic component, the home of Russell C. Jacobs and his family, while the overwhelming majority found by SAS and LAMAR Institute date to the colonial period. The LG²ES excavations yielded a historic artifact density of only 20.8 artifacts per m², or less than half that of the combined SAS and LAMAR artifact yield. However, it should be noted that most of the plow zone soils in the LG²ES blocks were screened through one-half inch mesh, rather than the one-quarter inch mesh used by previous excavators. LG²ES recovered approximately 5,763 artifacts from 9BN28 and 5,626 of these were located in hand-excavated block units.

These excavations that have been undertaken beginning in 1985 represent less than 25% of the core of the Fort Argyle sites. The outlying areas, beyond the fortifications, have barely been sampled for their archaeological content. The present study was focused on addressing the immediate threat from stream erosion along the Ogeechee River. While we also sampled areas away from the riverbank, we left so many intriguing areas unexplored. This is clearly evident from a cursory glimpse of our GIS site plan. The central core of the fort site has received very little attention, as the archaeologists traced the outlines of the three different forts at Fort Argyle. It seemed that the more we dug, the more questions we unearthed. As the senior author, I can definitively say that I now understand the architectural plans of Fort Argyle less than I did 23 years ago! Yet, we have learned a lot from our recent explorations. We know for certain that we were not so smart back then and that Fort Argyle is a far more complicated story than the archaeologists told in 1985 or 1997. Archaeologists learn on the job, and our job seems to never be done. Our Phase III Data Recovery excavation project at Fort Argyle is really just a beginning in understanding this important colonial fort. These admissions being said, we now offer our interpretations of Fort Argyle, as it exists in 2019.

7.1 Construction Features of Other Trustee-era Forts in Georgia

Fort Frederica's outer works were being, "palisaded with Cedar Posts to prevent our Enemies from turning up the green Sod. Upon the bastions, platforms of two-inch plank were laid for the cannon". Workmen built a powder magazine under one of the bastions of the fort. It was made of heavy timber covered with several feet of earth. Oglethorpe was saluted with fifteen guns from the fort. In November 1739 Oglethorpe advised the Trustees, 'I am fortifying the Town of Frederica. It is half a Hexagon with two Bastions, and two half Bastions and Towers, after Monsieur Vauban's method, upon the point of each Bastion. The Walls are of earth faced with Timber, 10-foot-high in the lowest place, and in the highest 13, and the Timbers from eight inches to twelve inches thick. There is a wet Ditch 10-foot-wide, and so

laid out that if we had an allowance for it, I can by widening the Ditch double the thickness of the Wall and make a covered way' (Jones 1878:61-62, 64, 68, 71-72). Major portions of Fort Frederica's outer fort walls, which surrounded the colonial town, remain intact today.

Fort St. Simons was a major British fortification on the southern tip of St. Simons Island. Figure 7.1 shows a portion of the building plan for Fort St. Simons, which was drafted by John Thomas in 1740. Thomas's plan clearly follows that of the French military engineer Vauban. The fort was abandoned by the British and destroyed by the invading Spanish forces who attacked Georgia in July 1742. The archaeological remains of Fort St. Simons have not been located. This part of the Village of St. Simons Island is experiencing active development, so the prospects for locating its archaeological remains are decreasing daily (Elliott and Burns 2007).

Figure 7.1 Portion of John Thomas' Plan of Fort St. Simons (Thomas 1740).

Delegal's Fort was located at the sea-point of St. Simons Island on Jekyll Sound. It was defended by "13 pieces of cannon" (Jones 1878:64). No plan drawings of Delegal's fort are known and any archaeological remains of Delegal's Fort remains to be discovered. The outlook for archaeological success appears grim due to modern development on St. Simons Island. One possible vestige of the fort is a tabby building that was reconnoitered only. It has since been repurposed as part of a larger residential development project (Figure 7.2) (Elliott 2009). It should be noted that Fort Argyle is located too far upstream on the Ogeechee River to expect any tabby architecture, since oyster shells are required for its construction and the hauling of oyster shells this distance upstream would have been an onerous task for the rangers. Ebenezer, which is located on the Savannah River at a similar distance upstream from the salt marshes, where oyster beds are found, also lacks any tabby structures.

Figure 7.2 Tabby Building Possibly Associated with Delegal's Fort on St. Simons Island (Elliott 2009).

Fort St. Andrews was a major fort located on the west side of Cumberland Island. It was garrisoned by Regular British Army troops. C.C. Jones repeated an early description of Fort St. Andrews with, "its walls were of wood, filled in with earth. Round about were a ditch and a palisade" (Jones 1878:61). Archaeological discovery of Fort St. Andrews in 2006 by archaeologist Carolyn Rock was soon followed by several seasons of archaeological fieldwork by the National Park Service, Southeast Archaeological Center (Rock 2006; Elliott 2006; Steve Kidd personal communication July 25, 2008; Meredith Hardy personal communication August 12, 2019). Like Fort Argyle, no contemporary plan maps exist of Fort St. Andrews. Archaeological erosion-control salvage investigations at Fort St. Andrews by the National Park Service since 2006 have revealed important aspects of this Georgia Trustee period fort (Rock 2006; Elliott 2006; Hardy in press). One impressive discovery was a large, well-preserved fort ditch at the edge of the bluff that contained a wide variety of mid-eighteenth-century artifacts (Figure 7.3). Fort St. Andrew is fast eroding off the high bluff into St. Andrews Sound. Elliott's gunflint study included a large surface collection made by a local resident from the shoreline below Fort St. Andrews (Elliott 2018a). Hardy's summary report on the excavations at Fort St. Andrews, anticipated to be released in 2020, should provide excellent comparative date for additional interpretation of Fort Argyle.

The Kings Surveyor William DeBrahm drafted a series of plans for forts in the southern colonies around 1756-1757. One example in Georgia was in the Ebenezer colony, where DeBrahm first settled in Georgia

Figure 7.3 Outer Ditch at Fort St. Andrews, Cumberland Island, Georgia (Courtesy of Daniel Elliott 2009).

by 1752. A close-up view of his plan of the fortifications within Ebenezer is shown in Figure 7.4 (DeVorse 1971). This fortification has been mapped using GPR as well as a total station laser transit, which tentatively confirm the implementation of DeBrahm's plan and its location within the town (Elliott 2003). While this fort was built to defend Ebenezer from French and Indian attack it was never assaulted and by 1779, when the town was invaded by British troops, this fort was long gone. It is interesting to note that DeBrahm incorporated many features of the Vauban fort design, but he also modified it to fit the existing landscape and terrain features.

7.2 Speculative Visions of Fort Argyle

Larry Ivers (1974) presented his conjecture of how Fort Argyle may have appeared during the period from 1733-1747. This image is reproduced in Figure 7.5. His is a "birds-eye" perspective view from the northeast facing west-southwest. It shows a rectangular log stockade enclosure with slightly projecting corner bastions on the northeast and northwest sides. Within the fort are several rows of single-story log buildings, which are oriented with an east-west long axis. An animal pen for horses is located within the parade ground. Two entrances to the fort are shown, one along the north-central wall, which crosses a dry moat, and another along the northern end of the east wall, which exits to level ground. Another closely arranged row of buildings is shown beyond the fort wall, a short distance to the south. These likely represent civilian dwellings. Ivers shows no central blockhouse, such as that drawn by William DeBrahm for forts Barrington and George. The eroding banks of the Ogeechee River are shown in the foreground.

Figure 7.4 Close-up View of DeBrahm's Plan for a Fortification within the Town of Ebenezer, ca. 1757 (The Kings Collection, The British Library; DeVorse 1971).

Figure 7.5 Larry Ivers' Conjectural View of Fort Argyle, ca. 1734-1747 (Ivers 1974).

Figure 7.6 shows artist Martin Pate's different interpretation of Fort Argyle, as it might have appeared in the mid-eighteenth century (Pate 2005; Maggioni 2012). His perspective from a ground-based position on the Ogeechee River bluff depicts the fort facing southwest. His artwork illustrates Rangers trading with lightly clad male Native Americans in the foreground. Pate's image shows a rectangular, vertical log-palisaded stockade with projecting corner bastions and a two-story central blockhouse with two large

cannon gun ports and a row of musket ports on its north and east sides. The area surrounding the fort is shown as cleared land and no other buildings are indicated outside of the fort. This artwork was commissioned by the National Park Service and was stimulated by the 1997 report by the LAMAR Institute (Elliott 1997). Consultation with Elliott was negligible during the artist's preparation and research for the execution of the painting. Current observation reveals several historical errors in its interpretation (Kane and Keeton 2005; Jameson 2005). Nevertheless, Pate's illustration offers a gestalt of the Fort Argyle environment.

Figure 7.6 Interpretive Painting of Fort Argyle by Martin Pate (Pate 2005; Maggioni 2012).

7.3 Plan of Three Fort Argyles

No contemporary plan drawings of Fort Argyle have been located to date. Contemporary details of the construction and architecture of Fort Argyle are remarkably sparse and quite rare. The absence of any illustrations or detailed descriptions of the fort heightens the importance of archaeology in our modern understanding of the fort and how it may have appeared at various times during its existence. Erosion from the Ogeechee River and from decades of agricultural cultivation has claimed a substantial portion of these architectural plans. The senior author [D. Elliott] offered two hypothetical fort plans for Fort Argyle based on the excavation data as of 1996. The present LG²ES excavations have proven his earlier interpretations to be inaccurate. The archaeological exploration of the fort site also left many areas of the site unexplored. Despite these odds, the archaeological record reveals three periods of fort construction. We have designated these three forts, Forts A, B and C (Figure 7.7) Should any future archaeologists venture back to Fort Argyle to explore its remaining resources, The senior author offer his apologies in advance for any errors in our 2019 architectural interpretation of the fort.

Figure 7.7 Plan of Fort A, B, and C, Fort Argyle

Figure 7.8 Modern aerial with outline of Forts A, B, and C.

7.3.1 Fort Argyle A

Fort Argyle A (Fort A) represents the initial construction phase of Fort Argyle. This fort was built at 9BN28 by the South Carolina Rangers in late 1733. The fort construction episode was first discovered by the LAMAR Institute's team in 1996 and further explored by the LG²ES team. Fort Argyle A is defined by southern, eastern and northwestern walls. Fort A represents the smallest configuration of Fort Argyle. The outline of Fort A was possibly triangular (or sub-rectangular).

Fort A's south wall is defined by features in Excavation Blocks J, V and AA. This early fort is expressed in F173, F176(A-C) and F314. F173 has a TPQ of 1720; F176 has a TPQ of 1733 and F314 has a TPQ of 1733. These dates are consistent with the 1733-1738 occupation by the South Carolina Rangers.

Fort A's east wall is defined in Excavation Blocks G, J, X and Y. It is expressed in F157, F158, F180, F214, F221 and F287. F157 has a TPQ of 1720 (F157a has a TPQ of 1762); F180 has a TPQ of 1733; F214 has a TPQ of 1670; F221 has a TPQ of 1742 (based on English soft paste porcelain) and F287 has a TPQ of 1733. These dates from 1720 to 1742 are consistent with the occupation by the South Carolina Rangers and the early years of the Georgia Rangers. Its northwest wall is only partially defined by F388 in Excavation Block AA. That trench joins with the western end of the south wall of Fort A to form an acute angle. F388 has a TPQ of 1733, which is consistent with the occupation by the South Carolina Rangers.

When General Oglethorpe visited Fort Argyle in early 1734, one writer who accompanied him described it as "being well flanked and having several pieces of Cannon mounted" (Harris 1841:80-81; Wright 1867:74-75; *South Carolina Gazette*, February 23, 1734:1; *The Pennsylvania Gazette*, March 21, 1734). John Wesley, who visited Fort Argyle in 1737, gave a more mournful perspective, describing it as, "a Small Squar wooden building, musket proof, with 4 little cannon... the Walls of the Fort are partly fallen already". Both of these descriptions refer to the Fort Argyle that was built and used by the South Carolina Rangers.

Braley et al. (1985) proposed that the cluster of posts his team uncovered within Excavation Block E represented the foundation supports for a blockhouse. Elliott (1997:188, 190) posited that Braley's proposed blockhouse was associated with Fort A. Elliott further speculated, based on findings from the 1995/1996 work, that Fort A was a square structure, with projecting corner bastions and measuring approximately 19.5 m by 19.5 m on each curtain wall. However, our current knowledge of Fort A suggests that it was not a square construction and the post cluster observed in Block E is likely outside the walls of Fort A. If these posts, which Elliott designated as Building 3, do represent the foundation support for a blockhouse, it was not centrally located within either Forts B or C.

Another building, designated Building 1 by Elliott (1997:188) was located outside of the south wall of Fort A, but was intruded by the palisade ditch of Fort B. This suggests that Building 1 was older than Fort B. Elliott (1997) interpreted Building 1 as possibly that of one of the civilians who settled at Fort Argyle in the Trustee period, or possibly the private residence of the family of one of the Georgia Rangers. This interpretation remains valid based on more recent findings.

7.3.2 Fort Argyle B

Fort Argyle B (Fort B) represents the intermediate construction phase of Fort Argyle. Fort B was built by the Georgia Rangers after 1738 and more likely around 1742. This fort was first discovered by the SAS team in 1985. Braley et al. (1985) and his team located what he interpreted as all four walls of Fort B. Braley interpreted Fort B as a square fort, measuring 110 feet by 110 feet. His historical reference for these dimensions, however, actually date to the third and final fort construction phase in the 1760s.

Fort Argyle B is defined by its north, east, south and west walls. It was likely a simple rectangle in outline. The north wall extends for 32 to 36 m (105-108.3 feet). This north wall is defined in Excavation Blocks AB, F, W, E, and U. It is expressed by F8, F36, F198, F207 [8A], F251 and F327. F8 has a TPQ of 1733; F36 and F198 yielded no dateable ceramics; F207 has a TPQ of 1670; F251 has a TPQ of 1742 and F327 has a TPQ of 1742. These dates are consistent with an occupation by Georgia Rangers from 1742 to 1747.

The east wall of Fort B extends for at approximately 27-31 m (88.6-101.7 feet). Its east wall is defined in Excavation Blocks X, Y, J and M. It is expressed by F20, F68, F156, F225 and F291. F20, F68, F156 and F225 yielded no dateable ceramics and F291 has a TPQ of 1670. This date is consistent with an occupation by Georgia Rangers from 1742 to 1747. The west wall extends at least 24 m (78.7 feet) and possibly as much as 33 m (108.3 feet). The west wall of Fort B is defined in Excavation Blocks L, AC, and possibly AB. It is expressed by F24, F350 and possibly F327. F24 and F350 yielded no dateable ceramics and F327 has a TPQ of 1762. These dates are consistent with an occupation by Georgia Rangers from 1738 to 1762. Fort B's south wall is the least well-defined of its four walls, but it may be expressed in Excavation Blocks O, N and AE. Assuming that Fort B is fairly symmetrical, then its south wall may extend between 32 and 36 m. The palisade wall may be represented by F23, F38, F120, F365. F23 has a TPQ of 1740 and F38, F120 and F365 yielded no dateable ceramics. These dates are consistent with an occupation by Georgia Rangers from 1738 to 1747.

Elliott (1997:123, 137) suggested that the numerous posts his team uncovered within Excavation Block J were probably associated with his Building 2, which was interpreted as a barracks complex. The brick H-chimney base likely served to heat two rooms, which Elliott designated Building 2, within this barracks complex. Building 2 was built after Fort A, since the 1996 excavations demonstrated that this feature intruded into the southeast corner bastion of Fort A. Thus Building 2 was associated with either Forts B or C. Despite extensive excavations by LG²ES, this proved to be the only brick chimney pad discovered within Fort Argyle.

7.3.3 Fort Argyle C

Fort Argyle C (Fort C) represents the largest, and probably the final construction phase of Fort Argyle. We suspect that Fort C was constructed during the French and Indian War period (1755-1763) by the First Troop of Georgia Rangers. While elements of Fort C were unearthed in 1985, and a potential third fort was suggested by Elliott in 1997, Fort C was not recognized as a distinct fort structure until it was revealed by LG²ES excavations in January and February 2019. Because of its late discovery, Fort Argyle C remains the least well-defined of the Fort Argyle palisade outlines.

Fort C is known only by its north wall, which was delineated in Excavation Blocks C, D, Z and AD. It is expressed in F35, F68, F299, 363 and 401. F35 and F68 yielded no dateable ceramics. F299 has a TPQ of 1733 (F299A has a TPQ of 1744). F363 has a TPQ of 1762, and F401 has a TPQ of 1733. While two of the three dates are early and one is a good match, the early dates are not inconsistent with an occupation by Georgia Rangers from 1762 to 1767, and possibly earlier.

The west, east and south walls of Fort C have not been firmly established. Fort C may share a common west, east and south wall with Fort B. These palisade walls were discussed previously in the Fort B discussion.

Proof of Fort C is shown by the northernmost wall identified at Fort Argyle. It contains a projecting V-shaped ditch feature, which extends outside the fort to the north. This projection probably was for a cannon emplacement, or at least a position for small arms to protect against enfilading small arms fire from the north. Since the absolute eastern and western ends of the northern palisade wall of Fort C remains undetermined, researchers speculate that this V-bastion projection was centered approximately along the northern wall on its east-west axis. If so, then the east-west dimensions of Fort C can be estimated at greater than 27 m (88.5 feet) and possibly more like 45 m (144.4 feet).

Another possible configuration for Fort C is that its western and southern boundaries were outside of the areas that have received excavation and remain to be discovered. On the west side, any search for the Fort C palisade wall is problematic. A series of deep vehicle ruts and perpetually wet soils hinder any terrestrial approach to archaeology there. Even GPR survey in this area was stymied by the wet soils and their masking effects on the subsurface anomalies. Groundwater often creates strong radar reflections. This seems to be the case on the west side of Fort Argyle. It may be feasible to sample more on Fort Argyle's west side during a prolonged period of drought. Otherwise, well points and sump pumps would need to be employed vigorously to combat the groundwater that constantly seeps into the excavation blocks, as it did in the recent LG²ES experience. However, pumping would not mitigate the issues of detecting, defining, and documenting the nuances of feature shapes in plan and profile and the differentiation of wet clayey feature fill and surrounding wet clayey subsoils.

Fort C's eastern wall also may not have been located. As noted in 1997, Elliott observed that F155 intruded into the eastern palisade wall (F156) of Fort Argyle B. This meant that F155 could not have been created until this wall (F156) was destroyed. This clue led Elliott to speculate that a third configuration of Fort Argyle existed. If the eastern wall of Fort C was located east of the Fort B east wall, then it may well have eroded into the Ogeechee River. The LG²ES excavations honored a safety buffer along the river boundary, so our excavation did not extend very far to the east of the Fort B east wall. Only about 50 cm of excavation in Block Y explored the area east of the Fort B palisade. Braley's excavations extended further to the east in Blocks J and S, but none of these test units encountered any evidence for another eastern palisade ditch.

To the south, the site appears to be increasingly eroded with shallower plow zone and feature depths. Researchers in 1985, 1995/1996 and 2019 placed excavation units on the suspected south end of Fort

Argyle and no indisputable evidence for a south palisade wall has been found for either Fort B or Fort C. Several narrower, shallower trench candidates were located, but these also may represent individual building trench footings, driplines, or other feature types rather than a south fortification wall. Probably the best candidate of the group is F38 in Block O. Braley's excavation and profile sketch of F38 shows that it has some depth and may represent a palisade wall. Braley also located two smaller north-south trenches in Block O, which likely represent building walls. Block O had an MCD of 1747.4 and a TPQ of 1762, which indicate that this area was occupied in both the forts B and C eras.

LG²ES Block AE, which is located about 4.2 m east of Block O, also contains a narrow, shallow east-west trench that may be a vestige of a south fort wall, but this remains debatable. At any rate, this east-west trench alignment was not observed in Block N. However, Block N does contain other evidence of the south end of Fort Argyle. This is represented by F134 at the southern edge of Test Unit 10 in Block N, which was interpreted by Elliott (1997) as the fort ditch. Unfortunately, only a small portion of this feature was exposed; no artifacts were recovered from it.

Block Q, which was a 4 m north-south by 1 m east-west excavation block located 2 m south of Block N, contained no obvious cultural features, but it did display some depth for the meager cultural materials (n=59) that this block contained. Elliott (1997) interpreted this fill deposit, which was only slightly darker than the surrounding subsoil, as a possible fort ditch. He stated, "No features were designated in Block Q; however, the entire excavation block was placed on top of a suspected section of dry moat" (Elliott 1997:167). Block Q had an MCD of 1744 and a TPQ of 1744, which led Elliott to conclude that this "dry moat" was associated with Fort B. If forts B and C shared a common south wall, then this dry moat may also be associated with Fort C. It seems unlikely that this dry moat would have been excavated for Fort C and not Fort B, since the trend over time was for expanding the fort rather than contracting it.

The complete absence of any cultural features and the low artifact yield (n=147) observed in Block R, a 7 m east-west by 1 m north-south trench on the southwest side of Fort Argyle, suggests that this block was beyond the fort (Braley et al. 1985). Block R contained only a few dateable sherds, which gave an MCD of 1745.1 and a TPQ of 1762 based on the presence of plain creamware. This TPQ would make the plow zone deposits in this part of the site associated with the Fort C era.

Perhaps our best insight into the full extent of Fort Argyle, as it would be represented by Fort C, is seen through the limits of the systematic metal detector survey and its findings. Figure 7.8 illustrates the extent of metal detector finds superimposed on a plan of the excavation blocks.

The best contemporary description of Fort Argyle's architecture, albeit with very slim details, was written by Royal Governor James Wright in 1766, who described it as, "a square fort of 110 feet each way, with 2 rows of Barracks, and is in good condition and garrisoned by 35 Rangers" (CRG 28(2):422). This description probably refers to the final building episode at Fort Argyle, as the fort was abandoned early the following year.

Figure 7.9 Extent of Metal Detector Finds, Fort Argyle.

Given the absence of additional walls on the east, south and west sides of the fort that would represent the other walls of Fort C, one explanation is that forts B and C shared common walls on these three sides and varied only on the north side, where the fort was enlarged after 1756. It is unfortunate that the archaeological preservation on the west and south sides of Fort Argyle are poor, as details of the final building episode were probably contained in those areas.

7.3.4 Early Federal-era Georgia Militia Fortifications at Fort Argyle

Fort Argyle's use during the early Federal period appears limited. General James Jackson, Georgia militia, wrote concerning the number of blockhouses on the Georgia frontier in 1788. He lists Fort Argyle as among the blockhouses (Hawes 1953).

7.4 The People Who Lived at Fort Argyle

The men who served as Rangers and were garrisoned at Fort Argyle represent a diverse group of people. Ethnically they include Brits, Germans, Jews, Scots, and possibly others. Our historical research has identified the names of many Rangers who served there. Others living in and around the fort probably will remain nameless, and even for those whose names are known, little else can be gleaned about their lives. This includes soldiers, enslaved people, servants, civilians, and Native Americans; both men and women, and children.

The Rangers who lived at Fort Argyle can be grouped into three chronological categories. These are the South Carolina Rangers (1733-1738), the Georgia Rangers (1739-1747) and the (reformed) Georgia Rangers (1757-1767).

7.4.1 South Carolina Rangers

The number of South Carolina Rangers varied from only 11 men in March 1734 to a maximum of 26 men in May 1738. Few records were located for the South Carolina Rangers who were at Fort Argyle. Captain James McPherson's mounted troop of 30 Rangers were divided into three groups of 10 each. McPherson commanded 10 Rangers at Fort Argyle; Lieutenant William Elbert commanded another 10 at the first Fort Argyle (several miles upstream from Fort Argyle on the east side of the Ogeechee River); and the other 10 were at Fort Prince George, which was located at Palachacolas Old Town on the Savannah River in South Carolina (Temple and Coleman 1961:42-43).

7.4.2 Georgia Rangers

From October 1738 through June 1739 only two Georgia Rangers, Lachlan McIntosh and William Francis, occupied Fort Argyle. That number remained slim from November 1739 through September 1740, ranging from four to nine men. In October 1740 Quartermaster James Dormer and 10 rangers were ordered by the Georgia Trustee government to Fort Argyle. It remains unclear whether Dormer went to Fort Argyle.

By February 1741 the garrison at Fort Argyle consisted of 22 men, which included a captain, a lieutenant and 20 men. However, by March 1741 that number had plummeted and only four Georgia Rangers were manning the fort. In March 1742 Lieutenant John Milledge was appointed to command Fort Argyle and by November 1742 the garrison included Lieutenant Milledge and 20 Georgia Rangers. Lieutenant Milledge was promoted to the rank of captain soon thereafter. By December 1743 Georgia had a total of 140 Rangers and they were organized into two troops. Presuming that one troop was posted to Fort Argyle, the fort may have held as many as 70 men at that time. In July 1747, as hostilities with Spain had ended, the Rangers at Fort Argyle were dismissed. If any Rangers manned the fort for the next decade, no historical records were located to substantiate this.

7.4.3 Georgia Rangers (Reformed)

In 1757 Fort Argyle was reactivated as a Georgia Ranger fort. By June 1757 Captain John Milledge, who had served as commander of Fort Argyle from 1742 to 1747 and had continued to reside nearby in the intervening years, took command of one troop of 20 Georgia Rangers. In October 1757 Captain Milledge's ranger troop was ordered to Fort Argyle to escort 150 Creek Indians to meet with government officials in Savannah.

By 1758 the number of Georgia Rangers in Captain Milledge's troop had increased to 33 men. The following year Captain Milledge's First Troop of Georgia Rangers grew to 80 men, including Milledge. Fort Argyle's Ranger population dropped again in 1760, down to only 15 men, but it increased the following year to 36. Those numbers were stable for the next five years holding at 35 men. Royal Governor Wright wrote that the fort was garrisoned by 35 Rangers in 1766. However, by late 1766 the number of rangers at the fort again dropped to only 15 men. When the Georgia Rangers were officially disbanded the following spring Fort Argyle contained 15 Rangers (CRG 27:14).

Over its 34-year period of its existence, from 1733 to 1767, Fort Argyle's Ranger population went from as few as zero (1748-1756) to possibly as many as 80 men (1759). If the camp followers and civilians who called Fort Argyle their home also were living inside of the fort with 80 rangers, it would have been a crowded place indeed. Added to that the periodic influx of 150 or more Creeks who relied on Fort Argyle as a way station on their trips back and forth from the Creek Nation to Savannah, Fort Argyle would have been a vibrant, bustling place. More often, however, the fort was likely garrisoned by 35 or fewer men.

And of course, as their name indicates, Rangers tended to range, as their duties took them over various parts of coastal Georgia and the interior. Many times the troop was patrolling or on duty elsewhere and were not in garrison at Fort Argyle. The Rangers' diverse duties, in addition to patrolling the frontier on the lookout for foreign threats, included cattle herding, escorting Creek Indians and other dignitaries, and capturing criminals and other domestic law enforcement tasks. The Rangers time spent in garrison at Fort Argyle may have only been a small percentage of their actual time in military service.

One Georgia Ranger who stands out as the longest to serve at Fort Argyle was its commander, Captain John Milledge. John Milledge's first years in Georgia were turbulent ones. After the death of his parents shortly before January 19, 1739, John and his brother Richard were taken into the Bethesda Orphanage.

John was indentured not long afterwards to James Oglethorpe (White 1854:332). John Milledge was appointed quartermaster to the Georgia Rangers, where he served at Fort Argyle and quickly rose to the rank of Captain. Later he again served as captain of the Georgia Rangers during two wars from 1742 to 1747 and from 1757 to 1767. In addition to his duties as a Ranger captain, Milledge also served as a church warden in Christ-church parish (*The Georgia Gazette* April 25, 1765:4). Milledge owned extensive real estate near Fort Argyle so he had a vested interest in the fort's survival during most of his adult life. John Milledge's son, John Milledge, Jr., who was born in Savannah but who served as a Ranger Cadet at Fort Argyle from 1762 to 1767 would later serve honorably as Governor of Georgia and be the namesake for one of its former state capitals, Milledgeville.

7.4.5 Civilians

If the rangers seem like a largely anonymous group of people, the civilian population of Fort Argyle during the colonial era proved even more elusive. At its peak there were 10 families living in or around Fort Argyle. History does not provide the surnames of all these families but several that have been identified include Burnside, Calvert, Finley, Haselfoot, Roth, Schlectermann, Schweitzer, Smyth, Teesdale, Weddal and Wicks.

The earliest civilians associated with Fort Argyle were Mr. Burnside, James Haselfoot and Michael Schweitzer. In a November 20 letter to Oglethorpe, Patrick Mackay referred to "Mr. Burnside at Fort Argyle" (PC14200:309). James Haselfoot was listed at Fort Argyle in 1735 with his indentured servant, Michael Schweitzer. Haselfoot is identified as a landowner during the Trustee period (1732-1752). Schweitzer was later granted lands in Georgia in 1751 and 1757 and was in Savannah by 1759 (Jones 1986:114; Davies 1963, Vol. 43:143; CRG 1:162; 2:97; 3:39; Bryant 1975:141). The terms of indenture in Trustee Georgia was three years, so Schweitzer would have been a free man and able to leave Fort Argyle if he so desired by at least 1738.

Probably the largest single family to settle at Fort Argyle were the Schlectermanns. This family arrived in Georgia in 1733 as indentured servants and were sent by the Georgia Trustees' representatives to live there. One of their children, Peter, may have become a Georgia Ranger after he reached adulthood. The Schlectermann parents were dead by February 11, 1739, when six-year-old Jeremiah Sleighterman was taken into the Bethesda Orphanage (White 1854:333).

Two other indentured servants, John Smyth and Helen Bere Smyth, who were indentured to the Georgia Trustees and lived at Fort Argyle met their violent demise in 1742. John and Helen had been sent to live at Fort Argyle by the Georgia Trustees. While Fort Argyle's rangers were all out on patrol two nefarious characters, William Shannon and Joseph A. Mazzique, entered the fort and caused terror. John Smyth's body, minus his head, was found several days later floating in a creek near Fort Argyle. His wife's body was never found. Shannon and Mazzique were both executed for their crime.

Maria Margaretha Stoud (Bach) Leimberger was a strong, enduring person who lived for a hectic, but brief time in her early years at Fort Argyle. Her first husband, Gabriel Bach was a Georgia Ranger in the fort. Both Maria and Gabriel had come to Georgia in 1734 from Memmingen, Swabia [Bavaria] to live in the Ebenezer settlement with other German-speaking immigrants from the Salzburg region of Europe.

Gabriel was enticed to join the Georgia Rangers and his wife accompanied him to Fort Argyle. Gabriel's days as a ranger were numbered, as he was among the rangers who were killed by Indians during General Oglethorpe's campaign against Spanish Florida. Reverend Johann Martin Boltzius of Ebenezer recorded in his detailed report on June 4, 1740, "Gabriel Bach, who left us for the Ogeechee and took up military service, was attacked by Spanish Indians, shot, beheaded, and almost completely skinned. Because he was bold and knew well how to get around in the woods, Mr. Oglethorpe regretted losing him. His head is supposed to have been recaptured from the Indians and brought to Mr. Oglethorpe, who had it sent in a box to the commandant in St. Augustine and let him know that he and his people would fare no better because of that atrocity" (Jones and Savelle 1983:148).

Gabriel's widow Maria, who went by Margaretha, continued to live at Fort Argyle for a while following his death, where she earned a reputation for being a "loose woman" and sharing favors with the other Rangers in the fort. She later returned to Ebenezer to seek forgiveness and to rejoin the fold in that pietist Lutheran town. Reverend Boltzius noted in the detailed report for July 9, 1741, "I met N. [Mrs. Margaretha Leinberger], who was going into the town to get some medications because of her infirmities. God has made her mellow and humble in the continual physical weakness she has had since her marriage to honest N. [Leinberger], so that she recognizes sins as the cause of all evil and is submitting herself to God's omnipotent hand, She sincerely detests her previous sins and the godless ways of her previous deceased husband [Gabriel Bach from Memmingen] and humbly praises the Lord for His goodness for saving her from such snares and bringing her here where her soul can be saved" (Jones 1985:293-294). Boltzius recorded a conversation with her in the detailed report four days later,

Yesterday before the prayer hour N. [Mrs. Margaretha Leinberger] spoke to me to arrange a time when she could visit me to talk about her soul. She came this morning one hour before my trip and confessed, trembling, fearful, crying, and moaning that she was the worst, most despicable sinner. Her sins oppressed her, she said, like heavy stones; and she will not have any peace until she has purified her soul through confession. Oh, how a single woman is subjected to many dangers here as well as in many places in Germany; and, as she thankfully recognizes, it is a great benefaction of God when such people who are exposed to sin [the filthiest horrors] through much temptation and their own sinfulness [acquiescence] can still find their way to God's word, to good people, and to reflection. Both before and during her marriage she committed many sins despite my warnings at the wedding and afterwards, based on Mark 5:18-20 [King James version- And when he was come into the ship, he that had been possessed with the devil prayed him that he might be with him. Howbeit Jesus suffered him not, but saith unto him, Go home to thy friends, and tell them how great things the Lord hath done for thee, and hath had compassion on thee.]; and her conscience is also burdened with sins committed against the seventh commandment [Thou shalt not commit adultery].

The unfortunate Bach had taken her from our place to Ogeechee or Fort Argyle and had left her there alone after his departure for the siege of St. Augustine. She knows from experience that several people who committed such sins [with her] have suffered in their bodies and she is now in holy terror [about her sin and the curse it observes]. She can almost put her hand on the source of her lasting infirmities [which she has had since her marriage to Leinberger], and she

knows what a salutary purpose God has. I reminded her again of her abominations, which were committed before the eyes of our all-seeing and holy God and warned her, since God is appealing to her conscience, to implore God day and night from now on with prayers and tears that her heart will be crushed and be strengthened for the good [in faith] (Jones 1985:297).

Reverend Boltzius' characterization of Margaretha as an adulteress, or a married woman who had sexual intercourse with a man other than her husband, and a sinner of "the filthiest horrors", while living at Fort Argyle, is graphic and damning. Boltzius' description of her "infirmities" and "continual physical weakness" may indicate that she contracted a debilitating venereal disease, such as syphilis or gonorrhea, at Fort Argyle. Treatment of sexually transmitted diseases in the eighteenth century was dangerous and often ineffective and physicians' and the general public's attitudes concerning sexually transmitted diseases were largely misinformed (Douglas 1737; Gallagher 2019). Physicians used mercury as a treatment for syphilis.

It would be speculation as to what type of affliction befell Margaretha Leimberger, but she seems to have survived it. Margaretha Bach married Christian Leimberger at Ebenezer in 1741, and she was welcomed back into the Lutheran community. Margaretha and Christian raised a family and amassed a modest plantation. Margaretha outlived her second husband as well, after Christian died in 1763. She then married Peter Janson in 1764 and continued to live on her plantation at Ebenezer's Mill District until her death at the respectable age of 95 (Smith 1986).

Several other Georgia Rangers with German surnames who served at Fort Argyle were associated with the Ebenezer colony or its offshoots (Smith 1986; Jones and Savelle 1983; Jones and Exley 1991). Fort Argyle's demographics were a blend of British, German, Jewish, local Georgians, Scottish and possibly other ethnic groups.

8.0 SUMMARY RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1 Recommendations for Future Research

Fort Argyle is an extremely complex site due to many factors. It was constructed, occupied, repaired, virtually abandoned, then reconstructed, re-occupied, repaired, and virtually abandoned in minimally three distinctive cycles. In addition, the military site is also associated directly with civilian and Native American cultural interactions. Its location on North America's colonial frontier places it in a nether-world of long-standing, traditional military and bureaucratic protocols laced with the harsh realities of life on the frontier. Such intricacies produce an incredibly complex archaeological site that, while difficult and slow to unravel, can reveal significant information about a myriad of subjects important to a comprehensive understanding of the colonial past.

Multiple archaeological excavations over the years at Fort Argyle have been extensive, but not exhaustive by any means due to the site's complexity. Considerable portions remain unexplored and these areas should be studied by future archaeologists. The present study was a data recovery effort specifically targeted to mitigate the impact from river erosion at the fort. Once these excavations were completed, at least 50 percent of the core area of the multiple forts remains to be fully explored. Previous shoreline research by LG²ES at Fort Argyle demonstrated an accelerated rate of bank erosion, which is expected to continue as global sea levels continue to rise as a result of climate warming. Our sampling efforts serve to mitigate this cultural loss along the eastern side of the archaeological site. While our data recovery excavations satisfied the contract requirements, an impressive portion of the colonial fort remains relatively intact and available for future professional archaeological study. The historical study and archaeological excavations of the LG²ES research project answered many of its research questions, adding a new layer to the fascinating story of Fort Argyle and its reflection of the 18th century American frontier. Those findings generated many new questions building on this work that beg for answers from future study. These are examined below.

8.1.1 Military Architecture

The design of military structures is critical to their success. Such designs have evolved over millennia as engineers and military strategists develop better ways to attack and defend populations using ever-evolving technology. Eighteenth century military architecture included evolving designs in fortification shapes and sizes. Additional archaeological excavation at Fort Argyle can uncover more of the puzzling architecture of the fort constructions and reconstructions, enabling answers to questions such as those below.

How do the three (or more) fort constructions reflect the evolving fort typologies of the 18th century? Are their sizes and shapes indicative of a specific frontier military strategy, type of enemy combatant, size of troops able to defend it, funding/economic support to construct and maintain it, and/or ongoing evolutionary engineering designs?

What can construction techniques reveal about the specific military strategy at Fort Argyle? For example, is palisade construction the same for all fort constructions there and if not, how does it vary in terms of

trench depth, post depth, uniformity of post size and depth, and method of securement? What type of bastion constructions are represented during which periods, and does each reflect strategic needs or economic realities? Where were the gates located for each fort? Does the number, size, and location of the gates suggest the type and direction of the perceived threat (i.e.- attack from the water versus from land; attack from Spanish-allied Native Americans with hand arms versus attack from Spanish troops with artillery) and/or do the gate location and size reflect everyday logistical needs for fort access and egress? What are the number, arrangement, and type of structures within the forts' interiors, and how does that change over time? Do the numbers of barracks and their sizes reflect fort population? Was there a block house, kitchen, powder magazine and/or other structures during any of the Fort Argyle constructions? Were there privies inside and/or outside the fort and if so where were they located? Did fort residents obtain their drinking water from the river, wells, springs, or cisterns? Where were their water sources located and how were they accessed? What other structures were located within and outside of the fort, how were they constructed, and what does the types of materials and methods of construction tell us about the structures' functions and the status of their users?

8.1.2 Material Culture

While cultural features are key to providing insights at archaeological sites, artifacts are critical to revealing information related to those features as well as the site as a whole. The majority of artifacts from the LG²ES data recovery work came from the plow zone stratum of the many test units excavated rather than from the less artifact-dense features. All the artifacts, particularly diagnostic types indicative of particular time periods, origins of manufacture, costs, and functions, are especially helpful in shedding light on status, socio-economic class, ethnicity, and quality of life. Additional future excavation of artifacts, especially those linked to specific features, can contribute greatly to a better understanding of life at Fort Argyle. This includes some of the research questions below.

The materiel and supply chain are critical for successful operation of a fort, particularly a frontier fort like Argyle. Historical documentation for this current report reveals how frequently commanding officers and higher bureaucrats requested, and often did not receive, important supplies, weaponry, food, pay, and items needed for fort construction or maintenance. How do additional artifact assemblages quantitatively and qualitatively reflect bureaucratic support (or lack of support) for the fort and its personnel? Is there evidence of the fort receiving official supplies, such as guns, swords, and lead balls of the type and caliber indicative of British-supplied materiel? Do any buttons indicate that Rangers were being supplied with some uniform materials? Documents indicate that supplies and pay at Fort Argyle were inadequate and irregular. Is there evidence in the material culture that reveals the degree of this shortage and how occupants dealt with it? Is there artifactual evidence revealing unofficial bartering and or purchase of items from Native Americans, area civilians, or other soldiers and officers? Can the in-house production of gunflints from European ballast stones and lead balls from recycled materials be quantified to reveal the degree to which soldiers relied on home-made weaponry accoutrements? What percentage of locally produced wares (in the southeastern colonies), such as coarse earthenware, constitutes the ceramic assemblage and does this reflect economic necessity or merely convenience? Soil analyses for the LG²ES project revealed the presence of rice and corn on the site. Were these items being cultivated by Fort Argyle inhabitants, nearby colonists, area plantations, and/or across Georgia and Carolina? Can additional soil studies expand our knowledge of the plant-portion of the diet of Fort Argyle occupants? Bone

preservation at the Fort Argyle site is extremely poor and few identifiable bone fragments have been located on all the excavations to date. Can future archaeology pinpoint features such as wells and privies that may offer better preservation in their non-aerobic soils? If so, can the existence of such bones reveal the carnivorous portions of Fort Argyle diets, including what percentages were constituted by subsistence such as hunting and fishing; by domestic animals; and by militarily supplied sources such as dried or salted meats? Can the quantification of artifacts such as fishing weights and small bird shot contribute to a better understanding of the diet of a Fort Argyle occupant?

Material culture can also provide socio-economic and ethnic identifiers, as discussed earlier in this report. The excavation of additional quantities and varieties of artifacts can enlarge this discussion greatly. Can high-status artifacts such as porcelain, tea dishes, coins, silver buttons and buckles, and even bricks help locate other areas associated with officers, such as the barracks mentioned earlier in the report. Status appears to be relative at Fort Argyle, rather than a reflection of comparisons to wealthy residents in the colonies or abroad. For instance, the possible officers' barracks chimney made of half-bricks and smaller pieces is high status in contrast to a mud and stick chimney likely used in the soldiers' barracks. How is status defined on this frontier fort and what other artifacts represent it in the material culture there? Can items be tied to particular cultures, such as the civilian colonial settlers living around the fort and relying heavily on its protection? What artifacts are representative of the Native Americans frequently traveling through the area and often staying at the fort? Can these artifacts provide more information on Native American interaction with Europeans, particularly from a neutral, non-historical text perspective? Can material culture provide any clues to the lifeways of the enslaved people at the fort?

8.1.3 Environments and Landscapes

Fort Argyle is an environmental contradiction. Located on an elevated bluff, its soils are frequently waterlogged. Situated in the sandy coastal plain, it contains silty clay. How did the colonial environment differ (if at all) from the current site environment? Are the water tables notably different and how did this affect fort construction, cultivation, and the accessing of drinking water through wells and springs? Soil analyses of pollen and phytoliths for the LG²ES work provides some initial data on the types of plants growing in the area and/or used at the fort during the colonial period. Additional data from new features can contribute to that knowledge of the historic landscape, perhaps isolating specific weather events and other landscape-related events during the four decades of site use. How did the landscape and the adaptation to it by Fort Argyle occupants compare and contrast (as revealed in historical documentation and archaeological excavation) to other frontier forts in colonial America?

8.1.4 Fort Argyle Life Cycle

Fort Argyle was one site with multiple lives. Every few decades it was reborn from its deteriorated ruins, with the same goals of protecting British settlers and defending one small edge of the British Empire. This cyclical abandonment and reconstruction of Fort Argyle provides an opportunity for the site's synchronic and diachronic study. The latest excavation has provided fodder for both. It looked at the fort as snapshots in time based on tying the year-by-year historical documentation to on-the-ground features, as well as tying artifacts and artifact assemblages to specific events and people. Likewise, the recent excavations have also looked at the site diachronically, trying to discern which palisades are related to

which building episodes over the decades, as well as how the features and artifact assemblages reflect changes over time. Additional excavation can contribute greatly to this static and evolutionary picture. What are the complete shapes of the forts and how did changes to them affect the fort's operation? During what period was Fort Argyle the most dominant in frontier strategic affairs and when was it the most successful in its goals? Did the relationship between Rangers at Fort Argyle and British-allied Native Americans change over time and how is this evidenced on the site? Was the relationship between the nearby settlers and the Rangers at Fort Argyle symbiotic or parasitic, and in what manner? Does Fort Argyle reflect global trends or exceptions in terms of fort construction, military strategy, and Ranger life?

8.1.5 Maritime Archaeology

Underwater archaeology in the Ogeechee River near Fort Argyle remains a relatively untapped avenue for research (Folse 1985; Braley et al. 1985; Martin et al. 1986). Fort Stewart does not have jurisdiction over the management of cultural resources that are submerged in the Ogeechee River, that authority falls to the State of Georgia. The State of Georgia's Historic Preservation Division should be encouraged to pursue this subject and inventory and assess Fort Argyle's submerged cultural resources. Underwater archaeologists have long touted that submerged resources should be considered routinely along with terrestrial archaeology, merely conducted in a different environment, with different tools and technology. In that light, much of what has been uncovered by a cursory dive in 1985 by Braley, as well as what can be uncovered in the future by comprehensive underwater investigations, can contribute to many of the research questions above. The material culture from both terrestrial and submerged sites can provide answers to the same types of questions. For instance, underwater survey and excavation may recover artifacts in the Ogeechee River that were tossed off the bank as a method of disposal. Other artifacts may have fallen in the river while being unloaded or (less likely) loaded onto boats. Such artifacts contribute to the overall research questions such as what types and quantities of supplies were shipped to the fort from local, Caribbean, and trans-Atlantic ports? It can also answer new questions such as, what types of losses did the fort sustain in terms of shipping and unloading mishaps? How did environmental conditions such as rough weather, tidal flow, and flooding contribute to these losses? What components of the site have already been lost because of the active erosion of the Ogeechee?

Arguably, the singular difference between terrestrial and underwater archaeology lies with the variable components of a site, including those that are generally found most often in a submerged environment. For example, site components such as wharves, docks, and vessels are most often located in underwater or semi-submerged environments. How extensive and sturdy were wharves and docks at Fort Argyle? How were they constructed and of what materials? Did flooding and erosion affect their construction and use? How did fort occupants make the wharves/docks a viable link in unloading vessels from the river and transporting the goods to the top of the bluff? What types of vessels were able to access Fort Argyle from the Ogeechee River? Which vessels were most often used by occupants? Which vessel types most frequently came to Fort Argyle? Is there evidence of local, vernacular watercraft wrecks (including European and Native American) in the Ogeechee River, riverbank, river sediments, or river channel near Fort Argyle? Can such evidence be located, documented, and interpreted? What were the largest and deepest-draft vessels that could and did travel to Fort Argyle via the Ogeechee River? Did these include vessels in the coastwise trade, ocean-going ships, or entirely smaller craft? Were dug-out canoes commonly seen at Fort Argyle?

The complexity of the Fort Argyle site warrants continued future excavation. Such work will continue to answer (and generate) new research questions and can incorporate new technologies to contribute additional fascinating layers to this amazing story. The questions above are just a few of the many tantalizing mysteries that continue to shroud the site yet can be answered slowly and methodically over time.

8.2 Public Outreach at Fort Argyle

A long-term plan for site interpretation at Fort Argyle is advisable. It should be a phased approach that incorporates an array of public outreach efforts. Because of its location, historical significance, and archaeological condition, Fort Argyle is an excellent site for educating the public about global American history as relatable and reflectable on a local level, the value of archaeological sites and historic and scientific research, and the goals of historic preservation as exemplified at Fort Argyle. A program of interpretive activities at Fort Argyle can include:

- Establishment of regular guided field trips several times a year to the site by the Fort Stewart Historic Communities Council for school children and other interested members of the public tied to specific calendrical events such as Veterans Day, Georgia Archaeology Month; Georgia History Day, Earth Day, etc.
- Creation of elementary, middle school, and high school curricula using Fort Argyle and its archaeology to teach multidisciplinary state-mandated and nationally-recommended standards in English/Language arts, mathematics, science, history, art, and STEM subjects.

Design and implementation of technological innovations in outreach and interpretation such as:

- Augmented Reality (AR) program that enables visitors to rotate their cell phone or on-site viewers to various areas of the site to see a virtual reconstruction of the various Fort Argyle (A, B, C) structures, to see Rangers, Native Americans, African Americans, and settlers interacting at the fort, river, and its surroundings.
- Development of an interactive web site using the wealth of information from the three archaeology excavation reports to showcase the site's history, archaeology, and environment, as well as Fort Stewart's commitment to preservation. Such a site could be created to be used by the public with no follow-up necessary (other than ensuring that the web page remains accessible to the public).
- Creation of professionally designed permanent interpretive signage on-site.
- Creation, fabrication, and installation of a modern, comprehensive, interactive Fort Argyle exhibit at the Fort Stewart Military Museum, the Richmond Hill Museum, or other venue that would be amenable.
- Opportunities for the public to observe and follow ongoing archaeological excavations.
- Publication (in print and digitally) of technical and non-technical research reports.
- Reconstruction and interpretation of the fort along with a permanent interpretive museum.

All of the items above would contribute substantially to a greater public awareness and understanding of our shared historical past. Fort Argyle represents a tangible connection to early America and the fragile link between Native, African, and European history. A well-interpreted site has the power to educate on multiple levels and in powerful ways.

Increasing public outreach results in more widespread awareness of history and archaeology at Fort Stewart. That should be tempered with the continual goal of preserving the site from environmental and human threats. Site preservation can be aided more easily now by inexpensive outdoor cameras in addition to low-tech military patrols and other means. Such preservation is key to ensuring that Fort Stewart remains a viable site for both public outreach and future scholarly and scientific research.

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APPENDIX A: Artifact Inventory, LG²ES Excavations, 9BN28.

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Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.001.001	Block Y, MD 1, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	17.1
201.002.001	MD 2, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	7.6
201.003.001	MD 3, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	6.1
201.004.001	MD 4, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Button		1	3.4
201.005.001	MD 5, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	12.7
201.006.001	MD 6, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	5.1
201.007.001	Block Z, MD 7, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	32.7
201.008.001	MD 8, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	29.4
201.009.001	Block W, MD 9, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Gun hardware		1	7.3
201.010.001	Block W, MD 10, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Button, Domed		1	1.8
201.011.001	Block W, MD 11, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	6.3
201.012.001	MD 12, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	11.6
201.013.001	Block Z, MD 13, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Shoe buckle		1	2.3
201.014.001	Block Z, MD 14, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	7.4
201.015.001	Block Z, MD 15, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	4.7
201.016.001	BLK A, MD 16, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	2.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.017.001	BLK A, MD 17, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	2.9
201.018.001	Block Z, MD 18, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	14.2
201.019.001	BLK A, MD 19, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	26.3
201.020.001	BLK A, MD 20, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	13.6
201.021.001	BLK A, MD 23, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	4.1
201.022.001	BLK A, MD 24, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	13.4
201.023.001	BLK A, MD 25, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Button		1	4.6
201.024.001	BLK A, MD 26, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	14.8
201.025.001	BLK A, MD 27, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Token, left facing bust surrounded by 13 stars		1	1
201.026.001	Block W, MD 28, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	5.1
201.027.001	BLK A, MD 29, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-4 cmbs		Metal	Lead strip		1	5.6
201.028.001	BLK A, MD 30, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-4 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	2.6
201.029.001	Block W, MD 31, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	6.8
201.030.001	BLK A, MD 32, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-5 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	18.2
201.031.001	BLK A, MD 33, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		2	7.4
201.032.001	Block W, MD 34, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-10 cmbs		Metal	Lead strip		1	26.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.033.001	BLK A, MD 35, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	29.7
201.034.001	BLK A, MD 36, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	15
201.035.001	BLK A, MD 38, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead, Partially Melted		1	5.6
201.036.001	BLK A, MD 39, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	14.5
201.037.001	BLK A, MD 40, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	3.4
201.038.001	BLK A , MD 41, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	3.2
201.039.001	BLK A , MD 42, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	4.1
201.040.001	BLK A, MD 43, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Brass strip		1	1.7
201.041.001	Block AD, MD 44, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	18.2
201.042.001	Block AD, MD 45, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Cylinder		1	22.6
201.043.001	Block X, MD 46, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	16.2
201.044.001	BLK A, MD 47, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Pot, cast iron		1	23.8
201.045.001	BLK A, MD 49, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	23.4
201.046.001	BLK A, MD 50, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	3.6
201.047.001	BLK A, MD 51, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	15.8
201.048.001	BLK B, MD 52, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Pot, cast iron		1	256.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.049.001	BLK B, MD 53, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead strip		1	2.2
201.050.001	Block Y, MD 54, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Shoe buckle		1	2.4
201.051.001	Block Y, MD 55, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	5.1
201.052.001	Block Y, MD 56, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	2.2
201.053.001	BLK B, MD 58, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	11.1
201.054.001	Block J, MD 59, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	1.7
201.055.001	BLK B, MD 60, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	2.8
201.056.001	BLK B, MD 61, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	30.2
201.057.001	Block N, MD 62, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	1.7
201.058.001	BLK B, MD 63, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	22.8
201.059.001	Block J, MD 65, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Pewter fragment		1	1
201.060.001	Block T, MD 66, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	6
201.061.001	BLK B, MD 67, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Bullet		1	8.8
201.062.001	BLK B, MD 68, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID metal		1	0.6
201.063.001	BLK B, MD 69, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Aluminum		1	2.8
201.064.001	Block Y, MD 70, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	15.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.065.001	Block Y, MD 71, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	17.9
201.066.001	BLK B, MD 72, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Coin, U.S. Nickel		1	4
201.067.001	Block N, MD 73, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Button, Engraved geometric flora		1	0.6
201.068.001	BLK B, MD 74, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	8.2
201.069.001	BLK B, MD 75, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	16.3
201.070.001	Block V, MD 76, F 176C, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead scrap		1	2.3
201.071.001	BLK B, MD 78, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	13
201.072.001	BLK B, MD 77, Plowzone	Plowzone	10-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	19.3
201.072.002	BLK B, MD 78, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		10	36
201.073.001	BLK B, MD 79, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	19.9
201.073.002	BLK B, MD 79, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Sword guard fragment		1	9
201.074.001	BLK B, MD 80, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Zinc		1	8.8
201.075.001	BLK B, MD 81, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Button		1	2
201.076.001	MD 82, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	17.5
201.076.002	MD 82, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	3.4
201.077.001	MD 83, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Pot, cast iron		1	155.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.078.001	MD 84, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	22.6
201.079.001	MD 85, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	3.8
201.080.001	MD 86, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	20.5
201.081.001	MD 88, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Cast Iron pot fragment		1	939.6
201.082.001	MD 91, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Shoe buckle		1	3.1
201.083.001	BLK C, MD 92, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	23.5
201.084.001	MD 93, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Glass	Container glass		1	1.1
201.085.001	MD 94, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	14
201.086.001	MD 95, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Button, Engraved geometric flora		1	0.6
201.087.001	Block N, MD 96, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead strip		1	10.9
201.088.001	Block N, MD 97, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead		1	4
201.089.001	Block N, MD 98, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	2.8
201.089.002	Block N, MD 98, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID Metal, possible Pewter		1	2.3
201.090.001	MD 99, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Screw		1	1.8
201.091.001	MD 100, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	4.8
201.092.001	MD 101, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	3.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.092.007					Lithic	Gunflint		1	4.1
201.093.001	MD 102, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	2.8
201.094.001	MD 103, Plowzone	Plowzone			Metal	Lead ball		1	1.8
201.095.001	MD 104, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	15.9
201.096.001	MD 105, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	16.5
201.097.001	MD 106, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Hinge, Door or Gate		1	574.8
201.098.001	MD 107, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID metal alloy		1	2.9
201.099.001	MD 108, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID metal alloy		1	2.9
201.100.001	MD 109, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Wire		1	3.8
201.101.001	MD 110, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Brass brad		1	5.3
201.102.001	MD 111, Plowzone	Plowzone	0-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	14.4
201.103.001	Transitpoint 20	Surface	0 cmbs		Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	3.2
201.103.003					Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.6
201.104.001	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat-altered		1	6.3
201.104.002	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		4	12.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.104.003	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat-altered		2	1.7
201.104.004	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.7
201.104.005	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3
201.104.006	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Plain		1	24.2
201.104.007	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		1	0.7
201.104.008	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, possibly tin glazed		1	0.9
201.104.009	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	21.4
201.104.010	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		1	14.6
201.104.011	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.3
201.104.012	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Lithics	Flake		1	0.5
201.104.013	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	6.4
201.104.014	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.5
201.104.015	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	0.9
201.104.016	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Relief-molded: dot, diaper and basket		1	1.4
201.104.017	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield, Lead glaze		2	4.7
201.104.018	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		5	37.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.104.019	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		23	119
201.104.020	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1			Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		2	1.2
201.104.021	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	2.3
201.104.022	Block T, TU 100, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.105.001	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.8
201.105.002	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.9
201.105.003	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		2	3.1
201.105.004	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat-altered		1	3.5
201.105.005	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield, Black glaze		1	2.1
201.105.006	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Lithics	Non-Cultural rock		1	1.8
201.105.007	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.3
201.105.008	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Lithics	Non-Cultural rock		1	0.6
201.105.009	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	0.8
201.105.010	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	0.3
201.105.011	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural rock		1	17
201.105.012	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		12	41.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.105.013	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	1.7
201.105.014	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.105.015	Block T, TU 101, L1	L1		0-19 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Red Filmed	Grit	1	2.2
201.106.001	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Metal	Slide adjustment		1	1
201.106.002	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	10.8
201.106.003	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat-altered		1	4.1
201.106.004	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Salt glazed		1	5.4
201.106.005	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Brown Slipped	Sand, Grog	1	1.8
201.106.006	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.3
201.106.007	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.2
201.106.008	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Melted		1	2.8
201.106.009	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Lithics	Possible whetstone		1	24.9
201.106.010	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	2.8
201.106.011	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.7
201.106.012	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	6.8
201.106.013	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	1.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.106.014	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	1
201.106.015	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		15	150.8
201.106.016	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	30.1
201.106.017	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		10	57.5
201.106.018	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.5
201.106.019	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.5
201.106.020	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.106.021	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Other	Fossiliferous limestone		1	1
201.106.022	Block T, TU 102, L1	L1		2-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Lead glazed		1	3.7
201.107.001	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	1.4
201.107.002	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat-altered		2	3.2
201.107.003	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.4
201.107.004	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Metal	Lead strip		1	8.1
201.107.005	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	6.7
201.107.006	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.5
201.107.007	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.107.008	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.107.009	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Red Filmed	Grit, sand	1	1.6
201.107.010	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.7
201.107.011	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	English soft-paste porcelain, Lead glazed		1	0.8
201.107.012	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.6
201.107.013	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Metal	Bullet casing		1	2.6
201.107.014	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	3.4
201.107.015	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	9.7
201.107.016	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		16	93.4
201.107.017	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.3
201.107.018	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.5
201.107.019	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.5
201.107.020	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.107.021	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	1.2
201.107.022	Block T, TU 103, L1	L1		5-24 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	0.3
201.108.001	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	8.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.108.002	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		17	47.1
201.108.003	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		2	0.9
201.108.004	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	1
201.108.005	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	4.5
201.108.006	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.5
201.108.007	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Lithics	Non-Cultural Stone		1	1.8
201.108.008	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	1.5
201.108.009	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.4
201.108.010	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Metal	Wire		1	0.8
201.108.011	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	5.1
201.108.012	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		11	49.2
201.108.013	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.108.014	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded glaze		1	0.2
201.108.015	Block V, TU 104, L1	L1		0-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded glaze		1	1.8
201.109.001	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Flat		1	1.6
201.109.002	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.109.003	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	5.7
201.109.004	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4.9
201.109.005	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.3
201.109.006	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Indeterminate Stamped	Sand, clay	1	2.3
201.109.007	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4
201.109.008	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.5
201.109.009	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	3
201.109.010	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	2.1
201.109.011	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Other	Fossiliferous limestone		1	0.7
201.109.012	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		7	43.8
201.109.013	Block V, TU 105, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.110.001	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	37.8
201.110.002	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	18.4
201.110.003	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Curved		1	0.4
201.110.004	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		2	3.1
201.110.005	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.110.006	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	3.3
201.110.007	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Lithics	Biface, Unifacial		1	0.8
201.110.008	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Refined Earthenware, tin glazed		1	0.8
201.110.009	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	1.8
201.110.010	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	2.7
201.110.011	Block V, TU 106, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.111.001	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		4	6.6
201.111.002	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	1.5
201.111.003	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	5.7
201.111.004	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	1.9
201.111.005	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.2
201.111.006	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	3.3
201.111.007	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4
201.111.008	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	2.8
201.111.009	Block V, TU 107, L1	L1		12-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.112.001	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.112.002	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3.5
201.112.003	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.6
201.112.004	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.112.005	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	2.4
201.112.006	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	1.6
201.112.007	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Tin glazed		1	4.2
201.112.008	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		8	37.9
201.112.009	Block V, TU 108, L1	L1		8-19 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.113.001	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	2.8
201.113.002	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Organics	Sturgeon scute		1	0.8
201.113.003	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	2
201.113.004	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe, Initials on heel		1	4.4
201.113.005	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	5.3
201.113.006	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		3	23.7
201.113.007	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	16
201.113.008	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, complete, wire		1	13.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.113.009	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Metal	Knapsack hook		1	8.1
201.113.010	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Lithics	Biface, Complete		1	1.3
201.113.011	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	2
201.113.012	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	2.2
201.113.013	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	4.7
201.113.014	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	0.9
201.113.015	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.113.016	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	1.5
201.113.017	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4
201.113.018	Block U, TU 109, L1	L1		11-26 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	8.1
201.114.001	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	12.1
201.114.002	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	44
201.114.003	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	29.8
201.114.004	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4
201.114.005	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	3	7.5
201.114.006	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.114.007	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.114.008	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	40.1
201.114.009	Block U, TU 110, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, modified		1	1.5
201.115.001	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.7
201.115.002	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	6.7
201.115.003	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.3
201.115.004	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	3
201.115.005	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	4.2
201.115.006	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	3.5
201.115.007	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glaze		1	1.2
201.115.008	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.3
201.115.009	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1
201.115.010	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2
201.115.011	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		12	51.3
201.115.012	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.115.013	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.115.014	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, modified		1	2.4
201.115.015	Block U, TU 111, L1	L1		6-32 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4
201.116.001	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.4
201.116.002	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	18.5
201.116.003	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	23.5
201.116.004	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	3.3
201.116.005	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Melted		3	7.2
201.116.006	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	2.4
201.116.007	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	12.5
201.116.008	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	1.5
201.116.009	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.8
201.116.010	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	0.9
201.116.011	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	14
201.116.012	Block U, TU 112, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.117.001	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	22.2
201.117.002	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		3	11.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.117.003	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.2
201.117.004	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		3	7
201.117.005	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		2	4.5
201.117.006	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.3
201.117.007	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield		1	2
201.117.008	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		8	13.9
201.117.009	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.6
201.117.010	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	14.2
201.117.011	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Glass	Other glass		1	2
201.117.012	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		20	92.3
201.117.013	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.117.014	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.9
201.117.015	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Lithics	Shatter		1	2.3
201.117.016	Block U, TU 113, L1	L1		8-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.4
201.118.001	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	5.5
201.118.002	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.118.003	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.8
201.118.004	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	5.3
201.118.005	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		9	36.7
201.118.006	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		11	45.4
201.118.007	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	10.8
201.118.008	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		7	69.6
201.118.009	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	36.3
201.118.010	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	5
201.118.011	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.118.012	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.4
201.118.014	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Modified		2	2.2
201.118.113	Block U, TU 114, L1	L1		0-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.119.001	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.2
201.119.002	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord Marked	Grit	1	5.6
201.119.003	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.1
201.119.004	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	10.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.119.005	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.9
201.119.006	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		5	22.6
201.119.007	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Eroded and lead glaze		1	2.6
201.119.008	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.4
201.119.009	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.2
201.119.010	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		3	22.8
201.119.011	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	2
201.119.012	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		9	34.5
201.119.015	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.3
201.119.113	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord marked	Grit	1	2.6
201.119.114	Block U, TU 115, L1	L1		5-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.120.001	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	6.9
201.120.002	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.4
201.120.003	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	4.8
201.120.004	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, lead glazed		1	1.8
201.120.005	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	0.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.120.006	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	11.4
201.120.007	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	2.2
201.120.008	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		2	15.5
201.120.009	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		16	36.6
201.120.010	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	2.4
201.120.011	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail or Spike		1	20.8
201.120.012	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	24.4
201.120.013	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.5
201.120.014	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord Marked	Sand	1	1.5
201.120.015	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, eroded lead glaze		2	2
201.120.016	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Lithics	Modified Quartz, Prism		1	2.9
201.120.017	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.8
201.120.018	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.4
201.120.119	Block U, TU 116, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.121.001	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	13
201.121.002	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Canning lid		1	1.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.121.003	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	9.1
201.121.004	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	0.9
201.121.005	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.4
201.121.006	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1
201.121.007	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, clay	1	2.8
201.121.008	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, lead glazed		1	1.3
201.121.009	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	22.9
201.121.010	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		3	40
201.121.011	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	1.6
201.121.012	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.4
201.121.013	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		15	33.1
201.121.014	Block W, TU 117, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.122.001	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	1.3
201.122.002	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	7.1
201.122.003	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	2.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.122.004	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Unglazed		1	3.2
201.122.005	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		2	4.8
201.122.006	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7.4
201.122.007	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	19.9
201.122.008	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat-altered		1	1.6
201.122.009	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.9
201.122.010	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	18.4
201.122.011	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	6
201.122.012	Block W, TU 118, L1	L1		7-22 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.123.001	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	4.2
201.123.002	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Modified		1	3.6
201.123.003	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	21
201.123.004	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.6
201.123.005	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	5.2
201.123.006	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	7.8
201.123.007	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Metal	Lead		1	8.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.123.008	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.123.009	Block W, TU 119, L1	L1		0-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.2
201.124.001	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.4
201.124.002	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	7.4
201.124.003	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.5
201.124.004	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Glass	Pharamceutical bottle fragment		1	1.8
201.124.005	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.4
201.124.006	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		8	28.6
201.124.007	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.124.008	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	51.3
201.124.009	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	4
201.124.010	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.5
201.124.011	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	7.4
201.124.012	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Burned		1	0.7
201.124.013	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		4	7
201.124.014	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, UID	Grit	2	3.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.124.015	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.6
201.124.016	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.5
201.124.017	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Organics	Petrified Wood		1	3.7
201.124.018	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Slipware, Trailed		1	0.6
201.124.019	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.124.020	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	3.1
201.124.021	Block W, TU 120, L1	L1		0-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	1.2
201.125.001	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	2.7
201.125.002	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	13.4
201.125.003	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5
201.125.004	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	7.8
201.125.005	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	12.2
201.125.006	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.9
201.125.007	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.7
201.125.008	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Molded		1	1.5
201.125.009	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Tumbler, Polychrome, Handpainted		1	1.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.125.010	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	2.9
201.125.011	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.5
201.125.012	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	5.9
201.125.013	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	3	7.8
201.125.014	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.125.015	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	12
201.125.016	Block W, TU 121, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	6.9
201.126.001	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	8.1
201.126.002	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.7
201.126.003	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	8.1
201.126.004	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	9.9
201.126.005	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.5
201.126.006	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	6.1
201.126.007	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, burned		1	2
201.126.008	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	4.1
201.126.009	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.126.010	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	6.6
201.126.011	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	28.1
201.126.012	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic??	Undecorated Pottery		1	1.1
201.126.013	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.126.014	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	9.8
201.126.015	Block W, TU 122, L1	L1		7-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Fine Sand, Grog	1	2
201.127.001	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	13.5
201.127.002	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	8.1
201.127.003	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	2.7
201.127.004	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.9
201.127.005	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	1.6
201.127.006	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	23.4
201.127.007	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	2.3
201.127.008	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4
201.127.009	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.2
201.127.010	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.127.011	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		1	2
201.127.012	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	12.7
201.127.013	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.8
201.127.014	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.9
201.127.015	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, burned		1	3.2
201.127.016	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	3.9
201.127.017	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.6
201.127.018	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glaze		1	1.3
201.127.019	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	1.4
201.127.020	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.127.021	Block W, TU 123, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	5.9
201.128.001	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	5
201.128.002	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	48.9
201.128.003	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Organics	Shell, oyster		2	3.1
201.128.004	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	14.9
201.128.005	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Lithics	Graver		1	6.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.128.006	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	7.3
201.128.007	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	2	3.7
201.128.008	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.8
201.128.009	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.128.010	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.4
201.128.011	Block W, TU 124, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	12.1
201.129.001	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.2
201.129.002	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	2.5
201.129.003	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	9.4
201.129.004	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		2	1.6
201.129.005	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		3	48.4
201.129.006	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.9
201.129.007	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	13.5
201.129.008	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	8.5
201.129.009	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	6.3
201.129.010	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.129.011	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	2.6
201.129.012	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit, Sand	2	7.1
201.129.013	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.129.014	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Glass, modified		1	1.2
201.129.015	Block W, TU 125, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.2
201.130.001	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	9.5
201.130.002	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	5.4
201.130.003	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.6
201.130.004	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	6.5
201.130.005	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		3	1.1
201.130.006	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	17.6
201.130.007	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		6	15.9
201.130.008	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	2.9
201.130.009	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.8
201.130.010	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Fine Sand, Grog	1	2.1
201.130.011	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Metal	Lead sprue strip		1	5.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.130.012	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.1
201.130.013	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	0.7
201.130.014	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.4
201.130.015	Block W, TU 126, L1	L1		0-17 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.131.001	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	7.9
201.131.002	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1.5
201.131.003	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	4.6
201.131.004	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	15.5
201.131.005	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	3.9
201.131.006	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	4.5
201.131.007	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.5
201.131.008	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Other	Fossiliferous limestone		1	4.3
201.131.009	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	4.9
201.131.010	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Fine Sand, Grog	1	2.1
201.131.011	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	6.7
201.131.012	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	16.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.131.013	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	5.4
201.131.014	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4
201.131.015	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	16.3
201.131.016	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	39.9
201.131.017	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Metal	Cast Iron pot fragment		1	9.9
201.131.018	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	30.7
201.131.019	Block W, TU 127, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.132.001	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.6
201.132.002	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	3.7
201.132.003	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		2	4
201.132.004	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.8
201.132.005	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1.8
201.132.006	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Flat		1	4.2
201.132.007	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	6.3
201.132.008	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	10.6
201.132.009	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	6.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.132.010	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.132.011	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Modified		2	10
201.132.012	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	4.7
201.132.013	Block W, TU 128, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.5
201.133.001	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, Cement		1	113.1
201.133.002	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	4.5
201.133.003	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	3.8
201.133.004	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	5.1
201.133.005	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.3
201.133.006	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	2.5
201.133.007	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	15
201.133.008	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2
201.133.009	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.6
201.133.010	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Glass	Incandescent bulb		1	0.2
201.133.011	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Glass	Indeterminate glass, Molded		1	1.1
201.133.012	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	0.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.133.013	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.4
201.133.014	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.9
201.133.015	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield		1	0.9
201.133.016	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.6
201.133.017	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.7
201.133.018	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Metal	Button, Plain		1	3.9
201.133.019	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Glass	Indeterminate glass		1	2.2
201.133.020	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	38.3
201.133.021	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Molded		1	7.1
201.133.022	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	13.4
201.133.023	Block X, TU 129, L1	L1		6-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.134.001	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		2	4.5
201.134.002	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.4
201.134.003	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	0.9
201.134.004	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	1.4
201.134.005	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	1.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.134.006	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	5.5
201.134.007	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	2.3
201.134.008	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3.8
201.134.009	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		1	4.1
201.134.010	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.2
201.134.011	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	3
201.134.012	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.5
201.134.013	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	
201.134.014	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.7
201.134.015	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	2.6
201.134.016	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		7	14.8
201.134.017	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Metal	Bullet		1	3.2
201.134.018	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	5.6
201.134.019	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		5	23.3
201.134.020	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		17	53.4
201.134.021	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	5.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.134.022	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.134.023	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.3
201.134.024	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, modified		1	2.9
201.134.025	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.5
201.134.026	Block X, TU 130, L1	L1		9-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.6
201.135.001	Block X, TU 131, L1	L1		15-37cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	30.7
201.135.002	Block X, TU 131, L1	L1		15-37cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		2	13.9
201.135.003	Block X, TU 131, L1	L1		15-37cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		3	4.9
201.135.004	Block X, TU 131, L1	L1		15-37cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4.5
201.135.005	Block X, TU 131, L1	L1		15-37cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.6
201.135.006	Block X, TU 131, L1	L1		15-37cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe, rim portion		1	1
201.135.007	Block X, TU 131, L1	L1		15-37cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1
201.135.008	Block X, TU 131, L1	L1		15-37cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.136.001	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	11.1
201.136.002	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Unifacial		1	1.3
201.136.003	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	1.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.136.004	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		3	3.2
201.136.005	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.9
201.136.006	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	4.3
201.136.007	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	27.8
201.136.008	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	6
201.136.009	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Handpainted		1	1
201.136.010	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Molded; Cauliflower motif		1	1.4
201.136.011	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.4
201.136.012	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5
201.136.013	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		8	20.1
201.136.014	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		7	12.7
201.136.015	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		9	41.5
201.136.016	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	16.2
201.136.017	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		2	23.9
201.136.018	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.136.019	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Handpainted and Molded		1	0.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.136.020	Block X, TU 132, L1	L1		8-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.5
201.137.001	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	5.7
201.137.002	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	6.9
201.137.003	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	6.6
201.137.004	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4.6
201.137.005	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		2	4.2
201.137.006	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	4.1
201.137.007	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	1.3
201.137.008	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Handpainted and Molded		1	1.4
201.137.009	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	19.8
201.137.010	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		5	10.2
201.137.011	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		5	12.4
201.137.012	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.137.013	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	1.6
201.137.014	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.8
201.137.015	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	1.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.137.016	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		19	84.5
201.137.017	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.137.018	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	12.5
201.137.019	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	1.4
201.137.020	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Molded		1	2
201.137.021	Block X, TU 133, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4.3
201.138.001	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		4	29
201.138.002	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	8.8
201.138.003	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	16.2
201.138.004	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	15.5
201.138.005	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Metal	Nail, complete, wire		1	14.3
201.138.006	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.9
201.138.007	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.5
201.138.008	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Metal	Lead, Melted		1	25
201.138.009	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	2
201.138.010	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.138.011	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	0.9
201.138.012	Block X, TU 134, L1	L1		8-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	8.4
201.139.001	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	5.7
201.139.002	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.3
201.139.003	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	21.4
201.139.004	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2
201.139.005	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	13.9
201.139.006	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7.4
201.139.007	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.7
201.139.008	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated, Check Stamped	Sand	1	2.3
201.139.009	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	5.4
201.139.010	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	5.5
201.139.011	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	6.9
201.139.012	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.2
201.139.013	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.2
201.139.014	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	3.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.139.015	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.2
201.139.016	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	6
201.139.017	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1
201.139.018	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.4
201.139.019	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	5.7
201.139.020	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.139.021	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.2
201.139.022	Block X, TU 135, L1	L1		3-21 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	1.5
201.140.001	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		16	56.9
201.140.002	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.9
201.140.003	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Ironstone		1	1.6
201.140.004	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	1.2
201.140.005	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.2
201.140.006	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.4
201.140.007	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.2
201.140.008	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.140.009	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.3
201.140.010	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		4	10.5
201.140.011	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Molded		2	2.2
201.140.012	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		15	42.9
201.140.013	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.2
201.140.014	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.8
201.140.015	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Metal	Fishing Weight		1	7.6
201.140.016	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.140.017	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.8
201.140.018	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.9
201.140.019	Block X, TU 136, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.141.001	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	0.5
201.141.002	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		18	65.3
201.141.003	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Ironstone		1	1.6
201.141.004	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	3.5
201.141.005	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.141.006	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	3.4
201.141.007	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.2
201.141.008	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1
201.141.009	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7.5
201.141.010	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Molded		1	1.2
201.141.011	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	9.5
201.141.012	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	37
201.141.013	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.141.014	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		2	2.6
201.141.015	Block X, TU 137, L1	L1		17-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Ironstone		2	4.2
201.142.001	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	6
201.142.002	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	2.2
201.142.003	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		2	2.6
201.142.004	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.8
201.142.005	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.2
201.142.006	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	4.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.142.007	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.1
201.142.008	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	6.1
201.142.009	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	30.7
201.142.010	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.142.011	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		2	7
201.142.012	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	6.4
201.142.013	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Molded		1	1.8
201.142.014	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Metal	Button, Domed		1	0.8
201.142.015	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.7
201.142.016	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1
201.142.017	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.3
201.142.018	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.6
201.142.019	Block X, TU 138, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Utilized flake		1	1.7
201.142.020	TU 138				Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.7
201.143.001	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		11	56.3
201.143.002	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	5.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.143.003	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	4.8
201.143.004	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.9
201.143.005	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	9
201.143.006	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.4
201.143.007	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Handpainted and Molded		1	1.7
201.143.008	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	2.2
201.143.009	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	6.7
201.143.010	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.8
201.143.011	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.2
201.143.012	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	5
201.143.013	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.3
201.143.014	Block X, TU 139, L1	L1		20-42 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.144.001	Block X, TU 140, L1	L1		15-49 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	15.9
201.144.002	Block X, TU 140, L1	L1		15-49 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	4.1
201.144.003	Block X, TU 140, L1	L1		15-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		1	7.2
201.144.004	Block X, TU 140, L1	L1		15-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	3.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.144.005	Block X, TU 140, L1	L1		15-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	10.6
201.144.006	Block X, TU 140, L1	L1		15-49 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.145.001	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		11	36
201.145.002	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Primary		1	2.5
201.145.003	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.2
201.145.004	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Molded		1	4
201.145.005	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Flat		2	3.4
201.145.006	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	12.3
201.145.007	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	4.7
201.145.008	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Plain		1	1
201.145.009	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.9
201.145.010	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		5	8
201.145.011	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	7.2
201.145.012	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	3.1
201.145.013	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	3.6
201.145.014	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		2	4.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.145.015	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.7
201.145.016	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed and trailed		2	19.9
201.145.017	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.145.018	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	3.3
201.145.019	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.5
201.145.020	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	5.7
201.145.021	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.7
201.145.022	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.5
201.145.023	Block U, TU 141, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.8
201.146.001	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Metal	Lead		1	20.3
201.146.002	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		7	16.9
201.146.003	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		2	5.7
201.146.004	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, modified		1	2.3
201.146.005	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.7
201.146.006	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		2	2
201.146.007	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.146.008	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, thinning		1	1.4
201.146.009	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	1.3
201.146.010	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	16
201.146.011	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	4
201.146.012	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	12
201.146.013	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	3.4
201.146.014	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	1.6
201.146.015	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	18.5
201.146.016	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		6	8.4
201.146.017	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.2
201.146.018	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1
201.146.019	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1.6
201.146.020	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		3	3.8
201.146.021	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.5
201.146.022	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Red Filmed	Sand, Grog	1	2.2
201.146.023	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.146.024	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	2.5
201.146.025	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		8	14.3
201.146.026	Block U, TU 142, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.147.001	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		9	23.5
201.147.002	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.147.003	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	15.9
201.147.004	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Unifacial		1	1.8
201.147.005	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, modified		1	3.3
201.147.006	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.6
201.147.007	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	25.4
201.147.008	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat altered		3	9.6
201.147.009	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	5.7
201.147.010	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.147.011	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	1.6
201.147.012	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	4.3
201.147.013	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	3.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.147.014	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1
201.147.015	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.1
201.147.016	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	17.5
201.147.017	Block U, TU 143, L1	L1		2-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	5.6
201.148.001	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		10	32.9
201.148.002	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	17.3
201.148.003	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	9.8
201.148.004	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		2	2.3
201.148.005	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		2	2.9
201.148.006	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	1
201.148.007	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Organics	UID shell		1	1.2
201.148.008	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		6	12.3
201.148.009	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	7.3
201.148.010	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.148.011	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	13.3
201.148.012	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	15.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.148.013	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	4
201.148.014	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	0.2
201.148.015	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.148.016	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	1
201.148.017	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.5
201.148.018	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.4
201.148.019	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	2.8
201.148.020	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	20.6
201.148.021	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead or alkaline glazed		1	3.7
201.148.022	Block U, TU 144, L1	L1		5-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	7.8
201.148.025									
201.149.001	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		4	14.5
201.149.002	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	33.1
201.149.003	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment, Honey flint		1	0.9
201.149.004	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	17.7
201.149.005	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Ironstone		1	1.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.149.006	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.7
201.149.007	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.149.008	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	4.6
201.149.009	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Brushed	Grit, Sand	1	5.6
201.149.010	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	3.2
201.149.011	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, eroded glazed		1	5.6
201.149.012	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	11.1
201.149.013	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1
201.149.014	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.5
201.149.015	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.4
201.149.016	Block Y, TU 145, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	0.8
201.150.001	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	17.9
201.150.002	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		18	83
201.150.003	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.6
201.150.004	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	7.2
201.150.005	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	16.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.150.006	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.9
201.150.007	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		2	13.6
201.150.008	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	2.8
201.150.009	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		5	14.7
201.150.010	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	0.9
201.150.011	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.150.012	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	3.4
201.150.013	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glaze		1	5.4
201.150.014	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.4
201.150.015	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.7
201.150.016	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.3
201.150.017	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	3.4
201.150.018	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Reverse Dotted		1	1.4
201.150.019	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.1
201.150.020	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	2.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.150.021	Block Y, TU 146, L1	L1		2-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	2
201.151.001	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		8	74.8
201.151.002	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	30
201.151.003	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	31.6
201.151.004	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	111.4
201.151.005	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		29	93.5
201.151.006	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	10.8
201.151.007	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.5
201.151.008	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Lithics	Biface		1	6.8
201.151.009	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	1
201.151.010	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	7.1
201.151.011	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass, Plate glass		1	0.7
201.151.012	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.9
201.151.013	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	12.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.151.014	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	5.8
201.151.015	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3
201.151.016	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	0.9
201.151.017	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	3.2
201.151.018	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.7
201.151.019	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	3.1
201.151.020	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	4	9
201.151.021	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	1.9
201.151.022	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		2	1.5
201.151.023	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.9
201.151.024	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Reverse Slipped		2	2.3
201.151.025	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.2
201.151.026	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	0.3
201.151.027	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	0.3
201.151.028	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	0.3
201.151.029	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	0.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.151.030	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	1.2
201.151.031	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1
201.151.032	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	5.1
201.151.033	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	12.5
201.151.034	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.3
201.151.035	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.1
201.151.036	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		1	1.6
201.151.037	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Molded; Cauliflower motif		1	1.4
201.151.038	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	2.2
201.151.039	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	1
201.151.040	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain		1	0.6
201.151.041	Block Y, TU 147, L1	L1		-3 - 19 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.152.001	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		8	26
201.152.002	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		9	81.3
201.152.003	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	5.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.152.004	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	18.1
201.152.005	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.5
201.152.006	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	6.6
201.152.007	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.5
201.152.008	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	3	5.3
201.152.009	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		2	5
201.152.010	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded		3	5.8
201.152.011	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Indeterminate		1	2.6
201.152.012	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	9
201.152.013	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	2.1
201.152.014	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.8
201.152.015	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Brushed	Sand	1	19.5
201.152.016	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand, Grit	1	5.3
201.152.017	Block Y, TU 148, L1	L1		5-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.153.001	F299, 3014.54N, 8151.44E		100.21 m elev		Metal	Gun barrel		1	445.5
201.153.001	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	11

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.153.002	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	3.2
201.153.003	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	6.6
201.153.004	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1.7
201.153.005	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	3.5
201.153.006	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.6
201.153.007	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	10.5
201.153.008	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	12.4
201.153.009	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Whieldon ware		1	1.3
201.153.010	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.7
201.153.011	Block Y, TU 149, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.154.001	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	42.6
201.154.002	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	8
201.154.003	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.1
201.154.004	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.1
201.154.005	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	2.7
201.154.006	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	10.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.154.007	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	8.3
201.154.008	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	4.6
201.154.009	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	0.7
201.154.010	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		4	5.6
201.154.011	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	1.7
201.154.012	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	3.9
201.154.013	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.8
201.154.014	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	9.7
201.154.015	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	14.5
201.154.016	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	9.1
201.154.017	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.9
201.154.018	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Whieldon ware		1	0.8
201.154.019	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.4
201.154.020	Block Y, TU 150, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.155.001	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	6.3
201.155.002	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	36

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.155.003	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		7	35.5
201.155.004	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		13	40.8
201.155.005	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		9	34.8
201.155.006	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	13.3
201.155.007	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat altered		1	2.2
201.155.008	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Melted		1	3.3
201.155.009	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	8
201.155.010	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.3
201.155.011	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	6.7
201.155.012	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		14	21.5
201.155.013	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		15	24.7
201.155.014	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		2	6.1
201.155.015	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	1	1.9
201.155.016	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	2.2
201.155.017	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trilled		1	1
201.155.018	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.155.019	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.8
201.155.020	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.4
201.155.021	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trilled		2	9.5
201.155.022	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd		,			
201.155.023	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Reverse Trilled		2	5.7
201.155.024	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Plain		1	0.2
201.155.025	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	2.5
201.155.026	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Handpainted		1	0.6
201.155.027	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Burned		1	0.4
201.155.028	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.6
201.155.029	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Chattahoochee Brushed Pottery	Sand	2	3.9
201.155.030	Block Y, TU 151, L1	L1		4-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.156.001	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	18.3
201.156.002	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		15	76.1
201.156.003	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		2	1.6
201.156.004	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	6.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.156.005	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	3.2
201.156.006	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.5
201.156.007	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.2
201.156.008	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	0.9
201.156.009	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	4.2
201.156.010	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	2.4
201.156.011	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.6
201.156.012	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	3.9
201.156.013	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.7
201.156.014	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	6.8
201.156.015	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	2.5
201.156.016	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		3	6.7
201.156.017	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.8
201.156.018	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	0.6
201.156.019	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	0.5
201.156.020	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Metal	Lead, melted		1	15.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.156.021	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.4
201.156.022	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.6
201.156.023	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.9
201.156.024	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Reverse Dotted		1	1.8
201.156.025	Block Y, TU 152, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.157.001	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	17.3
201.157.002	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		2	0.7
201.157.003	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	11.5
201.157.004	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.4
201.157.005	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	11.3
201.157.006	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	40.8
201.157.007	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	9.7
201.157.008	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.9
201.157.009	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	8.4
201.157.010	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	1
201.157.011	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	1.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.157.012	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		4	7.9
201.157.013	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	10.6
201.157.014	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	7.7
201.157.015	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	4.2
201.157.016	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Molded		1	1.8
201.157.017	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	1	1.9
201.157.018	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	1.5
201.157.019	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	1.7
201.157.020	Block Y, TU 153, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.158.001	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	13.4
201.158.002	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.9
201.158.003	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	13.2
201.158.004	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.1
201.158.005	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.4
201.158.006	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.1
201.158.007	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	0.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.158.008	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	4
201.158.009	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	4.8
201.158.010	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		2	3.2
201.158.011	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic??	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.9
201.158.012	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1.6
201.158.013	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware		1	1.5
201.158.014	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.4
201.158.015	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.2
201.158.016	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.6
201.158.017	Block Y, TU 154, L1	L1		4-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.159.001	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Metal	Counterfeit British Halfpiece		1	6.9
201.159.002	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	52.3
201.159.003	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		17	79.8
201.159.004	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	1.6
201.159.005	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.1
201.159.006	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		3	7.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.159.007	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	2.7
201.159.008	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		3	8.6
201.159.009	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.6
201.159.010	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	6.2
201.159.011	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.5
201.159.012	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	2.5
201.159.013	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.4
201.159.014	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.5
201.159.015	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	1.3
201.159.016	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		3	5.2
201.159.017	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2
201.159.018	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Reverse Trailed		2	5.5
201.159.019	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded glaze		1	0.6
201.159.020	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.4
201.159.021	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	6.4
201.159.022	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	4.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.159.023	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.9
201.159.024	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.159.025	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	3.2
201.159.026	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	12.1
201.159.027	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	9
201.159.028	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.159.029	Block Y, TU 155, L1	L1		0-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.1
201.160.*	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Metal	Flat pewter scrap		1	0.9
201.160.001	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	228.8
201.160.002	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		27	102.5
201.160.003	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	54.2
201.160.004	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	0.9
201.160.005	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick		1	708
201.160.006	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		9	42.6
201.160.007	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		3	9.7
201.160.008	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick		2	16.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.160.009	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		2	4.3
201.160.010	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	2.5
201.160.011	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Reverse Trailed		2	6.9
201.160.012	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.9
201.160.013	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.3
201.160.014	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1
201.160.015	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1
201.160.016	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	2.2
201.160.017	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.5
201.160.018	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		7	12.8
201.160.019	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4
201.160.020	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.9
201.160.021	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.7
201.160.022	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.5
201.160.023	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2
201.160.024	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.160.025	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.2
201.160.026	Block Y, TU 156, L1	L1		0-26 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1.3
201.161.001	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	52.5
201.161.002	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	61.6
201.161.003	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		7	23.1
201.161.004	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	18.5
201.161.005	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2
201.161.006	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		2	5.2
201.161.007	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		3	4
201.161.008	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	8
201.161.009	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Organics	Gastropod, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	2.5
201.161.010	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Organics	Bark		1	0.3
201.161.011	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	4.6
201.161.012	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		7	15.6
201.161.013	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	4.2
201.161.014	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	10.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.161.015	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	0.5
201.161.016	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1.4
201.161.017	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	1.1
201.161.018	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2
201.161.019	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	1.3
201.161.020	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	0.6
201.161.021	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		4	5.5
201.161.022	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.5
201.161.023	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Chattahoochee Brushed Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	10.6
201.161.024	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	1
201.161.025	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Unifacial		1	0.5
201.161.026	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.161.027	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.1
201.162.001	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		13	45.8
201.162.002	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	43.7
201.162.003	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.162.004	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.9
201.162.005	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.7
201.162.006	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Chunk/Shatter		1	2.7
201.162.007	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Unifacial		1	0.9
201.162.008	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.6
201.162.009	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	6.3
201.162.010	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		4	12.8
201.162.011	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	1.7
201.162.012	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	9.2
201.162.013	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.9
201.162.014	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.3
201.162.015	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	1.2
201.162.016	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.5
201.162.017	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield		1	1.2
201.162.018	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	0.6
201.162.019	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.162.020	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.2
201.162.021	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1
201.162.022	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1			Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	2.5
201.162.023	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1			Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	2.3
201.162.024	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1			Lithics	Gunflint		1	0.6
201.162.025	Block Y, TU 158, L1	L1		0-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub		1	0.6
201.163.001	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	27.8
201.163.002	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		25	96.6
201.163.003	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.8
201.163.004	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat altered		1	2.4
201.163.005	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		3	11
201.163.006	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		9	19.1
201.163.007	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2
201.163.008	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.5
201.163.009	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	7.3
201.163.010	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	13.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.163.011	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	1.9
201.163.012	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.7
201.163.013	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1.8
201.163.014	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.2
201.163.015	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1
201.163.016	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	1.4
201.163.017	Block Y, TU 159, L1	L1		-5-18 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.164.001	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		30	152.5
201.164.002	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Metal	Spike or nail, unidentified		2	129.3
201.164.003	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		8	55.6
201.164.004	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	3.3
201.164.005	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	1.5
201.164.006	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	2
201.164.007	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Melted		1	1.3
201.164.008	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	6.7
201.164.009	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.164.010	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.9
201.164.011	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		1	3.8
201.164.012	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	5.1
201.164.013	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	6.9
201.164.014	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.1
201.164.015	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Incised	Sand, clay	1	1.3
201.164.016	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	3.4
201.164.017	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	0.7
201.164.018	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1
201.164.019	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	10.3
201.164.020	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Staffordshire		1	0.8
201.164.021	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	3.6
201.164.022	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Plain		1	0.9
201.164.023	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Organics	Bone, unidentified, Unidentifiable Fragment		14	13.2
201.164.024	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.164.025	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.8
201.164.026	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	5
201.164.027	Block Y, TU 160, L1	L1		0-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.165.001	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	2.7
201.165.002	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.2
201.165.003	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		2	0.3
201.165.004	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Molded		1	4
201.165.005	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.8
201.165.006	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.2
201.165.007	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Pinched	Sand	1	2.9
201.165.008	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	3.2
201.165.009	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic??	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	2.3
201.165.010	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.1
201.165.011	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish White		2	1.9
201.165.012	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.9
201.165.025	Block Y, TU 157, L1	L1			Lithics	Flake fragment		1	0.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.165.028	Block Z, TU 161, L1	L1		45-61 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.166.001	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	27.7
201.166.002	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	3.5
201.166.003	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	24.3
201.166.004	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	13.2
201.166.005	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.3
201.166.006	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Cord Marked Pottery	Grit	1	8.3
201.166.007	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	4.2
201.166.008	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.6
201.166.009	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	4	8.4
201.166.010	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.9
201.166.011	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	0.6
201.166.012	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	4
201.166.013	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.8
201.166.014	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2
201.166.015	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.166.016	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	8.1
201.166.017	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.4
201.166.018	Block Z, TU 162, L1	L1		42-66 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.167.001	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	13.8
201.167.002	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	9.3
201.167.003	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Organics	Wood		2	24.6
201.167.004	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Lithics	Shatter		1	1.2
201.167.005	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Lithics	Shatter		1	2.1
201.167.006	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1.2
201.167.007	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	13.1
201.167.008	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	13.9
201.167.009	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	25.7
201.167.010	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	2.2
201.167.011	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Mission Red Pottery	Sand	1	3.6
201.167.012	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	3.1
201.167.013	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	6.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.167.014	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	5.8
201.167.015	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	7.1
201.167.016	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	4.1
201.167.017	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	2.4
201.167.018	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	3.7
201.167.019	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	3.1
201.167.020	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.167.021	Block Z, TU 163, L1	L1		20-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.1
201.168.001	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	6.6
201.168.002	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Metal	Buckle		1	4.6
201.168.003	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.8
201.168.004	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	9.3
201.168.005	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.1
201.168.006	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit, Sand	1	3.3
201.168.007	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	4.8
201.168.008	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	4.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.168.009	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	2.9
201.168.010	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain		1	1.1
201.168.011	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		7	24.8
201.168.012	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub	Fiber	1	1.9
201.168.013	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.2
201.168.014	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord Marked	Grit, Sand	1	8.7
201.168.015	Block Z, TU 164, L1	L1		-21-45 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.169.001	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	10.7
201.169.002	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	3.2
201.169.003	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	1.5
201.169.004	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1.1
201.169.005	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Molded		1	3.2
201.169.006	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.8
201.169.007	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	5.3
201.169.008	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.8
201.169.009	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat altered		1	1.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.169.010	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Lithics	Savannah River Stemmed PPK		1	1.9
201.169.011	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.2
201.169.012	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	7.9
201.169.013	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.8
201.169.014	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3
201.169.015	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	0.6
201.169.016	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	0.9
201.169.017	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	5.6
201.169.018	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		59	201.8
201.169.019	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	1.8
201.169.020	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.9
201.169.021	Block Z, TU 165, L1	L1		9-19 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.170.001	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	4.8
201.170.002	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		7	30.6
201.170.003	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	35.2
201.170.004	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.170.005	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	2
201.170.006	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3.3
201.170.007	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	5.9
201.170.008	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.4
201.170.009	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	6.9
201.170.010	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.6
201.170.011	Block Z, TU 166, L1	L1		5-18 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.171.001	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	108.2
201.171.002	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	4.7
201.171.003	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.7
201.171.004	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	0.6
201.171.005	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	17.9
201.171.006	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	2.1
201.171.007	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	15.8
201.171.008	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.7
201.171.009	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	10.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.171.010	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Cord Marked Pottery	Grit	1	2.4
201.171.011	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.2
201.171.012	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	13
201.171.013	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Turpentine Cup, Herty		1	3.7
201.171.014	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Nottingham		1	0.5
201.171.015	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	1.7
201.171.016	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.5
201.171.017	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	6.7
201.171.018	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.2
201.171.019	Block Z, TU 167, L1	L1		44-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.172.001	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	14.5
201.172.002	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	8.3
201.172.003	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	2	6
201.172.004	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	4.8
201.172.005	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	1.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.172.006	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Polychrome Handpainted		1	0.5
201.172.007	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	2.6
201.172.008	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	2.5
201.172.009	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.1
201.172.010	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.172.011	Block Z, TU 168, L1	L1		43-63 cmbd	Historic Ceramic			1	0.5
201.173.001	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	17.4
201.173.002	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	12.1
201.173.003	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.4
201.173.004	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	9.4
201.173.005	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.2
201.173.006	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	3.7
201.173.007	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.9
201.173.008	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.173.009	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		2	0.5
201.173.010	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Other	Rubber, Bumper		1	1.6
201.173.011	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord Marked	Clay, Sand	1	13.5
201.173.012	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	8.7
201.173.013	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.8
201.173.014	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.2
201.173.015	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.9
201.173.016	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Complicated Stamped	Sand	1	0.9
201.173.017	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		2	6.6
201.173.018	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	4.3
201.173.019	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.9
201.173.020	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Manganese Mottled, Lead glazed		1	2.6
201.173.021	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.173.022	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord Marked	Grit	1	2.1
201.173.023	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.173.024	Block Z, TU 169, L1	L1		20-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, eroded		1	1.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.174.*	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	
201.174.*	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Edgeware		1	
201.174.001	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	20.5
201.174.003	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	8.2
201.174.004	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	0.7
201.174.005	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.7
201.174.006	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2
201.174.007	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	9.8
201.174.008	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	4.8
201.174.009	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	4.3
201.174.010	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		5	8
201.174.011	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.5
201.174.012	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	3.2
201.174.013	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	6.4
201.174.014	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glaze		1	3.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.174.015	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	17
201.174.016	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2
201.174.017	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	3.6
201.174.018	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	2.1
201.174.019	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.4
201.174.020	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Handpainted		1	4.8
201.174.021	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4
201.174.022	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.1
201.174.023	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.174.024	Block Z, TU 170, L1	L1		25-52 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Melted		1	1.1
201.175.001	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Metal	Lead, melted		1	2.7
201.175.002	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	26.9
201.175.003	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Organics	Wood		1	1.4
201.175.004	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	33.8
201.175.005	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		70	327.7
201.175.006	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		1	4.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.175.007	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	4.8
201.175.008	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Etched and molded		1	0.7
201.175.009	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.7
201.175.010	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.2
201.175.011	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Lithics	Biface fragment		1	1.8
201.175.012	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.8
201.175.013	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	4.2
201.175.014	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.6
201.175.015	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	19.7
201.175.016	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	2.3
201.175.017	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.5
201.175.018	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	1.8
201.175.019	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2
201.175.020	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.175.021	Block Z, TU 171, L1	L1		6-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.3
201.176.001	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	30.4
201.176.002	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	3.3
201.176.003	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	5.2
201.176.004	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	14.1
201.176.005	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Organics	Bark		1	3.2
201.176.006	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.176.007	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1.6
201.176.008	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	10.2
201.176.009	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	6.3
201.176.010	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	3.5
201.176.011	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	6.4
201.176.012	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.5
201.176.013	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		1	10.4
201.176.014	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	6.8
201.176.015	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.176.016	Block Z, TU 172, L1	L1		1-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.177.001	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		8	21.4
201.177.002	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	6.2
201.177.003	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	7.8
201.177.004	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	28.8
201.177.005	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	19
201.177.006	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	4.9
201.177.007	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	2
201.177.008	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.5
201.177.009	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4.4
201.177.010	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	8.8
201.177.011	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3
201.177.012	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	3
201.177.013	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		2	2.8
201.177.014	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	6.6
201.177.015	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	0.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.177.016	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.177.017	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.1
201.177.018	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.2
201.177.019	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Savannah/St. Catherines Fine Cord Marked	Sand, Grit	1	5.2
201.177.020	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Savannah/St. Catherines Fine Cord Marked	Sand	1	5.8
201.177.021	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Lithics	Shatter		1	9
201.177.022	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.5
201.177.023	Block Z, TU 173, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.178.001	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	8.1
201.178.002	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	3.1
201.178.003	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Cord Marked Pottery	Clay, Sand	2	4.4
201.178.004	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	2.6
201.178.005	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	3.8
201.178.006	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.8
201.178.007	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Ironstone		1	1.8
201.178.008	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.178.009	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.8
201.178.010	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.8
201.178.011	Block Z, TU 174, L1	L1		45-62 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.179.001	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	4
201.179.002	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	26.3
201.179.003	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	20
201.179.004	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		2	4
201.179.005	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		6	31.6
201.179.006	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Organics	Wood, Petrified		1	4.4
201.179.007	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	18.9
201.179.008	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	2.8
201.179.009	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit, Sand	1	4.1
201.179.010	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.7
201.179.011	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	1.3
201.179.012	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	5.1
201.179.013	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.179.014	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1
201.179.015	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.179.016	Block Z, TU 175, L1	L1		15-53 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.5
201.180.001	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	11.6
201.180.002	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	18.2
201.180.003	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	5.8
201.180.004	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	2.6
201.180.005	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	22
201.180.006	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		12	66.3
201.180.007	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	14.7
201.180.008	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	2.7
201.180.009	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	3	18.1
201.180.010	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand, Grit	2	5.8
201.180.011	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	4.8
201.180.012	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	4.5
201.180.013	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	4.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.180.014	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3.9
201.180.015	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.7
201.180.016	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	5.6
201.180.017	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	0.7
201.180.018	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	0.8
201.180.019	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.2
201.180.020	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.7
201.180.021	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.7
201.180.022	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick, indeterminate		1	116.9
201.180.023	Block Z, TU 176, L1	L1		4-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.181.001	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Metal	Button, Domed		1	2.2
201.181.002	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Metal	Thimble		1	5.9
201.181.003	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		2	1.4
201.181.004	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		10	241.6
201.181.005	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		15	65.7
201.181.006	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		34	85.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.181.007	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub, Burned		23	71.7
201.181.008	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	11.4
201.181.009	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	6.4
201.181.010	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.3
201.181.011	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	0.8
201.181.012	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.8
201.181.013	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	1
201.181.014	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Wilmington Cord Marked Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	13.6
201.181.015	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	6.4
201.181.016	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	6.5
201.181.017	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	5.4
201.181.018	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	7.3
201.181.019	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	3.5
201.181.020	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.7
201.181.021	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	7.6
201.181.022	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	2.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.181.023	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Indeterminate		1	0.9
201.181.024	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	6.2
201.181.025	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.3
201.181.026	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.181.027	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.5
201.181.028	Block Z, TU 177, L1	L1		3-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	1.9
201.182.001	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		63	300.6
201.182.002	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Organics	Wood, Petrified		1	51.9
201.182.003	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	28.7
201.182.004	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	49.9
201.182.005	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Lithics	Granite		1	8.1
201.182.006	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.7
201.182.007	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Lithics	PPK, Distal end		1	2.5
201.182.008	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	55.8
201.182.009	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	11.3
201.182.010	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	6.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.182.011	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.3
201.182.012	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.7
201.182.013	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.4
201.182.014	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.182.015	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	4.6
201.182.016	Block Z, TU 178, L1	L1		3-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		4	18.6
201.183.001	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	14.4
201.183.002	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	2.7
201.183.003	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	14.3
201.183.004	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	5.6
201.183.005	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.7
201.183.006	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.8
201.183.007	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield		1	1.5
201.183.008	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.9
201.183.009	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	23.6
201.183.010	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	3.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.183.011	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.5
201.183.012	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.3
201.183.013	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	6.6
201.183.014	Block Y, TU 179, L1	L1		2-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.184.001	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		14	94.9
201.184.002	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	16.1
201.184.003	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	10.2
201.184.004	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.8
201.184.005	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	6.2
201.184.006	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2
201.184.007	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	16.7
201.184.008	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Metal	Lead, Strip		1	3
201.184.009	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		3	6.8
201.184.010	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	1.7
201.184.011	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	0.8
201.184.012	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.184.013	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	10.2
201.184.014	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.5
201.184.015	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.9
201.184.016	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3
201.184.017	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1
201.184.018	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.184.019	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.4
201.184.020	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.1
201.184.021	Block Y, TU 180, L1	L1		3-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.185.*	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Metal	Gunflint fragment		1	
201.185.*	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	
201.185.*	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Metal	Buckle		1	2.8
201.185.*	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Polychrome Handpainted		1	
201.185.001	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Utilized		1	1.6
201.185.002	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		4	43.3
201.185.003	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	4.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.185.004	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	14.6
201.185.005	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	11.4
201.185.006	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.2
201.185.007	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.8
201.185.008	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	3.8
201.185.009	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Other	Concretion		1	3.1
201.185.010	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1
201.185.011	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1.8
201.185.012	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3
201.185.013	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	14.1
201.185.014	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	9.8
201.185.015	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	7.2
201.185.016	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.9
201.185.017	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.6
201.185.018	Block AA, TU 181, L1	L1		25-50 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.186.001	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		4	8.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.186.002	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	24.2
201.186.003	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	21.1
201.186.004	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	10.7
201.186.005	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		8	19.3
201.186.006	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	3.4
201.186.007	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, unglazed		1	1.2
201.186.008	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.1
201.186.009	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	4
201.186.010	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Handpainted Polychrome		1	1.2
201.186.011	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Transfer-printed		1	2.9
201.186.012	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.5
201.186.013	Block AA, TU 182, L1	L1		33-50 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.187.001	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Organics	Resin		2	0.8
201.187.002	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.6
201.187.003	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.2
201.187.004	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		2	0.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.187.005	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	29.1
201.187.006	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	30.3
201.187.007	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		4	57.5
201.187.008	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	10.6
201.187.009	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.2
201.187.010	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	15
201.187.011	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.9
201.187.012	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	8.3
201.187.013	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	7.1
201.187.014	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	5.8
201.187.015	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Unglazed		1	5.7
201.187.016	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		4	13.6
201.187.017	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	4.3
201.187.018	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.1
201.187.019	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	4.7
201.187.020	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.187.021	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.187.022	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.9
201.187.023	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	11.3
201.187.024	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		2	1.8
201.187.025	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.187.026	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.1
201.187.027	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.9
201.187.028	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Node	Sand	1	7.6
201.187.029	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	7.6
201.187.030	Block AA, TU 183, L1	L1		25-49 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.188.001	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Metal	Buckle		1	2.7
201.188.002	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	20.5
201.188.003	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Metal	Lead, Melted		1	5.1
201.188.004	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.4
201.188.005	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	169.6
201.188.006	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.188.007	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	18.5
201.188.008	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Modified		1	8
201.188.009	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.9
201.188.010	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	36
201.188.011	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		4	1.7
201.188.012	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		8	39.4
201.188.013	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	11.4
201.188.014	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	13.8
201.188.015	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		6	18.9
201.188.016	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.1
201.188.017	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit, Sand	1	1.6
201.188.018	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.2
201.188.019	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	0.3
201.188.020	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Transfer-printed		2	2.7
201.188.021	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		2	2.3
201.188.022	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.188.023	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.8
201.188.024	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.7
201.188.025	Block AA, TU 184, L1	L1		3-26 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.189.001	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Metal	Trigger guard		1	13
201.189.002	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	54.7
201.189.003	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	12.1
201.189.004	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	19
201.189.005	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	22.6
201.189.006	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		7	21.3
201.189.007	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.5
201.189.008	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Debitage		1	1.3
201.189.009	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.7
201.189.010	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.4
201.189.011	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	13
201.189.012	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	17.5
201.189.013	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	8.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.189.014	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	St. Catherine's Plain Pottery	Sand, Grog	1	2.7
201.189.015	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	4.1
201.189.016	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3
201.189.017	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.7
201.189.018	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.4
201.189.019	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Annularware, Lead glazed		2	1.2
201.189.020	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	5.6
201.189.021	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1
201.189.022	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Annularware, Lead glazed		1	2.2
201.189.023	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.5
201.189.024	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.3
201.189.025	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.4
201.189.026	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1			Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.2
201.189.027	Block AA, TU 185, L1	L1		24-50 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.189.028					Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	4.8
201.190.001	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	8.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.190.002	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		11	35.8
201.190.003	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		8	50.9
201.190.004	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.7
201.190.005	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	23.9
201.190.006	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		2	4.4
201.190.007	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.5
201.190.008	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	8.1
201.190.009	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	3.7
201.190.010	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.7
201.190.011	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Mission Red Pottery	Sand	1	3.2
201.190.012	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	2	2.6
201.190.013	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.6
201.190.014	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded glaze		1	1.7
201.190.015	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	1.2
201.190.016	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.8
201.190.017	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, trailed		1	2.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.190.018	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Manganese Mottled, Lead glazed		1	2.6
201.190.019	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Molded		1	1.4
201.190.020	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.5
201.190.021	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.1
201.190.022	Block AA, TU 186, L1	L1		2-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.191.*	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield		1	
201.191.001	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	11.1
201.191.002	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	10.5
201.191.003	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.2
201.191.004	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		9	53.1
201.191.005	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	1.2
201.191.006	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	23.4
201.191.007	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, grit	3	9.3
201.191.008	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	3.6
201.191.009	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	2.7
201.191.010	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, lead glazed		1	3.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.191.011	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1			Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.1
201.191.012	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.2
201.191.013	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.3
201.191.014	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	0.9
201.191.015	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3
201.191.016	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.1
201.191.017	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	14.8
201.191.018	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.7
201.191.019	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.1
201.191.020	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2
201.191.021	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.191.022	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.7
201.191.023	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Organics	Shell, oyster		1	1.9
201.191.024	Block AB, TU 187, L1	L1		30-40 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.192.001	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	15.1
201.192.002	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	12.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.192.003	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	13.1
201.192.004	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7
201.192.005	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	9.7
201.192.006	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		4	38.7
201.192.007	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.1
201.192.008	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	2
201.192.009	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	3.2
201.192.010	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	1.3
201.192.011	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, UID stamped	Sand, Grit	1	1.6
201.192.012	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.5
201.192.013	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.7
201.192.014	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Ironstone		2	2.4
201.192.015	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.1
201.192.016	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3
201.192.017	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.5
201.192.018	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	sand	1	2.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.192.019	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Savannah Fine Cord Marked Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	7.9
201.192.020	Block AB, TU 188, L1	L1		33-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.192.021					Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4
201.193.001	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	5.7
201.193.002	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	15.8
201.193.003	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.8
201.193.004	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	4.3
201.193.005	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	9.9
201.193.006	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Check Stamped Pottery	Grit	1	3
201.193.007	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Incised	Sand	1	2.1
201.193.008	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Plain		1	19.6
201.193.009	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.4
201.193.010	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	6.5
201.193.011	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	4	5.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.193.012	Block AB, TU 189, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.194.001	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	4.8
201.194.002	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	12.7
201.194.003	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.7
201.194.004	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.4
201.194.005	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Lithics	Biface fragment		1	2.9
201.194.006	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Lithics	Shatter		1	1.2
201.194.007	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	34
201.194.008	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	7.6
201.194.009	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	16.2
201.194.010	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	1.3
201.194.011	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	1.7
201.194.012	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	2.4
201.194.013	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	9.8
201.194.014	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.194.015	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	9.2
201.194.016	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	8.7
201.194.017	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.6
201.194.018	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	0.9
201.194.019	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.2
201.194.020	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.1
201.194.021	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	3.8
201.194.022	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand, Grit	1	1.4
201.194.023	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.194.024	Block AB, TU 190, L1	L1		28-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1
201.195.*	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	
201.195.001	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	17.2
201.195.002	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	26
201.195.003	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.3
201.195.004	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	7.8
201.195.005	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	5.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.195.006	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord marked	Grit	1	7.1
201.195.007	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.2
201.195.008	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	5.7
201.195.009	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic		Sand	1	2.8
201.195.010	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	3.1
201.195.011	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	10
201.195.012	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	2.1
201.195.013	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	1.6
201.195.014	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1.2
201.195.015	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1
201.195.016	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.8
201.195.017	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.195.018	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Ironstone, Molded		1	1.7
201.195.019	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	5.7
201.195.020	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.9
201.195.021	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.195.022	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.195.023	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.195.024	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1			Lithics	Modified gunflint		2	4.6
201.196.*	Block AB, TU 191, L1	L1		34-43 cmbd	Metal	Button		1	
201.196.001	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	46.9
201.196.002	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	Buckle		1	57
201.196.003	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	28.6
201.196.004	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	7.2
201.196.005	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	2.2
201.196.006	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	Wire		1	27.2
201.196.007	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	1.2
201.196.008	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Organics	Paper fragment		1	0.8
201.196.009	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Organics	Wood		1	
201.196.010	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Other	Shotgun Shell cap		1	2.3
201.196.011	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	6.3
201.196.012	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	1.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.196.013	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		2	5.9
201.196.014	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	3.7
201.196.015	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	5.6
201.196.016	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	10.9
201.196.017	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		1	0.4
201.196.018	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.196.019	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.3
201.196.020	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.7
201.196.021	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.196.022	Block AB, TU 192, L1	L1			Lithics	Gunflint		2	2.6
201.197.001	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Metal	UID iron, Flat		1	15.9
201.197.002	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		12	64.8
201.197.003	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Metal	Lead strip		1	10.2
201.197.004	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.3
201.197.005	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	85
201.197.006	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	11.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.197.007	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		8	32.7
201.197.008	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	12.1
201.197.009	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Unglazed	Sand, Grog	1	4.5
201.197.010	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Check Stamped Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	5.1
201.197.011	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Indeterminate Stamped	Sand	1	3.9
201.197.012	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	1	9.4
201.197.013	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Wilmington Plain Pottery	Sand, Clay	1	9.9
201.197.014	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded glaze		1	5.5
201.197.015	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	4.8
201.197.016	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	1.5
201.197.017	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	5.7
201.197.018	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		2	2.5
201.197.019	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.8
201.197.020	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	0.7
201.197.021	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.7
201.197.022	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic			1	1.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.197.023	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.2
201.197.024	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.5
201.197.025	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.3
201.197.026	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.9
201.197.027	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Check Stamped Pottery	sand, clay	1	4.2
201.197.028	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.197.029	Block AB, TU 193, L1	L1		8-45 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	2.3
201.198.001	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	39.6
201.198.002	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	21.6
201.198.003	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.8
201.198.004	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	12.7
201.198.005	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	9.7
201.198.006	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	17.3
201.198.007	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.5
201.198.008	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Wilmington Plain Pottery	Sand, Clay	1	7.2
201.198.009	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	3.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.198.010	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		1	4.2
201.198.011	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	3.8
201.198.012	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	2
201.198.013	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.2
201.198.014	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.3
201.198.015	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.1
201.198.016	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.9
201.198.017	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	0.6
201.198.018	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.4
201.198.019	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	4.9
201.198.020	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	9
201.198.021	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	3.6
201.198.022	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	sand	2	6.6
201.198.023	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Savannah Burnished Plain Pottery	Sand	1	2.9
201.198.024	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.198.025	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.198.026	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.7
201.198.027	Block AB, TU 194, L1	L1		25-46 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		3	5.7
201.199.001	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Organics	Nut shell		1	1
201.199.002	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	1.1
201.199.003	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	10.4
201.199.004	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	11.4
201.199.005	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	2.9
201.199.006	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	39.3
201.199.007	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		19	50.5
201.199.008	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		8	35.7
201.199.009	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		5	14.5
201.199.010	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	5	20.7
201.199.011	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.1
201.199.012	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	2.9
201.199.013	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	8	15.4
201.199.014	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Red Filmed	Sand, Grog	2	5.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.199.015	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.5
201.199.016	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.6
201.199.017	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.9
201.199.018	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2
201.199.019	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		2	1.9
201.199.020	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.7
201.199.021	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	0.8
201.199.022	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.3
201.199.023	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.3
201.199.024	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	5.4
201.199.025	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	5
201.199.026	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord marked		1	1.9
201.199.027	Block AB, TU 195, L1	L1		2-18 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.200.001	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Lithics	Biface fragment		1	2.8
201.200.002	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.5
201.200.003	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		3	9.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.200.004	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Glass	Container glass		3	4
201.200.005	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	0.9
201.200.006	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	23.8
201.200.007	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	0.9
201.200.008	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit, Sand	4	8.2
201.200.009	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Ceramics	Fired clay		3	3.7
201.200.010	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Historic Ceramic	Redware, lead glaze		1	4.9
201.200.011	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.4
201.200.012	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.5
201.200.013	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.6
201.200.014	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	3
201.200.015	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		7	13.5
201.200.016	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.4
201.200.017	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.8
201.200.018	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.200.019	Block AB, TU 196, L1	L1		-1-17	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.201.001	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Lithics	Shatter		1	3.4
201.201.002	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	1.6
201.201.003	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		2	6.5
201.201.004	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.3
201.201.005	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.1
201.201.006	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	4.3
201.201.007	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		4	49
201.201.008	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	17.3
201.201.009	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		5	9.2
201.201.010	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	6.7
201.201.011	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	2	6.2
201.201.012	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Eroded glaze		2	7.4
201.201.013	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	6
201.201.014	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	2.3
201.201.015	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Brushed	Grit	1	2.3
201.201.016	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Brown		1	2.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.201.017	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	1.9
201.201.018	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.1
201.201.019	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Whiteware, Lead glazed		1	0.5
201.201.020	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	0.4
201.201.021	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	2.7
201.201.022	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		5	7.1
201.201.023	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.201.024	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.9
201.201.025	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.5
201.201.026	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Lithics	Shatter		2	2.4
201.201.027	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint, fragment		1	0.8
201.201.028	Block AB, TU 197, L1	L1		7-21 cmbd	Glass	Glass fragment, Possibly modified		1	
201.202.001	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	27.8
201.202.002	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	12.5
201.202.003	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	8.8
201.202.004	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	3.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.202.005	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.1
201.202.006	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Dunlap Fabric Marked	Grit, Sand	1	10
201.202.007	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, eroded		1	2.8
201.202.008	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	3.1
201.202.009	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	2	4.3
201.202.010	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Clay	1	5.7
201.202.011	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	2.8
201.202.012	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	3.3
201.202.013	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3
201.202.014	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.2
201.202.015	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1
201.202.016	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.5
201.202.017	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic			1	0.7
201.202.018	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.5
201.202.019	Block AB, TU 198, L1	L1		7-20 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.203.001	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		12	102.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.203.002	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	17.4
201.203.003	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	4.8
201.203.004	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.9
201.203.005	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1
201.203.006	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	28.7
201.203.007	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		7	41.6
201.203.008	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Ceramics	Clay		1	32.2
201.203.009	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Eroded Fabric or Cord Marked	Grit, Sand	1	2.9
201.203.010	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.4
201.203.011	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.5
201.203.012	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, lead glaze		1	2
201.203.013	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Indeterminate design		1	0.8
201.203.014	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	3.1
201.203.015	Block AB, TU 199, L1	L1		5-22 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.204.001	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Lithics	Biface fragment		1	4.6
201.204.002	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	1.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.204.003	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	27.1
201.204.004	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	1.4
201.204.005	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.4
201.204.006	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.1
201.204.007	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	10.5
201.204.008	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		8	27.2
201.204.009	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand, Grit	4	12.8
201.204.010	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	5.6
201.204.011	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.9
201.204.012	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	3.7
201.204.013	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		2	9.7
201.204.014	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	3.8
201.204.015	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	3.9
201.204.016	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.5
201.204.017	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.3
201.204.018	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.204.019	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.3
201.204.020	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.204.021	Block AB, TU 200, L1	L1		4-20 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord Marked	Grit	1	3.3
201.205.001	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	3.8
201.205.002	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		3	51.5
201.205.003	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	Lead, Melted, Scratched		1	16.2
201.205.004	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	18.2
201.205.005	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Metal	Spike head, Wrought		1	94
201.205.006	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	14.6
201.205.007	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	4.3
201.205.008	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Indeterminate Stamped	Sand	1	5.4
201.205.009	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Incised	Sand	1	3.5
201.205.010	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		2	3.9
201.205.011	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Whiteware, Lead glazed		1	
201.205.012	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.4
201.205.013	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.205.014	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		2	14.7
201.205.015	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.205.016	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	8.4
201.205.017	Block AB, TU 201, L1	L1		5-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.206.001	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		2	20
201.206.002	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	4.3
201.206.003	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	31.5
201.206.004	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	24.6
201.206.005	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		3	21.3
201.206.006	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	7.5
201.206.007	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.4
201.206.008	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield, Lead glazed		1	7.4
201.206.009	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.9
201.206.010	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.9
201.206.011	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Whiteware		1	1.6
201.206.012	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	English soft-paste Porcelain		1	1.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.206.013	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.1
201.206.014	Block AA, TU 202, L1	L1		6-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.207.001	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.7
201.207.002	Block AA, TU 203, L2	L2		18-44 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		5	15.5
201.207.003	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Organics	Shell		2	1.9
201.207.004	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		4	1.2
201.207.005	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Metal	Lead scrap		1	4.2
201.207.006	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Metal	UID Copper, Flat		1	0.8
201.207.007	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Metal	Button, Domed		1	2.4
201.207.008	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	14.6
201.207.009	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		13	83.9
201.207.010	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.1
201.207.011	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	6
201.207.012	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	10.3
201.207.013	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.2
201.207.014	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	8.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.207.015	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	3	12.2
201.207.016	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Savannah/St. Catherines Fine Cord Marked	Sand	1	5.6
201.207.017	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	2	4.7
201.207.018	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit, Sand	1	2.1
201.207.019	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		3	10.5
201.207.020	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3
201.207.021	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.2
201.207.022	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.3
201.207.023	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.9
201.207.024	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.9
201.207.025	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	4.5
201.207.026	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.207.027	Block AA, TU 203, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	2.5
201.208.001	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Organics	UID shell		1	1.9
201.208.002	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	2.7
201.208.003	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.208.004	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	43.9
201.208.005	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	15.5
201.208.006	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	19.5
201.208.007	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	10
201.208.008	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	10.4
201.208.009	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	19.8
201.208.010	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	3.8
201.208.011	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		10	42.9
201.208.012	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	16.9
201.208.013	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, eroded glaze		2	33.7
201.208.014	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	4.4
201.208.015	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	11.9
201.208.016	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	5.2
201.208.017	Block AA, TU 204, L1	L1		14-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.209.001	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Organics	Shell, mussel		1	2.1
201.209.002	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	9.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.209.003	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		2	6
201.209.004	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.9
201.209.005	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	0.8
201.209.006	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Metal	Pot		1	85.9
201.209.007	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	5
201.209.008	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	16.7
201.209.009	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	6.9
201.209.010	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		8	29.2
201.209.011	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	7.9
201.209.012	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	7
201.209.013	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	1.6
201.209.014	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Mission Red Pottery	Sand	1	3.1
201.209.015	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	0.8
201.209.016	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	3.5
201.209.017	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.7
201.209.018	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.209.019	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	2.2
201.209.020	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.209.021	Block AA, TU 205, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.1
201.219.001	MD 112, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	15.8
201.220.001	MD 113, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	8.3
201.221.001	MD 114, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Grommet		1	4.3
201.222.001	Block AB, MD 115, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	6.7
201.223.001	MD 116, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Buckle, Floral, cast		1	2.1
201.224.001	MD 117, Plowzone	Plowzone	5 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	1.6
201.225.001	Block AF, MD 118, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	17.3
201.226.001	Block AF, MD 119, Plowzone	Plowzone	5 cmbs		Metal	Button, South Type 31, 18th c		1	1.8
201.227.001	Block AB, MD 120, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Melted Pewter		1	75
201.228.001	Block AB, MD 121, Plowzone	Plowzone	8 cmbs		Metal	Modified lead,		1	20.7
201.229.001	Block AB, MD 122, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Button, South Type 31, 18th c		1	2.6
201.230.001	Block AB, MD 123, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	1.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.231.001	Block AB, MD 124, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Side Plate, stamped dragon motif		1	2.8
201.232.001	Block AB, MD 125, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	17.8
201.233.001	MD 126, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	4.2
201.234.001	MD 127, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Pot		1	494.9
201.235.001	MD 128, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	17.2
201.236.001	MD 129, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	16.2
201.237.001	Block AB, MD 130, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Lead, melted		1	0.4
201.238.001	Block AC, MD 131, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead, melted		1	46.7
201.239.001	MD 132, Plowzone	Plowzone	12 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	8.6
201.240.001	MD 133, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Pot		1	435.8
201.241.001	MD 134, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Rear ramrod guide		1	2
201.242.001	MD 135, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Escutcheon		1	8.7
201.243.001	MD 136, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	31.7
201.244.001	Block Z, MD 137, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	17.8
201.245.001	MD 138, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	17.1
201.246.001	Block AB, MD 139, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	16.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.247.001	Block AB, MD 140, Plowzone	Plowzone	15 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	4.9
201.248.001	MD 141, Plowzone	Plowzone	8 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	9.8
201.249.001	MD 142, Plowzone	Plowzone	5 cmbs		Metal	Lead, melted		1	10.8
201.250.001	MD 143, Plowzone	Plowzone	5 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	3.1
201.251.001	MD 144, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	UID Copper		1	2.3
201.252.001	MD 145, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Buckle		1	3.9
201.254.001	Block Y, TU 145, F 258 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		22-51 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	8.8
201.254.002	Block Y, TU 145, F 258 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		22-51 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	4.1
201.255.001	Block Y, TU 153, 157, F 271 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		28-57 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.1
201.255.002	Block Y, TU 153, 157, F 271 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		28-57 cmbd	Metal	Lead scrap		1	3.8
201.256.001	Block Y, TU 157, F 265 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		28-55 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	7.2
201.257.001	Block Y, TU 145, 146, 149, 150, F 259, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-59 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Tin glazed		1	0.1
201.258.001	Block Y, TU 153, F 272 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.1
201.259.001	Block Y, TU 157, F 274 N 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	UID Iron		1	2.8
201.260.001	Block Y, TU 153, F 276 S 1/2, Base of L1, S 1/2	Base of L1, S 1/2			Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.261.001	Block Y, TU 158, F 281 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Ceramics	Daub		1	6.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.262.001	Block Y, TU 146, 150, F 261 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Lead ball		1	
201.262.002	Block Y, TU 146, 150, F 261 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Ceramics	Daub		1	4.8
201.262.003	Block Y, TU 146, 150, F 261 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	10.5
201.263.001	Block Y, TU 150, 151, F 277 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	10.9
201.264.001	Block Y, TU 150, F 278 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Lithics	Indeterminate modification		1	2.3
201.265.001	Block Y, TU 150, F 260 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	10.7
201.266.001	Block Y, TU 146, F 284 S 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Lead ball		1	
201.267.001	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		7	42.6
201.267.002	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	60.8
201.267.003	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	2.6
201.267.004	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	5.7
201.267.005	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.3
201.267.006	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	15.2
201.267.007	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware		1	0.7
201.267.008	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	11

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.267.009	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Slipped		1	2.1
201.267.010	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4
201.267.011	Block Y, TU 146, 147, 151, F 285 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		26-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.268.001	Block Y, TU 151, F 283 S 1/2, Base of L1, S 1/2	Base of L1, S 1/2		27-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		4	90.4
201.269.001	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	22.4
201.269.002	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		2	0.6
201.269.003	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		3	7.5
201.269.004	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	9.1
201.269.005	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.9
201.269.006	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.2
201.269.007	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	1.7
201.269.008	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.9
201.269.009	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.3
201.269.010	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1			Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	6.5
201.269.011	Block Y, TU 152, F 289, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-34 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.270.001	Block Y, TU 158, F 376 W 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-37 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick, indeterminate		1	5.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.271.001	Block Y, TU 158, F 376 E 1/2, Base of L1	Base of L1		30-37 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		9	105.3
201.272.001	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		3	2.1
201.272.002	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		2	4.9
201.272.003	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.3
201.272.004	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.4
201.272.005	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Indeterminate Design		1	3
201.272.006	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Indeterminate Design		1	1.2
201.272.007	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	3.6
201.272.008	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.3
201.272.009	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.7
201.272.010	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.272.011	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		11	54.9
201.272.012	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	16
201.272.013	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	13.1
201.272.014	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone A	Base of L1, Zone A		27-37 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		13	49.4
201.273.001	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Glass	Container glass		1	108.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.273.002	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Glass	Container glass		5	4.6
201.273.003	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Glass	Container glass		1	2.6
201.273.004	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Glass	Container glass		1	3
201.273.005	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Glass	Mirror glass		2	4.2
201.273.006	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Organics	Bone		6	9.4
201.273.007	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Organics	Bone		18	10.9
201.273.008	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Lithics	Shatter		1	1.3
201.273.009	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	0.6
201.273.010	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Organics	Petrified wood		1	2.7
201.273.011	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Lead ball		1	17.5
201.273.012	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Lead ball		1	12.9
201.273.013	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Historic Ceramic	Cufflink/button		1	0.6
201.273.014	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.1
201.273.015	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	0.5
201.273.016	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.273.017	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	10.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.273.018	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.3
201.273.019	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Spike fragment		3	118.4
201.273.020	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Nail, unidentified		8	97.9
201.273.021	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	15
201.273.022	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	10.9
201.273.023	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	UID iron		10	51.9
201.273.024	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	5.9
201.273.025	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1	Base of L1			Metal	Nail, unidentified		16	62.2
201.274.001	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Metal	Melted Lead		1	8.1
201.274.002	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Glass	Other glass		1	0.5
201.274.003	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.8
201.274.004	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	1.2
201.274.005	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic??	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery		1	0.5
201.274.006	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		1	0.2
201.274.007	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, tertiary		1	0.2
201.274.008	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	3.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.274.009	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	4
201.274.010	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.5
201.274.011	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	3.4
201.274.012	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.7
201.274.015	Block Y, TU 179, 180, F 291, Base of L1	Base of L1		25-52 cmbd	Metal	UID lead		1	8.1
201.275.001	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287 N 1/4, Base of L1, Zone B	Base of L1, Zone B		75 cmbs	Lithics	Gunflint		1	8.8
201.276.001	Block Y, TU 147, 151, F 280 S 1/2, L1	L1		27-85 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	0.6
201.276.002	Block Y, TU 147, 151, F 280 S 1/2, L1	L1		27-85 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.2
201.276.003	Block Y, TU 147, 151, F 280 S 1/2, L1	L1		27-85 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	0.4
201.276.004	Block Y, TU 147, 151, F 280 S 1/2, L1	L1		27-85 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	6.3
201.276.005	Block Y, TU 147, 151, F 280 S 1/2, L1	L1		27-85 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.7
201.276.006	Block Y, TU 147, 151, F 280 S 1/2, L1	L1		27-85 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.277.001	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.3
201.277.002	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.2
201.277.003	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	19.2
201.277.004	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.277.005	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	5
201.277.006	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Eroded, Indeterminate	Sand	1	4.2
201.277.007	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	4.2
201.277.008	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Stamped	Sand	1	1.4
201.277.009	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	3	6.2
201.277.010	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.9
201.277.011	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	6.4
201.277.012	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Salt glazed		1	2
201.277.013	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Whiteware		1	4.4
201.277.014	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.3
201.277.015	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	24.3
201.277.016	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Whiteware		1	1.1
201.277.017	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.4
201.277.018	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.7
201.277.019	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.277.020	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.277.021	Block AC, TU 206, L1	L1		6-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.6
201.278.001	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6
201.278.002	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	0.9
201.278.003	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Lead, melted		1	12.4
201.278.004	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	8.3
201.278.005	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	11.2
201.278.006	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	4.8
201.278.007	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Modified		2	2
201.278.008	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.4
201.278.009	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	26.7
201.278.010	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	6
201.278.011	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	6.2
201.278.012	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	3.1
201.278.013	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	5.3
201.278.014	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	3.5
201.278.015	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	2.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.278.016	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	1.8
201.278.017	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	10.4
201.278.018	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	0.7
201.278.019	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.278.020	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	4
201.278.021	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware		1	3.7
201.278.022	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.2
201.278.023	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.8
201.278.024	Block AC, TU 207, L1	L1		8-28 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.279.001	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	7.1
201.279.002	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7.1
201.279.003	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	26.1
201.279.004	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.7
201.279.005	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	6.1
201.279.006	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	2.8
201.279.007	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		4	18.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.279.008	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Lead glazed		1	1.1
201.279.009	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		2	3.1
201.279.010	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	6.1
201.279.011	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Slipped		1	2.8
201.279.012	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	10.7
201.279.013	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		2	5.1
201.279.014	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.3
201.279.015	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	2.8
201.279.016	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.4
201.279.017	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.279.018	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.6
201.279.019	Block AC, TU 208, L1	L1		8-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.280.001	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.2
201.280.002	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	9.8
201.280.003	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	3.5
201.280.004	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		9	32.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.280.005	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	2
201.280.006	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	10.5
201.280.007	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	12.3
201.280.008	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	4
201.280.009	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, eroded		1	1.8
201.280.010	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	3
201.280.011	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1			Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery		1	2.2
201.280.012	Block AC, TU 209, L1	L1		4-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.281.001	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.2
201.281.002	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary Flake		1	0.6
201.281.003	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	22.2
201.281.004	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.1
201.281.005	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.6
201.281.006	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3.2
201.281.007	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	4.7
201.281.008	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.281.009	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	2
201.281.010	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Metal	Buckle, Ornate engraving		1	5.4
201.281.011	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	11.8
201.281.012	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Metal	Nail, wrought		1	0.9
201.281.013	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	4	8.5
201.281.014	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		7	45.4
201.281.015	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	1.9
201.281.016	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	1	1.8
201.281.017	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	9.5
201.281.018	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	6.1
201.281.019	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.8
201.281.020	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.5
201.281.021	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	7.7
201.281.022	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1			Prehistoric Ceramic??	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grog	1	4
201.281.023	Block AD, TU 210, L1	L1		6-36 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.282.001	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	23.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.282.002	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.7
201.282.003	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.9
201.282.004	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	1.1
201.282.005	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.7
201.282.006	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand, Grit	1	5.5
201.282.007	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.8
201.282.008	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		2	2.7
201.282.009	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	
201.282.010	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.1
201.282.011	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	15.2
201.282.012	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	5.4
201.282.013	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		2	5.9
201.282.014	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.5
201.282.015	Block AD, TU 211, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.283.001	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.7
201.283.002	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	11.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.283.003	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	17.4
201.283.004	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	11.4
201.283.005	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	6.4
201.283.006	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		2	2
201.283.007	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	5.1
201.283.008	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		42	106.6
201.283.009	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		6	19.2
201.283.010	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	8.9
201.283.011	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		2	3.9
201.283.012	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	2.3
201.283.013	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, lead glazed		1	1.7
201.283.014	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	10.4
201.283.015	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.2
201.283.016	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.283.017	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.9
201.283.018	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.283.019	Block AD, TU 212, L1	L1		3-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.284.001	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	1.2
201.284.002	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7.1
201.284.003	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		10	26.2
201.284.004	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Metal	Lead		1	7.3
201.284.005	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	13.6
201.284.006	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	16.9
201.284.007	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	22.5
201.284.008	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	40.4
201.284.009	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	44.2
201.284.010	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	15.1
201.284.011	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded Glaze		1	1.6
201.284.012	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Stallings Plain Pottery	Fiber	2	5
201.284.013	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	3	6.9
201.284.014	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	8.3
201.284.015	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		2	3.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.284.016	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Whiteware		1	0.8
201.284.017	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	8.7
201.284.018	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	4
201.284.019	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.284.020	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.2
201.284.021	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	2.8
201.284.022	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	3.6
201.284.023	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.2
201.284.024	Block AD, TU 213, L1	L1		6-35 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery		1	3
201.285.001	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.9
201.285.002	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		4	25.1
201.285.003	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	34.3
201.285.004	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	19.4
201.285.005	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	11.5
201.285.006	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	12.5
201.285.007	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	3.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.285.008	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	12.3
201.285.009	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	6.1
201.285.010	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2
201.285.011	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	4.6
201.285.012	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Refuge Simple Stamped	Sand, Grit	1	4.1
201.285.013	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.5
201.285.014	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.9
201.285.015	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	4
201.285.016	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Whiteware		1	0.6
201.285.017	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	1.4
201.285.018	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		7	15.2
201.285.019	Block AD, TU 214, L1	L1		18-44 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.286.001	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	1.5
201.286.002	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, eroded		1	1.5
201.286.003	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		6	62.8
201.286.004	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.286.005	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	12.6
201.286.006	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	12
201.286.007	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	6.7
201.286.008	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	9.4
201.286.009	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	3
201.286.010	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	2.7
201.286.011	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	3.6
201.286.012	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Stallings Plain Pottery	Fiber	1	2.6
201.286.013	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	6.9
201.286.014	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Mission Red Pottery	Grog, Grit	1	6.7
201.286.015	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3.1
201.286.016	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	3.9
201.286.017	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	5.9
201.286.018	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	5.9
201.286.019	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.2
201.286.020	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	0.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.286.021	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, eroded		1	0.9
201.286.022	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Brown		1	72.6
201.286.023	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4
201.286.024	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		6	8.5
201.286.025	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.286.026	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		16-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.8
201.287.001	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.9
201.287.002	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Glass	Other glass		1	2
201.287.003	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Glass	Other glass		1	1.2
201.287.004	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	11.1
201.287.005	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	14.1
201.287.006	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.5
201.287.007	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.7
201.287.008	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick, indeterminate		1	947.8
201.287.009	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.9
201.287.010	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.287.011	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.9
201.287.012	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	0.9
201.287.013	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.9
201.287.014	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	7.6
201.287.015	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	25.3
201.287.016	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		10	45.1
201.287.017	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	6.8
201.287.018	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	15.4
201.287.019	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	32.4
201.287.020	Block AE, TU 216, L1	L1		6-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.288.001	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	1
201.288.002	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Metal	Lead Patch		1	11.9
201.288.003	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Metal	Handle		1	19.9
201.288.004	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Metal	UID Copper, Flat piece		1	1.3
201.288.005	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.288.006	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	5.2
201.288.007	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	10.3
201.288.008	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.1
201.288.009	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		8	38.4
201.288.010	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	24.7
201.288.011	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded		1	25.4
201.288.012	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, American		1	1.2
201.288.013	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.3
201.288.014	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.2
201.288.015	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.3
201.288.016	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.288.017	Block AE, TU 217, L1	L1		11-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	5.1
201.289.001	Block AD, TU 215, L1	L1		39 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	1034.1
201.290.*	Block Y, TU 151, F 286 E 1/2, L1	L1		28-73 cmbd	Metal	Bucket strap		1	0.6
201.290.001	Block Y, TU 151, F 286 E 1/2, L1	L1		28-73 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		4	36.9
201.291.001	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		3	2.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.291.002	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	8.5
201.291.003	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	10.2
201.291.004	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Organics	Wood		1	0.3
201.291.005	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	108.3
201.291.006	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	14.4
201.291.007	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	2.6
201.291.008	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand, Charcoal	3	11.8
201.291.009	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.7
201.291.010	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.6
201.291.011	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.6
201.291.012	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	
201.291.013	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Organics	Shell		1	
201.291.014	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Lithics	Fossiliferous Limestone		2	1.2
201.291.015	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone A (1m sect of fea)	Zone A (1m sect of fea)		30-43 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	3.2
201.292.001	Block X, TU 130, F 221	Zone B		79-80 cmbd	Organics	Pollen/Phytolith Sample			
201.293.001	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		53-95 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.293.002	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		53-95 cmbd	Organics	Botanical sample			
201.293.003	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		53-95 cmbd	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.293.004	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		53-95 cmbd	Organics	Wood sample, pine			
201.293.005	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		53-95 cmbd	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.293.006	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		53-95 cmbd	Organics	Macro botanical sample, <HF			
201.293.007	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		53-95 cmbd	Organics	Macro botanical sample, >HF			
201.294.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		25	9.9
201.294.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.7
201.294.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	12.2
201.294.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.2
201.294.005	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Metal	Sprue casting strip		1	6.5
201.294.006	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		28	6
201.294.007	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		9	49.8
201.294.008	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	33.3
201.294.009	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	2.8
201.294.010	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	46.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.294.011	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	5.1
201.294.012	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	18.7
201.294.013	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	3	3.4
201.294.014	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Burnished Plain	Sand, Charcoal	2	15.8
201.294.015	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A			Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	2.2
201.294.016	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.6
201.294.017	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Mission Red Pottery	Sand, Charcoal	1	2.8
201.294.018	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	2.1
201.294.019	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	3.1
201.294.020	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	10.9
201.294.021	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		3	13.7
201.294.022	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	108.7
201.294.023	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick, indeterminate		1	197.7
201.294.024	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.8
201.294.025	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	0.9
201.294.026	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.294.027	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	3.1
201.294.028	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	1
201.294.029	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint, fragment		1	15.6
201.294.030	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Savannah Burnished Plain Pottery	Sand	1	2.4
201.294.031	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone A	Zone A		18-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.8
201.295.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176D, Zone A partially	Zone A partially		35-41 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		22	427
201.295.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176D, Zone A partially	Zone A partially		35-41 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	30.7
201.295.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176D, Zone A partially	Zone A partially		35-41 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		80	342.8
201.295.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176D, Zone A partially	Zone A partially		35-41 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	0.6
201.296.001	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		49 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		4	997.2
201.297.001	Block X, TU 133, F 221			34 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	2.2
201.297.002	Block X, TU 133, F 221			34 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	
201.298.001	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		32	18.2
201.298.002	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.9
201.298.003	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	18.1
201.298.004	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		6	0.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.298.005	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Metal	Lead, Melted		1	4.4
201.298.006	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		7	25.8
201.298.007	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	2.6
201.298.008	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	9
201.298.009	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	1
201.298.010	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	8.3
201.298.011	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	10.6
201.298.012	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.3
201.298.013	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone B	Zone B		49-105 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		2	4.2
201.299.001	Block Y, F. 291, N Wall			27-29	Lithics	Non-cultural stone			1.6
201.299.002	Block Y, F. 291, N Wall			27-29	Lithics	Non-cultural stone			0.1
201.300.001	Block Y, TU 179, F 291, Zone A	Zone A		17-27	Other	String		2	
201.300.002	Block Y, TU 179, F 291, Zone A	Zone A		17-27	Organics	Charcoal		10	0.1
201.300.003	Block Y, TU 179, F 291, Zone A	Zone A		17-27	Ceramics	Brick fragment		6	0.6
201.300.004	Block Y, TU 179, F 291, Zone A	Zone A		17-27	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction		1	0.2
201.300.005	Block Y, TU 179, F 291, Zone A	Zone A		17-27	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			5.5
201.300.006	Block Y, TU 179, F 291, Zone A	Zone A		17-27	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			92.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.301.001	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		17	7.3
201.301.002	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.5
201.301.003	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.4
201.301.004	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Organics	Charred wood sample		22	9.8
201.301.005	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		12	35
201.301.006	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	11.4
201.301.007	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	4.3
201.301.008	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit, Sand	3	9.4
201.301.009	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		5	9.8
201.301.010	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand, Grit	9	16.1
201.301.011	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	3.1
201.301.012	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		9	13.7
201.301.013	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	0.4
201.301.014	Block U, TU 144, F 214 S 1/2, Zone B (1m sect of Fea)	Zone B (1m sect of Fea)		30-112 cmbd	Lithics	Fossiliferous Limestone		2	4.2
201.302.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone B	Zone B		18-41 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	8.2
201.302.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone B	Zone B		18-41 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.302.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C, Zone B	Zone B		18-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.2
201.303.001	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	
201.303.002	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	3.1
201.305.001	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	
201.305.002	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	
201.305.003	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51	Organics	wood sample, nutshell			
201.305.004	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.305.005	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.305.006	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.305.007	Block X, TU 131, F 225, Zone A	Zone A		31-51	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.306.001	Block U, TU 144, F 214, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		78-94	Organics	Macro botanical sample, wood and pine			
201.306.002	Block U, TU 144, F 214, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		78-94	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.306.003	Block U, TU 144, F 214, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		78-94	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.306.004	Block U, TU 144, F 214, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		78-94	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.306.005	Block U, TU 144, F 214, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		78-94	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.307.001	Block U, TU 144, F214	Zone A, S 1/2		78-84	Organics	Pollen/Phytolith Sample, >1/8" inch fraction			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.307.002	Block U, TU 144, F215	Zone A, S 1/3		78-84	Organics	Pollen/Phytolith Sample, >1/8" inch fraction			1.8
201.307.003	Block U, TU 144, F216	Zone A, S 1/4		78-84	Organics	Pollen/Phytolith Sample, >1/16" inch fraction			0.2
201.307.004	Block U, TU 144, F217	Zone A, S 1/5		78-84	Organics	Pollen/Phytolith Sample, >1/8" inch fraction			16.8
201.307.005	Block U, TU 144, F218	Zone A, S 1/6		78-84	Organics	Pollen/Phytolith Sample, <1/16" inch fraction			3.1
201.308.001	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287, Zone B/PM, N 1/4	Zone B/PM, N 1/4			Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.3
201.308.002	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287, Zone B/PM, N 1/4	Zone B/PM, N 1/4			Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	3.1
201.308.003	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287, Zone B/PM, N 1/4	Zone B/PM, N 1/4			Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.4
201.308.004	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287, Zone B/PM, N 1/4	Zone B/PM, N 1/4			Ceramics	Daub		51	24.3
201.308.005	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287, Zone B/PM, N 1/4	Zone B/PM, N 1/4			Ceramics	Fired clay		28	8.1
201.308.006	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287, Zone B/PM, N 1/4	Zone B/PM, N 1/4			Organics	Bone, Calcined		12	1
201.308.007	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287, Zone B/PM, N 1/4	Zone B/PM, N 1/4			Organics	Charcoal		32	1.4
201.308.008	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F 287, Zone B/PM, N 1/4	Zone B/PM, N 1/4			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			296.8
201.309.001	Block Y, TU 147, 148, F287, Zone B	Zone B		95-100	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.9
201.309.002		Zone B		95-100	Ceramics	Daub		6	9.8
201.309.003		Zone B		95-100	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	2.8
201.309.004		Zone B		95-100	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8" inch fraction			3.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.309.005		Zone B		95-100	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16" inch fraction			40.1
201.310.001	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		3	3.1
201.310.002	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.8
201.310.003	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	15.2
201.310.004	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		3	2.2
201.310.005	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	2
201.310.006	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		2	8.4
201.310.007	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	13
201.310.008	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Lead glazed		1	0.6
201.311.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	3.4
201.311.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.1
201.311.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		2	0.9
201.311.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Organics	Charred wood sample		2	0.8
201.311.005	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		2	37
201.311.006	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		5	19.7
201.311.007	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		17	3.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.311.008	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	3.8
201.311.009	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	8.5
201.311.010	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		3	8.3
201.311.011	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	2.3
201.311.012	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	499.2
201.311.013	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone C, Zone C	Zone C		41-94/104 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.5
201.312.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone D, Zone D	Zone D		41-71 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	9
201.312.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone D, Zone D	Zone D		41-71 cmbd	Organics	Charred wood sample		4	0.6
201.312.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone D, Zone D	Zone D		41-71 cmbd	Metal	Buckle		1	10.2
201.312.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone D, Zone D	Zone D		41-71 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	16.8
201.312.005	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone D, Zone D	Zone D		41-71 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		31	6.2
201.312.006	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone D, Zone D	Zone D		41-71 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		35	2.6
201.312.007	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone D, Zone D	Zone D		41-71 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	7.2
201.313.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone E, Zone E	Zone E		41-71 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		8	1.4
201.313.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone E, Zone E	Zone E		41-71 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	19.2
201.313.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone E, Zone E	Zone E		41-71 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	10.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.313.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, 106, F 176C Zone E, Zone E	Zone E		41-71 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2
201.314.001	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		27-38	Organics	Macro botanical sample, wood and pine			
201.314.002	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		27-38	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.314.003	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		27-38	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.314.004	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		27-38	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.314.005	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		27-38	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.316.001	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	21.5
201.316.002	Block AD, TU 213, 214, F 362 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		26-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.5
201.318.001	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		90-110	Organics	Macro botanical sample, Wood, Pine			
201.318.002	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		90-110	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.318.003	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		90-110	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.318.004	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		90-110	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.318.005	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		90-110	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.319.001	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Metal	Coin, clipped Mexico mint		1	3.4
201.319.002	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint, fragment		1	1.4
201.319.003	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.319.004	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	4.4
201.319.005	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	2.2
201.319.006	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.9
201.319.007	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	
201.319.008	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	
201.319.009	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Metal	Trigger guard		3	13.4
201.319.010	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Organics	Charred wood sample		7	4.1
201.319.011	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	27.8
201.319.012	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.1
201.319.013	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		13	34
201.319.014	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		3	1.1
201.319.015	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	5.3
201.319.016	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		10	14.6
201.319.017	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		23	61.4
201.319.018	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	97.3
201.319.019	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	191.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.319.020	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Red Filmed		2	39.6
201.319.021	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2
201.319.022	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	
201.319.023	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.8
201.319.024	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.6
201.319.025	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	2.1
201.319.026	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		41-111 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.5
201.319.027	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A			Lithics	Gunflint		1	11.3
201.319.028	Block AD, TU 214, F 363 W 1/2, N/A	N/A			Lithics	Gunflint		1	29.1
201.320.001	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	2.3
201.320.002	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, secondary		1	0.5
201.320.003	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Lithics	Fossiliferous Limestone		1	1.6
201.320.004	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Organics	Tooth, domestic swine		5	2.2
201.320.005	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		5	1
201.320.006	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	9.9
201.320.007	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	10.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.320.008	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	14.3
201.320.009	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Prehistoric ceramics	Undecorated Pottery	Fiber	3	7.3
201.320.010	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	6.3
201.320.011	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.3
201.320.012	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.1
201.320.013	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	1
201.320.014	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		4	28.4
201.320.015	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	12.6
201.320.016	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	4.7
201.320.017	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	2	1.9
201.320.018	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	2.9
201.320.019	Block U, TU 111 E 1/2, F 207, Zone A	Zone A		28-77 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	
201.321.001	Block U, Feat. 207, East 1/2	Zone A		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Fossiliferous Limestone		2	0.5
201.321.002	Block U, Feat. 207, East 1/3	Zone A		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Macro botanical sample			1.5
201.321.003	Block U, Feat. 207, East 1/4	Zone A		50-80 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	
201.321.004	Block U, Feat. 207, East 1/5	Zone A		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Macro botanical sample			15.8
201.322.001	Block U, TU 111, F 207, Zone A E 1/2	Zone A E 1/2		50-80 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	
201.322.002	Block U, TU 111, F 207, Zone A E 1/2	Zone A E 1/2		50-80 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Staffordshire		1	4.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.322.003	Block U, TU 111, F 207, Zone A E 1/2	Zone A E 1/2		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Botanical sample			
201.322.004	Block U, TU 111, F 207, Zone A E 1/2	Zone A E 1/2		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, wood and pine			
201.322.005	Block U, TU 111, F 207, Zone A E 1/2	Zone A E 1/2		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, LF<2mm			
201.322.006	Block U, TU 111, F 207, Zone A E 1/2	Zone A E 1/2		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.322.007	Block U, TU 111, F 207, Zone A E 1/2	Zone A E 1/2		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.322.008	Block U, TU 111, F 207, Zone A E 1/2	Zone A E 1/2		50-80 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.323.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone C, E 1/2	Zone C, E 1/2		51-74 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	1
201.323.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone C, E 1/2	Zone C, E 1/2		51-74 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.6
201.323.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone C, E 1/2	Zone C, E 1/2		51-74 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			11.7
201.323.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone C, E 1/2	Zone C, E 1/2		51-74 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			68.8
201.324.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone C	Zone C		51-74 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		3	0.7
201.324.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone C	Zone C		51-74 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction			1.7
201.324.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone C	Zone C		51-74 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			8
201.324.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone C	Zone C		51-74 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			79.7
201.325.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone D	Zone D		52-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			105.5
201.325.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone D	Zone D		52-65 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		3	

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.325.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone D	Zone D		52-65 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		7	0.1
201.325.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone D	Zone D		52-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction			2.4
201.325.005	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone D	Zone D		52-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			7.9
201.326.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone D	Zone D		52-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction			1.1
201.326.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone D	Zone D		52-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			6.6
201.326.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone D	Zone D		52-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			67.4
201.327.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone E	Zone E		55-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction			0.8
201.327.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone E	Zone E		55-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			14
201.327.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone E	Zone E		55-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			80.7
201.328.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone E	Zone E		55-65 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		8	0.6
201.328.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone E	Zone E		55-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			6.5
201.328.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone E	Zone E		55-65 cmbd	Metal	Shot		1	
201.328.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone E	Zone E		55-65 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			50.3
201.329.001	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		8	3.4
201.329.002	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Lithics	Possible lithic, Primary		1	1.2
201.329.003	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		5	1.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.329.004	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		1	1.1
201.329.005	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	12.8
201.329.006	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	3.2
201.329.007	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Metal	Trigger guard		1	115
201.329.008	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	9.3
201.329.009	Block X, TU 130, F 221, Zone A	Zone A		34-49 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	
201.330.001	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	9.9
201.330.002	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	8
201.330.003	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.4
201.330.004	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.1
201.330.005	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	16.7
201.330.006	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	8.3
201.330.007	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Cord Marked	Grit	1	3.2
201.330.008	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded		1	2
201.330.009	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2.7
201.330.010	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.330.011	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Organics	Wood, Unidentifiable material		2	1.2
201.330.012	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.7
201.330.013	Block AB, TU 218, L1	L1		29-46 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.331.001	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		6	28.1
201.331.002	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	0.6
201.331.003	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	47.2
201.331.004	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1			Glass	Container glass		6	17.7
201.331.005	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	10.4
201.331.006	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Metal	Metal ornament, Bow		1	6.2
201.331.007	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Metal	Nail fragment, wire		5	15.1
201.331.008	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Metal	Nail, probably wrought		3	13.8
201.331.009	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		2	6.6
201.331.010	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand, Clay	2	6.3
201.331.011	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1			Historic Ceramic	Creamware, lead glazed		1	1.9
201.331.012	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	2.8
201.331.013	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	6.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.331.014	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	1.5
201.331.015	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	5
201.331.016	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	17.7
201.331.017	Block AA, TU 219, L1	L1		9-33 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.331.018					Metal	UID Iron		1	3.8
201.332.001	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	1.9
201.332.002	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Organics	Fossiliferous Limestone		1	2.6
201.332.003	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2
201.332.004	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.9
201.332.005	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	
201.332.006	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		2	
201.332.007	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	2.5
201.332.008	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	7.4
201.332.009	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		13	71
201.332.010	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.5
201.332.011	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.332.012	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	2
201.332.013	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	7.4
201.332.014	Block T, TU 220, L1	L1		1-23 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.334.001	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.4
201.334.002	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Glass	Thin pane glass		1	
201.334.003	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		1	1.3
201.334.004	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware		1	0.5
201.334.005	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Organics	Bone fragment, UID		47	4.1
201.334.006	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		8	28.2
201.334.007	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, wood and pine			
201.334.008	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.334.009	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.334.010	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.334.011	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-25 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.335.???	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint, fragment		1	4.1
201.335.001	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Organics	Bone fragment, UID		5	1.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.335.003	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.5
201.335.004	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	5.7
201.335.005	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		16	43.7
201.335.006	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		8	63.9
201.335.007	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	21
201.335.008	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		9	18.8
201.335.009	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield		1	4.5
201.335.010	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.336.001	Block T, TU 100, F 175F, Base of L1	Base of L1			Organics	Macrobotanical sample, >1/8 inch fraction			2.8
201.336.002	Block T, TU 100, F 175F, Base of L1	Base of L1			Ceramics	Brick fragment		14	1.3
201.336.003	Block T, TU 100, F 175F, Base of L1	Base of L1			Organics	Charcoal		70	3.4
201.336.004	Block T, TU 100, F 175F, Base of L1	Base of L1			Organics	Macrobotanical sample, >1/16 inch fraction			23.4
201.337.001	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		2	2
201.337.002	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			23-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.5
201.338.001	Block T, TU 220, F 175F				Organics	Bone		6	0.7
201.338.002	Block T, TU 220, F 175F				Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	0.1
201.338.003	Block T, TU 220, F 175F				Organics	Macrobotanical sample, >1/8 inch fraction			2.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.338.004	Block T, TU 220, F 175F				Organics	Macrobotanical sample, >1/16 inch fraction			16.8
201.339.001	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Flake		1	0.2
201.339.002	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Fossiliferous Limestone		1	5.4
201.339.003	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Organics	Wood		3	1.2
201.339.004	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	0.6
201.339.005	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		2	0.4
201.339.006	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Organics	Shell, oyster		1	0.6
201.339.007	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Glass	Tumbler, Polychrome, Handpainted		1	1.2
201.339.008	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		12	8.8
201.339.009	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.9
201.339.010	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Unglazed		1	1.7
201.339.011	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	4	6.1
201.339.012	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	3.8
201.339.013	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2
201.339.014	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Savannah Fine Cord Marked Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	8.2
201.339.015	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment	Sand	1	0.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.339.016	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Redware, Lead glazed		1	0.5
201.339.017	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	0.7
201.339.018	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	2	1.8
201.339.019	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.2
201.339.020	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	7.5
201.339.021	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		3	1.6
201.339.022	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Proto-Historic Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	1	1.1
201.339.023	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	5.6
201.339.024	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		10	35.5
201.339.025	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1.5
201.339.026	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		6	4.2
201.339.027	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4
201.339.028	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	0.8
201.339.029	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe, Halved fragments		3	0.9
201.339.030	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		6	10.4
201.339.031	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Cord Marked	Grit, Sand	1	5.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.339.032		Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	5.2
201.339.033	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.3
201.339.034	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.4
201.339.035	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		3	1.2
201.339.036	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.7
201.339.037	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	0.4
201.339.038	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		3	2.3
201.340.001	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		1	0.7
201.340.002	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	0.5
201.340.003	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	2.7
201.340.004	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Ceramics	Brick fragment		4	4.6
201.340.005	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Organics	Macro botanical sample, Wood, Pine			
201.340.006	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.340.007	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.340.008	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.340.009	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.341.001	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Organics	Macro botanical sample, >1/16 inch fraction		3	0.1
201.341.002	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Ceramics	Fired clay, >1/8" inch fraction		16	1.9
201.341.003	Block AB, TU 218, F 328 N wall profile, Zone A	Zone A		41-64	Organics	Macro botanical sample, >1/16" inch fraction			58
201.344.001	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		2	0.5
201.344.002	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	2.9
201.344.003	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		2	14.4
201.344.004	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	14.8
201.344.005	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	38.5
201.344.006	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		4	18.6
201.344.007	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	116.2
201.344.008	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Metal	Buckle fragment		1	2.2
201.344.009	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	3.1
201.344.010	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Ceramics	Stoneware, Refined White		2	0.6
201.344.011	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	1.2
201.344.012	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.4
201.344.013	Block AB, TU 197, 199, F 343, N/A	N/A		29-71 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.345.001	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			17-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick, handmade		1	1446.8
201.346.001	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			20-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick, handmade		1	1108.6
201.347.001	Block T, TU 220, F 175F			18-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, oyster shell		11	53.3
201.348.001	Block AB, TU 218, Rut (modern)	Rut (modern)		34-51 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	48
201.348.002	Block AB, TU 218, Rut (modern)	Rut (modern)		34-51 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	2.6
201.348.003	Block AB, TU 218, Rut (modern)	Rut (modern)		34-51 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	5.8
201.348.004	Block AB, TU 218, Rut (modern)	Rut (modern)		34-51 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		2	5.6
201.348.005	Block AB, TU 218, Rut (modern)	Rut (modern)		34-51 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	1.3
201.348.006	Block AB, TU 218, Rut (modern)	Rut (modern)		34-51 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		6	147.4
201.348.007	Block AB, TU 218, Rut (modern)	Rut (modern)		34-51 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		9	22.9
201.349.001	Block AB, TU 218, F 328, Zone C	Zone C		51-60 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		12	98.3
201.350.001	Block AB, TU 195, F 353, N/A	N/A		20-31 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	1.2
201.350.002	Block AB, TU 195, F 353, N/A	N/A		20-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		6	8.1
201.350.003	Block AB, TU 195, F 353, N/A	N/A		20-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.3
201.351.001	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone A	Zone A		20-40 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		2	2.3
201.351.002	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone A	Zone A		20-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.351.003	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone A	Zone A		20-40 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	1.4
201.351.004	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone A	Zone A		20-40 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.351.005	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone A	Zone A		20-40 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	0.7
201.351.006	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone A	Zone A		20-40 cmbd	Organics	Fossiliferous Limestone		1	1.5
201.352.001	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		13	35.9
201.352.002	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		4	2.4
201.352.003	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	5.9
201.352.004	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.7
201.352.005	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware		1	1.2
201.352.006	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		3	2.3
201.352.007	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.2
201.352.008	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.5
201.352.009	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	0.2
201.352.010	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	2.5
201.352.011	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.6
201.352.012	Block AB, TU 197, F 348, Zone B	Zone B		20-70 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	16.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.353.001	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Organics	Shell, oyster		1	0.2
201.353.002	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Lithics	Shatter		1	6.3
201.353.003	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.4
201.353.004	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	11.8
201.353.005	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1
201.353.006	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	2.8
201.353.007	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		21	120.5
201.353.008	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		2	13.7
201.353.009	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	1.7
201.353.010	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	6
201.353.011	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	3.3
201.353.012	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 S 1/2 (1 m section), N/A	N/A		38-92 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1
201.354.001	Block AB, TU 194, F 337 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		44-51 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		7	12.6
201.354.002	Block AB, TU 194, F 337 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		44-51 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4.5
201.354.003	Block AB, TU 194, F 337 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		44-51 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	2.5
201.355.001	Block AB, TU 194, F 335 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		44-54 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.355.002	Block AB, TU 194, F 335 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		44-54 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	5.4
201.356.001	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Historic Ceramic	Redware, Eroded		1	1.3
201.356.002	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Ceramics	Brick fragment		9	3.1
201.356.003	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Organics	Bone		6	0.3
201.356.004	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Organics	Charcoal		6	0.2
201.356.005	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			627.1
201.356.006	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			45.7
201.356.007	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction		12	3.8
201.356.008	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Metal	UID iron		7	1.2
201.356.009	Block AB, TU 187, F 327 E wall profile, N/A	N/A			Lithics	Chert debitage		6	0.3
201.357.001	Block AB, TU 187, F327 E profile			85-89 cmbd	Metal	Lead shot		1	0.2
201.357.002	Block AB, TU 187, F327 E profile			85-89 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	2.3
201.357.003	Block AB, TU 187, F327 E profile			85-89 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			2.6
201.357.004	Block AB, TU 187, F327 E profile			85-89 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			34.5
201.358.001	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1
201.358.002	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Organics	Charred wood sample		2	0.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.358.003	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.3
201.358.004	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	2.5
201.358.005	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, heat altered		1	0.5
201.358.006	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	11.2
201.358.007	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		14	69.3
201.358.008	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		14	34.5
201.358.009	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	35.1
201.358.010	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		4	19.7
201.358.011	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	13.1
201.358.012	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		5	20
201.358.013	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	0.6
201.358.014	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	2	3
201.358.015	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	3.4
201.358.016	Block AB, TU 188, F 328, Zone A	Zone A		34-64 cmbd	Metal	Hinge, strap		1	227.1
201.359.001	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	18.1
201.359.002	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		4	36.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.359.003	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	2.5
201.359.004	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	2.8
201.359.005	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.6
201.359.006	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Lithics	Flint, Modified		1	1.7
201.359.007	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	17.2
201.359.008	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	8.7
201.359.009	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.4
201.359.010	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	28.2
201.359.011	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	29.3
201.359.012	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Organics	Shell		1	1.4
201.359.013	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	6.7
201.359.014	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Ceramics	Coarse Earthenware, unglazed or eroded		1	8.4
201.359.015	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	3
201.359.016	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	4.5
201.359.017	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3.9
201.359.018	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.359.019	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	3.5
201.359.020	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	2.4
201.359.021	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		2	3.2
201.359.022	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.6
201.359.023	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.3
201.359.024	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	5.6
201.359.025	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4
201.359.026	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.7
201.359.027	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Lithics	Soapstone		1	2.1
201.359.028	Block AF, TU 221, L1	L1		17-38 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.360.001	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Metal	Lead, melted		1	13.1
201.360.002	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		4	35.4
201.360.003	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.4
201.360.004	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Lithics	Core		1	38.8
201.360.005	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	1
201.360.006	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		2	6.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.360.007	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	3.2
201.360.008	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	13.1
201.360.009	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	20
201.360.010	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		9	18
201.360.011	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	9.5
201.360.012	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		3	16.3
201.360.013	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	2.4
201.360.014	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		2	4.4
201.360.015	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	5.2
201.360.016	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	3.9
201.360.017	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.6
201.360.018	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.5
201.360.019	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	6.3
201.360.020	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.4
201.360.021	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	5
201.360.022	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.360.023	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	7
201.360.024	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.2
201.360.025	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.4
201.360.026	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.4
201.360.027	Block AF, TU 222, L1	L1		19-38 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.361.001	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Mammal		1	1.1
201.361.002	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	15
201.361.003	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	10.3
201.361.004	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	11.3
201.361.005	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	13.4
201.361.006	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.3
201.361.007	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	15.7
201.361.008	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	6.5
201.361.009	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	2.1
201.361.010	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.9
201.361.011	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery		1	1.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.361.012	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1
201.361.013	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.2
201.361.014	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	1.9
201.361.015	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	2.5
201.361.016	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.1
201.361.017	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.9
201.361.018	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.361.019	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	6.5
201.361.020	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	1.4
201.361.021	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.361.022	Block AF, TU 223, L1	L1		7-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	2.1
201.362.001	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Metal	Spur		1	12.1
201.362.002	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	2.8
201.362.003	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Modified		1	1.8
201.362.004	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.5
201.362.005	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	10.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.362.006	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	11.8
201.362.007	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	6.5
201.362.008	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	4.8
201.362.009	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	10.1
201.362.010	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	3	15.7
201.362.011	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	4.1
201.362.012	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	4
201.362.013	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	5.2
201.362.014	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		3	4.6
201.362.015	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	1.8
201.362.016	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	5.7
201.362.017	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.3
201.362.018	Block AG, TU 224, L1	L1		8-34 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.363.001	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Organics	Wood		1	101.3
201.363.002	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	1.3
201.363.003	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		8	56.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.363.004	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.6
201.363.005	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	1.2
201.363.006	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Melted		1	3.2
201.363.007	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	6.7
201.363.008	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.8
201.363.009	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.3
201.363.010	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Metal	Split ring		1	6.5
201.363.011	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	9
201.363.012	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	2	5.8
201.363.013	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	43.9
201.363.014	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	43.6
201.363.015	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery		1	2.8
201.363.016	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded		1	3
201.363.017	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		3	44.8
201.363.018	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		3	18.8
201.363.019	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Queens Pattern molding		1	5.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.363.020	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	25.2
201.363.021	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield, Lead glazed		1	1.5
201.363.022	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.2
201.363.023	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Organics	Shell bead, tubular cane		1	0.4
201.363.024	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.9
201.363.025	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.4
201.363.026	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.363.027	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.363.028	Block AG, TU 225, L1	L1		3-41 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	3.3
201.364.001	Block AF, TU 221, F 378 W 1/2			35-43 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		5	11.5
201.365.001	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Organics	Charred wood sample		32	18.5
201.365.002	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Organics	Bark		1	0.3
201.365.003	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	1.5
201.365.004	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	19.7
201.365.005	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.1
201.365.006	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	10.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.365.007	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	23
201.365.008	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.4
201.365.009	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	
201.365.010	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.6
201.365.011	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	5.3
201.365.012	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		7	21.2
201.365.013	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	9.4
201.365.014	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		2	5.8
201.365.015	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		5	3
201.365.016	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded		1	0.6
201.365.017	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.8
201.365.018	Block AF, TU 222, F 379 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-52 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.3
201.366.001	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	18.5
201.366.002	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	4
201.366.003	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Metal	UID Copper		1	1.5
201.366.004	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	59.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.366.005	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	43.9
201.366.006	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	12.5
201.366.007	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	12.2
201.366.008	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.8
201.366.009	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.1
201.366.010	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1
201.366.011	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Metal	Sprue casting strip		1	9.5
201.366.012	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	14.3
201.366.013	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	12.4
201.366.014	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	0.9
201.366.015	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	2	6.4
201.366.016	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	1	1.1
201.366.017	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	3	4.1
201.366.018	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	9.8
201.366.019	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	3.4
201.366.020	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	4.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.366.021	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	4.5
201.366.022	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.1
201.366.023	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.1
201.366.024	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.9
201.366.025	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		5	5.8
201.366.026	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.4
201.366.027	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		5	8.3
201.366.028	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Organics	Wood		1	0.4
201.366.029	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	9.4
201.366.030	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	1.8
201.366.031	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.366.032	Block AF, TU 226, L1	L1		2-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		2	2.5
201.367.001	MD 146, Plowzone	Plowzone	8 cmbs		Metal	Williams Cleaner Bullet		1	28.8
201.368.001	MD 147, Plowzone	Plowzone	5 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	19.1
201.369.001	MD 148, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Rivet		1	7.2
201.370.001	MD 149, Plowzone	Plowzone	5 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	7.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.371.001	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.3
201.371.002	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Glass	Tableware, Etched		1	3.1
201.371.003	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	28.5
201.371.004	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		13	41.4
201.371.005	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		12	26.2
201.371.006	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Metal	UID Copper		1	1.4
201.371.007	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		8	38.6
201.371.008	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	16.2
201.371.009	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	35.6
201.371.010	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	1.7
201.371.011	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1			Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	2	11.3
201.371.012	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	5.1
201.371.013	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	2	3.3
201.371.014	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	3.2
201.371.015	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	1.9
201.371.016	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.371.017	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	2.8
201.371.018	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.5
201.371.019	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		3	3.2
201.371.020	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		6	13.3
201.371.021	Block AA, TU 227, L1	L1		22-42 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.372.001	Block AB, TU 188, F 327, Zone A	Zone A		38-92 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.4
201.372.002	Block AB, TU 188, F 327, Zone A	Zone A		38-92 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		2	4.8
201.372.003	Block AB, TU 188, F 327, Zone A	Zone A		38-92 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery,	Sand	1	2.7
201.372.004	Block AB, TU 188, F 327, Zone A	Zone A		38-92 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		2	0.8
201.374.001	Block AF, TU 226, F 385 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-44 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	0.3
201.374.002	Block AF, TU 226, F 385 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-44 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick, handmade		1	84.4
201.374.003	Block AF, TU 226, F 385 W 1/2, N/A	N/A		32-44 cmbd	Metal	UID Copper		1	
201.375.001	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Glass bead, tubular cane		1	
201.375.002	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	7
201.375.003	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	7
201.375.004	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.375.005	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		39	8.5
201.375.006	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		20	20.2
201.375.007	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	11.1
201.375.008	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	0.6
201.375.009	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery		2	17.8
201.375.010	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Eroded glaze		1	7.2
201.375.011	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	18.4
201.375.012	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		3	9.9
201.375.013	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		2	17.3
201.375.014	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic??	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	1	1.1
201.375.015	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, ,Grit	2	4.7
201.375.016	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.8
201.375.017	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	3.1
201.375.018	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead or gravel tempered glaze		1	0.7
201.375.019	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		3	1.5
201.375.020	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	UID Copper		1	0.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.375.021	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		7	5.3
201.375.022	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	9.4
201.375.023	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		19	33.7
201.375.024	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	151.4
201.375.025	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		44	144
201.375.026	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		30	107.4
201.375.027	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	16.2
201.375.028	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		2	14.8
201.375.029	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		17	4.7
201.375.030	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Modified		8	1.5
201.375.031	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, burned		3	5.5
201.375.032	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	166.8
201.375.033	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	101.1
201.375.034	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.9
201.375.035	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7.8
201.375.036	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Plate glass		1	1.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.375.037	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Molded		1	0.7
201.375.038	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.4
201.375.039	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		13	67.2
201.375.040	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	9.3
201.375.041	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		10	71.1
201.375.042	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	32.2
201.375.043	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		10	14.7
201.375.044	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	23.7
201.375.045	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	37.3
201.375.046	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	71.7
201.375.047	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	56.5
201.375.048	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, wire		17	58
201.375.049	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		13	43.1
201.375.050	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.7
201.375.051	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.8
201.375.052	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	3.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.375.053	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		4	0.7
201.375.054	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		52-108 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		9	1.6
201.376.001	Block AG, TU 224, F 390, Zone A	Zone A		41-64 cmbd	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	0.5
201.376.002	Block AG, TU 224, F 390, Zone A	Zone A		41-64 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		4	53.3
201.377.001	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	5.7
201.377.002	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	1.5
201.377.003	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Lithics	Savannah River Stemmed PPK		1	16.2
201.377.004	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1
201.377.005	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	6.6
201.377.006	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		1	5.6
201.377.007	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	20.9
201.377.008	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	4.4
201.377.009	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	6.6
201.377.010	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		2	
201.377.011	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.4
201.377.012	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded glaze		1	

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.377.013	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	3.9
201.377.014	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.9
201.377.015	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B	Zone B		41-60 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Cord marked or Simple Stamped		2	8.5
201.378.001	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-45 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction		3	0.4
201.378.002	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-45 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			0.6
201.378.003	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-45 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			12.1
201.379.001	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.7
201.379.002	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		156	39.4
201.379.003	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		26	27
201.379.004	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		7	19
201.379.005	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		70	47.3
201.379.006	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		67	22.7
201.379.007	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction		3	1.4
201.379.008	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			14.8
201.379.009	Block AG, TU 225, F 390, Zone B, S wall	Zone B		39-59 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			246.7
201.380.001	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.3
201.380.002	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	4.3
201.380.003	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	0.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.380.004	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	0.3
201.380.005	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.2
201.380.006	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	0.7
201.380.007	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	2.4
201.381.001	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, F 299, Zone A L2	Zone A L2		47-57 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	0.7
201.381.002	Block Z, TU 164 E 1/2, F 299, Zone A L2	Zone A L2		47-57 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	
201.382.001	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		2	0.8
201.382.002	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	2.3
201.382.003	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.2
201.382.004	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.6
201.382.005	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Other	Fossiliferous Limestone		1	1.1
201.382.006	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		37	169.7
201.382.007	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		3	3.3
201.382.008	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, British Brown		1	6.3
201.382.009	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	2.7
201.382.010	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		7	15.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.382.011	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Metal	UID iron		2	13.5
201.382.012	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2
201.382.013	Block Z, TU 176, F 301 N 1/2, N/A	N/A		22-56 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		3	0.9
201.383.001	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	
201.383.002	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.9
201.383.003	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	7.3
201.383.004	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1.4
201.383.005	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	7
201.383.006	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4.1
201.383.007	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Lead glazed		1	0.1
201.383.008	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	8.1
201.383.009	Block AF, TU 222, F 384 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-116 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.5
201.385.001	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	2.6
201.385.001	Block AA, F 314, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		103-107 cmbd	Organics	Pollen/Phyto analysis			
201.385.002	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	17
201.385.003	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.385.004	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		9	5
201.385.005	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		10	2.4
201.385.006	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Organics	Bone		7	0.6
201.385.007	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		54	2.1
201.385.008	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			35.8
201.385.009	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			290.3
201.385.010	Block AA, TU 203 S 1/2, F 314/388, Zone A	Zone A		60-103 cmbd	Metal	UID metal		8	1.1
201.386.001	Block AA, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		105-108 cmbd	Organics	Pollen/Phyto analysis			
201.387.001	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	4.8
201.387.002	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	1.3
201.387.003	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		2	
201.387.004	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	3.3
201.387.005	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.3
201.387.006	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Ceramics	Mortar fragment		1	0.4
201.387.007	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.1
201.387.008	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Organics	Organic samples, corn kernel, sumac, hickory			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.387.009	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Organics	Wood sample, pine, R. omc,			
201.387.010	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.387.011	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.387.012	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.387.013	Block AA, TU 227 E 1/2, F 388, Zone A	Zone A		72-105	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.388.001	Block Z, TU 164, F 304, L2	L2		48-62 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		3	0.2
201.388.002	Block Z, TU 164, F 304, L2	L2		48-62 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.2
201.388.003	Block Z, TU 164, F 304, L2	L2		48-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glaze		1	3.2
201.388.004	Block Z, TU 164, F 304, L2	L2		48-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.8
201.388.005	Block Z, TU 164, F 304, L2	L2		48-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft		1	0.4
201.388.006	Block Z, TU 164, F 304, L2	L2		48-62 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	6.3
201.388.007	Block Z, TU 164, F 304, L2	L2		48-62 cmbd	Ceramics	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.9
201.388.008	Block Z, TU 164, F 304, L2	L2		48-62 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	2.8
201.389.001	Block AF, TU 222, F 380 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-75 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	4.7
201.389.002	Block AF, TU 222, F 380 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		36-75 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	3.4
201.390.001	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		11	5.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.390.002	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		2	1.8
201.390.003	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Glass bead		1	0.1
201.390.004	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		20	4.7
201.390.005	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		3	0.3
201.390.006	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	41.4
201.390.007	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	24.1
201.390.008	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	26.5
201.390.009	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		13	31.7
201.390.010	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		20	9.2
201.390.011	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	23.2
201.390.012	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	12.1
201.390.013	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	6.8
201.390.014	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	20.8
201.390.015	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Metal	Iron concretion		2	5.4
201.390.016	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		6	62.4
201.390.017	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		26	92.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.390.018	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	5
201.390.019	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.7
201.390.020	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Tin glazed		1	0.9
201.390.021	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	22.6
201.390.022	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	9.9
201.390.023	Block AA, TU 227, F 388, Zone B	Zone B		52-108 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		3	1.5
201.391.001	Block AA, TU 227, F 388 E wall, Zone A	Zone A		72-105 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		8	1.4
201.391.002	Block AA, TU 227, F 388 E wall, Zone A	Zone A		72-105 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.5
201.391.003	Block AA, TU 227, F 388 E wall, Zone A	Zone A		72-105 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		22	1.1
201.391.004	Block AA, TU 227, F 388 E wall, Zone A	Zone A		72-105 cmbd	Metal	Nail fragment, wrought		1	1.4
201.391.005	Block AA, TU 227, F 388 E wall, Zone A	Zone A		72-105 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction			2
201.391.006	Block AA, TU 227, F 388 E wall, Zone A	Zone A		72-105 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			14.6
201.391.007	Block AA, TU 227, F 388 E wall, Zone A	Zone A		72-105 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			178.7
201.392.001	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		12	4
201.392.002	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Gun barrel plug		1	14.9
201.392.003	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		2	2.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.392.004	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Lead patch		1	11
201.392.005	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Debitage		2	1.2
201.392.006	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Nail, Wire		6	53.1
201.392.007	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	38.2
201.392.008	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	28.9
201.392.009	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		10	29.3
201.392.010	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		5	6.1
201.392.011	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Molded		2	1
201.392.012	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		2	0.6
201.392.013	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		2	4.3
201.392.014	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		14	59.9
201.392.015	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	26.9
201.392.016	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	17.5
201.392.017	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Glass	Heat-altered glass		1	1.2
201.392.018	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Savannah/St. Catherine's Fine Cord Marked Pottery	Sand, Clay	1	8.5
201.392.019	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Simple Stamped	Sand	2	32

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.392.020	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	19.8
201.392.021	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		24	48
201.392.022	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		44	93.6
201.392.023	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	21.3
201.392.024	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		2	4.5
201.392.025	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware		2	3.3
201.392.026	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	0.7
201.392.027	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	1	0.8
201.392.028	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		5	29.2
201.392.029	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware		1	12.5
201.392.030	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	7.7
201.392.031	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		16	14.5
201.392.032	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		11	16.6
201.392.033	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	12
201.392.034	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		13	15.2
201.392.035	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Metal	Button, Composite type		1	1.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.392.036	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	10.2
201.392.037	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3
201.392.038	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone A	Zone A		46-99 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	7.1
201.393.001	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		6	1.7
201.393.002	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		2	1
201.393.003	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		23	7.8
201.393.004	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	8
201.393.005	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		7	36.7
201.393.006	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		6	67.3
201.393.007	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		13	40
201.393.008	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	15
201.393.009	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	2.9
201.393.010	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	19.2
201.393.011	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	11
201.393.012	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	11.3
201.393.013	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	133.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.393.014	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		18	65.2
201.393.015	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grit	2	42
201.393.016	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Tin glazed		2	0.6
201.393.017	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		5	3.4
201.393.018	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand, Grit	2	5.4
201.393.019	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		46-103 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		8	14.2
201.393.020	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B			Lithics	Gunflint		1	7.1
201.393.021	Block AA, TU 203, F 314, Zone B	Zone B			Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.2
201.394.001	Block Z, TU 165, F 305, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.5
201.394.002	Block Z, TU 165, F 305, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		4	0.5
201.394.003	Block Z, TU 165, F 305, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		2	0.5
201.394.004	Block Z, TU 165, F 305, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	2.7
201.394.005	Block Z, TU 165, F 305, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	10.8
201.394.006	Block Z, TU 165, F 305, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Metal	Hinge, strap		2	61.8
201.394.007	Block Z, TU 165, F 305, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	1.8
201.394.008	Block Z, TU 165, F 305, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.395.001	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 W 1/2, L2	L2		22-32 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		1	2.6
201.395.002	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 W 1/2, L2	L2		22-32 cmbd	Lithics	Petrified wood		1	3.9
201.395.003	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 W 1/2, L2	L2		22-32 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	12.5
201.395.004	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 W 1/2, L2	L2		22-32 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.7
201.395.005	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 W 1/2, L2	L2		22-32 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	0.8
201.395.006	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 W 1/2, L2	L2		22-32 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		5	4.1
201.395.007	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 W 1/2, L2	L2		22-32 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.396.001	Block Z, TU 165, F 304, L2	L2		47-60 cmbd	Lithics	Biface fragment		7	1.1
201.396.002	Block Z, TU 165, F 304, L2	L2		47-60 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	9.8
201.396.003	Block Z, TU 165, F 304, L2	L2		47-60 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	4.2
201.397.001	Block Z, TU 165 E 1/2, L2	L2		19-28 cmbd	Lithics	Chunk/Shatter		1	2.8
201.397.002	Block Z, TU 165 E 1/2, L2	L2		19-28 cmbd	Other	Fossiliferous Limestone		1	1
201.397.003	Block Z, TU 165 E 1/2, L2	L2		19-28 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.8
201.397.004	Block Z, TU 165 E 1/2, L2	L2		19-28 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	3
201.398.001	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Organics	Bark		1	0.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.398.002	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.5
201.398.003	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	7.1
201.398.004	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	7.6
201.398.005	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		1	2.2
201.398.006	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	0.5
201.398.007	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		1	1.6
201.398.008	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.7
201.398.009	Block Z, TU 228, L1	L1		17- 35 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.399.001	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 E 1/2, L2	L2		22-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		5	15.3
201.399.002	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 E 1/2, L2	L2		22-35 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	
201.399.002	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 E 1/2, L2	L2		22-35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.7
201.399.003	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 E 1/2, L2	L2		22-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		1	3.7
201.399.004	Block Z, TU 165, F 306 E 1/2, L2	L2		22-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Coarse Earthenware		1	2.1
201.400.001	Block Z, TU 170, 171, 176, 177, F 302 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		0-32+ cm	Metal	Lead ball		1	0.3
201.400.002	Block Z, TU 170, 171, 176, 177, F 302 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		0-32+ cm	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		3	11.3
201.400.003	Block Z, TU 170, 171, 176, 177, F 302 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		0-32+ cm	Glass	Container glass, Heat altered		1	1.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.400.004	Block Z, TU 170, 171, 176, 177, F 302 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		0-32+ cm	Ceramics	Fired clay		7	10.8
201.400.005	Block Z, TU 170, 171, 176, 177, F 302 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		0-32+ cm	Ceramics	Brick fragment		13	18.1
201.401.001	Block Z, TU 165 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	2.8
201.401.002	Block Z, TU 165 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		20-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	7.1
201.402.001	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	0.4
201.402.002	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	5
201.402.003	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.2
201.402.004	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		25	76
201.402.005	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		8	68.8
201.402.006	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		3	18
201.402.007	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		5	5.2
201.402.008	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		14	73.3
201.402.009	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 299, L2	L2		23-31 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	
201.403.001	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Metal	Sprue casting strip		1	30.3
201.403.002	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	21.3
201.403.003	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.8

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.403.004	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1
201.403.005	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		6	51.7
201.403.006	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		4	20.1
201.403.007	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		9	28.9
201.403.008	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		15	30.2
201.403.009	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.3
201.403.010	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, F 308, L2	L2		29-35 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	0.7
201.404.001	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, L2	L2		23-35 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	8.2
201.404.002	Block Z, TU 171 E 1/2, L2	L2		23-35 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	2.2
201.405.001	Block Z, TU 171, F 307 E 1/2, L2	L2		27-30 cmbd	Metal	UID Metal alloy		1	0.5
201.405.002	Block Z, TU 171, F 307 E 1/2, L2	L2		27-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	9.2
201.405.003	Block Z, TU 171, F 307 E 1/2, L2	L2		27-30 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	2
201.405.004	Block Z, TU 171, F 307 E 1/2, L2	L2		27-30 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.406.001	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		9	32.6
201.406.002	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		3	0.7
201.406.003	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	3.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.406.004	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	3.5
201.406.005	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.9
201.406.006	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		6	5.7
201.406.007	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	14.7
201.406.008	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		12	59.9
201.406.009	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	18.6
201.406.010	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	9.4
201.406.011	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		2	0.3
201.406.012	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	53.4
201.406.013	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware		1	13
201.406.014	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Kasita Red Filmed Pottery	Sand	2	8.6
201.406.015	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	2	2.8
201.406.016	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	1.2
201.406.017	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	0.2
201.406.018	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Ceramics	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.3
201.406.019	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Ceramics	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.406.020	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Ceramics	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.2
201.406.021	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304, L3	L3		65-128 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.7
201.407.001	MD 150, Plowzone	Plowzone	10-20 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	21.3
201.408.001	MD 151, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	16.9
201.409.001	MD 152, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Lead ball		1	15
201.410.001	MD 153, Plowzone	Plowzone	10 cmbs		Metal	Concretion		1	2.8
201.411.001	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		12	0.8
201.411.002	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Metal	Melted lead		9	24.5
201.411.003	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		20	6.6
201.411.004	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	16.2
201.411.005	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		3	1.7
201.411.006	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass		4	11.3
201.411.007	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.6
201.411.008	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3			Metal	Nail, wrought		8	59.8
201.411.009	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		8	35.7
201.411.010	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	34

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.411.011	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	1.1
201.411.012	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	0.2
201.411.013	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	
201.411.014	Block Z, TU 171, F 308, L3	L3		35-108 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.2
201.412.001	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	0.9
201.412.002	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		7	4
201.412.003	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.9
201.412.004	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Metal	Hinge		2	13.9
201.412.005	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		10	94.3
201.412.006	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	21.3
201.412.007	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit, Sand	1	14.4
201.412.008	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	28
201.412.009	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	428.7
201.412.010	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	2.8
201.412.011	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3		31-65 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	12.4
201.412.012	Block Z, TU 165, 171, F 299, L3	L3			Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	7.2

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.413.001	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2.2
201.413.002	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Calcined		11	0.3
201.413.003	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		7	1.1
201.413.004	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	3.6
201.413.005	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	
201.413.006	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	
201.413.007	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, <1/8 inch fraction			26.8
201.413.008	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		13	3.7
201.413.009	Block AA, TU 203, F 314	Zone A		71-94 cmbd	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			169.3
201.414.001	Block AA, TU 203 E wall profile, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		75 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	87.4
201.414.014	Block AA, TU 203 E wall profile, F 314, Zone B	Zone B		75 cmbd	Ceramics	Decorated Pottery, Indeterminate		1	1
201.415.001	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Other	Sheave		1	3.9
201.415.002	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		4	5.7
201.415.003	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1
201.415.004	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	2.1
201.415.005	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	1.5
201.415.006	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass		1	0.3
201.415.007	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		9	32.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.415.008	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	8.9
201.415.009	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	1.1
201.415.010	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	0.9
201.415.011	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Deptford Cord Marked Pottery	Grit	1	1.9
201.415.012	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	0.6
201.415.013	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand, Grog	1	3.3
201.415.014	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1			Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded		1	1
201.415.015	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	1.1
201.415.016	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	12.4
201.415.017	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.415.018	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	3.5
201.415.019	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.9
201.415.020	Block W, TU 229, L1	L1		4-24 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.416.001	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		5	40.2
201.416.002	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		2	6.1
201.416.003	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	7.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.416.004	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, Wire		5	17.8
201.416.005	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	10.5
201.416.006	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	8.6
201.416.007	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	5	26.5
201.416.008	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		5	22.1
201.416.009	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	29.6
201.416.010	Block AH, TU 230, L1	L1		10-29 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	6.3
201.417.001	Block AA, MD 154, F 314		20 cmbs		Metal	Lead patch		1	18.1
201.418.001	Block X, MD 155, F 221, Base of L1	Base of L1	1-15 cmbs		Metal	Melted lead		1	3.8
201.419.001	Block AH, TU 231, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery		1	1.6
201.419.002	Block AH, TU 231, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	1.9
201.419.003	Block AH, TU 231, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		10	53.6
201.419.004	Block AH, TU 231, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Secondary		1	1
201.419.005	Block AH, TU 231, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	33.2
201.419.006	Block AH, TU 231, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		5	82.2
201.419.007	Block AH, TU 231, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	2.1

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.419.008	Block AH, TU 231, L1	L1		3-27 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	4.3
201.420.001	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.3
201.420.002	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	0.2
201.420.003	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	
201.420.004	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Porcelain, Handpainted		1	
201.420.005	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		15	37.3
201.420.006	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		27	350.9
201.420.007	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Ceramics	Mortar, unidentifiable fragment		13	21.7
201.420.008	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		4	1.8
201.420.009	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.5
201.420.010	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone A S 1/2	Zone A S 1/2		29-53 cmbd	Other	Fossiliferous Limestone		1	0.6
201.421.001	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone B, S 1/2	Zone B, S 1/2		53-85 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		4	12
201.421.002	Block W, TU 120, F 251, Zone B, S 1/2	Zone B, S 1/2		53-85 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	49.3
201.422.001	Block W, TU 120, F 251A			28-36 cmbd	Other	Plastic fragment		2	0.4
201.422.002	Block W, TU 120, F 251A			28-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.422.003	Block W, TU 120, F 251A			28-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.422.004	Block W, TU 120, F 251A			28-36 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		1	5.2
201.423.001	Block W, TU 117, F 251, 254, L2	L2		26-37 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	5.2
201.423.002	Block W, TU 117, F 251, 254, L2	L2		26-37 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	0.7
201.423.003	Block W, TU 117, F 251, 254, L2	L2		26-37 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	4.3
201.423.004	Block W, TU 117, F 251, 254, L2	L2		26-37 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	2.1
201.423.005	Block W, TU 117, F 251, 254, L2	L2		26-37 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.424.001	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 251 N 1/2, Zone A	Zone A		29-53 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		3	38.2
201.424.002	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 251 N 1/2, Zone A	Zone A		29-53 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		7	204.2
201.424.003	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 251 N 1/2, Zone A	Zone A		29-53 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	108.7
201.424.004	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 251 N 1/2, Zone A	Zone A		29-53 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	13
201.425.001	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 254, N/A	N/A		12-48 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.6
201.425.002	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 254, N/A	N/A		12-48 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	6
201.426.001	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304 N wall, N/A	N/A			Ceramics	Fired clay		31	9
201.426.002	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304 N wall, N/A	N/A			Ceramics	Daub		9	2.6
201.426.003	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304 N wall, N/A	N/A			Organics	Charcoal		115	6.1
201.426.004	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304 N wall, N/A	N/A			Organics	Bone, Calcined		17	0.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.426.005	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304 N wall, N/A	N/A			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/4 inch fraction		4	1.4
201.426.006	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304 N wall, N/A	N/A			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			26
201.426.007	Block Z, TU 164, 165, F 304 N wall, N/A	N/A			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			356.8
201.427.001	Block Z, F 304, N Wall	Below L2			Organics	Charcoal		6	0.9
201.427.002	Block Z, F 304, N Wall	Below L2			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			1.2
201.427.003	Block Z, F 304, N Wall	Below L2			Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			24.4
201.428.001	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 251, Zone B, N 1/2	Zone B, N 1/2		53-85 cmbd	Metal	Eye bolt		1	76.6
201.428.002	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 251, Zone B, N 1/2	Zone B, N 1/2		53-85 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	10.2
201.428.003	Block W, TU 117 W 1/2, F 251, Zone B, N 1/2	Zone B, N 1/2		53-85 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	2
201.430.001	Block W, TU 117, 120, F 251, Zone B W Wall	Zone B W Wall		48-66	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	
201.430.002	Block W, TU 117, 120, F 251, Zone B W Wall	Zone B W Wall		48-66	Metal	Nail, Wrought		2	13.7
201.430.003	Block W, TU 117, 120, F 251, Zone B W Wall	Zone B W Wall		48-66	Organics	Macro botanical sample, assorted			
201.430.004	Block W, TU 117, 120, F 251, Zone B W Wall	Zone B W Wall		48-66	Organics	Macro botanical sample, wood and pine			
201.430.005	Block W, TU 117, 120, F 251, Zone B W Wall	Zone B W Wall		48-66	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.430.006	Block W, TU 117, 120, F 251, Zone B W Wall	Zone B W Wall		48-66	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.430.007	Block W, TU 117, 120, F 251, Zone B W Wall	Zone B W Wall		48-66	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.430.008	Block W, TU 117, 120, F 251, Zone B W Wall	Zone B W Wall		48-66	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.431.001	Block Z, TU 162 E 1/2, L2	L2		63-73 cmbd	Lithics	PPK, Reworked		1	2.6
201.431.002	Block Z, TU 162 E 1/2, L2	L2		63-73 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint fragment		1	6.4
201.431.003	Block Z, TU 162 E 1/2, L2	L2		63-73 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	8.7
201.431.004	Block Z, TU 162 E 1/2, L2	L2		63-73 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	2.9
201.431.005	Block Z, TU 162 E 1/2, L2	L2		63-73 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	2
201.431.006	Block Z, TU 162 E 1/2, L2	L2		63-73 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Grit	1	1.5
201.431.007	Block Z, TU 162 E 1/2, L2	L2		63-73 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.7
201.431.008	Block Z, TU 162 E 1/2, L2	L2		63-73 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.432.001	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	6.8
201.432.002	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	11.7
201.432.003	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.6
201.432.004	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Organics	Wood		4	8.1
201.432.005	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		10	1.9
201.432.006	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	1.3
201.432.007	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		7	27.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.432.008	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		4	12
201.432.009	Block Z, TU 164 W 1/2, L2	L2		52-62 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	2
201.434.001	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	2.6
201.434.002	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	2
201.434.003	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Metal	Nail, Wrought		4	27.6
201.434.004	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Organics	Macro botanical sample, Nutshell, unid. Seed, unid. Gen			
201.434.005	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Organics	Macro botanical sample, Wood, Pine			
201.434.006	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.434.007	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.434.008	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.434.009	Block Z, TU 165, F 299A, N/A	N/A		80-90	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.435.001	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Organics	Shell, Whelk		1	2.6
201.435.002	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		9	58.1
201.435.003	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		4	22.1
201.435.004	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Organics	Wood		2	0.9
201.435.005	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	10.7

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.435.006	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		5	33
201.435.007	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		5	54.2
201.435.008	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	5.8
201.435.009	Block AH, TU 232, L1	L1		10-22 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware		2	5.2
201.436.001	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	7.3
201.436.002	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Lithics	Biface fragment		1	9
201.436.003	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.7
201.436.004	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4.8
201.436.005	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	5.6
201.436.006	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	1.5
201.436.007	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		3	8.3
201.436.008	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, Indeterminate	Sand	1	4
201.436.009	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	3
201.436.010	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery, Eroded	Sand	1	1.9
201.436.011	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	2.1
201.436.012	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.436.013	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, dry bodied, engine turned		1	1.2
201.436.014	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1
201.436.015	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Rhenish Blue		1	3.4
201.436.016	Block Z, TU 233, L1	L1		17-44 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.437.001	Block Z, TU 171, F 299A, L3	L3		70-90 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	202.3
201.438.001	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Lithics	Biface fragment		1	6.8
201.438.002	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	1
201.438.003	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	0.7
201.438.004	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Other	Non-cultural stone		2	1.8
201.438.005	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Other	Non-cultural stone		8	39.6
201.438.006	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Organics	Petrified wood		1	7.2
201.438.007	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	3.1
201.438.008	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	2
201.438.009	Block Z, TU 234, L1	L1		16-33 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.439.001	Block AH, TU 232, F 177			25-47 cmbd	Misc	Bisque figurine, rabbit		1	
201.439.001	Block AH, TU 232, F 177			25-47 cmbd	Misc	Whelk shell, red painted		1	

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.440.001	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	14.5
201.440.002	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	11.3
201.440.003	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	5.1
201.440.004	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	15.6
201.440.005	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		3	1.1
201.440.006	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.8
201.440.007	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Stallings Plain Pottery	Fiber	2	3.6
201.440.008	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		1	1.9
201.440.009	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		1	12.5
201.440.010	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick		2	52.3
201.440.011	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	16.6
201.440.012	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick		2	26
201.440.013	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	3.6
201.440.014	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	1.5
201.440.015	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		3	7.8
201.440.016	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Stallings Plain Pottery	Fiber	2	7.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.440.017	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401, N/A	N/A		44-109 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Grit	1	9.1
201.441.001	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Shell fragments, unidentified		1	0.3
201.441.002	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Ceramics	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	4.6
201.441.003	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Macro botanical sample, Wood, Pine			
201.441.004	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF <2mm			
201.441.005	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Macro botanical sample, LF >2mm			
201.441.006	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF <2mm			
201.441.007	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Macro botanical sample, HF >2mm			
201.443.001	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Charcoal		23	0.3
201.443.002	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/8 inch fraction			13.6
201.443.003	Block Z, TU 233 W 1/2, F 401 S profile, N/A	N/A		72-103	Organics	Macrobotanical Sample, >1/16 inch fraction			153.4
201.445.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	15.8
201.445.002	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	2.9
201.445.003	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		12	1.9
201.445.004	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		1	1.4
201.445.005	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		1	0.4

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.445.006	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		1	3.4
201.445.007	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	1.8
201.445.008	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	
201.446.001	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.9
201.446.002	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		3	34.1
201.446.003	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Lithics	Non-cultural stone		4	44.9
201.446.004	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Other	Fossiliferous Limestone		1	3.9
201.446.005	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	3.3
201.446.006	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	4
201.446.007	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	0.7
201.446.008	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Metal	UID object		11	44.1
201.446.009	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	4.1
201.446.010	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Decorated Pottery, UID stamped	Grit	1	2.9
201.446.011	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	2.1
201.446.012	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	1.3
201.446.013	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	3.6

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.446.014	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Whiteware, Transfer printed		1	11.4
201.446.015	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Trailed		1	1.3
201.446.016	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.8
201.446.017	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Scratch Blue		1	0.7
201.446.018	Block W, TU 235, L1	L1		4-19 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.447.001	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.8
201.447.002	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Jackfield, molded		1	1.8
201.447.003	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	6.8
201.447.004	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	16
201.447.005	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		1	6.1
201.447.006	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	4.9
201.447.007	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Glass	Container glass		3	3.8
201.447.008	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Glass	Flat glass, Plate glass		7	6.7
201.447.009	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		1	9.4
201.447.010	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		6	74.9
201.447.011	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1			Metal	Nail, unidentified		11	43.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.447.012	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		6	11.8
201.447.013	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Prehistoric Ceramic	Undecorated Pottery	Sand	1	3.3
201.447.014	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		2	4.4
201.447.015	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded glaze		1	2.9
201.447.016	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Combed		2	7.4
201.447.017	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Lead glazed		1	1.7
201.447.018	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	1.4
201.447.019	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1
201.447.020	Block AI, TU 236, L1	L1		12-36 cmbd	Ceramics	Discarded brick or daub			
201.448.001	Block W, TU 235, F 397 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		16-84 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		6	440.4
201.448.002	Block W, TU 235, F 397 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		16-84 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		2	1.4
201.448.003	Block W, TU 235, F 397 S 1/2, N/A	N/A		16-84 cmbd	Metal	UID Iron		1	
201.449.001	MD 156, Plowzone	Plowzone	5 cmbs		Metal	UID Iron		1	70.4
201.450.001	MD 157, Plowzone	Plowzone	8 cmbs		Metal	Lead, melted		1	4.9
201.451.001	MD 158, Plowzone	Plowzone	5 cmbs		Metal	UID Iron		1	504.2
201.452.001	Block V, MD 159, F 176C, Base of Plowzone/Level 1	Base of Plowzone/Level 1	20 cmbs		Metal	Lead patch		1	11.5

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.454.001	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Lithics	Flake, Tertiary		1	0.3
201.454.002	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Glass	Misc glass, Heat altered		1	2.8
201.454.003	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	5.5
201.454.004	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		3	17.2
201.454.005	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Ceramics	Fired clay		2	5.2
201.454.006	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware, Dotted		1	1.1
201.454.007	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Slipware		1	0.6
201.454.008	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.6
201.454.009	Block AI, TU 236, F 403 E 1/2, N/A	N/A		35-132 cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		2	4.7
201.455.001	Block V, TU 104, 105, F 176C, Zone F	Zone F		71-90 cmbd	Organics	Charcoal		2	12.1
201.456.001	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Metal	Sprue casting strip (2); Melted lead (1),		3	7.8
201.456.002	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Metal	Lead ball		8	1.6
201.456.003	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	1.5
201.456.004	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	7
201.456.005	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Organics	Bone, Unidentifiable Fragment		4	0.8
201.456.006	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	24

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.456.007	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Glass	Container glass		2	1.8
201.456.008	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	19.3
201.456.009	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Delft, Handpainted		1	
201.456.010	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Eroded glaze		1	11.7
201.456.011	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Ceramics	Brick fragment		2	1.2
201.456.012	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Redware, Lead glazed		1	1
201.456.013	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1
201.456.014	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Ceramics	Daub		2	1.9
201.456.015	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	1.1
201.456.016	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	5.9
201.456.017	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Historic Ceramic	Kaolin tobacco pipe		1	0.3
201.456.018	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	7.4
201.456.019	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint		1	3.7
201.456.020	Block AB, TU 197, F 348 S 1/2, Zone B	Zone B		48 + cmbd	Lithics	Gunflint, fragment		1	8.3
201.457.001	Block Z, TU 165 SE corner, F 299A, L3	L3		65-90 cmbd	Ceramics	Daub w/wattle impression		1	154.8
201.457.002	Block Z, TU 165 SE corner, F 299A, L3	L3		65-90 cmbd	Metal	Nail, unidentified		2	7.9

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.458.001	Surface find, during site prep		0 surface		Historic Ceramic	Coarse Earthenware, Eroded glaze		1	4.7
201.458.001	Surface find, during site prep		0 surface		Historic Ceramic	Creamware, Lead glazed		1	5.4
201.458.002	Surface find, during site prep		0 surface		Historic Ceramic	Stoneware, Refined White		1	1
201.460.001	Surface find, during site prep		0 surface		Lithics	Gunflint		1	5.3

Lot #	Provenience	Strat/Level	Depth Below Surface	Depth Below Datum	Class	Artifact Description	Temper	Count	Weight (grams)
201.461.001	Surface find, during site prep		0 surface		Lithics	Gunflint		1	6.2
201.462.001	MD 21		0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID iron		1	
201.463.001	MD 22		0-20 cmbs		Metal	Iron pipe, Modern		1	
201.464.001	MD 48		0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID iron		1	
201.465.001	MD 57		0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID iron		1	
201.466.001	MD 64		0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID iron		1	
201.467.001	MD 87		0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID iron		1	
201.468.001	MD 89		0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID iron		1	
					Metal	Nail, unidentified		5	20.7
	TU 173				Lithics	Gunflint		1	3
					Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.7
					Lithics	Gunflint		1	4.2
	MD 90		0-20 cmbs		Metal	UID iron and brick concentration		1	
TOTAL								9305	

APPENDIX B: Additional Portable X-Ray Fluorescence (pXRF) Documentation, LG²ES Excavations, 9BN28.

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Appendix B.

Elemental Analysis of Selected Artifacts from the Fort Argyle Site (9BN28)

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Submitted to LG2 Environmental Solutions, Inc.

Jacksonville, Florida

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Introduction

Small arms ammunition in America, throughout the eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries, consisted of round soft-metal balls. These were mostly lead, although archeologists have documented other metals as additives. Available small arms and related ammunition varied by military unit, and included pistols, rifles, trade guns, carbines, fowlers, and large caliber wall guns, as well as American, French and English muskets. Macroscopic identification of associated bullets alone limits battlefield interpretations. Traditional analysis documents diameter, weight, firing condition (impact evidence, rifling, worming, ramrod impact, casting evidence), alterations (chewing, cutting, carving), other post-depositional damage (rodent gnawing), and archaeological context. This report documents a portable X-Ray fluorescence study by the LAMAR Institute of lead ammunition from Fort Argyle (9BN28) in Bryan County, Georgia. This study builds on the recent research by the author and others on elemental analysis using pXRF on eighteenth- and early nineteenth-century military sites in the eastern United States (Seibert et al. 2014; Elliott 2016; Elliott and Seibert 2017).

Methods

Methods Employed in the Fort Argyle Elemental Analysis

Samples were collected from each specimen using a Bruker III-V handheld device for 180 seconds each using the Black filter. Energy settings were 45 kV voltage, and 29 μ A of current.

Elemental Analysis of Military Lead

Lead mining in North America in the colonial era was widespread quite limited in scope. Lead was mined in French Louisiana, present-day southeast Missouri, as early as 1721. Early mining operations also were established at Mine La Motte. Lead ore was taken from the mines down the Mississippi River to Saint Genevieve and eventually to France (Seeger 2008:5, 10). The lead mining operations at Mine La Motte ceased in 1769, when it was destroyed by Chickasaw Indians. Mining there did not resume until 1780 or 1782 (Ingalls 1907:981). Filson (2013:21) noted in 1793, "the lead mine on the Mississippi must prove inexhaustible. It extends from the mouth of Rock river more than 100 miles upwards. Besides these there are several others, some of which lie on the Spanish side of the Mississippi, and have been used for years past." To date we have located no documentary evidence for any British colonial lead mines in the Carolinas and Georgia. The lack of documentation does not mean that no lead was mined in those three states, as all three states possess lead deposits. The lack of any reference to lead mines or lead mining in the southern colonies suggests that, if any took place, it was on a local scale and failed to catch the notice of state politicians or military leaders. Great Britain, however, abounds in major lead deposits that have been mined since at least Roman times. England was a major producer of lead (Percival 1774:33, 36; Pilkington 2007:95-130; Pryce 2010:243). Lead also was mined in Ireland since at least 1667 (Petty 2007:vi). Currently scholars are lacking elemental data on eighteenth and early nineteenth century lead sources. A pXRF study of those lead sources will further strengthen the value of this database in understanding those relatively anonymous round bullets that are the building blocks of conflict studies. Collecting lead samples from early mines in both America, Great Britain and Europe is a high priority task.

Portable X-Ray Fluorescence (pXRF) has been used for several decades as a non-destructive method of analyzing archaeological artifacts and sediments. Hunt and Speakman (2014) point out many of the problems and pitfalls in pXRF studies of archaeological materials. Previous study of eighteenth- and early nineteenth-century lead artifacts from archaeological sites provide a backdrop for the present study (Sivilich 1996, 2004, 2014; Branstner 2008). These studies explored various physical aspects and characteristics of round ball ammunition. A recent study by Siebert and colleagues from National Park Service, Southeast Archeological Center and Bruce Kaiser examined lead shot from Palo Alto battlefield, Mexican-American War, 1846 (Seibert et al. 2016). Their study analyzed 700 lead shot. They were able to distinguish between shot from Mexican

(British Brown Bess, Indian Pattern) weapons and shot from American (Springfield Arsenal, Model 1816/1822 and 1835 muskets). The simplified result is that Mexican shot contained more silver (Ag).

In his recent book on musket balls, Daniel Sivilich (2016) presented some information on pXRF results from six musket balls from Valley Forge, Pennsylvania and 104 musket balls from Monmouth Battlefield in New Jersey. He compares the frequencies of lead, iron and tin in these balls.

In 2015 archaeologists Michael Seibert and Dan Elliott conceived a pilot study using pXRF technology to identify and characterize round ball ammunition from early sites (primarily Revolutionary War period) in the eastern states. They were joined in this endeavor by archaeologist Meg Waters, who had recently recovered a small sample from the Parker's Revenge battlefield in Massachusetts. On the advice of Bruce Kaiser, inventor of the Bruker Tracer handheld device, the archaeologists attempted to gather data systematically. Data files for the study were collected by Seibert and Elliott with Bruker Tracer III devices. Data was collected for 180 seconds for each sample using 45 kV voltage and 20 μ A and Bruker's Green filter (Ti/Al). No vacuum was employed. On December 4 and 5, 2015 a meeting of the National Park Service and the LAMAR Institute archaeologists was held at NPS Southeastern Archeological Center in Tallahassee, Florida. This pilot study gathered elemental data on 440 round metal balls through a systematic data collection protocol. This sample was obtained from 14 different archeological sites from the U.S. Eastern seaboard with emphasis on the southeast. The sample spans the early eighteenth century through early nineteenth centuries and it covers Native American and Euro-American towns, as well as French and Indian War, Revolutionary War, Indian Wars, and War of 1812 battle and fort sites. The preliminary findings from the 2015 pilot study demonstrated that Portable X-ray Fluorescence (pXRF) can be a useful technology in distinguishing round ball assemblages from eighteenth and early nineteenth century sites in the eastern United States. Bruce Kaiser confounded the group by announcing a new and improved filter for the Bruker Tracer, which he called the "Black Filter". This filter had the addition of thin copper sheets and was designed to reduce the masking effect caused by lead in the round balls. The group then proceeded to sample 72 lead balls from a variety of sites using the Black filter. The task before us is to solidify the pXRF data collection protocol so that an international database can be created and maintained. The group agreed that the database should be housed and maintained by the National Park Service. We also agreed that the breadth of the database should be widened to include the international community.

Building on the interest from the 2015 session Elliott and Seibert organized a second session in 2017. This workshop was sponsored by a generous grant from the National Park Service, National Center for Preservation Technology and Training and a small grant from the LAMAR Institute. The results of the second session are summarized in a LAMAR Institute report (Elliott and Seibert 2017). These preliminary musket ball elemental data gathered from the two workshops demonstrated that Antimony (Sb) and Tin (Sn) are

very important elements for measuring differences in round balls. These two elements are common components of pewter. Bullet elemental composition also varies over time and space from 1720s to 1820s.

Archeologists can improve on the lead ball information by incorporating pXRF analysis of the lead balls into existing analytical framework. The ultimate goal is to elevate the diagnostic value of round ball ammunition so that we can determine where the lead came from, who was firing the bullets, and how did access to lead vary over the course of history. This now appears to be an achievable goal (see Elliott and Seibert 2017). Researchers are encouraged to provide input in improving this database.

Archeologists have made significant advances in musket ball analysis and interpretation over the past several decades. Musket ball diameters, represented in calibers (hundredths of inches) generally are associated with the following arms:

- American Long Rifle- .38-.51
- Fusil, American Musket, Long Rifle, Fowling Gun- .52-.59
- French Standard- .60-.66
- British Standard- .67-.74
- Buck shot- .29-.35

Buck shot ranging between .29-.35 caliber were used in the American Revolution by the Americans in buck-and-ball loads in smoothbore muskets. These were prepared paper cartridge loads that contained one large ball and two to three buck shot. The scatter of buck shot on the battlefield provides supporting information on the American firing patterns. Some Loyalist units also used buck-and-ball loads during the American Revolution. Buck shot also was used in non-military contexts for hunting.

I. Fort Argyle pXRF Samples

Lead Balls

It is against the previously described scientific backdrop that an elemental analysis of the lead ammunition and related items from Fort Argyle was set. The age range of the Fort Argyle lead balls is tightly bracketed by historical and archaeological research, which place them between 1733 and 1767. pXRF data were collected for 319 round balls of the 503 total lead balls recovered from Fort Argyle by LG2ES. Most of the 184 lead balls that were not included in this analysis were smaller shot. The pXRF sample included 263 examples for which accurate diameters were obtained. The Fort Argyle lead balls were collected using three different recovery methods.

First, a large sample of lead balls was collected from the plow zone in the systematic metal detector survey. While this category includes many balls that would not have been recovered by traditional archaeological excavations, it likely excludes many smaller balls that would have gone undetected by the metal detectorists. In theory, this should have excluded any lead balls smaller than 0.50 inches in diameter, but careful excavation and screening by the field crew managed to recover many examples of smaller balls using this method. Secondly, plow zone deposits were in all test units were screened through ½ inch (0.50 inch) mesh hardware cloth and lead balls were collected from these areas. This also should have excluded any lead balls smaller than 0.25 inches in diameter, but careful excavation and screening by the field crew managed to recover many examples of smaller balls using this method. Thirdly, lead balls were recovered from excavated feature contexts and from Level 2 excavations using ¼ inch (0.25 inch) mesh hardware cloth. In theory, this also should have excluded any lead balls smaller than 0.25 inches in diameter, but careful excavation and screening by the field crew managed to recover many examples of smaller balls using this method.

These balls were grouped into four major size classes. These were named Class 1, 2, 3 and 4. Class 1 was the smallest diameter grouping (measuring between .104 and .204 inches) but were the probably most common ball type (n=71 measured specimens). These conform to the historical, vernacular category of bird shot. Three balls fell between the Class 1 and Class 2 size groups. Class 2 was the next most common ball type (n=119 measured specimens) and these measured between (.285-.398 inches). Class 2 can be further subdivided into two sub-types—2a and 2b. Class 2a balls measure less than .38 inches and Class 2b balls measure from .38-.398 inches. The Class 2a balls are in the size range for buck shot but some may represent pistol shot. The Class 2b balls are in the size range for use as rifle shot. One ball fell between the Class 2 and Class 3 size groups. Class 3 balls measured between .524 and .637 inches and are represented by 63 measured examples. Class 3 can be further subdivided into two sub-types—3a and 3b. Class 3a balls measure from .52 to .59 inches. These may represent carbine, fusil, fowler or long rifle balls. Class 3b measure from .60 to .637. These may represent French Charleville musket balls, although this is most unlikely. Class 4 balls, which measured between .65 and .724 inches, are the least common group (n=6 measured examples).

Class 4 balls were likely intended for use with British Brown Bess military muskets, which was the weapon typically associated with the British Infantry. Some of these larger Class 4 balls may have been used in case shot as artillery loads.

Figure 1. Scatterplot of Lead Ball Samples by Increasing Caliber, Fort Argyle.

Table 1 contains a list of photons emitted for selected elements for 97 larger lead balls (Class 3 and 4) from Fort Argyle. The elements in this table include Silver, Arsenic, Cadmium, Copper, Iron, Manganese, Molybdenum, Nickel, Lead, Palladium (which is contained in the Bruker III-V hardware), Antimony, Tin, Zinc and Zirconium. The current elemental dataset from Fort Argyle contains information on two particular elements that are now recognized as important elements in the differentiation of the elemental characterization of round ball ammunition. We examined the relationship between Antimony (Sb) and Tin (Sn) in the Fort Argyle data. This was accomplished by expressing each as a ratio relative to the Palladium (Pd) values, or Pd/Sb and Pd/Sn. Palladium represents a constant in the Bruker Tracer hardware, which allows for a more even comparison between the Antimony and Tin values.

Antimony (Sb) is a silvery white, brittle metalloid with the atomic number 51 (Butterman and Carlin 2004; Royal Society of Chemistry 2017). Antimony has a high melting point (1170°F) compared to lead. It has a value of 3 on Mohs hardness scale. Antimony occurs naturally with lead ores. In early America, Antimony was a key minor ingredient in the alloy pewter, where it served to harden and strengthen the pewter object. Antimony is well represented in the Fort Argyle lead ball assemblage. Eleven balls in the Fort Argyle sample each displayed more than 1,000 photons of Antimony. Only one ball yielded more than 5,000 photons of this element.

Figure 2. Scatterplot of Antimony for All Lead Balls, Fort Argyle.

Figure 3. Scatterplot of Antimony in Class 1 Balls, Fort Argyle.

Figure 4. Scatterplot of Antimony in Larger Lead Balls, Fort Argyle.

Tin (Sn) is a soft, white metal with the atomic number 50 (Calvert 2002). Tin has a melting point of 449°F, which is lower than that of lead. It has a value of 1.5 on Mohs hardness scale. Tin occurs naturally with lead ores. Tin also is a major component of pewter alloy.

Tin is well represented in the Fort Argyle lead ball assemblage. Eleven samples recorded more than 5,000 photons each in the analysis, which is substantially more than was observed for Antimony. Seventeen samples yielded more than 1,000 photons each.

I examined a subset of 38 of the 318 lead balls that were analyzed for their elemental content from Fort Argyle that displayed higher Antimony and Tin photon counts and higher Pd/Sb and Pd/Sn ratios. These 38 balls represent 12% of the total sample. These were the top 11 ranked samples in each of these four categories. These balls represent balls whose lead content was “diluted” with other metals. Three lead balls had both high Antimony and high Tin photon counts (Samples 103, 276 and 538). One lead ball (Sample 2) had both high Pd/Sb and Pd/Sn ratios. The remaining 34 balls met only one of the four sorting criteria.

Measured calibers for the High Antimony/Tin sample (n=39) range from .33 to .63 caliber. Twenty-eight of the subset were greater than .50 caliber. Of these 28 balls, eight came from excavation Block V and are mostly associated with Fort A, ca. 1733-1742. Two of the balls measuring less than .50 caliber in the 28-ball subset were from Block V. One mis-cast ball that was not measured for caliber also was in the 38-ball sample. Thus, 11 of the 39 high Antimony/Tin ball subset were from Block V. All of these were from either

Feature 176C or 176D and are likely associated with Fort A—the earliest configuration of Fort Argyle. This represents 3.5% of the entire lead ball assemblage examined in this study. Block V provided 166 lead balls for the pXRF analysis and all except one came from Features 176C or 176D. The high Antimony/Tin balls from Block V represent 6.6% of the lead balls from these two features.

Five of the High Antimony/Tin sample came from Block Z, which is 63% of the lead balls sampled from that block. Block Z is located beyond the bounds of Forts A and B and artifacts from that part of Fort Argyle are more likely associated with Fort C, ca. 1757-1763. Three of these had high Tin content and two had high Antimony content, while one displayed a high Pd/Sb ratio. The Block Z specimens ranged in diameter from 0.37 to 0.60 caliber.

These metals, Antimony and Tin, co-occur in natural geological deposits of galena (the mineral state of lead), which may explain their presence in the lead balls. These two elements also are components of pewter, which may indicate the intentional introduction of these metals into the lead mixture. When faced with any shortage of lead on the frontier, pewter was likely melted down with the lead to increase the metal available for casting lead balls. Tin is a major component of pewter, whereas the use of Antimony in pewter was optional.

Figure 5. Scatterplot of Tin in All Lead Balls, Fort Argyle.

Figure 6. Scatterplot of High Antimony/Tin Lead Balls by Caliber, Fort Argyle.

Figures 7 and 8 show a comparison of the spectra for Tin and Antimony photons for dropped lead balls from two contemporary Georgia Ranger forts, Fort Argyle and Fort Mount Pleasant. Both illustrations display low frequencies of photons for these two elements for both forts, although both assemblages contain numerous examples with higher frequencies of both elements. Tin content is more pronounced in both samples compared to Antimony.

Silver is another element that may have an important relationship with lead in early ammunition. Silver (Ag) is a precious silver metal with the atomic number 47 (Butterman and Hilliard 2004). Silver has a high melting point (1761°F) compared to lead. It has a value of 2.5 on Mohs hardness scale. It commonly occurs with lead ores. Silver is present in relatively low frequencies in the Fort Argyle lead ball assemblage. The scatterplot of Silver photons by increasing caliber, which is shown in Figure 9 reveals no trend towards increasing Nickel content as ball diameter increases, although three specimens exhibited more than 300 photons emitted during analysis.

Arsenic is present in relatively moderate frequencies in the Fort Argyle lead ball assemblage. The scatterplot of Arsenic photons by increasing caliber, which is shown in Figure 10 reveals a pronounced trend towards increasing Arsenic content as ball diameter increases. The relationship between arsenic and lead in lead ball production remains unclear. This subject deserves more study.

Zirconium (Zr) is a lustrous, grey-white strong transition metal with the atomic number 40. It has a melting point of 3371°F. It has a value of 5.0 on Mohs hardness scale (Greenwood and Earnshaw 1997). Zirconium is present in relatively moderate frequencies in the Fort Argyle lead ball assemblage. The scatterplot of Zirconium photons by increasing caliber, which is shown in Figure 11 reveals a trend towards increasing Nickel

content as ball diameter increases. The relationship between zirconium and lead in lead ball production remains unclear. This subject deserves more study.

Figure 7. Spectra in Tin and Antimony Range for Dropped Lead Balls, Fort Argyle.

Figure 8. Spectra in Tin and Antimony Range for Dropped Lead Balls, Fort Mt. Pleasant.

Figure 9. Scatterplot of Silver Photons by Increasing Caliber, Fort Argyle.

Figure 10. Scatterplot of Arsenic by Increasing Caliber, Fort Argyle.

Figure 11. Scatterplot of Zirconium by Increasing Caliber, Fort Argyle.

Nickel (Ni) is a silvery-white lustrous metal with the atomic number 28 (Nickel Institute 2017). Nickel has a very high melting point (2646°F) compared to lead. It has a value of 4.0 on Mohs hardness scale. Nickel is present in relatively low frequencies in the Fort Argyle lead ball assemblage. The scatterplot of Nickel photons by increasing caliber, which is shown in Figure 12 reveals a trend towards increasing Nickel content as ball diameter increases. The relationship between nickel and lead in lead ball production remains unclear. This subject deserves more study.

Other Arms Group Lead Artifacts

Eight lead sprue casting strips or sprue blobs were analyzed for their elemental content. One casting strip and the three sprue were associated with Fort A. Two casting strips came from F348, one was from F308 and one was from plow zone context. The photons emitted for selected elements by these samples are shown in Table 2 and are graphically illustrated on the spectra in Figure 13. The elements in this table include Silver, Arsenic, Cadmium, Copper, Nickel, Lead, Palladium (which is contained in the Bruker III-V hardware), Rhodium (which also contained in the Bruker III-V hardware), Antimony, Tin, Zinc and Zirconium.

Figure 12. Scatterplot of Nickel by Increasing Caliber, Fort Argyle.

Table 2. Photons Emitted for Lead Ball Casting Sprue Strips, Fort Argyle.

pXRF No.	Ag K12	As K12	As L1	Cd K12	Cu K12	Ni K12	Pb L1	Pb M1	Pd K12*	Pd L1*	Rh K12*	Sb K12	Sb L1	Sn K12	Sn L1	Zn K12	Zr K12	Zr L1
Argyle8	128	3139	114	193	315	213	99574	485	85	7	57	291	27	1023	26	19	456	40
Argyle77h	97	2853	117	109	338	175	93649	651	69	25	50	213	70	270	23	13	412	12
Argyle77i	136	2973	102	142	361	237	97590	608	89	19	21	161	30	339	0	5	471	43
Argyle77k	113	1925	144	76	229	154	62290	385	43	31	58	215	29	265	26	5	300	35
Argyle77L	152	1813	88	96	212	238	61490	317	76	10	67	760	43	2552	17	33	328	40
Argyle506	88	2352	116	110	341	230	81777	338	56	8	24	102	38	388	16	11	414	21
Argyle518	129	2364	102	89	337	187	82306	338	69	26	37	78	26	277	29	32	372	12
Argyle539	147	2365	76	133	302	215	70546	332	65	19	30	82	24	288	18	20	594	51
Argyle540	107	2873	55	140	367	160	90820	525	80	11	47	162	22	420	20	54	450	18
Total	1097	22657	914	1088	2802	1809	740042	3979	632	156	391	2064	309	5822	175	192	3797	272
Average	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122	122

*- Note: Rhodium and Palladium photons are emitted by the Bruker III-V hardware.

Figure 13. Close-up of Spectra Showing Tin and Antimony, Casting Sprue Strips, Fort Argyle.

Four lead gunflint patches were analyzed for their elemental content. Three of these were associated with Fort A and the other was from plow zone context. We suspect that these items were crafted by each ranger on site and that each patch began its use trajectory as a lead musket ball. The photons emitted for selected elements by these samples are shown in Table 2. The elements in this table include Silver, Arsenic, Gold, Cadmium, Copper, Iron, Gallium, Nickel, Lead, Palladium (which is contained in the Bruker III-V hardware), Rhodium (which also contained in the Bruker III-V hardware), Antimony, Tin, Zinc and Zirconium.

Table 3. Photons Emitted for Gunflint Lead Patches, Fort Argyle.

pXRF No.	Ag K12	Ag L1	As K12	As L1	Au L1	Au M1	Cd K12	Cu K12	Fe K12	Ga K12	Ga L1	Mn K12	Ni K12	Pb L1	Pb M1	Pd K12 ^a	Rh K12 ^a	Sb K12	Sb L1	Sn K12	Sn L1	Zn K12	Zr K12	Zr L1
Argyle318	172	1	1	106	40	4	37	449	1259	241	81	14	104	52524	56	96	69	1068	34	1103	20	13	1769	2
Argyle527	97	17	1	51	62	11	83	430	1113	485	0	37	165	72307	81	22	32	569	39	1403	3	1	483	31
Argyle533	78	1	1	98	26	16	197	429	699	753	0	29	180	105633	480	70	49	463	37	1283	16	11	501	40
Argyle534	100	1	1	117	84	27	209	378	388	675	0	62	206	106065	614	105	64	83	18	329	1	4	458	0
Total	447	20	4	372	212	58	526	1686	3459	2154	81	142	655	336529	1231	293	214	2183	128	4118	40	29	3211	73
Average	112	5	1	93	53	15	132	422	865	539	20	36	164	84132	308	73	54	546	32	1030	10	7	803	18

^a- Note: Rhodium and Palladium photons are emitted by the Bruker III-V hardware.

Figure 14. Spectra and Photon Counts for Gunflint Lead Patches, Fort Argyle.

Brass Gun Hardware

Six pieces of brass gun hardware from Fort Argyle were analyzed for their elemental content. One trigger guard was associated with Fort B; another was associated with Fort C and the remaining four hardware pieces were from plow zone contexts.

Brass is an alloy of copper and zinc in varying proportions. It is distinguished from bronze, which is an alloy composed primarily of copper and tin and sometimes minor amounts of zinc and lead. Copper (Cu) is a malleable reddish-gold colored metal with the atomic number 29 (Doebrich 2009:1-4). It often occurs with lead ores. Copper has a very high melting point (1984°F) compared to lead. It has a value of 3 on Mohs hardness scale.

The primary elemental components in the six brass items (addressed collectively) were Copper, Lead and Tin. Substantial amounts of Iron, Zinc, Silver, Antimony and lesser amounts of Vanadium, Arsenic and Zirconium also were detected.

Brass Sword Guard

One brass small sword, or “hanger” guard from Fort Argyle was analyzed for its elemental content. It was recovered from the plow zone on the western part of Fort Argyle by the metal detector survey. This hanger was probably worn as part of a non-commissioned officer’s uniform. It is a sword style common in the late-seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries and was most likely made in Great Britain, and probably in England. Figure 16 shows the spectra and photon counts for the sword guard. Its primary composition is copper with substantial amounts of Zinc, Iron, Arsenic, and Vanadium.

Figure 15. Spectra and Photon Counts for Brass Gun Hardware, Fort Argyle.

Figure 16. Spectra and Photon Counts for Brass Sword Guard, Fort Argyle.

Gunflints

A total of 34 gunflints (25 gunflints and nine gunflint fragments) were included in the pXRF study. The sample includes four probable French blade type flints and 30 English spall types. Eight specimens displayed evidence of intense heat, shown by crazing, spalling and thermal cracks and breaks. Figure 17 shows the spectra and photons for all gunflints that were examined. In addition to Silica, which is a basic component of chert and flint, the analysis revealed moderate frequencies of Lead, Tin, Arsenic, Nickel and Iron. The high incidence of Lead and Tin is problematic. I question how these two elements were introduced into the stone material, which does not naturally contain these two elements. One possible explanation is that the Lead and Tin were infused into the stone during a structure fire at Fort Argyle.

Figure 17. Spectra and Photons of All Analyzed Gunflints, Fort Argyle.

Brass Buckles

Eight brass buckles from Fort Argyle were included in the pXRF study. Table 4 provides photon counts for six of these samples and Figure 18 contains the spectra and photon counts for all eight examples. The buckle sample contains high frequencies of Tin and Copper and moderate amounts of Silver, Arsenic, Cadmium, Iron, Lead, Antimony, Zinc and Zirconium.

Table 4. Photons Emitted for Six Brass Buckles, Fort Argyle.

	Ag K12	Ag L1	As K12	As L1	Au L1	Au M1	Cd K12	Cu K12	Fe K12	Kr K12	Kr L1	Pb L1	Pb M1	Sb K12	Sb L1	Sn K12	Sn L1	V K12	Zn K12	Zr K12	Zr L1
Argyle13	2036	2	202	145	61	11	584	28332	9621	2359	109	10071	21	1283	189	112109	352	65	4559	735	194
Argyle54	1859	1	238	138	68	11	400	19162	5460	2311	91	8906	82	1508	64	104751	50	49	2681	1241	268
Argyle91	1392	20	517	120	28	8	-1	134548	7157	538	63	7345	85	979	90	8445	218	200	8867	182	35
Argyle252	1660	1	301	86	79	19	871	19809	9676	4042	113	19582	109	533	400	172574	1012	52	4033	767	270
Argyle302	922	10	78	46	25	3	128	45823	4112	728	32	4339	20	439	71	22381	156	65	8870	443	68
Argyle308	1793	0	1341	169	69	3	541	56422	5281	890	103	8623	28	725	83	115711	277	162	11038	563	210
Total	9662	34	2677	704	330	55	2523	304096	41307	10868	511	58866	345	5467	897	535971	2065	593	40048	3931	1045
Average	1610	6	446	117	55	9	421	50683	6885	1811	85	9811	58	911	150	89329	344	99	6675	655	174

Figure 18. Spectra and Photon Summaries of Eight Brass Buckles, Fort Argyle.

Brass and Silver Buttons

Ten brass and two silver buttons from Fort Argyle were included in the pXRF study. Figure 19 shows the spectra and photon counts from these samples.

Figure 19. Spectra and Photon Summaries for 10 Brass and 2 Silver Buttons, Fort Argyle.

Brass Spur

One brass spur fragment from Fort Argyle was included in the pXRF study. It was an early to mid-eighteenth-century English spur type that was recovered from the plow zone in the northeastern part of Fort Argyle. Figure 20 shows the spectra and photon summary for this item.

Figure 20. Spectra and Photon Summary for Brass Spur, Fort Argyle.

Coins

Two coins were recovered by LG2ES from its Fort Argyle project. Both were analyzed for their elemental content. The photon values for selected elements for these two artifacts is shown in Table 5. One was a copper-colored disc the approximate size of a British halfpence. It was recovered during the metal detector survey from the plow zone. Upon closer scrutiny that included comparing the disc diameter and weight to other examples of British halfpence minted in the reigns of George II and George III, I suspected that our Fort Argyle coin was a forgery. It turns out that British halfpence were notorious for being counterfeited in the eighteenth century. My suspicions were borne out when the disc was examined for its elemental content and compared with two other George II halfpence minted in 1737 and 1738. The 1737 and 1738 coins were nearly all copper in their composition, whereas the Fort Argyle disc contained substantial quantities of other, mostly cheaper metals, including Silver, Arsenic, Nickel, Lead, Tin and others minor components, as shown in Figure 21.

The other coin was a clipped Spanish cob real, with a Mexico mint mark recovered from F363, the north palisade ditch for Fort C. The silver cob coin was minted before 1732,

which is when milled Spanish coins began in production in Mexico. This coin was composed mostly of silver, although other metals were detected in it. These included Arsenic, Cadmium, Copper, Nickel, Lead, Antimony, Tin and Zirconium. The Fort Argyle specimen was compared to a roughly similar-aged silver cob coin, minted in Bolivia, and the two spectra are remarkably similar. The Fort Argyle silver coin is primarily composed of Silver with substantial amounts of Tin and minute amounts of Copper, and Arsenic as shown in Figure 22.

Historic Ceramics

A variety of historic ceramics from Fort Argyle were included in the pXRF study. These included: coarse earthenware, lead glazed; unrefined redware, lead glazed; English blue hand-painted delftware; Blue decorated Rhenish stoneware; Whieldon ware, green cauliflower motif; and undecorated creamware. The spectra and photon counts for all of these specimens combined is shown in Figure 20. Figure 21 shows the spectra and photon counts for three coarse earthenware sherds. These three sherds are glazed mostly with lead, but substantial amounts of Iron, Copper, Zinc, Arsenic, Zirconium and Tin also are present. The spectra of the other sherds were not studied in detail for this report.

Table 5. Photon Values for Two Coins, Fort Argyle.

		Ag K12	Ag L1	As K12	As L1	Cd K12	Cd L1	Cu K12	Kr K12	Kr L1	Ni K12	Pb L1	Pb M1	Sb K12	Sb L1	Sn K12	Sn L1	Zr K12	Zr L1
Counterfeit halfpence	Argyle273	2195	35	2148	90	286	0	27806	8137	74	983	33365	120	18480	262	58461	489	389	123
Silver coin	Argyle424	479395	1542	592	455	278	582	422	1180	600	339	978	30	-13	5	1189	1	397	175

Figure 21. Spectra and Photon Summary of Counterfeit British Halfpence, Fort Argyle.

Figure 22. Spectra and Photon Summary of Spanish Silver Coin, Fort Argyle.

Figure 23. Spectra and Photon Summaries of Various Historic Ceramics, Fort Argyle.

Figure 24. Spectra and Photon Summary for Three Coarse Earthenware, Lead Glazed Sherds, Fort Argyle.

Clay Tobacco Pipes

Three ball clay (kaolin) tobacco smoking pipe bowls from Fort Argyle were included in the study. All three were early to mid- eighteenth-century pipe tobacco bowl forms that

lacked any foot support. They bore no maker's mark or other design elements. All three displayed similar spectra, as shown in Figure 22.

Brick, Daub and Mortar

Six bricks or brick fragments from Fort Argyle were included in the pXRF study. These included two samples taken from the H-shaped double hearth (Feature 175F) and other samples from plow zone contexts. Their spectra and photon counts are shown in Figure 23.

Two daub fragments from Fort Argyle were included in the pXRF study. They included one sample that was fiber-tempered and another sand-tempered example that had well preserved wattle impressions. The spectra and photon counts for these two specimens are shown in Figure 24.

Zinc Activity Items

Zinc (Zn) is a lustrous metal with the atomic number 30 (Bleiwias and diFrancesco 2010; International Zinc Association 2017). It is found with lead ores. Zinc has a high melting point (787°F). Zinc has a value of 2.5-3 on Mohs hardness scale. Zinc was present in low frequencies in many of the lead balls in the pXRF study, but they displayed no particular trend as shown in Figure 25. Two suspected zinc artifacts in the Activities Group category also were included in the study and the spectra and photon counts for these two items are shown in Figure 26.

Figure 25. Spectra and Photon Summary for Three Clay (Kaolin) Tobacco Pipe Bowls.

Figure 26. Spectra and Photon Summaries for Six Bricks, Fort Argyle.

Figure 27. Spectra of Daub Samples (Fiber-tempered daub, shown in red; Daub with wattle impressions, shown in green), Fort Argyle.

Figure 28. Scatterplot of Zinc Photons by Increasing Caliber, Fort Argyle.

Figure 29. Spectra and Photon Summaries of Two Zinc Samples, Fort Argyle.

II. Summary

Elemental analysis of historic period artifacts from Fort Argyle has been shown to be useful in the interpretation and understanding of important aspects of the archaeological record. Many examples of this were shown in this report. The primary goal of LG2ES's pXRF study at Fort Argyle was the examination of lead ball ammunition. This report demonstrates that many other metal and ceramic items also have stories to tell when their elemental composition is analyzed.

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APPENDIX C: Ethnobotanical Analysis, LG²ES Excavations, 9BN28.

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Appendix C.

Archaeobotanical Remains from Fort Argyle (9BN28)

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Introduction

This report describes archaeobotanical remains recovered from Fort Argyle [9BN28], Georgia. Twelve flotation samples totaling 120 liters were analyzed. The samples are dominated by wood charcoal, particularly southern yellow pine (*Pinus* sp.). Trace amounts of plant debris are also present, including nutshell, corn, legume, and sumac (Tables 1 to 3). The recovered carbonized materials are heavily ground and fragmented, probably from the clay matrix.

Background

Archaeobotanical studies became more common in historic archaeology beginning in the 1990s (Andrews 2004; Holt 1991; Rossen 1992a; Scarry 1993). These studies are instrumental in understanding foodways, agricultural systems, market trade, and local environments, to give but a few examples. Historic archaeobotany (or paleoethnobotany) is essentially an adaptation to more recent materials of methods used in prehistoric archaeology. Much like prehistoric archaeobotany, the analysis of historic plant remains depends on the systematic and opportunistic field collection of soil samples and their processing by water flotation. At military sites such as Fort Argyle, archaeobotany may help understand the selection of wood for construction and other uses, as well as food provisioning in terms of both cultivated and wild collected plants. At military sites such as Camp Nelson, Kentucky, archaeobotanical remains contributed to more complex research issues such as understanding social stratification in terms of differential access to resources and disparities between archival sources and archaeological evidence (Rossen 2003).

Methods

Botanical remains are produced from archaeological sites using a method known as water flotation. Soil samples from the site are placed in a tank with agitated water, and the lighter charcoal and roots float to the surface and are collected separately (light fraction). Portions of the sample that sink are caught below in fine screen (heavy fraction).

Soil samples were floated at the author's Lutz, Florida lab. The dried samples were passed through a 2 mm geological sieve, before sorting charcoal from uncarbonized contaminants such as roots. Plant material such as wood and nutshell from the larger than 2 mm sample were identified, counted, and weighed. Sievings smaller than 2 mm were carefully scanned for seeds. Both light and heavy fractions were treated in this manner. This procedure is followed because fragments of wood and nutshell smaller than 2 mm are difficult to reliably identify. Charcoal specimens larger than 2 mm are representative of smaller specimens, with a few possible exceptions such as acorn nutshell

and squash and gourd rind (Asch and Asch 1975). Laboratory sieving thus saves considerable laboratory sorting time without a loss of information.

The samples were analyzed under an Olympus SZ40 binocular microscope at magnifications of 10 to 30x. Identification of materials was aided by a comparative collection of both archaeological and modern specimens, along with standard catalogs and databases (Cappers et al. 2009; Delorit 1970; Martin and Barkley 1973; U.S. Department of Agriculture 1948). Specimens were sorted by species, counted, and weighed to the nearest tenth of a gram. Macroscopic wood characteristics were observed from specimen cross-sections (Core et al. 1979; Panshin and deZeeuw 1970). Changes in the visibility of macroscopic characteristics that occur during carbonization were also accounted for, to insure maximum accuracy of identification (Rossen and Olson 1985; Smart and Hoffman 1988). Non-wood specimens that are badly deformed were classified as "unidentified-general" and one fragmented seed was classified as "unidentified-seed."

Archaeobotanical preservation and character of the samples

Archaeobotanical materials on open sites are usually carbonized, while uncarbonized, desiccated materials are considered modern, although there are important exceptions where desiccated remains are clearly concentrated in feature contexts (Rossen 2015). Archaeobotanical preservation varies greatly between sites for reasons that are only partially understood. Two factors that influence preservation are soil drainage and the chemical composition of midden deposits (such as soil pH and ash content). The circumstances surrounding plant carbonization, including firing temperature and the amount of oxygen reduction present, also influence preservation. Soil particle size and inclusions affect whether or not carbonized plant remains are eroded or destroyed by mechanical grinding.

The Fort Argyle soil samples consisted of heavy clay that had dried into brick-like clumps. Flotation was difficult and substantial manipulation of the soil was required to break clumps and release charcoal fragments. Once properly fragmented, the samples floated charcoal specimens. The resulting specimens are heavily eroded, reflecting mechanical grinding in the clay matrix. The scarcity of carbonized seeds and even modern desiccated seeds is indicative of this process. Most historic sites contain an abundance of desiccated seeds that reflect the present-day or in some cases the historic weedy flora of the site. These materials are virtually absent from these samples.

One sample (FS 314) exhibited a dark gray color that was different than the brown clay matrix of other samples. This may explain the relatively large amount of wood charcoal in this sample. However, this sample did not contain carbonized or desiccated seeds to indicate a substantive distinction in overall archaeobotanical preservation. A second sample (FS 334) contains numerous mouse feces, indicating substantial rodent disturbance of this context.

Analysis Results

Wood Charcoal

All twelve samples contain carbonized wood specimens (Tables 1 and 2). Pine heavily dominates the samples. Although a species identification cannot be made from small wood charcoal fragments, these are probably southern yellow pine (*Pinus* sp.), with its typical abrupt early to latewood transition and large, visible resin canals. Small amounts of red oak group and maple group are also present in three samples. The wood charcoal profile suggests that the samples contain construction materials rather than firewood samples, which should be more mixed.

Food plant remains

Field cultigens are present in trace amounts. These include corn (*Zea mays*) and possible bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*?). Both are Native American cultigens that were rapidly adopted by Euro-Americans. Corn is present in Feature 251 and TU 277. This includes two eroded kernel fragments and one cupule, the inedible outer layer of the cob that holds the kernels. The cupule has a length of 2.9 mm and a width of 4.8 mm. Since cupules run perpendicular to the cob, the long dimension is considered to be its width. The prehistoric corn of the eastern U.S. seaboard is known as “Eastern Eight,” an eight-row variety with open cupules that varied in cupule width from 5.0 to 11.6 mm (Rossen 1992b; Rossen and Turner, in press). In considering this size range and the present specimen, it must be remembered that The Fort Argyle specimen may be small due to its original size, its position at the end of a cob, or the conditions of carbonization and the resulting shrinkage. Thus, no firm conclusions can be made from a single specimen.

Likewise, the two legume specimens from Feature 221 are fragmentary and heavily eroded. Both specimens are dicotyledons, or two-part, halved seeds. Seedcoats are absent, however, precluding secure identification. One specimen measures 6.9 mm in length and 3.0 mm in width, within the lower end of the range of common bean, *Phaseolus vulgaris*.

Nutshell includes traces of hickory (*Carya* sp.) and a thin nutshell that may be acorn (*Quercus* sp.) or American chestnut (*Castanea dentata*). Nuts were a focal resource of Native Americans in this region, and nuts appear as a supplemental resource at historic military sites (Swanton 1946; Rossen 2003).

Two sumac seeds are present in TU 277. Sumac (*Rhus* sp) is quite common in prehistoric sites of the eastern U.S. A bush or small tree that produces edible berries, sumac is best-known for its use in a high Vitamin C tea and as a high energy food source and medicine (Gilmore 1931:47-48; Vogel 1982:378). Do these sumac seeds represent their historic use, the transfer of Native American knowledge to Euro-Americans at the site, or merely a fortuitous inclusion?

Summary

The collection and analysis of archaeobotanical materials at Fort Argyle was hampered by the heavy clay matrix, which ground and destroyed botanical materials that may have been present. The wood charcoal indicates a preponderance of pine in the fort construction. A small collection of corn, possible bean, hickory, thin nutshell (acorn or American chestnut), and sumac gives tantalizing evidence of plant food materials at the site.

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Table 1. Fort Argyle site archaeobotanical remains. Materials are all carbonized. All samples are 10 liters of soil.

<i>sample</i>	<i>species</i>	<i>freq</i>	<i>gm wt</i>
FS 293, TU 130	wood (pine)	424	5.8
Feat 221, 53-95bd	legume (bean?)	2	.0
	nutshell – small (acorn or American chestnut?)	1	.0
	unidentified – general (amorphous)	7	.0
FS 305, TU 131	wood (pine)	110	1.1
Feat 225, 31-51bd	nutshell – small (acorn or American chestnut?)	2	.0
FS 306, TU 144	wood (pine 95%, maple group 5%)	295	4.0
Feat 214, 78-94bd			
FS 314, TU 213	wood (pine)	626	7.1
Feat 362, 27-38bd	unidentified – general (amorphous)	8	.0
FS 318, Feat 363	wood (pine)	262	2.8
10-110bd			
FS 322, Feat 207	wood (pine)	269	6.0
50-80bd	hickory (<i>Carya</i> sp.)	2	.0
	unidentified – general (amorphous)	2	.0
FS 334, TU 220	wood (pine)	101	.9
Feat 175F, 23-25bd	(numerous mouse feces)		
FS 340, TU 218	wood (pine)	153	1.8
Feat 328, 41-64bd			
FS 387, TU 277	wood (pine 90%, red oak group 10%)	772	10.3
72-105bd	hickory (<i>Carya</i> sp.)	2	.0
	sumac (<i>Rhus</i> sp.)	2	--
	corn – kernel fragment (<i>Zea mays</i>)	1	.0
FS 430	wood (pine 80%, red oak group 20%)	195	2.3
Feature 251	nutshell – small (hickory?)	2	.0
48-66bd	nutshell – small (acorn or American chestnut?)	1	.0
	corn – cupule (<i>Zea mays</i>)	1	.0
	corn – kernel fragment	1	.0
	unidentified – general (amorphous)	2	.0
FS 434	wood (pine)	654	9.8
Feat 225 (299)	nutshell – small (hickory?)	2	.0
Level 3, 80-90bd	seed – fragment (no seedcoat)	1	--
	unidentified – general (amorphous)	4	.0
FS 441, TU 233	wood (pine)	442	5.6
Feat 401, 72-103bd			

Table 2. Wood charcoal from Fort Argyle site.

<i>species</i>	<i>freq</i>	<i>pct</i>	<i>gm wt</i>	<i>pct*</i>
pine (<i>Pinus</i> sp.)	4,172	97.0	55.8	97.0
red oak group (<i>Quercus</i> sp.)	116	2.7	1.5	2.6
maple group (<i>Acer</i> sp.)	15	0.3	0.2	0.3
Total wood charcoal	4,303	100.0	57.5	100.0

*percentages calculated to nearest 0.1%

Table 3. Food plant remains from Fort Argyle site.

<i>plant type/species</i>	<i>freq</i>	<i>gm wt</i>	<i>ubiquity</i>
Cultigens			
corn – kernel fragment	2	.0	.17
corn – cupule (<i>Zea mays</i>)	1	.0	.08
legume (<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> ?)	2	.0	.08
Nutshell			
hickory (<i>Carya</i> sp.)	7	.0	.33
acorn (<i>Quercus</i> sp.) or American chestnut (<i>Castanea dentata</i>)	5	.0	.25
Wild plant seeds*			
sumac (<i>Rhus</i> sp.)	2	--	.08
Miscellaneous			
unidentified – general (amorphous)	23	.0	
unidentified - seed fragment	1	--	

APPENDIX D: Palynology and Phytolith Analysis, LG²ES Excavations, 9BN28.

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Appendix D

POLLEN, PHYTOLITH, AND PARASITE ANALYSES OF SEDIMENT SAMPLES FROM FORT ARGYLE, 9BN28, BRYAN COUNTY, GEORGIA

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Jacksonville, Florida

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INTRODUCTION

The Fort Argyle Site (9BN28) is situated upon a bluff on the west bank of the Ogeechee River on the eastern margin of the modern Fort Stewart US Army Reservation in Bryan County, Georgia. The site contains the historical Fort Argyle, which was an important early colonial outpost (AD 1733–1767). Eleven sediment samples collected primarily from palisade trenches were submitted for pollen and phytolith analysis in conjunction with Phase III archaeological work. In addition, individual samples represent a cellar, a pit, and the chimney base. Parasite analysis was also conducted on one of the sediment samples (Sample 343) from a cellar in Zone A. Analyses were conducted to determine an environmental signature of Fort Argyle and its surroundings during and shortly following its occupation.

METHODS

Pollen and Parasite

Sediments often present unique challenges for pollen preservation and recovery, meaning that larger samples are required for land sediments than for pollen recovery from lake sediments or peat bogs. A chemical extraction technique based on flotation is the standard preparation technique used at PaleoResearch Institute for recovering pollen grains from sediments. This particular process was developed for extracting pollen from soils where the ratio of pollen to inorganic material is relatively low. Note that the successful recovery of pollen for analysis does not rely on the repetition of specific and individual steps in the laboratory alone, but rather requires mastery of extraction concepts, in addition to experience in how best to achieve desired results given different sediment matrices. As well as pollen analysis, one sample (Sample 343) from the Fort Argyle Site was also designated for parasite analysis. For recovery of parasite eggs, we used the same pollen extraction techniques here listed.

Hydrochloric acid (10%) was used to remove calcium carbonates if present in the sediment samples, after which, they were screened through a 250-micron mesh. Multiple water rinses were utilized until neutral employ Stoke's Law for settling time. After settling, the supernatant was poured off. A small quantity of sodium hexametaphosphate was mixed into each sample to suspend clay-sized particles prior to filling the beakers with water. Again, multiple rinses employing Stoke's Law and decanting facilitated clay removal. Treatment with sodium hexametaphosphate was repeated, as necessary, to remove clay. This process was repeated with ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA), which removes clay, soluble organics, and iron. Finally, the samples were freeze-dried under vacuum.

Once dry, the samples were mixed with sodium polytungstate (SPT), at a 1.8 g/ml density, and centrifuged to separate the organic material including pollen and starch, which floats, from the inorganic remains and silica, which do not float. The supernatant containing pollen and organic remains was decanted and retained. The sodium polytungstate process was repeated to recover all of the organics. Once the organics were recovered, the accumulated supernatant was centrifuged at 1,500 rpm for 10 minutes to allow small-sized silica to be separated from the organics. This supernatant was decanted into a 50-ml conical

tube and diluted with reverse osmosis deionized (RODI) water and centrifuged at 3,000 rpm to concentrate the organic fraction in the bottom of the tube. This pollen-rich organic fraction was rinsed, then all samples received a short (25 minute) treatment in hot hydrofluoric acid to remove remaining inorganic particles. The samples were acetylated twice for 10 minutes each to remove extraneous organic matter. The samples were rinsed with RODI water to neutral. Following this, a few drops of potassium hydroxide (KOH) were added to each sample, which was then stained lightly with safranin. Due to the presence of large quantities of minute organic debris, the samples were centrifuged at high speeds for short intervals to remove this debris for better viewing.

A light microscope was used to count pollen at a magnification of 500x. Pollen preservation in these samples varied from good to poor. An extensive comparative reference housed at PaleoResearch aided pollen identification to the family, genus, and species level, where possible.

Pollen aggregates were recorded during pollen identification. Aggregates are clumps of a single type of pollen and may be interpreted to represent either pollen dispersal over short distances or the introduction of portions of the plant represented into an archaeological setting. The aggregates were included in the pollen counts as single grains, as is customary. An "A" next to the pollen frequency on the percentage pollen diagram notes the presence of aggregates. A plus sign (+) on the pollen diagram indicates that the pollen type was observed outside the regular count while scanning the remainder of the microscope slide. The percentage pollen diagram was produced using Tilia Version 2.1.1. Total pollen concentrations were calculated in Tilia using the quantity of sample processed in cubic centimeters (cc), the quantity of exotics (spores) added to the sample, the quantity of exotics counted, and the total pollen counted and expressed as pollen per cc of sediment.

Pollen analysis also included observing and recording starch granules and, if they were present, their assignment to general categories. We did not, however, search for starches outside the pollen count. An additional search for starches is performed only when starch analysis is part of the suite of analyses performed. Starch granules are a plant's mechanism for storing carbohydrates. Starches are found in numerous seeds, as well as in starchy roots and tubers. The primary categories of starches include the following: with or without visible hila, hilum centric or eccentric, hila patterns (dot, cracked, elongated), and shape of starch (angular, ellipse, circular, or lenticular). Some of these starch categories are typical of specific plants, while others are more common and tend to occur in many different types of plants.

Parasite eggs are counted while examining the sample for pollen and starches. Then, the remaining portion of the microscope slide was scanned in search of parasite eggs. No parasite eggs were observed.

Phytolith

Extraction to recover phytoliths from the sediment samples is based primarily on our phytolith extraction method. First, 15 ml of sediment from each sample was placed in a beaker with bleach. After being agitated it was covered and allowed to stand overnight. The next day, beakers containing samples were filled with water and allowed to settle by gravity for one and

one-half hours, after which the supernatant was poured off. This rinse was repeated four times to remove the bleach. A small quantity (10 ml) of dilute (10%) potassium hydroxide (KOH) was added to each sample after the fourth rinse, allowed to sit for two minutes, and then the beakers were filled with water for another series of four rinses on the same schedule. Once these steps were complete, 15 ml of a 5% solution of sodium hexametaphosphate was mixed into each sample to suspend clay-sized particles. Again, the beakers were filled with water and allowed to settle by gravity for two hours, after which the clay-sized particles that were still in suspension were decanted. This was repeated four more times. The samples were then freeze-dried using a vacuum system, which freezes out all moisture at -107 °C and < 10 millitorr. The dried samples were mixed with sodium polytungstate (SPT, density 2.1 g/ml) and centrifuged to separate the phytolith fraction, which will float, from most of the inorganic silica fraction, which will not. The light fraction of each sample was retained and rinsed to remove the heavy liquid. The phytolith-rich fraction of each sample was rinsed in alcohol to remove any remaining water. Microscope slides were made by putting a drop of sample on a slide, allowing it to dry, then mixing with optical immersion oil prior to covering with a cover slip for counting with a light microscope at a magnification of 500x. A percentage and/or frequency diagram was produced using Tilia 2.0 and TGView 2.1.1.

ETHNOBOTANIC REVIEW

Evidence for the exploitation of numerous plants in historic times, both by broad categories and by specific example, can be found in ethnobotanic literature, as well as a variety of historic records. Ethnographic sources document the development and persistence of plant use from history to the present. References on plant domestication, cooking, and food cultures are often consulted when describing plants whose evidence we encounter in the pollen, phytolith, starch, or macrofloral records. Consultation of a broad range of ethnographic sources, both inside and outside the study area, has permitted an exhaustive review of potential plant uses for this project.

Many of the plants encountered in this project through the analysis of pollen and phytoliths potentially evidence food or medicinal resources, while others indicate weedy or ornamental plants that grew nearby. In addition, a few plants with medicinal qualities and used in prehistory likely persisted to historic times. However, from the start of the historic period to the present, North American cultures succumbed to well-documented knowledge loss regarding native plant use as they transitioned from subsistence to agricultural economies or otherwise adopted European cultivated plants and agricultural techniques. Forced displacement and transhumance throughout the historic period removed native peoples from their traditional environs, further exacerbating knowledge loss. As a result, neither a complete record for native uses of plants nor the transfer of such knowledge to and use by Europeans exists for consultation today.

Edible and Economically Important Plants

***Ilex* (Holly)**

Generally, the genus *Ilex* represents large, evergreen shrubs or vines with small, red, berry-like fruit that grow in thickets, clearings, on coastal plains, and damp, sandy woods. In North America, numerous native and several naturalized species are present. Species of *Ilex* mainly range east of the Mississippi River, throughout southeastern and eastern North America, but they also appear in states bordering the west bank of the Mississippi River, and as far west as Kansas, Oklahoma, and Texas.

I. cassine and *I. vomitoria*, the leaves of which contain caffeine, were used by native groups to make tea and as a stimulant and emetic for purification after making a “black drink”. Holly decoctions treated sore eyes, measles, and hay fever while berries were chewed for indigestion and colic (Couplan 1998:286,344; Moerman 1998:273; Peterson 1977:192; USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service 2014).

Cultigens

***Oryza sativa* (Rice)**

Oryza sativa is the principal food crop for about half of the global population. Although rice “is often thought to be a native of India, it probably originated in the warm, wet parts of southwestern China, Thailand or Malaya in about 7000 BC” (Phillips and Rix 1993:10). Today, there are about 2500 varieties of rice. Brown rice consists of the intact grain containing the bran layers. White rice has been milled and polished. About 15 percent of the protein in rice is lost in milling and polishing, as well as most of the amino acid lysine and the vitamin thiamine. Rice is most often cooked in water and consumed as individual grains (McGee 1984:237-239, 429).

Based on tracts collected by Peter Force in 1838 relating to the American colonies, *O. sativa* was first sown in North America in Virginia by Governor William Berkeley in 1647 (Hedrick 1972:399). E. L. Sturtevant, based on reports from the US Patents Office, suggests that *O. sativa* then appeared in South Carolina in 1694 when the captain of a Dutch brigantine sailing from Madagascar put in at Charles Town (modern Charleston) and gave Governor Thomas Smith a peck of paddy rice as a gift. Smith distributed the rice to his friends for cultivation (Hedrick 1972:399). However, Smith and Dilday (2003) refute both the 1647 and 1694 introductions of *O. sativa*, instead claiming that an English brigantine captained by John Thurber put to port in Charles Town in 1686 with rice from Madagascar aboard. Thurber gifted famed colonist Dr Henry Woodward a peck of paddy rice, and from Woodward the cultivation of *O. sativa* spread throughout the colony and, by 1800, much of the American southeast. Following the Civil War and the abolition of slavery (the practice by which the rice economy of the South depended), the production of *O. sativa* declined along the Atlantic coast. Today, *O. sativa* is grown mainly in the Gulf States, along the Mississippi, and in California (Smith and Dilday 2003:viii); (USDA Rice Yearbook 2019).

***Vitis* (Wild Grape)**

Vitis (wild grape) are native and introduced, woody, thornless, climbing shrubs or vines with round, edible fruits and three-lobed leaves that grow throughout the North America in thickets, along the edges of woods, climbing trees, and along streams, riverbanks, and wetlands often in sandy soils. The fruits ripen in the late summer and autumn and are round, few-seeded, juicy berries that can be purple, blue, black, red, or amber. Economic products of *Vitis* species include juice, wine, raisins, and jelly (Angell 1981:156; Brill and Dean 1994:165; Hickey and King 1981:253; Medsger 1966:53-59; USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service 2017; Zomlefer 1994:188). Grapes contain potassium, beta carotene, niacin, tartaric and malic acids, tannin, and vitamins A, B₁, B₂, C, and E (Brill and Dean 1994:167; Couplan 1998:297).

Grapes, the fruits of the *Vitis* species, are eaten raw; made into juice and wine, jelly, pies, and syrup; included in dumplings, stew, and mush; and dried for future use. Dried whole or mashed, grapes are used to make cakes or sweet breads (Couplan 1998:297; Medsger 1966:53-59; Moerman 1998:598-600). Young grape leaves, which contain niacin and beta carotene, are eaten raw, chewed to alleviate thirst, or boiled as greens (Angell 1981:156-158; Brill and Dean 1994:167; Couplan 1998:297; Moerman 1998:600; Peterson 1977:198). In certain Mediterranean and southwest Asian cultures, young *Vitis* species leaves can be used as the wrap for making *dolmas*, a stuffed-dish cuisine.

Many groups use various parts of the *Vitis* species as a tonic. Leaves are astringent and a leaf or seed infusion was used to treat bleeding, diarrhea, liver problems, headaches, fever, hepatitis, stomachache, and thrush (Brill and Dean 1994:168; Couplan 1998:297; Foster and Duke 1990:300; Moerman 1998:598-600). Bark infusions treated urinary problems while a root infusion or decoction treated rheumatism, purified blood, and was used as an emetic. Sap was used to keep hair healthy, and the vine was chewed for hiccups. Additionally, leaf poultices treated headaches, pain, snakebite, internal organ disorders, wounds, and fever (Foster and Duke 1990:300; Kirk 1975:265; Mead 2003:441; Moerman 1998:598-600). Grape skins contain resveratrol, which has been shown to help prevent heart disease (Brill and Dean 1994:167).

Vitis species are native to both Asia Minor and North America. Its fruits have been cultivated for millennia, especially for wine-making. Early Neolithic pottery from Georgia in the South Caucasus region, suggest wine-making began as early as 8000 years ago (McGovern et al. 2017). Most wines and table grapes come from varieties of the European species *Vitis vinifera* (Kiple and Ornelas 2000:1781; McGee 1984:187). Columbus introduced *Vitis vinifera* to the New World, where its cultivation can be dated to 1494 in Haiti. *Vitis vinifera* cultivation in the North American colonies ultimately failed due to harsh climate and exposure to disease and pests to which European grapes had no resistance. Subsequently, it was hybridized with North American *Vitis* species to increase its hardiness (Hedrick 1972:603-604). *Vitis* species native to the United States produce edible purple, blue, black, or amber fruit. Often, wild grapes are too tart to be eaten raw, but are used in jams, jellies, and juices (Angell 1981:156). American grape jelly, juice, and northeastern wines are made from Concord grapes, a variety of the American species *Vitis labrusca* (fox grape) (Hedrick 1972:603-604).

***Zea mays* (Maize, corn)**

Zea mays (corn, maize) is a New World cultigen in the Poaceae (grass) family. Endosperm composition allows identification of five different maize types. Flour corn, often used by Native Americans, is starchy with little protein. Popcorn and flint corn have hard starch and more protein than other varieties. Dent corn has a waxy starch, and sweet corn contains little starch and is mostly sugar (Heiser 1990:95; McGee 1984:241). Experimental processing reveals maize pollen on husks, silks, in shelled maize, and in ground maize flour (Scott Cummings, personal communication, 1983).

Z. mays evolved in the southern highlands of Mexico from the annual grass, teosinte. Maize is a staple of many groups around the world and is the second most cultivated crop in the world (Cushing 1920:267; Kiple and Ornelas 2000:99-100; Mangelsdorf 1974:122-125; McGee 1984:240). At the species level, maize demonstrates great variability in kernel color, size, and shape; in ear size and shape; and in maturation time. Maize kernel colors include white, yellow, blue, red, and black, and combinations of these (Heiser 1990:95; Huckell and Toll 2004:45; Kiple and Ornelas 2000:99-100; Whiting 1939:67-70).

Z. mays is known to have been cultivated in the southwestern United States since approximately 1500 BC, and likely earlier (by ca. 2000 BC). Madsen (1989:7) places the beginning of Fremont maize cultivation in Utah by 2000 years ago. Maize reached the northeastern United States by at least AD 200, and likely earlier and is noted in eastern Florida around AD 750 (Milanich 1998:45). The Great Plains acted as a gene flow barrier, resulting in eastern maize species that are enzymatically different than their southwestern counterparts. Northeastern introduction began with minor crops that were grown in small quantities for hundreds of years. However, by the Late Woodland period, maize had become the principal food crop and was the focus of many northeastern tribes' activities (Heiser 1990:89). At European contact, "maize was the most widely grown plant in the Americas, extending from southern Canada to southern South America, growing at sea level in some places and at elevations higher than eleven thousand feet in others" (Heiser 1990:89).

Often, maize was husked immediately upon harvesting. Ears were dried on the roofs of homes, and ristras of maize were hung inside from the roof. Whole ears or shelled kernels were stored for future use. Shelled maize was stored in bark containers, large baskets, and underground storage pits (Hurt 1987:40; Robbins et al. 1916:83-93; Stevenson 1915:73-76; Vestal 1952:18-19; Whiting 1939:67-70).

Early-ripening maize was picked while still green and roasted on the cob, while late-ripening maize was made into bread (Hurt 1987:40). Because pollen is retained on the silks and silks are very difficult to remove entirely from the kernels while shucking maize or even when removing kernels from the cobs, pollen is introduced into the prehistoric food record. In addition, corn silks were dried and ground with parched maize to add sweetness, adding even more pollen to the food and archaeological record. Although maize is frequently husked immediately upon harvesting (Cushing 1920:264-267; Kiple and Ornelas 2000:107; Moerman 1998:610-612), which reduces the quantity of maize pollen introduced into archaeological proveniences, pollen is still retained on the silks, and hence is mixed with the shelled maize that may ultimately be ground.

An infusion of corn silks (collected before pollination) was used for many urinary tract disorders such as incontinence, infection, and kidney stones (Rogers 1980:42). Maize was used ceremonially by many tribes, and as well as for making toys, containers, thatch, cigarette paper, ribbons, and ceremonial items. Often, cornmeal was colored with *Atriplex* (saltbush) ashes. Black maize was made into dye for basketry, textiles, and body paint. Clean husks were saved for smoking and other uses, such as wrapping food. Maize pollen was widely used in various rituals and ceremonies (Robbins, et al. 1916:83-93; Stevenson 1915:73-76; Vestal 1952:18-19; Whiting 1939:67-70).

Green corn was eaten fresh, and mature ears were roasted or wrapped in husks and boiled. Dried kernels were ground into a multipurpose flour. Maize was eaten boiled, baked, popped, parched, or dried for later use or grinding into meal. It was made into mushes, *pinole*, a variety of breads and cakes, dumplings, porridge, and hominy (*pozole*). Maize served to feed both humans and livestock. In addition to a variety of preparations, ripe kernels could be dried, parched, and ground into meal or flour or hulled with lye from ashes to make hominy (Gilmore 1977:15). Hominy is made by soaking kernels in lye water created with ash, which removes the outer skin of the kernels (Gilmore 1977:15). Dried maize was boiled, often with meat and dried pumpkin or squash, or ground into meal that was used to make bread, mush, or dumplings (Hurt 1987:40; Moerman 1998:612). Parched maize was frequently served as a beverage similar to coffee (Moerman 1998:611). Easily transportable, both ground maize flour and a thin bread made from it provided a useful travel food (Elmore 1944:28; Stevenson 1915:73-74). Whole ears also were boiled and eaten. The corn smut fungus *Ustilago* also was used for food. The fungi were gathered when the spores were firm and ripe, and boiled (Rogers 1980:42).

Cherokee cultivated small private gardens that usually were fenced off to protect crops from horses. Harvesting and new seed planting occurred in the spring so that birds would not disturb new seeds. Portions of private crops were donated to the chief (Hurt 1987:32).

Maize was the most important agricultural product for native groups in Florida. Ears were harvested and stored in cribs or warehouses with palm-leaf roofs for later use, or were husked and shelled for more immediate use. Kernels were ground into flour using log mortars and long wooden pestles. The ground maize meal was eaten as porridge or gruel, often containing meat and other foods, or baked into cakes. For the Timucua, planting, harvesting, storing, and preparing maize was accompanied by prayers, offerings, and rituals. Both Apalachee and Timucua groups cleared the land by burning the brush; then, the soil was prepared for planting using hoes made from sticks, shells, and bone (Hurt 1987:27-28; Milanich 1998:43).

Today, maize is used for food, starch, alcohol, sweetener, and animal feed. It is still a staple for millions of people in developing nations in Latin America, Africa, and Asia. In North America, maize is grown in garden plots, as well as large commercial farms, as in the Midwest "corn belt." Maize is often consumed fresh when in season, and canned or frozen kernels provide maize the remainder of the year. In addition, dried kernels are ground to produce cornmeal. The kernels of a variant, popcorn, are heated and popped before consumption. Maize is fermented into bourbon whiskey (Rhoades 1993:92-117).

Weeds

Muenscher (1980:3) describes weeds as:

... those plants that grow where they are not wanted. Whether a plant of a given species is considered a weed depends not only on its characteristics and habitats, but also on its relative position with reference to other plants and man.

Often weeds are able to thrive in diverse and adverse circumstances. Commonly, weeds are found in disturbed areas or in places undesirable to other plants. Many weed species produce enormous quantities of seeds, which are widely dispersed. Other weed species are capable of reproducing vegetatively. These factors combine to produce a plant that is very successful in competition with other plant species. The word "weed" is assigned here to those plants that were most likely not eaten, but rather were part of the grassy environment or lawn or grew around foundations.

Low-Spine Asteraceae (Ragweed Group)

The Asteraceae (sunflower) family is the world's largest family of dicots, consisting mostly of herbaceous plants, usually with a taproot (Hickey and King 1981:418; Hickman 1993:174; Zomlefer 1994:203). Members of the Low-spine Asteraceae (Ambrosieae) group are weedy, herbaceous plants that grow in fields, meadows, waste places, in drainages, along waterways, in disturbed sites, and along roadsides (Hickman 1993:193-194; Muenscher 1980:422-425). The pollen grains are buoyant and more capable of transport on the wind over longer distances than those of most members of the High-spine group. The plants usually pollinate in late summer or early autumn and cause allergic reactions in many people (Niering and Olmstead 1979:355-356).

Low-spine Asteraceae taxa include wind-pollinated plants such as *Ambrosia* (ragweed), *Xanthium* (cocklebur), and *Iva* (sumpweed) that have pollen with spines (echinae) less than 2.0 μm in length. They also possess other defined morphologic characteristics (Kapp 1969).

***Commelina* (Dayflower)**

Commelina (dayflower) is an herbaceous, perennial monocot with mostly blue flowers. It grows in rocky woods and hillsides, scrub oak woods, pine woods and barrens, sand dunes, hummocks, shale barrens, rock outcrops, roadsides, railroad rights-of-way, fields, and occasionally as a weed in cultivated ground (Bailey and Bailey 1976:300-301; Grimm 1993:39). In some areas *Commelina* seeds are eaten by quail during winter (Kamees et al. 2008:3, 15).

Commelina seed phytoliths have been recovered in samples representing ground stone tools, hearth and thermal features, vessel fill and wash samples, storage pits, pipe residue, ceramic residue, and midden sediments in numerous studies in New Mexico, Texas, Georgia (Yost and Cummings 2010b), and Ohio (Scott Cummings and Yost 2009). In our largest study, *Commelina* seed phytoliths were recovered in 348 of 500 thermal feature samples (69%) from southeast New Mexico (Scott Cummings and Kovácik 2013). We have also recovered *Commelina* seed phytoliths from historic agricultural fields in Canada (Yost 2010b) and Connecticut (Yost 2010a), and from stone-lined prehistoric agricultural fields in Argentina (Yost

and Cummings 2010a). The most striking recovery was of thousands of *Commelina* seed phytoliths in sediments beneath an intact/fractured Jornada Brown bowl left in place within a thermal feature in southeastern New Mexico (Scott Cummings et al. 2009). Even the vessel residue exhibited *Commelina* seed phytoliths. Although *Commelina* seed phytoliths have been recovered from this variety of cultural contexts, there is no ethnographic evidence of their intentional use. *Commelina* greens, on the other hand, are well known as an edible potherb (Goode 1989:77).

Because species of *Commelina* are well known weeds of agricultural fields around the world, it is possible their incorporation into archaeological records at sites with other evidence of agricultural activity represents inadvertent incorporation into harvested plant stores and processed foodstuffs.

Because of their mucilaginous tissues, *Commelina* plant material may have been a particularly good steam generator and buffering layer in earth ovens. Although a wide variety of foods, both plant and animal, can be cooked using earth ovens, these ovens are particularly effective at cooking starchy or inulin-rich roots and tubers, as well as cactus pads and mesquite pods. When recovered from earth ovens it is possible *Commelina* seed phytoliths represent collection of the plants while they bore seeds (Simpson 2010).

***Commelina diffusa* (Climbing dayflower)**

Commelina diffusa is a non-native plant that was introduced to the United States from Asia (Austin 1985). *Commelina diffusa* var. *gigas* is noted to grow in portions of the Everglades and Big Cypress National Preserve in hammocks, streamsides, ditches, cypress swamps, wet woods, and lake shores (Faden 2000). *Commelina diffusa* is a common weed of many different types of agricultural crops, especially in the New World, and in particular, in southeastern portions of the United States where white rice (*Oryza sativa*) was once or still is cultivated (Wilson 1981). It's possible that *Commelina diffusa* was introduced to Florida when sugar cane and rice were first cultivated in the mid- to late 1700's (Barkworth and Terrell 2007; Sitterson 1937).

Sporormiella

Sporormiella, an ascomycete fungus, grows only on herbivore dung in sub-boreal and temperate regions. Produced from ascospores on the surface of drying dung, *Sporormiella* spores spread passively to nearby vegetation, where they are then often ingested inadvertently by grazing herbivores (Davis and Shafer 2006). Many coprophilous fungi, such as *Sporormiella*, rely on a cyclic process involving herbivore ingestion of spores with foliage, germination of spores following passage through the gut, mycelial growth within, and eventual sporulation on the surface of drying dung (Wicklów et al. 1980). Ascospores, the fruiting bodies on dung, contain millions of individual spores, contributing to the environmental record in areas where dense herbivore populations exist (Aptroot and Geel 2006). Depending on a sample's context, *Sporormiella* recovery in archaeological samples can indicate the presence of herbivores or the possible use of their byproducts. Interpretations range from the presence of dung on the landscape, to burning dung for fuel, to the consumption of intestinal material for cooking and subsistence.

Following the historic introduction of grazing animals, *Sporormiella* becomes more abundant in Historic Period sediments. Numerous palynological studies document this increased occurrence in historic samples (Davis 1987). *Sporormiella* fungal spores are recoverable not only from introduced herbivores, but also, bison, moose, wild sheep, deer, elk, caribou, and rabbit dung. Increased recovery of *Sporormiella* spores in historic sediments may relate to changing land use patterns, as well as the increased time length that herds occupy any given area.

DISCUSSION

The Fort Argyle Site lies alongside the Ogeechee River, approximately 23.5 km southwest of central Savannah, Georgia. The northeast/southwest-trending I-95 freeway corridor crosses the Ogeechee approximately 5.25 km downstream from the site. Upstream of the site, the Ogeechee is freshwater, narrower, and split into numerous tributaries. The site lies at a bend in the river where the river itself is broader, deeper, and just within the tidal zone (Elliott 1997:3-4). Further downstream, the Ogeechee becomes much wider and brackish, reflecting similar tidewater streams in the region. Arboreal populations include *Taxodium distichum* (bald cypress), *Liquidambar styraciflua* (sweetgum), and *Nyssa sylvatica* (tupelo) (Rita Elliott, personal communication, 18 May 2019).

The initial erection of Fort Argyle came in late 1733 as an extension of both the influence James Oglethorpe of the Trustees of the Georgia colony out of Savannah and the British Army, specifically the South Carolina Rangers (1723 muster) (Elliott 1997:28; Gober Temple and Coleman 1961:42-43). The land was ceded by treaty between the Trustees and the Mvskoke (Creek), with the intended purpose of fortification against incursions from the Spanish colony at St. Augustine, Florida. Its location on a low prominence on the west bank of the Ogeechee made Fort Argyle a key defensible outpost along the so-called Southern Frontier. Between 1733–1737, up to 50 rangers were stationed at the fort under the authority of the Assembly of South Carolina, with the intention of cultivation, settlement, and improvements, both military and otherwise. Initially, significant trade did not pass through forts or ports on the Georgian frontier, but rather through longer-established Carolinian settlements, especially Charles Town (modern Charleston). Gradually, with the growth of the tidewater economy in Georgia, regional trade and political control shifted to Savannah.

To better understand agriculture in the region of Fort Argyle, it helps to visit the broader machinations of the politics and economy of Georgia during the 18th century. The Trustee government's initial plans for the Georgia colony (often called the Georgia or Oglethorpe Plan) traced their roots to Enlightenment ideals, particularly those of John Locke (Floyd Smith 1985:17). As such, Georgia differed from its northern neighbor on a number of policies, at least up to the reversion of colonial control to Parliament in 1751. Paramount of these policies was an act banning slavery in the colony to provide indentured servants (primarily those imprisoned in Britain for debts), as well as other Europeans (primarily Protestants, such as a group expelled by the Prince-Archbishop of Salzburg), a hard-earned opportunity for economic independence (Gober Temple and Coleman 1961:56). In contrast with South Carolina, where a small echelon of landowners relied on slavery to exploit expansive rice (*Oryza sativa*) and indigo (*Indigofera* spp.) plantations in the tidewater, the Trustees encouraged Georgian settlers

to undertake cultivation of products requiring less intensive labor, such as wine (*Vitis vinifera*) and silk (Floyd Smith 1985:17).

Widespread resentment of the Georgia Plan was based on several factors including the geology of the coastal plain, colonists generally unaccustomed to agriculture, and a complex land-tenure system (Gober Temple and Coleman 1961:262-263). Land along the Ogeechee, like much of the land in the Atlantic coastal plain in the region, is generally composed of sandy-loam soils (Wilkes et al. 1974:29). As experienced by colonist Thomas Causton, topsoil deposition is uncommon, and, due to low absorption, extensive drainage is necessary for cultivation of crops such as corn (*Zea mays*) (Stewart 1996:66; Wilkes, et al. 1974:29). Many of the British colonists, whether lured by the prospects expounded by the Trust or serving as indentured servants, came from urban backgrounds and were initially unprepared to cultivate such a challenging landscape (Stewart 1996:55-56). The Trust provided seed for crops to Georgia colonists, and those seeds were often ill-suited for the environs, resulting in poor crop yields prior to 1740 (Stewart 1996:54-60). In some cases, particularly in the instances of the expelled Salzburgers who were more agriculturally savvy, production of so-called Indian corn and squashes was successful on the small scale, but could not compete with the scale or price of products from South Carolina. Compounding the challenges of geology and expertise, a land-tenure system devised to prevent the rise of a landed gentry (as well as the settlement of non-British populations too close together) prohibited granting more than 500 acres divided into parsed-out 50-acre lots to any one individual (Ready 1974; Stewart 1996 #11529:56). Planting mulberry trees for use in the silk trade was also required as part of a land grant, which further reduced the amount of cultivable land (Ready 1974:353). The Trust thereby quashed large-scale irrigation and settlement relocation through untenable policy. Although cracks in the Georgia Plan were evident by 1748, the Trust was not disbanded until 1751, after which economic and agricultural practices more in tune with those of South Carolina were adopted. In the ten years following the transition of Georgia to a crown colony in 1755, the economic complexion dramatically shifted from small yeoman farmsteads to large slaveholding plantations (Gober Temple and Coleman 1961:262-263).

Agricultural production shifted, too, with rice and indigo, as well as corn and peas (*Pisum sativum*), increasing in export from Savannah by as much as 3.5 times from 1755 to 1763 (Floyd Smith 1985:22-23). Slavery, previously banned in Georgia, quickly became a critical component of wealth following the repeal of the ban in 1751, with several prominent landowners establishing up to two-thirds of their property wealth from the practice by 1850 (Floyd Smith 1985:5). Acreage previously divvied up in small lots was now granted in larger, consecutive tracts, such as it was for the Butler family near Fort Argyle in 1760 (Elliott 1997:86-87). These wealthy landowners quickly consolidated their freeholdings in lowland Georgia, wherein there were only 71 rice planters in Georgia by 1850, which contrasts with South Carolina's 256 in the same year (Floyd Smith 1985:10).

White rice (*O. sativa*) purportedly was introduced to South Carolina in 1686 from a cache of seed brought from Madagascar (Smith and Dilday 2003:vii-viii). By the end of the 17th century, rice production became the primary commodity exported from South Carolina. Red rice (*O. glaberrima*), native to the Niger River in western Africa and known colloquially as 'Guinea rice' or 'bearded rice', appears to have been a staple in the diet of slaves in Georgia by the end of the 18th century (Carney 2001:387-388). Interestingly, Thomas Jefferson attempted to introduce Guinea rice throughout higher elevations of the Deep South, but widespread

production for commercial trade was halted due to low-yields resulting from problems in milling (Carney 2001:388). Additional strains of red rice (*O. punctata* and *O. longistaminata*), known colloquially as 'Volunteer' rice and also native to Africa, were found at Georgia plantations, but were considered weeds and not harvested as commodities (Stewart 1996:160).

Production techniques stemming from West African traditions already in use in South Carolina also appear in Georgia in the 18th century (Chaplin 1992:31-33; Stewart 1996:93). Trade and exchange between the Georgia (and, more broadly, Southern) gentry and Europeans, particularly the Dutch, gradually altered rice production (Chaplin 1992:36). Irrigation technology improved throughout the second half of the 18th century, with tidal planting quickly reclaiming brackish and marshy land throughout the Georgia lowlands (Chaplin 1992:39-40). The effects of irrigation can still be seen in satellite imagery of the landscape, particularly north of the Ogeechee (Whitley 2008:Figure 3).

As with rice, indigo production ballooned in Georgia in the years leading up to and following the American Revolution (Floyd Smith 1985:20-23). The production of indigo in South Carolina, and later Georgia, notably increased beginning in 1740 due to constraints in the global market imposed by King George's War and the Seven Years War and the preference for sugar and coffee cultivation over indigo in Britain's colonies in the West Indies (Rembert 1979:129). Probably three different species of indigo were cultivated for export in Georgia: French indigo (*I. tinctoria*), Guatemalan indigo (*I. suffruticosa*), and Carolinian indigo (*I. caroliniana*).

Production of corn continued in Georgia beyond 1750. Commercially, the place of corn fell well below the levels of production in rice and indigo (Floyd Smith 1985:23-24,116). Instead, corn became a crucial part of domestic production, used as the primary foodstuff for slaves and in plantation gardens (Swanson 2011:135).

Pollen and phytolith analyses were conducted on 11 sediment samples from a variety of locations at the Fort Argyle Site (Table 1). Pollen and phytolith samples were collected from the cellar (Sample 343), a pit (Sample 315), the base of the chimney (Sample 333), and five locations along the Palisade Trench (Samples 292, 304, 317, 384, 386, 429, 433, and 442). The sample from the cellar, Sample 343, was also examined for parasite eggs.

The pollen record in Sample 343, collected from the cellar, was dominated by *Pinus* pollen (Table 2 and Figure 1), reflecting growth of pine trees in the vicinity of the fort. Other trees are represented by *Alnus* (alder), *Ostrya/Carpinus* (hop hornbeam/hornbeam), *Quercus* (oak), *Carya* (hickory), *Ilex* (holly), *Liquidambar*, and *Salix* (willow) pollen. *Ilex* species are classified as trees here due to the fact that they grow to reach a height of 25 m (82 ft). Poaceae pollen, representing grasses, was sub-dominant in the sample. Small quantities of Amaranthaceae, *Artemisia*, *Cirsium*, Low-spine Asteraceae, High-spine Asteraceae, Brassicaceae, *Melilotus*, *Eriogonum*, *Persicaria*, Rosaceae, and *Sphaeralcea* pollen reflect local growth of plants in the goosefoot/amaranth family, sagebrush or wormwood, thistle, ragweed, other plants in the sunflower family, members of the mustard family, clover, wild buckwheat, knotweed that prefers wet locations, members of the rose family, and globe mallow. Recovery of small quantities of cf. *Oryza* and *Z. mays* pollen suggest the possibility that rice and corn were stored in the cellar. A small quantity of monolete and trilete spores were recovered in this sample, indicating that ferns also were part of the local landscape. The cellar sample yielded a

moderately small quantity of microscopic charcoal. Total pollen concentration is calculated as nearly 3500 pollen per cubic centimeter (cc) of sediment. No parasite eggs were observed either in the pollen count or while scanning this sample.

The phytolith record for the cellar yielded moderate quantities of elongate and bulliform phytoliths (Figure 2), which are typical of grasses and sedges. Bulliforms are the cells that control leaf rolling in response to drought. In grasses, most elongate forms and most bulliforms are not considered diagnostic. Cultivated rice, however, is one of the grasses that produce a diagnostic bulliform. In light of the fact that grass short cells are far more abundant than the sedge short cells, the majority of these non-diagnostic forms are presumed to represent grasses. Trichomes, observed in a moderately small quantity in this sample, are silicified hairs on grass and sedge leaves and are not diagnostic beyond this level.

Phytoliths typical of festucoid or cool season grasses observed in Sample 343 include rondel and trapeziform phytoliths. Saddle-shaped phytoliths represent chloridoid or short season grasses that thrive in hot, dry conditions of summer. Panicoid or tall grasses are represented by bilobate, cross, and polylobate forms. Tall grasses thrive in hot, humid conditions, growing in areas with moisture sediment than do short grasses. A few *Oryza*-type bulliforms were observed, which supports the observation of *Oryza* pollen in the same sample and the interpretation that rice was present in the cellar. A few *Commelina* seed phytoliths were noted, suggesting that dayflower was a common weed, perhaps growing in an agricultural area. All of the *Commelina* seed phytoliths were badly eroded, so they were not identified to species level. Introduction of these seeds and their phytoliths into the cellar record might represent transport with rice when it was harvested. Throughout this report we interpret the presence of *Commelina* seed phytoliths as indicating accidental presence of these seeds within each feature, as the seeds probably were harvested along with the rice. Diatoms and sponge spicules and spherasters are present in Sample 343 and also might have been transported with the rice since many of these forms are associated with wet habitats.

Sample 315, removed from a pit located in Block AD, yielded a pollen record dominated by *Pinus* pollen, reflecting local growth of pine trees. Small quantities of *Ostrya/Carpinus*, *Quercus*, *Carya*, *Ilex*, *Liquidambar*, and *Ulmus* (elm) pollen were also present. The Poaceae pollen frequency was moderate. Small quantities of Amaranthaceae, Low-spine Asteraceae, High-spine Asteraceae, Brassicaceae, Cyperaceae, *Euphorbia*, and *Sphaeralcea* pollen represent plants in the goosefoot/amaranth family, ragweed, other plants in the sunflower family, members of the mustard family, sedges, spurge, and globemallow. Sample 315 also contained small quantities of cf. *Oryza* and *Z. mays* pollen, suggesting that the pit contained both rice and corn. A large quantity of trilete spores was observed, suggesting the probability that ferns were used in some capacity in this pit. Monolete spores were less well represented, suggesting that this type of fern is represented here only as part of the environmental signature. Microscopic charcoal was not particularly abundant and total pollen concentration is calculated at nearly 4850 pollen per cc of sediment.

The phytolith record from Sample 315 yielded moderate quantities of bulliform and elongate phytoliths representing grasses in general. Cool season or festucoid grasses are represented by small quantities of rondel and trapeziform phytoliths. Saddle-shaped chloridoid phytoliths are more abundant, representing short grasses and suggesting hot, dry conditions during part of the summer. Tall grasses are represented by bilobate and cross-shaped

phytoliths, forming the panicoid group. Trichomes and interstomatal cells represent grasses or sedges in genera. No Cyperaceae (sedge family) phytoliths were observed in this sample. Phytoliths indicating the presence of dicotyledenous plants (dicots) include tabular and parallelepiped forms. Both *Oryza* bulliforms and *Commelina* seed phytoliths were observed in this sample, indicating that this pit also was used to process rice. A few diatoms and sponge spherasters and spicules were observed that were probably transported along with the rice.

Sample 333 was collected from the base of a chimney in Block T. The pollen signature from this location was similar to that noted elsewhere at the site in many respects. It was dominated by *Pinus* pollen and exhibited small quantities of *Acer* (maple), *Ostrya/Carpinus*, Cupressaceae (juniper/swamp cypress family), *Quercus*, *Carya*, and *Liquidambar* pollen. Previously, the acronym TCT was used to indicate pollen that is very similar in morphology that represents trees or shrubs in the Taxodiaceae (swamp cypress family), Cupressaceae, and Taxaceae (yew family). More recently all but one of the genera that comprise Taxodiaceae (swamp cypress family) have been merged into the Cupressaceae. There are no members of Taxaceae noted to grow in Georgia, according to the USDA Plants Database.

The Poaceae pollen frequency is small in Sample 333, and nearly equal to the frequency of Low-spine Asteraceae pollen. Small quantities of Amaranthaceae, *Artemisia*, High-spine Asteraceae, Liguliflorae, Brassicaceae, Cyperaceae, *Dalea*, *Eriogonum*, and *Sphaeralcea* pollen reflect local growth of plants in the goosefoot/amaranth family, wormwood, members of the sunflower family, plants in the chicory tribe of the sunflower family such as dandelion, members of the mustard family, sedges, prairie clover, wild buckwheat, and globemallow. This sample contained small quantities of both *Oryza* and *Z. mays* pollen, reflecting the presence of rice and corn in the vicinity of the chimney. Monolete and trilete spores represent locally growing ferns. Microscopic charcoal was moderately abundant. Total pollen concentration is calculated at nearly 3200 pollen per cc of sediment.

The phytolith record for Sample 333 is very similar to others from this site in composition of bulliform, elongate, and trichome phytoliths, which are interpreted to represent primarily grasses. Few phytoliths observed were typical of festucoid grasses and include rondels and trapeziforms. Saddles typical of chloridoid grasses were not particularly abundant in this sample. Instead, bilobates, typical of panicoid grasses, were moderately abundant. *Oryza*-type bulliforms were observed in a slightly elevated frequency, and *Commelina* seed phytoliths were also noted. Diatoms and sponge spherasters and spicules that likely were introduced with rice were present.

The Palisade Trench was sampled in five locations. Palisade Trench North provided four samples from three locations, Block Z (Samples 433 and 442), Block W (Sample 429), and Block AD (Sample 317). Note that the pit, which is represented by Sample 315, was also located in Block AD. Two samples (Samples 292 and 304) were collected from Palisade Trench East in Block X. Another two samples (Samples 384 and 386) were recovered from part of the southwest corner of the Triangular Fort in Block AA.

Two samples from Block Z—Sample 442 recovered from Feature 401 and Sample 433 obtained from Feature 299a—yielded pollen records dominated by *Pinus* pollen, reflecting the local pine forest. Using the quantity of *Pinus* pollen displayed in Sample 442 as a benchmark, all of the Palisade Trench North and East samples exhibited at least as much *Pinus* pollen as

Sample 442, with the single exception of Sample 429 collected in Block W, which is situated near the cellar. Sample 429 displayed the largest Low-spine Asteraceae pollen frequency of this study, indicating considerable land disturbance that swamped the pollen record and created the anomaly.

All of the Palisade Trench North and East samples exhibit Poaceae, representing grasses, as the sub-dominant pollen taxon. Trees are represented in the Palisade Trench North and East samples by a variety of pollen, of which *Quercus* is the most abundant. Small quantities of *Acer*, *Alnus*, *Betula* (birch), *Ostrya/Carpinus*, Cupressaceae, *Fraxinus* (ash), *Ilex*, *Carya*, *Liquidambar*, *Salix*, and *Ulmus* pollen are observed in some or all of the Palisade Trench North and East samples. This mixture of pollen represents trees growing in a mixed forest along the Ogeechee.

Amaranthaceae, Low-spine Asteraceae, and High-spine Asteraceae pollen, representing plants in the goosefoot/amaranth family, ragweed and related plants, and other plants in the sunflower family, were observed in all of the Palisade Trench North and East samples. Small quantities of Apiaceae (umbel family), *Artemisia*, *Cirsium*, Liguliflorae, Brassicaceae, *Convolvulus* (bindweed), Cyperaceae, Ericaceae (heath/blueberry family), *Euphorbia* (spurge), *Dalea* (prairie clover), Fabaceae (legume family), *Eriogonum* (wild buckwheat), *Persicaria* (wetland knotweed), Rhamnaceae (buckthorn family), Rosaceae (rose family), and *Sphaeralcea* (globemallow) pollen, were noted in one, some, many, or all of the Palisade Trench North and East samples.

Small quantities of *Oryza*-type pollen were observed in all of the North and East Palisade Trench samples. This recovery suggests ubiquitous presence of rice at the fort, most likely as a result of local cultivation. A small quantity of *Vitis* (grape) pollen, representing grapes, was noted in Sample 292, collected from Feature 221 in Palisade Trench East. Finally, small quantities of *Z. mays* pollen were observed in three of the Palisade Trench North samples. This record suggests that rice was more actively cultivated than was corn at Fort Argyle during the period represented by these samples.

Monolete and trilete spores were present in all samples, indicating that ferns grew in the local ecosystem. *Osmunda* spores, representing deciduous ferns that grow in woodland bogs and on the banks of streams, were observed in four of the Palisade Trench North and East samples. *Sporormiella* dung fungal spores were observed only in Sample 304, collected from Feature 225 in Block X.

Moderately small quantities of microscopic charcoal are typical of most of the Palisade Trench North and East samples with the exception of Samples 442 and 433 from Features 401 and 299A in Block Z. Total pollen concentration varied from nearly 2000 to approximately 4360 pollen/cc of sediment, with the exception of Sample 429, collected in Feature 251 in Block W. This sample, which was dominated by Low-spine Asteraceae pollen, exhibited a very low total pollen concentration of approximately 230 pollen/cc of sediment.

The phytolith signatures for the Palisade Trench North and East samples contained moderate quantities of bulliform and elongate phytoliths, representing primarily grasses. Trichomes, also representing primarily grasses, were present. Grass short cells varied in frequency. Sample 442, collected from Feature 401 in Block Z yielded the largest quantity of

bilobate phytoliths. Sample 442 also exhibited *Z. mays* pollen, suggesting that this elevated bilobate frequency represents the presence or discard of corn leaves or stalks. Moderate quantities of bilobate phytoliths were recorded in Samples 317 and 433, also from Palisade Trench North. Although these two samples also contained *Z. mays* pollen, the quantities of bilobates are not sufficient to be considered indicators of the presence of corn. Rondels, representing festucoid grasses, and saddles, indicating chloridoid grasses, were approximately as abundant as were bilobates in most of the Palisade Trench North and East samples. All of the Palisade Trench North and East samples, with the exception of Sample 317, collected from Feature 363 in Block AD, exhibited *Oryza*-type rice phytoliths, suggesting that debris from growing rice either was used extensively across the landscape or that remains of rice leaves dried out and were carried on the wind across the landscape. *Commelina*-type seed phytoliths also were observed in all of the Palisade Trench North and East samples with the exception of Sample 292, collected from Feature 221 in Block X. *Commelina* is a well-known agricultural weed with very hard seeds. As noted above, the *Commelina* seed phytoliths likely represent accidental inclusion with the rice harvest.

A few dicot-type phytoliths were observed in the Palisade Trench North and East samples, possibly introduced as a result of building a wooden palisade. Samples 317 and 442 exhibited phytoliths that are typical of *Quercus*. Sample 317 also contained a lenticular starch that is typical of wheat, barley, rye, and oats and the related large-seeded native grasses, such as wheatgrass, barley grass, rye grass, and wild oat grasses. Only a few diatoms and sponge spherasters and spicules were typically observed in the Palisade Trench North and East samples. Sponge spicules were particularly abundant in Sample 292, collected from Feature 221 in Block X. All of the Palisade Trench North and East samples contained at least some evidence of the presence of *Oryza* and *Commelina* seeds, with the exception of Sample 292, which yielded no *Commelina* seed phytoliths in the count. Three of the Palisade Trench North and East samples yielded *Z. mays* phytoliths, signaling either growth of corn by the occupants of the fort or trading for corn. Sample 317 exhibited weak signatures for rice and cereals.

Two samples were examined from the Palisade Trench Southwest. The pollen signature for these samples was generally similar to those from the other Palisade Trench samples. Exceptions include recovery of larger quantities of *Ilex* and *Salix* pollen, suggesting that holly and willow grew more dense closer to this portion of the fort. In addition, both of these samples, contain *Acer* pollen, suggesting maple trees were located closer to the south side of the fort than the north. This is the only part of the fort that yielded *Castanea* and *Juglans* pollen, indicating that chestnut and walnut trees also grew farther south, perhaps with the maples. Poaceae pollen was elevated in Sample 384 and reduced in the lower Sample 386. This suggests greater grass cover at the time the upper sample accumulated. The upper sample (Sample 384) also exhibited a large microscopic charcoal frequency, suggesting proximity to a thermal feature or a source of ash. It is also possible that ash cleaned from a thermal feature was deposited in this location. Neither of these samples exhibited *Oryza* or *Z. mays* pollen, although both yielded *Oryza*-type bulliforms. The phytolith record suggests that the elevated Poaceae pollen frequency is the result of local growth of short grasses in the area, as saddle-shaped phytoliths indicating chloridoid grasses increased in frequency.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

In general, the pollen signatures revealed that Fort Argyle was situated in an area of pine woods that also supported a wide variety of hardwood trees or shrubs likely growing along the Ogeechee River or in lower, wet areas. The pollen record indicates the presence of maples, alder, birch, hophornbeam/hornbeam, cypress family, chestnut, oak, ash, holly, hickory, walnut, sweetgum, willow, and elm trees. Grassy areas are suggested by moderately large quantities of Poaceae pollen throughout and particularly by the elevated Poaceae pollen frequency in Sample 384, representing Palisade Trench Southwest. Pollen suggests the presence of other herbaceous plants including members of the goosefoot/amaranth family, umbels, wormwood, thistle, ragweed and/or marshelder, other plants in the sunflower family, dandelion and related plants, members of the mustard family, bindweed, sedges, a member of the heath or blueberry family, spurge, two types of clover, legumes, wild buckwheat, wetland knotweed, a member of the buckthorn family, a member of the rose family, and globemallow.

In addition, the pollen record indicates local growth of grapes, rice, and corn, which is supported in the phytolith record by recovery of rice bulliforms and *Commelina* seed phytoliths. Dung fungal spores, recovered in one sample from Palisade Trench East, suggest the presence of grazing animals such as horses. The combined presence of *Oryza*-type pollen or *Oryza*-type bulliforms in all of the samples from this site suggests rice cultivation was important at this site. Ubiquitous distribution of the agricultural remnants of crops is most likely an indicator of their relative abundance. This was accompanied by recovery of *Commelina* seed phytoliths in all but one of the samples examined, suggesting dayflower was a persistent agricultural weed likely associated with rice agriculture.

Z. mays pollen was observed in samples from the cellar, the pit, the chimney base, and three of the Palisade Trench North samples, but not in the Palisade Trench East or Southwest samples. *Vitis* pollen, representing grapes, was noted only in Sample 292 from Palisade Trench East. Grapes were a crop that was recommended as being less labor-intensive, so recovery of even this small quantity of *Vitis* pollen is indicative that this strategy was adopted to some extent at Fort Argyle. Recovery of a lenticular starch in Sample 317, collected from Palisade Trench North, suggests growing or processing wheat unless this starch represents seeds from a native festucoid or cool season grass with large seeds. It is not considered diagnostic, but is common in seeds from the cultivated grains wheat, rye, oats, and barley and in their native counterparts.

TABLES

TABLE 1
 PROVENIENCE DATA FOR SEDIMENT SAMPLES FROM FORT ARGYLE,
 9BN28, BRYAN COUNTY, GEORGIA

Sample No.	Feature	Block	Unit	Depth (cmbd)	Provenience/ Description	Analysis
442	401	Z	233	103–107	Palisade Trench, corner angle, south profile	Pollen Phytolith
433	299A		165	80–84	Palisade Trench north with post, east profile	Pollen Phytolith
315	362	AD	213, 214	16–18	Pit, north profile	Pollen Phytolith
317	363		214	108–110	Palisade Trench north, east profile	Pollen Phytolith
304	225	X	131	42–47	Palisade Trench east, north profile	Pollen Phytolith
292	221		130	76–78	Palisade Trench east, Zone B, north profile	Pollen Phytolith
429	251	W	120	65–67	Palisade Trench north, west profile	Pollen Phytolith
343	328	AB	218	40–42	Cellar, Zone A, north profile	Pollen Phytolith Parasite
384	388	AA	227	103–107	Palisade Trench north part of southwest corner, Triangular Fort, south half profile at the intersection of Features 314 and 388	Pollen Phytolith
386				105–108	Palisade Trench, north part of southwest corner, Triangular Fort, east profile	Pollen Phytolith
333	175F	T	220	23–25	Chimney base	Pollen Phytolith

TABLE 2
 POLLEN TYPES OBSERVED IN SAMPLES FROM FORT ARGYLE,
 9BN28, BRYAN COUNTY, GEORGIA

Scientific Name	Common Name
ARBOREAL POLLEN:	
<i>Acer</i>	Maple
Betulaceae:	Birch family
<i>Alnus</i>	Alder
<i>Betula</i>	Birch
<i>Ostrya/Carpinus</i>	Hophornbeam/Hornbeam
Cupressaceae	Cypress family
Fagaceae:	Legume family
<i>Castanea</i>	Chestnut
<i>Quercus</i>	Oak
<i>Fraxinus</i>	Ash
<i>Ilex</i>	Holly
Juglandaceae:	Walnut family
<i>Carya</i>	Hickory, Pecan
<i>Juglans</i>	Walnut
<i>Liquidambar</i>	Sweetgum
<i>Pinus</i>	Pine
<i>Salix</i>	Willow
<i>Ulmus</i>	Elm
NON-ARBOREAL POLLEN:	
Amaranthaceae	Amaranth family (now includes Chenopodiaceae, these two families were combined based on genetic testing and the pollen category "Cheno-ams")
Apiaceae	Umbel family
Asteraceae:	Sunflower family
<i>Artemisia</i>	Sagebrush, Wormwood
<i>Cirsium</i>	Thistle

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Scientific Name	Common Name
Low-spine	Includes Ragweed, Cocklebur, Sumpweed
High-spine	Includes Aster, Rabbitbrush, Snakeweed, Sunflower, etc.
Liguliflorae	Chicory tribe, includes Dandelion and Chicory
Brassicaceae	Mustard or Cabbage family
<i>Convolvulus</i>	Bindweed
Cyperaceae	Sedge family
Ericaceae	Heath family
<i>Euphorbia</i>	Spurge
Fabaceae:	Bean or Legume family
<i>Dalea</i>	Prairie clover
<i>Melilotus</i>	Sweet clover
Poaceae	Grass family
Polygonaceae:	Knotweed/Smartweed family
<i>Eriogonum</i>	Wild buckwheat
<i>Persicaria</i>	Persicaria, Smartweed, Pinkweed
Rhamnaceae	Buckthorn family
Rosaceae	Rose family
<i>Sphaeralcea</i>	Globemallow
<i>Vitis</i>	Grape
CULTIGENS:	
<i>Oryza</i>	Rice
<i>Zea mays</i>	Maize, corn
SPORES:	
Monolete - smooth	Fern
<i>Osmunda</i>	Flowering fern
Trilete - smooth	Fern

TABLE 2 (Continued)

Scientific Name	Common Name
FUNGAL SPORES:	
<i>Sporormiella</i>	Dung fungus
OTHER:	
Microscopic charcoal	Microscopic charcoal fragments
Total pollen concentration	Quantity of pollen per cubic centimeter (cc) of sediment

FIGURES

FIGURE 1. POLLEN DIAGRAM FOR FORT ARGYLE, 9BN28, BRYAN COUNTY, GEORGIA.

FIGURE 2. PHYTOLITH DIAGRAM FOR FORT ARGYLE, 9BN28, BRYAN COUNTY, GEORGIA.

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APPENDIX E: Additional Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) Documentation, LG²ES Excavations, 9BN28.

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tt1: 0.0-1.0ns 0.0-4.0cm

tt10. 9.1-10.1ns 35.9-39.9cm

tt20: 19.1-20.1ns 75.3-79.2cm

tt30: 29.1-30.2ns 115.1-119.1cm

tt40 39.2-40.2ns 155.0-159.0cm

tt50 49.2-50.2ns 194.4-198.4cm

tt60 59.3-60.2ns 234.2-237.7cm

Appendix E. GPR Survey,
Supplemental Materials, Fort
Argyle, 9BN28, LG2ES, Inc.

Compiled by Daniel T. Elliott, 2019

Radargram DAT_0008, GPR Block ABC

Radargram DAT_0023, GPR Block ABC

Distance [m]

Radargram DAT_0032, GPR Block ABC

Radargram DAT_0042, GPR Block ABC

Radargram DAT_0053, GPR Block ABC

Radargram DAT_0064, GPR Block ABC

Radargram DAT_0077, GPR Block ABC

Distance [m]

Radargram DAT_0086, GPR Block ABC

Distance [m]

Radargram Plan, GPR Block F.

Radargram Plan, GPR Block H.

Overlay Plan Map, GPR Block H.

Radogram Plan, GPR Block D, Grid North is UP

APPENDIX F: Excavation Block, Test Unit and Feature Locations, 2018-2019 Excavations, 9BN28.

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Southwestern Corner Coordinates and Block Location for LG2ES Test Units, 2018-2019.

	Southwest Corner		
Test Unit	North	East	Block
100	2985.85	8169.89	T
101	2985.85	8167.89	T
102	2984.85	8169.89	T
103	2984.85	8167.89	T
104	2992.93	8163.99	V
105	2991.92	8164.00	V
106	2992.97	8162.00	V
107	2993.97	8162.00	V
108	2994.97	8162.00	V
109	3008.11	8165.00	U
110	3006.06	8166.92	U
111	3008.01	8169.02	U
112	3007.06	8166.92	U
113	3007.04	8169.02	U
114	3005.06	8166.92	U
115	3004.06	8166.92	U
116	3003.06	8166.92	U
117	3009.40	8154.93	W
118	3009.40	8156.93	W
119	3009.40	8158.93	W
120	3008.40	8154.93	W
121	3008.40	8156.93	W
122	3008.40	8158.93	W
123	3007.40	8154.93	W
124	3007.40	8156.93	W
125	3007.40	8158.93	W
126	3006.40	8154.93	W
127	3006.40	8156.93	W
128	3006.40	8158.93	W
129	3003.64	8170.79	X
130	3003.64	8172.79	X
131	3003.64	8174.79	X
132	3002.64	8170.79	X
133	3002.64	8172.79	X
134	3002.64	8174.79	X
135	3001.64	8170.79	X
136	3001.64	8172.79	X
137	3001.64	8174.79	X
138	3000.64	8170.79	X
139	3000.64	8172.79	X
140	3000.64	8174.79	X
141	3008.01	8171.02	U

Southwestern Corner Coordinates and Block Location for LG2ES Test Units, 2018-2019.

Test Unit	Southwest Corner		Block
	North	East	
142	3007.04	8171.02	U
143	3008.04	8173.02	U
144	3007.04	8173.02	U
145	2995.93	8167.14	Y
146	2995.93	8169.14	Y
147	2995.93	8171.14	Y
148	2995.93	8173.14	Y
149	2994.93	8167.14	Y
150	2994.93	8169.14	Y
151	2994.93	8171.14	Y
152	2994.93	8173.14	Y
153	2993.93	8167.14	Y
154	2993.93	8169.14	Y
155	2993.93	8171.14	Y
156	2993.93	8173.14	Y
157	2992.93	8167.14	Y
158	2992.93	8169.14	Y
159	2992.93	8171.14	Y
160	2992.93	8173.14	Y
161	3014.46	8149.03	Z
162	3014.46	8151.03	Z
163	3014.46	8153.03	Z
164	3014.46	8155.03	Z
165	3014.46	8157.03	Z
166	3014.46	8159.03	Z
167	3013.46	8149.03	Z
168	3013.46	8151.03	Z
169	3013.46	8153.03	Z
170	3013.46	8155.03	Z
171	3013.46	8157.03	Z
172	3013.46	8159.03	Z
173	3012.46	8149.03	Z
174	3012.46	8151.03	Z
175	3012.46	8153.03	Z
176	3012.46	8155.03	Z
177	3012.46	8157.03	Z
178	3012.46	8159.03	Z
179	2995.93	8175.14	Y
180	2994.93	8175.14	Y
181	2995.90	8152.04	AA
182	2995.90	8154.01	AA
183	2994.93	8152.01	AA

Southwestern Corner Coordinates and Block Location for LG2ES Test Units, 2018-2019.

Test Unit	Southwest Corner		Block
	North	East	
184	2994.93	8154.01	AA
185	2993.93	8152.01	AA
186	2993.93	8154.01	AA
187	3008.91	8145.01	AB
188	3008.89	8147.07	AB
189	3008.89	8149.01	AB
190	3006.92	8145.03	AB
191	3007.92	8147.04	AB
192	3007.91	8149.01	AB
193	3008.91	8143.01	AB
194	3006.91	8147.01	AB
195	3006.90	8149.01	AB
196	3005.91	8149.01	AB
197	3005.91	8151.01	AB
198	3004.91	8149.01	AB
199	3004.91	8151.01	AB
200	3003.91	8149.01	AB
201	3003.91	8151.01	AB
202	2994.93	8148.01	AA
203	2994.93	8150.01	AA
204	2993.93	8148.01	AA
205	2993.93	8150.01	AA
206	2998.90	8144.04	AC
207	2997.90	8144.04	AC
208	2996.90	8144.04	AC
209	2995.90	8144.04	AC
210	3015.89	8170.04	AD
211	3014.89	8170.04	AD
212	3013.89	8170.04	AD
213	3012.89	8170.04	AD
214	3011.89	8170.04	AD
215	3010.89	8170.04	AD
216	2978.85	8157.90	AE
217	2977.85	8157.90	AE
218	3009.91	8148.01	AB
219	2995.93	8147.01	AA
220	2986.85	8170.89	T
221	3000.02	8148.00	AF
222	3001.02	8148.00	AF
223	3002.02	8150.00	AF
224	3014.88	8173.05	AG
225	3013.88	8173.05	AG

Southwestern Corner Coordinates and Block Location for LG2ES Test Units, 2018-2019.

	Southwest Corner		
Test Unit	North	East	Block
226	3000.02	8146.00	AF
227	2995.93	8149.01	AA
228	3016.46	8157.03	Z
229	3005.14	8161.95	W
230	3022.74	8176.78	AH
231	3020.74	8176.78	AH
232	3024.74	8176.78	AH
233	3017.46	8154.03	Z
234	3017.46	8157.53	Z
235	3004.14	8159.95	W
236	2975.03	8152.94	AI

Feature Centerpoints and Block Locations, LG2ES Excavations, 2018-2019.

Feature	North	East	Block
8	3008.59	8166.00	E & U
192	3009.40	8175.30	C & U
200	2987.30	8170.03	T
201	2986.25	8168.20	T
202	2985.45	8169.82	T
203	2985.69	8169.56	T
204	2984.93	8169.33	T
205	2985.33	8168.35	T
206	2995.68	8163.82	V
207	3008.41	8171.13	U
208	3007.68	8170.04	U
209	3007.60	8170.40	U
210	3007.65	8171.29	E & U
211	3007.00	8171.43	U
212	3008.74	8173.26	U
213	3008.80	8173.70	U
214	3007.91	8173.97	U
215	3007.47	8172.96	U
216	3003.21	8167.73	U
217	3004.01	8170.98	X
218	3004.10	8171.55	X
219	3004.07	8172.10	X
220	3004.59	8173.32	X
221	3003.12	8173.72	X
222	3003.85	8173.15	X
223	3003.91	8172.42	X
224	3003.92	8176.05	X
225	3003.15	8176.39	X
226	3003.31	8176.69	X
227	3002.20	8170.87	X
228	3002.67	8174.94	X
229	3001.26	8174.91	X
230	3000.95	8173.55	X
231	3006.56	8155.19	W
232	3007.21	8155.38	W
233	3007.49	8155.04	W
234	3007.94	8155.48	W
235	3008.10	8156.18	W
236	3006.84	8156.69	W
237	3006.45	8157.25	W
238	3006.75	8157.48	W
239	3006.46	8157.64	W
240	3006.47	8158.34	W
241	3006.40	8159.55	W

Feature Centerpoints and Block Locations, LG2ES Excavations, 2018-2019.

Feature	North	East	Block
242	3006.94	8159.63	W
243	3006.92	8158.93	W
244	3006.71	8158.22	W
245	3008.33	8160.02	W
246	3008.17	8159.52	W
247	3008.39	8158.07	W
248	3008.55	8157.58	W
249	3008.10	8157.73	W
250	3008.53	8156.05	W
251	3009.29	8155.76	W
252	3010.25	8155.18	W
253	3008.95	8158.12	W
254	3009.73	8156.26	W
255	3009.50	8159.45	W
256	2995.03	8168.41	Y
257	2995.67	8170.21	Y
258	2996.29	8167.81	Y
259	2995.93	8169.15	Y
260	2995.64	8170.88	Y
261	2995.78	8169.91	Y
262	2995.30	8170.44	Y
263	2994.09	8169.72	Y
264	2993.45	8169.72	Y
265	2993.35	8168.95	Y
266	2993.50	8168.36	Y
267	2994.42	8168.46	Y
268	2994.67	8170.62	Y
269	2992.98	8167.28	Y
270	2993.72	8170.42	Y
271	2993.71	8167.62	Y
272	2994.56	8167.25	Y
273	2994.45	8167.62	Y
274	2992.96	8168.28	Y
275	2994.25	8169.28	Y
276	2994.55	8168.98	Y
277	2995.41	8169.03	Y
278	2995.42	8169.66	Y
279	2995.15	8170.08	Y
280	2995.72	8171.83	Y
281	2993.07	8170.12	Y
282	2993.27	8170.83	Y
283	2995.40	8172.12	Y
284	2996.37	8170.93	Y
285	2996.25	8172.28	Y

Feature Centerpoints and Block Locations, LG2ES Excavations, 2018-2019.

Feature	North	East	Block
286	2995.49	8172.45	Y
287	2994.39	8173.32	Y
288	2994.24	8172.89	Y
289	2995.72	8174.32	Y
290	2993.00	8174.18	Y
291	2995.76	8176.45	Y
292	3012.73	8149.61	Z
293	3012.68	8150.06	Z
294	3013.00	8149.86	Z
295	3013.25	8149.65	Z
296	3012.68	8151.00	Z
297	3013.54	8150.59	Z
298	3013.74	8151.40	Z
299	3014.34	8149.99	Z
300	3014.93	8151.14	Z
301	3012.38	8155.49	Z
302	3013.33	8156.45	Z
303	3013.45	8160.17	Z
304	3015.01	8157.84	Z
305	3014.55	8157.69	Z
306	3013.96	8157.69	Z
307	3013.17	8157.77	Z
308	3013.47	8158.96	Z
309	3015.04	8161.01	Z
310	2996.29	8155.78	AA
311	2995.95	8154.87	AA
312	2996.75	8154.69	AA
313	2996.82	8154.15	AA
314	2995.33	8152.08	AA
315	2996.22	8153.10	AA
316	2996.16	8152.52	AA
317	2996.83	8152.41	AA
318	2994.60	8151.90	AA
319	2994.03	8152.69	AA
320	2994.08	8151.18	AA
321	2994.12	8150.81	AA
322	2994.10	8149.27	AA
323	2993.92	8149.95	AA
324	2994.54	8150.24	AA
325	2994.23	8150.72	AA
326	2994.45	8150.66	AA
327	3009.67	8146.04	AB
328	3009.80	8148.90	AB
329	3008.92	8150.48	AB

Feature Centerpoints and Block Locations, LG2ES Excavations, 2018-2019.

Feature	North	East	Block
330	3008.84	8148.39	AB
331	3008.62	8148.38	AB
332	3008.40	8148.40	AB
333	3007.74	8147.31	AB
334	3007.48	8147.27	AB
335	3007.46	8147.60	AB
336	3007.34	8147.86	AB
337	3007.35	8148.32	AB
338	3004.73	8151.06	AA
339	3004.07	8151.40	AB
340	3005.06	8150.63	AB
341	3004.91	8151.54	AB
342	3005.47	8151.66	AB
343	3005.76	8152.91	AB
344	3006.22	8149.93	AB
345	3004.59	8149.75	AB
346	3006.86	8150.22	AB
347	3006.60	8151.10	AB
348	3006.77	8151.79	AB
349	3006.12	8152.06	AB
350	2997.90	8145.04	AC
351	2998.36	8144.07	AC
352	3008.53	8147.66	AB
353	3007.46	8150.87	AB
354	3006.14	8150.91	AB
355	3004.07	8149.04	AB
356	3008.54	8149.31	AB
357	3003.96	8150.05	AB
358	3011.16	8171.80	AD
359	3011.16	8170.12	AD
360	3014.64	8171.61	AD
361	3014.19	8172.03	AD
362	3013.09	8171.40	AD
363	3012.17	8171.11	AD
364	2979.83	8158.84	AE
365	2979.24	8158.90	AE
366	2979.10	8158.00	AE
367	2979.07	8159.63	AE
368	2978.44	8158.35	AE
369	2978.40	8158.74	AE
370	2977.94	8158.22	AE
371	2977.88	8159.57	AE
372	2978.01	8159.83	AE
373	3012.85	8170.48	AD

Feature Centerpoints and Block Locations, LG2ES Excavations, 2018-2019.

Feature	North	East	Block
373	3012.85	8170.48	AD
374	3015.13	8170.39	AD
375	2996.24	8172.20	Y
376	2996.15	8173.77	Y
377	2997.17	8147.94	AA
378	3000.35	8148.70	AF
379	3001.09	8150.02	AF
380	3001.86	8148.82	AF
381	3000.97	8149.04	AF
382	3002.85	8151.70	AF
383	3002.24	8151.54	AF
384	3001.81	8149.70	AF
385	3000.59	8147.24	AF
386	3000.71	8149.38	AF
387	3001.25	8148.23	AF
388	2996.33	8149.61	AA
388	2296.33	8149.61	AA
389	2996.49	8150.92	AA
390	3015.00	8174.07	AG
391	3015.17	8157.54	Z
392	3016.45	8157.97	Z
393	3017.25	8157.99	Z
394	3016.89	8157.42	Z
395	3005.36	8163.60	W
396	3005.90	8162.44	W
397	3004.53	8160.12	W
398	3020.76	8177.27	AH
399	3015.18	8152.59	Z
400	3015.27	8155.95	Z
401	3017.40	8154.73	Z
402	3025.10	8176.84	AH
403	2975.92	8153.22	AI
404	2976.67	8153.59	AI
405	2975.87	8153.75	AI

APPENDIX G: Artifact Inventory, 1985-1996 Excavations. 9BN28.

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1985 SAS Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
ST 2					1	Handmade brick	16	
ST 2					2	Unidentified nail		
ST 2					1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 2					4	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 2					0	None		
ST 3					3	Unspecified flake		
ST 3					1	Daub	1	
ST 3					1	Handmade brick	6	
ST 3					1	Unmeasured window glass		
ST 3					1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 3					0	None		
ST 4					1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
ST 4					1	Handmade brick	45	
ST 4					1	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 4					0	None		
ST 5					1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
ST 5					1	Daub	6	
ST 5					1	Handmade brick	65	
ST 5					6	Unidentified nail		
ST 5					2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 5					1	Unidentified lead		
ST 5					0	None		
ST 6					1	Unspecified flake		
ST 6					1	Daub	5	
ST 6					1	Handmade brick	115	
ST 6					2	Unidentified nail		
ST 6					3	Combed clear glaze slipware		
ST 6					1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 6					4	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 6					0	None		
ST 7					4	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
ST 7					1	Handmade brick	293	
ST 7					10	Unidentified nail		
ST 7					1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
ST 7					2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
ST 7					1	Bone	0	
ST 7					1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
ST 7					3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		

1985 SAS Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
ST 7					8	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 7					1	Buck shot		
ST 7					1	Unidentified lead		
ST 7					0	None		
ST 8					1	Daub	1	
ST 8					1	Handmade brick	33	
ST 8					1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
ST 8					5	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 8					1	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 8					1	English dark gray gunfint, unident. Spall or blade		
ST 8					2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
ST 8					1	Unidentified lead		
ST 8					0	None		
ST 9					1	Shatter 0% cortex		C.P. chert
ST 9					1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
ST 9					1	Handmade brick	4	
ST 9					1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 9					1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
ST 9					0	None		
ST 10					1	Handmade brick	542	
ST 10					2	Unidentified nail		
ST 10					1	Bone	2	
ST 10					1	Olive green spirit bottl glass		
ST 10					2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
ST 11					1	Daub	12	
ST 11					1	Handmade brick	50	
ST 11					1	Unidentified nail		
ST 11					1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
ST 11					2	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 11					0	None		
ST 12					2	Unspecified flake		
ST 12					1	Daub		
ST 12					1	Handmade brick		
ST 12					13	Unidentified nail		
ST 12					1	White salt glazed stoneware		
ST 12					2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
ST 12					1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 12					7	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 12					1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
ST 12					0	None		
ST 13					1	Handmade brick	230	
ST 13					5	Unmeasured window glass		
ST 13					17	Unidentified nail		
ST 13					1	Unidentified porcelain tile		
ST 13					1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
ST 13					3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 13					2	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 13					1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
ST 13					2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
ST 13					0	None		
ST 14					5	Shatter 0% cortex		C.P. chert
ST 14					2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
ST 14					1	Handmade brick	680	
ST 14					4	Unidentified nail		

1985 SAS Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
ST 14					1	Bone	1	
ST 14					2	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
ST 14					1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
ST 14					3	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 14					1	Buck shot		
ST 14					1	English dark gray gunfint, unident. Spall or blade		
ST 14					1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
ST 14					3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
ST 14					1	Unidentified lead		
ST 14					0	None		
ST 15					1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
ST 15					1	Handmade brick	9	
ST 15					8	Unidentified nail		
ST 15					3	Unidentified iron/steel		
ST 15					0	None		
ST 16					1	Handmade brick	135	
ST 16					0	None		
ST 17					1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
ST 17					1	Handmade brick	124	
ST 17					0	None		
43	C	1			1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
43	C	1			1	Daub	20	
43	C	1			1	Handmade brick	6	
43	C	1			3	Unidentified nail		
43	C	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
43	C	1			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
43	C	1			1	Unidentified iron/steel		
43	C	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
43	C	1			5	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
43	C	1			0	None		
44	C	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
44	C	1			1	Daub	5	
44	C	1			1	Handmade brick	12	
44	C	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
44	C	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
44	C	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
44	C	1			0	None		
44	C	2			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
44	C	2			1	Daub	17	
44	C	2			1	Handmade brick	225	
44	C	2			15	Unidentified nail		
44	C	2			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
44	C	2			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
44	C	2			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
44	C	2			9	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
44	C	2			3	Unidentified iron/steel		
44	C	2			1	Unidentified lead		
44	C	2			0	None		
45	C	1			1	Handmade brick	6	
45	C	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
45	C	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
45	C	1			0	None		
45	C	2			1	Shatter 0% cortex		C.P. chert
45	C	2			3	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert

1985 SAS Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
45	C	2			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
45	C	2			1	Daub	63	
45	C	2			1	Handmade brick	672	
45	C	2			17	Unidentified nail		
45	C	2			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
45	C	2			1	Dotted slipware		
45	C	2			10	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
45	C	2			1	Bone		
45	C	2			17	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
45	C	2			10	Unidentified iron/steel		
45	C	2			3	Unidentified lead		
45	C	2			0	None		
46	D	1			2	Check stamped ceramic, body		Untempered
46	D	1			1	Daub	36	
46	D	1			1	Unidentified nail		
46	D	1			1	Metropolitan-like ware		
46	D	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
46	D	1			0	None		
46	D	2			1	Unspecified flake		
46	D	2			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
46	D	2			1	Daub	195	
46	D	2			1	Handmade brick	46	
46	D	2			4	Unidentified nail		
46	D	2			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
46	D	2			1	Unidentified delft		
46	D	2			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
46	D	2			2	Unidentified iron/steel		
46	D	2			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
46	D	2			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
46	D	2			0	None		
47	D	1			1	Daub	35	
47	D	1			1	Handmade brick	26	
47	D	1			1	Unmeasured window glass		
47	D	1			8	Unidentified nail		
47	D	1			1	Unspecified flake		
47	D	1			1	None		
47	D	2			1	Unspecified flake		Quartz
47	D	2			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
47	D	2			1	Daub	772	
47	D	2			15	Handmade brick	780	
47	D	2			1	Unmeasured window glass		
47	D	2			1	Unidentified nail		
47	D	2			1	Other brass button shank		
47	D	2			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
47	D	2			5	Combed clear glaze slipware		
47	D	2			8	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
47	D	2			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
47	D	2			3	Unidentified iron/steel		
47	D	2			0	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
47	D	2				Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
	D		34	Postmold	1	Daub	11	
	D		34	Postmold	0	None		
	D		35	Trench	1	Dirt dauber nest		
	D		35	Trench	1	Daub	2522	

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
	D		35	Trench	22	Unidentified nail		
	D		35	Trench	8	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	D		35	Trench	1	Buck shot		
	D		35	Trench	2	Lead ball		
	D		35	Trench	1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
	D		35	Trench	1	Unidentified lead		
	D		35	Trench	0	None		
48	D	1			1	Plain ceramic, body		
48	D	1			1	Simple stamped ceramic, body		
48	D	1			1	Daub	56	
48	D	1			1	Handmade brick	46	
48	D	1			20	Unidentified nail		
48	D	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
48	D	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
48	D	1			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
48	D	1			4	Unidentified iron/steel		
48	D	1			2	2 Unidentified lead		
48	D	1			0			
48	D	1			2	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
48	D	2			1	Daub	242	
48	D	2			1	Handmade brick	159	
48	D	2			1	Unmeasured window glass		
48	D	2			17	Unidentified nail		
48	D	2			1	Buckle fragment		Brass or iron
48	D	2			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
48	D	2			3	Combed clear glaze slipware		
48	D	2			5	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
48	D	2			1	Lead ball		
48	D	2			6	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
48	D	2			2	Unidentified lead		
48	D	2			0	None		
49	D	1			1	Unspecified flake		
49	D	1			1	1 Daub		
49	D	1			1	1 Handmade brick		
49	D	1			10	10 Unidentified nail		
49	D	1			1	1 Unidentified coarse earthenware		
49	D	1			2	2 Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
49	D	1			3	3 Olive green spirit bottle glass		
49	D	1			1	1 Unidentified lead		
49	D	1			0	None		
49	D	2			4	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
49	D	2			2	Plain ceramic, body		
49	D	2			1	Complicated stamped ceramic, body		
49	D	2			1	Daub	128	
49	D	2			1	Handmade brick	29	
49	D	2			8	Unidentified nail		
49	D	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
49	D	2			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
49	D	2			1	Unidentified delft		
49	D	2			5	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
49	D	2			2	Unidentified iron/steel		
49	D	2			1	Lead ball		
49	D	2			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		

1985 SAS Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
49	D	2			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
49	D	2			2	Unidentified lead		
49	D	2			0	None		
50	D	1			1	Daub	16	
50	D	1			1	Handmade brick	74	
50	D	1			2	Unidentified nail		
50	D	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
50	D	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
50	D	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
50	D	1			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
50	D	1			0	None		
50	D	2			1	Daub	67	
50	D	2			1	Handmade brick	145	
50	D	2			5	Unidentified nail		
50	D	2			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
50	D	2			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
50	D	2			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
50	D	2			1	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
50	D	2			7	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
50	D	2			3	Unidentified iron/steel		
50	D	2			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
50	D	2			3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
50	D	2			0	None		
51	L	1			1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
51	L	1			3	Unspecified flake		Quartz
51	L	1			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
51	L	1			1	Handmade brick	214	
51	L	1			4	Unmeasured window glass		
51	L	1			32	Unidentified nail		
51	L	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
51	L	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
51	L	1			6	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
51	L	1			1	Whole bottle, medicinal		
51	L	1			1	English dark gray gunflint, unident. Spall or blade		
51	L	1			1	Unidentified lead		
51	L	1			0	None		
	L		24	Trench	1	Handmade brick	44	
	L		24	Trench	2	Unidentified nail		
	L		24	Trench	2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	L		24	Trench	0	None		
	L		26	Tree	1	Handmade brick	3	
	L		26	Tree	1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
	L		26	Tree	1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
	L		26	Tree	0	None		
52	L	1			3	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
52	L	1			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
52	L	1			1	Handmade brick	211	
52	L	1			7	Unmeasured window glass		
52	L	1			1	Spike, wrought iron		
52	L	1			65	Unidentified nail		
52	L	1			1	Unidentified lead glazed stoneware		
52	L	1			4	Plain clear glaze slipware		
52	L	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
52	L	1			2	Dotted slipware		
52	L	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
52	L	1			5	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
52	L	1			8	Unidentified iron/steel		
52	L	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
52	L	1			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
52	L	1			0	None		
	L		25	Tree	1	Handmade brick	26	
	L		25	Tree	13	Unidentified nail		
	L		25	Tree	1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
	L		25	Tree	2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	L		25	Tree	0	None		
53	L	1			1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
53	L	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
53	L	1			1	Handmade brick	169	
53	L	1			7	Unmeasured window glass		
53	L	1			26	Unidentified nail		
53	L	1			1	Whieldon ware		
53	L	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
53	L	1			7	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
53	L	1			1	Unidentified iron/steel		
53	L	1			6	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
53	L	1			0	None		
53	L	2			1	Unspecified flake		Quartzite
53	L	2			0	None		
54	L	1			7	Unspecified flake		Quartzite
54	L	1			7	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
54	L	1			1	Daub	1	
54	L	1			1	Handmade brick	2096	
54	L	1			11	Unmeasured window glass		
54	L	1			29	Unidentified nail		
54	L	1			1	Rubber shoe part		
54	L	1			1	Refined brown salt glazed stoneware body		
54	L	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
54	L	1			3	Combed clear glaze slipware		
54	L	1			1	Dotted slipware		
54	L	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
54	L	1			8	Olive gree spirit bottle glass		
54	L	1			11	Unidentified iron/steel		
54	L	1			4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
54	L	1			0	None		
54	L	2			5	Unspecified flake		Quartzite
54	L	2			1	Handmade brick	9	
54	L	2			0	None		
55	L	1			3	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
55	L	1			1	Handmade brick	148	
55	L	1			17	Unmeasured window glass		
55	L	1			58	Unidentified nail		
55	L	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
55	L	1			5	Combed clear glaze slipware		
55	L	1			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
55	L	1			1	Milk glass		
55	L	1			5	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
55	L	1			14	Unidentified iron/steel		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
55	L	1			3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
55	L	1			0	None		
55	L	2			2	Simple stamped ceramic, body		
55	L	2			1	Handmade brick	7	
55	L	2			1	Unidentified nail		
55	L	2			0	None		
56	N	1			1	Daub	1	
56	N	1			1	Handmade brick	105	
56	N	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
56	N	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
56	N	1			0	None		
56	N	2			1	Handmade brick	662	
56	N	2			1	Unmeasured window glass		
56	N	2			7	Unidentified nail		
56	N	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
56	N	2			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
56	N	2			1	Bone	2	
56	N	2			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
56	N	2			10	Unidentified iron/steel		
56	N	2			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
56	N	2			0	None		
	N		13	Postmold	1	Handmade brick	8	
	N		13	Postmold	1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
	N		13	Postmold	0	None		
57	N	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
57	N	1			1	Handmade brick	166	
57	N	1			3	Unidentified nail		
57	N	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
57	N	1			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
57	N	1			0	None		
57	N	2			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
57	N	2			1	Handmade brick	175	
57	N	2			16	Unidentified nail		
57	N	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
57	N	2			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
57	N	2			2	Dotted slipware		
57	N	2			1	Bone	5	
57	N	2			1	Aqua bottle glass		
57	N	2			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
57	N	2			1	Olive greens spirit bottle glass		
57	N	2			16	Unidentified iron/steel		
57	N	2			1	Spall type gunflint, burned		
57	N	2			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
57	N	2			3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
57	N	2			0	None		
58	N	1			1	Daub	3	
58	N	1			1	Handmade brick	111	
58	N	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
58	N	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
58	N	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
58	N	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
58	N	1			0	None		
58	N	2			4	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
58	N	2			1	Handmade brick	168	
58	N	2			2	Unmeasured window glass		

1985 SAS Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
58	N	2			8	Unidentified nail		
58	N	2			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
58	N	2			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
58	N	2			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
58	N	2			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
58	N	2			0	None		
	N		11	Trench	1	Handmade brick	2	
	N		11	Trench	1	Unidentified nail		
	N		11	Trench	0	None		
59	N	1			1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
59	N	1			1	Handmade brick	375	
59	N	1			1	Unmeasured window glass		
59	N	1			1	Unidentified iron/steel		
59	N	1			0	None		
59	N	2			1	Biface fragment		C.P. chert
59	N	2			1	Daub	2	
59	N	2			1	Handmade brick	213	
59	N	2			1	Unidentified nail		
59	N	2			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
59	N	2			0	None		
	N		23	Trench	1	Unspecified flake		
	N		23	Trench	3	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
	N		23	Trench	1	Handmade brick	17	
	N		23	Trench	3	Unidentified nail		
	N		23	Trench	1	White salt glazed stoneware		
	N		23	Trench	1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
	N		23	Trench	1	Unidentified iron/steel		
	N		23	Trench	3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
	N		23	Trench	0	None		
60	N	1			1	Handmade brick	74	
60	N	1			0	None		
60	N	2			1	Daub	1	
60	N	2			1	Handmade brick	71	
60	N	2			1	Unmeasured window glass		
60	N	2			1	Unidentified nail		
60	N	2			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
60	N	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
60	N	2			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
60	N	2			0	None		
61	R	1			1	Handmade brick	40	
61	R	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
61	R	1			0	None		
61	R	2			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
61	R	2			1	Daub	39	
61	R	2			1	Handmade brick	738	
61	R	2			10	Unidentified nail		
61	R	2			1	Plain c.c. ware		
61	R	2			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
61	R	2			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
61	R	2			2	Ollvie green spirit bottle glass		
61	R	2			1	Unidentified iron/steel		
61	R	2			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
61	R	2			3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
61	R	2			0	None		
62	R	1			1	Handmade brick	16	

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
62	R	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
62	R	1			0	None		
62	R	2			1	Unspecified flake		
62	R	2			11	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
62	R	2			1	Handmade brick	471	
62	R	2			3	Unidentified nail		
62	R	2			1	Refined brown salt glazed stoneware body		
62	R	2			1	Plain c.c. ware		
62	R	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
62	R	2			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
62	R	2			1	Refined agateware		
62	R	2			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
62	R	2			0	None		
63	R	1			1	Handmade brick	7	
63	R	1			1	Olive greens spirit bottle glass		
63	R	1						
63	R	1			0	None		
63	R	2			1	Daub	29	
63	R	2			1	Handmade brick	323	
63	R	2			1	Unidentified brick		
63	R	2			10	Unidentified nail		
63	R	2			1	Plain creamware		
63	R	2			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
63	R	2			3	Unidentified iron/steel		
63	R	2			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
63	R	2			4	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
63	R	2			1	Unidentified lead		
63	R	2			0	None		
64	R	1			1	Handmade brick	24	
64	R	1			0	None		
64	R	2			1	Handmade brick	296	
64	R	2			2	Unidentified nail		
64	R	2			1	Plain creamware		
64	R	2			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
64	R	2			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
64	R	2			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
64	R	2			0	None		
65	R	1			1	Handmade brick	1	
65	R	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
65	R	1			0	None		
65	R	2			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
65	R	2			1	Handmade brick	100	
65	R	2			1	Unidentified nail		
65	R	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
65	R	2			1	Dotted slipware		
65	R	2			4	Unidentified iron/steel		
65	R	2			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
65	R	2			3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
65	R	2			0	None		
66	R	1			1	Handmade brick		
66	R	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
66	R	1			36	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
66	R	1			0	None		
66	R	2			2	Plain ceramic, body		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
66	R	2			1	Complicated stamped ceramic, body		
66	R	2			1	Daub	21	
66	R	2			1	Handmade brick	126	
66	R	2			1	Fragment wire common nail		
66	R	2			1	White saltglazed stoneware		
66	R	2			1	buck shot		
66	R	2			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
66	R	2			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
66	R	2			0	None		
67	R	1			1	Handmade brick	12	
67	R	1			0	None		
67	R	2			1	Daub	4	
67	R	2			1	Handmade brick	267	
67	R	2			1	Unidentified nail		
67	R	2			1	Plain c.c. ware		
67	R	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
67	R	2			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
67	R	2			2	Unidentified iron/steel		
67	R	2			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
67	R	2			0	None		
68	F	1			6	Plain ceramic, body		
68	F	1			1	Simple stamped ceramic, body		
68	F	1			1	Kasita Red Filmed ceramic body		
68	F	1			1	Daub	7	
68	F	1			1	Handmade brick	564	
68	F	1			2	Unmeasured window glass		
68	F	1			4	Unidentified nail		
68	F	1			1	Refined brown salt glazed stoneware body		
68	F	1			2	White saltglazed stoneware		
68	F	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
68	F	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
68	F	1			6	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
68	F	1			1	Unidentified delft		
68	F	1			10	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
68	F	1			1	Vacuum packed can, key, or lid		Tin
68	F	1			6	Unidentified iron/steel		
68	F	1			1	English dark gray gunflint, unident, spall or blade		
68	F	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
68	F	1			6	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
68	F	1			2	Unidentified lead		
68	F	1			0	None		
68	F	2			1	Handmade brick	331	
68	F	2			4	Unidentified nail		
68	F	2			2	White saltglazed stoneware		
68	F	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
68	F	2			1	Bone	0	
68	F	2			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
68	F	2			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
68	F	2			1	English dark gray gunflint, unident, spall or blade		
68	F	2			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
68	F	2			0	None		
68	F	3			1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
68	F	3			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
68	F	3			1	Handmade brick	475	
68	F	3			2	Unidentified nail		
68	F	3			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
68	F	3			3	Combed clear glaze slipware		
68	F	3			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
68	F	3			2	Unidentified delft		
68	F	3			1	Bone	1	
68	F	3			10	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
68	F	3			4	Unidentified iron/steel		
68	F	3			1	buck shot		
68	F	3			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
68	F	3			5	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
68	F	3			0	None		
68	F	4			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
68	F	4			1	Daub	2	
68	F	4			1	Handmade brick	217	
68	F	4			1	Unidentified nail		
68	F	4			4	White saltglazed stoneware		
68	F	4			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
68	F	4			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
68	F	4			1	Unidentified delft		
68	F	4			6	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
68	F	4			1	Unidentified burned bottle glass		
68	F	4			1	Vacuum packed can, key, or lid		
68	F	4			7	Unidentified iron/steel		
68	F	4			3	buck shot		
68	F	4			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
68	F	4			0	None		
	F		36	Trench	1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
	F		36	Trench	2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
	F		36	Trench	1	Handmade brick	4	
	F		36	Trench	1	White saltglazed stoneware		
	F		36	Trench	1	Olive greens spirit bottle glass		
	F		36	Trench	1	Unidentified iron/steel		
	F		36	Trench	2	buck shot		
	F		36	Trench	0	None		
69	E	1			3	Unspecified flake		
69	E	1			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
69	E	1			1	Daub	6	
69	E	1			1	Handmade brick	293	
69	E	1			1	Refined brown salt glazed stoneware body		
69	E	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
69	E	1			1	Dotted slipware		
69	E	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
69	E	1			2	Underglaze stippled transfer print		
69	E	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
69	E	1			9	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
69	E	1			4	Unidentified iron/steel		
69	E	1			0	None		
69	E	2			4	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
69	E	2			1	Daub	105	
69	E	2			1	Handmade brick	438	
69	E	2			6	Unidentified nail		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
69	E	2			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
69	E	2			3	Combed clear glaze slipware		
69	E	2			2	Dotted slipware		
69	E	2			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
69	E	2			1	Dark blue underglaze stippled transfer print		
69	E	2			1	Bone	1	
69	E	2			15	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
69	E	2			7	Unidentified iron/steel		
69	E	2			1	Pewter ornament		
69	E	2			2	buck shot		
69	E	2			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
69	E	2			8	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
69	E	2			0	None		
	E		1	Tree	1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
	E		1	Tree	1	Daub	10	
	E		1	Tree	1	Handmade brick	14	
	E		1	Tree	3	Unidentified nail		
	E		1	Tree	1	Bone	1	
	E		1	Tree	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	E		1	Tree	0	None		
	E		2	Postmold	1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
	E		2	Postmold	1	Daub	10	
	E		2	Postmold	1	Handmade brick	5	
	E		2	Postmold	2	Unidentified nail		
	E		2	Postmold	1	Bone	4	
	E		2	Postmold	4	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	E		2	Postmold	1	Unidentified iron/steel		
	E		2	Postmold	2	Buck shot		
	E		2	Postmold	3	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
	E		2	Postmold	0	None		
	E		3	Postmold	1	Handmade brick	2	
	E		3	Postmold	3	Unidentified nail		
	E		3	Postmold	5	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	E		3	Postmold	1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
	E		3	Postmold	0	None		
	E		8	Pit	1	Daub		
	E		8	Pit	1	Handmade brick		
	E		8	Pit	4	Unidentified nail		
	E		8	Pit	1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
	E		8	Pit	1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
	E		8	Pit	2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	E		8	Pit	1	Buck shot		
	E		8	Pit	1	Lead sprue		
	E		8	Pit	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
	E		8	Pit	3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
	E		8	Pit	0	None		
70/237	H	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		Untempered
70/237	H	1			1	Handmade brick	518	
70/237	H	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
70/237	H	1			1	Metropolitan-like ware		
70/237	H	1			5	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
70/237	H	1			1	Unidentified delft		
70/237	H	1			9	Olive green spirit bottle glass		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
70/237	H	1			1	Dark European chert chunk		
70/237	H	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
70/237	H	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
70/237	H	2			1	Check stamped ceramic, body		Untempered
70/237	H	2			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual	6	
70/237	H	2			1	Daub	472	
70/237	H	2			1	Handmade brick		
70/237	H	2			7	Unidentified nail		
70/237	H	2			1	Molded creamware		
70/237	H	2			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
70/237	H	2			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
70/237	H	2			9	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
70/237	H	2			14	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
70/237	H	2			1	French (honey) chert gunflint fragment		
70/237	H	2			7	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
70/237	H	2			3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
70/237	H	2			1	Unidentified lead		
70/237	H	2			0	None		
	H		56	Rodent burrow	1	Handmade brick		5
	H		56	Rodent burrow	1	Unidentified nail		
	H		56	Rodent burrow	0	None		
	H		62	Tree or rodent burrow	1	Handmade brick	10	
	H		62	Tree or rodent burrow	1	Unidentified nail		
	H		62	Tree or rodent burrow	1	buck shot		
	H		62	Tree or rodent burrow	0	None		
71	J	1			1	Complicated stamped ceramic, body		
71	J	1			1	Daub	5	
71	J	1			1	Handmade brick	1213	
71	J	1			2	Unidentified nail		
71	J	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
71	J	1			1	Plain creamware		
71	J	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
71	J	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
71	J	1			1	Jackfield		
71	J	1			1	Unidentified porcelain tile		
71	J	1			1	Unidentified iron/steel		
71	J	1			1	glass gemstone, paste		
71	J	1			3	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
71	J	1			3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
71	J	1			0	None		
71	J	2			1	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
71	J	2			1	Daub	3	

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
71	J	2			1	Handmade brick	231	
71	J	2			1	Spike, wrought iron		
71	J	2			29	Unidentified nail		
71	J	2			1	Refined brown salt glazed stoneware body		
71	J	2			2	Plain creamware		
71	J	2			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
71	J	2			1	Dotted slipware		
71	J	2			1	Unidentified delft		
71	J	2			1	Unidentified porcelain tile		
71	J	2			0	Animal teeth	1	
71	J	2			2	Aqua bottle glass		
71	J	2			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
71	J	2			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
71	J	2			15	Unidentified iron/steel		
71	J	2			2	Buck shot		
71	J	2			1	Lead sprue		
71	J	2			6	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
71	J	2			4	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
71	J	2			1	Unidentified lead		
71	J	2			1	Unidentified brass		
71	J	2			0	None		
71	J	3			9	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
71	J	3			3	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
71	J	3			1	Daub	39	
71	J	3			1	Handmade brick	3170	
71	J	3			1	Spike, wrought iron		
71	J	3			115	Unidentified nail		
71	J	3			1	Button, South type 4		
71	J	3			1	Other brass button shank		
71	J	3			2	Refined brown salt glazed stoneware body		
71	J	3			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
71	J	3			1	Plain creamware		
71	J	3			1	Hand painted creamware		
71	J	3			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
71	J	3			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
71	J	3			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
71	J	3			1	Astbury refined redware		
71	J	3			2	Jackfield		
71	J	3			2	Unidentified delft		
71	J	3			3	Unidentified porcelain tile		
71	J	3			1	Bone	13	
71	J	3			0	Animal teeth	9	
71	J	3			3	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
71	J	3			11	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
71	J	3			1	Kettle/pot, iron		
71	J	3			45	Unidentified iron/steel		
71	J	3			1	Buckle, whole, breeches		Brass
71	J	3			5	buck shot		
71	J	3			1	Lead sprue		
71	J	3			2	English dark gray gunflint, unident. Spall or blade		
71	J	3			16	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
71	J	3			17	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
71	J	3			5	Unidentified lead		
71	J	3			1	Unidentified brass		
71	J	3			0	None		
72	M	1			1	Handmade brick	234	
72	M	1			9	Unidentified nail		
72	M	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
72	M	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
72	M	1			1	Unidentified porcelain tile		
72	M	1			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
72	M	1			6	Unidentified iron/steel		
72	M	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
72	M	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
72	M	1			0	None		
72	M	2			1	Handmade brick	2370	
72	M	2			1	Unmeasured window glass		
72	M	2			53	Unidentified nail		
72	M	2			3	White salt glazed stoneware		
72	M	2			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
72	M	2			1	Unidentified stoneware (yellow)		
72	M	2			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
72	M	2			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
72	M	2			2	Dotted slipware		
72	M	2			2	Jackfield		
72	M	2			3	Unidentified delft		
72	M	2			1	Unidentified porcelain tile		
72	M	2			1	Bone	1	
72	M	2			8	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
72	M	2			1	Soda green machine made bottle glass		
72	M	2			10	Unidentified iron/steel		
72	M	2			1	Writing slate		
72	M	2			4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
72	M	2			12	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
72	M	2			1	Unidentified brass		
72	M	2			0	Other		
72	M	3			1	Unspecified flake		C.P chert
72	M	3			1	Daub	2	
72	M	3			1	Handmade brick		
72	M	3			27	Unidentified nail	1581	
72	M	3			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
72	M	3			2	Whieldon ware		
72	M	3			1	Plain creamware		
72	M	3			2	Plain c.c. ware		
72	M	3			8	Plain clear glaze slipware		
72	M	3			5	Combed clear glaze slipware		
72	M	3			5	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
72	M	3			2	Jackfield		
72	M	3			2	Unidentified delft		
72	M	3			2	Unidentified porcelain tile		
72	M	3			1	Bone	5	
72	M	3			5	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
72	M	3			6	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
72	M	3			13	Unidentified iron/steel		
72	M	3			2	Buckle		copper
72	M	3			1	Buck shot		
72	M	3			5	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
72	M	3			9	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
72	M	3			0	None		
	M		19	Possible post	1	Handmade brick	47	
	M		19	Possible post	3	Unidentified nail		
	M		19	Possible post	6	Plain clear glaze slipware		
	M		19	Possible post	6	Combed clear glaze slipware		
	M		19	Possible post	2	Dotted slipware		
	M		19	Possible post	1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
	M		19	Possible post	1	Unidentified delft		
	M		19	Possible post	1	Bone	1	
	M		19	Possible post	2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	M		19	Possible post	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
	M		19	Possible post	4	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
	M		19	Possible post	2	Unidentified lead		
	M		19	Possible post	0	None		
	M		21	Pit	1	Handmade brick	2	
	M		21	Pit	0	None		
73	O	1			1	Handmade brick	274	
73	O	1			4	Unmeasured window glass		
73	O	1			4	Unidentified nail		
73	O	1			1	Plain creamware		
73	O	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
73	O	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
73	O	1			4	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
73	O	1			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
73	O	1			1	Vacuum packed can, key, or lid		Tin
73	O	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
73	O	1			3	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
73	O	1			0	None		
73	O	2			2	Unspecified flake		C.P. chert
73	O	2			3	Unspecified flake		Quartzite
73	O	2			3	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
73	O	2			1	Daub	44	
73	O	2			1	Handmade brick	2170	
73	O	2			23	Unidentified nail		
73	O	2			3	White salt glazed stoneware		
73	O	2			6	Combed clear glaze slipware		
73	O	2			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
73	O	2			2	Jackfield		
73	O	2			2	Unidentified delft		
73	O	2			1	Bone	2	
73	O	2			4	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		

1985 SAS Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
73	O	2			13	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
73	O	2			1	Kettle/pot, iron		
73	O	2			12	Unidentified iron/steel		
73	O	2			13	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
73	O	2			0	None		
74	N	1			1	Biface fragment		C.P. chert
74	N	1			4	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
74	N	1			1	Handmade brick	428	
74	N	1			1	Unmeasured window glass		
74	N	1			5	Unidentified nail		
74	N	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
74	N	1			6	Plain clear glaze slipware		
74	N	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
74	N	1			5	Dotted slipware		
74	N	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
74	N	1			5	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
74	N	1			2	Unidentified iron/steel		
74	N	1			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
74	N	1			4	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
74	N	1			0	None		
			177	Grave	0	Not excavated		
			178	Post (scaffolding)	0	Not excavated		
			179	Builders trench for chimney	0	Not excavated		
			1	Tree	0			
			2	Postmold	0			
			3	Postmold	0			
			4	Postmold	0			
			5	Postmold	0			
			6	Postmold	0			
			7	Postmold	0			
			8	Plt	0			
			9	Postmold	0			
			10	Unknown	0			
			11	Trench	0			
			12	Irregular stain	0			
			13	Postmold	0			
			14	Postmold	0			
			15	Postmold	0			
			16	Postmold	0			
			17	Postmold	0			
			18	Postmold	0			
			19	Possible post	0			
			20	Trench	0			
			21	Plt	0			
			22	Plt	0			
			23	Trench	0			
			24	Trench	0			
			25	Tree	0			
			26	Tree	0			

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
			27	Pit/tree	0			
			28	Possible post	0			
			29	Stain, noncultural	0			
			30	Stain, noncultural	0			
			31	Band of soil	0			
			32	Possible post	0			
			33	Stain, noncultural	0			
			34	Postmold	0			
			35	Trench	0			
			36	Trench	0			
			37	Unknown	0			
			38	Trench	0			
			39	Trench	0			
			40	Trench	0			
			41	Postmolds	0			
			42	Posthole	0			
			43	Postmold	0			
			44	Postmold	0			
			45	Postmold	0			
			46	Postmold	0			
			47	Postmold	0			
			48	Postmold	0			
			49	Burned area	0			
			50	Posthole	0			
			51	Postmold	0			
			52	Faint stain	0			
			53	Tree	0			
			54	Postmold	0			
			55	Shallow stain	0			
			56	Rodent burrow	0			
			57	Tree or rodent burrow	0			
			58	Tree	0			
			59	Faint stain	0			
			60	Faint stain	0			
			61	Rodent burrow	0			
			62	Tree or rodent burrow	0			
			63	Ditch/dry moat	0			

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
			64	Possible post	0			
			65	Possible post	0			
			66	Possible post	0			
			67	Possible post	0			
			68	trench	0			
			102	Trench	0			
			104	Tree	0			
			205	Root	0			
			206	Post	0			
			109	Low spot	0			
			110	Low spot	0			
			111	Post/tree	0			
			113	Post	0			
			115	Post	0			
			116	Tree	0			
			117	Pit	0			
			118	Tree	0			
			121	Post	0			
			122	Post	0			
			123	Post	0			
			124	Post	0			
			125	Post	0			
			126	Unknown	0			
			128	Post	0			
			130	Post	0			
			131	Tree	0			
			132	Post	0			
			133	Tree	0			
			134	Tree	0			
			137	Tree	0			
			139	Post	0			
			140	Tree	0			
			141	Rut	0			
			142	Post	0			
			144	Post	0			
			145	Tree	0			
			147	Post	0			
			148	Low spot	0			
			149	Post	0			
			150 a	Post	0			
			151	Post	0			
			158	trench	0			
			160	Post	0			
			161	Low spot	0			
			162	Low spot	0			
			163	Low spot	0			
			167	Trench or g?	0			
			168	Tree	0			
			169	Plowscar	0			
			170	Tree	0			

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
			171	Tree	0			
			172	Possible post	0			
			173 b	Trench	0			
			174	Post	0			
			180 b	Trench	0			
			182	Trench	0			
			184	Possible post	0			
			190	Tree	0			
			191	Possible pit	0			
			192	Trench	0			

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
ST 1					1	Plain ceramic, body		Fine sand tempered
ST 1					2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
1	S	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
1	S	1			1	Bottle glass slipware		Olive glass
1	S	1			3	Glass unifacial tool		Oliveglass
1	S	1			1	Chattahoochee Brushed ceramic, body		
1	S	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
1	S	1			1	Handmade brick	1000	
1	S	1			8	Unidentified nail		
1	S	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
1	S	1			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
1	S	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
1	S	1			1	green tinted molded refined white salt glazed stoneware		
1	S	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
1	S	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
1	S	1			5	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
1	S	1			2	Jackfield		
1	S	1			1	Polychrome delft		
1	S	1			1	Bone		
1	S	1			3	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
1	S	1			6	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
1	S	1			2	Unidentified iron/steel		
1	S	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
1	S	1			3	Unidentified scrap pewter		
1	S	1			1	Unidentified lead		
2	N	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
2	N	1			2	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
2	N	1			1	Handmade brick	3500	
2	N	1			1	1.6-1.8mm thick, Crown window glass		
2	N	1			1	1.8-2.0 mm thick, Crown window glass		
2	N	1			2	Cut or wrought square nail		
2	N	1			13	Unidentified nail		
2	N	1			1	Nottingham stoneware		
2	N	1			5	White salt glazed stoneware		
2	N	1			2	Whieldon ware		
2	N	1			2	Plain creamware		
2	N	1			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
2	N	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
2	N	1			3	Dotted slipware		
2	N	1			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
2	N	1			1	Astbury refined redware		
2	N	1			1	Jackfield		
2	N	1			1	Delft sherds without glaze		
2	N	1			1	Unidentified delft		
2	N	1			2	Bone		
2	N	1			7	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
2	N	1			1	Goblet base		
2	N	1			1	Goblet glass		
2	N	1			2	Unidentified Iron/steel		
2	N	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
2	N	1			1	English dark gray gunflint, unident spall or blade		
2	N	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
2	N	1			4	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
2	N	1			1	Unidentified lead		
4	N	1			4	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
4	N	1			1	Shatter >50% cortex		Quartz
4	N	1			1	Glass unifacial tool		Olive
4	N	1			3	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
4	N	1			1	Handmade brick	2000	
4	N	1			1	Fragment wire common nail		
4	N	1			17	Cut or wrought square nail		
4	N	1			17	Unidentified nail		
4	N	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
4	N	1			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
4	N	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
4	N	1			3	Combed clear glaze slipware		
4	N	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
4	N	1			5	Dotted slipware		
4	N	1			2	Jackfield		
4	N	1			1	Bone		
4	N	1			1	Oyster shell		
4	N	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
4	N	1			7	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
4	N	1			1	Unidentified Iron/steel		
4	N	1			2	French (honey) chert gunflint fragment		
4	N	1			1	Coastal plain chert gunflint		
4	N	1			3	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
4	N	1			2	4/64 Inch ball clay stem/bowl		
4	N	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
4	N	1			1	Molded brown glazed pipe bowl		
4	N	1			1	Unidentified lead		
1	S		100	Post	1	Handmade brick	2	

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
1	S		100	Post	1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
3	N	1			4	Thinning flake 0% cortex		
3	N	1			2	Flake fragment 0% cortex		
3	N	1			3	Shatter 0% cortex		
3	N	1			1	Biface fragment		
3	N	1			1	Glass unifacial tool		
3	N	1			1	Handmade brick		
3	N	1			27	Cut or wrought square nail		
3	N	1			17	Unidentified nail		
3	N	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
3	N	1			1	Molded white salt glazed stoneware rlm		
3	N	1			4	White salt glazed stoneware		
3	N	1			2	Plain creamware		
3	N	1			10	Plain clear glaze slipware		
3	N	1			6	Combed clear glaze slipware		
3	N	1			1	Dotted slipware		
3	N	1			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
3	N	1			1	Jackfield		
3	N	1			1	Blue and white delft		
3	N	1			3	Plain white delft		
3	N	1			1	Bone		
3	N	1			1	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
3	N	1			1	Aqua hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
3	N	1			1	Clear bottle glass		
3	N	1			8	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
3	N	1			1	Crown cap		
3	N	1			14	Unidentified iron/steel		
3	N	1			1	Lead ball		
3	N	1			3	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
3	N	1			1	5/64 Inch ball clay stem/bowl		
3	N	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
3	N	1			5	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
3	N	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
3	N	1			1	Molded brown glazed pipe bowl		
4	N		101	Pit	1	Wood charcoal fragments	109	
3	N		103	Trench	1	Indeterminante ceramic, residual		
3	N		103	Trench	1	Unidentified nail		
5	N	1			2	Shatter 0% cortex		
5	N	1			1	Bottle glass slipware		
5	N	1			1	Handmade brick		
5	N	1			2	1.2-14 mm thick, Crown window glass		
5	N	1			9	Cut or wrought square nail		
5	N	1			15	Unidentified nail		
5	N	1			1	Blue and gray Rhenish stoneware rlm		
5	N	1			2	Molded white salt glazed stoneware rlm		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
5	N	1			3	White salt glazed stoneware		
5	N	1			1	Plain brown salt glazed stoneware		
5	N	1			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
5	N	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
5	N	1			3	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
5	N	1			4	Purple slip on yellow slipware		
5	N	1			3	Dotted slipware		
5	N	1			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
5	N	1			1	Jackfield		
5	N	1			1	Bone		
5	N	1			1	Amethyst bottle glass		
5	N	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
5	N	1			7	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
5	N	1			1	Unidentified Burned bottle glass		
5	N	1			5	Unidentified iron/steel		
5	N	1			1	Brass/copper cartridge		
5	N	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
5	N	1			1	Dark European chert chunk		
5	N	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
5	N	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
5	N	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
5	N	1			4	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
5	N	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
5	N	1			1	Unidentified lead		
5	N	1			1	Unidentified brass		
6	N	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		Quartz
6	N	1			2	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
6	N	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		Quartz
6	N	1			2	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
6	N	1			1	Plain ceramic, body		Grit
6	N	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
6	N	1			1	Handmade brick	3250	
6	N	1			1	1.6-1.8 mm thick, Crown window glass		
6	N	1			1	1.4-1.6 mm thick, Plate window glass		
6	N	1			1	>3.0 mm thick, Plate window glass		
6	N	1			1	Fragment T-head wrought nail		
6	N	1			20	Cut or wrought square nail		
6	N	1			30	Unidentified nail		
6	N	1			1	Overglaze polychrome h.p. porcelain		
6	N	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
6	N	1			3	Nottingham stoneware		
6	N	1			5	White salt glazed stoneware		
6	N	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
6	N	1			1	Plain brown salt glazed stoneware		
6	N	1			3	Whieldon ware		
6	N	1			8	Plain clear glaze slipware		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
6	N	1			5	Combed clear glaze slipware		
6	N	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
6	N	1			1	Dotted and Trailed slipware		
6	N	1			1	Dotted slipware		
6	N	1			6	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
6	N	1			1	Plain White delft		
6	N	1			1	DeJft sherds without glaze		
6	N	1			4	Bone		
6	N	1			1	Animal teeth		
6	N	1			1	Amethyst bottle glass		
6	N	1			1	Light green bottle glass		
6	N	1			3	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
6	N	1			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
6	N	1			10	Unidentified iron/steel		
6	N	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
6	N	1			2	Dark gray European chert flake		
6	N	1			3	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
6	N	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
6	N	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
6	N	1			1	Activities, Unidentified lead scrap		
5	N		108	Postmold	1	Handmade brick		
5	N		108	Postmold	1	Unidentified nail		
5	N		108	Postmold	1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
5	N		108	Postmold	1	Jackfield		
5	N		108	Postmold	1	French (honey) chert flake		
5	N		108	Postmold	1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
7	N	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
7	N	1			3	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
7	N	1			1	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Sand
7	N	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
7	N	1			1	Handmade brick	2750	
7	N	1			19	Cut or wrought square nail		
7	N	1			25	Unidentified nail		
7	N	1			1	Round glass bead		
7	N	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
7	N	1			1	Molded White salt glazed stoneware rim		
7	N	1			3	White salt glazed stoneware		
7	N	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
7	N	1			3	Plain White granite		
7	N	1			1	Whieldon ware		
7	N	1			7	Plain clear glaze slipware		
7	N	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
7	N	1			2	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
7	N	1			1	Dotted slipware		
7	N	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
7	N	1			1	Blue and White delft		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
7	N	1			4	Bone		
7	N	1			4	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
7	N	1			1	Goblet base		
7	N	1			2	Leadsprue		
7	N	1			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
7	N	1			1	6/64 Inch ball clay stem/bowl		
7	N	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
7	N	1			3	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
7	N	1			1	Activities, Unidentified lead scrap		
7	N	1			3	Unidentified scrap pewter		
8	N	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		
8	N	1			2	Flake fragment 0% cortex		
8	N	1			1	Shatter 0% cortex		
8	N	1			1	Plain ceramic, body		
8	N	1			1	Indeterminate stamped ceramic, body		
8	N	1			1	Stallings Plain ceramic, body		
8	N	1			1	Handmade brick		
8	N	1			1	Fragment rosehead nail		
8	N	1			16	Cut or wrought square nail		
8	N	1			21	Unidentified nail		
8	N	1			1	Blue h.p . porcelain		
8	N	1			3	White salt glazed stoneware		
8	N	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
8	N	1			10	Unidentified light gray and brown salt glazed stoneware		
8	N	1			4	Plain clear glaze slipware		
8	N	1			6	Combed clear glaze slipware		
8	N	1			2	Dotted slipware		
8	N	1			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
8	N	1			1	Blue and White delft		
8	N	1			2	Plain White delft		
8	N	1			4	Delft sherds without glaze		
8	N	1			3	Bone		
8	N	1			1	Animal teeth		
8	N	1			1	Aqua hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
8	N	1			1	Cobalt blue pharmaceutical bottle		
8	N	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
8	N	1			5	Unidentified Iron/steel		
8	N	1			1	Lead sprue		
8	N	1			1	Altered musket ball		
8	N	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
8	N	1			1	French (honey) gunflint, blade type		
8	N	1			1	French (honey) chert flake		
8	N	1			1	French (honey) chert gunflint fragment		
8	N	1			7	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
8	N	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
8	N	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
8	N	1			1	Unidentified lead		
9	N	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		
9	N	1			1	Ocmulgee Fields Incised ceramic, unidentified rim		Untempered
9	N	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
9	N	1			1	Handmade brick	1500	
9	N	1			2	1.2-1.4 mm thick, Crown window glass		
9	N	1			5	Cut or wrought square nail		
9	N	1			9	Unidentified nail		
9	N	1			1	Undecorated porcelain		
9	N	1			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
9	N	1			1	Overglaze h.p. refined White salt glazed stoneware		
9	N	1			1	Plain creamware		
9	N	1			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
9	N	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
9	N	1			1	Purple slip on yellow slipware		
9	N	1			2	Dotted slipware		
9	N	1			8	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
9	N	1			1	White slipped clear glazed redware		
9	N	1			2	Clear bottle glass		
9	N	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
9	N	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
9	N	1			2	Unidentified Iron/steel		
9	N	1			3	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
9	N	1			1	6/64 Inch ball clay stem/bowl		
9	N	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
9	N	1			3	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
6	N		112	Post	1	Handmade brick	9	
6	N		112	Post	1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
8	N		119	Post	1	Handmade brick	2	
8	N		119	Post	1	Cut or wrought square nail		
8	N		119	Post	3	Unidentified nail		
8	N		254	Trench	1	Daub	14	
8	N		254	Trench	1	Buckshot		
8	N		254	Trench	1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
7	N		114	Tree	1	Handmade brick	59	
7	N		114	Tree	1	Unidentified nail		
7	N		114	Tree	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
11	N	1			1	Thinning flake <50% cortex		C.P. chert
11	N	1			3	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
11	N	1			5	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
11	N	1			1	Plain ceramic, body		Grit
11	N	1			3	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
11	N	1			1	Handmade brick	2000	

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
11	N	1			3	1.2-1.4 mm thick, Crown window glass		
11	N	1			1	3.5 to 4.0 Wire common nail 20 penny		
11	N	1			12	Cut or wrought square nail		
11	N	1			23	Unidentified nail		
11	N	1			1	Round glass bead		
11	N	1			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
11	N	1			11	Plain clear glaze slipware		
11	N	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
11	N	1			1	Dotted slipware		
11	N	1			5	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
11	N	1			2	Jackfield		
11	N	1			3	Plain White delft		
11	N	1			1	Unidentified delft		
11	N	1			1	Bone		
11	N	1			1	Animal teeth		
11	N	1			1	Post bottom mold bottle glass		
11	N	1			1	Amethyst bottle glass		
11	N	1			1	Light green bottle glass		
11	N	1			2	Aqua bottle glass		
11	N	1			7	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
11	N	1			1	Goblet rim		
11	N	1			1	Goblet base		
11	N	1			14	Unidentified Iron/steel		
11	N	1			1	Unmodified stone		
11	N	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		European chert
11	N	1			1	Impacted lead ball		
11	N	1			1	Gray chalcedony percussion flake		
11	N	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
11	N	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
11	N	1			1	Molded brown glazed pipe bowl		
11	N	1			1	Unidentified lead		
11	N	1			1	Grinding stone		
12	N	1			1	Tested cobble		Quartz
12	N	1			3	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P chert
12	N	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
12	N	1			1	Plain ceramic, body		Grit tempered
12	N	1			1	Plain ceramic, body		Fine sand tempered
12	N	1			1	Handmade brick	2500	
12	N	1			1	1.2-1.4 mm thick, Crown window glass		
12	N	1			16	Cut or wrought square nail		
12	N	1			17	Unidentified nail		
12	N	1			1	Button, South type 7		
12	N	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
12	N	1			2	Overglaze h.p. refined White salt glazed stoneware		
12	N	1			4	Whieldon ware		
12	N	1			3	Plain creamware		
12	N	1			4	Plain clear glaze slipware		
12	N	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
12	N	1			1	Molded yellow slipware, floral		
12	N	1			2	Dotted slipware		
12	N	1			1	Blue and White delft		
12	N	1			1	Plain White delft		
12	N	1			2	Unidentified delft		
12	N	1			1	Bone		
12	N	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
12	N	1			4	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
12	N	1			8	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
12	N	1			1	Kettle/pot, iron		
12	N	1			1	Large metal spoon		Iron
12	N	1			16	Unidentified iron/steel		
12	N	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
12	N	1			4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
12	N	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
12	N	1			6	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
12	N	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
12	N	1			1	Unidentified lead		
10	N	1			1	Handmade brick	363	
10	N	1			3	1.2-1.4 mm thick, Crown window glass		
10	N	1			1	Cut or wrought square nail		
10	N	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
10	N	1			1	Overglaze h.p. refined White salt glazed stoneware		
10	N	1			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
10	N	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
10	N	1			1	Dotted slipware		
10	N	1			7	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
10	N	1			1	Plain White delft		
10	N	1			1	Delft sherds without glaze		
10	N	1			1	Bone		
10	N	1			2	Aqua bottle glass		
10	N	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
10	N	1			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
10	N	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
10	N	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
10	N	1			1	Unidentified lead		
9	N		107 a	Post	1	Unmodified fossilized shell		
9	N		120 a	Trench	1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
9	N		120 a	Trench	1	Handmade brick	250	

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
9	N		120 a	Trench	5	Unidentified nail		
9	N		120 a	Trench	0	0		
9	N		120 b	Trench	0	0		
	N		127	Post	1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		
	N		127 north	Post	7	Unidentified nail		
	N		127 north	Post	1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
	N		127 north	Post	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	N		127 north	Post	0	None		
12	N		129	Post	1	Unidentified nail		
12	N		129	Post	6	Bone		
12	N		129	Post	2	Unidentified Iron/steel		
12	N		129	Post	1	Dark gray European chert flake		
12	N		129	Post	0	0		
13	E	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
13	E	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
13	E	1			1	Bottle glass slipware		Olive glass
13	E	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
13	E	1			1	Daub	5	
13	E	1			1	Handmade brick	500	
13	E	1			1	Fragment rosehead nail		
13	E	1			2	Cut or wrought square nail		
13	E	1			5	Unidentified nail		
13	E	1			1	Undecorated porcelain		
13	E	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
13	E	1			2	Plain creamware		
13	E	1			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
13	E	1			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
13	E	1			1	Blue and White delft		
13	E	1			9	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
13	E	1			3	Unidentified Iron/steel		
13	E	1			2	Lead ball		
13	E	1			1	Leadsprue		
13	E	1			2	Dark gray European chert flake		
13	E	1			1	French (honey) chert flake		
13	E	1			2	English dark gray gunflint, unident spall or blade		
13	E	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
13	E	1			3	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
13	E	1			3	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
13	E	1			1	6/ 64 Inch ball clay stem		
13	E	1			1	Unidentified lead		
14	E	1			1	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Heavy grit

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
14	E	1			1	Dirt dauber nest		
14	E	1			4	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
14	E	1			1	Daub	6	
14	E	1			1	Handmade brick	1000	
14	E	1			5	Cut or wrought square nail		
14	E	1			3	Unidentified nail		
14	E	1			1	Button, South type 1		
14	E	1			1	Other brass button shank		
14	E	1			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
14	E	1			1	Plain White granite		
14	E	1			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
14	E	1			3	Combed clear glaze slipware		
14	E	1			2	Dotted slipware		
14	E	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
14	E	1			1	Blue and White delft		
14	E	1			1	Ameythst bottle glass		
14	E	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
14	E	1			15	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
14	E	1			1	Goblet rim		
14	E	1			6	Unidentified Iron/steel		
14	E	1			1	Lead ball		
14	E	1			1	Lead ball		
14	E	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
14	E	1			1	5/64 Inch ball clay stem/bowl		
14	E	1			1	6/64 Inch ball clay stem/bowl		
14	E	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
14	E	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
14	E	1			1	6/ 64 Inch ball clay stem		
14	E	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
14	E	1			1	Activities, unidentified lead scrap		
14	E	1			1	Unidentified lead		
14	E	1			0	None		
15	E	1			1	Indeterminate ground stone		
15	E	1			1	Unspeclalized slipware >50% cortex		Petrified
15	E	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
15	E	1			1	Indetermlnate decorated ceramic, body		Heavy grit
15	E	1			8	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
15	E	1			1	Daub	3	
15	E	1			1	Handmade brick	1200	
15	E	1			1	Cut or wrought square nail		
15	E	1			15	Unidentified nail		
15	E	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
15	E	1			1	Plain brown salt glazed stoneware		
15	E	1			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
15	E	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
15	E	1			2	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
15	E	1			1	Dotted slipware		
15	E	1			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
15	E	1			1	Amethyst bottle glass		
15	E	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
15	E	1			11	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
15	E	1			6	Unidentified Iron/steel		
15	E	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
15	E	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
15	E	1			5	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
15	E	1			0	None		
16	E	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
16	E	1			1	Unspecialized slipware 0% cortex		C.P. chert
16	E	1			1	Flake <50% cortex		Quartz
16	E	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
16	E	1			2	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Grit
16	E	1			4	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
16	E	1			1	Daub	25	
16	E	1			1	Handmade brick	500	
16	E	1			13	Unidentified nail		
16	E	1			1	Button, South type 1		
16	E	1			1	Molded White salt glazed stoneware rim		
16	E	1			3	White salt glazed stoneware		
16	E	1			7	Plain clear glaze slipware		
16	E	1			4	Combed clear glaze slipware		
16	E	1			3	Dotted slipware		
16	E	1			6	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
16	E	1			1	Bone		
16	E	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
16	E	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
16	E	1			22	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
16	E	1			4	Unidentified iron/steel		
16	E	1			1	Lead ball		
16	E	1			3	Dark gray European chert flake		
16	E	1			1	French (honey) chert flake		
16	E	1			7	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
16	E	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
16	E	1			3	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
16	E	1			0	None		
17	J	1			1	Handmade brick	1000	
17	J	1			4	Cut or wrought square nail		
17	J	1			6	Unidentified nail		
17	J	1			1	Nottingham stoneware		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
17	J	1			1	Plain c.c. ware		
17	J	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
17	J	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
17	J	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
17	J	1			1	Goblet base		
17	J	1			1	Goblet glass		
17	J	1			2	Unidentified iron/steel		
17	J	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
17	J	1			1	6/64 Inch ball clay stem		
17	J	1			0	None		
18	J	1			1	Daub		
18	J	1			1	Handmade brick		
18	J	1			1	1.4-1.6mm thick, Crown window glass		
18	J	1			4	Cut or wrought square nail		
18	J	1			25	Unidentified nail		
18	J	1			1	Nottingham stoneware		
18	J	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
18	J	1			1	Plain white granite		
18	J	1			1	Plain creamware		
18	J	1			2	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
18	J	1			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
18	J	1			15	Bone		
18	J	1			1	Olive green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
18	J	1			2	Aqua hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
18	J	1			1	Clear bottle glass		
18	J	1			2	Aqua bottle glass		
18	J	1			1	Melted olive green bottle glass		
18	J	1			9	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
18	J	1			1	Unidentified Iron/steel		
18	J	1			2	Writing slate		
18	J	1			4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
18	J	1			1	5/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
18	J	1			3	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
18	J	1			1	6/ 64 Inch ball clay stem		
18	J	1			0	None		
13	J				2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
19	J	1			2	Bottle glass slipware		Olive glass
19	J	1			1	Daub	41	
19	J	1			1	Handmade brick	3000	
19	J	1			7	Cut or wrought square nail		
19	J	1			21	Unidentified nail		
19	J	1			1	Nottingham stoneware		
19	J	1			5	White salt glazed stoneware		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
19	J	1			1	Overglaze h.p. refined white salt glazed stoneware		
19	J	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
19	J	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
19	J	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
19	J	1			1	Dotted slipware		
19	J	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
19	J	1			32	Bone		
19	J	1			3	Aqua bottle glass		
19	J	1			1	Melted olive green bottle glass		
19	J	1			8	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
19	J	1			1	Goblet rim		
19	J	1			2	Kettle/pot, iron		
19	J	1			7	Unidentified Iron/steel		
19	J	1			1	Lead ball		
19	J	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
19	J	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
19	J	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
19	J	1			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
19	J	1			0	None		
16	E		150 west	Post	1	Unidentified Iron/steel		
16	E		150 west	Post	0	None		
15	E		146 south	Post	1	Cut or wrought square nail		
15	E		146 south	Post	0	None		
16	E		152 south	Post	1	Unidentified nail		
16	E		152 south	Post	0	None		
13	E		135	Tree	1	Unidentified lead		
13	E		135	Tree	0	None		
13	E		138	Post	1	Cut or wrought square nail		
13	E		138	Post	1	Unidentified nail		
13	E		138	Post	1	Aqua hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
13	E		138	Post	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
13	E		138	Post	0	None		
13	E		136	Tree	1	Fossil shell, unmodified stone		
13	E		136	Tree	0	None		
18	J	2			2	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
18	J	2			1	Handmade brick		
18	J	2			7	Cut or wrought square nail		
18	J	2			74	Unidentified nail		
18	J	2			1	Button, South type 7		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
18	J	2			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
18	J	2			1	Undecorated porcelain		
18	J	2			3	Nottingham stoneware		
18	J	2			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
18	J	2			5	Plain creamware		
18	J	2			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
18	J	2			3	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
18	J	2			1	Blue and White delft		
18	J	2			3	Plain White delft		
18	J	2			1	Delft sherds without glaze		
18	J	2			19	Bone		
18	J	2			5	Animal teeth		
18	J	2			3	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
18	J	2			11	Aqua bottle glass		
18	J	2			4	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
18	J	2			1	Goblet rim		
18	J	2			1	Goblet base		
18	J	2			1	Dark European chert shatter		
18	J	2			3	Burned chert shatter		
18	J	2			6	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
18	J	2			2	5/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
18	J	2			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
18	J	2			1	6/ 64 Inch ball clay stem		
18	J	2			1	Activities, Unidentified lead scrap		
18	J	2			2	Unidentified lead		
18	J	2			0	None		
13 and 14	E				1	Daub		
13 and 14	E				1	Cut or wrought square nail		
13 and 14	E				1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
13 and 14	E				1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
13 and 14	E				0	None		
13	E		143	Post	1	Cut or wrought square nail		
13	E		143	Post	0	None		
20	J	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
20	J	1			1	Bottle glass flake		Olive
20	J	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
20	J	1			1	Daub	14	
20	J	1			1	Handmade brick	6000	
20	J	1			17	Cut or wrought square nail		
20	J	1			49	Unidentified nail		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
20	J	1			2	Blue h.p. porcelain		
20	J	1			2	Nottingham stoneware		
20	J	1			4	White salt glazed stoneware		
20	J	1			1	Plain creamware		
20	J	1			6	Plain clear glaze slipware		
20	J	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
20	J	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
20	J	1			1	Purple slip on yellow slipware		
20	J	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
20	J	1			6	Bone		
20	J	1			4	Aqua bottle glass		
20	J	1			6	Melted olive green bottle glass		
20	J	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
20	J	1			23	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
20	J	1			1	Olive green case bottle glass		
20	J	1			1	Goblet glass		
20	J	1			2	Kettle/pot, Iron		
20	J	1			7	Unidentified Iron/steel		
20	J	1			1	Glass jewelry parts		
20	J	1			2	Dark gray European chert flake		
20	J	1			1	Dark European chert shatter		
20	J	1			2	Unidentified material, unident. gunflint spall or blade		
20	J	1			1	French (honey) chert flake		
20	J	1			3	Ball clay pipe bowl fragment		
20	J	1			1	5/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
20	J	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
20	J	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
20	J	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
20	J	1			3	Activities, Unidentified lead scrap		
20	J	1			0	None		
19	J	2			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		
19	J	2			3	Flake fragment 0% cortex		
19	J	2			1	Daub		
19	J	2			1	Handmade brick		
19	J	2			10	Cut or wrought square nail		
19	J	2			29	Unidentified nail		
19	J	2			1	Clothing buckle		
19	J	2			1	Nottingham stoneware		
19	J	2			1	Blue and gray Rhenish stoneware rim		
19	J	2			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
19	J	2			5	Plain creamware		
19	J	2			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
19	J	2			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
19	J	2			1	Molded yellow slipware, floral		
19	J	2			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
Space								
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Daub		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Handmade brick	750	
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	4	Cut or wrought square nail		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	21	Unidentified nail		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Brass shoe buckle		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Undecorated porcelain		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Plain white delft		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	2	Bone		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Animal teeth		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	2	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	2	Unidentified iron/steel		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Miscellaneous stone	12	
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Dark gray European eher! slipware		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	French (honey) chert flake		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	3	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Unidentified lead		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	1	Unidentified brass		
18 and 19	J		155	Pit	0	None		
21	J	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		
21	J	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
21	J	1			1	Handmade brick	6500	
21	J	1				Unidentified nail		
21	J	1			47	Mortar		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
21	J	1			1	Button, South type7		
21	J	1			1	Nottingham stoneware		
21	J	1			1	Blue and gray Rhenish stoneware rim		
21	J	1			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
21	J	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
21	J	1			1	Plain creamware		
21	J	1			4	Plain clear glaze slipware		
21	J	1			2	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
21	J	1			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
21	J	1			2	Blue and white delft		
21	J	1			5	Bone		
21	J	1			1	Aqua hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
21	J	1			4	Melted olive green bottle glass		
21	J	1			4	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
21	J	1			15	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
21	J	1			1	Enameled cast iron pol		
21	J	1			4	Unidentified iron/steel		
21	J	1			1	Writing slate		
21	J	1			2	Lead sprue		
21	J	1			1	Honey colored opaque European chert flake		
21	J	1			1	Unident material, unident gunflint spall or blade		
21	J	1			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
21	J	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
21	J	1			2	Unidentified lead		
21	J	1			0	None		
18	J		155	Pit	1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		
18	J		155	Pit	1	Handmade brick	6	
18	J		155	Pit	4	Unidentified nail		
18	J		155	Pit	1	Round glass bead		
18	J		155	Pit	1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
18	J		155	Pit	1	Delft sherds without glaze		
18	J		155	Pit	1	Aqua bottle glass		
18	J		155	Pit	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
18	J		155	Pit	0	None		
19	J		153 east	Post	1	Undecorated porcelain		
19	J		153 east	Post	0	None		
18	J		154	Post	1	Handmade brick	135	
18	J		154	Post	4	Unidentified nail		
18	J		154	Post	1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
18	J		154	Post	16	Bone		
18	J		154	Post	0	None		
18	J		154	Post	1	Handmade brick	1750	

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
18	J		154	Post	11	Unidentified nail		
18	J		154	Post	1	Molded creamware		
18	J		154	Post	1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
18	J		154	Post	1	Bone		
18	J		154	Post	4	Animal teeth		
18	J		154	Post	1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
18	J		154	Post	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
18	J		154	Post	0	0		
21	J	2			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
21	J	2			1	Daub	32	
21	J	2			1	Handmade brick	6000	
21	J	2			12	Cut or wrought square nail		
21	J	2			20	Unidentified nail		
21	J	2			1	Nottingham stoneware		
21	J	2			3	White salt glazed stoneware		
21	J	2			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
21	J	2			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
21	J	2			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
21	J	2			1	Jackfield		
21	J	2			2	Delft sherds without glaze		
21	J	2			19	Bone		
21	J	2			2	Animal teeth		
21	J	2			3	Aqua bottle glass		
21	J	2			1	Melted olive green bottle glass		
21	J	2			4	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
21	J	2			6	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
21	J	2			1	Goblet glass		
21	J	2			3	Kettle/pot, iron		
21	J	2			6	Unidentified iron/steel		
21	J	2			1	Lead ball		
21	J	2			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
21	J	2			0	None		
18	J		164	Post	1	Handmade brick	1000	
18	J		164	Post	1	unmodified stone	72	Limestone
18	J		164	Post	0	None		
18	J		156 b	Trench	1	Daib		
18	J		156 b	Trench	1	Handmade brick	130	
18	J		156 b	Trench	3	Unidentified nail		
18	J		156 b	Trench	1	Bone		
18	J		156 b	Trench	1	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
18	J		156 b	Trench	1	Unmodified stone		Limestone
18	J		156 b	Trench	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
18	J		156 b	Trench	1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
	J		156 a	Trench	1	Handmade brick	3	
	J		156 a	Trench	2	Cut or wrought square nail		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
	J		156 a	Trench	3	Unidentified nail		
	J		156 a	Trench	2	Bone		
	J		156 a	Trench	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
	J		156 a	Trench	1	Tobacco pipe stem 4/64 inch		
	J		156 a	Trench	1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
	J		156 a	Trench	1	6/64 inch ball clay stem		
	J		156 a	Trench	0	None		
20	J		157	Trench	1	Handmade brick	38	
20	J		157	Trench	13	Unidentified nail		
20	J		157	Trench	1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
20	J		157	Trench	1	Dotted slipware		
20	J		157	Trench	100	Bone		
20	J		157	Trench	4	Animal teeth		
20	J		157	Trench	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
20	J		157	Trench	1	Wood		
20	J		157	Trench	2	Dark gray European chert flake		
20	J		157	Trench	0	None		
21	J		157	Trench	1	Daub	18	
21	J		157	Trench	1	Handmade brick	300	
21	J		157	Trench	13	Unidentified nail		
21	J		157	Trench	2	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
21	J		157	Trench	1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
21	J		157	Trench	2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
21	J		157	Trench	1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
21	J		157	Trench	1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
21	J		157	Trench	33	Bone		
21	J		157	Trench	3	Animal teeth		
21	J		157	Trench	2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
21	J		157	Trench	1	Goblet rim		
21	J		157	Trench	1	Unidentified chert percussion flake		
21	J		157	Trench	1	French (honey) chert flake		
21	J		157	Trench	10	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
21	J		157	Trench	1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
21	J		157	Trench	2	Unidentified scrap pewter		
21	J		157	Trench	1	Unidentified brass		
21	J		157	Trench	0	None		
22	P	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
22	P	1			1	Flake fragment >50% cortex		Quartz
22	P	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		Quartzite
22	P	1			1	Shatter >50% cortex		Quartz
22	P	1			1	Handmade brick	250	
22	P	1			2	1.4-1.6mm thick, Crown window glass		
22	P	1			8	1.6-1.8 mm thick, Crown window glass		
22	P	1			5	1.8-2.0 mm thick, Crown window glass		
22	P	1			2	2.0-2.2 mm thick, Crown window glass		
22	P	1			1	2.2-2.4 mm thick, Crown window glass		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
22	P	1			1	2.4-2.6 mm thick, Crown window glass		
22	P	1			8	Cut or wrought square nail		
22	P	1			54	Unidentified nail		
22	P	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
22	P	1			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
22	P	1			6	Unidentified Iron/steel		
22	P	1			4	Shotgun shell casing		
22	P	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
22	P	1			1	English dark gray gunflint, unident spall or blade		
22	P	1			1	Milk glass canning seal		
22	P	1			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
22	P	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
22	P	1			1	3/64 Inch ball clay stem		
22	P	1			1	Electric Wire		
22	P	1			0	None		
24	Q	2			1	Daub	2	
24	Q	2			1	Handmade brick	4	
24	Q	2			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
24	Q	2			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
24	Q	2			0	None		
20	J		157	Trench	2	Daub	2	
20	J		157	Trench	4	Handmade brick	6	
20	J		157	Trench	1	Round glass bead		
20	J		157	Trench	2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
20	J		157	Trench	10	Bone		
20	J		157	Trench	4	Animal teeth		
20	J		157	Trench	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
20	J		157	Trench	1	Buckshot		
20	J		157	Trench	1	Buckshot		
20	J		157	Trench	1	French (choney) chert flake		
20	J		157	Trench	0	None		
20	J		159	Pit	1	Handmade brick	2	
20	J		159	Pit	8	Bone		
20	J		159	Pit	3	Wood		
20	J		159	Pit	0	None		
23	K	1			1	Plain ceramic, body Grit tempered		Grit tempered
23	K	1			1	Check stamped ceramic, body		
23	K	1			1	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Grog tempered
23	K	1			1	Handmade brick	250	
23	K	1			1	1.6-1.8 mm thick, Crown window glass		
23	K	1			1	Cut or wrought square nail		
23	K	1			6	Unidentified nail		
23	K	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
23	K	1			2	Molded White salt glazed stoneware rim		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
23	K	1			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
23	K	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
23	K	1			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
23	K	1			1	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
23	K	1			1	Cobalt blue pharmaceutical bottle		
23	K	1			2	Ameythst bottle glass		
23	K	1			8	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
23	K	1			1	5/64 Inch ball clay stem/bowl		
23	K	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
23	K	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
23	K	1			0	None		
24	Q	1			1	Daub	1	
24	Q	1			1	Handmade brick	970	
24	Q	1			1	Unidentified nail		
24	Q	1			2	Whieldon ware		
24	Q	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
24	Q	1			7	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
24	Q	1			1	Unidentified ceramic body		
24	Q	1			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
24	Q	1			1	Unidentified Iron/steel		
24	Q	1			1	Shotgun shell casng		
24	Q	1						
25	Q	1			1	Flake <50% cortex		Quartz
25	Q	1			1	Triangular PPK		C.P. chert
25	Q	1			1	Handmade brick	7	
25	Q	1			1	Handmade brick	300	
25	Q	1			1	1.6-1.8 mm thick, Crown window glass		
25	Q	1			1	Cut or wrought square nail		
25	Q	1			4	Unidentified nail		
25	Q	1			1	Blue and gray Rhenish stoneware rim		
25	Q	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
25	Q	1			1	Brown salt glazed stoneware		
25	Q	1			1	Whieldon ware		
25	Q	1			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
25	Q	1			2	Trailed clear giaze s11pware		
25	Q	1			5	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
25	Q	1			1	Plain White delft		
25	Q	1			1	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
25	Q	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
25	Q	1			8	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
25	Q	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflnt		
25	Q	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
25	Q	1			1	6/64 inch ball clay stem		
25	Q	1			0	None		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
23	K		165	Tree/pit?	1	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Sand tempered
23	K		165	Tree/pit?	1	Cut or wrought square nail		
23	K		165	Tree/pit?	1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
23	K		165	Tree/pit?	4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
23	K		165	Tree/pit?	1	Unidentified Iron/steel		
23	K		165	Tree/pit?	0	None		
25	K	2			1	Handmade brick	139	
25	K	2			1	cut or wrought square nail		
25	K	2			2	Unidentified nail		
25	K	2			1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
25	K	2			0	None		
20	J		166	Pit	1	Handmade brick	2	
20	J		166	Pit	1	1.4-1.6 mm thick, Crown window glass		
20	J		166	Pit	1	Unidentified nail		
20	J		166	Pit	1	Bone		
20	J		166	Pit	0	None		
27	K	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		Quartz
27	K	1			2	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
27	K	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
27	K	1			2	Shatter 0% cortex		Quartz
27	K	1			1	Glass unifacial tool		
27	K	1			1	Indeterminate stamped ceramic, body		
27	K	1			1	Check stamped ceramic, body		
27	K	1			1	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		
27	K	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
27	K	1			1	Handmade brick	500	
27	K	1			2	1.0 to 1.25 Wire common nail 3 penny		
27	K	1			5	2.5 to 2.75 Wire common nail 9 penny		
27	K	1			4	3.0 to 3.25 Wire common nail 12 penny		
27	K	1			1	4.0 to 4.5 Wire common nail 30 penny		
27	K	1			3	Fragment wire common nail		
27	K	1			9	Cut or wrought square nail		
27	K	1			62	Unidentified nail		
27	K	1			1	Molded white salt glazed stoneware rim		
27	K	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
27	K	1			1	Plain brown salt glazed stoneware		
27	K	1			1	Unidentified domestic stoneware		
27	K	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
27	K	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
27	K	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
27	K	1			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
27	K	1			1	Polychrome delft		
27	K	1			1	Delft sherds without glaze		
27	K	1			1	green bottle glass		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
27	K	1			3	Light green bottle glass		
27	K	1			4	Clear machine made bottle glass		
27	K	1			6	Unidentified iron/steel		
27	K	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
27	K	1			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
27	K	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
27	K	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
27	K	1			0	None		
26	J	1			1	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Grit tempered
26	J	1			1	Handmade brick	2000	
26	J	1			1	1.4-1.6 mm thick, Crown window glass		
26	J	1			20	Unidentified nail		
26	J	1			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
26	J	1			1	Unidentified domestic stoneware		
26	J	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
26	J	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
26	J	1			1	Molded yellow slipware, floral		
26	J	1			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
26	J	1			2	Bone		
26	J	1			8	Melted olive green bottle glass		
26	J	1			11	Olive green splint bottle glass		
26	J	1			4	Unidentified iron/steel		
26	J	1			1	Lead ball		
26	J	1			2	Dark gray European chert flake		
26	J	1			1	Unident material, unident gunflint spall or blade		
26	J	1			1	Dark green bottle glass unifacial flake tool		
26	J	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
26	J	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
26	J	1			1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
26	J	1			0	None		
25	J	3			1	Handmade brick	63	
25	J	3			1	Blue and White delft		
25	J	3			0	None		
26	J	2			1	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Sabd
26	J	2			1	Handmade brick	4000	
26	J	2			1	Spike, wrought Iron		
26	J	2			30	Unidentified nail		
26	J	2			1	Shell mortar	4	
26	J	2			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
26	J	2			1	Refined brown salt glazed stoneware body		
26	J	2			1	White salt glazed stoneware		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
26	J	2			2	Whieldon ware		
26	J	2			1	Plain creamware		
26	J	2			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
26	J	2			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
26	J	2			1	Molded yellow slipware, floral		
26	J	2			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
26	J	2			1	Jackfield		
26	J	2			1	Plain White delft		
26	J	2			1	Indeterminate ceramic		
26	J	2			20	Bone		
26	J	2			1	Olive green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
26	J	2			1	Aqua hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
26	J	2			9	Melted olive green bottle glass		
26	J	2			12	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
26	J	2			11	Unidentified iron/steel		
26	J	2			1	Writing slate		
26	J	2			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
26	J	2			1	Unidentified material, Unidentified gunflint spall or blade		
26	J	2			1	French (honey) chert flake		
26	J	2			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
26	J	2			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
26	J	2			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
26	J	2			4	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
26	J	2			1	Other clay tobacco pipestem		
26	J	2			0	None		
28	J	1			1	1 Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Grit
28	J	1			1	1 Handmade brick	14000	
28	J	1			1	1 1.0-1.2 mm thick, Crown window glass		
28	J	1			41	41 Unidentified nail		
28	J	1			1	1 Shell mortar	18	
28	J	1			1	1 Faceted glass bead		
28	J	1			1	1 Blue h.p. porcelain		
28	J	1			2	2 Whieldon ware		
28	J	1			1	1 Underglaze blue edgware		
28	J	1			6	6 Plain clear glaze slipware		
28	J	1			1	1 Combed clear glaze slipware		
28	J	1			1	1 Dotted slipware		
28	J	1			6	6 Unidentified coarse earthenware		
28	J	1			1	1 Blue and white delft		
28	J	1			1	1 Majolica, Puebla Blue on White		
28	J	1			15	Bone		
28	J	1			3	Aqua hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
28	J	1			13	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
28	J	1			1	Goblet glass		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
28	J	1			2	Unidentified iron/steel		
28	J	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
28	J	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
28	J	1			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
28	J	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/ 64 Inch		
28	J	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
28	J	1			1	Unidentified lead		
28	J	1			0	None		
29	J	1			3	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
29	J	1			3	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
29	J	1			1	Dark green bottle glass unifacial tool		Glass
29	J	1			1	Daub	11	
29	J	1			1	Handmade brick	3500	
29	J	1			1	1.6-1.8 mm thick, Crown window glass		
29	J	1			18	Cut or wrought square nail		
29	J	1			29	Unidentified nail		
29	J	1			1	Button, South type 1		
29	J	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
29	J	1			1	Nottingham stoneware		
29	J	1			4	White salt glazed stoneware		
29	J	1			1	Scratch blue salt glazed stoneware		
29	J	1			1	Plain brown salt glazed stoneware		
29	J	1			1	Plain White granite		
29	J	1			1	Molded/embossed white granite		
29	J	1			3	Plain creamware		
29	J	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
29	J	1			3	Combed clear glaze slipware		
29	J	1			1	Dotted slipware		
29	J	1			7	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
29	J	1			1	Jackfield		
29	J	1			9	Bone		
29	J	1			1	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
29	J	1			2	Aqua bottle glass		
29	J	1			18	Melted olive green bottle glass		
29	J	1			3	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
29	J	1			17	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
29	J	1			1	Coal		
29	J	1			7	Unidentified Iron/steel		
29	J	1			1	French (honey) gunflint, spall type		
29	J	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
29	J	1			1	Modern bullet		
29	J	1			1	Leadsprue		
29	J	1			3	English dark gray gunflint, unident spall or blade		
29	J	1			4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
29	J	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 Inch		
29	J	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
29	J	1			1	Activities, Unidentified lead scrap		
29	J	1			1	Unidentified lead		
29	J	1			0	None		
30	J	1			1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P chert
30	J	1			1	Handmade brick	2100	
30	J	1			1	1.0-1.2 mm thick, Crown window glass		
30	J	1			8	Unidentified nail		
30	J	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
30	J	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
30	J	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
30	J	1			1	Dotted slipware		
30	J	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
30	J	1			2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
30	J	1			1	Copper coin		
30	J	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
30	J	1			1	Underglaze blue handpainted pearlware		
30	J	1			0	None		
31	J	1			1	Daub	15	
31	J	1			1	Handmade brick	2750	
31	J	1			4	Cut or wrought square nail		
31	J	1			13	Unidentified nail		
31	J	1			5	Undecorated porcelain		
31	J	1			2	Nottingham stoneware		
31	J	1			1	Molded white salt glazed stoneware rim		
31	J	1			2	White salt glazed stoneware		
31	J	1			3	Whieldon ware		
31	J	1			1	Plain creamware		
31	J	1			6	Plain clear glaze slipware		
31	J	1			5	Combed clear glaze slipware		
31	J	1			4	Dotted slipware		
31	J	1			4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
31	J	1			1	Bone		
31	J	1			2	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
31	J	1			1	Semi-automatic narrow mouth bottle glass		
31	J	1			1	Melted olive green bottle glass		
31	J	1			2	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
31	J	1			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
31	J	1			1	Goblet base		
31	J	1			1	5/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
31	J	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
31	J	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
31	J	1			0	None		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
32	I	1			4	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
32	I	1			4	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
32	I	1			1	Bottle glass slipware		
32	I	1			4	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
32	I	1			1	Handmade brick	660	
32	I	1			1	1.2-1.4 mm thick, Crown window glass		
32	I	1			9	Cut or wrought square nail		
32	I	1			11	Unidentified nail		
32	I	1			4	Nottingham stoneware		
32	I	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
32	I	1			2	Plain brown saltglazed stoneware		
32	I	1			1	Whieldon ware		
32	I	1			2	Plain creamware		
32	I	1			2	Plain clear glaze slipware		
32	I	1			2	Dotted slipware		
32	I	1			2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
32	I	1			1	Blue and white delft		
32	I	1			4	Bone		
32	I	1			3	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
32	I	1			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
32	I	1			9	Unidentified iron/steel		
32	I	1			1	Unmodified stone		
32	I	1			1	Lead ball		
32	I	1			1	Lead sprue		
32	I	1			4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
32	I	1			1	4/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
32	I	1			3	5/64 inch ball clay stem		
32	I	1			2	6 / 64 Inch ball clay stem		
32	I	1			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
32	I	1			2	Activites, Unidentified lead scrap		
32	I	1			0	None		
33	B	1			2	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
33	B	1			1	Handmade brick	53	
33	B	1			3	Unidentified nail		
33	B	1			3	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
33	B	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
33	B	1			0	None		
29	J		175 a		1	Shell mortar		
29	J		175 a		1	Bone		
29	J		175 a		0	None		
29	J		175 a		1	Handmade brick	20	
29	J		175 a		1	Unidentified nail		
29	J		175 a		1	Unidentified Iron/steel		
29	J		175 a		0	None		
25	Q	Strata1				OCR sample		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
25	Q	Strata2				OCR sample		
25	Q	Strata3				OCR sample		
25	Q	Strata4				OCR sample		
25	Q	Strata5				OCR sample		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	3	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Daub	2	
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Handmade brick	250	
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	4	Cut or wrought square nail		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	29	Unidentified nail		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Nottingham stoneware		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Whieldon ware		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	4	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	18	Bone		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Aqua bottle glass		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	4	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Iron ball, grapeshot	260	
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	2	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	5	Dark gray European chert flake		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	2	Dark European chert shatter		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	2	Leadsprue		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	2	Burned chert shatter		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	6/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Unidentified lead		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	0	0		
32	I	1						
32	I	1						
32	I	1	176	Trench	2	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	1	Daub	447	
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	3	Cut or wrought square nail		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	8	Unidentified nail		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	1	Plain brown salt glazed stoneware		
32	I	1	176	Trench	35	Bone		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	0	0		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Daub	69	
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Handmade brick	2	

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	5	Unidentified nail		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Indeterminate cerarnlc		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	8	Bone		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Buckshot		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Lead sprue		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Dark European chert shatter		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Burned chert shatter		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	2	Reed sternmed pipe/stem bowl		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	1	6/ 64 inch ball clay stem		
32	I	1	176 a	Trench	0	0		
32	I	1	176	Trench	1	Daub		
32	I	1	176	Trench	4	Unidentified nail	42	
32	I	1	176	Trench	1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	3	Bone		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	1	English gray/black spall type gunflint		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	1	English gray/black spall type gunflint		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	2	Unidentified lead		
32	I	1	176 b	Trench	0	0		
29	J		175 c	Hearth	0	Soil Sample		
34	J	1			1	Plain ceramic, body		Fine sand tempered
34	J	1			1	Handmade brick	3500	
34	J	1			14	Cut or wrought square nail		
34	J	1			19	Unidentified nail		
34	J	1			1	Shell mortar	33500	
34	J	1			1	Plain brown salt glazed stoneware		
34	J	1			1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
34	J	1			4	Plain clear glaze slipware		
34	J	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
34	J	1			1	Molded yellow slipware, floral		
34	J	1			5	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
34	J	1			1	Astbury Refined redware		
34	J	1			1	Refined agateware		
34	J	1			26	Bone		
34	J	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
34	J	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
34	J	1			8	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
34	J	1			1	Goblet rim		
34	J	1			1	Kettle/pot, iron		
34	J	1			2	Unidentified iron/steel		
34	J	1			1	Burned chert shatter		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
34	J	1			1	Underglaze blue handpainted pearlware		
34	J	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
34	J	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
34	J	1			2	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
34	J	1			1	Unidentified lead		
34	J	1			0	None		
35	G	1			1	Bipolar core		Quartz
35	G	1			1	Flake fragment 0% corex		C.P. chert
35	G	1			1	Flake fragment 0% corex		Quartz
35	G	1			1	Bottle glass slipware		
35	G	1			1	Unifacially retouched slipware, possibly Early Archaic		C.P. chert
35	G	1			2	Glass unifacial tool		
35	G	1			1	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
35	G	1			1	Daub	4	
35	G	1			1	Handmade brick	250	
35	G	1			4	But or wrought square nail		
35	G	1			13	Unidentified nail		
35	G	1			1	Nottingham stoneware		
35	G	1			1	Blue and gray Rhenish stoneware rim		
35	G	1			5	Plain clear glaze slipware		
35	G	1			1	Molded yellow slipware, floral		
35	G	1			3	Dotted slipware		
35	G	1			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
35	G	1			1	Bone		
35	G	1			1	Clear bottle glass		
35	G	1			1	Aqua bottle glass		
35	G	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
35	G	1			15	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
35	G	1			1	Other kitchen metal		
35	G	1			10	Unidentified iron/steel		
35	G	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
35	G	1			2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
35	G	1			4	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
35	G	1			6	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
35	G	1			1	6/64 inch ball clay stem		
35	G	1			2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
35	G	1			0	None		
32	I		175 a	Trench	0	OCR sample		
32	I		175 b	Trench	0	OCR sample		
32	I		175 b	Trench	0	OCR sample		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Daub	8500	
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Handmade brick	350	

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	4	Cut or rough square nail		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	8	Unidentified nail		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	White salt glazed stoneware		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Plain clear glaze slipware		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Combed and dotted slipware		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	43	Bone		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Aqua bottle glass		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Melted olive green bottle glass		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	5	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	4	Unidentified iron/steel		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Glass gunflint		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	3	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	2	Unidentified brass		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	0	None		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	1	Handmade brick	16	
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	0	None		
26 and 29	J		157 b	Pit	0	None		
35	G		180	Trench	1	Handmade brick	31	
35	G		180	Trench	1	Spike, wrought iron		
35	G		180	Trench	2	Unidentified nail		
35	G		180	Trench	1	Purple slip on yellow slipware		
35	G		180	Trench	2	Olive greens spirit bottle glass		
35	G		180	Trench	2	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
35	G		180	Trench	0	None		
35	G		181	Post	1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
35	G		181	Post	1	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
35	G		181	Post	0	None		
26	J		157 c	Trench	1	Handmade brick	100	
26	J		157 c	Trench	4	Cut or wrought square nail		
26	J		157 c	Trench	4	Unidentified nail		
26	J		157 c	Trench	1	White salt glazed stoneware		
26	J		157 c	Trench	4	Bone		
26	J		157 c	Trench	1	Melted olive green bottle glass		
26	J		157 c	Trench	1	Burned chert shatter		
26	J		157 c	Trench	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
26	J		157 c	Trench	0	None		
26	J		157 c	Trench	1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
26	J		157 c	Trench	1	Handmade brick	90	
26	J		157 c	Trench	2	Unidentified nail		
26	J		157 c	Trench	1	Unidentified Iron/steel		
26	J		157 c	Trench	0	None		
29	J		173 a	Trench	1	Handmade brick	90	
29	J		173 a	Trench	3	Unidentified nail		
29	J		173 a	Trench	1	White salt glazed stoneware		
29	J		173 a	Trench	4	Bone		
29	J		173 a	Trench	1	Melted olive green bottle glass		
29	J		173 a	Trench	1	Unidentified lead		
29	J		173 a	Trench	0	None		
36	C	1			1	Shatter 0% cortex		C.P. chert
36	C	1			1	Bottle glass slipware		green glass
36	C	1			2	Check stamped pinched rim		
36	C	1			1	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Heavy grit tempered
36	C	1			4	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
36	C	1			1	Daub	10	
36	C	1			1	Handmade brick	500	
36	C	1			5	Cut or wrought square nail		
36	C	1			6	Unidentified nail		
36	C	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
36	C	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
36	C	1			7	Plain clear glaze slipware		
36	C	1			2	Combed clear glaze slipware		
36	C	1			1	Molded yellow slipware, floral		
36	C	1			1	Dotted slipware		
36	C	1			3	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
36	C	1			4	Bone		
36	C	1			2	Clear bottle glass		
36	C	1			16	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
36	C	1			9	Unidentified Iron/steel		
36	C	1			2	Lead ball		
36	C	1			3	Leadspue		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
36	C	1			2	Dark gray European chert flake		
36	C	1			1	French (honey) chert flake		
36	C	1			8	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
36	C	1			2	4/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
36	C	1			8	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/ 64 inch		
36	C	1			3	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
36	C	1			2	6/64 inch ball clay stem		
36	C	1			1	Unidentified Jead		
36	C	1			0	None		
37	C	1			4	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
37	C	1			1	Daub	26	
37	C	1			1	Handmade brick	750	
37	C	1			5	Cut or wrought square nail		
37	C	1			3	Unidentified nail		
37	C	1			1	Other brass button shank		9.2 mm
37	C	1			1	Other brass button shank		12 mm
37	C	1			1	Brass buckle, belt		
37	C	1			1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
37	C	1			1	White salt glazed stoneware		
37	C	1			7	Plain clear glaze slipware		
37	C	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
37	C	1			2	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
37	C	1			1	Dotted slipware		
37	C	1			9	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
37	C	1			1	Plain white delft		
37	C	1			1	Delft sherds without glaze		
37	C	1			1	Dark blue underglaze stippled transfer print		
37	C	1			40	Bone		
37	C	1			2	Animal teeth		
37	C	1			1	Aqua hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
37	C	1			3	Light green bottle glass		
37	C	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
37	C	1			23	Olive green spirt bottle glass		
37	C	1			8	Unidentified Iron/steel		
37	C	1			2	Buckshot		
37	C	1			4	Leadsprue		
37	C	1			1	Gray chalcedony percussion flake		
37	C	1			2	Burned chert shatter		
37	C	1			16	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
37	C	1			1	5/64 Inch ball clay stem/bowl		
37	C	1			7	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 Inch		
37	C	1			1	6 / 64 Inch ball clay stem		
37	C	1			5	Unidentified lead		
37	C	1			0	None		
36	C		182	Trench	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		

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Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
36	C		182	Trench	0	None		
37	C		183	Trench	1	Daub	120	
37	C		183	Trench	1	Handmade brick	88	
37	C		183	Trench	1	Unidentified nail		
37	C		183	Trench	4	Bone		
37	C		183	Trench	2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
37	C		183	Trench	1	Buckshot		3.7
37	C		183	Trench	1	Lead ball		4.7
37	C		183	Trench	1	Lead ball		4.7
37	C		183	Trench	2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
37	C		183	Trench	0	None		
26	J		185	Post	1	Handmade brick	90	
26	J		185	Post	1	Unidentified nail		
26	J		185	Post	1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
26	J		185	Post	2	Bone		
26	J		185	Post	0	None		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	Thinning flake 0% cortex		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	Handmade brick	100	
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	Cut or wrought square nail		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	3	Unidentified nail		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	White salt glazed stoneware		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	2	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	40	Bone		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	2	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	Unidentified Iron/steel		
26	J	2	173 a	Trench	0	None		
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	Handmade brick	150	
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	11	Unidentified nail		
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	Blue h.p. porcelain		
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	Refined brown salt glazed stoneware body		
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	2	Bone		
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	1	Fine lipping tool finish bottle glass		
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	2	Olive green spirit bottle		
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
29	J	2	173 a	Trench	0	None		
34	J		175 e	Firebox	1	Handmade brick	100	
34	J		175 e	Firebox	0	None		
28	J		175 c	Hearth	1	Handmade brick	33	
28	J		175 c	Hearth	0	None		
	J		157 b	Pit	1	Handmade brick	32	
	J		157 b	Pit	2	Unidentified nail		
	J		157 b	Pit	1	Shell mortar		
	J		157 b	Pit	4	Bone	1	
	J		157 b	Pit	0	None		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
34	J		188	Post	1	Dirt dauber nest	2	
34	J		188	Post	1	Handmade brick	2	
34	J		188	Post	2	1.25 to 1.5 rosehead nail 4 penny		
34	J		188	Post	3	Unidentified nail		
34	J		188	Post	1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
34	J		188	Post	23	Bone		
34	J		188	Post	2	Unidentified iron/steel		
34	J		188	Post	1	5/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
34	J		188	Post	0	None		
37	C		186	Post	1	Handmade brick	2000	
37	C		186	Post	1	Handmade brick	1892	7.5X3.75X2.25 in
37	C		186	Post	1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
37	C		186	Post	0	None		
37	C		187	Clay layer	1	Daub	29	
37	C		187	Clay layer	2	Olive green spiri bottle glass		
37	C		187	Clay layer	0	None		
	C		183 a	Trench	1	Daub		
	C		183 a	Trench	4	Unidentified nail		
	C		183 a	Trench	1	Leadsprue		
	C		183 a	Trench	2	English gray/black spall type gunflint		
	C		183 a	Trench	1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
	C		183 a	Trench	0	None		
28	J		175 d	Brick chimney	1	Handmade brick	961	UNKX3.75X2.5 1
28	J		175 d	Brick chimney	0	None		
34	J		175 d	Brick chimney	1	Handmade brick	1559	8Z4X2.5 inch
34	J		175 d	Brick chimney	1	Mortar		
34	J		175 d	Brick chimney	0	None		
26	J		189	Post	1	Daub	8	
26	J		189	Post	1	Unidentified nail		
26	J		189	Post	1	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
26	J		189	Post	2	Bone		
26	J		189	Post	43	Olive green sp!rit bottle glass		
26	J		189	Post	1	Dark gray European chert flake		
26	J		189	Post	2	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
26	J		189	Post	0	None		
26	J		157 a	Chimney fall	1	Daub	4	
26	J		157 a	Chimney fall	1	Handmade brick	50000	

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
26	J		157 a	Chimney fall	1	Molded creamware		
26	J		157 a	Chimney fall	1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
26	J		157 a	Chimney fall	25	Bone		
26	J		157 a	Chimney fall	1	6/64 inch ball clay stem/bowl		
26	J		157 a	Chimney fall	0	None		
26	J		157 a&b		0	None		
38	A	1			7	Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
38	A	1			8	Flake fragment 0% corex		C.P. chert
38	A	1			3	Shatter 0% cortex		C.P. chert
38	A	1			2	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		
38	A	1			18	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
38	A	1			1	Daub	38	
38	A	1			1	Handmade brick	500	
38	A	1			4	Unidentified nail		
38	A	1			1	Plain white granite		
38	A	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
38	A	1			1	Trailed clear glaze slipware		
38	A	1			1	Dotted slipware		
38	A	1			1	Plain white delft		
38	A	1			3	Bone		
38	A	1			1	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
38	A	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
38	A	1			1	Clear machine made bottle glass		
38	A	1			3	Unidentified iron/steel		
38	A	1			1	English (grey/black) spall type gunflint		
38	A	1			1	Dark gray European chert flake		
38	A	1			1	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
38	A	1			1	Barbed wire		
38	A	1			0	None		
39	B	1			2	2 Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
39	B	1			1	1 Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		
39	B	1			4	4 Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
39	B	1			1	1 Handmade brick	107	
39	B	1			1	1 Spike, wrought Iron		
39	B	1			1	1 Cut or wrought square nail		
39	B	1			3	3 Unidentified nail		
39	B	1			1	1 Other brass button shank		
39	B	1			1	1 Overglaze h.p. refined white salt glazed stoneware		
39	B	1			1	1 Plain creamware		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
39	B	1			3	3 Olive green spirit bottle glass		
39	B	1			3	3 Unidentified iron/steel		
39	B	1			3	3 6/ 64 Inch ball clay stem		
39	B	1			0	None		
40	A	1			1	1 Random core		C.P. chert
40	A	1			3	3 Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
40	A	1			1	1 Unspecialized slipware 0% cortex		C.P. chert
40	A	1			1	1 Bipolar slipware, 0% cortex		C.P. chert
40	A	1			2	2 Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
40	A	1			1	1 Shatter 0% cortex		C.P. chert
40	A	1			2	2 Biface fragment		C.P. chert
40	A	1			3	3 Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Fine sand tempered
40	A	1			2	2 Stallings Plain ceramic, body		Fiber tempered
40	A	1			5	5 Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
40	A	1			1	1 Daub	8	
40	A	1			1	1 Handmade brick	400	
40	A	1			3	3 Unidentified nail		
40	A	1			1	1 Unidentified Iron hinge		
40	A	1			1	1 Plain clear glaze slipware		
40	A	1			1	1 Olive green spirit bottle glass		
40	A	1			1	1 Clear machine made bottle glass		
40	A	1			1	1 Kettle/pot, Iron		
40	A	1			3	3 Unidentified Iron/steel		
40	A	1			1	1 Brass/copper cartridge		
40	A	1			1	1 Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
40	A	1			1	1 Harness parts, Iron/steel buckle		
40	A	1			0	None		
41	B	1			2	2 Thinning flake 0% cortex		C.P. chert
41	B	1			1	1 Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
41	B	1			2	2 Non-retouched heavily utilized slipware		C.P. chert
41	B	1			1	1 Biface fragment		C.P. chert
41	B	1			1	1 Plain ceramic, body		Heavy grit tempered
41	B	1			2	2 Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Heavy grit tempered
41	B	1			6	6 Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
41	B	1			1	1 Handmade brick	99	
41	B	1			4	4 Unidentified delft		
41	B	1			1	1 Blue h.p. pearlware		
41	B	1			1	1 Melted olive green bottle glass		
41	B	1			1	1 Olive green spirit bottle glass		
41	B	1			1	1 Unidentified Iron/steel		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
41	B	1			1	1 Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
41	B	1			0			
23	K	2	165	Tree/pit?	7	Simple stamped ceramic, body		Sand tempered
23	K	2	165	Tree/pit?	6	Indeterminate decorated ceramic, body		Sand tempered
23	K	2	165	Tree/pit?	1	Unidentified nail		
23	K	2	165	Tree/pit?	0	None		
42	C	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		Quartz
42	C	1			1	Flake fragment 0% cortex		C.P. chert
42	C	1			1	Shatter 0% cortex		C.P. chert
42	C	1			1	Biface fragment		
42	C	1			2	Plain ceramic, body		Very fine sand tempered
42	C	1			7	Indeterminate ceramic, residual		
42	C	1			1	Daub	274	
42	C	1			20	Cut or wrought nail		
42	C	1			3	Unidentified nail		
42	C	1			3	Plain clear glaze slipware		
42	C	1			1	Combed clear glaze slipware		
42	C	1			11	Unidentified coarse earthenware		
42	C	1			1	Blue and white delft		
42	C	1			19	Bone		
42	C	1			1	Light green hand blown pharmaceutical bottle		
42	C	1			2	Clear curved glass, probable tableware		
42	C	1			18	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
42	C	1			1	Olive green spirit bottle glass		
42	C	1			1	Flat glass, clear		
42	C	1			1	Lead ball		
42	C	1			4	Ball clay pipe bowl fragments		
42	C	1			2	5/64 inch ball clay stem		
42	C	1			1	Tobacco pipe stem, 4/64 inch		
42	C	1			3	Tobacco pipe stem, 5/64 inch		
42	C	1			1	6/64 inch ball clay stem		
42	C	1			4	Other clay tobacco pipe stem		
42	C	1			0	None		
6	N		115	Post	1	Handmade brick	1	
6	N		115	Post	0	None		
6 and 7	N		113	Post	1	Handmade brick	60	
6 and 7	N		113	Post	0	None		
9	N		132	Post	1	Handmade brick	500	
9	N		132	Post	0	None		
14	E		141	Rut	1	Handmade brick	200	
14	E		141	Rut	0	None		

1995-1996 Ft. Argyle Excavation Data. rfe v4.14.19 *ST denotes ST, others are TU.

Test Unit Number*	Block	Level	Feature		Artifact			
			No.	Type	Count	Type	Weight (g)	Material
29	J		175 b		1	Handmade brick	90	
29	J		175 b		0	None		
38	A		191	Possible pit	1	Handmade brick	20	
38	A		191	Possible pit	0	None		
	N		106	Post	1	Handmade brick	1750	
	N		106	Post	0	None		

APPENDIX H: Fort Argyle Site Plan with Features and Excavation Units 1985-2019.

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